

Water Resources Data Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands Water Year 1998

CALENDAR FOR WATER YEAR 1998

1997

OCTOBER							NOVEMBER							DECEMBER						
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S
			1	2	3	4							1		1	2	3	4	5	6
5	6	7	8	9	10	11	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
12	13	14	15	16	17	18	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	21	22	23	24	25	26	27
26	27	28	29	30	31		23	24	25	26	27	28	29	28	29	30	31			
							30													

1998

JANUARY							FEBRUARY							MARCH						
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S
				1	2	3	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4	5	6	7	8	9	10	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
18	19	20	21	22	23	24	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
25	26	27	28	29	30	31								29	30	31				

APRIL							MAY							JUNE						
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S
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5	6	7	8	9	10	11	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
12	13	14	15	16	17	18	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	21	22	23	24	25	26	27
26	27	28	29	30			24	25	26	27	28	29	30	28	29	30				
							31													

JULY							AUGUST							SEPTEMBER						
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S
			1	2	3	4						1			1	2	3	4	5	
5	6	7	8	9	10	11	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
12	13	14	15	16	17	18	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
26	27	28	29	30	31		23	24	25	26	27	28	29	27	28	29	30			
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Water Resources Data Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands Water Year 1998

By Pedro L. Díaz, Zaida Aquino, Carlos Figueroa-Alamo, Ricardo J. Vachier,
and Ana V. Sánchez

Water-Data Report PR-98-1

Prepared in cooperation with the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico,
the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands, and with other agencies

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR
BRUCE BABBITT, Secretary

U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY
Charles G. Groat, Director

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1999

PREFACE

This annual hydrologic data report of Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands is one of a series of annual reports that document hydrologic data gathered from the U.S. Geological Survey's surface- and ground-water data-collection networks in each state, Puerto Rico, the U.S. Virgin Islands, and the other Trust Territories. These records of streamflow, ground-water levels, and quality of water provide the hydrologic information needed by state, local, and Federal agencies, and the private sector for developing and managing our Nation's land and water resources.

The report is the culmination of a concerted effort by dedicated personnel of the U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division, who collected, compiled, analyzed, verified, and organized the data, and who typed, edited, and assembled the report. In addition to the authors, who had primary responsibility for assuring that the information contained herein is accurate, complete, and adheres to the U.S. Geological Survey policy and established guidelines, the Caribbean District would like to acknowledge Heriberto Torres-Sierra, Surface-Water Specialist, for his dedication and long hours of hard work. With the help of the Hydrologic Studies Section, he determined peak discharges for the Hurricane Georges floods. The following personnel contributed significantly to the collection, processing and tabulations of the data:

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This report was prepared in cooperation with agencies of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands, and with other federal agencies under the general supervision of Rafael W. Rodríguez, District Chief, Caribbean District, San Juan, Puerto Rico.

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**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED IN THIS VOLUME**

(Letter after station name designates type of data:
(d) discharge, (c) chemical, (b) biological, (s) sediment, (p) pesticide, (e) elevation, gage heights)

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Well 182422067015100 Local number 165	486
Well 182647066552400 Local number 202	487
RIO CAMUY BASIN	
Well 182723066511200 Local number Z-4.....	488
Well 182431066463400 Local number CA-4.....	490
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN	
Well 182756066454700 Local number BARR-1	492
Well 182737066370900 Local number 204	493
Well 182616066364100 Local number EN-1	494
Well 182626066345100 Local number TI-1	495
Well 182603066333601 Local number FA-2	496
Well 182209066340600 Local number FL-1	498
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN	
Well 182757066325600 Local number 206	499
Well 182710066303700 Local number 207	500
Well 182549066304300 Local number 166	501
Well 182506066280200 Local number HI-2.....	502
Well 182308066260400 Local number 210	503
Well 182548066265700 Local number CS-7	504
RIO CIBUCO BASIN	
Well 182614066261500 Local number PA-2	505
Well 182712066251700 Local number TO-3.....	506
Well 182615066235300 Local number 211	507
Well 182647066201700 Local number 70	508
Well 182515066194000 Local number 212	509
Well 182330066185700 Local number 213	510
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN	
Well 182804066173500 Local number DA-1	511
Well 182526066165001 Local number SR-2	512
Well 182548066164401 Local number MA-2.....	513
Well 182620066163400 Local number HG-1	514
Well 182620066163403 Local number HG-4	517
Well 182657066162700 Local number SA-1	518
Well 182657066162701 Local number SA-3.....	519
Well 182654066150600 Local number TB-1	520
Well 182530066135400 Local number 216	521
Well 182655066142400 Local number 217	522

GROUND-WATER WELLS, BY BASIN, FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

Well 182441066082600 Local number 219	523
Well 182531066075900 Local number 652	524
Well 182511066045401 Local number PN-2	526
Well 182435066052700 Local number PN-5	527
Well 182445066043401 Local number PN-6	528
Well 182443066041502 Local number PN-8c	529
Well 182417066042700 Local number PN-10	530
Well 182349066032600 Local number PN-13	531
Well 182406066034700 Local number PN-19	532

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

Well 181352066025300 Local number CJ-TW19A	533
Well 181311066022500 Local number CJ-TW11	534
Well 181446066013400 Local number CJ-TW20	536
Well 181539066014500 Local number CJ-TW15	538
Well 181550065593200 Local number 50	540
Well 182515065594100 Local number 222	541
Well 181540065580300 Local number CJ-TW18	542
Well 181513065554600 Local number CJ-TW3B	544

RIO HERRERA TO RIO ANTON RUIZ BASINS

Well 182344065490801 Local number RE-2A	545
Well 182223065455900 Local number RM-02	547
Well 181230065444900 Local number ARR-1	548
Well 182138065431800 Local number RS-02	549
Well 182131065421100 Local number RP-04	550
Well 181823065401900 Local number RF-04	551
Well 181917065382701 Local number RF-12	552

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES BASINS

Well 180358065503600 Local number YDO-1	553
Well 180415065513900 Local number 96	554
Well 175855066023100 Local number FID-2	555
Well 175855066050500 Local number ALG-1	557
Well 175728066072200 Local number BAR-1	559
Well 175719066085500 Local number P-13	561
Well 175858066100200 Local number 6	562
Well 180002066132200 Local number HW-TW-01	563
Well 180001066122002 Local number HW-TW-03C	564
Well 175947066130601 Local number HW-TW-5B	565
Well 175957066123400 Local number HW-TW-13	566

GROUND-WATER WELLS, BY BASIN, FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

Well 175809066133100 Local number CQ-1.....567
 Well 180206066135500 Local number RM-5.....568
 Well 180104066152300 Local number RM-10.....569
 Well 175910066155500 Local number SA-D.....570
 Well 175708066163000 Local number EC-1.....572

 Well 175903066165000 Local number PG-07.....574
 Well 175943066224800 Local number PS-07.....575
 Well 175829066232200 Local number 87.....576
 Well 180020066261500 Local number CA-1.....577
 Well 180048066301800 Local number FA-1.....579

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

Well 175950066354200 Local number 141.....581
 Well 175934066364800 Local number CO-3.....582
 Well 180045066381600 Local number AN-1.....585
 Well 180156066434000 Local number LV-1.....586
 Well 180133066503300 Local number 132.....588

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

Well 180132067033800 Local number 143.....589
 Well 180542067084000 Local number CR-1.....590
 Well 180628067084300 Local number CR-TW9A.....593
 Well 180628067084301 Local number CR-TW9B.....594

RIO YAGUEZ TO RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASINS

Well 181232067083700 Local number CI-1.....597

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

Well 181911067140500 Local number C-4.....599
 Well 182017067143300 Local number R-4.....601
 Well 182442067091700 Local number 200.....604

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

Well 174225064472000 Local number 2.....616
 Well 174243064475100 Local number 3.....617
 Well 174316064480800 Local number 13.....618

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

Well 182038064550300 Local number 6.....619
 Well 182038064580000 Local number 8.....620

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

Well 181956064464500 Local number 11.....621

**WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998 DISCONTINUED
STREAMFLOW STATIONS**

The following continuous-record streamflow stations in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands have been discontinued or converted to partial-record stations. Daily streamflow or stage records were collected for the period of record shown for each station.

Station number	Station name	Drainage area (mi²)	Period of record
50007000	Quebrada de los Cedros near Isabela	6.91	1970
50010600	Río Guajataca above Lago de Guajataca	--	1984-89
50011000	Canal Diversion Lago Guajataca	--	1970
50011200	Río Guajataca below Lago Guajataca	--	1969-70,1984-87
50011400	Río Guajataca above mouth near Quebradillas	--	1969-70,1984-89
50013000	Río Camuy near Lares	7.62	1969-71
50014000	Río Criminales near Lares	4.68	1969-70
50014600	Río Camuy at Tres Pueblos Sinkhole	--	1990-96
50015700	Río Camuy near Hatillo	--	1984-96
50016000	Río Camuy near Camuy	--	1969-73
50021000	Río Pellejas at Central Pellejas	5.46	1968-70
50021050	Río Pellejas below Central Pellejas	7.89	1972-75
50021500	Río Pellejas near Utuado	9.55	1969-71
50023000	Río Viví near Central Pellejas	5.66	1969-75
50027200	Río Grande de Arecibo blw. Lago dos Bocas	169	1970-71
50029000	Río Grande de Arecibo at Central Cambalache	200	1969-83
50031500	Río Sana Muerto near Orocovic	3.68	1965-70
50035200	Río Grande de Manatí at Hwy 145 at Ciales	132	1972
50035950	Río Cialitos at Hwy 649 at Ciales	17	1970-82
50038360	Río Mavilla near Corozal	9.51	1969-70
50038600	Río Unibón near Morovis	5.29	1969-70
50038700	Río Morovis at Morovis	1.26	1968
50038900	Río Indio at Vega Baja	--	1963,66,71
50039600	Río Cibuco at Central San Vicente	--	1969-72
50043200	Río Usabon near Barranquitas	9.15	1968-69,71
50043400	Río Aibonito Tributary near Aibonito	1.13	1968-71
50044600	Río Guadiana near Naranjito	1.73	1971
50044650	Quebrada del Toro near Naranjito	0.54	1971
50044800	Quebrada Anones near Naranjito	2.32	1971
50045700	Río Lajas at Toa Alta	8.65	1966-75
50047820	Río de Bayamón at Hwy 174 near Bayamón	31.90	1966
50048000	Río de Bayamón at Bayamón	71.90	1963-67
50049000	Río Piedras at Río Piedras	12.5	1971-82, 1987-93
50049310	Quebrada Josefina at Piñero Avenue	3.84	1988-91
50053050	Río Turabo at Borinquen	7.89	1984-90
50054000	Quebrada de las Quebradillas near Caguas	6.25	1969-71,73
50055170	Río Cagüitas near Caguas	8.27	1992-97
50055650	Quebrada Caimito near Juncos	0.82	1984-87
50056000	Río Valenciano near Las Piedras	6.85	1971
50056900	Quebrada Mamey near Gurabo	2.30	1984-92

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998
DISCONTINUED STREAMFLOW STATIONS--Continued

Station number	Station name	Drainage area (mi²)	Period of record
50058300	Quebrada Arena near Caguas	--	1971
50059000	Río Piedras at Río Piedras	12.5	1971-82, 1987-93
50061300	Río Canovanillas near Loíza	14.40	1968-73
50062500	Río Herrera near Colonia Dolores	2.75	1968-72
50063300	Río Espíritu Santo near El Verde	2.23	1968-73
50063500	Quebrada Toronja at El Verde	0.064	1983-96
50065700	Río Mameyes at Hwy 191 at Mameyes	11.80	1967-85
50072000	Río Fajardo at Fajardo	21.60	1960-63
50073200	Río Daguao at Daguao	2.26	1966-82
50073400	Quebrada Palma at Daguao	4.84	1972-77
50074000	Río Santiago at Naguabo	4.99	1966-82
50075500	Río Blanco at Florida	11.00	1966-82
50076000	Río Blanco near Florida	12.30	1983-85
50077000	Río Blanco at Río Blanco	17.60	1973-77
50077400	Río Blanco at Colonia La Fe	18.80	1967-70
50078500	Río Anton Ruíz at Central Pasto Viejo	4.33	1968
50081500	Río Humacao near Humacao	9.23	1973
50082000	Río Humacao at Hwy 3 at Humacao	17.30	1983-85
50082200	Río Humacao near La Suiza	19.90	1965-66, 1969-71
50082800	Río Guayanés near Colonia Laura	4.69	1969-82
50083500	Río Guayanés near Yabucoa	17.20	1969-71
50084000	Río Limones near Yabucoa	7.89	1969-71
50085100	Río Guayanés at Central Roig	26.60	1965-66, 1968,70
50086100	Río del Ingenio at Comunas	5.50	1965-66, 1968-69
50086500	Río Guayanés at Playa Guayanés	34.00	1965-66, 1968-71
50087200	Caño Santiago near Central Roig	6.04	1965-71
50091000	Río Maunabo at Maunabo	12.40	1965,67, 1969-82
50091200	Río Maunabo near Maunabo	12.70	1971-72
50091400	Río Jacaboa near Lamboglia	4.13	1965-73
50091700	Río Chico at Patillas	6.82	1965, 1969-72
50091800	Río Chico at Providencia	4.90	1965, 1967-69, 1971
50094200	Río Grande de Patillas at Patillas	27.90	1967, 1969, 1971
50094300	Río Grande de Patillas at Providencia	29.00	1971
50094400	Río Nigua at Pitahaya	5.86	1965, 1969, 1970-71, 1973
50095200	Río Guamaní at Guayama	8.22	1969-71
50095500	Río Guamaní near Guayama	12.30	1969-70
50099000	Quebrada Aguas Verdes near Salinas	0.39	1989
50106500	Río Coamo near Coamo	46.00	1967-68, 1984-85, 1986
50106900	Río Coamo below Lago Coamo near Coamo	65.40	1967-68
50107200	Río Coamo at mouth near Santa Isabel	69.30	1967-68
50108200	Río Descalabrado at Las Ollas	13.90	1965, 1967-71
50108500	Río Descalabrado near Santa Isabel	18.10	1966-67
50111200	Río Toa Vaca near Villalba	21.40	1966-70
50111700	Río Jacaguas near Juana Díaz	53.20	1966-68
50111750	Río Jacaguas below Quebrada Guanábana	56.30	1989

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998
DISCONTINUED STREAMFLOW STATIONS--Continued

Station number	Station name	Drainage area (mi²)	Period of record
50112100	Río Jacaguas near Arús	59.60	1966-67
50112600	Río Inabón at Coto Laurel	--	1967-71
50113100	Río Guayo near Coto Laurel	11.80	1965, 1968-71
50113500	Río Inabón near Arús	30.20	1964-65
50114400	Río Bucaná near Ponce	25.60	1965-81
50114700	Río Bucaná near Playa de Ponce	28.40	1964-67
50115000	Río Portugués near Ponce	8.82	1964-97
50116500	Río Portugués at Highway 2 Bypass at Ponce	20.50	1964-65
50119000	Río Matilde at Ponce	19.40	1965-66
50121000	Río Tallaboa at Peñuelas	24.20	1959-82
50122000	Río Tallaboa at Tallaboa	31.50	1959-63
50124000	Río Guayanilla nr Guayanilla	18.50	1961-69
50124500	Río Guayanilla at Guayanilla	20.80	1971-82
50125900	Río Duey above Diversion near Yauco	8.93	1977-80
50126150	Río Yauco above Diversion Monserrate near Yauco	27.20	1978-85
50128000	Río Yauco near Yauco	45.50	1962-64, 1977-85
50129000	Río Loco near Yauco	8.50	1963-67
50129500	Río Loco near Guánica	21.00	1963-69
50129900	Laguna Cartagena near Boquerón	--	1984-86
50130320	Quebrada Mamey at Joyuda	0.38	1986-88
50136000	Río Rosario at Rosario	16.40	1975-86
50141000	Río Yahuecas near Adjuntas	15.40	1980-85
50145000	Río Grande de Añasco at El Espino	108.00	1959-66, 1961-63
50147000	Río Culebrinas at San Sebastian	16.70	1960-82
50214500	Quebrada Resaca near Monte Resaca, Culebra	0.23	1991-93
50215000	Drainage Canal at Culebra Airport, Culebra	0.08	1991-93
50231000	Quebrada Confresí Tributary near Isabel II, Vieques	0.28	1991-93
50232000	Quebrada La Mina near Esperanza, Vieques	0.68	1991-96
50233000	Quebrada Pilon at Colonia Puerto Real, Vieques	0.67	1991-96
50276000	Turpentine Run at Mariendal	2.97	1963-69, 1978-86
50292600	Lameshur Bay Gut at Lameshur, St. John	0.38	1992-94
50294000	Fish Bay Gut at Fish Bay, St. John	1.48	1992-94
50295500	Cruz Bay Gut at Cruz Bay, St. John, V	0.09	1992-93
50332000	River Gut at River	1.42	1991-93
50333500	River Gut near Golden Grove	5.40	1990-93
50333700	River Gut at Hwy 66 at Fairplanes	5.89	1990-96
50334500	Bethehem Gut at Hwy 66 at Fairplanes	4.11	1990-96
50337500	Gut 4.5 at Cane Valley	0.2	1991-93
50348000	Salt River at Canaan	0.36	1991-93
50349000	Gut 10 near Altona	0.13	1991-93

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998

INTRODUCTION

The Water Resources Division of the U.S. Geological Survey, in cooperation with local and federal agencies obtains a large amount of data pertaining to the water resources of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico and the Territory of the U.S. Virgin Islands each water year. These data, accumulated during many water years, constitute a valuable data base for developing an improved understanding of the water resources of the area. To make these data readily available to interested parties outside the U.S. Geological Survey, the data are published annually in this report series entitled "Water Resources Data for Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands, 1998."

This report includes records on both surface and ground water. Specifically, it contains: (1) discharge records for 76 streamflow gaging stations, daily sediment records for 27 streamflow stations, 99 partial-record or miscellaneous streamflow stations, stage records for 17 reservoirs, and (2) water-quality records for 16 streamflow-gaging stations, and for 42 ungaged stream sites, 11 lake sites, 2 lagoons, and 1 bay, and (3) water-level records for 97 observation wells.

Water-resources data for Puerto Rico for calendar years 1958-67 were released in a series of reports entitled "Water Records of Puerto Rico." Water-resources data for the U.S. Virgin Islands for the calendar years 1962-69 were released in a report entitled "Water Records of U.S. Virgin Islands." Included were records of streamflow, ground-water levels, and water-quality data for both surface and ground water.

Beginning with the 1968 calendar year, surface-water records for Puerto Rico were released separately on an annual basis. Ground-water level records and water-quality data for surface and ground water were released in companion reports covering periods of several years. Data for the 1973-74 reports were published under separate covers. Water-resources data reports for 1975-76, 1977, 1978, 1979-80, 1981-82, 1983, 1984, 1985, 1986, 1987, 1988, 1989, 1990, 1991, 1992, 1993, 1994, 1995, 1996, and 1997 water years consist of one volume each and contain data for streamflow, water quality, and ground water.

Publications similar to this report are published annually by the U.S. Geological Survey for all States. These official Survey reports have an identification number consisting of the two-letter State abbreviation, the last two digits of the water year, and the volume number. For example, this volume is identified as "U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-98-1." These water-data reports are for sale in paper copy or in microfiche by the National Technical Information Service, U.S. Department of Commerce, Springfield, Virginia, 22161.

Additional information, including current prices, for ordering specific reports may be obtained from the District Chief at the address given on back of the title page or by telephone (787) 749-4346.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998**COOPERATION**

The U.S. Geological Survey has had cooperative agreements with organizations of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico and the Territory of the U.S. Virgin Islands for the systematic collections of water resources data since 1958. Organizations that supplied data are acknowledged in the station descriptions. Organizations that assisted in collecting data through cooperative agreements with the U.S. Geological Survey are:

- Puerto Rico Environmental Quality Board
- Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority
- Puerto Rico Department of Agriculture
- Puerto Rico Industrial Development Company
- Puerto Rico Department of Housing
- Puerto Rico Highway Authority
- Puerto Rico Department of Natural and Environmental Resources
- Puerto Rico Department of Health
- Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority
- Puerto Rico Solid Waste Management Authority
- Puerto Rico Legislature
- Puerto Rico Civil Defense
- U.S. Virgin Islands Department of Planning and Natural Resources

Funds were also provided by the U.S. Army, Corps of Engineers, for the collection of records at six gaging stations published in this report.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998

SUMMARY OF HYDROLOGIC CONDITIONS

Rainfall

Rainfall throughout Puerto Rico during water year 1998 (October 1997 to September 1998) averaged about 117 percent above normal. Rainfall was above normal during the months of October, January, February, March, July, August, and September (table 1). Significant above-normal rainfall conditions were recorded during September as rainfall averaged 225 percent above normal, mostly due to the passage of Hurricane Georges over Puerto Rico during September 21-22, 1998. As much as 25 inches of rain fell on some of the island's interior municipios during a 24-hour period. Severe floods and landslides resulted from the intensive rainfall and serious damages to homes, businesses, and infrastructure were reported. During the months of November, December, April, May, and June, rainfall was deficient with averages that ranged from 28 to 97 percent of normal. Rainfall, during the 1998 water year, averaged 102 percent of normal in northern Puerto Rico, 126 percent of normal in southern Puerto Rico, 123 percent of normal in western Puerto Rico, and 121 percent of normal in eastern Puerto Rico. Monthly average rainfall islandwide for the 1998 water year and for the 30-year period (1961-1990) used to define normal rainfall, as reported by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration are listed in table 1.

Table 1. Islandwide monthly rainfall for the water year 1998 and annual averages for the 30-year reference period, 1961-1990

Month	1998 Water Year (inches)	30-year normal (inches)
October	9.52	8.29
November	4.68	6.55
December	1.23	4.38
January	4.16	2.86
February	4.08	2.52
March	3.59	3.02
April	4.32	4.46
May	6.46	6.96
June	4.66	4.99
July	5.39	5.08
August	9.52	6.89
September	<u>16.04</u>	<u>7.14</u>
TOTAL	73.65	63.14

Surface Water

Streamflow in Puerto Rico during most of the 1998 water year was, in general, above normal in southern and eastern Puerto Rico, but below normal in the northern and western regions, based on the four index stations. A comparison of the monthly-mean flows during the 1998 water year with the long-term minimum, median and maximum of the monthly mean flows, for the period of record at the index stations on the Río Grande de Manatí (north), the Río Fajardo (east), the Río Inabón (south), and the Río Grande de Añasco (west) is shown in figure 1. During December, below normal flows were recorded at the four index stations. At the Río Grande de Manatí and Río Grande de Añasco index stations these below normal flows established new historical minimum monthly-mean flows. Excessive flows occurred at the four index stations during September due to intensive rainfall produced by the passage of Hurricane Georges over Puerto Rico. Historical maximum monthly-mean flows for September, were recorded at the Río Grande de Manatí and Río Grande de Añasco.

In the northern area, the Río Grande de Manatí index station recorded flows below the long-term monthly median during October to January, March, April, and July. Monthly mean flows during these months ranged from 22 to 82 percent of the long-term median of the monthly mean flows. Monthly mean flow during February, May, June, August, and September was above normal, and ranged from 121 to 1,100 percent of normal. Historical minimum and maximum monthly mean flows were recorded at this index station during December and September, respectively.

In the eastern area, the index station on the Río Fajardo, recorded monthly mean flows above the long-term median during eleven of the twelve months of the 1998 water year. At this station, only the December mean flow was slightly below the long-term monthly median. The flow in December was 96 percent of normal. The rest of the year, monthly mean flows ranged from 124 to 220 percent of the long-term median.

Unshaded area indicates range between highest and lowest monthly-mean discharges for the period of record to water year 1998.

Figure 1. Monthly-mean discharge of selected streams in Puerto Rico.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998

In the southern area, the Río Inabón index station recorded monthly mean flows below the long-term median during October to January. During these months, the monthly mean flows ranged from 42 to 88 percent of normal. During April, a new historical minimum monthly mean flow was recorded. The rest of the year, the monthly mean flows were above the long-term monthly median, and ranged from 145 to 510 percent of normal.

In the western area, the index station on the Río Grande de Añasco, recorded monthly mean flows below the long-term median during the first seven months of the 1998 water year. A below normal monthly mean flow was also recorded during June. During these months, the monthly mean flows ranged from 41 to 89 percent of the long-term median. Historical minimum monthly mean flows were recorded during November and December at this index station. Mean monthly flows were above normal during May and from July to September. Monthly mean flows during these months ranged from 226 to 560 percent of the long-term median. A historical maximum monthly mean flow was recorded during September.

The most important hydrologic event that happened during the 1998 water year was the flooding caused by the intense rainfall generated by the passage of Hurricane Georges over Puerto Rico. The eye of Hurricane Georges made landfall near the municipios of Humacao and Yabucoa on the east coast of Puerto Rico and moved over the mountainous central region of the Island during September 21-22. Hurricane Georges produced heavy rains over Puerto Rico, especially in the mountainous interior. This heavy rain produced moderate to severe floods through the island. Almost all of the island's 78 municipios were affected by the floods. The most severe flooding occurred within the basins of the north and west areas: the Río Grande de Arecibo, the Río Grande de Manatí, the Río de la Plata, the Río Grande de Añasco, and the Río Culebrinas. Floodwaters inundated urban areas and communities, washing away and damaging homes, businesses, vehicles, bridges, and roads. Fortunately, there were no deaths directly associated with the passage of the hurricane over Puerto Rico. Damage to the island infrastructure was enormous. The U.S. Geological Survey data network was highly affected with many stations destroyed or severely damaged. Historical maximum peak stages and discharges were recorded during this event in several streamflow gaging stations. Peak stages and discharges at selected streamflow gaging stations in Puerto Rico are listed in table 2.

Table 2. Summary of peak stages and discharges prior to and during September 21-22, 1998, at selected U.S. Geological Survey streamflow gaging stations in Puerto Rico

[mi², square miles; ft³/s, cubic feet per second; mm/dd/yy, month/day/year]

Station number and name	Drainage area (mi ²)	Period of record	Previous maximum discharge			Flood of September 22, 1998	
			Date mm/dd/yy	Peak stage (feet)	Maximum discharge (ft ³ /s)	Peak stage (feet)	Peak discharge (ft ³ /s)
50034000 Río Bauta near Orocovis	16.7	1970-1982 1989-1998	9/10/1996	25.14	25,900	25.93	28,200
50050900 Río Grande de Loíza at Quebrada Arenas	6.0	1978-1998	9/10/1996	25.93	44,000	26.37	45,000
50061800 Río Canóvanas near Campo Rico	9.84	1967-1998	9/13/1982	13.10	15,000	15.90	17,300
50064200 Río Grande near El Verde	7.31	1967-1998	9/16/1975	15.50	17,400	19.30	22,000
50074950 Quebrada Guaba near Naguabo	0.05	1992-1998	9/10/1996	10.74	102	10.78	104
50106100 Río Coamo at Coamo	3.5	1987-1998	1/8/1992	25.67	51,600	25.94	52,700
50113800 Río Cerillos above Lago Cerrillos near Ponce	15.4	1989-1998	9/10/1996	10.62	10,600	12.42	16,200
50124200 Río Guayanilla near Guayanilla	18.9	1981-1998	9/12/1982	20.40	14,700	21.88	18,700
50131990 Río Guanajibo at Hwy 119 at San Germán	34.6	1991-1998	1/6/1992	13.23	6,610	19.53	24,900
50144000 Río Grande de Añasco near San Sebastián	94.3	1963-1998	9/16/1975	33.90	140,000	34.50	163,000

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998**Ground Water**

Ground-water levels in most aquifers in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands followed seasonal fluctuations associated with rainfall patterns during water year 1998. Generally, late into the water year, the ground-water levels increased in response to above-normal rainfall from July through November, especially during the passage of Hurricane Georges, on September 21-22, 1998, which caused flooding throughout most of the coastal plains. Ground-water levels generally declined during the months of April, May, and July through August in response, primarily, to ground-water withdrawals for public and industrial use in the north coast, and irrigation in the south coast. Record-low and record-high water levels were recorded at several wells in Puerto Rico during water year 1998 (tables 3 and 4).

Ground-water levels in the North Coast Limestone aquifer system of Puerto Rico fluctuated from October to August in response to seasonal rainfall patterns and sustained ground-water withdrawals. This trend was altered by the rainfall produced by Hurricane Georges in late September, which caused water levels to rise significantly at the Sabana Hoyos index well, where the ground-water levels rose 1.20 ft (fig. 2).

In the South Coastal Plain aquifer system of Puerto Rico, the ground-water levels remained relatively stable from October to August, in response to above-normal rainfall runoff which may have neutralized the drawdown trend from sustained ground-water withdrawals for agricultural, public, and industrial use. A significant rise was recorded during September, when Hurricane Georges affected the area and ground-water levels rose 2.50 ft at the Alomar index well (fig. 2).

In the U.S. Virgin Islands (St. Croix, St. Thomas, and St. John) ground-water levels rose significantly from mid-October to early December as heavy rainfall was recorded in the area. The ground-water levels generally declined from early December to mid-September in response to below-normal rainfall and sustained ground-level withdrawals. The declining trend was reversed by above-normal rainfall produced by the passage of Hurricane Georges by the area. At the Guinea Gut well, the ground-water levels rose about 15.50 ft (fig. 2).

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Table 3. Highest ground-water levels recorded during 1998 water year and previous high ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico

[PR, Puerto Rico; mm/dd/yy, month/day/year; ft-blsd, feet below land-surface datum; mm/yy, month/year]

Well name or number	Local number	Location	Period of record (mm/yy)	Previous highest water level (ft-blsd)	Date (mm/dd/yy)	1998 Highest water level (ft-blsd)	Date (mm/dd/yy)
Florida #01	FL-1	PR	08/96 to 09/98	139.90	09/20/96	137.91	09/22/98
La Esperanza 2	PN-2	PR	07/89 to 09/98	8.01	12/30/92 12/31/92	7.71	09/23/98
CJ-TW-19A	CJ-TW-19A	PR	06/92 to 09/98	22.60	09/14/96	22.07	09/25/98 09/26/98 09/27/98
Jardín Botánico #3	PN-19	PR	06/91 to 09/98	3.06	09/11/96	2.84	09/22/98 09/23/98
Yabucoa 7	96	PR	04/78 to 09/98	13.10	12/02/87	9.67	09/30/98
HW-TW-5B	HW-TW-5B	PR	04/88 to 09/98	7.89	05/26/92	5.93	09/22/98
Albergue de Niños Ponce	AN-1	PR	03/92 to 09/98	35.29	06/22/92	28.57	09/27/98
Aguadilla Cement	200	PR	10/85 to 09/98	2.24	08/25/88	1.61	09/22/98

Table 4. Lowest ground-water levels recorded during 1998 water year and previous low ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico

[PR, Puerto Rico; mm/dd/yy, month/day/year; ft-blsd, feet below land-surface datum; mm/yy, month/year]

Well name or number	Local number	Location	Period of record (mm/yy)	Previous lowest water level (ft-blsd)	Date (mm/dd/yy)	1998 lowest water level (ft-blsd)	Date (mm/dd/yy)
Encantada 1	EN-1	PR	08/96 to 09/98	313.74	07/05/98 07/06/97	313.84	04/03/98
Palo Alto 2	PA-2	PR	05/96 to 09/98	240.04	08/12/96 to 08/15/96	240.14	08/18/98
Phillips 13	P-13	PR	09/91 to 09/98	28.88	09/22/95	31.22	08/24/98
HW-TW-13	HW-TW-13	PR	04/88 to 09/98	48.10	11/06/92 11/07/92	48.12	09/03/98
Vivoni Col. Amistad	143	PR	10/85 to 09/98	40.70	09/26/97 10/09/97	40.85	10/08/97
CR-TW-9A	CR-TW-9A	PR	05/96 to 09/98	7.22	08/14/97	8.53	03/21/98

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Figure 2. Ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.

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Water Quality

In the water year 1998 the U.S. Geological Survey, in cooperation with several local government agencies, collected water-quality data at 73 surface-water stations in Puerto Rico. The water-quality data collected at these stations included the major chemical constituents, such as calcium, magnesium, sodium, chloride and sulfate. The data also included constituents listed in table 5. The highest concentration for each of these constituents detected during water year 1998 and the station where it was detected are summarized in table 5.

Table 5. Surface-water quality stations in Puerto Rico with highest concentration of selected constituents during water year 1998

[All constituent concentrations are in milligrams per liter; MBAS, Methylene blue active substance]

Station number	Station name	Constituent	Concentration
50144000	Río Grande de Añasco near San Sebastián	Sulfide	1.2
50047530	Río Hondo at Flood Channel	Boron	1.9
50147600	Río Culebrinas near San Sebastián	Manganese	1.1
50025000	Río Grande de Arecibo near Utuado	Iron	8.4
50055400	Río Bairoa near Caguas	Zinc	0.60
*	*	Cyanide	<0.01
50049100	Río Piedras at Hato Rey	Phenols	0.04
50055400	Río Bairoa near Caguas	MBAS	0.91

* Cyanide concentrations at all water-quality stations were below the detection limit (<0.010).

The presence of high concentrations of fecal coliform (fig. 3) and fecal streptococcal (fig. 4) bacteria continued to be the principal surface-water quality problem in Puerto Rico during water year 1998. The highest concentrations observed during this year occurred in stations located in the San Juan Metropolitan area which has the highest population concentration in Puerto Rico. The main sources of contamination in surface-water systems in Puerto Rico are discharges of liquid wastes from industrial and municipal sources. The highest concentration of fecal coliform and fecal streptococcal bacterial in surface waters in Puerto Rico generally occurred in streams draining densely populated and industrialized areas.

Suspended-sediment concentration were monitored at 27 stations in Puerto Rico during water year 1998 as part of the cooperative program between the U.S. Geological Survey and various local and federal agencies. High suspended-sediment concentrations are a common problem in many streams in Puerto Rico. Most of the streams with high suspended-sediment concentrations were related to land use, especially urban development, agriculture, and activities where soil movement was involved. The high suspended-sediment concentrations affect the quality of drinking water sources and the storage capacities of reservoirs used for water supply.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998

SPECIAL NETWORKS AND PROGRAMS

Hydrologic Bench-Mark Network is a network of 57 sites in small drainage basins around the country whose purpose is to provide consistent data on the hydrology, including water quality, and related factors in representative undeveloped watersheds nationwide, and to provide analyses on a continuing basis to compare and contrast conditions observed in basins more obviously affected by the activities of man.

National Stream Quality Accounting Network (NASQAN) is a nationwide data-collection network designed by the U.S. Geological Survey to meet many of the information needs of government agencies and other groups involved in natural or regional water-quality planning and management. The 500 or so sites on NASQAN are generally located at the downstream ends of hydrologic accounting units designated by the U.S. Geological Survey Office of Water Data Coordination in consultation with the Water Resources Council. The objectives of NASQAN are (1) to obtain information on the quality and quantity of water moving within and from the United States through a systematic and uniform process of data collection, summarization, analysis, and reporting such that the data may be used for, (2) description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of data from this and other programs, (3) detection of changes or trends with time in the pattern of occurrence of water-quality characteristics, and (4) providing a nationally consistent data base useful for water-quality assessment and hydrologic research.

The National Trends Network (NTN) is a 150-station network for sampling atmospheric deposition in the United States. The purpose of the network is to determine the variability, both in location and in time, of the composition of atmospheric deposition, which includes snow, rain, dust particles, aerosols, and gases. The core from which the NTN was built was the already-existing deposition-monitoring network of the National Atmospheric Deposition Program (NADP).

The National Water-Quality Assessment (NAWQA) Program of the U.S. Geological Survey is a long-term program with goals to describe the status and trends of water-quality conditions for a large, diverse, and geographically distributed part of the Nation's ground- and surface-water resources, and to identify, describe, and explain the major natural and human factors that affect these observed conditions and trends.

Assessment activities have begun in more than one-third of the study units and ultimately will be conducted in 60 study units (major watersheds and aquifer systems) that represent a wide range of environmental settings nationwide and that account for a large percentage of the Nation's water use. A wide array of chemical constituents will be measured in ground water, surface water, streambed sediments, and fish tissues. The coordinated application of comparative hydrologic studies at a wide range of spatial and temporal scales will provide information for decision making by water-resources managers and a foundation for aggregation and comparison of findings to address water-quality issues of regional and national interest.

Radiochemical Programs is a network of regularly sampled water-quality stations where samples are collected to be analyzed for radioisotopes. The streams that are sampled represent major drainage basins in the conterminous United States.

Tritium Network is a network of stations which has been established to provide baseline information on the occurrence of tritium in the Nation's surface waters. In addition to the surface-water stations in the network, tritium data are also obtained at a number of precipitation stations. The purpose of the precipitation stations is to provide an estimate sufficient for hydrologic studies of the tritium input to the United States.

EXPLANATION OF RECORDS

The surface- and ground-water records published in this report are for the 1998 water year that began October 1, 1997 and ended September 30, 1998. A calendar of the water year is provided on the inside of the front cover. The records contain streamflow data, water-quality data for surface and ground water, and ground-water-level data. The locations of the stations and wells where the data were collected are shown in figures 3 to 9. The following sections of the introductory text are presented to provide users with a more detailed explanation of how the hydrologic data published in this report were collected, analyzed, computed, and arranged for presentation.

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Station Identification Numbers

Each data station, whether stream site or well, in this report is assigned a unique identification number. This number is unique in that it applies specifically to a given station and to no other. The number usually is assigned when a station is first established and is retained for that station indefinitely. The systems used by the U.S. Geological Survey to assign identification numbers for surface-water stations and for ground-water well sites differ, but both are based on geographic location. The "downstream order" system is used for regular surface-water stations and the "latitude-longitude" system is used for wells.

Downstream Order System

Since October 1, 1950, the order of listing hydrologic-station records in Survey reports is in a downstream direction along the main stream. All stations on a tributary entering upstream from a main-stream station are listed before that station. A station on a tributary that enters between two main-stream stations is listed between them. A similar order is followed in listing stations in first rank, second rank, and other ranks of tributaries.

As an added means of identification, each hydrologic station and partial-record station has been assigned a station number. These are in the same downstream order used in this report. In assigning station numbers, no distinction is made between partial-record stations and other stations; therefore, the station number for a partial-record station indicates downstream order position in a list made up of both types of stations that may be established; hence, the numbers are not consecutive. The complete 8-digit number for each station such as 50028000, which appears just to the left of the station name, includes the 2-digit part number "50" plus the 6-digit downstream order number "028000."

Latitude-Longitude System

The 8-digit downstream order station numbers are not assigned to wells and miscellaneous sites where only random water-quality samples or discharge measurements are taken.

The well and miscellaneous site numbering system of the U.S. Geological Survey is based on the grid system of latitude and longitude. The system provides the geographic location of the well or miscellaneous site and a unique number for each site. The number consists of 15 digits. The first 6 digits denote the degrees, minutes, and seconds of latitude, the next 7 digits denote degrees, minutes, and seconds of longitude, and the last 2 digits (assigned sequentially) identify the wells or other sites within a 1-second grid. The numbers shown in the grid correspond to the local numbers assigned to each well as visited in the field. An example is well 16 (fig. 10).

Figure 3. Location of maximum concentration of fecal coliform bacteria at the water-quality sampling sites in Puerto Rico.

Figure 4. Location of maximum concentration of fecal streptococci bacteria at the water-quality sampling sites in Puerto Rico.

Figure 5. Location of surface-water stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 6. Location of water-quality stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 7. Location of ground-water stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 8. Location of surface-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.

Figure 9. Location of ground-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.

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Figure 10. Grid showing system for numbering wells and miscellaneous sites (latitude and longitude).

Records of Stage and Water Discharge

Records of stage and water discharge may be complete or partial. Complete records of discharge are those obtained using a continuous stage-recording device through which either instantaneous or mean daily discharges may be computed for any time, or any period of time, during the period of record. Complete records of lake or reservoir content, similarly, are those for which stage or content may be computed or estimated with reasonable accuracy for any time, or period of time. They may be obtained using a continuous stage-recording device, but need not be. Because daily mean discharges and end-of-day contents commonly are published for such stations, they are referred to as "daily stations."

By contrast, partial records are obtained through discrete measurements without using a continuous stage-recording device and pertain only to a few flow characteristics, or perhaps only one. The nature of the partial record is indicated by table titles such as "Low-flow partial records." Records of miscellaneous discharge measurements or of measurements from special studies, such as low-flow seepage studies, may be considered as partial records, but they are presented separately in this type of report. Location of all complete-record stations for which data are given in this report are shown in figures 5 and 8.

Data Collection and Computation

The data obtained at a complete-record gaging station on a stream or canal consists of a continuous record of stage, individual measurements of discharge throughout a range of stages, and notations regarding factors that may affect the relationships between stage and discharge. These data, together with supplemental information, such as weather records, are used to compute daily discharges. The data obtained at a complete-record gaging station on a lake or reservoir consist of a record of stage and of notations regarding factors that may affect the relationship between stage and lake content. These data are used with stage-area and stage-capacity curves or tables to compute water-surface areas and lake storage.

Continuous records of stage are obtained with analog recorders that trace continuous graphs of stage or with digital recorders that punch stage values on paper tapes at selected time intervals or electronic satellite data collector platforms that receive stage values at selected time intervals. Measurements of discharge are made with current meters using methods adapted by the Geological Survey as a result of experience accumulated since 1880. These methods are described in standard textbooks, in Water-Supply Paper 2175, and in U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations, Book 3, Chapter A6.

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In computing discharge records, results of individual measurements are plotted against the corresponding stages, and stage-discharge relation curves are then constructed. From these curves, rating tables indicating the approximate discharge for any stage within the range of the measurements are prepared. If it is necessary to define extremes of discharge outside the range of the current-meter measurements, the curves are extended using: (1) logarithmic plotting; (2) velocity-area studies; (3) results of indirect measurements of peak discharge, such as slope-area or contracted-opening measurements, and computations of flow-over-dams or weirs; or (4) step-backwater techniques.

Daily mean discharges are computed by applying the daily mean stages (gage heights) to the stage-discharge curves or tables. If the stage-discharge relation is subject to change because of frequent or continual change in the physical features that form the control, the daily mean discharge is determined by the shifting-control method, in which correction factors based on the individual discharge measurements and notes of the personnel making the measurements are applied to the gage heights before the discharges are determined from the curves or tables. This shifting-control method also is used if the stage-discharge relation is changed temporarily because of aquatic growth or debris on the control. At some stations the stage-discharge relation is affected by changing stage; at these stations the rate of change in stage is used as a factor in computing discharge.

In computing records of lake or reservoir contents, it is necessary to have available from surveys, curves or tables defining the relationship of stage and contents. The application of stage to the stage-content curves or tables gives the contents from which daily, monthly or yearly changes then are determined. If the stage-content relationship changes because of deposition of sediment in a lake or reservoir, periodic surveys may be necessary to redefine it. Even when this is done, as time between the last survey increases, the contents computed may increase in error. Discharges over lake or reservoir spillways are computed from stage-discharge relationships much as other stream discharges are computed.

For some gaging stations there are periods when no gage-height record is obtained, or the recorded gage height is so faulty that it cannot be used to compute daily discharge or contents. This happens when the recorder stops or otherwise fails to operate properly, intakes are plugged, the float is loose in the well, or for various other reasons. For such periods, the daily discharges are estimated from the recorded range in stage, previous or following record, discharge measurements, weather records, and comparison with other station records from the same or nearby basins. Likewise, daily contents may be estimated from operator's logs, previous or following record, inflow-outflow studies, and other information. Information explaining how estimated daily-discharge values are identified in station records is included in the next two sections, "Data Presentation" (REMARKS paragraph) and "Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge."

Data Presentation

Streamflow data in this report are presented in a new format that is considerably different from the format in data reports prior to the 1992 water year. The major changes are that statistical characteristics of discharge now appear in tabular summaries following the water-year data table and less information is provided in the text or station manuscript above the table. These changes represent the results of a pilot program to reformat the annual water-data report to meet current user needs and data preferences.

The records published for each continuous-record surface-water discharge station (gaging station) now consist of four parts, the manuscript or station description; the data table of daily mean values of discharge for the current water year with summary data; a tabular statistical summary of monthly mean flow data for a designated period, by water year; and a summary statistics table that includes statistical data of annual, daily, and instantaneous flows as well as data pertaining to annual runoff, 7-day low-flow minimum, and flow duration.

Station manuscript

The manuscript provides, under various headings, descriptive information, such as station location; period of record; historical extremes outside the period of record; record accuracy; and other remarks pertinent to station operation and regulation. The following information, as appropriate, is provided with each continuous record of discharge or lake content. Comments to follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the stations descriptions.

LOCATION.--Information on locations is obtained from the most accurate maps available. The location of the gage with respect to the cultural and physical features in the vicinity and with respect to the reference place mentioned in the station name is given.

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DRAINAGE AREA.--Drainage areas are measured using the most accurate maps available. Drainage areas are updated as better maps become available.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This indicates the period for which there are published records for the station or for an equivalent station. An equivalent station is one that was in operation at a time that the present station was not, and whose location was such that records from it can reasonable be considered equivalent with records from the present station.

REVISED RECORDS.--Because of new information, published records occasionally are found to be incorrect, and revisions are printed in later reports. Listed under this heading are all the reports in which revisions have been published for the station and the water years to which the revisions apply. If a revision did not include daily, monthly, or annual figures of discharge, that fact is noted after the year dates as follows: "(M)" means that only the instantaneous maximum discharge was revised; "(m)" that only the instantaneous minimum was revised; and "(P)" that only peak discharges were revised. If the drainage area has been revised, the report in which the most recently revised figure was first published is given.

GAGE.--The type of gage in current use, the datum of the current gage, and a condensed history of the types, locations, and datums of previous gages are given under this heading.

REMARKS.--All periods of estimated daily-discharge record will either be identified by date in this paragraph of the station description for water-discharge stations or flagged in the daily-discharge table. (See next section, "Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge.") If a remarks statement is used to identify estimated record, the paragraph will begin with this information presented as the first entry. The paragraph is also used to present information relative to the accuracy of the records, to special methods of computations, to conditions that affect natural flow at the station and, possibly, to other pertinent items. For reservoir stations, information is given on the dam forming the reservoir, the capacity, outlet works and spillway, and purpose and use of the reservoir.

COOPERATION.--Records provided by a cooperating organization or obtained for the Geological Survey by a cooperating organization are identified here.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Included here is information concerning major floods or unusually low flows that occurred outside the stated period of record. The information may or may not have been obtained by the U.S. Geological Survey.

REVISIONS.--If a critical error in published records is discovered, a revision is included in the first report published following discovery of the error.

Although rare, occasionally the records of a discontinued gaging station may need revision. Because, for these stations, there would be no current or, possibly, future station manuscript published to document the revision in a "Revised Records" entry, users of data for these stations who obtained the record from previously published data reports may wish to contact the District office to determine if the published records were ever revised after the station was discontinued. Of course, if the data were obtained by computer retrieval, the data would be current and there would be no need to check because any published revision of data is always accompanied by revision of the corresponding data in computer storage.

Manuscript information for lake or reservoir stations differs from that for stream stations in the nature of the "Remarks" and in the inclusion of a skeleton stage-capacity table when daily contents are given.

Data table of daily mean value

The daily table of discharge records for stream gaging stations gives mean discharge for each day of the water year. In the monthly summary for the table, the line headed "TOTAL" gives the sum of the daily figures for each month; the line headed "MEAN" gives the average flow in cubic feet per second for the month; and the lines headed "MAX" and "MIN" give the maximum and minimum daily mean discharges, respectively, for each month. Discharge for the month also is usually expressed in cubic feet per second per square mile (line headed "CFSM"); or in inches (line headed "IN"); or in acre-feet (line headed "AC-FT"). Figures for cubic feet per second per square mile and runoff in inches or in acre-feet may be omitted if there is extensive regulations or diversion or if the drainage area includes large noncontributing areas.

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Statistics of monthly mean data

A tabular summary of the mean (line headed "MEAN"), maximum (line headed "MAX"), and minimum (line headed "MIN") of monthly mean flows for each month for a designated period is provided below the mean values table. The water years of the first occurrence of the maximum and minimum monthly flow are provided immediately below those figures. The designated period will be expressed as "FOR WATER YEARS ____ - ____, BY WATER YEAR (WY)," and will list the first and last water years of the range of years selected from the PERIOD OF RECORD paragraph in the station manuscript. It will consist of all of the station records within the specified water years, including complete months of record for partial water years, if any, and may coincide with the period of record for the station. The water years for which the statistics are computed will be consecutive, unless a break in the station record is indicated in the manuscript.

Summary statistics

A table titled "SUMMARY STATISTICS" follows the statistics of monthly mean data tabulation. This table consists of four columns, with the first column containing the line headings of the statistics being reported. The table provides a statistical summary of yearly, daily, and instantaneous flows, not only for the current water year but also for the previous calendar year and for a designated period, as appropriate. The designated period selected, "WATER YEARS ____ - ____," will consist of all of the station records within the specified water years, inclusive, including complete months of record for partial water years, if any, and may coincide with the period of record for the station. The water years for which the statistics are computed will be consecutive, unless a break in the station record is indicated in the manuscript. All of the calculations for the statistical characteristics designated ANNUAL (see line headings below), except for the "ANNUAL 7-DAY MINIMUM" statistic, are calculated for the designated period using complete water years. The other statistical characteristics may be calculated using partial water years.

The date or water year, as appropriate, of the first occurrence of each statistic reporting extreme values of discharge is provided adjacent to the statistic. Repeated occurrences may be noted in the REMARKS paragraph of the manuscript or in footnotes. Because the designated period may not be the same as the station period of record published in the manuscript, occasionally the dates of occurrence listed for the daily and instantaneous extremes in the designated-period column may not be within the selected water years listed in the heading. When this occurs, it will be noted in the REMARKS paragraph or in footnotes. Selected streamflow duration curve statistics and runoff data are also given. Runoff data may be omitted if there is extensive regulation or diversion of flow in the drainage basin.

The following summary statistics data, as appropriate, are provided with each continuous record of discharge. Comments to follow clarify information presented under the various line headings of the summary statistics table.

ANNUAL TOTAL.--The sum of the daily mean values of discharge for the year. At some stations the annual total discharge is adjusted for reservoir storage or diversion. The adjusted figures are identified by a symbol and corresponding footnotes.

ANNUAL MEAN.--The arithmetic mean of the individual daily mean discharges for the year noted or for the designated period. At some stations the yearly mean discharge is adjusted for reservoir storage or diversion. The adjusted figures are identified by a symbol and corresponding footnotes.

HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN.--The maximum annual mean discharge occurring for the designated period.

LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN.--The minimum annual mean discharge occurring for the designated period.

HIGHEST DAILY MEAN.--The maximum daily mean discharge for the year or for the designated period.

LOWEST DAILY MEAN.--The minimum daily mean discharge for the year or for the designated period.

ANNUAL 7-DAY MINIMUM.--The lowest mean discharge for 7 consecutive days for a calendar year or a water year. Note that most low-flow frequency analyses of annual 7-day minimum flows use a climatic year (April 1 - March 31). The date shown in the summary statistics table is the initial date of the 7-day period. (This value should not be confused with the 7-day 10-year low-flow statistics).

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INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW.--The maximum instantaneous discharge occurring for the water year or for the designated period. Note that secondary instantaneous peak discharges above a selected base discharge are stored in District computer files for stations meeting certain criteria. Those discharge values may be obtained by writing to the District Office. (See address on back of the title page of this report.)

INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE.--The maximum instantaneous stage occurring for the water year or for the designated period. If the dates of occurrence for the instantaneous peak flow and instantaneous peak stage differ, the REMARKS paragraph in the manuscript or a footnote may be used to provide further information.

INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW.--The minimum instantaneous discharge occurring for the water year or for the designated period.

ANNUAL RUNOFF.--Indicates the total quantity of water in runoff for a drainage area for the year. Data reports may use any of the following units of measurements in presenting annual runoff data:

Acre-foot (AC-FT) is the quantity of water required to cover 1 acre to a depth of 1 foot and is equivalent to 43,560 cubic feet or about 326,000 gallons or 1,233 cubic meters.

Cubic feet per second per square mile (CFSM) is the average number of cubic feet of water flowing per second from each square mile of area drained, assuming the runoff is distributed uniformly in time and area.

Inches (INCHES) indicates the depth to which the drainage area would be covered if all of the runoff for given time period were uniformly distributed on it.

10 PERCENT EXCEEDS.--The discharge that is exceeded 10 percent of the time for the designated period.

50 PERCENT EXCEEDS.--The discharge that is exceeded 50 percent of the time for the designated period.

90 PERCENT EXCEEDS.--The discharge that is exceeded 90 percent of the time for the designated period.

Data collected at partial-record stations follow the information for continuous-record sites. Data for partial-record discharge stations are presented in a table of discharge measurements at low-flow partial-record stations. These measurements are generally made in times of drought to give better areal coverage to those events. Those measurements and others collected for some special reason are called measurements at miscellaneous sites.

Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge

Estimated daily-discharge values published in the water-discharge tables are identified by flagging individual daily values with the letter symbol "e" and printing a table footnote, "e Estimated."

Accuracy of the Records

The accuracy of streamflow records depends primarily on: (1) The stability of the stage-discharge relation or, if the control is unstable, the frequency of discharge measurements; and (2) the accuracy of measurements of stage, measurements of discharge, and interpretation of records.

The accuracy attributed to the records is indicated under "REMARKS." "Excellent" means that about 95 percent of the daily discharges are within 5 percent of the true; "good," within 10 percent; and "fair," within 15 percent. Records that do not meet the criteria mentioned, are rated "poor." Different accuracies may be attributed to different parts of a given record.

Daily mean discharges in this report are given to the nearest hundredth of a cubic foot per second for values less than 1 ft³/s; to the nearest tenth between 1.0 and 10 ft³/s; to whole numbers between 10 and 1,000 ft³/s; and to 3 significant figures for more than 1,000 ft³/s. The number of significant figures used is based solely on the magnitude of the discharge value. The same rounding rules apply to discharges listed for partial-record stations and miscellaneous sites.

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Information used in the preparation of the records in this publication, such as discharge-measurement notes, gage-height records, temperature measurements, and rating tables are on file in the Caribbean District office. Also, most of the daily mean discharges are in computer-readable form and have been analyzed statistically. Information on the availability of the unpublished information or on the results of statistical analyses of the published records may be obtained from the District office.

Records of Surface-Water Quality

Records of surface-water quality ordinarily are obtained at or near stream gaging stations because interpretation of records of surface-water quality nearly always requires corresponding discharge data. Records of surface-water quality in this report may involve a variety of types of data and measurement frequencies.

Classification of Records

Water-quality data for surface-water sites are grouped into one of three classifications. A **continuing-record station** is a site where data are collected on a regularly scheduled basis. Frequency may be once or more times daily, weekly, monthly, or quarterly. A **partial-record station** is a site where limited water-quality data are collected systematically over a period of years. Frequency of sampling is usually less than quarterly. A **miscellaneous** sampling site is a location other than a continuing or partial-record station, where random samples are collected to give better areal coverage to define water-quality conditions in the river basin.

A careful distinction needs to be made between "continuing records" as used in this report and "continuous recordings," which refers to a continuous graph or a series of discrete values punched at short intervals on a paper tape. Some records of water quality, such as temperature and specific conductance, may be obtained through continuous recordings; however, because of costs, most data are obtained only monthly or less frequently. Locations of stations for which records on the quality of surface water appear in this report are shown in figure 6.

Arrangement of Records

Water-quality records collected at a surface-water daily record station are published immediately following that record, regardless of the frequency of sample collection. Station number and name are the same for both records. Where a surface-water daily record station is not available or where the water quality differs significantly from that at the nearby surface-water station, the continuing water-quality record is published with its own station number and name in the regular downstream-order sequence. Water-quality data for partial-record stations and for miscellaneous sampling sites appear in separate tables following the table of discharge measurement at miscellaneous sites.

On-site Measurements and Sample Collection

In obtaining water-quality data, a major concern needs to be assuring that the data obtained represent the in situ quality of the water. To assure this, certain measurements, such as water temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen, need to be made onsite when the samples are taken. To assure that measurements made in the laboratory also represent the in situ water, carefully prescribed procedures need to be followed in collecting the samples, in treating the samples to prevent changes in quality pending analysis, and in shipping the samples to the laboratory. Procedures for onsite measurements and for collecting, treating, and shipping samples are given in publications on "Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations," Book 1, Chap. D2; Book 3, Chap. C2; Book 5, Chap. A1, A3, and A4. Detailed information on collecting, treating, and shipping samples may be obtained from the Geological Survey District office.

One sample can define adequately the water quality at a given time if the mixture of solutes throughout the stream cross section is homogeneous. However, the concentration of solutes at different locations in the cross section may vary widely with different rates of water discharge, depending on the source of material and the turbulence and mixing of the stream. Some streams must be sampled through several vertical sections to obtain a representative sample needed for an accurate mean concentration and for use in calculating load. All samples obtained for the National Stream Quality Accounting Network (see definitions) are obtained from at least several verticals. Whether samples are obtained from the centroid of flow or from several verticals, depends on flow conditions and other factors which must be evaluated by the collector.

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Chemical-quality data published in this report are considered to be the most representative values available for the stations listed. The values reported represent water-quality conditions at the time of sampling as much as possible, consistent with available sampling techniques and methods of analysis. In the rare case where an apparent inconsistency exists between a reported pH value and the relative abundance of carbon dioxide species (carbonate and bicarbonate), the inconsistency is the result of a slight uptake of carbon dioxide from the air by the sample between measurement of pH in the field and determination of carbonate and bicarbonate in the laboratory.

For chemical-quality stations equipped with digital monitors, the records consist of daily maximum, minimum, and mean values for each constituent measured and are based upon hourly punches beginning at 0100 hours and ending at 2400 hours for the day of record. More detailed records, when available, (hourly values) may be obtained from the U.S.G.S. District office whose address is given on the back of the title page of this report.

Water Temperature

Water temperatures are measured at most of the water-quality stations. In addition, water temperatures are taken at time of discharge measurements for water-discharge stations. For stations where water temperatures are taken manually once or twice daily, the water temperatures are taken at about the same time each day. Large streams have a small diurnal temperature change; shallow streams may have a daily range of several degrees and may follow closely the changes in air temperature. Some streams may be affected by waste-heat discharges.

At stations where recording instruments are used, either mean temperatures or maximum and minimum temperatures for each day are published. Water temperatures measured at the time of water-discharge measurements are on file in the District office.

Sediment

Suspended-sediment concentrations are determined from samples collected by using depth-integrating and pumping sediment samplers. Samples usually are obtained at several verticals in the cross section, or a single sample may be obtained at a fixed point and a coefficient applied to determine the mean concentration in the cross sections.

During periods of rapidly changing flow or rapidly changing concentration, samples may have been collected more frequently (twice daily or hourly). The published sediment discharges for days of rapidly changing flow or concentration were computed by the subdivided-day method (time-discharge weighted average). Therefore, for those days when the published sediment discharge value differs from the value computed as the product of discharge times mean concentration times 0.0027, the reader can assume that the sediment discharge for that day was computed by the subdivided-day method. For periods when no samples were collected, daily discharges of suspended sediment were estimated on the basis of water discharge, sediment concentrations observed immediately before and after the periods, suspended-sediment loads for other periods of similar discharge, and computed by the subdivided-day method using the transport curves.

At other stations, suspended-sediment samples were collected periodically at many verticals in the stream cross section. Although data collected periodically may represent conditions only at the time of observations, such data are useful in establishing seasonal relations between quality and streamflow and in predicting long-term sediment-discharge characteristics of the stream.

In addition to the records of suspended-sediment discharge, records of the periodic measurements of the particle-size distribution of the suspended sediment are included for some stations.

Laboratory Measurements

Sediment samples, samples for biochemical-oxygen demand (BOD), samples for indicator bacteria, and daily samples for specific conductance are analyzed locally. All other samples are analyzed in the Geological Survey laboratories in Denver, Co. or Ocala, Fla. Methods used in analyzing sediment samples and computing sediment records are given in TWRI, Book 5, Chap. C1. Methods used by the Geological Survey laboratories are given in TWRI, Book 1, Chap. D2; Book 3, Chap. C2; Book 5, Chap. A1, A3, and A4.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998**Data Presentation**

For continuing-record stations, information pertinent to the history of station operation is provided in descriptive headings preceding the tabular data. These descriptive headings give details regarding location, drainage area, period of record, type of data available, instrumentation, general remarks, cooperation, and extremes for parameters currently measured daily. Tables of chemical, physical, biological, radiochemical data, and so forth, obtained at a frequency less than daily are presented first, and tables of "daily values" of specific conductance, pH, water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and suspended sediment then follow in sequence, when these parameters are studied.

In the descriptive headings, if the location is identical to that of the discharge gaging station, neither the LOCATION nor the DRAINAGE AREA statements are repeated. The following information, as appropriate, is provided with each continuous-record station. Comments that follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the station description.

LOCATION.--See Data Presentation under "Records of Stage and Water Discharge;" same comments apply.

DRAINAGE AREA.--See Data Presentation under "Records of Stage and Water Discharge;" same comments apply.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This indicates the periods for which there are published water-quality records for the station. The periods are shown separately for records of parameters measured daily or continuously and those measured less than daily. For those measured daily or continuously, periods of record are given for the parameters individually.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Information on instrumentation is given only if a water-quality monitor temperature record, sediment pumping sampler, or other sampling device is in operation at a station.

REMARKS.--Remarks provide added information pertinent to the collection, analysis, or computation of the records.

COOPERATION.--Records provided by a cooperating organization or obtained for the Geological Survey by a cooperating organization are identified here.

EXTREMES.--Maximums and minimums are given only for parameters measured daily or more frequently. None are given for parameters measured weekly or less frequently, because the true maximums or minimums may not have been sampled. Extremes, when given, are provided for both the period of record and for the current water year.

REVISIONS.--If errors in published water-quality records are discovered after publication, appropriate updates are made to the Water-Quality File in the U.S. Geological Survey's computerized data system, WATSTORE, and subsequently by monthly transfer of update transactions to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's STORET system. Because the usual volume of updates makes it impractical to document individual changes in the State data-report series or elsewhere, potential users of U.S. Geological Survey water-quality data are encouraged to obtain all required data from the appropriate computer file to insure the most recent updates.

The surface-water-quality records for partial-record stations and miscellaneous sampling sites are published in separate tables following the table of discharge measurements at miscellaneous sites. No descriptive statements are given for these records. Each station is published with its own station number and name in the regular downstream-order sequence.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998

Remark Codes

The following remark codes may appear with the water-quality data in this report:

<u>PRINTED OUTPUT</u>	<u>REMARK</u>
E	Estimated value
>	Actual value is known to be greater than the value shown
<	Actual value is known to be less than the value shown
K	Results based on colony count outside the acceptance range (non-ideal colony count)
L	Biological organism count less than 0.5 percent (organism may be observed rather than counted)
D	Biological organism count equal to or greater than 15 percent (dominant)
&	Biological organism estimated as dominant

Records of Ground-Water Levels

Only ground-water level data from a basic network of observation wells are published herein. This basic network contains observation wells so located that the most significant data are obtained from the fewest wells in the most important aquifers.

Data Collection and Computation

Measurements of water levels are made in many types of wells under varying conditions, but the methods of measurement are standardized to the extent possible. The equipment and measuring techniques used at each observation well ensure that measurements at each well are of consistent accuracy and reliability.

Each well is identified by means of (1) a 15-digit number that is based on latitude and longitude and (2) a local number that is provided for local needs. See figure 9.

Water-level records are obtained from direct measurements with a steel tape or from the graph or punched tape of a water-stage recorder. The water-level measurements in this report are given in feet with reference to land-surface datum (l_{sd}). Land-surface datum is a datum plane that is approximately at land surface at each well. If known, the elevation of the land-surface datum is given in the well description. The height of the measuring point (MP) above or below land-surface datum is given in each well description. Water levels in wells equipped with recording gages are reported for every day and as an instantaneous observation at noon.

Water levels are reported to as many significant figures as can be justified by the local conditions. For example, in a measurement of a depth to water of several hundred feet, the error of determining the absolute value of the total depth to water may be a few tenths of a foot, whereas the error in determining the net change of water level between successive measurements may be only a hundredth of a few hundredths of a foot. For lesser depths to water, the accuracy is greater. Accordingly, most measurements reported to a hundredth of a foot, but some are given to a tenth of a foot or a larger unit.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998**Data Presentation**

Each well record consists of three parts, the station description, the data table of water levels observed during the water year and a graph of the water levels for the current water year and other selected period. The description of the well is presented first through use of descriptive headings preceding the tabular data. The comments to follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the well description.

LOCATION.--This paragraph follows the well-identification number and reports the latitude and longitude (given in degrees, minutes, and seconds); a landline location designation; the hydrologic-unit number; the distance and direction from a geographic point of reference; and the owner's name.

AQUIFER.--This entry designates by name (if a name exists) and geologic age the aquifer(s) open to the well.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--This entry describes the well in terms of depth, diameter, casing depth and/or screened interval, method of construction, use, and additional information such as casing breaks, collapsed screen, and other changes since construction.

INSTRUMENTATION.--This paragraph provides information on both the frequency of measurement and the collection method used, allowing the user to better evaluate the reported water-level extremes by knowing whether they are based on weekly, monthly, or some other frequency of measurement.

DATUM.--This entry describes both the measuring point and the land-surface elevation at the well. The measuring point is described physically (such as top of collar, notch in top of casing, plug in pump base and so on), and in relation to land surface (such as 1.3 ft above land-surface datum). The elevation of the land-surface datum is described in feet above (or below) sea level; it is reported with a precision depending on the method of determination.

REMARKS.--This entry describes factors that may influence the water level in a well or the measurement of the water level. It should identify wells that also are water-quality observation wells, and may be used to acknowledge the assistance of local (non-Survey) observers.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This entry indicates the period for which there are published records for the well. It reports the month and year of the start of publication of water-level records by the U.S. Geological Survey and the words "to current year" if the records are to be continued into the following year. Periods for which water-level records are available, but are not published by the Geological Survey, may be noted.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--This entry contains the highest and lowest water levels of the period of published record, with respect to land-surface datum, and the dates of their occurrence.

A table of water levels follows the station description for each well. Water levels are reported in feet below land-surface datum and all taped measurements of water level are listed. For wells equipped with recorders, daily values tables are published for the instantaneous water-level observation at noon. The highest and lowest water levels of the water year and their dates of occurrence are shown on a line below the table. Because all values are not published for wells with recorders, the extremes may be values that are not listed in the table. Missing records are indicated by dashes in place of the water level. A hydrograph for a selected period of record follows each water-level table.

Records of Ground-Water Quality

Records of ground-water quality in this type of report differ from other types of records in that for most sampling sites they consist of only one set of measurements for the water year. The quality of ground water ordinarily changes only slowly; therefore, for most general purposes one annual sampling, or only a few samples taken at infrequent intervals during the year, is sufficient. Frequent measurement of the same constituents is not necessary unless one is concerned with a particular problem, such as monitoring for trends in nitrate concentration. In the special cases where the quality of ground water may change more rapidly, more frequent measurements are made to identify the nature of the changes.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998

Data Collection and Computation

The records of ground-water quality in this report were obtained mostly as a part of special studies in specific areas. Consequently, a number of chemical analyses are presented for some counties but none are presented for others. As a result, the records for this year, by themselves, do not provide a balanced view of ground-water quality Statewide. Such a view can be attained only by considering records for this year in context with similar records obtained for these and other counties in earlier years.

Most methods for collecting and analyzing water samples are described in the "U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations" manuals listed on a following page. The values reported in this type of report represent water-quality conditions at the time of sampling as much as possible, consistent with available sampling techniques and methods of analysis. All samples are obtained by trained personnel. The wells sampled are pumped long enough to assure that the water collected comes directly from the aquifer and has not stood for a long time in the well casing where it would have been exposed to the atmosphere and to the material, possibly metal, comprising the casings.

Data Presentation

The records of ground-water quality, when available, are published in a section titled QUALITY OF GROUND WATER immediately following the ground-water level records. Data for quality of ground water are listed alphabetically by County, and are identified by well number. The prime identification number for wells sampled is the 15-digit number derived from the latitude-longitude locations. No descriptive statements are given for ground-water-quality records; however, the well number, depth of well, date of sampling, and other pertinent data are given in the table containing the chemical analyses of the ground water. The REMARK codes listed for surface-water-quality records are also applicable to ground-water-quality records.

ACCESS TO U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY WATER DATA

The U.S. Geological Survey provides near real-time stage and discharge data for many of the gaging stations equipped with the necessary telemetry and historic daily-mean and peak-flow discharge data for most current or discontinued gaging stations through the world wide web (WWW). These data may be accessed at

<http://water.usgs.gov>

Some water-quality and ground-water data also are available through the WWW. In addition, data can be provided in various machine-readable formats on magnetic tape or 3-1/2 inch floppy disk. Information about the availability of specific types of data or products, and user charges, can be obtained locally from each of the Water Resources Division District Offices (see address on the back of the title page).

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1998**DEFINITION OF TERMS**

Terms related to streamflow, water-quality, and other hydrologic data as used in this report, are defined below. See also the table for converting inch- pound units to the International System of units (SI) on the inside of the back cover.

Acre-foot (AC-FT, acre-ft) is the quantity of water required to cover 1 acre to a depth of 1 foot and is equal to about 326,000 gallons or 1,233 cubic meters.

Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) is an organic, phosphate-rich, compound important in the transfer of energy in organisms. Its central role in living cells makes it an excellent indicator of the presence of living material in water. A measure of ATP therefore provides a sensitive and rapid estimate of biomass. ATP is reported in micrograms per liter of the original water sample.

Algae growth potential (AGP) is the maximum algal dry weight biomass that can be produced in a natural water sample under standardized laboratory conditions. The growth potential is the algal biomass present a stationary phase and is expressed as milligrams dry weight of algae produced per liter of sample.

Aquifer is a geologic formation, group of formations, or part of a formation that contains sufficient saturated permeable material to yield significant quantities of water to wells and springs.

Artesian means confined and is used to describe a well in which the water level stands above the top of the aquifer, tapped by the well. A flowing artesian well is one in which the water level is above the land surface.

Bacteria are microscopic unicellular organisms, typically spherical, rodlike, or spiral and threadlike in shape, often clumped into colonies. Some bacteria cause disease, while others perform an essential role in nature in the recycling of materials; for example, by decomposing organic matter into a form available for reuse by plants.

Total coliform bacteria are a particular group of bacteria that are used as indicators of possible sewage pollution. They are characterized as aerobic or facultative anaerobic, gram-negative, nonspore-forming, rod-shaped bacteria which ferment lactose with gas formation within 48 hours at 35°C. In the laboratory these bacteria are defined as all the organisms which produce colonies with a golden-green metallic sheen within 24 hours when incubated at 35°C \pm 1.0°C on M-Endo medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

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Fecal coliform bacteria are bacteria that are present in the intestines or feces of warm-blooded animals. They are often used as indicators of the sanitary quality of the water. In the laboratory they are defined as all organisms which produce blue colonies within 24 hours when incubated at $44.5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ on M-FC medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

Fecal streptococcal bacteria are bacteria found also in intestines of warm-blooded animals. Their presence in water is considered to verify fecal pollution. They are characterized as Gram-positive, cocci bacteria which are capable of growth in brain-heart infusion broth. In the laboratory they are defined as all the organisms which produce red or pink colonies within 48 hours at $35^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ on KF-streptococcus medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

Bed material is the unconsolidated material of which a streambed, lake, pond, reservoir, or estuary bottom is composed.

Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is a measure of the quantity of dissolved oxygen, in milligrams per liter, necessary for the decomposition of organic matter by microorganisms, such as bacteria.

Biomass is the amount of living matter present at any given time, expressed as the mass per unit area or volume of habitat.

Ash mass is the mass or amount of residue present after the residue from the dry mass determination has been ashed in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 500°C for 1 hour. The ash mass values of zooplankton and phytoplankton are expressed in grams per cubic meter (g/m^3), and periphyton and benthic organisms in grams per square meter (g/m^2).

Dry mass refers to the mass of residue present after drying in an oven at 105°C for zooplankton and periphyton, until the mass remains unchanged. This mass represents the total organic matter, ash and sediment, in the sample. Dry-mass values are expressed in the same units as ash mass.

Organic mass or volatile mass of the living substance is the difference between the dry mass and the ash mass and represents the actual matter. The organic mass is expressed in the same units as for ash and dry mass.

Wet mass is the mass of living matter plus contained water.

Bottom material: See Bed material.

Cells/volume refers to the number of cells of any organism which is counted by using a microscope and grid or counting cell. Many planktonic organisms are multicelled and are counted according to the number of contained cells per sample, usually milliliters (mL) or liters (L).

Chemical oxygen demand (COD) is a measure of the chemically oxidizable material in the water, and furnishes an approximation of the amount of organic and reducing material present. The determined value may correlate with natural water color or with carbonaceous organic pollution from sewage or industrial wastes.

Chlorophyll refers to the green pigments of plants. Chlorophyll a and b are the two most common green pigments in plants.

Color unit is produced by one milligram per liter of platinum in the form of the chloroplatinate ion. Color is expressed in units of the platinum-cobalt scale.

Contents is the volume of water in a reservoir or lake. Unless otherwise indicated, volume is computed on the basis of a level pool and does not include bank storage.

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Control designates a feature downstream from the gage that determines the stage-discharge relation at the gage. This feature may be a natural constriction of the channel, an artificial structure, or a uniform cross section over a long reach of the channel.

Control structure as used in this report is a structure on a stream or canal that is used to regulate the flow or stage of the stream or to prevent the intrusion of salt water.

Cubic foot per second (ft³/s) is the rate of discharge representing a volume of 1 cubic foot passing a given point during 1 second and is equivalent to 7.48 gallons per second or 448.8 gallons per minute or 0.02832 cubic meters per second.

Cubic foot per second-day (ft³/s/day) is the volume of water represented by a flow of 1 cubic foot per second for 24 hours. It is equivalent to 86,400 cubic feet, approximately 1.9835 acre-feet, about 646,000 gallons, or 2,445 cubic meters.

Cubic feet per second per square mile (CFSM) is the average number of cubic feet of water flowing per second from each square mile of area drained, assuming that the runoff is distributed uniformly in time and area.

Discharge is the volume of water (or more broadly, volume of fluid plus suspended sediment), that passes a given point within a given period of time.

Instantaneous discharge is the discharge at a particular instant of time.

Mean discharge (MEAN) is the arithmetic mean of individual daily mean discharges during a specific period.

Annual 7-day minimum is the lowest mean discharge for 7 consecutive days for a calendar year or a water year. Note that most low-flow frequency analyses of annual 7-day minimum flows use a climatic year (April 1 - March 31). The date shown in the summary statistics table is the initial date of the 7-day period. (This value should not be confused with the 7-day 10-year low-flow statistic.)

Dissolved refers to that material in a representative water sample which passes through a 0.45 um membrane filter. This is a convenient operational definition used by Federal agencies that collect water data. Determinations of "dissolved" constituents are made on subsamples of the filtrate.

Dissolved-solids concentration of water is determined either analytically by the "residue-on-evaporation" method, or mathematically by totaling the concentrations of individual constituents reported in a comprehensive chemical analysis. During the analytical determination of dissolved solids, the bicarbonate (generally a major dissolved component of water) is converted to carbonate. Therefore, in the mathematical calculations of dissolved-solids concentration, the bicarbonate value, in milligrams per liter, is multiplied by 0.492 to reflect the change.

Diversity index is a numerical expression of evenness of distribution of aquatic organisms. The formula for diversity index is:

$$d = \frac{s}{\sum_{i=1}^s \frac{n_i}{n} \log_2 \frac{n_i}{n}}$$

Where n_i is the number of individuals per taxon, n is the total number of individuals, and s is the total number of taxa in the sample of the community. Diversity index values range from zero, when all the organisms in the sample are the same, to some positive number, when some or all of the organisms in the sample are different.

Drainage area of a stream at a specified location is that area, measured in a horizontal plane, enclosed by a topographic divide from which direct surface runoff from precipitation normally drains by gravity into the stream above the specified point. Figures of drainage area given herein include all closed basins, or noncontribution areas, within the area unless otherwise noted.

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Drainage basin is a part of the surface of the earth that is occupied by a drainage system, which consists of a surface stream or a body of impounded surface water together with all tributary surface streams and bodies of impounded surface water.

Gage height (gh) is the water-surface elevation referred to some arbitrary gage datum. Gage height is often used interchangeably with the more general term "stage," although gage height is more appropriate when used with a reading on a gage.

Gaging station is a particular site on a stream, canal, lake, or reservoir where systematic observations of hydrologic data are obtained.

Ground-water station is a well at which observations of ground-water level are made, either continuously by recorder, or periodically by hand. In addition, various chemical or physical parameters may be obtained, usually on a periodic basis.

Hardness of water is a physical-chemical characteristic that is commonly recognized by the increased quantity of soap required to produce lather. It is attributable to the presence of alkaline earths (principally calcium and magnesium) and is expressed as equivalent calcium carbonate (CaCO_3).

Hydrologic Bench-Mark Network is a network in small drainage basins around the country whose purpose is to provide consistent data on the hydrology, including water quality, and related factors in representative undeveloped watersheds nationwide, and to provide analyses on a continuing basis to compare and contrast conditions observed in basins more obviously affected by the activities of man.

Hydrologic unit is a geographic area representing part or all of a surface drainage basin or distinct hydrologic feature as delineated by the Office of Water Data Coordination on the State Hydrologic Unit Maps; each hydrologic unit is identified by an eight-digit number.

Land-surface datum (LSD) is a datum plane that is approximately at land surface at each ground-water observation well.

Measuring point (MP) is an arbitrary permanent reference point from which the distance to the water surface in a well is measured to obtain the water level.

Metamorphic stage refers to the stage of development that an organism exhibits during its transformation from an immature form to an adult form. This developmental process exists for most insects, and the degree of difference from the immature stage to the adult form varies from relatively slight to pronounced, with many intermediates. Examples of metamorphic stages of insects are egg-larva-adult or egg-nymph-adult.

Methylene blue active substances (MBAS) are apparent detergents. The determination depends on the formation of a blue color when methylene blue dye reacts with synthetic anionic detergent compounds.

Micrograms per gram ($\mu\text{g/g}$) is a unit expressing the concentration of a chemical element as the mass (micrograms) of the element per unit mass (gram) of material analyzed.

Micrograms per liter ($\mu\text{G/L}$, $\mu\text{g/L}$) is a unit expressing the concentration of chemical constituents in solution as mass (micrograms) of solute per unit volume (liter) of water. One thousand micrograms per liter is equivalent to one milligram per liter.

Milligrams per liter (MG/L, mg/L) is a unit for expressing the concentration of chemical constituents in solution. Milligrams per liter represent the mass of solute per unit volume (liter) of water. Concentration of suspended sediment also is expressed in mg/L, and is based on the mass of sediment per liter of water-sediment mixture. Conversion of chemical concentrations in Mg/L to milliequivalents per liter can be done by using the factors in table 6.

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Table 6. Factors for conversion of chemical constituents in milligrams per liter to milliequivalents per liter

<u>Ion</u>	<u>Multiply by</u>	<u>Ion</u>	<u>Multiply by</u>
Aluminum (Al+3)*	0.11119	Iodide (I-1)	0.00788
Ammonia as NH ₄ +105544	Iron (Fe+3).....	.05372
Barium (Ba+2)01456	Lead (Pb+2)00965
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ -1).....	.01639	Lithium (Li+1)14411
Bromide (Br-1).....	.01251	Magnesium (Mg+2).....	.08226
Calcium (Ca+2).....	.04990	Manganese (Mn+2)*.....	.03640
Carbonate (CO ₃ -2).....	.03333	Nickel (Ni+2).....	.03406
Chloride (Cl-1).....	.02821	Nitrate (NO ₃ -1).....	.01613
Chromium (Cr+6)*11539	Nitrite (NO ₂ -1)02174
Cobalt (Co+2)*03394	Phosphate (PO ₄ -3).....	.03159
Copper (Cu+2)*03148	Potassium (K+1)02557
Cyanide (CN-1).....	.03844	Sodium (NA+1)04350
Fluoride (F-1).....	.05264	Strontium (Sr+2).....	.02283
Hydrogen (H+1).....	.99209	Sulfate (SO ₄ -2)02082
Hydroxide (OH-1).....	.05880	Zinc (Zn+2)*03060

*Constituent reported in micrograms per liter; multiply by factor and divide results by 1,000.

National Stream Quality Accounting Network (NASQAN) is a nationwide data-collection network designed by the U.S. Geological Survey to meet many of the information needs of government agencies and other groups involved in natural or regional water-quality planning and management. The 500 or so sites in NASQAN are generally located at the downstream ends of hydrologic accounting units designated by the U.S. Geological Survey office of Water Data Coordination in consultation with the Water Resources Council. The objectives of NASQAN are (1) to obtain information on the quality and quantity of water moving within and from the United States through a systematic and uniform process of data collection, summarization, analysis, and reporting such that the data may be used for, (2) description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of data from this and other programs, (3) detection of changes or trends with time in the pattern of occurrence of water-quality characteristics, and (4) providing a nationally consistent data base useful for water-quality assessment and hydrologic research.

National Trends Network (NTN) is a network for sampling atmospheric deposition in the United States. The purpose of the network is to determine the variability, both in location and in time, of the composition of atmospheric deposition, which includes snow, rain, dust particles, aerosols, and gases. The core from which the NTN was built was the already-existing deposition-monitoring network of the National Atmospheric Deposition Program (NADP).

Organism is any living entity.

Organism count/area refers to the number of organisms collected and enumerated in a sample and adjusted to the number per unit area habitat, usually square meters (m²), acres, or hectare. Periphyton, benthic organisms, and macrophytes are expressed in these terms.

Organism count/volume refers to the number of organisms collected and enumerated in a sample and adjusted to the number per sample volume, usually milliliters (mL) or liters (L). Numbers of planktonic organisms can be expressed in these terms.

Total organism count is the total number of organisms collected and enumerated in any particular sample.

Parameter Code is a 5-digit number used in the U.S. Geological Survey computerized data system, WATSTORE, to uniquely identify a specific constituent. The codes used in WATSTORE are the same as those used in the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency data system, STORET. The Environmental Protection Agency assigns and approves all requests for new codes.

Partial-record station is a particular site where limited streamflow and/or water-quality data are collected systematically over a period of years for use in hydrologic analyses.

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Particle-size is the diameter, in millimeters (mm), of a particle determined by either sieve or sedimentation methods. Sedimentation methods (pipet, bottom-withdrawal tube, visual-accumulation tube) determine fall diameter of particles in either distilled water (chemically dispersed) or in native water (the river water at the time and point of sampling).

Particle-size classification used in this report agrees with recommendations made by the American Geophysical Union Subcommittee on Sediment Terminology. The classification is as follows:

<u>Classification</u>	<u>Size (mm)</u>	<u>Method of analysis</u>
Clay.....	0.00024 - 0.004	Sedimentation
Silt004 - .062	Sedimentation
Sand.....	.062 - 2.0	Sedimentation or sieve
Gravel....	2.0 - 64.0	Sieve

The particle-size distributions given in this report are not necessarily representative of all particles in transport in the stream. Most of the organic matter is removed and the sample is subjected to mechanical and chemical dispersion before analysis in distilled water. Chemical dispersion is not used for native water analysis.

Percent composition is a unit for expressing the ratio of a particular part of a sample or population to the total sample or population, in terms of types, numbers, mass or volume.

Periphyton is the assemblage of microorganisms attached to and living upon submerged solid surfaces. While primarily consisting of algae, they also include bacteria, fungi, protozoa, rotifers, and other small organisms.

Pesticides are chemical compounds used to control undesirable organisms. Major categories of pesticides include insecticides, miticides, fungicides, herbicides, and rodenticides.

Picocurie (PC, pCi) is one trillionth (1×10^{-12}) of the amount of radioactivity represented by a curie (Ci). A curie is the amount of radioactivity that yields 3.7×10^{10} radioactive disintegrations per second. A picocurie yields 2.22 disintegrations per minute (dpm).

Plankton is the community of suspended, floating, or weakly swimming organisms that live in the open water of lakes and rivers.

Phytoplankton is the plant part of the plankton. They are usually microscopic and their movement is subject to the water currents. Phytoplankton growth is dependent upon solar radiation and nutrient substances. Because they are able to incorporate as well as release materials to the surrounding water, the phytoplankton have a profound effect upon the quality of the water. They are the primary food producers in the aquatic environment, and are commonly known as algae.

Blue-green algae are a group of phytoplankton organisms having a blue pigment, in addition to the green pigment called chlorophyll. Blue-green algae often cause nuisance conditions in water.

Diatoms are the unicellular or colonial algae having a siliceous shell. Their concentrations are expressed as number of cells per milliliter (cells/mL) of sample.

Green algae have chlorophyll pigments similar in color to those of higher green plants. Some forms produce algae mats or floating "moss" in lakes. Their concentrations are expressed as number of cells per milliliter (cells/mL) of sample.

Zooplankton is the animal part of the plankton. Zooplankton are capable of extensive movements within the water column and are often large enough to be seen with the unaided eye. Zooplankton are secondary consumers feeding upon bacteria, phytoplankton, and detritus. Because they are the grazers in the aquatic environment, the zooplankton are a vital part of the aquatic food web. The zooplankton community is dominated by small crustaceans and rotifers.

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Primary productivity is a measure of the rate at which new organic matter is formed and accumulated through photosynthetic and chemosynthetic activity of producer organisms (chiefly, green plants). The rate of primary production is estimated by measuring the amount of oxygen released (oxygen method) or the amount of carbon assimilated by the plants (carbon method).

Milligrams of carbon per area or volume per unit time [mg C/(m².time)] for periphyton and macrophytes and [mg C/(m³.time)] for phytoplankton are units for expressing primary productivity. They define the amount of carbon dioxide consumed as measured by radioactive carbon (carbon 14). The carbon 14 method is of greater sensitivity than the oxygen light and dark bottle method, and is preferred for use in unenriched waters. Unit time may be either hour or day, depending on the incubation period.

Milligrams of oxygen per area or volume per unit time [mgO / (m².time)] for periphyton and macrophytes and [mgO / (m³.time)] for phytoplankton are the units for expressing primary productivity. They define production and respiration rates as estimated from changes in the measured dissolved-oxygen concentration. The oxygen light and dark bottle method is preferred if the rate of primary production is sufficient for accurate measurements to be made within 24 hours. Unit time may be either the hour or day, depending on the incubation period.

Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) are industrial chemicals that are mixtures of chlorinated biphenyl compounds having various percentages of chlorine. They are similar in structure to organochlorine insecticides.

Radiochemical program is a network of regularly sampled water-quality stations where samples are collected to be analyzed for radioisotopes. The streams that are sampled represent major drainage basins in the conterminous United States.

Recoverable from bottom material is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after a representative sample of bottom material has been digested by a method (usually using an acid or mixture of acids) that results in dissolution of readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all bottom material is not achieved by the digestion treatment and thus the determination represents less than the total amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent in the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures would be required of all laboratories performing such analyses because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Return period is the average time interval between occurrences of a hydrological event of a given or greater magnitude, usually expressed in years. May also be called recurrence interval.

Runoff in inches (IN, in) shows the depth to which the drainage area would be covered if all the runoff for a given time period were uniformly distributed on it.

Sediment is solid material that originates mostly from disintegrated rocks and is transported by, suspended in, or deposited from water; it includes chemical and biochemical precipitates and decomposed organic material, such as humus. The quantity, characteristics, and cause of the occurrence of sediment in streams are influenced by environmental factors. Some major factors are degree of slope, length of slope, soil characteristics, land usage, and quantity and intensity of precipitation.

Bed load is the sediment that is transported in a stream by rolling, sliding, or skipping along the bed and very close to it. In this report, bed load is considered to consist of particles in transit within 0.25 ft of the streambed.

Bed load discharge (tons per day) is the quantity of bed load measured by dry weight that moves past a section as bed load in a given time.

Suspended sediment is the sediment that at any given time is maintained in suspension by the upward components of turbulent currents or that exists in suspension as a colloid.

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Suspended-sediment concentration is the velocity-weighted concentration of suspended sediment in the sampled zone (from the water surface to a point approximately 0.3 ft above the bed) expressed as milligrams of dry sediment per liter of water-sediment mixture (mg/L).

Mean concentration is the time-weighted concentration of suspended sediment passing a stream section during a 24-hour day.

Suspended-sediment discharge (tons/day) is the rate at which dry mass of sediment passes a section of a stream or is the quantity of sediment, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes a section in a given time. It is calculated in units of tons per day as follows: concentrations (mg/L) x discharge (ft³/s) x 0.0027.

Suspended-sediment load is a general term that refers to material in suspension. It is not synonymous with either discharge or concentration.

Total sediment discharge (tons/day) is the sum of the suspended-sediment discharge and the bed-load discharge. It is the total quantity of sediment, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes a section during a given time.

Total-sediment load or total load is a term which refers to the total sediment (bed load plus suspended-sediment load) that is in transport. It is not synonymous with total-sediment discharge.

7-day 10-year low flow (7Q10) is the discharge at the 10-year recurrence interval taken from a frequency curve of annual values of the lowest mean discharge for 7 consecutive days (the 7-day low flow).

Sodium-adsorption-ratio (SAR) is the expression of relative activity of sodium ions in exchange reactions within soil and is an index of sodium or alkali hazard to the soil. Waters range in respect to sodium hazard from those which can be used for irrigation on almost all soils to those which are generally unsatisfactory for irrigation.

Solute is any substance that is dissolved in water.

Specific conductance is a measure of the ability of a water to conduct an electric current. It is expressed in microsiemens per centimeter at 25°C. Specific conductance is related to the type and concentration of ions in solution and can be used for approximating the dissolved-solids content of the water. Commonly, the concentration of dissolved solids (in milligrams per liter) is about 65 percent of the specific conductance (in micromhos). This relation is not constant from stream to stream, and it may vary in the same source with changes in the composition of the water.

Stage-discharge relation is the relation between gage height (stage) and volume of water per unit of time, flowing in a channel.

Streamflow is the discharge that occurs in a natural channel. Although the term "discharge" can be applied to the flow of a canal, the word "streamflow" uniquely describes the discharge in a surface stream course. The term "streamflow" is more general than "runoff" as streamflow may be applied to discharge whether or not it is affected by diversion or regulation.

Substrate is the physical surface upon which an organism lives.

Natural substrate refers to any naturally occurring emersed or submersed solid surface, such as a rock or tree, upon which an organism lives.

Artificial substrate is a device which is purposely placed in a stream or lake for colonization of organisms. The artificial substrate simplifies the community structure by standardizing the substrate from which each sample is taken. Examples of artificial substrates are basket samplers (made of wire cages filled with clean streamside rocks) and multiplate samplers (made of hardboard) for benthic organism collection, and plexiglass strips for periphyton.

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Surface area of a lake is that area outlined on the latest U.S.G.S. topographic map as the boundary of the lake and measured by a planimeter in acres. In localities not covered by topographic maps, the areas are computed from the best maps available at the time planimeted. All areas shown are those for the stage when the planimeted map was made.

Surficial bed material is that part (0.1 to 0.2 ft) of the bed material that is sampled using U.S. Series Bed-Material Samplers.

Suspended (as used in tables of chemical analyses) refers to the amount (concentration) of the total concentration in a water-sediment mixture. It is associated with the material retained on a 0.45-micrometer filter.

Suspended, recoverable is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after the part of a representative water-suspended sediment sample that is retained on a 0.45 um membrane filter has been digested by a method (usually using a dilute acid solution) that results in dissolution of only readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all the particulate matter is not achieved by the digestion treatment and thus the determination represents something less than the "total" amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent present in the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures are required of all laboratories performing such analyses because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Determinations of "suspended, recoverable" constituents are made either by analyzing portions of the material collected on the filter or, more commonly, by difference, based on determinations of (1) dissolved and (2) total recoverable concentrations of the constituent.

Suspended, total is the total amount of a given constituent in the part of representative water-suspended sediment sample that is retained on a 0.45 um membrane filter. This term is used only when the analytical procedure assures measurement of at least 95 percent of the constituent determined. A knowledge of the expected form of the constituent in the sample, as well as the analytical methodology used, is required to determine when the results should be reported as "suspended, total."

Determinations of "suspended, total" constituents are made either by analyzing portions of the material collected on the filter or, more commonly, by difference, based on determinations of (1) dissolved and (2) total concentrations of the constituent.

Taxonomy is the division of biology concerned with the classification and naming of organisms. The classification of organisms is based upon a hierarchial scheme beginning with Kingdom and ending with Species at the base. The higher the classification level, the fewer features the organisms have in common. For example, the taxonomy of a particular mayfly, Hexagenia limbata, is the following:

Kingdom.....Animal
Phylum.....Arthropoda
Class.....Insecta
Order.....Ephemeroptera
Family.....Ephemeridae
Genus.....Hexagenia
Species.....Hexagenia limbata

Thermograph is an instrument that continuously records variations of temperature on a chart. The more general term "temperature recorder" is used in the table heading and refers to any instrument that records temperature whether on a chart, a tape, or any other medium.

Time-weighted average is computed by multiplying the number of days in the sampling period by the concentrations of individual constituents for the corresponding period and dividing the sum of the products by the total number of days. A time-weighted average represents the composition of water that would be contained in a vessel or reservoir that had received equal quantities of water from the stream each day for the year.

Tons per acre-foot indicates the dry mass of dissolved solids in 1 acre-foot of water. It is computed by multiplying the concentration of the constituent, in milligrams per liter by 0.00136.

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Tons per day (T/DAY) is the quantity of a substance in solution or suspension that passes a stream section during a 24-hour period.

Total is the total amount of a given constituent in a representative water-suspended sediment sample, regardless of the constituent's physical or chemical form. This term is used only when the analytical procedure assures measurement of at least 95 percent of the constituent present in both the dissolved and suspended phases of the sample. A knowledge of the expected form of the constituent in the sample, as well as the analytical methodology used, is required to judge when the results should be reported as "total." (Note that the word "total" does double duty here, indicating both that the sample consists of a water-suspended sediment mixture and that the analytical method determined all of the constituent in the sample.)

Total discharge is the total quantity of any individual constituent, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes through a stream cross-section per unit of time. This term needs to be qualified, such as "total sediment discharge," "total chloride discharge," and so on.

Total, recoverable is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after a representative water-suspended sediment sample has been digested by a method (usually using a dilute acid solution) that results in dissolution of only readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all particulate matter is not achieved by the digestion treatment, and thus the determination represents something less than the "total" amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent present in the dissolved and suspended phases of the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures are required of all laboratories performing such analyses, because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Tritium Network is a network of stations which has been established to provide baseline information on the occurrence of tritium in the Nation's surface waters. In addition to the surface-water stations in the network, tritium data are also obtained at a number of precipitation stations. The purpose of the precipitation stations is to provide an estimate sufficient for hydrologic studies of the tritium input to the United States.

Water year in U.S. Geological Survey reports dealing with surface water supply is the 12-month period, October 1 through September 30. The water year is designated by the calendar year in which it ends and which includes 9 of the 12 months. Thus, the year ending September 30, 1980, is called the "1980 water year."

WDR is used as an abbreviation for "Water-Data Report" in the REVISED RECORDS paragraph to refer to State annual hydrologic-data reports (WRD was used as an abbreviation for "Water-Resources Data" in reports published prior to 1976).

Weighted average is used in this report to indicate discharge-weighted average. It is computed by multiplying the discharge for a sampling period by the concentrations of individual constituents for the corresponding period and dividing the sum of the products by the sum of the discharges. A discharge-weighted average approximates the composition of water that would be found in a reservoir containing all the water passing a given location during the water year after thorough mixing in the reservoir.

WSP is used as an abbreviation for "Water-Supply Paper" in references to previously published reports.

PUBLICATIONS ON TECHNIQUES OF WATER-RESOURCES INVESTIGATIONS

The U.S. Geological Survey publishes a series of manuals describing procedures for planning and conducting specialized work in water-resources investigations. The material is grouped under major subject headings called books and is further divided into sections and chapters. For example, Section A of Book 3 (Applications of Hydraulics) pertains to surface water. The chapter, the unit of publication, is limited to a narrow field of subject matter. This format permits flexibility in revision and publication as the need arises.

The reports listed below are for sale by the U.S. Geological Survey, Branch of Information Services, Box 25286, Federal Center, Denver, Colorado 80225 (authorized agent of the Superintendent of Documents, Government Printing Office). Prepayment is required. Remittance should be sent by check or money order payable to the U.S. Geological Survey. Prices are not included because they are subject to change. Current prices can be obtained by writing to the above address. When ordering or inquiring about prices for any of these publications, please give the title, book number, chapter number, and "U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations."

Book 1. Collection of Water Data by Direct Measurement

Section D. Water Quality

- 1-D1. *Water temperature—influential factors, field measurement, and data presentation*, by H. H. Stevens, Jr., J.F. Ficke, and G. F. Smoot: USGS–TWRI Book 1, Chapter D1. 1975. 65 pages.
- 1-D2. *Guidelines for collection and field analysis of ground-water samples for selected unstable constituents*, by W.W. Wood: USGS–TWRI Book 1, Chapter D2. 1976. 24 pages.

Book 2. Collection of Environmental Data

Section D. Surface Geophysical Methods

- 2-D1. *Application of surface geophysics to ground-water investigations*, by A.A. R. Zohdy, G.P. Eaton, and D.R. Mabey: USGS–TWRI Book 2, Chapter D1. 1974. 116 pages.
- 2-D2. *Application of seismic-refraction techniques to hydrologic studies*, by F.P. Haeni: USGS–TWRI Book 2, Chapter D2. 1988. 86 pages.

Section E. Subsurface Geophysical Methods

- 2-E1. *Application of borehole geophysics to water-resources investigations*, by W.S. Keys and L.M. MacCary: USGS–TWRI Book 2, Chapter E1. 1971. 126 pages.
- 2-E2. *Borehole geophysics applied to ground-water investigations*, by W.S. Keys: USGS–TWRI Book 2, Chapter E2. 1990. 150 pages.

Section F. Drilling and Sampling Methods

- 2-F1. *Application of drilling, coring, and sampling techniques to test holes and wells*, by Eugene Shuter and W.E. Teasdale: USGS–TWRI Book 2, Chapter F1. 1989. 97 pages.

Book 3. Applications of Hydraulics

Section A. Surface-Water Techniques

- 3-A1. *General field and office procedures for indirect discharge measurements*, by M.A. Benson and Tate Dalrymple: USGS–TWRI Book 3, Chapter A1. 1967. 30 pages.
- 3-A2. *Measurement of peak discharge by the slope-area method*, by Tate Dalrymple and M.A. Benson: USGS–TWRI Book 3, Chapter A2. 1967. 12 pages.
- 3-A3. *Measurement of peak discharge at culverts by indirect methods*, by G.L. Bodhaine: USGS–TWRI Book 3, Chapter A3. 1968. 60 pages.
- 3-A4. *Measurement of peak discharge at width contractions by indirect methods*, by H.F. Matthai: USGS–TWRI Book 3, Chapter A4. 1967. 44 pages.
- 3-A5. *Measurement of peak discharge at dams by indirect methods*, by Harry Hulsing: USGS–TWRI Book 3. Chapter A5. 1967. 29 pages.
- 3-A6. *General procedure for gaging streams*, by R.W. Carter and Jacob Davidian: USGS–TWRI Book 3, Chapter A6. 1968. 13 pages.
- 3-A7. *Stage measurement at gaging stations*, by T.J. Buchanan and W.P. Somers: USGS–TWRI Book 3, Chapter A7. 1968. 28 pages.
- 3-A8. *Discharge measurements at gaging stations*, by T.J. Buchanan and W.P. Somers: USGS–TWRI Book 3, Chapter A8. 1969. 65 pages.
- 3-A9. *Measurement of time of travel in streams by dye tracing*, by F.A. Kilpatrick and J.F. Wilson, Jr.: USGS–TWRI Book 3, Chapter A9. 1989. 27 pages.

PUBLICATIONS ON TECHNIQUES OF WATER-RESOURCES INVESTIGATIONS--Continued

- 3-A10. *Discharge ratings at gaging stations*, by E.J. Kennedy: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A10. 1984. 59 pages.
- 3-A11. *Measurement of discharge by the moving-boat method*, by G.F. Smoot and C.E. Novak: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A11. 1969. 22 pages.
- 3-A12. *Fluorometric procedures for dye tracing*, Revised, by J.F. Wilson, Jr., E.D. Cobb, and F.A. Kilpatrick: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A12. 1986. 34 pages.
- 3-A13. *Computation of continuous records of streamflow*, by E.J. Kennedy: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A13. 1983. 53 pages.
- 3-A14. *Use of flumes in measuring discharge*, by F.A. Kilpatrick and V.R. Schneider: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A14. 1983. 46 pages.
- 3-A15. *Computation of water-surface profiles in open channels*, by Jacob Davidian: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A15. 1984. 48 pages.
- 3-A16. *Measurement of discharge using tracers*, by F.A. Kilpatrick and E.D. Cobb: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A16. 1985. 52 pages.
- 3-A17. *Acoustic velocity meter systems*, by Antonius Laenen: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A17. 1985. 38 pages.
- 3-A18. *Determination of stream reaeration coefficients by use of tracers*, by F.A. Kilpatrick, R.E. Rathbun, Nobuhiro Yotsukura, G.W. Parker, and L.L. DeLong: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A18. 1989. 52 pages.
- 3-A19. *Levels at streamflow gaging stations*, by E.J. Kennedy: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A19. 1990. 31 pages.
- 3-A20. *Simulation of soluble waste transport and buildup in surface waters using tracers*, by F.A. Kilpatrick: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A20. 1993. 38 pages.
- 3-A21. *Stream-gaging cableways*, by C. Russell Wagner: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter A21. 1995. 56 pages.

Section B. Ground-Water Techniques

- 3-B1. *Aquifer-test design, observation, and data analysis*, by R.W. Stallman: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter B1. 1971. 26 pages.
- 3-B2. *Introduction to ground-water hydraulics, a programmed text for self-instruction*, by G.D. Bennett: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter B2. 1976. 172 pages.
- 3-B3. *Type curves for selected problems of flow to wells in confined aquifers*, by J.E. Reed: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter B3. 1980. 106 pages.
- 3-B4. *Regression modeling of ground-water flow*, by R.L. Cooley and R.L. Naff: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter B4. 1990. 232 pages.
- 3-B4. *Supplement 1. Regression modeling of ground-water flow --Modifications to the computer code for nonlinear regression solution of steady-state ground-water flow problems*, by R.L. Cooley: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter B4. 1993. 8 pages.
- 3-B5. *Definition of boundary and initial conditions in the analysis of saturated ground-water flow systems—An introduction*, by O.L. Franke, T.E. Reilly, and G.D. Bennett: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter B5. 1987. 15 pages.
- 3-B6. *The principle of superposition and its application in ground-water hydraulics*, by T.E. Reilly, O.L. Franke, and G.D. Bennett: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter B6. 1987. 28 pages.
- 3-B7. *Analytical solutions for one-, two-, and three-dimensional solute transport in ground-water systems with uniform flow*, by E.J. Wexler: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter B7. 1992. 190 pages.

Section C. Sedimentation and Erosion Techniques

- 3-C1. *Fluvial sediment concepts*, by H.P. Guy: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter C1. 1970. 55 pages.
- 3-C2. *Field methods for measurement of fluvial sediment*, by H.P. Guy and V.W. Norman: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter C2. 1970. 59 pages.
- 3-C3. *Computation of fluvial-sediment discharge*, by George Porterfield: USGS-TWRI Book 3, Chapter C3. 1972. 66 pages.

Book 4. Hydrologic Analysis and Interpretation

Section A. Statistical Analysis

- 4-A1. *Some statistical tools in hydrology*, by H.C. Riggs: USGS-TWRI Book 4, Chapter A1. 1968. 39 pages.
- 4-A2. *Frequency curves*, by H.C. Riggs: USGS-TWRI Book 4, Chapter A2. 1968. 15 pages.

Section B. Surface Water

- 4-B1. *Low-flow investigations*, by H.C. Riggs: USGS-TWRI Book 4, Chapter B1. 1972. 18 pages.
- 4-B2. *Storage analyses for water supply*, by H.C. Riggs and C.H. Hardison: USGS-TWRI Book 4, Chapter B2. 1973. 20 pages.
- 4-B3. *Regional analyses of streamflow characteristics*, by H.C. Riggs: USGS-TWRI Book 4, Chapter B3. 1973. 15 pages.

PUBLICATIONS ON TECHNIQUES OF WATER-RESOURCES INVESTIGATIONS--Continued

Section D. Interrelated Phases of the Hydrologic Cycle

- 4-D1. *Computation of rate and volume of stream depletion by wells*, by C.T. Jenkins: USGS-TWRI Book 4, Chapter D1. 1970. 17 pages.

Book 5. Laboratory Analysis**Section A. Water Analysis**

- 5-A1. *Methods for determination of inorganic substances in water and fluvial sediments*, by M.J. Fishman and L.C. Friedman, editors: USGS-TWRI Book 5, Chapter A1. 1989. 545 pages.
- 5-A2. *Determination of minor elements in water by emission spectroscopy*, by P.R. Barnett and E.C. Mallory, Jr.: USGS-TWRI Book 5, Chapter A2. 1971. 31 pages.
- 5-A3. *Methods for the determination of organic substances in water and fluvial sediments*, edited by R.L. Wershaw, M.J. Fishman, R.R. Grabbe, and L.E. Lowe: USGS-TWRI Book 5, Chapter A3. 1987. 80 pages.
- 5-A4. *Methods for collection and analysis of aquatic biological and microbiological samples*, by L.J. Britton and P.E. Greeson, editors: USGS-TWRI Book 5, Chapter A4. 1989. 363 pages.
- 5-A5. *Methods for determination of radioactive substances in water and fluvial sediments*, by L.L. Thatcher, V.J. Janzer, and K.W. Edwards: USGS-TWRI Book 5, Chapter A5. 1977. 95 pages.
- 5-A6. *Quality assurance practices for the chemical and biological analyses of water and fluvial sediments*, by L.C. Friedman and D.E. Erdmann: USGS-TWRI Book 5, Chapter A6. 1982. 181 pages.

Section C. Sediment Analysis

- 5-C1. *Laboratory theory and methods for sediment analysis*, by H.P. Guy: USGS-TWRI Book 5, Chapter C1. 1969. 58 pages.

Book 6. Modeling Techniques**Section A. Ground Water**

- 6-A1. *A modular three-dimensional finite-difference ground-water flow model*, by M.G. McDonald and A.W. Harbaugh: USGS-TWRI Book 6, Chapter A1. 1988. 586 pages.
- 6-A2. *Documentation of a computer program to simulate aquifer-system compaction using the modular finite-difference ground-water flow model*, by S.A. Leake and D.E. Prudic: USGS-TWRI Book 6, Chapter A2. 1991. 68 pages.
- 6-A3. *A modular finite-element model (MODFE) for areal and axisymmetric ground-water-flow problems, Part 1: Model Description and User's Manual*, by L.J. Torak: USGS-TWRI Book 6, Chapter A3. 1993. 136 pages.
- 6-A4. *A modular finite-element model (MODFE) for areal and axisymmetric ground-water-flow problems, Part 2: Derivation of finite-element equations and comparisons with analytical solutions*, by R.L. Cooley: USGS-TWRI Book 6, Chapter A4. 1992. 108 pages.
- 6-A5. *A modular finite-element model (MODFE) for areal and axisymmetric ground-water-flow problems, Part 3: Design philosophy and programming details*, by L.J. Torak: USGS-TWRI Book 6, Chapter A5, 1993. 243 pages.
- 6-A6. *A coupled surface-water and ground-water flow model (MODBRANCH) for simulation of stream-aquifer interaction*, by Eric D. Swain and Eliezer J. Wexler. 1996. 125 pages.

Book 7. Automated Data Processing and Computations**Section C. Computer Programs**

- 7-C1. *Finite difference model for aquifer simulation in two dimensions with results of numerical experiments*, by P.C. Trescott, G.F. Pinder, and S.P. Larson: USGS-TWRI Book 7, Chapter C1. 1976. 116 pages.
- 7-C2. *Computer model of two-dimensional solute transport and dispersion in ground water*, by L.F. Konikow and J.D. Bredehoeft: USGS-TWRI Book 7, Chapter C2. 1978. 90 pages.
- 7-C3. *A model for simulation of flow in singular and interconnected channels*, by R.W. Schaffranek, R.A. Baltzer, and D.E. Goldberg: USGS-TWRI Book 7, Chapter C3. 1981. 110 pages.

Book 8. Instrumentation**Section A. Instruments for Measurement of Water Level**

- 8-A1. *Methods of measuring water levels in deep wells*, by M.S. Garber and F.C. Koopman: USGS-TWRI Book 8, Chapter A1. 1968. 23 pages.
- 8-A2. *Installation and service manual for U.S. Geological Survey manometers*, by J.D. Craig: USGS-TWRI Book 8, Chapter A2. 1983. 57 pages.

PUBLICATIONS ON TECHNIQUES OF WATER-RESOURCES INVESTIGATIONS--Continued

Section B. Instruments for Measurement of Discharge

- 8-B2. *Calibration and maintenance of vertical-axis type current meters*, by G.F. Smoot and C.E. Novak: USGS-TWRI Book 8, Chapter B2. 1968. 15 pages.

Book 9. Handbooks for Water-Resources Investigations**Section A. National Field Manual for the Collection of Water-Quality Data**

- 9-A6. *National Field Manual for the Collection of Water-Quality Data: Field Measurements*, edited by F.D. Wilde and D.B. Radtke: USGS-TWRI Book 9, Chapter A6. 1998. Various pages.
- 9-A7. *National Field Manual for the Collection of Water-Quality Data: Biological Indicators*, by D.N. Myers and F.D. Wilde: USGS-TWRI Book 9, Chapter A7. 1997. 49 pages.
- 9-A8. *National Field Manual for the Collection of Water-Quality Data: Bottom-material samples*, by D.B. Radtke: USGS-TWRI Book 9, Chapter A8. 1998. 48 pages.
- 9-A9. *National Field Manual for the Collection of Water-Quality Data: Safety in Field Activities*, by S.L. Lane and R.G. Fay: USGS-TWRI Book 9, Chapter A9. 1998. 60 pages.

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EXPLANATION

- 0105 ▲ SURFACE-WATER STATION AND NUMBER
- 0105 ▼ QUALITY-OF-WATER STATION AND NUMBER
- 165 ● WELL AND WELL NUMBER
- 0108 △ LAKE-ELEVATION STATION AND NUMBER
- TOWN OR CITY
- CHANNEL FLOW DIRECTION
- - - DRAINAGE BASIN BOUNDARY

PUERTO RICO

Figure 11. Río Guajataca basin.

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010500 RIO GUAJATACA AT LARES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'01", long 66°52'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010001 at bridge on Highway 111, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Anón, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) east of Lares.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.16 mi² (8.18 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to February 1962 (annual low-flow measurements only), January 1963 to April 1969 (monthly measurements only), May 1969 to December 1970 (February to May 1971 and March 1974 to November 1989, monthly measurements only), December 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 935 ft (285 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Small diversion above station for sewage treatment plant; effluent re-enters stream below station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	18	3.4	2.7	2.6	1.8	1.3	1.1	.98	2.8	1.2	1.8	5.9
2	11	2.4	2.3	2.2	1.7	1.2	1.2	.98	2.5	1.3	1.6	71
3	6.0	2.3	1.6	2.3	1.7	1.1	.73	.92	5.7	4.0	1.7	25
4	3.7	2.2	1.6	2.2	4.0	1.0	.61	.69	2.4	2.9	2.4	16
5	3.6	2.0	1.5	2.4	7.4	1.1	.59	.68	20	2.1	2.0	12
6	6.5	2.4	1.3	2.5	2.6	1.1	.55	5.0	4.6	3.5	1.5	32
7	15	1.7	1.3	3.8	2.0	1.7	.77	3.3	1.8	3.3	4.7	20
8	6.5	1.7	1.4	2.6	5.4	1.1	.80	1.7	1.6	5.2	3.0	12
9	3.9	1.7	1.5	2.2	3.0	.91	.75	1.7	2.4	2.2	30	9.6
10	2.9	1.9	1.6	2.2	1.6	.84	.74	1.2	2.6	2.2	11	7.8
11	6.8	1.8	2.1	5.5	1.5	.85	.66	1.1	2.6	2.0	11	7.2
12	49	2.4	1.4	3.5	1.6	.85	.76	.98	2.3	13	3.5	77
13	20	2.6	1.5	2.5	1.6	.80	.66	.97	19	21	2.0	18
14	39	4.9	1.4	2.6	1.8	2.3	.62	.80	7.1	8.8	1.9	11
15	49	3.2	1.4	2.0	1.8	2.3	.57	1.6	4.3	9.8	1.9	8.3
16	27	1.8	1.4	1.8	1.8	1.5	.81	1.1	81	24	2.1	17
17	27	1.4	1.7	6.2	1.7	.92	.74	15	9.7	22	19	15
18	18	1.3	3.0	8.2	1.6	1.1	.73	8.3	19	11	3.8	41
19	12	1.4	2.9	4.9	1.5	.77	8.5	10	7.4	5.4	2.2	13
20	9.2	1.6	3.1	3.0	1.8	.73	4.9	36	3.9	4.3	1.9	8.2
21	6.8	1.2	2.3	2.2	1.6	.68	1.1	26	3.6	3.3	11	43
22	6.1	1.1	4.3	2.0	1.2	.61	1.1	17	2.8	2.3	4.2	505
23	5.3	1.6	5.8	2.1	1.1	.64	.93	9.9	2.2	2.3	2.3	91
24	5.5	1.2	4.2	2.0	1.0	.79	.87	3.7	2.0	2.3	7.2	57
25	4.2	1.2	3.4	2.0	1.1	.80	.82	2.1	1.9	2.0	17	44
26	3.9	2.2	2.8	2.7	1.2	.73	.94	2.6	1.8	1.8	3.6	37
27	4.4	3.6	2.3	1.6	.95	.78	1.0	2.4	3.5	1.8	3.1	32
28	3.7	2.2	2.3	1.6	1.3	.73	.83	2.0	1.9	1.8	50	36
29	3.8	9.8	2.2	2.1	---	.76	.72	2.3	1.4	1.5	12	44
30	3.5	4.4	3.7	2.1	---	2.4	.82	4.4	1.4	1.4	15	39
31	3.1	---	2.7	1.7	---	.81	---	2.9	---	7.6	16	---
TOTAL	384.4	72.6	72.7	87.3	57.35	33.20	35.92	168.30	225.2	177.3	250.4	1355.0
MEAN	12.4	2.42	2.35	2.82	2.05	1.07	1.20	5.43	7.51	5.72	8.08	45.2
MAX	49	9.8	5.8	8.2	7.4	2.4	8.5	36	81	24	50	505
MIN	2.9	1.1	1.3	1.6	.95	.61	.55	.68	1.4	1.2	1.5	5.9
AC-FT	762	144	144	173	114	66	71	334	447	352	497	2690
CFSM	3.92	.77	.74	.89	.65	.34	.38	1.72	2.38	1.81	2.56	14.3
IN.	4.53	.85	.86	1.03	.68	.39	.42	1.98	2.65	2.09	2.95	15.95

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	MEAN	MAX	(WY)	MIN	(WY)
	16.4	33.7	1991	8.52	1995
	8.03	16.7	1971	2.42	1998
	3.69	7.31	1971	1.35	1991
	3.36	8.91	1997	.66	1991
	2.65	7.21	1996	.93	1992
	2.13	6.38	1971	.92	1994
	3.18	7.63	1993	1.09	1994
	8.85	20.2	1995	2.37	1997
	7.26	16.4	1995	1.70	1997
	4.26	9.85	1969	1.73	1997
	6.29	11.1	1996	3.34	1970
	14.9	45.2	1998	5.95	1993

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	1583.27	2919.67	
ANNUAL MEAN	4.34	8.00	6.58
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			9.08
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			4.13
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	88	Sep 24	505
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.50	May 17	.55
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.56	May 13	.68
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			3880
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			19.20
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	3140	5790	4770
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.37	2.53	2.08
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	18.64	34.37	28.31
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.3	18	15
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.1	2.3	3.3
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.95	.84	.96

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN
50010500 RIO GUAJATACA AT LARES, PR--Continued

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010500 RIO GUAJATACA AT LARES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'01", long 66°52'24", at bridge on Highway 111 (km 32.9), 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Anón, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of Lares plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.16 mi² (8.18 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)		
OCT	20...	1310	7.9	227	8.0	24.0	2.2	7.3	90	<10	40000	K1200
FEB	23...	1245	1.6	255	7.7	21.5	1.5	7.5	88	<10	K1500	580
MAY	21...	1155	6.1	229	7.5	23.5	14	7.6	92	<10	3400	7000
AUG	31...	1315	5.7	278	7.4	24.5	6.9	7.5	93	<10	2400	2400

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)	
OCT	20...	87	25	5.7	10	.5	2.5	82	<.5	7.2	12
FEB	23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	97	--	--	--
MAY	21...	84	25	5.1	9.6	.5	4.3	66	--	16	12
AUG	31...	110	35	5.9	11	.5	2.9	110	<1.0	13	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	
OCT	20...	.11	29	141	3.02	2	.570	.190	.760	1.70	.40
FEB	23...	--	--	--	--	3	--	<.010	.830	.030	.22
MAY	21...	<.10	20	132	2.16	20	2.18	.019	2.20	.060	.22
AUG	31...	<.10	25	170	2.60	9	--	<.010	1.50	.030	--

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)	
OCT	20...	2.1	2.9	13	.340	<1	<100	10	<1	<1	<10
FEB	23...	.25	1.1	4.8	.030	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY	21...	.28	2.5	11	.030	<1	<100	<10	<1	<1	<10
AUG	31...	<.20	--	--	.080	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010800 LAGO GUAJATACA AT DAMSITE NEAR QUEBRADILLAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'02", long 66°55'25", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on right bank, in a concrete intake tower at Damsite, 5.2 mi (8.4 km) southeast from Quebradillas plaza, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) northeast from Iglesia San Antonio de Padua and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) from Escuela Segunda Unidad Baldorioty de Castro.

DRAINAGE AREA.--24.6 mi² (63.71 km²)

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1995 to current year.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Guajataca was completed in 1928. The dam is a semihydraulic earthfill structure about 123 ft (37 m) high, a top width of 31 ft (9.5 m) at crest elevation of 664 ft (202.5 m), a base width of 623 ft (190 m), a crest length of 1,036 ft (316 m) and has a maximum storage capacity of 49,200 acre-feet (60.6 hm³). The Guajataca Dam is owned by the Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority (P.R.E.P.A) and provides water for the municipalities of Aguadilla, Isabela, Moca, Aguada and Quebradillas although its primary purpose is for agricultural irrigation for the flatlands of the area. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 648.3 ft (197.60 m), Sept. 23, 1998; minimum elevation, 608.07 ft (185.34 m), May 17, 1998.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 648.3 ft (197.60 m), Sept. 23; minimum elevation, 608.07 ft (185.34 m), May 17.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
593	0	625	15,295
600	2,405	650	36,403

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	614.32	625.22	624.56	620.40	616.57	611.36	611.87	608.92	621.82	629.34	634.67	641.96
2	615.67	625.10	624.44	620.20	616.39	611.20	611.77	608.75	621.83	629.21	634.57	642.71
3	616.31	625.00	624.33	620.02	616.21	611.02	A	608.66	621.85	629.10	634.51	642.55
4	616.30	624.87	624.19	619.84	616.19	610.88	611.52	608.59	621.81	629.00	634.45	642.17
5	616.73	624.72	624.03	619.64	616.14	612.30	611.39	608.46	621.87	628.94	634.48	641.82
6	617.17	624.58	623.89	619.49	615.99	612.71	611.25	608.61	622.15	628.96	634.41	642.59
7	618.88	624.43	623.73	619.30	615.81	613.05	611.11	608.92	622.12	628.84	634.32	642.73
8	619.69	624.28	623.59	619.13	615.73	613.21	610.96	608.89	622.01	628.87	634.22	642.43
9	619.78	624.15	623.46	618.94	615.59	613.16	610.73	608.79	621.88	628.81	634.42	642.11
10	619.76	624.00	623.32	618.79	615.42	613.06	610.57	608.68	621.72	628.74	634.40	641.74
11	619.71	623.95	623.18	618.67	615.20	612.96	610.41	608.54	623.04	629.07	634.97	641.71
12	621.46	623.99	623.02	618.55	615.00	612.83	610.26	608.43	624.77	629.77	636.20	642.16
13	622.28	623.88	622.88	618.39	614.80	612.70	610.10	608.26	626.57	632.58	636.63	643.36
14	623.95	623.75	622.72	618.17	614.60	612.57	609.92	608.18	627.86	633.51	636.65	643.00
15	625.20	623.84	622.57	617.97	614.39	612.46	609.78	608.18	628.46	634.08	636.59	642.42
16	626.16	623.78	622.41	617.76	614.17	612.37	609.76	608.14	629.20	634.80	636.60	641.98
17	626.45	623.64	622.26	617.86	613.97	612.24	609.62	608.53	629.46	635.27	636.57	641.86
18	626.52	623.44	622.13	618.13	613.73	612.10	609.48	608.81	629.78	635.36	636.49	642.28
19	626.51	623.28	621.99	618.33	613.51	611.95	609.65	609.16	629.97	635.36	636.38	642.03
20	626.48	623.12	621.84	618.29	613.29	611.78	609.74	612.97	630.00	635.34	636.27	641.38
21	626.43	622.95	621.69	618.15	613.05	611.66	609.73	614.81	629.99	635.27	636.40	641.26
22	626.36	622.78	621.78	617.99	612.81	611.53	609.63	616.76	629.94	635.19	636.38	647.94
23	626.27	622.61	621.71	617.85	612.58	611.39	609.48	619.88	629.87	635.19	636.29	648.27
24	626.16	622.44	621.59	617.70	612.36	611.27	609.60	620.97	629.78	635.23	636.34	647.97
25	626.06	622.39	621.44	617.58	612.16	611.13	609.75	621.25	629.72	635.16	636.84	647.53
26	625.94	623.44	621.28	617.40	611.92	610.99	609.66	621.65	629.65	635.06	636.95	647.04
27	625.81	624.01	621.12	617.25	611.69	610.87	609.53	621.77	629.71	635.03	636.99	646.51
28	625.69	624.35	620.97	617.20	611.51	610.75	609.40	621.76	629.69	634.93	639.35	645.99
29	625.56	624.47	620.78	617.05	---	611.79	609.24	621.71	629.56	634.86	640.27	645.63
30	625.42	624.62	620.72	616.89	---	611.96	609.08	621.64	629.45	634.76	640.72	645.86
31	625.29	---	620.57	616.74	---	611.95	---	621.58	---	634.72	641.63	---
MAX	626.52	625.22	624.56	620.40	616.57	613.21	---	621.77	630.00	635.36	641.63	648.27
MIN	614.32	622.39	620.57	616.74	611.51	610.75	---	608.14	621.72	628.74	634.22	641.26

A No gage-height record

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011000 CANAL PRINCIPAL DE DIVERSIONES AT LAGO DE GUAJATACA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'02", long 66°55'27", off Highway 476 at Lago Guajataca outlet, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) southwest of Segunda Unidad Baldorioty de Castro, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) south of Quebradillas Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-64, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD) (00400)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TURBIDITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLIFORM, FECA, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 23...	0715	E65	324	8.1	25.5	1.2	1.2	15	<10	200	66
MAR 13...	1400	40	313	8.0	26.0	.65	9.1	115	<10	<10	<10
JUN 02...	1615	65	317	6.8	26.5	.83	2.8	36	<10	K120	K110
AUG 31...	1530	65	327	7.4	25.5	1.1	1.7	21	<10	240	260

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORPTION RATIO (00931)	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 23...	150	54	3.6	5.1	.2	2.0	140	<.5	9.0	7.8
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
JUN 02...	140	49	3.8	6.0	.2	2.4	140	--	11	8.9
AUG 31...	150	53	3.5	5.6	.2	2.1	160	<1.0	8.1	6.9

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 23...	<.10	6.1	171	E30.0	<1	.156	.054	.210	.660	.25
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	3	--	<.010	.040	.040	.52
JUN 02...	.11	6.3	171	30.1	1	.116	.014	.130	.740	.36
AUG 31...	<.10	6.4	181	31.9	3	--	<.010	<.020	.240	.38

DATE	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 23...	.91	1.1	5.0	<.020	20	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
MAR 13...	.56	.60	2.7	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 02...	1.1	1.2	5.4	<.020	2	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
AUG 31...	.62	--	--	.070	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011400 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE MOUTH NEAR QUEBRADILLAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°28'31", long 66°57'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank at ford 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from bridge on highway 2, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) west of Quebradillas plaza, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean, and 6.6 mi (10.6 km) downstream from Lago Guajataca.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 22...	1200	20	466	7.8	25.5	.97	7.0	85	<10	210	1000
MAR 13...	1215	8.7	611	7.8	24.5	.85	4.8	57	<10	K60	K45
JUN 04...	1215	29	409	8.1	25.5	8.6	7.4	90	<10	600	200
SEP 11...	1400	100	378	7.6	26.0	4.9	7.3	112	<10	3900	320

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 22...	200	71	6.3	14	.4	1.4	190	<.5	8.5	25
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--
JUN 04...	180	65	4.9	10	.3	1.7	180	--	8.3	16
SEP 11...	180	64	3.8	6.3	.2	1.6	180	<1.0	7.4	9.2

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 22...	<.10	6.7	246	13.3	<1	--	<.010	1.50	.010	--
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	2	2.59	.010	2.60	.040	.22
JUN 04...	<.10	6.3	220	17.1	7	--	<.010	1.10	.010	.21
SEP 11...	<.10	6.6	207	56.2	3	.575	.015	.590	.030	--

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 22...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	30	<1	1	<10
MAR 13...	.26	2.9	13	.030	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 04...	.22	1.3	5.8	<.020	<1	<100	30	<1	1	<10
SEP 11...	<.20	--	--	<.020	--	--	--	--	--	--

Figure 12. Río Camuy basin.

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50014800 RIO CAMUY NEAR BAYANEY, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'48", long 66°49'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank at Highway 488, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) southeast of school at Santiago, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northwest from Escuela Manuel A. Rivera at Bayaney and 9.1 mi (14.6 km) upstream from mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 341 ft (104 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	82	58	54	e29	27	25	37	26	e60	57	112	259
2	182	59	49	e29	26	25	29	25	e52	55	62	426
3	183	56	43	e29	26	24	e27	25	e89	53	56	347
4	75	55	41	e27	28	23	e26	28	82	55	56	203
5	97	53	41	e28	63	50	25	27	238	52	64	142
6	97	53	41	e29	44	65	25	101	198	51	53	247
7	186	52	39	e47	30	43	25	137	106	106	74	304
8	217	52	39	e35	29	38	26	54	74	59	82	196
9	95	50	38	e27	41	29	24	64	60	85	205	138
10	71	49	39	e27	31	27	23	44	59	55	177	116
11	65	49	37	e26	29	26	23	33	117	63	482	102
12	309	58	36	e27	29	25	23	30	242	55	615	239
13	313	60	36	e49	28	26	23	29	414	56	296	272
14	385	52	35	e35	27	26	23	39	227	84	136	160
15	329	51	35	e27	27	42	22	31	123	101	103	109
16	378	55	35	e26	27	35	59	31	261	460	118	130
17	229	50	34	33	27	27	42	28	275	324	125	181
18	177	47	33	76	26	27	28	72	194	149	100	298
19	134	45	32	52	25	25	146	152	155	94	84	257
20	116	43	32	50	25	24	153	603	94	81	77	141
21	103	43	32	36	25	24	77	571	79	73	138	255
22	92	42	32	33	25	24	54	257	75	66	120	9010
23	85	41	34	31	25	23	39	e130	65	63	84	3140
24	79	41	41	30	24	23	44	e94	59	87	82	1140
25	75	40	33	30	24	22	61	e79	67	65	276	835
26	72	44	32	31	27	23	38	e73	70	58	131	580
27	68	67	e32	29	26	23	33	e65	184	89	114	e540
28	66	70	e32	28	25	23	31	e62	122	65	687	e520
29	64	66	e32	27	---	40	28	e61	72	58	463	e900
30	61	102	e30	27	---	88	27	87	62	55	197	e600
31	59	---	e31	27	---	66	---	78	---	127	436	---
TOTAL	4544	1603	1130	1037	816	1011	1241	3136	3975	2901	5805	21787
MEAN	147	53.4	36.5	33.5	29.1	32.6	41.4	101	133	93.6	187	726
MAX	385	102	54	76	63	88	153	603	414	460	687	9010
MIN	59	40	30	26	24	22	22	25	52	51	53	102

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	197	113	66.5	57.2	50.0	46.8	86.6	167	110	75.2	97.9	201			
MAX	427	244	97.4	163	96.4	66.0	202	624	235	109	187	726			
(WY)	1986	1986	1988	1997	1996	1992	1986	1986	1995	1989	1998	1998			
MIN	81.6	53.4	36.5	33.1	29.1	23.7	28.0	43.2	42.7	38.8	47.9	61.8			
(WY)	1988	1998	1998	1991	1998	1994	1994	1989	1997	1994	1993	1997			

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	26693	48986		
ANNUAL MEAN	73.1	134		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			106	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			179	1986
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	600	Jan 22	9010	Sep 22 1998
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	29	Jun 10	22	Mar 25 1994
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	32	Dec 25	23	Mar 22 1994
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			11600	Sep 22 1998
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			21.69	Sep 22 1998
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			22	Mar 25 1994
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	124		256	204
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	52		55	66
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	34		26	33

e Estimated

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50014800 RIO CAMUY NEAR BAYANEY, PR--Continued

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Figure 13. Río Grande de Arecibo basin.

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50020100 LAGO GARZAS NEAR ADJUNTAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°08'20", long 66°44'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, in power gate tower of Garzas Dam on Río Vacas, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from Río Garzas, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) southwest of Adjuntas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.02 mi² (15.6 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1988 to May 1989, March 1993 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 2,400.00 ft (731.520 m) above mean sea level. Prior to May 25, 1988 at datum 2,376.80 ft (724.449 m), May 25 to July 13, 1988 at datum 2,338.08 ft (712.647 m), July 14, 1988 to May 25, 1989 at datum 2,337.82 ft (712.560 m), above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lake is formed by earthfill dam completed in 1943. Outflow from lake controlled by vertical-lift sluice gate and fixed-crest concrete spillway. Spillway elevation, 2,415.00 ft (736.09 m), Lake is used for irrigation and power production. Operated by P.R. Electric Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 2,418.28 ft (737.092 m), Sept. 22, 1998; minimum elevation, 2,364.79 ft (720.788 m), Aug. 23, 1988.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 2,418.28 ft (737.092 m), Sept. 22; minimum elevation, 2,403.38 ft (732.550 m), Feb. 10.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
2,364	660	2,415	4,082
2,382	1,500	2,418	4,411
2,394	2,250		

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	A	2407.94	2407.87	2409.77	2406.42	2407.73	2408.09	2410.19	2414.73	2414.71	2414.84	2414.86
2	A	2407.67	2408.07	2409.89	2406.50	2407.66	2408.51	2410.15	2414.74	2414.83	2414.85	2414.90
3	A	2407.39	2408.31	2410.03	2406.56	2407.61	2408.59	2410.11	2414.75	2414.80	2414.73	2414.97
4	A	2407.16	2408.25	2410.14	2405.30	2407.53	2408.60	2410.20	2414.78	2414.77	2414.68	2414.91
5	A	2407.05	2408.33	2410.25	2403.69	2407.47	2408.59	2410.31	2414.78	A	2414.62	2414.92
6	A	2407.06	2408.39	2410.26	2403.60	2407.43	2408.57	2410.54	2414.76	2414.70	A	2414.96
7	A	2407.12	2408.46	2410.36	2403.62	2407.37	2409.56	2410.67	2414.74	2414.73	2414.80	2414.92
8	A	2407.17	2408.53	2410.48	2403.42	2407.29	2409.74	2411.70	2414.78	2414.72	2414.83	2414.90
9	A	2406.47	2408.59	2410.58	2403.40	2407.21	2409.80	2411.93	2414.79	2414.72	2414.87	2414.89
10	A	2405.95	2408.67	2410.68	2403.43	2407.13	2409.82	A	2414.79	2414.86	2414.73	2414.88
11	A	2405.69	2408.77	2410.83	2403.46	2407.05	2409.89	2412.10	2414.67	2414.75	2414.68	2414.93
12	A	2405.73	2408.87	2410.91	2403.51	2407.00	2410.13	2412.20	2414.66	2414.72	2414.54	2414.88
13	A	2405.85	2408.95	2410.99	2408.48	2406.92	2410.23	A	2414.66	2414.71	2414.40	2414.89
14	A	2406.01	2409.01	2411.11	2408.48	2406.87	2410.27	2413.60	2414.66	2414.70	2414.50	2414.87
15	A	2405.57	2409.11	2410.94	2408.46	2406.89	2410.29	2414.20	2414.69	2414.70	2414.73	2414.87
16	A	2405.61	2409.19	2410.99	2408.40	2406.88	2410.30	2414.40	2414.72	2414.72	2414.77	A
17	A	2405.71	2409.27	2411.09	2408.35	2406.84	2410.29	2414.49	2414.89	2414.83	2414.49	A
18	A	2405.83	2409.28	2411.16	2408.30	2406.77	2410.36	2414.56	2414.79	2414.78	2414.49	A
19	A	2405.97	2408.59	2411.26	2408.24	2406.70	2410.44	2414.61	2414.74	2414.76	2414.52	2414.20
20	A	2406.10	2408.66	2411.36	2408.20	2406.66	2410.46	2414.70	2414.73	2414.80	2414.77	2411.60
21	A	2406.24	2408.69	2411.38	2408.14	2406.59	2410.46	2414.94	2414.74	2414.73	2414.83	2416.72
22	A	2406.39	2408.76	2406.02	2408.08	2406.52	2410.45	2414.77	2414.74	2414.71	2414.86	2415.45
23	A	2406.57	2408.87	2406.07	2408.00	2406.43	2410.43	2414.81	2414.81	2414.90	2414.81	2415.10
24	A	2406.71	2408.95	2406.10	2407.96	2406.35	2410.39	2414.81	2414.82	2414.79	2416.11	2415.06
25	A	2406.87	2409.05	2406.14	2407.92	2406.34	2410.37	2414.75	2414.76	2414.77	2414.92	2415.04
26	A	2406.97	2409.15	2406.18	2407.91	2406.26	2410.34	2414.75	2414.70	2414.77	2414.88	2415.04
27	A	2407.13	2409.25	2406.24	2407.85	2406.20	2410.32	2414.73	2414.68	2414.81	2414.86	2414.98
28	A	2407.31	2409.35	2406.26	2407.79	2406.12	2410.29	2414.77	2414.67	2414.77	2414.69	2414.98
29	2408.79	2407.47	2409.45	2406.28	---	2406.10	2410.25	2414.73	2414.70	2414.76	2414.84	2414.97
30	2408.47	2407.65	2409.55	2406.32	---	2406.41	2410.21	2414.73	2414.71	2414.75	2414.86	2414.97
31	2408.20	---	2409.65	2406.36	---	2406.43	---	2414.72	---	2414.74	2414.86	---
MAX	---	2407.94	2409.65	2411.38	2408.48	2407.73	2410.46	---	2414.89	---	---	---
MIN	---	2405.57	2407.87	2406.02	2403.40	2406.10	2408.09	---	2414.66	---	---	---

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50020500 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO NEAR ADJUNTAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'54", long 66°44'12", at Highway 135 bridge, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream from Lago Adjuntas, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northwest of Adjuntas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.7 mi² (32.9 km²) this does not include 6.0 mi² (15.6 km²) above Lago Garzas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)
OCT 29...	0900	18	328	8.4	21.5	1.0	8.4	100	<10	K890 450
MAR 11...	0800	8.5	381	7.6	19.0	.30	7.9	89	<10	K1200 470
JUN 17...	1100	23	328	7.9	24.0	.35	8.4	105	<10	K750 480
SEP 08...	1455	136	240	7.4	25.5	2.2	7.3	94	<10	K680 520

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD CACO3 (MG/L AS) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 29...	150	34	15	17	.6	2.7	120	<.5	17	24
MAR 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
JUN 17...	110	28	9.1	21	.9	1.8	110	--	8.5	30
SEP 08...	82	22	6.7	10	.5	1.8	89	<1.0	8.4	12

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 29...	.20	24	206	10.0	3	--	<.010	1.30	.020	--
MAR 11...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.26	.040	1.30	.050	.29
JUN 17...	<.10	28	192	12.0	<1	.982	.018	1.00	.020	--
SEP 08...	<.10	27	142	52.2	5	.985	.015	1.00	.040	--

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 29...	<.20	--	--	.080	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
MAR 11...	.34	1.6	7.3	.120	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 17...	<.20	--	--	.080	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
SEP 08...	<.20	--	--	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50024950 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW UTUADO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'07", long 66°42'15", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, 2.4 mi (3.9 km) north of Utuado Plaza, 3.4 mi (5.5 km) southwest from Dos Bocas Dam, 3.5 mi (5.6 km) northwest from Caonillas Dam.

DRAINAGE AREA.--65.62 mi² (170 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1996 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 295.28 ft (90 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	123	65	71	39	e32	27	59	46	66	61	189	252
2	69	63	63	39	e32	27	156	39	67	65	302	400
3	56	63	67	39	30	27	e126	39	64	85	292	355
4	53	63	64	38	55	28	e51	37	72	72	283	573
5	51	63	65	38	217	28	47	38	250	67	229	405
6	50	62	64	e44	58	31	45	99	126	105	310	601
7	345	61	63	e60	34	68	117	60	79	88	e534	495
8	224	59	60	47	55	36	159	190	69	70	561	366
9	153	74	59	38	74	29	56	173	71	67	567	379
10	81	193	57	39	46	31	44	76	70	82	513	285
11	110	149	55	39	47	28	44	63	94	89	827	325
12	572	118	54	44	52	29	51	66	66	71	670	353
13	386	108	53	65	49	29	63	72	60	68	611	262
14	450	91	52	45	50	31	50	79	58	96	434	227
15	323	96	51	38	54	53	43	262	55	131	310	215
16	210	119	50	37	45	30	49	117	90	444	345	255
17	316	96	49	41	40	43	67	67	176	433	280	333
18	323	90	48	41	38	33	65	152	217	499	216	541
19	220	85	48	44	35	24	e148	211	105	434	207	e401
20	174	81	55	39	32	22	62	216	76	310	207	e305
21	148	77	48	41	29	24	41	915	73	289	246	589
22	130	75	46	34	28	22	54	454	73	215	244	e7600
23	116	70	61	33	27	22	68	333	67	207	247	e1500
24	105	69	48	34	27	22	54	222	70	345	281	e980
25	95	67	44	e36	27	22	51	167	104	213	956	e700
26	89	e63	44	e36	35	24	51	125	76	168	599	e580
27	80	71	43	32	28	23	50	101	72	175	551	e520
28	76	65	42	31	28	24	58	86	65	166	356	e500
29	71	102	40	31	---	73	52	83	61	158	295	e860
30	69	85	39	31	---	77	49	89	60	155	253	e560
31	66	---	39	30	---	61	---	74	---	263	282	---
TOTAL	5334	2543	1642	1223	1304	1048	2030	4751	2652	5691	12197	21717
MEAN	172	84.8	53.0	39.5	46.6	33.8	67.7	153	88.4	184	393	724
MAX	572	193	71	65	217	77	159	915	250	499	956	7600
MIN	50	59	39	30	27	22	41	37	55	61	189	215
AC-FT	10580	5040	3260	2430	2590	2080	4030	9420	5260	11290	24190	43080
CFSM	2.62	1.29	.81	.60	.71	.52	1.03	2.34	1.35	2.80	6.00	11.0
IN.	3.02	1.44	.93	.69	.74	.59	1.15	2.69	1.50	3.23	6.91	12.31

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1996 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1996	1997	1998	1996	1997	1998	1996	1997	1998	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	198	163	85.6	79.6	65.0	50.9	56.9	105	83.1	102	188	445
MAX	224	242	118	120	83.5	68.0	67.7	153	120	184	393	724
(WY)	1997	1997	1997	1997	1997	1997	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998
MIN	172	84.8	53.0	39.5	46.6	33.8	46.2	50.8	40.8	36.6	77.0	87.3
(WY)	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1997	1997	1997	1997	1997	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1998 WATER YEAR	FOR 1996 WATER YEAR	FOR 1997 WATER YEAR	FOR 1998 WATER YEAR	FOR 1999 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1996 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	28001	62132					
ANNUAL MEAN	76.7	170					135
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN							170
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN							99.6
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	572	Oct 12	7600	Sep 22	7600	Sep 22	1998
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	23	Aug 7	22	Mar 20	22	Mar 20	1998
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	28	Aug 1	23	Mar 19	23	Mar 19	1998
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			33000	Sep 22	33000	Sep 22	1998
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			21.28	Sep 22	21.28	Sep 22	1998
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			20	Mar 24	20	Mar 24	1998
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	55540	123200					97740
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.17	2.59					2.06
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	15.87	35.22					27.94
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	117	392					295
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	61	69					71
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	34	32					36

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50024950 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW UTUADO, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50024950 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW UTUADO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- April, 1996 to current water year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: April, 1996 to current water year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1996.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediments samples were collected by local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 10,600 mg/L September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 3 mg/L August 6, 1996.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 768,000 tons (e698,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.50 ton (0.45 tonne) August 6, 1996.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,830 mg/L October 12, 1997; Minimum daily mean, 6 mg/L May 2, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e768,000 tons (e698,000 tonne) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.68 tons (0.61 tonne).

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	123	1370	1160	65	33	5.8	71	79	15
2	69	318	61	63	33	5.6	63	44	7.5
3	56	156	24	63	33	5.7	67	48	8.7
4	53	144	20	63	35	5.9	64	56	9.8
5	51	147	20	63	42	7.2	65	59	10
6	50	151	20	62	51	8.6	64	58	10
7	345	2880	10100	61	49	8.1	63	58	9.7
8	224	1450	898	59	44	7.0	60	56	9.2
9	153	590	279	74	84	30	59	43	6.8
10	81	242	53	193	1240	713	57	30	4.7
11	110	493	174	149	1280	745	55	40	6.0
12	572	3810	15900	118	877	398	54	57	8.3
13	386	1600	1810	108	303	92	53	36	5.2
14	450	313	395	91	195	48	52	20	2.9
15	323	275	252	96	151	39	51	20	2.7
16	210	618	1020	119	122	39	50	24	3.2
17	316	3020	4570	96	125	32	49	29	3.9
18	323	2830	2600	90	136	33	48	35	4.6
19	220	518	323	85	147	34	48	42	5.3
20	174	177	84	81	151	33	55	40	5.9
21	148	139	56	77	75	16	48	37	4.8
22	130	109	38	75	33	6.7	46	33	4.1
23	116	96	30	70	36	6.7	61	316	91
24	105	130	37	69	45	8.4	48	316	41
25	95	173	44	67	56	10	44	250	29
26	89	168	40	e63	48	e11	44	215	25
27	80	150	33	71	37	7.0	43	187	22
28	76	109	22	65	33	5.8	42	139	16
29	71	74	14	102	608	410	40	99	11
30	69	50	9.3	85	191	44	39	80	8.5
31	66	35	6.2	---	---	---	39	68	7.1
TOTAL	5334	---	40092.5	2543	---	2815.5	1642	---	398.9

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50024950 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	39	58	6.1	e32	183	e15	27	94	6.9
2	39	52	5.4	e32	174	e14	27	114	8.2
3	39	87	9.0	30	165	13	27	115	8.4
4	38	148	15	55	1600	969	28	110	8.2
5	38	95	9.8	217	2630	2410	28	106	8.0
6	e44	56	e6.5	58	303	58	31	107	10
7	e60	166	e26	34	134	12	68	249	56
8	47	185	23	55	190	40	36	93	9.4
9	38	189	20	74	282	67	29	64	5.0
10	39	207	22	46	75	9.4	31	52	4.4
11	39	227	24	47	58	7.4	28	32	2.4
12	44	261	32	52	57	7.9	29	20	1.6
13	65	421	75	49	40	5.3	29	19	1.5
14	45	361	44	50	39	5.3	31	29	2.7
15	38	323	33	54	35	5.2	53	215	57
16	37	293	29	45	31	3.7	30	60	4.9
17	41	275	31	40	23	2.5	43	111	17
18	41	194	21	38	18	1.8	33	165	15
19	44	151	18	35	22	2.0	24	115	7.4
20	39	149	16	32	32	2.8	22	111	6.7
21	41	143	16	29	47	3.7	24	120	7.9
22	34	120	11	28	68	5.1	22	131	7.8
23	33	122	11	27	84	6.1	22	141	8.5
24	34	132	12	27	95	6.8	22	149	8.7
25	e36	142	e13	27	78	5.7	22	156	9.2
26	e36	153	e14	35	66	6.5	24	163	11
27	32	159	14	28	61	4.7	23	170	11
28	31	165	14	28	76	5.7	24	163	10
29	31	180	15	---	---	---	73	1690	712
30	31	196	16	---	---	---	77	1110	261
31	30	193	16	---	---	---	61	387	66
TOTAL	1223	---	617.8	1304	---	3695.6	1048	---	1353.8
APRIL									
1	59	488	169	46	7	.87	66	24	4.3
2	156	1020	469	39	6	.68	67	21	3.9
3	e126	614	e231	39	7	.75	64	21	3.6
4	e51	153	e22	37	11	1.1	72	120	34
5	47	84	11	38	15	1.5	250	2180	2930
6	45	64	7.9	99	826	580	126	428	186
7	117	654	588	60	168	32	79	102	22
8	159	1020	479	190	1120	1700	69	92	17
9	56	156	25	173	583	321	71	199	42
10	44	61	7.2	76	99	21	70	119	23
11	44	33	3.9	63	28	4.8	94	472	291
12	51	29	4.0	66	19	3.4	66	163	30
13	63	144	26	72	15	2.9	60	47	7.7
14	50	73	9.9	79	18	4.5	58	38	5.9
15	43	47	5.5	262	1270	1310	55	35	5.2
16	49	36	4.7	117	175	61	90	957	560
17	67	506	162	67	75	14	176	1120	1210
18	65	298	114	152	819	984	217	1810	1640
19	e148	596	e197	211	1260	997	105	333	109
20	62	235	43	216	1420	1110	76	54	11
21	41	64	7.4	915	3490	23900	73	45	8.8
22	54	281	78	454	786	1110	73	37	7.3
23	68	156	31	333	221	199	67	32	5.7
24	54	67	9.8	222	183	111	70	28	5.4
25	51	52	7.0	167	109	50	104	622	337
26	51	40	5.5	125	62	21	76	214	46
27	50	31	4.2	101	35	9.8	72	94	18
28	58	29	4.5	86	21	4.9	65	80	14
29	52	27	3.7	83	14	3.2	61	90	15
30	49	14	1.9	89	424	139	60	98	16
31	---	---	---	74	104	21	---	---	---
TOTAL	2030	---	2732.1	4751	---	32719.40	2652	---	7608.8
MAY									
JUNE									

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50024950 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN			MEAN			MEAN		
		CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	
JULY										
1	61	54	8.8	189	127	65	252	198	137	
2	65	28	4.9	302	993	1300	400	1440	2620	
3	85	43	9.7	292	679	531	355	2600	2810	
4	72	73	14	283	498	574	573	2360	4540	
5	67	82	15	229	78	49	405	460	534	
6	105	826	441	310	2120	4060	601	2670	6760	
7	88	196	53	e534	2440	e4710	495	239	321	
8	70	47	8.9	561	2340	4400	366	225	222	
9	67	44	7.9	567	1130	1860	379	1240	1700	
10	82	44	9.7	513	1830	3760	285	148	115	
11	89	39	9.4	827	3230	12300	325	606	1020	
12	71	35	6.7	670	695	1310	353	812	1140	
13	68	38	6.9	611	144	242	262	179	127	
14	96	413	187	434	81	96	227	148	91	
15	131	1230	556	310	57	48	215	124	72	
16	444	2050	4150	345	1580	2280	255	601	682	
17	433	443	522	280	749	765	333	1540	2360	
18	499	347	543	216	78	45	541	2650	4980	
19	434	272	319	207	73	41	e401	90	e102	
20	310	215	181	207	71	40	e305	73	e60	
21	289	142	112	246	771	585	589	1370	11200	
22	215	96	56	244	215	140	e7600	1470	e768000	
23	207	115	70	247	139	93	e1500	986	e82500	
24	345	632	619	281	301	495	e980	663	e27200	
25	213	201	121	956	1260	5330	e700	2670	e7000	
26	168	72	33	599	155	253	e580	2360	e4540	
27	175	51	24	551	328	624	e520	1830	e3760	
28	166	47	21	356	1590	1720	e500	1820	e3500	
29	158	56	24	295	210	168	e860	3230	e12300	
30	155	63	26	253	120	82	e560	2340	e4400	
31	263	1050	1610	282	370	363	---	---	---	
TOTAL	5691	---	9769.9	12197	---	48329	21717	---	954793	
YEAR	62132		1104926.30							

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
01...	1945	247	6190	4130	95
NOV					
29...	1700	346	13000	12100	98
DEC					
23...	1850	113	1780	543	89
MAR					
29...	1635	165	5500	2450	94
APR					
17...	1555	170	1970	904	96
MAY					
20...	1715	350	5690	5380	75
SEP					
02...	1645	786	3660	7770	79

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50024950 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW UTUADO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)
		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)
OCT							
01...	1715	499	9460	12700	27	37	50
07...	1845	766	13400	27700	30	42	58
NOV							
11...	1745	361	8370	8160	34	45	62
FEB							
04...	2215	215	12500	7260	20	27	38
MAY							
06...	1745	322	5160	4490	36	48	61
SEP							
02...	1500	934	6880	17400	30	40	54
DATE							
OCT							
01...	63	74	79	90	96	98	99
07...	72	86	90	97	99	100	100
NOV							
11...	78	90	94	99	100	100	100
FEB							
04...	55	75	82	92	100	100	100
MAY							
06...	73	83	87	97	99	100	100
SEP							
02...	69	81	86	96	99	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50025000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO NEAR UTUADO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'11", long 66°41'59", at bridge near Highway 10 at km 56.4, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) downstream from Río de Caguana, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) north of Utuado plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--66.0 mi² (170.9 km²) this excludes 6.0 mi² (15.5 km²) upstream from Lago Garzas to Río Guayanes in the Río Tallaboa basin.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 29...	1130	80	292	8.0	27.5	6.3	7.9	99	<10	K1600	810
MAR 11...	0945	34	316	7.9	21.5	2.9	8.6	104	<10	20000	K1100
JUN 18...	1245	240	173	7.8	26.5	130	7.2	90	<10	30000	28000
SEP 02...	1040	215	257	7.5	26.5	7.1	7.7	97	<10	3000	950
DATE		HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 29...		81	19	7.9	34	2	3.7	93	<.5	15	33
MAR 11...		--	--	--	--	--	--	97	--	--	--
JUN 18...		64	17	5.1	8.2	.4	2.6	54	--	14	8.2
SEP 02...		84	21	7.6	10	.5	2.1	82	<1.0	8.7	12
DATE		FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 29...		<.10	25	192	41.5	9	1.23	.075	1.30	.020	.23
MAR 11...		--	--	--	--	6	1.28	.015	1.30	.030	.20
JUN 18...		<.10	18	106	68.5	176	1.17	.033	1.20	.100	.54
SEP 02...		<.10	24	139	80.7	74	1.27	.028	1.30	.060	.22
DATE		NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 29...		.25	1.5	6.9	.220	<1	<100	20	<1	1	15
MAR 11...		.23	1.5	6.8	.080	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 18...		.64	1.8	8.1	.250	<1	<100	20	<1	3	29
SEP 02...		.28	1.6	7.0	.080	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50025155 RIO SALIENTE AT COABEY NEAR JAYUYA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'48", long 66°33'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) southeast of Jayuya, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) northeast of Hacienda Gripiñas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.25 mi² (23.96 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 1,706 ft (520 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14	9.9	9.2	4.0	4.9	6.5	24	14	25	12	11	27
2	16	9.6	9.5	4.1	4.9	6.3	22	14	36	12	13	267
3	16	9.1	8.6	3.9	4.9	7.3	22	13	30	13	13	354
4	11	9.1	7.4	3.6	126	8.2	20	13	41	14	10	356
5	9.4	8.7	7.0	3.6	259	6.6	15	12	222	12	9.5	138
6	8.7	8.0	6.6	3.7	28	13	13	15	82	29	21	161
7	38	7.5	6.0	4.5	16	55	340	17	45	24	51	103
8	45	7.1	5.8	4.1	57	27	105	139	35	16	110	71
9	32	29	5.7	3.7	48	12	43	55	32	14	60	92
10	25	54	5.6	3.9	22	9.5	28	27	28	16	39	58
11	18	17	5.4	5.8	16	8.3	27	21	25	15	62	230
12	30	17	5.1	4.8	14	7.7	72	17	23	13	62	116
13	101	14	5.1	7.8	12	7.2	60	17	22	13	40	148
14	306	12	4.9	7.3	12	17	37	244	20	81	28	89
15	285	33	4.9	4.5	15	68	28	158	19	49	22	60
16	150	22	4.6	4.0	11	30	28	59	44	32	30	56
17	199	14	4.7	3.7	10	16	36	39	69	26	29	52
18	173	12	5.1	9.6	9.4	12	56	32	39	22	25	108
19	73	11	5.6	18	8.7	10	53	31	25	19	23	76
20	46	11	4.6	11	8.3	16	88	226	21	17	19	55
21	34	10	5.1	7.2	8.1	18	63	269	20	16	43	e2420
22	27	9.8	4.7	6.5	7.8	15	39	124	26	13	87	e1050
23	23	9.0	4.4	5.9	7.3	16	32	68	19	14	55	e270
24	19	9.0	4.2	5.6	7.6	12	30	50	17	16	462	e150
25	17	8.8	4.1	5.8	7.7	12	27	40	17	14	629	e110
26	15	9.8	4.1	5.8	9.3	12	23	35	16	12	93	e98
27	14	9.6	3.9	5.4	7.5	11	21	31	15	16	95	e90
28	13	8.2	3.8	5.1	6.8	12	19	28	14	13	58	e86
29	12	29	3.9	5.1	---	13	17	25	13	12	43	e145
30	11	17	4.0	5.1	---	48	15	45	13	11	33	e98
31	10	---	4.0	5.1	---	39	---	31	---	11	34	---
TOTAL	1791.1	435.2	167.6	178.2	749.2	551.6	1403	1909	1053	597	2309.5	7134
MEAN	57.8	14.5	5.41	5.75	26.8	17.8	46.8	61.6	35.1	19.3	74.5	238
MAX	306	54	9.5	18	259	68	340	269	222	81	629	2420
MIN	8.7	7.1	3.8	3.6	4.9	6.3	13	12	13	11	9.5	27
AC-FT	3550	863	332	353	1490	1090	2780	3790	2090	1180	4580	14150
CFSM	6.25	1.57	.58	.62	2.89	1.92	5.06	6.66	3.79	2.08	8.05	25.7
IN.	7.20	1.75	.67	.72	3.01	2.22	5.64	7.68	4.23	2.40	9.29	28.69

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000
MEAN	40.7	23.3	12.3	18.2	17.1	11.5	23.3	40.6	23.3	17.0	28.7	105
MAX	72.0	40.0	22.7	48.1	44.4	17.8	46.8	98.6	35.4	50.9	74.5	365
(WY)	1996	1991	1993	1992	1996	1998	1998	1995	1994	1996	1998	1996
MIN	11.6	10.0	5.41	4.13	4.67	4.79	5.95	5.35	5.30	2.83	9.82	10.8
(WY)	1992	1994	1998	1995	1994	1994	1994	1990	1997	1994	1994	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1998

	1997 CALENDAR YEAR	1998 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1989 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	6112.2	18278.4	
ANNUAL MEAN	16.7	50.1	30.0
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			64.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.9
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	306	Oct 14	2420
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.1	Aug 7	3.6
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.5	Jul 5	3.8
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			14200
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			19.16
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			3.6
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	12120	36260	21760
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.81	5.41	3.25
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	24.58	73.51	44.11
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	30	99	54
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.8	17	13
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.0	5.1	4.5

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50025155 RIO SALIENTE AT COABEY NEAR JAYUYA, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026025 RIO CAONILLAS AT PASO PALMA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'53", long 66°38'14", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, 3.5 mi (5.6 km) south of Lago Caonillas Dam, 4.8 mi (7.72 km) southeast of Utuado Plaza and 2.78 mi (4.47 km) east of Lago Vivi Dam.

DRAINAGE AREA.--37.94 mi² (98.26 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1995 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 984 ft (300 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	40	39	40	15	14	18	117	48	67	40	63	119
2	36	38	35	15	14	17	127	47	e69.0	40	67	490
3	28	36	32	15	14	17	e87	43	e78.0	46	59	527
4	24	36	28	14	57	21	e60	40	e77.0	43	43	544
5	22	35	25	14	448	18	42	39	e165	40	41	340
6	21	33	24	15	79	37	36	53	e150	e56.0	e63.0	366
7	100	31	23	21	42	169	458	65	e94	e55.0	e194	282
8	122	29	22	23	89	104	249	284	e82.0	e45.0	e186	220
9	93	58	21	16	126	44	127	183	e77.0	e43.0	e168	212
10	60	112	21	15	57	32	93	90	e75.0	e47.0	e206	173
11	48	52	20	22	45	27	80	68	e70.0	e47.0	e211	300
12	77	69	20	39	38	25	132	57	e67.0	e45.0	e227	249
13	146	56	19	e33	28	23	135	52	e68.0	e45.0	158	280
14	421	41	19	e43	29	29	99	339	e64.0	e62.0	114	218
15	332	45	19	e25	36	71	80	371	e63.0	e167	95	167
16	250	68	17	e19	26	74	80	154	e71.0	161	148	155
17	583	43	18	e17	24	44	104	112	e183	99	131	227
18	370	38	18	e18	22	32	128	131	e108	89	106	218
19	189	35	21	e32	22	26	e141	107	e75.0	83	92	184
20	131	33	20	24	21	26	140	305	60	e70	78	142
21	103	32	20	20	21	39	142	390	58	e60	106	e1420
22	86	31	20	18	20	28	131	e252	66	50	177	e13000
23	74	29	19	16	19	30	107	e146	52	47	149	e1370
24	65	28	18	16	18	25	84	e106	49	e60	360	e663
25	59	31	17	16	20	23	83	e90	56	e51	e498	e528
26	54	36	17	16	39	26	72	e81	50	43	e233	450
27	49	34	16	15	24	23	67	e76	46	69	e247	401
28	47	28	16	14	20	24	65	e73	44	49	191	455
29	45	72	16	14	---	30	54	69	43	45	147	387
30	43	79	15	14	---	106	49	79	41	42	124	353
31	41	---	15	14	---	102	---	83	---	87	153	---
TOTAL	3759	1327	651	608	1412	1310	3369	4033	2268.0	1926.0	4835.0	24440
MEAN	121	44.2	21.0	19.6	50.4	42.3	112	130	75.6	62.1	156	815
MAX	583	112	40	43	448	169	458	390	183	167	498	13000
MIN	21	28	15	14	14	17	36	39	41	40	41	119
AC-FT	7460	2630	1290	1210	2800	2600	6680	8000	4500	3820	9590	48480
CFSM	3.20	1.17	.55	.52	1.33	1.11	2.96	3.43	1.99	1.64	4.11	21.5
IN.	3.69	1.30	.64	.60	1.38	1.28	3.30	3.95	2.22	1.89	4.74	23.96

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1996 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1996	1997	1998	1996	1997	1998	1996	1997	1998	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	119	82.5	48.6	53.1	59.8	39.8	62.2	95.2	57.7	64.9	88.9	413
MAX	162	114	78.2	89.8	86.0	51.3	112	130	81.4	117	156	815
(WY)	1996	1997	1997	1997	1996	1996	1998	1998	1996	1996	1998	1998
MIN	72.9	44.2	21.0	19.6	41.9	25.7	17.0	29.1	16.1	15.5	47.9	33.2
(WY)	1997	1998	1998	1998	1997	1997	1997	1997	1997	1997	1996	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1996 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	15818	49938.0	
ANNUAL MEAN	43.3	137	98.4
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			137
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			49.9
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	583	Oct 17	13000
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	10	Jul 4	14
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	11	Jul 1	14
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			36000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			31.15
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			13
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	31380	99050	71260
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.14	3.61	2.59
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	15.51	48.96	35.22
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	76	239	164
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	28	54	47
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	13	18	17

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50026025 RIO CAONILLAS AT PASO PALMA, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026025 RIO CAONILLAS AT PASO PALMA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- October, 1995 to current water year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October, 1995 to current water year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1996.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediments samples were collected by local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 24,800 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e952,000 tons (e864,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.04 ton (0.03 tonne) December 29-30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 24,800 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e952,000 tons (e864,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998 ; Minimum daily mean, 0.04 ton (0.03 tonne) December 29-30, 1997 .

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	40	73	14	39	1	.13	40	96	11
2	36	88	9.6	38	1	.15	35	41	3.8
3	28	26	1.9	36	2	.23	32	30	2.7
4	24	29	1.9	36	4	.39	28	23	1.7
5	22	36	2.1	35	5	.44	25	18	1.2
6	21	34	1.9	33	4	.34	24	14	.92
7	100	1170	774	31	3	.26	23	11	.67
8	122	1190	271	29	3	.24	22	8	.49
9	93	250	76	58	5	.84	21	5	.26
10	60	50	8.3	112	13	225	21	2	.13
11	48	21	2.8	52	49	7.5	20	2	.11
12	77	199	94	69	241	113	20	2	.12
13	146	685	391	56	155	26	19	5	.27
14	421	677	904	41	22	2.5	19	10	.52
15	332	434	426	45	69	18	19	10	.52
16	250	400	270	68	112	28	17	9	.43
17	583	3850	17600	43	19	2.2	18	4	.17
18	370	4750	5540	38	8	.79	18	1	.06
19	189	366	205	35	6	.61	21	1	.06
20	131	32	12	33	8	.73	20	1	.06
21	103	22	6.2	32	17	1.4	20	1	.08
22	86	18	4.2	31	26	2.2	20	2	.10
23	74	15	3.0	29	12	.94	19	1	.07
24	65	12	2.2	28	5	.40	18	1	.06
25	59	9	1.4	31	22	3.5	17	3	.12
26	54	7	.99	36	29	3.3	17	5	.22
27	49	10	1.3	34	12	1.1	16	2	.11
28	47	16	2.0	28	11	.83	16	1	.05
29	45	13	1.6	72	899	526	16	1	.04
30	43	8	.94	79	410	117	15	1	.04
31	41	3	.33	---	---	---	15	1	.06
TOTAL	3759	---	26629.66	1327	---	1167.18	651	---	26.14

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026025 RIO CAONILLAS AT PASO PALMA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	15	2	.08	14	3	.09	18	4	.22
2	15	2	.08	14	3	.11	17	2	.11
3	15	2	.08	14	2	.09	17	4	.17
4	14	2	.08	57	176	502	21	6	.33
5	14	2	.08	448	555	1800	18	7	.35
6	15	2	.08	79	35	8.3	37	127	38
7	21	19	1.7	42	8	.92	169	1840	2070
8	23	27	1.8	89	703	469	104	1250	439
9	16	4	.19	126	675	303	44	112	14
10	15	3	.11	57	67	11	32	40	3.5
11	22	33	8.3	45	52	6.4	27	12	.89
12	39	71	10	38	42	4.3	25	4	.28
13	e33	33	e3.2	28	18	1.4	23	3	.21
14	e43	101	e13	29	8	.63	29	36	5.1
15	e25	26	e1.8	36	10	.94	71	484	110
16	e19	21	e1.1	26	11	.80	74	126	36
17	e17	21	e.98	24	5	.35	44	122	16
18	e18	20	e.98	22	2	.14	32	31	2.8
19	e32	66	e6.7	22	2	.12	26	10	.72
20	24	45	3.0	21	2	.12	26	6	.40
21	20	32	1.7	21	3	.16	39	60	7.2
22	18	10	.49	20	4	.19	28	7	.52
23	16	3	.15	19	3	.14	30	5	.43
24	16	3	.13	18	2	.10	25	5	.32
25	16	3	.13	20	2	.11	23	4	.28
26	16	3	.13	39	89	10	26	4	.26
27	15	3	.12	24	30	2.0	23	3	.17
28	14	3	.11	20	10	.52	24	2	.14
29	14	3	.11	---	---	---	30	3	.22
30	14	2	.09	---	---	---	106	6	205
31	14	2	.08	---	---	---	102	14	159
TOTAL	608	---	56.58	1412	---	3122.93	1310	---	3133.40
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	117	762	751	48	5	.62	67	7	1.4
2	127	729	280	47	2	.30	e69.0	7	e1.3
3	e87	112	e30	43	2	.23	e78.0	10	e2.1
4	e60	50	e8.2	40	2	.22	e77.0	53	e16
5	42	42	4.8	39	2	.26	e165	527	e925
6	36	38	3.7	53	110	31	e150	470	e288
7	458	724	5800	65	85	19	e94	31	e7.7
8	249	129	101	284	1090	2140	e82.0	26	e5.7
9	127	20	7.2	183	578	377	e77.0	22	e4.6
10	93	11	2.7	90	29	7.3	e75.0	19	e3.8
11	80	7	1.5	68	13	2.3	e70.0	16	e3.0
12	132	171	279	57	8	1.3	e67.0	14	e2.5
13	135	249	109	52	17	2.4	e68.0	12	e2.2
14	99	28	7.6	339	1470	7100	e64.0	11	e2.0
15	80	26	5.8	371	815	1600	e63.0	11	e1.8
16	80	10	2.2	154	60	26	e71.0	75	e31
17	104	253	117	112	17	5.1	e183	1490	e1280
18	128	708	325	131	353	203	e108	152	e56
19	e141	890	e401	107	595	172	e75.0	32	e6.5
20	140	979	412	305	2020	4090	60	16	2.6
21	142	167	99	390	3050	3570	58	7	1.1
22	131	321	176	e252	717	e574	66	5	.94
23	107	405	125	e146	47	e19	52	4	.60
24	84	73	17	e106	26	e7.6	49	5	.65
25	83	36	8.0	e90	20	e4.9	56	6	.87
26	72	21	4.1	e81	18	e4.0	50	5	.71
27	67	12	2.2	e76	16	e3.3	46	5	.60
28	65	9	1.5	e73	12	e2.4	44	4	.52
29	54	10	1.5	69	10	1.9	43	5	.57
30	49	10	1.3	79	81	27	41	11	1.2
31	---	---	---	83	24	6.0	---	---	---
TOTAL	3369	---	9084.3	4033	---	19998.13	2268.0	---	2650.96

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026025 RIO CAONILLAS AT PASO PALMA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN			MEAN			MEAN		
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	40	18	1.9	63	203	37	119	82	29
2	40	8	.91	67	237	71	490	3390	11100
3	46	4	.53	59	164	29	527	5350	11400
4	43	5	.53	43	33	3.8	544	4260	12300
5	40	5	.54	41	29	3.1	340	3390	3410
6	e56.0	446	e112	e63.0	37	e6.3	366	2690	5560
7	e55.0	66	e11	e194	755	e893	282	230	33
8	e45.0	21	e2.6	e186	505	e431	220	229	31
9	e43.0	23	e2.7	e168	634	e344	212	226	619
10	e47.0	26	e3.3	e206	814	e1100	173	190	57
11	e47.0	26	e3.3	e211	854	e857	300	287	2140
12	e45.0	26	e3.1	e227	841	e619	249	33	33
13	e45.0	25	e3.1	158	287	134	280	287	2100
14	e62.0	160	e99	114	149	46	218	27	30
15	e167	446	e296	95	161	41	167	26	10
16	161	376	253	148	1200	933	155	25	10
17	99	72	20	131	81	33	227	755	e900
18	89	21	5.1	106	32	9.1	218	1200	933
19	83	18	4.0	92	29	7.2	184	97	57
20	e70	16	e3.1	78	27	5.6	142	26	10
21	e60	13	e2.2	106	69	164	e1420	4920	e110000
22	50	13	1.7	177	219	675	e13000	24800	e952000
23	47	22	2.8	149	71	386	e1370	12200	e47200
24	e60	30	e4.8	360	949	6430	e663	6000	e19100
25	e51	21	e2.9	e498	211	e698	e528	5300	e10900
26	43	14	1.7	e233	53	e33	450	2690	7060
27	69	11	52	e247	347	e352	401	1000	5190
28	49	9	1.3	191	97	57	455	1500	8180
29	45	11	1.4	147	26	10	387	900	4760
30	42	13	1.5	124	33	11	353	878	3710
31	87	430	298	153	443	296	---	---	---
TOTAL	1926.0	---	1196.01	4835.0	---	14715.1	24440	---	1218862
YEAR	49938.0		1300642.39						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
NOV					
30...	1030	69	260	48	63
FEB					
05...	0245	1210	908	2970	73
08...	1800	117	1610	509	58
JUL					
06...	1800	88	4110	977	91
AUG					
31...	1845	299	2010	1620	94

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026025 RIO CAONILLAS AT PASO PALMA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)
		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)
OCT							
07...	1730	270	5110	3730	43	56	71
NOV							
12...	1630	41	2270	251	38	48	61
FEB							
04...	2400	1890	5610	28600	42	53	67
MAR							
07...	1630	76	4320	886	19	26	36
07...	1900	536	6750	9770	37	48	61
JUL							
31...	1915	288	3260	2540	42	54	69
AUG							
16...	1830	340	5380	4940	33	47	61
DATE							
OCT							
07...	83	88	90	94	96	98	99
NOV							
12...	73	81	87	96	99	100	100
FEB							
04...	78	84	86	91	96	100	100
MAR							
07...	45	53	54	97	99	100	100
07...	74	85	89	97	99	100	100
JUL							
31...	82	91	94	98	100	100	100
AUG							
16...	75	88	90	97	99	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026050 RIO CAONILLAS ABOVE LAGO CAONILLAS NEAR JAYUYA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'26", long 66°38'22", 300 ft (91 m) off Highway 531, 700 ft (213 m) upstream from Lago Caonillas, 3.3 mi (5.3 km) northwest of Jayuya plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--40.4 mi² (104.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD) (00400)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TURBIDITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 28...	1340	51	214	8.1	28.0	23	7.4	97	<10	K130	K100
MAR 10...	1245	37	236	7.9	25.0	1.5	8.1	100	<10	4100	210
JUN 17...	1445	114	159	7.4	26.0	110	7.3	93	<10	K120000	70000
SEP 08...	1155	E300	168	7.3	25.5	120	7.8	101	<10	K1500	570

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORPTION RATIO (00931)	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET CACO3 (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 28...	63	16	6.3	9.9	.5	3.1	66	<.5	10	8.2
MAR 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	74	--	--	--
JUN 17...	58	15	5.0	8.0	.5	1.7	51	--	10	10
SEP 08...	60	16	5.0	9.0	.5	1.9	54	<1.0	12	9.2

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 28...	<.10	22	109	15.0	174	--	<.010	.680	.020	--
MAR 10...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<.010	1.20	.030	--
JUN 17...	<.10	19	100	30.7	270	.862	.018	.880	.040	1.2
SEP 08...	<.10	25	111	E90.0	8	1.09	.014	1.10	.050	.66

DATE	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 28...	<.20	--	--	.060	<1	<100	10	<1	<1	<10
MAR 10...	<.20	--	--	.080	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 17...	1.2	2.1	9.2	.400	<1	<100	30	<1	9	34
SEP 08...	.71	1.8	8.0	.070	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026140 LAGO CAONILLAS AT DAMSITE NEAR UTUADO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'43", long 66°39'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, at Lago Caonillas Dam on Río Caonillas, 2.9 mi (4.7 km) northeast of Plaza de Utuado, 0.3 mi (0.6 km) west from Iglesia Santa María del Monte Carmelo, and 1.8 mi (3.0 km) northwest from Hacienda Carbonell.

DRAINAGE AREA.--48.4 mi² (125.4 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1991 to current year. Prior to October 1994, published as Lago Caonillas at Caonillas.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Caonillas was completed in 1948. The dam is a concrete gravity structure with a total length of 815 ft (248 m), a maximum height of 235 ft (72 m), and a maximum base width of 195 ft (59 m). Non-overflow sections on each abutment have a total length of 603 ft (184 m). The dam is the main unit of Caonillas Hydroelectric Project, and provides 49,000 acre-feet (60 km³) of usable storage for power generation at Caonillas Power Plant No. 1 located 2.5 mi (4.0 km) downstream from the dam. The dam is owned by Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 841.29 ft (256.42 m), Sept. 22, 1998; minimum elevation, 737.92 ft (224.92 m), Aug. 8, 1997.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 841.29 ft (256.42 m), Sept. 22; minimum elevation, 766.57 ft (233.65 m), Oct. 5.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
705	0	800	27,982
750	8,421	830	46,161

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	768.16	784.66	786.24	785.63	785.57	A	788.67	799.11	815.66	A	821.04	823.54
2	768.22	784.68	786.32	785.61	785.54	A	789.16	799.19	815.82	A	820.68	825.57
3	768.20	784.70	786.39	785.63	784.56	A	789.47	799.26	816.02	A	820.28	826.38
4	768.20	784.65	786.44	785.63	784.85	A	789.61	799.18	816.19	A	820.08	825.11
5	767.90	784.67	786.43	785.66	788.02	A	789.76	799.23	817.76	A	819.61	824.38
6	767.83	784.29	786.45	785.68	787.12	788.30	789.76	799.46	818.37	A	819.42	825.46
7	769.06	784.30	786.45	785.36	786.76	789.15	792.90	799.62	818.49	A	820.19	825.65
8	769.82	784.01	786.47	785.37	787.17	789.49	793.99	801.34	818.66	A	820.97	825.43
9	769.76	784.18	786.48	785.33	787.75	789.59	794.39	802.13	818.74	A	821.50	823.32
10	769.81	784.66	786.35	785.32	787.93	789.62	794.65	802.40	818.78	A	822.13	824.37
11	769.82	784.87	786.36	785.32	788.03	789.67	794.84	802.58	818.93	A	823.29	824.42
12	770.35	785.28	786.36	785.44	788.12	789.09	795.26	802.71	818.51	A	824.08	824.39
13	771.15	785.44	786.37	785.53	788.17	787.90	795.51	802.83	818.53	822.74	824.38	824.56
14	774.72	785.56	786.38	785.61	788.24	787.85	795.40	804.59	818.67	822.54	824.22	824.50
15	775.52	785.66	786.37	785.62	788.32	788.10	795.50	806.51	818.46	822.93	823.97	824.06
16	776.98	785.52	786.36	785.62	788.37	787.48	795.66	807.05	818.65	823.28	824.42	824.16
17	782.73	785.26	786.35	785.61	788.40	787.62	796.05	807.39	819.35	823.43	824.38	824.37
18	785.35	785.34	786.35	785.69	788.42	787.61	796.23	807.22	819.73	823.66	824.22	824.12
19	786.05	785.23	786.36	785.74	A	787.66	796.66	807.71	819.52	823.68	823.92	823.77
20	787.56	785.30	786.15	785.88	A	787.69	797.17	809.28	818.92	823.91	823.62	822.61
21	787.35	785.34	785.99	785.90	A	787.79	797.70	811.98	819.48	823.69	823.56	830.08
22	787.54	785.38	786.05	785.89	A	787.85	797.92	813.24	819.65	823.32	823.72	830.98
23	787.16	785.31	786.06	785.88	A	787.90	798.30	813.82	819.80	823.41	824.01	827.71
24	787.32	785.35	785.85	785.86	A	787.73	798.55	814.21	819.98	823.08	824.52	827.15
25	787.31	785.28	785.84	785.84	A	787.77	798.80	814.31	820.22	823.17	826.79	826.87
26	787.04	785.37	785.82	785.82	A	787.79	798.98	814.57	820.37	822.78	826.29	826.76
27	786.01	785.44	785.82	785.75	A	787.82	799.15	814.78	820.52	822.78	826.17	826.67
28	785.03	785.48	785.78	785.72	A	787.85	799.26	814.95	820.66	822.42	825.81	827.06
29	785.08	785.79	785.75	785.68	---	787.94	799.28	815.12	A	822.10	825.41	826.83
30	785.12	786.14	785.62	785.65	---	788.37	799.09	815.31	A	821.57	824.93	826.68
31	785.08	---	785.60	785.61	---	788.19	---	815.52	---	821.41	824.35	---
MAX	787.56	786.14	786.48	785.90	---	---	799.28	815.52	---	---	826.79	830.98
MIN	767.83	784.01	785.60	785.32	---	---	788.67	799.11	---	---	819.42	822.61

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027250 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW LAGO DOS BOCAS NEAR FLORIDA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'50", long 66°40'02", at pedestrian bridge, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) downstream from Lago Dos Bocas and 6.6 mi (10.6 km) west of Florida plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--169 mi² (436 km²) does not include 6.0 mi² (15.6 km²) above Lago Garzas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1970-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 28...	0930	E2000	213	7.6	26.5	1.8	4.0	49	<10	K40	K50
MAR 10...	1015	30	256	7.9	25.0	.80	5.5	67	<10	4400	<10
JUN 23...	0900	26	210	7.7	26.5	5.7	4.6	57	<10	270	K140
SEP 04...	0905	E1800	176	6.9	26.0	68	5.1	62	<10	2600	5600

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 28...	80	23	5.8	9.4	.5	2.1	71	<.5	11	9.2
MAR 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
JUN 23...	80	22	5.9	9.2	.4	2.4	74	--	13	10
SEP 04...	66	18	5.0	8.1	.4	2.6	62	<1.0	11	8.9

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 28...	<.10	21	123	E664	9	--	<.010	.810	.010	.30
MAR 10...	--	--	--	--	<1	.251	.029	.280	.110	.27
JUN 23...	<.10	18	125	8.93	6	--	<.010	.490	.050	--
SEP 04...	<.10	20	110	E535	62	.703	.017	.720	.080	.43

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 28...	.31	1.1	5.0	.060	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
MAR 10...	.38	.66	2.9	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 23...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	<10	<1	<1	<10
SEP 04...	.51	1.2	5.4	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'22", long 66°41'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Río Tanamá, 3.6 mi (5.8 km) south of Arecibo and 4.9 mi (7.9 km) above mouth, and 10.4 mi (16.7 km) downstream from Lago Dos Bocas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--174 mi² (451 km²), approximately, of which an undetermined amount does not contribute directly to surface runoff.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 30 ft (9 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Flow regulated by Lago Dos Bocas Dam 10.4 mi (16.7 km) upstream from gage. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	149	102	109	115	156	24	162	127	467	e52	168	526
2	77	155	172	134	79	27	92	101	273	e44	138	426
3	355	166	255	150	262	30	39	41	102	45	271	381
4	136	243	355	67	182	251	41	85	107	39	327	e222
5	111	220	301	54	101	366	36	50	350	35	325	351
6	147	229	114	52	460	71	34	69	418	48	301	e370
7	213	159	148	69	248	40	41	120	252	55	452	e410
8	187	83	162	172	164	37	232	84	322	160	306	e390
9	98	156	161	55	146	27	77	191	224	248	335	484
10	250	57	181	58	54	24	121	104	201	368	524	691
11	182	48	110	45	49	22	51	269	295	135	644	263
12	253	122	89	114	46	24	33	395	655	203	987	226
13	1290	191	74	107	43	24	142	146	573	294	646	410
14	659	120	124	48	43	23	240	45	236	220	557	483
15	646	59	88	116	41	25	83	37	315	92	547	468
16	475	128	167	198	78	25	156	30	294	297	391	663
17	420	349	155	113	299	22	128	124	92	296	409	426
18	694	221	142	48	108	27	158	315	89	146	454	420
19	398	111	86	44	60	27	139	166	169	311	267	667
20	351	274	73	38	248	28	224	693	117	270	266	748
21	386	93	154	47	361	27	194	1340	98	326	471	765
22	307	58	153	68	212	26	244	982	371	472	466	e7290
23	343	58	127	99	104	26	240	419	292	400	261	2680
24	335	182	196	210	70	26	301	341	84	416	444	1600
25	275	116	84	107	35	85	196	182	64	245	807	1080
26	259	122	67	42	123	41	176	305	56	96	735	834
27	350	58	63	138	41	65	43	304	344	95	737	638
28	381	55	101	85	27	37	168	121	95	101	633	530
29	400	93	68	286	---	121	61	204	90	204	666	738
30	191	62	81	387	---	107	160	92	e96	320	620	753
31	182	---	96	119	---	159	---	68	---	366	378	---
TOTAL	10500	4090	4256	3385	3840	1864	4012	7550	7141	6399	14533	25933
MEAN	339	136	137	109	137	60.1	134	244	238	206	469	864
MAX	1290	349	355	387	460	366	301	1340	655	472	987	7290
MIN	77	48	63	38	27	22	33	30	56	35	138	222
AC-FT	20830	8110	8440	6710	7620	3700	7960	14980	14160	12690	28830	51440
CFSM	1.95	.78	.79	.63	.79	.35	.77	1.40	1.37	1.19	2.69	4.97
IN.	2.24	.87	.91	.72	.82	.40	.86	1.61	1.53	1.37	3.11	5.54

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1982 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	584	500	277	240	223	208	329	547	333	243	259	527
MEAN	584	500	277	240	223	208	329	547	333	243	259	527
MAX	1984	1413	570	437	428	351	617	2000	683	374	474	1479
(WY)	1986	1986	1988	1988	1988	1985	1986	1986	1987	1987	1988	1996
MIN	171	123	72.4	83.5	61.3	60.1	65.7	178	69.3	62.7	82.8	99.9
(WY)	1995	1995	1995	1995	1995	1998	1995	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1982 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	77375	93503										
ANNUAL MEAN	212	256								355		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN										729		1986
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN										132		1994
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2730	Jan 22				7290	Sep 22		14800	May 18		1985
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	29	Jun 21				22	Mar 11		16	Apr 14		1994
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	39	Jun 24				24	Mar 11		22	Mar 30		1994
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW						Not determined	Sep 22		45800	May 18		1985
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE						15.87	Sep 22		18.22	May 18		1985
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	153500	185500							257400			
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.22	1.47							2.04			
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	16.54	19.99							27.74			
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	360	500							733			
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	181	159							232			
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	56	41							54			

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water year 1982 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October, 1995 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1995.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediments samples were collected by automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,510 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e84,900 tons (77,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.14 ton (0.013 tonne) March 24, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,510 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e84,900 tons (77,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.14 ton (0.013 tonne) March 24, 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	149	37	19	102	31	8.9	109	20	10			
2	77	17	3.8	155	36	21	172	21	12			
3	355	68	82	166	30	22	255	46	39			
4	136	35	16	243	55	44	355	58	64			
5	111	29	13	220	44	35	301	63	58			
6	147	24	16	229	46	38	114	32	10			
7	213	31	38	159	53	27	148	42	19			
8	187	33	32	83	23	5.3	162	45	24			
9	98	18	5.6	156	50	24	161	39	21			
10	250	41	49	57	39	6.0	181	45	25			
11	182	36	23	48	31	4.1	110	40	12			
12	253	41	47	122	36	19	89	50	12			
13	1290	88	315	191	40	25	74	30	6.1			
14	659	75	147	120	34	13	124	33	12			
15	646	78	137	59	20	3.6	88	17	4.0			
16	475	54	71	128	36	16	167	31	19			
17	420	79	116	349	60	74	155	29	16			
18	694	126	249	221	44	31	142	24	12			
19	398	74	98	111	28	10	86	12	2.7			
20	351	62	65	274	63	54	73	11	2.1			
21	386	56	64	93	27	7.5	154	38	19			
22	307	53	48	58	16	2.5	153	41	19			
23	343	61	65	58	12	2.4	127	34	13			
24	335	61	64	182	36	21	196	47	27			
25	275	53	47	116	25	10	84	26	5.9			
26	259	53	44	122	21	9.7	67	22	4.0			
27	350	64	72	58	10	1.5	63	20	3.4			
28	381	74	91	55	9	1.4	101	29	8.6			
29	400	53	69	93	14	4.3	68	19	3.5			
30	191	49	34	62	10	1.6	81	22	7.2			
31	182	47	27	---	---	---	96	30	8.8			
TOTAL	10500	---	2167.4	4090	---	542.8	4256	---	499.3			

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN			MEAN			MEAN		
		CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	
JANUARY										
1	115	33	12	156	25	17	24	5	.35	
2	134	37	16	79	21	5.1	27	10	.76	
3	150	39	20	262	37	68	30	18	1.4	
4	67	20	3.6	182	25	30	251	22	21	
5	54	18	2.7	101	8	2.3	366	19	23	
6	52	18	2.5	460	57	111	71	4	.79	
7	69	20	4.7	248	53	45	40	3	.36	
8	172	28	22	164	43	26	37	4	.35	
9	55	9	1.3	146	37	22	27	4	.28	
10	58	8	1.2	54	18	2.6	24	5	.31	
11	45	7	.84	49	16	2.1	22	10	.58	
12	114	24	14	46	15	1.8	24	19	1.3	
13	107	17	7.4	43	13	1.5	24	27	1.8	
14	48	5	.70	43	12	1.4	23	16	1.0	
15	116	21	11	41	11	1.2	25	9	.62	
16	198	41	30	78	18	6.1	25	7	.45	
17	113	31	13	299	42	44	22	8	.47	
18	48	16	2.1	108	17	5.1	27	9	.67	
19	44	15	1.8	60	17	2.8	27	7	.52	
20	38	14	1.5	248	53	45	28	6	.41	
21	47	15	2.7	361	20	23	27	4	.31	
22	68	21	4.3	212	9	5.5	26	3	.22	
23	99	25	11	104	8	2.2	26	2	.17	
24	210	45	32	70	7	1.4	26	2	.14	
25	107	30	11	35	7	.66	85	11	3.9	
26	42	15	1.8	123	12	6.2	41	3	.34	
27	138	27	20	41	7	.77	65	2	.45	
28	85	25	6.6	27	7	.52	37	2	.22	
29	286	49	82	---	---	---	121	31	14	
30	387	67	98	---	---	---	107	21	7.2	
31	119	19	9.1	---	---	---	159	28	24	
TOTAL	3385	---	446.84	3840	---	480.25	1864	---	107.37	
FEBRUARY										
MARCH										
APRIL										
1	162	28	19	127	8	3.3	467	58	110	
2	92	17	5.9	101	9	2.5	273	46	43	
3	39	10	1.1	41	7	.73	102	30	9.3	
4	41	10	1.1	85	7	2.3	107	29	12	
5	36	9	.92	50	8	1.1	350	81	125	
6	34	9	.84	69	9	5.0	418	86	116	
7	41	31	3.3	120	42	18	252	55	59	
8	232	26	20	84	28	11	322	66	73	
9	77	10	2.4	191	40	27	224	57	51	
10	121	22	16	104	23	8.6	201	52	36	
11	51	37	5.4	269	45	80	295	75	86	
12	33	20	1.8	395	50	84	655	121	300	
13	142	27	21	146	47	24	573	102	184	
14	240	31	49	45	16	1.9	236	106	70	
15	83	12	4.0	37	13	1.3	315	87	88	
16	156	40	18	30	11	.98	294	68	70	
17	128	36	16	124	79	26	92	12	3.4	
18	158	34	24	315	85	99	89	18	4.8	
19	139	34	19	166	38	24	169	34	23	
20	224	36	37	693	127	277	117	28	10	
21	194	33	32	1340	127	516	98	18	5.6	
22	244	40	45	982	265	691	371	44	79	
23	240	13	10	419	254	292	292	48	53	
24	301	10	13	341	214	214	84	8	1.8	
25	196	7	5.2	182	64	55	64	5	.89	
26	176	8	4.9	305	118	105	56	5	.68	
27	43	6	.67	304	62	65	344	45	77	
28	168	7	4.0	121	38	17	95	14	5.4	
29	61	8	1.3	204	79	58	90	12	4.4	
30	160	7	5.4	92	44	12	e96	10	e1.2	
31	---	---	---	68	23	4.1	---	---	---	
TOTAL	4012	---	387.23	7550	---	2726.81	7141	---	1702.47	
MAY										
JUNE										

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	e52	9	e.89	168	6	3.0	526	94	144
2	e44	8	e.71	138	4	1.5	426	69	90
3	45	8	.91	271	12	17	381	61	65
4	39	7	.73	327	37	47	e222	47	e33
5	35	6	.60	325	34	34	351	50	50
6	48	8	1.3	301	22	27	e370	86	e65
7	55	9	1.3	452	36	61	e410	95	e95
8	160	18	17	306	70	57	e390	104	e65
9	248	31	33	335	51	48	484	77	120
10	368	38	50	524	71	117	691	115	218
11	135	9	3.7	644	103	213	263	60	52
12	203	17	16	987	174	466	226	44	31
13	294	23	29	646	123	223	410	78	95
14	220	22	24	557	95	153	483	90	126
15	92	9	2.2	547	97	154	468	86	121
16	297	51	47	391	79	91	663	70	127
17	296	19	24	409	80	95	426	68	85
18	146	13	11	454	83	109	420	75	93
19	311	40	44	267	60	46	667	108	202
20	270	36	33	266	62	47	748	108	218
21	326	40	44	471	58	86	765	121	251
22	472	41	66	466	62	87	e7290	3510	e84900
23	400	50	69	261	60	47	2680	725	5710
24	416	37	59	444	77	103	1600	244	1060
25	245	10	10	807	133	294	1080	183	534
26	96	5	1.3	735	123	244	834	145	328
27	95	4	1.1	737	111	220	638	123	212
28	101	5	1.4	633	113	198	530	102	146
29	204	29	28	666	122	220	738	124	257
30	320	30	40	620	111	199	753	149	310
31	366	51	57	378	68	81	---	---	---
TOTAL	6399	---	717.14	14533	---	3788.5	25933	---	95803
YEAR	93503		109369.11						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
13...	0230	2120	124	710	88
FEB					
06...	2015	898	113	274	97
17...	1600	702	114	216	86
MAR					
04...	1815	620	85	142	92
JUN					
02...	1726	635	103	177	84
AUG					
07...	2100	845	78	178	95
13...	0640	466	146	184	100

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)
SEP 22...	0356	5750	7150	111000	47	65	81

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN 1.00 MM (70335)
SEP 22...	87	92	94	97	99	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'02", long 66°46'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on downstream side of left abutment of bridge on Highway 111, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from natural tunnel, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northeast of Angeles, and 5.8 mi (9.3 km) northwest of Utuado.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.4 mi² (47.7 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1944 to June 1958 (daily stage and two to four measurements per month by Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority), November 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 938.32 ft (286.000 m) above mean sea level. Datum of gage was increased by 3.00 ft (0.914 m) on Oct. 1978.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	53	46	23	15	10	15	e17	e14	33	36	34	e83
2	41	45	22	15	11	15	20	e15	36	37	33	e100
3	31	44	22	15	11	14	16	e16	35	36	34	e95
4	28	42	22	14	16	14	14	e26	37	36	33	e92
5	26	41	21	14	68	15	18	e40	168	36	34	78
6	28	40	20	16	24	16	13	e78	e190	43	34	82
7	106	40	20	24	21	19	e23	e88	e50	37	34	67
8	45	38	19	18	25	16	e31	e60	e40	33	34	59
9	31	37	19	14	31	14	e17	e53	e36	33	66	60
10	28	39	19	14	21	14	e16	29	e34	e50	121	51
11	44	60	18	13	20	13	e15	23	e140	e40	182	45
12	191	48	18	14	20	13	e14	21	e230	32	111	89
13	101	48	18	25	19	13	e13	20	e96	31	75	65
14	140	41	17	20	18	17	e19	19	e86	e60	64	56
15	109	67	17	15	22	24	e23	21	e47	84	57	51
16	95	42	17	14	19	19	e23	20	e49	89	57	63
17	136	35	17	14	18	28	e19	22	e76	51	66	57
18	108	32	17	16	17	25	e28	27	79	52	55	87
19	82	31	17	19	17	14	e50	124	52	41	51	60
20	73	30	17	14	16	13	e60	128	47	34	49	49
21	66	30	17	14	16	13	e27	380	e43	33	80	155
22	64	29	16	16	16	12	e24	117	36	33	58	3310
23	62	28	17	13	15	11	e23	73	36	34	52	375
24	59	29	19	12	16	12	e20	55	36	36	69	220
25	56	29	16	13	16	10	e19	47	52	34	129	152
26	54	33	16	11	20	11	e18	45	38	33	68	128
27	52	25	16	11	16	11	e17	40	47	32	91	113
28	50	24	16	11	15	11	e17	37	36	32	e187	106
29	49	25	16	11	---	44	e16	36	36	31	e95	184
30	47	24	15	10	---	86	e15	45	36	30	e86	120
31	46	---	16	10	---	e36	---	36	---	31	e90	---
TOTAL	2101	1122	560	455	554	588	645	1755	1957	1250	2229	6252
MEAN	67.8	37.4	18.1	14.7	19.8	19.0	21.5	56.6	65.2	40.3	71.9	208
MAX	191	67	23	25	68	86	60	380	230	89	187	3310
MIN	26	24	15	10	10	10	13	14	33	30	33	45
AC-FT	4170	2230	1110	902	1100	1170	1280	3480	3880	2480	4420	12400
CFSM	3.68	2.03	.98	.80	1.08	1.03	1.17	3.08	3.55	2.19	3.91	11.3
IN.	4.25	2.27	1.13	.92	1.12	1.19	1.30	3.55	3.96	2.53	4.51	12.64

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1960 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	79.8	67.1	41.9	29.6	26.0	24.8	35.6	56.8	42.6	35.8	46.2	77.7
MAX	195	159	121	71.0	50.8	71.2	143	193	116	65.7	110	208
(WY)	1990	1969	1966	1997	1996	1972	1969	1963	1979	1981	1979	1998
MIN	25.4	25.1	18.1	14.7	13.3	11.0	9.70	12.4	15.6	9.18	15.9	25.0
(WY)	1963	1995	1998	1998	1965	1984	1984	1977	1994	1994	1994	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1960 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	13416	19468										
ANNUAL MEAN	36.8	53.3								47.0		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN										71.1		1969
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN										20.7		1994
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN				251	Jan 22		3310	Sep 22		3310	Sep 22	1998
LOWEST DAILY MEAN				14	May 20		10	Jan 30		5.4	Aug 4	1994
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM				15	May 15		11	Jan 26		6.4	Jul 29	1994
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW							25500	Sep 22		25500	Sep 22	1998
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE							21.24	Sep 22		21.24	Sep 22	1998
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW							9.1	Mar 25		5.4	Aug 4	1994
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	26610	38610								34080		
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.00	2.90								2.56		
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	27.12	39.36								34.73		
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	62	91								83		
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	29	32								33		
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	16	14								16		

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RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--
SUSPENDED SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1968 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.--US D-49 SEDIMENT SAMPLER SINCE OCTOBER 1968.SEDIMENT PUMPING SAMPLER SINCE 1990

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean,20,400 mg/L November 27, 1968; minimum daily mean,<1 mg/L during water year 1985.
SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily,240,000 tons (218,000 tonnes) Sept. 22,1998, minimum daily, <0.01 ton (<0.01tonne) several days during many years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean,2,950 mg/L September 22, 1998; minimum daily mean,4 mg/L several days.
SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 240,000 tons (218,000 tonnes) September 22,1998; minimum daily,0.17 ton (0.15 tonne) several days.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT (HIGH SATUR-ATION) (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 23...	0935	62	164	7.8	23.0	2.0	8.2	98	<10	240	620
FEB 23...	1525	15	174	7.5	25.5	1.4	8.3	105	<10	K30	230
JUN 02...	1100	30	168	8.2	25.5	3.0	8.8	111	<10	K30	K120
SEP 04...	1300	87	148	6.8	24.7	52	7.8	94	<10	K11000	20000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 23...	74	21	5.5	7.3	.4	1.9	52	<.5	10	8.4
FEB 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	61	--	--	--
JUN 02...	62	15	5.8	8.4	.5	2.3	57	--	12	8.5
SEP 04...	53	14	4.8	6.8	.4	2.5	49	<1.0	8.0	7.3

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 23...	<.10	25	111	18.5	<1	--	<.010	1.10	.010	--
FEB 23...	--	--	--	--	1	--	<.010	.620	.010	--
JUN 02...	<.10	24	111	8.90	<1	--	<.010	.680	<.010	--
SEP 04...	<.10	23	96	22.3	64	1.08	.018	1.10	.040	.47

DATE	NITRO-GEN,AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 23...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	<10	<1	<1	<10
FEB 23...	<.20	--	--	<.020	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 02...	.23	.91	4.0	<.020	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
SEP 04...	.51	1.6	7.1	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE) (01045)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB) (01051)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN) (01055)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG) (71900)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS SE) (01147)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG) (01077)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN) (01092)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN) (00720)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L) (32730)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L) (38260)
OCT 23...	380	<1	30	<.10	<1	<1	<10	<.010	<1	<.02
FEB 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 02...	220	<1	18	<.10	<1	<1	<10	<.010	<1	<.02
SEP 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	53	183	56	46	31	3.8	23	38	2.4
2	41	108	12	45	28	3.3	22	36	2.1
3	31	72	6.1	44	23	2.7	22	34	2.0
4	28	57	4.2	42	19	2.1	22	32	1.9
5	26	50	3.6	41	15	1.7	21	31	1.7
6	28	58	4.9	40	11	1.2	20	27	1.5
7	106	683	704	40	8	.84	20	22	1.2
8	45	140	19	38	6	.65	19	18	.95
9	31	64	5.4	37	7	.68	19	15	.77
10	28	58	4.3	39	7	.78	19	13	.63
11	44	151	30	60	169	48	18	10	.51
12	191	928	1350	48	159	22	18	9	.41
13	101	476	134	48	166	24	18	7	.33
14	140	971	427	41	52	6.3	17	7	.32
15	109	421	137	67	431	141	17	10	.47
16	95	492	128	42	112	14	17	16	.72
17	136	1220	992	35	26	2.5	17	20	.92
18	108	260	85	32	23	1.9	17	15	.68
19	82	95	21	31	21	1.8	17	11	.48
20	73	53	11	30	20	1.6	17	8	.37
21	66	33	5.9	30	17	1.3	17	8	.36
22	64	23	3.9	29	13	1.0	16	8	.35
23	62	9	1.5	28	12	.89	17	9	.44
24	59	9	1.5	29	14	1.1	19	36	1.9
25	56	11	1.7	29	16	1.3	16	29	1.3
26	54	15	2.1	33	77	8.8	16	26	1.1
27	52	16	2.3	25	45	3.1	16	22	.95
28	50	11	1.6	24	41	2.6	16	19	.78
29	49	8	1.0	25	41	2.7	16	15	.63
30	47	15	1.9	24	40	2.6	15	10	.43
31	46	33	4.1	---	---	---	16	7	.30
TOTAL	2101	---	4162.0	1122	---	306.24	560	---	28.90

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	15	5	.21	10	9	.23	15	4	.17
2	15	5	.22	11	8	.23	15	4	.17
3	15	6	.23	11	7	.20	14	7	.28
4	14	6	.25	16	13	1.3	14	12	.46
5	14	8	.32	68	345	90	15	18	.74
6	16	11	.44	24	79	5.3	16	16	.70
7	24	39	3.7	21	53	3.0	19	13	.68
8	18	31	1.6	25	64	5.9	16	11	.49
9	14	13	.50	31	115	11	14	10	.37
10	14	7	.28	21	36	2.1	14	8	.31
11	13	7	.26	20	15	.79	13	7	.26
12	14	8	.29	20	8	.43	13	8	.27
13	25	63	4.5	19	6	.31	13	8	.28
14	20	75	4.1	18	6	.28	17	16	.84
15	15	71	2.8	22	5	.29	24	46	3.1
16	14	68	2.5	19	5	.25	19	32	1.7
17	14	63	2.4	18	5	.23	28	65	11
18	16	59	2.5	17	4	.21	25	60	5.5
19	19	50	2.7	17	4	.19	14	17	.64
20	14	26	1.0	16	4	.18	13	16	.57
21	14	18	.69	16	4	.18	13	14	.48
22	16	17	.78	16	4	.19	12	12	.37
23	13	8	.27	15	5	.19	11	10	.31
24	12	8	.27	16	5	.22	12	9	.29
25	13	8	.29	16	5	.22	10	9	.24
26	11	10	.30	20	5	.28	11	8	.24
27	11	11	.35	16	5	.21	11	9	.27
28	11	13	.36	15	5	.19	11	11	.31
29	11	12	.34	---	---	---	44	203	76
30	10	11	.30	---	---	---	86	522	203
31	10	9	.25	---	---	---	e36	119	e14
TOTAL	455	---	35.00	554	---	124.10	588	---	324.04
FEBRUARY									
MARCH									
APRIL									
MAY									
JUNE									
1	e17	28	e1.3	e14	7	e.28	33	53	4.7
2	20	35	2.1	e15	7	e.18	36	68	7.3
3	16	19	.82	e16	7	e.16	35	62	5.9
4	14	15	.55	e26	7	e2.9	37	106	12
5	18	16	.80	e40	7	e1.5	168	1080	1690
6	13	17	.62	e78	6	e79	e190	318	e2080
7	e23	16	e1.2	e88	6	e86	e50	106	e6.6
8	e31	15	e11	e60	1060	e55	e40	35	e1.5
9	e17	15	e1.3	s53	214	e55	e36	86	e7.3
10	e16	14	e.22	29	35	2.9	e34	89	e5.9
11	e15	14	e.17	23	18	1.2	e140	903	e129
12	e14	14	e.55	21	16	.91	e230	251	e2080
13	e13	13	e.62	20	13	.70	e96	183	e453
14	e19	13	e.48	19	9	.48	e86	134	e203
15	e23	12	e1.2	21	7	.38	e47	97	e3.4
16	e23	12	e1.2	20	5	.28	e49	71	e3.4
17	e19	12	e.48	22	26	1.9	e76	310	e15
18	e28	11	e2.9	27	108	11	79	481	172
19	e50	11	e6.6	124	1660	1060	52	156	23
20	e60	11	e15	128	987	522	47	51	6.5
21	e27	10	e2.9	380	1070	1780	e43	19	e2.0
22	e24	10	e3.1	117	221	80	36	14	1.4
23	e23	10	e1.2	73	76	15	36	12	1.1
24	e20	9	e2.1	55	44	6.6	36	10	.97
25	e19	9	e1.7	47	27	3.4	52	159	43
26	e18	9	e1.3	45	19	2.3	38	86	9.1
27	e17	8	e1.3	40	14	1.5	47	137	29
28	e17	8	e1.3	37	10	1.0	36	60	5.8
29	e16	8	e.49	36	10	.96	36	28	2.7
30	e15	8	e.18	45	87	14	36	16	1.5
31	---	---	---	36	61	6.0	---	---	---
TOTAL	645	---	64.68	1755	---	3792.53	1957	---	7006.07

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	36	15	1.4	34	20	1.8	e83	179	e40
2	37	31	3.8	33	30	2.7	e100	563	e205
3	36	57	5.6	34	69	6.2	e95	421	e108
4	36	28	2.6	33	159	14	e92	490	e128
5	36	17	1.7	34	277	25	78	501	107
6	43	497	90	34	237	22	82	231	49
7	37	91	9.0	34	195	18	67	84	15
8	33	68	6.2	34	141	13	59	37	6.0
9	33	54	4.8	66	741	378	60	141	27
10	e50	87	e29	121	665	786	51	63	8.8
11	e40	91	e17	182	1980	2080	45	25	3.0
12	32	35	3.0	111	551	173	89	345	224
13	31	32	2.7	75	155	32	65	129	23
14	e60	62	e35	64	56	9.7	56	37	5.6
15	84	1200	876	57	40	6.1	51	33	4.5
16	89	564	239	57	30	4.6	63	117	26
17	51	194	29	66	140	35	57	128	22
18	52	848	320	55	82	12	87	361	120
19	41	131	17	51	41	5.7	60	106	18
20	34	62	5.8	49	22	2.9	49	34	4.5
21	33	36	3.3	80	294	67	155	1710	3930
22	33	33	2.9	58	55	8.8	3310	2950	240000
23	34	30	2.7	52	18	2.5	375	2610	3080
24	36	28	2.7	69	182	80	220	156	99.8
25	34	25	2.3	129	1610	811	152	50	21
26	33	23	2.1	68	50	9.6	128	42	15
27	32	21	1.8	91	796	453	113	36	11
28	32	17	1.5	e187	2200	e3450	106	35	10
29	31	14	1.2	e95	449	e116	184	991	1130
30	30	13	1.0	e86	323	e75	120	166	56
31	31	16	1.3	e90	232	e56	---	---	---
TOTAL	1250	---	1721.4	2229	---	8756.6	6252	---	249497.2
YEAR	19468		275818.96						

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WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT			
		DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
18...	0715	113	187	57	76
MAY					
07...	1035	3.1	188	1.6	94
08...	1841	314	2510	2130	93
19...	1635	359	3510	3400	93
20...	2145	372	1600	1610	83
JUN					
11...	1825	453	1980	2420	92
JUL					
06...	1758	128	2220	767	76
AUG					
10...	1754	535	2450	3540	93
SEP					
02...	1722	236	1920	1220	86

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)	
MAY								
08...	1631	1530	7660	31600	33	43	57	
21...	1615	625	3850	6500	32	44	58	
JUN								
11...	1640	1620	12000	52400	38	49	60	
SEP								
02...	1730	356	1650	1590	27	38	55	
DATE		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN 1.00 MM (70335)
MAY								
08...	69	79	82	92	98	99	100	
21...	71	82	85	92	96	99	100	
JUN								
11...	69	77	79	89	96	99	100	
SEP								
02...	65	81	83	94	98	100	100	

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028400 RIO TANAMA AT CHARCO HONDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'52", long 66°42'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010002 on right bank near to an abandoned power house at Charco Hondo, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) upstream from mouth, and 4 mi (6 km) south of Arecibo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--57.6 mi² (149.2 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1969 to June 1971, October 1981 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 60 ft (18 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Diversion 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream for municipal supply of Arecibo. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	91	71	49	38	32	30	45	30	66	52	134	229
2	125	71	46	39	32	30	40	28	50	50	71	198
3	105	68	45	39	32	29	e35	29	64	57	82	197
4	79	68	44	38	32	29	31	30	75	54	66	174
5	77	66	44	38	88	34	35	34	150	49	103	160
6	77	65	43	39	48	33	30	83	172	86	64	161
7	125	63	e42	43	37	41	28	164	88	104	156	205
8	152	64	e42	51	36	36	63	125	71	60	146	176
9	89	61	42	37	51	31	37	120	64	53	206	152
10	79	62	e42	36	38	29	32	55	69	64	257	122
11	90	71	43	36	35	27	30	43	231	100	328	102
12	148	81	42	36	35	27	29	38	214	56	349	144
13	291	61	41	46	33	27	29	36	128	53	228	159
14	665	58	41	49	33	28	28	36	112	77	161	132
15	367	69	41	39	36	36	27	34	81	117	137	101
16	237	80	41	36	34	38	46	35	86	249	145	105
17	171	54	40	36	33	33	45	34	133	292	152	113
18	205	52	41	44	32	45	37	e40	151	166	116	205
19	146	50	41	45	36	27	66	e72	122	120	94	189
20	126	48	40	39	31	25	123	e221	79	94	86	124
21	112	e47	40	39	31	25	67	e254	70	80	157	488
22	104	47	43	39	30	24	46	e527	72	69	144	e6400
23	97	46	44	36	30	23	49	167	63	76	96	e1500
24	92	46	47	35	29	24	42	126	58	125	88	e350
25	87	e46	42	35	30	24	39	83	65	89	272	e280
26	84	e52	41	35	34	24	35	96	86	63	124	e240
27	81	51	41	35	32	24	35	110	80	69	140	e220
28	78	46	40	33	32	24	34	70	98	71	434	e210
29	76	48	40	33	---	39	33	57	61	58	330	e360
30	74	63	e86	33	---	180	30	64	55	61	175	e240
31	72	---	39	33	---	90	---	92	---	130	175	---
TOTAL	4402	1775	1353	1190	1012	1136	1246	2933	2914	2844	5216	13436
MEAN	142	59.2	43.6	38.4	36.1	36.6	41.5	94.6	97.1	91.7	168	448
MAX	665	81	86	51	88	180	123	527	231	292	434	6400
MIN	72	46	39	33	29	23	27	28	50	49	64	101
AC-FT	8730	3520	2680	2360	2010	2250	2470	5820	5780	5640	10350	26650
CFSM	6.40	2.67	1.97	1.73	1.63	1.65	1.87	4.26	4.38	4.13	7.58	20.2
IN.	7.38	2.97	2.27	1.99	1.70	1.90	2.09	4.91	4.88	4.77	8.74	22.51

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	
MEAN	162	131	78.4	59.5	50.1	42.6	65.6	126	88.7	65.3	81.0	141										
MAX	335	260	219	167	106	70.0	141	371	196	120	168	448										
(WY)	1990	1982	1982	1997	1996	1971	1986	1986	1995	1969	1998	1998										
MIN	72.1	50.4	36.4	22.3	16.8	16.6	25.9	15.8	23.3	22.0	35.1	44.9										
(WY)	1983	1995	1989	1989	1989	1988	1989	1989	1989	1989	1994	1994										

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	28311	39457	
ANNUAL MEAN	77.6	108	89.1
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			124
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			46.9
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	665	Oct 14	6400
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	33	May 1	23
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	34	May 14	24
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			Not determined
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			Not determined
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	56150	78260	64510
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.49	4.87	4.01
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	47.44	66.12	54.50
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	127	184	176
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	61	58	65
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	38	31	29

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50028400 RIO TANAMA AT CHARCO HONDO, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50029000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO AT CENTRAL CAMBALACHE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'20", long 66°42'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, at bridge on unimproved road, about 500 ft (152 m) upstream from Central Cambalache, near Highway 2, 13.9 mi (22.4 km) downstream from Dos Bocas Reservoir, 1.9 mi (3.1 km) downstream from Río Tanamá, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) southeast of Arecibo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--200 mi² (520 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to January 1965 (monthly measurements only), February 1965 to April 1969 (occasional measurements only), May 1969 to September 1983, October 1996 to September 1997.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 3.73 ft (1.14 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Flow regulated by Lago Dos Bocas dam, 13.9 mi (22.4 km) upstream. The mean daily discharge for September 22, 1998 is not available ,because there not rating definition above 13.0 ft; gage-height peak for September 21, 1998 was 17.0 ft. Gage-height satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	272	151	119	132	209	82	291	223	639	e110	303	927
2	187	241	183	160	140	82	172	181	453	e109	205	1020
3	462	218	286	196	307	80	85	102	236	127	445	1380
4	247	353	435	91	306	326	75	159	240	117	494	983
5	160	316	392	78	209	590	71	114	525	108	499	1280
6	237	328	136	73	564	175	65	118	625	122	434	1340
7	273	273	172	96	355	108	72	308	454	181	e729	1510
8	353	140	185	265	247	107	339	196	481	272	516	1400
9	172	249	198	96	239	91	158	363	392	415	578	868
10	334	119	199	95	96	83	197	241	340	612	875	1280
11	276	114	122	79	85	79	112	362	439	292	1120	516
12	379	201	86	164	78	74	74	593	941	362	1940	430
13	1840	297	70	169	78	69	220	290	862	475	1050	720
14	966	216	116	106	e76	61	327	118	435	428	855	847
15	912	118	82	138	e70	69	168	101	465	231	832	825
16	742	231	170	289	e121	78	266	91	495	522	584	1150
17	607	456	159	214	e494	69	227	240	255	566	590	756
18	975	302	135	105	e187	90	255	463	255	323	748	739
19	599	164	80	104	e135	72	233	334	342	567	427	1180
20	531	336	62	90	e407	63	379	960	239	499	355	1310
21	557	146	149	87	513	60	355	1940	199	577	778	1360
22	451	90	149	126	385	59	363	2330	494	825	792	---
23	498	84	115	145	205	64	393	786	457	719	435	9390
24	495	214	206	299	149	61	435	618	187	731	704	5500
25	383	143	87	172	91	123	285	394	154	483	1510	3630
26	384	160	74	85	224	68	314	442	174	192	1310	2780
27	477	90	69	187	113	91	106	514	470	185	1320	e2190
28	529	80	113	151	88	56	259	248	194	1120	1870	1870
29	554	104	87	335	---	197	133	341	193	341	1140	2600
30	325	93	90	541	---	266	257	222	e171	516	1130	2800
31	271	---	131	199	---	280	---	214	---	615	636	---
TOTAL	15448	6027	4657	5067	6171	3773	6686	13617	11860	11816	24454	---
MEAN	498	201	150	163	220	122	223	439	395	381	789	---
MAX	1840	456	435	541	564	590	435	2330	941	825	1940	---
MIN	160	80	62	73	70	56	65	91	154	108	205	---
AC-FT	30640	11950	9240	10050	12240	7480	13260	27010	23520	23440	48500	---
CFSM	2.49	1.00	.75	.82	1.10	.61	1.11	2.20	1.98	1.91	3.94	---
IN.	2.87	1.12	.87	.94	1.15	.70	1.24	2.53	2.21	2.20	4.55	---

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	
MEAN	792	720	515	353	297	315	377	556	454	381	442	704																			
MAX	1577	1388	1327	651	425	627	641	1192	1220	854	1269	1866																			
(WY)	1971	1978	1982	1997	1997	1972	1983	1980	1979	1979	1979	1979																			
MIN	404	201	150	155	152	122	196	188	139	189	218	271																			
(WY)	1983	1998	1998	1973	1974	1998	1975	1977	1977	1997	1974	1997																			

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	114972	
ANNUAL MEAN	315	501
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN		691
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN		290
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	4120	Jan 22
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	56	Mar 28
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	93	Dec 25
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	Not determined	Sep 22
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	19.28	Sep 22
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		50
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	228000	363100
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.57	2.51
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	21.38	34.05
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	518	962
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	272	351
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	100	133

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50029000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO AT CENTRAL CAMBALACHE, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50029000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO AT CENTRAL CAMBALACHE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'20", long 66°42'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, at bridge on unimproved road, about 500 ft (152 m) upstream from Central Cambalache, near Highway 2, 8.3 mi (13.4 km) downstream from Dos Bocas Reservoir, 1.9 mi (3.1 km) downstream from Rio Tanama, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) southeast of Arecibo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--200 mi² (520 km²), approximately.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1963-66, 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATUR-ATION (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
NOV 06...	1030	194	254	7.5	25.5	7.6	7.5	90	<10	210	K160
FEB 27...	0945	101	281	7.7	24.0	3.4	7.9	93	<10	500	270
JUN 23...	1120	214	273	8.0	28.0	10	6.8	86	<10	390	240
SEP 14...	1230	E500	254	7.4	26.5	27	7.1	88	<5	3000	2500

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 06...	96	28	7.0	11	.5	1.7	98	<.5	6.1	11
FEB 27...	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
JUN 23...	110	34	5.6	8.8	.4	2.1	100	--	14	10
SEP 14...	110	35	4.9	8.0	.3	2.0	100	<1.0	11	9.3

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 06...	<.10	29	148	77.5	1	.704	.016	.720	.020	--
FEB 27...	--	--	--	--	5	.426	.014	.440	.030	--
JUN 23...	<.10	15	150	87.0	11	--	<.010	.630	.040	--
SEP 14...	<.10	16	146	E197	3	.844	.016	.860	.030	.21

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 06...	<.20	--	--	.030	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
FEB 27...	<.20	--	--	<.020	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 23...	<.20	--	--	.060	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
SEP 14...	.24	1.1	4.9	.060	--	--	--	--	--	--

Figure 14. Río Grande de Manatí basin.

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50030460 RIO OROCOVIS AT OROCOVIS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'25", long 66°23'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on right bank, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) south of junction of Highways 155 and 156 in Orocovis, 2.1 mi (3.38 km) upstream from Río Botijas, and 250 ft (76 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 599.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.03 mi² (13.03 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1981 to September 1982, October 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 500 ft (152 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Low flow affected by diversions for water supply. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1.1	.88	.56	e.41	.35	e.59	.89	.61	3.9	1.2	1.3	1.5
2	2.2	.77	.56	e.38	.33	e.56	.76	.73	3.8	1.3	1.1	67
3	1.7	.82	.80	e.41	.35	e.54	.64	.70	3.4	1.5	1.0	49
4	3.0	.94	1.2	e.50	23	e.57	.68	.55	3.7	1.7	1.0	30
5	3.2	.83	.67	e1.1	162	e.80	.81	.42	3.3	1.9	1.2	11
6	2.1	.85	.51	e11	e22	.98	.60	.58	2.7	2.5	4.9	11
7	11	.82	.49	e4.3	e2.9	1.0	1.1	.65	2.3	3.0	11	55
8	10	.76	.45	e2.5	e37	1.0	1.2	40	2.5	3.0	2.5	29
9	4.3	.78	.48	e2.0	e30	1.0	.74	14	2.5	2.1	2.0	11
10	1.3	5.5	.47	e3.0	e2.9	.84	.68	3.1	2.5	1.7	1.8	6.4
11	2.7	.97	.47	e1.2	e1.2	.70	.89	1.5	2.2	1.7	1.6	8.4
12	3.3	.85	.50	e1.4	e.82	.58	128	.62	7.4	1.7	2.0	5.2
13	4.1	.78	e.46	e2.5	e.60	.55	34	10	3.7	1.7	1.5	5.4
14	98	.77	e.48	e2.9	e.69	.60	6.1	219	2.0	1.8	1.2	10
15	51	.75	e.45	e1.1	e1.1	.68	2.3	110	1.5	1.9	1.2	7.9
16	28	.75	e.48	e.85	e.79	.68	1.7	21	1.5	1.5	1.7	4.7
17	60	.77	e.46	e.70	e.70	.60	1.0	10	1.9	1.4	1.8	3.6
18	30	.76	e.47	e.63	e.71	.71	1.4	56	1.7	1.5	1.6	4.5
19	9.7	.76	e.48	e.57	e.67	.79	2.3	31	1.5	1.4	1.5	4.3
20	4.1	.78	e.61	e.56	e.66	.74	1.7	23	1.3	1.8	1.2	5.8
21	2.2	.77	e.58	e.51	e.65	.70	2.4	99	1.3	1.9	5.9	e575
22	1.4	.71	e.49	e.48	e.65	.60	4.0	53	2.2	1.8	16	e1130
23	1.3	.74	e.48	e.46	e.81	.70	6.1	18	1.0	1.4	11	e158
24	1.2	1.1	e.48	e.43	e.58	.61	1.9	12	1.4	1.4	50	e71
25	1.5	.62	e.45	e.42	e.56	.65	1.3	10	1.0	1.2	124	e48
26	1.2	.65	e.55	e.41	e.67	.49	1.1	9.2	.91	1.3	10	e37
27	.85	.66	e.45	e.44	e.60	.70	.86	9.2	.85	1.8	3.1	e31
28	.87	.61	e.44	.41	e.67	.63	.64	6.5	.96	1.4	1.9	e28
29	.84	.61	e.46	.56	---	5.5	.56	5.4	1.1	1.1	1.6	e48
30	.83	.57	e.45	.44	---	2.0	.62	4.7	1.2	1.5	1.2	e33
31	.85	---	e.44	.33	---	1.2	---	4.6	---	1.2	1.4	---
TOTAL	343.84	27.93	16.32	42.90	293.96	28.29	206.97	775.06	67.22	52.3	269.2	2489.7
MEAN	11.1	.93	.53	1.38	10.5	.91	6.90	25.0	2.24	1.69	8.68	83.0
MAX	98	5.5	1.2	11	162	5.5	128	219	7.4	3.0	124	1130
MIN	.83	.57	.44	.33	.33	.49	.56	.42	.85	1.1	1.0	1.5
AC-FT	682	55	32	85	583	56	411	1540	133	104	534	4940
CFSM	2.21	.19	.10	.28	2.09	.18	1.37	4.97	.45	.34	1.73	16.5
IN.	2.54	.21	.12	.32	2.17	.21	1.53	5.73	.50	.39	1.99	18.41

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1981 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	15.8	6.37	4.74	6.08	4.15	1.73	5.38	14.9	4.20	3.40	4.08	24.8						
MAX	58.0	15.2	15.8	34.3	15.7	3.07	21.0	45.9	15.2	9.07	12.3	83.0						
(WY)	1990	1991	1982	1992	1996	1996	1993	1995	1992	1996	1989	1998						
MIN	1.95	.93	.53	.77	.96	.90	.93	.86	.88	.88	1.03	.88						
(WY)	1994	1998	1998	1995	1995	1994	1995	1997	1994	1994	1982	1994						

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1981 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	1043.62	4613.69	
ANNUAL MEAN	2.86	12.6	7.89
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			12.6
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			1.49
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	98	Oct 14	1130
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.23	Jul 10	.33
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.40	Jun 16	.40
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			6930
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			16.06
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	2070		9150
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.57		2.51
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	7.72		34.12
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.8		22
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.1		1.2
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.48		.49

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN
50030460 RIO OROCOVIS AT OROCOVIS, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50030700 RIO OROCOVIS NEAR OROCOVIS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'20", long 66°22'58", at flat low bridge about 300 ft (91 m) northwest of Highway 568, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) north of Orocovis plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--10.1 mi² (26.2 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 15...	1430	44	225	7.4	23.5	27	7.6	95	<10	6000	33000
FEB 19...	0930	5.9	356	7.9	20.5	1.6	8.1	94	<10	320	K170
JUN 16...	1030	8.0	313	8.1	26.0	4.0	7.4	97	<10	290	360
SEP 01...	0815	5.8	333	7.9	24.5	1.1	7.5	95	<10	K620	400

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 15...	82	19	8.3	10	.5	1.9	66	<.5	13	17
FEB 19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
JUN 16...	130	31	12	13	.5	2.2	130	--	8.3	15
SEP 01...	140	35	12	14	.5	8.3	140	<1.0	8.4	17

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 15...	.10	26	134	16.0	31	.650	.110	.750	.260	.34
FEB 19...	--	--	--	--	<1	.680	.050	.730	.110	--
JUN 16...	<.10	33	193	4.18	2	--	<.010	.920	.020	--
SEP 01...	.11	33	213	3.32	3	--	<.010	.750	.020	--

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 15...	.59	1.3	6.0	.230	<1	<100	20	<1	3	<10
FEB 19...	<.20	--	--	.110	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 16...	<.20	--	--	.120	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
SEP 01...	<.20	--	--	.120	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50031200 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI NEAR MOROVIS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'45", long 66°24'47", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on right bank , 0.1 mi (0.2 km) downstream from Quebrada Perchas, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream from Río Sana Muerto, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) south of Morovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--55.2 mi² (143.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1965 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Elevation of gage is 440 ft (134 m), from topographic map. Feb. 2, 1966 to Apr. 27, 1967, staff gage read twice daily.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Public water-supply pumpage, about 300 ft (91 m) above the station, influences low-flow discharges. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	10	e16	13	9.4	6.1	12	e37	e17	48	24	16	e17
2	10	e15	14	10	6.2	11	22	e16	44	25	16	e77
3	31	e15	14	11	8.6	12	e17	e16	96	58	16	e89
4	13	e15	13	9.7	41	12	e13	e17	63	46	16	e73
5	10	e15	13	11	633	11	13	e16	51	31	16	e43
6	8.9	e16	13	38	131	12	12	e22	41	32	18	e38
7	86	e15	13	e39	54	12	11	e14	37	34	33	e55
8	129	e14	11	e15	105	13	16	e21	36	25	e25	e51
9	138	e14	10	e12	264	11	12	e27	35	25	e21	e34
10	47	e20	11	e10	93	11	9.8	e20	37	25	e18	e29
11	25	44	11	e15	52	10	9.2	33	30	26	e19	33
12	47	35	10	e35	36	9.6	157	23	28	22	e18	56
13	69	19	10	e15	28	9.8	166	20	43	22	e17	39
14	235	16	10	e28	22	9.4	76	1070	33	20	e16	40
15	e160	15	9.8	e25	27	9.8	37	780	27	23	e16	37
16	e130	15	9.8	e15	21	10	81	170	27	20	e17	26
17	e160	17	9.6	e10	17	e7.4	40	122	53	20	e17	22
18	e220	16	10	e9.0	18	e6.9	44	79	e58	21	e19	24
19	e110	16	13	e23	15	e8.4	e154	183	e39	21	e18	32
20	e70	15	10	e22	15	9.4	76	220	34	21	e20	28
21	e45	14	9.7	e15	15	20	56	254	33	48	e24	1530
22	e35	13	9.7	e17	14	14	36	224	45	23	e25	7010
23	e30	13	9.8	e13	13	11	35	132	37	19	e22	540
24	e25	14	10	e10	12	11	38	99	37	20	e89	254
25	e23	14	10	e9.0	11	8.1	25	77	35	19	e27	216
26	e21	13	9.5	e8.0	14	8.5	29	68	31	18	e21	184
27	e20	14	9.7	e7.0	14	7.8	34	84	29	57	e21	175
28	e18	13	9.2	6.6	14	9.2	e28	67	27	27	e19	179
29	e18	12	8.7	6.3	---	10	e21	55	26	20	28	436
30	e16	13	8.7	6.2	---	e120	e18	58	25	19	23	302
31	e16	---	8.8	6.9	---	e150	---	73	---	19	19	---
TOTAL	1975.9	496	332.0	467.1	1699.9	577.3	1323.0	4077	1185	830	690	11669
MEAN	63.7	16.5	10.7	15.1	60.7	18.6	44.1	132	39.5	26.8	22.3	389
MAX	235	44	14	39	633	150	166	1070	96	58	89	7010
MIN	8.9	12	8.7	6.2	6.1	6.9	9.2	14	25	18	16	17
AC-FT	3920	984	659	926	3370	1150	2620	8090	2350	1650	1370	23150
CFSM	1.15	.30	.19	.27	1.10	.34	.80	2.38	.72	.49	.40	7.05
IN.	1.33	.33	.22	.31	1.15	.39	.89	2.75	.80	.56	.46	7.86

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1965 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998					
MEAN	149	139	105	80.1	63.4	63.1	105	157	59.6	44.7	52.9	109																											
MAX	1037	491	522	228	179	226	412	915	173	157	435	432																											
(WY)	1971	1971	1966	1997	1969	1972	1969	1985	1987	1979	1979	1996																											
MIN	24.0	11.4	8.65	10.4	15.3	12.7	8.80	15.7	6.75	5.54	9.70	6.87																											
(WY)	1978	1995	1995	1995	1994	1984	1995	1994	1994	1994	1984	1994																											

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1998 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1965 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	18105.5	25322.2	
ANNUAL MEAN	49.6	69.4	93.8
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			248
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			24.2
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2100	Jan 22	7010
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	7.2	Sep 18	6.1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	7.7	Sep 15	6.5
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			32700
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			15.65
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	35910	50230	67960
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.90	1.26	1.70
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	12.20	17.06	23.09
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	88	101	169
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	23	20	47
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.7	9.8	20

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN
50031200 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI NEAR MOROVIS, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50031200 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI NEAR MOROVIS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1968 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 15...	1030	149	240	8.0	25.0	58	8.5	105	<10	6000	5500
FEB 19...	1115	14	321	7.9	24.5	3.8	7.9	97	<10	K130	K72
JUN 16...	1330	27	284	8.4	31.0	.45	8.7	120	<10	<10	<10
SEP 01...	1010	18	290	7.8	28.5	1.3	7.9	104	<10	K27	K100

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 15...	88	22	8.4	11	.5	2.9	66	<.5	14	19
FEB 19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
JUN 16...	110	27	12	13	.5	2.9	110	--	8.6	16
SEP 01...	120	28	11	14	.5	2.6	110	<1.0	10	17

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 15...	.12	24	141	56.7	58	.390	.060	.460	.170	.20
FEB 19...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<.010	.580	<.010	--
JUN 16...	.13	17	162	11.7	<1	--	<.010	.220	.020	--
SEP 01...	.13	26	175	8.31	2	--	<.010	.510	.030	--

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 15...	.37	.83	3.7	.060	<1	<100	20	<1	5	<10
FEB 19...	<.20	--	--	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 16...	<.20	--	--	.020	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
SEP 01...	<.20	--	--	.070	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50032290 LAGO EL GUINEO AT DAMSITE NEAR VILLALBA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'41", long 66°31'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, at damsite on Río Toro Negro, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northwest from Villalba plaza and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) northeast of Cerro Maravillas. The reservoir itself fixes the territorial limits between the Municipality of Ciales and Orocovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.64 mi² (4.25 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1988 to current year. Prior to October 1994, published as Lago El Guineo at Damsite.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago El Guineo was completed in 1931. It provides a maximum storage of approximately 2,180 ac-ft (2.688 hm³) for power and irrigation. Waters are discharged through an outlet power tunnel into the Río Toro Negro and conveyed to the head water works of Toro Negro Hydroelectric Plant No.2, for energy generation at Toro Negro Hydroelectric plant No.1, and are discharged into the Guayabal Reservoir to be later used for irrigation at South Coast Irrigation System. The dam is rockfill with a vertical concrete corewall, rock toes, and riprap facing of upstream slope, with a total length of 565 ft (172 m), a maximum structural height of 125 ft (38 m) to top of corewall. At a maximum reservoir water surface elevation the uncontrolled morning-glory tunnel spillway crest has an elevation of 2,960 ft (902 m) above mean sea level and a design capacity of 7,000 ft³/s. The dam is owned by Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 2,964.40 ft (903.55 m), Sept. 22, 1998; minimum elevation, 2,919.79 ft (899.95 m), May 27, 1988.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 2,964.40 ft (903.55 m), Sept. 22; minimum elevation, 2,939.48 ft (895.95 m), Oct. 1.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
2,872	0	2,950	1,308
2,919	361	2,961	1,852
2,925	491	2,966	2,180
2,943	1,029		

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2939.70	2949.92	2953.22	2952.61	2952.64	2955.12	2959.46	2960.68	2960.71	2960.66	2960.64	A
2	2939.85	2950.07	2953.32	2952.66	2952.69	2955.19	2959.58	2960.68	2960.71	2960.70	2960.71	A
3	2939.98	2950.22	2953.27	2952.71	2952.55	2955.36	A	2960.68	2960.71	2960.71	2960.54	A
4	2940.07	2950.15	2953.23	2952.77	2952.97	2955.43	2959.80	2960.68	2960.74	2960.71	2960.35	2959.60
5	2940.11	2950.08	2953.32	2952.81	2953.66	2955.49	2959.97	2960.68	2960.81	2960.69	2960.16	2959.39
6	2940.18	2949.48	2953.39	2952.86	2953.18	2955.56	2960.06	2960.70	2960.72	2960.74	A	2959.91
7	2941.08	2949.41	2953.47	2952.95	2953.29	2955.71	A	2960.70	2960.70	2960.69	2960.70	2960.51
8	2941.33	2949.54	2953.55	2952.89	2953.95	2955.79	A	2960.79	2960.71	2960.69	2960.78	2959.77
9	2941.52	2950.20	2953.53	2952.75	2952.87	2955.84	2960.71	2960.70	2960.71	2960.49	2960.74	2958.42
10	2941.69	2950.49	2953.60	2952.79	2953.48	2955.89	2960.70	2960.69	2960.58	2960.41	2960.63	2957.06
11	2941.87	2950.65	2953.58	2952.94	2953.60	2955.94	2960.82	2960.69	2960.40	2960.49	2960.67	2955.84
12	2942.25	2950.79	2953.64	2953.02	2953.69	2956.00	2960.80	2960.70	2960.36	2960.56	2960.63	2955.36
13	2944.01	2950.91	2953.71	2952.67	2953.76	2956.04	2960.72	2960.77	2960.52	2960.54	2960.56	2955.32
14	2946.56	2950.83	2953.79	2952.71	2953.97	2956.46	2960.71	2960.96	2960.66	2960.91	2960.59	2954.13
15	2947.48	2951.74	2953.82	2952.64	2954.08	2957.01	2960.70	2960.76	2960.50	2960.68	2960.69	2953.87
16	2947.30	2951.93	2953.45	2952.68	2954.18	2957.16	2960.70	2960.72	2960.40	2960.83	2960.72	2953.99
17	2953.36	2952.08	2952.86	2952.72	2954.26	2957.24	2960.69	2960.71	2960.67	2960.82	2960.64	2953.87
18	2954.38	2952.03	2952.50	2953.03	2954.33	2957.30	2960.73	2960.71	A	2960.81	2960.57	2952.98
19	2954.94	2952.16	2952.26	2953.18	2954.39	2957.37	2960.70	2960.70	2960.50	2960.79	2960.43	2951.64
20	2954.37	2952.10	2952.05	2953.25	2954.47	2957.56	2960.84	2960.85	2960.69	2960.77	2960.28	2951.07
21	2953.74	2952.22	2952.15	2953.31	2954.54	2957.68	2960.71	2960.78	2960.73	2960.72	2960.37	2962.62
22	2953.05	2952.34	2952.21	2952.63	2954.61	2957.81	2960.69	2960.72	2960.55	2960.72	2960.75	A
23	2952.25	2952.45	2952.28	2952.67	2954.65	2957.92	2960.75	2960.71	2960.61	2960.55	2960.70	A
24	2951.45	2952.55	2952.25	2952.74	2954.78	2958.00	2960.83	2960.71	2960.69	2960.49	A	A
25	2951.68	2952.50	2952.31	2952.79	2954.87	2958.16	2960.72	2960.71	2960.69	2960.61	A	A
26	2951.88	2952.64	2952.37	2952.69	2954.93	2958.26	2960.70	2960.72	2960.69	2960.68	A	2962.30
27	2951.37	2952.74	2952.44	2952.53	2954.99	2958.40	2960.70	2960.71	2960.69	2960.69	A	A
28	2950.50	2952.84	2952.50	2952.57	2955.05	2958.49	2960.70	2960.71	2960.69	2960.69	A	2958.28
29	2949.60	2953.01	2952.55	2952.61	---	2958.68	2960.68	2960.70	2960.61	2960.59	A	2957.08
30	2949.61	2953.12	2952.55	2952.57	---	2959.12	2960.68	2960.72	2960.67	2960.48	A	2955.78
31	2949.76	---	2952.56	2952.60	---	2959.32	---	2960.70	---	2960.45	A	---
MAX	2954.94	2953.12	2953.82	2953.31	2955.05	2959.32	---	2960.96	---	2960.91	---	---
MIN	2939.70	2949.41	2952.05	2952.53	2952.55	2955.12	---	2960.68	---	2960.41	---	---

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50032590 LAGO DE MATRULLAS AT DAMSITE NEAR OROCOVIS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'46", long 66°28'50", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, in shelter house at damsite, and 5.8 mi (9.3 km) southwest of Orocovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.46 mi² (11.55 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1988 to current year. Prior to October 1994, published as Lago de Matrullas at Dam site.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Matrullas was completed in 1934. The dam is an earthfill structure about 120 ft (37 m) height, a top width of 30 ft (9 m) and a length of 710 ft (216 m), and has a maximum storage capacity of about 4,274 ac-ft (5.220 hm³) at top of dam elevation. The Matrullas Dam is owned by the Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority and is part of the Toro Negro Hydroelectric Project; a project developed by the P.R.E.P.A. for the primary purpose of generating electric power. Discharges from the Power Plants are collected by the Jacaguas River which flows into Guayabal Dam, at which dam they are regulated for irrigation of lands served by the Juana Díaz Canal. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 2,419.90 ft (737.58 m), Sept. 10, 1996; minimum elevation, 2,375.55 ft (724.06 m), Sept. 24, 25, 1994.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 2,419.60 ft (737.49 m), Sept. 22; minimum elevation, 2,409.24 ft (734.34 m), Oct. 1.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
2,338	2	2,399	1,845
2,360	302	2,420	3,331

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2409.64	2414.70	2413.64	2413.28	2413.34	2413.85	2410.38	2414.72	2415.25	2414.93	2415.16	2413.93
2	2409.90	2414.84	2413.53	2413.35	2413.40	2413.64	2410.50	2414.89	2415.25	2414.82	2415.25	2415.40
3	2410.03	2414.73	2413.34	2413.41	2413.16	2413.46	A	2415.06	2415.20	2414.63	2415.17	2415.28
4	2410.14	2414.59	2413.14	2413.48	2414.16	2413.24	2410.51	2414.92	2415.37	2414.84	2415.05	2415.28
5	2410.25	2414.47	2412.94	2413.55	2415.26	2413.02	2410.66	2414.79	2415.44	2415.02	2414.89	2415.27
6	2410.34	2414.26	2413.02	2413.61	2415.10	2412.83	2410.44	2414.73	2415.33	2415.01	A	2415.45
7	2410.40	2414.10	2413.11	2413.68	2415.22	2413.10	2412.48	2414.64	2415.32	2415.19	2415.33	2415.38
8	2410.64	2414.23	2412.89	2413.46	2415.50	2413.22	2412.56	2414.99	2415.23	2415.26	2415.34	2415.08
9	2410.69	2414.44	2412.67	2413.30	2415.19	2413.00	2412.78	2415.22	2415.20	2415.09	2415.33	2414.69
10	2410.70	2414.42	2412.45	2413.37	2415.05	2412.77	2412.95	2415.27	2415.17	2415.00	2415.17	2414.25
11	2410.89	2414.57	2412.30	2413.43	2414.91	2412.52	2413.28	2415.17	2415.16	2415.15	2415.29	2414.05
12	2411.11	2414.41	2412.11	2413.51	2414.67	2412.30	2414.44	2415.19	2415.27	2415.25	2415.23	2413.85
13	2412.30	2414.24	2412.20	2413.44	2414.49	2412.06	2414.62	2415.10	2415.31	2415.08	2415.14	2413.94
14	2414.33	2414.05	2412.29	2413.23	2414.67	2412.15	2414.61	2413.56	2415.30	2415.15	2415.05	2413.79
15	2414.90	2414.19	2412.07	2412.99	2414.80	2412.25	2414.53	2413.94	2415.18	2415.13	2415.18	2413.67
16	2415.10	2414.31	2412.07	2412.76	2414.91	2412.01	2414.56	2414.27	2415.16	2415.03	2415.26	2413.77
17	2415.51	2414.13	2412.17	2412.83	2414.78	2411.78	2414.76	2414.12	2415.23	2414.91	2415.12	2413.85
18	A	2413.96	2412.31	2413.33	2414.58	2411.53	2415.19	2413.88	A	2415.08	2415.33	2414.88
19	A	2414.06	2412.41	2413.47	2414.42	2411.29	2415.32	2414.46	2415.11	2415.22	2415.14	2414.56
20	2415.16	2413.87	2412.49	2413.56	2414.22	2411.09	2415.36	2414.36	2415.27	2415.27	2415.09	2414.38
21	2415.06	2413.79	2412.57	2413.64	2414.30	2411.18	2415.19	2414.03	2415.30	2415.08	2415.28	2418.56
22	2415.01	2413.89	2412.67	2413.33	2414.39	2411.28	2415.15	2414.89	2415.16	2414.99	2415.40	2416.21
23	2414.96	2414.00	2412.65	2413.40	2414.17	2411.36	2415.10	2415.08	2415.28	2414.87	2415.31	2415.76
24	2414.85	2413.79	2412.72	2413.47	2413.95	2411.11	2415.04	2415.36	2415.28	2415.03	A	2415.64
25	2415.05	2413.60	2412.79	2413.54	2413.77	2410.88	2415.22	2415.36	2415.28	2415.16	2415.28	2415.56
26	2415.21	2413.41	2412.87	2413.30	2413.60	2410.63	2415.25	2415.34	2415.13	2415.25	2415.13	2415.52
27	2415.06	2413.50	2412.94	2413.06	2413.68	2410.41	2415.09	2415.31	2415.26	2415.26	2414.94	2415.49
28	2414.91	2413.59	2413.02	2413.11	2413.76	2410.50	2414.98	2415.30	2415.27	2415.25	2414.73	2415.58
29	2414.76	2413.71	2413.09	2413.17	---	2410.65	2414.84	2415.28	2415.12	2415.25	2414.57	2415.46
30	2414.65	2413.82	2413.15	2413.23	---	2410.75	2414.83	2415.34	2415.03	2415.25	2414.43	2415.44
31	2414.54	---	2413.21	2413.28	---	2410.59	---	2415.32	---	2415.04	2414.20	---
MAX	---	2414.84	2413.64	2413.68	2415.50	2413.85	---	2415.36	---	2415.27	---	2418.56
MIN	---	2413.41	2412.07	2412.76	2413.16	2410.41	---	2413.56	---	2414.63	---	2413.67

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50034000 RIO BAUTA NEAR OROCOVIS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'10", long 66°27'18", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 157 (12.1 km), and 4.2 mi (6.8 km) west of Orocovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--16.7 mi² (43.3 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to April 1966 (annual low-flow measurements only), February to September 1969 (occasional measurements only), October 1969 to September 1982, October 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 772.82 ft (235.556 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	46	12	7.6	6.2	5.9	8.3	15	10	23	14	9.5	19
2	35	12	8.5	6.3	5.9	7.9	21	9.1	23	14	8.5	189
3	25	11	8.4	6.1	5.9	8.2	37	8.7	23	15	8.6	195
4	22	11	7.6	6.2	6.2	8.7	16	8.3	28	16	7.9	213
5	20	12	7.6	6.8	403	8.2	12	7.9	68	16	7.9	75
6	19	11	7.6	6.5	73	8.0	11	8.3	38	16	8.2	80
7	67	10	7.2	6.6	33	8.7	79	12	27	16	31	102
8	107	10	7.2	6.7	174	8.6	74	106	23	15	20	72
9	74	10	7.2	6.1	174	7.4	31	70	22	14	20	47
10	36	21	7.2	5.9	50	6.8	20	26	21	14	17	37
11	53	13	7.1	5.9	31	6.5	15	16	20	14	13	38
12	91	12	7.3	5.9	24	6.5	392	11	25	13	15	38
13	94	11	7.2	8.5	18	6.5	147	54	24	12	11	46
14	517	10	7.2	13	16	6.2	53	351	20	14	9.0	58
15	268	10	7.2	7.2	17	6.2	32	339	19	17	7.9	60
16	133	9.6	7.1	6.5	13	5.9	31	109	18	15	10	43
17	118	9.6	8.2	6.2	12	5.6	30	62	23	13	13	36
18	145	9.4	7.7	46	11	5.6	98	218	21	12	17	195
19	58	9.1	7.4	33	9.9	5.5	97	215	18	12	17	114
20	35	8.7	6.7	9.7	9.1	5.8	38	184	17	12	22	55
21	26	8.7	6.5	8.7	9.0	7.9	41	434	17	14	36	e1820
22	21	8.7	11	7.7	8.3	6.2	34	191	19	11	99	e10000
23	19	8.7	11	6.7	7.7	6.4	41	73	17	11	90	e1400
24	17	8.3	7.4	6.5	7.3	5.9	32	50	17	11	156	e290
25	16	8.3	6.6	6.5	7.7	5.8	24	41	17	11	386	e200
26	15	8.3	6.5	6.5	13	6.1	20	36	17	9.5	70	e150
27	14	8.1	6.1	6.4	9.6	5.6	17	34	16	14	43	e120
28	14	7.9	6.2	6.2	8.7	5.6	14	30	15	11	34	e100
29	13	8.1	6.5	6.2	---	14	12	28	15	11	27	e240
30	13	8.5	6.4	6.2	---	48	10	27	15	10	23	e280
31	12	---	6.1	6.1	---	30	---	25	---	9.9	20	---
TOTAL	2143	306.0	229.5	279.0	1219.0	282.6	1494	2794.3	666	407.4	1257.5	16312
MEAN	69.1	10.2	7.40	9.00	43.5	9.12	49.8	90.1	22.2	13.1	40.6	544
MAX	517	21	1.1	46	403	48	392	434	68	17	386	10000
MIN	12	7.9	6.1	5.9	5.9	5.5	10	7.9	15	9.5	7.9	19
AC-FT	4250	607	455	553	2420	561	2960	5540	1320	808	2490	32350
CFSM	4.14	.61	.44	.54	2.61	.55	2.98	5.40	1.33	.79	2.43	32.6
IN.	4.77	.68	.51	.62	2.72	.63	3.33	6.22	1.48	.91	2.80	36.34

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	83.8	50.7	27.0	20.7	16.3	14.8	27.2	50.6	18.8	15.9	21.0	120
MEAN	83.8	50.7	27.0	20.7	16.3	14.8	27.2	50.6	18.8	15.9	21.0	120
MAX	392	205	108	83.4	43.5	59.9	80.2	179	78.6	104	152	1104
(WY)	1971	1971	1971	1992	1998	1972	1980	1981	1979	1979	1979	1996
MIN	14.6	7.12	4.29	3.66	5.70	4.18	4.92	4.24	3.59	3.22	3.97	3.55
(WY)	1994	1995	1995	1995	1994	1994	1995	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL		7009.4		27390.3								
ANNUAL MEAN		19.2		75.0						38.9		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN										117		1996
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN										6.56		1994
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN				517	Oct 14		10000	Sep 22		19500		Sep 10 1996
LOWEST DAILY MEAN				3.6	Jul 18		5.5	Mar 19		2.8		Jul 23 1994
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM				4.2	Jul 22		5.8	Mar 14		2.8		Jul 23 1994
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW							28200	Sep 22		28200		Sep 22 1998
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE							25.93	Sep 22		25.93		Sep 22 1998
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW							5.0	Mar 19		2.6		Jul 26 1994
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)		13900					54330			28190		
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)		1.15					4.49			2.33		
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)		15.61					61.01			31.66		
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS		32					104			64		
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS		9.5					14			13		
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS		5.3					6.5			5.4		

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN
50034000 RIO BAUTA NEAR OROCOVIS, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50035000 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT CIALES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'26", long 66°27'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on left bank, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream from Hwy 145 bridge, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) downstream from Quebrada Saliente, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) upstream from Quebrada Cojo Valés, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southeast of Ciales.

DRAINAGE AREA.--128 mi² (332 km²), excludes 6.0 mi² (15.5 km²), the runoff from which is diverted through El Guineo and Matrullas reservoirs.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1946 to September 1953, May 1956 to December 1957 (unpublished, available in files of Caribbean District Office and in the National Water Data Storage and Retrieval System, Washington, D.C.); February 1959 to September 1960 (monthly discharge measurements only); October 1960 to current year. Equivalent record from January 1971 to December 1972 published as 50035200 Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 145 at Ciales at site 1.6 mi (2.6 km) downstream, drainage area 132 mi² (342 km²).

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 140 ft (43 m), from topographic map. Prior to Apr. 1, 1962, staff gage, read twice daily, at site 100 ft (30 m) upstream at same datum. January 1971 to December 1972 at site 1.6 mi (2.6 km) downstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate gage heights of major floods, pointed out by local residents are as follows: August 1899, 50 ft (15 m), September 1928, 36 ft (11 m), and September 1932, 34 ft (10 m) at site 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	68	48	51	e31	e25	e45	e130	e71	127	56	e52	60
2	173	49	47	e34	e25	e43	e86	e63	161	57	e40	543
3	99	46	53	e36	e28	e44	e72	e60	174	105	e38	635
4	63	49	47	e39	e56	e45	e72	e56	163	e100	e36	505
5	47	50	44	e37	e1060	e43	e58	e55	293	e71	e37	269
6	41	50	42	e59	e291	e43	e50	57	267	e67	e58	231
7	169	45	41	e182	e146	e46	e48	58	153	e77	e245	361
8	440	43	37	e84	e190	e51	e410	68	138	e64	298	332
9	442	44	32	e57	e498	e44	e130	77	123	e61	249	194
10	150	121	e34	e46	e191	e42	e82	66	119	e67	166	158
11	95	149	e36	e235	e118	e41	e68	63	115	e65	90	115
12	330	137	e37	e94	e87	e40	e300	63	96	e61	117	186
13	308	75	e37	e89	e75	e41	e460	62	138	e52	79	132
14	1180	58	e37	e324	e63	e41	e200	e205	115	e54	55	137
15	581	55	e35	e117	e73	e42	e135	e1510	103	e58	54	139
16	479	68	e34	e63	e62	e42	e140	e321	94	e60	52	95
17	669	60	e34	e47	e55	e38	e540	e258	152	e55	64	112
18	808	61	e34	e49	e56	e37	e220	e254	213	e56	64	282
19	324	55	e38	e268	e49	e37	e367	e411	127	e58	104	336
20	204	53	e39	e93	e51	e39	e320	e549	103	e54	82	182
21	136	53	e35	e57	e49	e64	e332	e556	118	e86	135	e3290
22	101	51	e40	e95	e46	e50	e279	e804	160	63	231	e10100
23	85	49	e44	e48	e46	e43	e233	e454	103	49	259	e1090
24	74	49	e38	e35	e44	e43	e203	e311	99	52	174	e593
25	67	49	e33	e33	e43	e39	e168	e236	106	51	1710	e492
26	65	55	e31	e35	e48	e37	e142	e188	85	46	299	e451
27	58	53	e32	e31	e49	e38	e127	200	65	109	155	e426
28	54	47	e31	e28	e49	e38	e103	157	63	74	156	e446
29	52	45	e32	e26	---	e40	e87	138	65	56	103	e861
30	51	61	e32	e25	---	e120	e80	154	60	53	79	e688
31	51	---	e33	e25	---	e350	---	174	---	e66	84	---
TOTAL	7464	1828	1170	2422	3573	1706	5642	7699	3898	2003	5365	23441
MEAN	241	60.9	37.7	78.1	128	55.0	188	248	130	64.6	173	781
MAX	1180	149	53	324	1060	350	540	1510	293	109	1710	10100
MIN	41	43	31	25	25	37	48	55	60	46	36	60
AC-FT	14800	3630	2320	4800	7090	3380	11190	15270	7730	3970	10640	46500
CFSM	1.88	.48	.29	.61	1.00	.43	1.47	1.94	1.02	.50	1.35	6.10
IN.	2.17	.53	.34	.70	1.04	.50	1.64	2.24	1.13	.58	1.56	6.81

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1946 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	421	335	252	192	167	135	254	411	151	104	149	309
MAX	2422	1006	1296	679	1394	477	1174	2293	458	438	1212	1295
(WY)	1971	1971	1966	1952	1950	1969	1969	1985	1979	1979	1979	1996
MIN	91.9	34.7	29.7	26.2	41.6	29.7	28.5	29.6	17.8	14.1	27.0	23.9
(WY)	1994	1995	1995	1995	1995	1994	1984	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50035000 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT CIALES, PR--Continued

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1998 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1946 - 1998	
ANNUAL TOTAL	47478		66211			
ANNUAL MEAN	130		181		241	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					520	1971
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					47.3	1994
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	4200	Jan 22	10100	Sep 22	42700	May 18 1985
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	22	Aug 7	25	Jan 30	8.5	Jul 28 1994
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	28	Jul 24	26	Jan 28	9.5	Jul 24 1994
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			78900	Sep 21	128000	Sep 10 1996
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			22.38	Sep 21	25.20	Sep 10 1996
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			21	Feb 4	8.5	Jul 27 1994
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	94170		131300		174600	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.02		1.42		1.88	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	13.80		19.24		25.58	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	206		334		435	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	61		66		112	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	35		37		50	

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50035950 RIO CIALITOS AT HIGHWAY 649 AT CIALES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'18", long 66°28'28", 100 ft (30 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 649, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) upstream from mouth, and about 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Ciales plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.0 mi² (44.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)
NOV 04...	1105	12	227	8.1	24.0	3.2	8.4	<10	2000
MAR 03...	1300	4.6	256	7.8	23.0	2.2	8.3	<10	420
MAY 28...	1110	15	220	8.3	26.0	4.0	8.0	<10	430
AUG 19...	1205	20	228	7.9	26.5	13	7.8	<10	K930

DATE	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	HARD-NESS, TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)
NOV 04...	500	89	21	8.9	31	1	3.2	95	<.5	14
MAR 03...	380	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--
MAY 28...	310	84	24	5.8	10	.5	1.9	90	--	6.4
AUG 19...	2000	88	25	6.0	9.6	.4	2.0	87	<1.0	6.4

DATE	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDE (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 04...	27	<.10	28	190	6.20	8	<.010	.400	.020	--
MAR 03...	--	--	--	--	--	2	<.010	.250	.020	--
MAY 28...	11	<.10	26	140	5.79	8	<.010	.410	.030	--
AUG 19...	10	<.10	26	138	7.56	13	<.010	.620	.030	.24

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 04...	<.20	--	--	.060	<1	<100	10	<1	<1	<10
MAR 03...	<.20	--	--	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 28...	<.20	--	--	.050	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
AUG 19...	.27	.89	3.9	.060	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'52", long 66°31'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, at bridge on Highway 2, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) west of Manati.

DRAINAGE AREA.--197 mi² (510 km²), approximately, of which about 38 mi² (98 km²) is partly or entirely noncontributing, excludes 6.0 mi² (15.5 km²) upstream from Lago El Guineo and Lago de Matrullas.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1963-68 (annual maximum discharge only), February 1970 to current year.

REVISED RECORDS.--WRD PR-86-1: 1970-71 (M), 1975, 1979, 1982-85 (P).

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 14 ft (4 m), from topographic map. Prior to 1968 crest-stage gage at same site and datum 3.57 ft (1.09 m) lower.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Possible water extraction about 500 ft (152.4 m) upstream of gage by unknown source affecting low flow.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate gage heights to gage datum of major floods, pointed out by local residents, are as follows: Sept. 13, 1928, 36.6 ft (11.16 m), Sept. 27, 1932, 36.3 ft (11.06 m), and Aug. 4, 1945, 34.3 ft (10.45 m).

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	155	86	e76	48	48	72	172	94	276	97	77	129
2	219	84	e65	51	49	68	114	89	251	92	69	570
3	171	84	65	52	47	65	95	90	288	95	68	1720
4	138	82	66	55	53	64	94	94	271	191	80	914
5	123	84	61	e56	5180	66	76	88	251	114	68	518
6	94	86	59	e51	599	67	67	94	546	101	e66	310
7	82	80	58	e110	273	65	64	101	272	104	79	569
8	391	80	57	98	179	97	532	139	225	104	412	573
9	711	76	55	75	1050	88	172	1010	213	91	270	317
10	258	113	54	62	353	68	109	256	196	90	226	252
11	182	143	53	63	213	61	88	172	170	88	148	201
12	231	273	53	163	170	57	369	154	156	87	137	246
13	646	137	53	88	140	56	612	115	192	80	177	267
14	1410	105	52	165	122	55	265	e333	206	81	116	266
15	847	90	52	151	118	55	175	e9510	164	223	91	236
16	656	90	50	92	117	103	251	1050	146	129	85	202
17	484	94	51	74	104	81	715	e658	141	106	158	178
18	1490	93	49	65	95	62	289	e421	251	115	117	166
19	476	87	51	138	89	55	502	1530	173	99	149	594
20	298	80	55	129	87	52	425	1570	142	99	127	238
21	219	79	53	86	84	55	400	2240	136	105	164	235
22	173	73	50	93	80	65	387	2590	147	112	258	80400
23	149	71	56	82	75	58	243	821	148	85	371	12000
24	133	69	60	63	73	52	211	544	120	83	218	2380
25	120	67	53	59	71	52	193	392	124	89	2500	1540
26	114	68	51	61	75	49	155	331	153	80	676	1160
27	109	e73	50	57	80	50	150	301	124	103	299	950
28	105	e67	50	53	75	50	137	263	110	142	257	774
29	96	65	50	50	---	53	114	242	107	96	251	1830
30	93	67	50	51	---	153	99	541	105	82	172	2240
31	90	---	51	47	---	462	---	495	---	79	141	---
TOTAL	10463	2746	1709	2488	9699	2456	7275	26328	5804	3242	8027	111975
MEAN	338	91.5	55.1	80.3	346	79.2	243	849	193	105	259	3733
MAX	1490	273	76	165	5180	462	715	9510	546	223	2500	80400
MIN	82	65	49	47	47	49	64	88	105	79	66	129
AC-FT	20750	5450	3390	4930	19240	4870	14430	52220	11510	6430	15920	222100
CFSM	1.71	.46	.28	.41	1.76	.40	1.23	4.31	.98	.53	1.31	18.9
IN.	1.98	.52	.32	.47	1.83	.46	1.37	4.97	1.10	.61	1.52	21.14

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1970 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998							
MEAN	708	522	351	263	207	182	349	661	228	153	212	620	708	522	351	263	207	182	349	661	228	153	212	620	708	522	351	263	207	182	349	661	228	153	212	620
MAX	2958	1803	1498	879	444	521	1037	3178	747	577	1644	3733	2958	1803	1498	879	444	521	1037	3178	747	577	1644	3733	2958	1803	1498	879	444	521	1037	3178	747	577	1644	3733
(WY)	1971	1971	1971	1997	1988	1972	1993	1985	1987	1979	1979	1998	1971	1971	1971	1997	1988	1972	1993	1985	1987	1979	1979	1998	1971	1971	1971	1997	1988	1972	1993	1985	1987	1979	1979	1998
MIN	154	71.0	55.1	59.1	72.0	56.2	49.9	93.7	63.8	53.0	67.9	67.4	154	71.0	55.1	59.1	72.0	56.2	49.9	93.7	63.8	53.0	67.9	67.4	154	71.0	55.1	59.1	72.0	56.2	49.9	93.7	63.8	53.0	67.9	67.4
(WY)	1995	1995	1998	1995	1994	1994	1995	1989	1994	1994	1984	1994	1995	1995	1998	1995	1994	1994	1995	1989	1994	1994	1984	1994	1995	1995	1998	1995	1994	1994	1995	1989	1994	1994	1984	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1998 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1970 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	73217	192212	
ANNUAL MEAN	201	527	370
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			756
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			96.5
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	6880	Jan 22	80400
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	49	Dec 18	31
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	51	Dec 25	49
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			136000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			34.90
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			28
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	145200	381300	268100
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.02	2.67	1.88
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	13.83	36.30	25.52
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	296	569	632
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	98	109	164
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	55	53	81

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR.

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 27...	1030	108	307	7.6	28.0	4.9	6.3	80	<10	K8100	340
FEB 25...	1150	71	351	7.8	27.5	5.7	7.8	98	<10	4000	790
JUN 24...	1015	120	296	7.8	29.0	3.9	7.1	92	<10	410	K82
AUG 28...	1135	284	223	7.3	29.0	19	6.5	84	<10	K270	K540

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 27...	130	38	7.5	11	.4	1.9	120	<.5	9.7	13
FEB 25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
JUN 24...	120	37	7.6	11	.4	2.0	130	--	8.5	13
AUG 28...	88	25	5.9	9.3	.4	2.0	83	<1.0	7.9	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 27...	.10	21	174	50.5	17	.809	.021	.830	.050	.50
FEB 25...	--	--	--	--	7	.588	.012	.600	.030	.52
JUN 24...	.11	15	172	55.6	13	--	<.010	.550	.040	--
AUG 28...	<.10	22	133	102	29	1.07	.030	1.10	.150	.23

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 27...	.55	1.4	6.1	.170	<1	<100	20	<1	1	<10
FEB 25...	.55	1.1	5.1	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 24...	<.20	--	--	.070	1	<100	30	<1	1	<10
AUG 28...	.38	1.5	6.6	.080	--	--	--	--	--	--

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EXPLANATION

- 038320 ▲ SURFACE-WATER STATION AND NUMBER
- 038320 ▼ QUALITY-OF-WATER STATION AND NUMBER
- 213 ● WELL AND WELL NUMBER
- TOWN OR CITY
- - - DRAINAGE BASIN BOUNDARY

Figure 15. Río Cibuco basin.

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50038320 RIO CIBUCO BELOW COROZAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'13", long 66°20'07", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on right bank, 150 ft (46 m) downstream from junction with Rio Corozal, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) northwest of Corozal.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.1 mi² (39.1 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1969 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 195 ft (59 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Daily discharge affected by sewage treatment plant about 0.6 mi (1.0 km) upstream from station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.8	5.4	e2.2	e3.0	e2.6	e3.6	9.5	e5.8	10	5.3	7.0	6.7
2	7.5	4.6	e2.1	e3.8	e3.2	e3.4	5.2	11	22	7.0	6.1	9.6
3	6.7	e5.0	e2.1	e3.2	3.2	e3.5	e3.7	35	58	16	6.0	8.8
4	9.1	4.9	e2.0	e3.7	e168	e3.5	e3.0	10	23	13	6.4	7.9
5	11	e5.8	e2.1	e3.5	424	e3.4	e2.6	6.7	14	7.9	6.3	e11
6	7.3	e4.8	e2.1	e12	40	e4.9	2.5	7.4	12	12	e8.7	11
7	13	4.3	e2.1	e44	16	e4.2	3.3	7.8	14	9.9	35	8.2
8	22	3.8	e2.1	e12	27	e3.4	4.8	e11	10	6.8	13	6.4
9	10	3.5	e1.9	e6.0	36	2.7	2.9	e9.5	15	7.4	21	5.7
10	8.6	4.6	e1.9	e5.8	e16	e3.3	e2.2	7.1	12	7.7	9.1	5.2
11	9.6	e35	e1.8	e53	e10	e3.2	2.5	6.5	9.6	7.7	7.7	5.0
12	e62	e15	e1.9	e11	e9.2	e3.4	34	4.8	8.9	5.9	7.8	5.2
13	e29	e5.0	e2.3	e108	e7.2	e3.1	e42	3.9	45	6.8	8.5	e6.1
14	41	e4.1	e1.8	e42	e23	e3.4	e7.6	126	15	6.2	7.4	5.3
15	15	e3.8	e1.7	e8.1	e18	e3.2	e5.5	141	11	9.1	6.2	4.7
16	15	e3.8	e1.6	e5.1	e8.3	e3.2	e297	8.9	8.0	5.7	6.3	4.4
17	21	3.3	e1.6	e4.3	e6.4	e3.0	e105	85	26	7.8	13	4.3
18	12	e5.5	e1.8	e3.7	e5.8	e3.5	e39	28	e16	13	8.2	5.4
19	9.3	11	e2.2	e3.7	e5.3	e3.1	e16	319	9.8	8.4	9.3	e6.8
20	8.4	e4.2	e2.1	e3.1	e5.2	7.4	18	108	6.9	31	10	5.3
21	7.3	3.5	1.8	e3.1	e4.5	e7.8	e13	43	28	13	e27	150
22	6.8	2.9	e1.8	e3.5	e4.4	e3.6	e26	29	12	8.1	9.9	e1200
23	6.0	2.3	e2.0	e3.0	e4.5	e2.9	12	23	8.9	9.7	7.9	e139
24	5.8	2.6	e2.0	e3.0	e4.0	e2.4	8.8	19	7.7	9.6	54	e46
25	5.9	e2.5	e1.9	e3.1	e4.0	2.0	7.6	16	11	7.0	39	27
26	5.8	4.9	e2.1	e3.3	e4.8	e1.8	7.3	14	9.8	7.4	12	20
27	5.2	e3.7	e1.7	e3.7	e4.4	1.7	16	13	8.1	47	19	20
28	5.1	e3.1	e1.8	e3.0	e4.1	e1.6	9.4	12	7.3	17	65	19
29	5.1	e3.2	e1.7	e3.3	---	e36	7.2	13	7.0	11	18	85
30	4.9	e2.8	e1.7	e3.2	---	e48	e6.6	11	6.3	8.5	8.8	e48
31	4.8	---	e2.2	e2.9	---	90	---	8.9	---	8.1	6.9	---
TOTAL	389.0	168.9	60.1	374.1	869.1	270.2	720.2	1144.3	452.3	341.0	470.5	1887.0
MEAN	12.5	5.63	1.94	12.1	31.0	8.72	24.0	36.9	15.1	11.0	15.2	62.9
MAX	62	35	2.3	108	424	90	297	319	58	47	65	1200
MIN	4.8	2.3	1.6	2.9	2.6	1.6	2.2	3.9	6.3	5.3	6.0	4.3
AC-FT	772	335	119	742	1720	536	1430	2270	897	676	933	3740
CFSM	.83	.37	.13	.80	2.06	.58	1.59	2.44	1.00	.73	1.01	4.17
IN.	.96	.42	.15	.92	2.14	.67	1.77	2.82	1.11	.84	1.16	4.65

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980
MEAN	40.1	46.3	34.3	24.9	21.5	21.0	32.3	43.9	14.6	11.8	16.5	33.6
MAX	135	155	169	69.6	51.3	65.1	111	157	44.4	34.6	50.8	191
(WY)	1991	1971	1971	1992	1988	1981	1973	1986	1987	1979	1979	1996
MIN	8.05	5.63	1.94	6.93	7.75	4.36	3.32	3.20	1.63	2.19	3.44	3.88
(WY)	1979	1998	1998	1995	1994	1984	1984	1977	1994	1994	1978	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1969 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	5383.8	7146.7	
ANNUAL MEAN	14.8	19.6	28.5
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			56.5
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			7.47
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	380	Jan 22	1200
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.6	Dec 16	1.6
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.8	Dec 11	1.8
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			3910
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			12.61
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	10680	14180	20640
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.98	1.30	1.89
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	13.26	17.61	25.64
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	30	35	50
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	7.5	7.0	13
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.7	2.3	5.0

e Estimated

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50038320 RIO CIBUCO BELOW COROZAL, PR--Continued

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50038320 RIO CIBUCO BELOW COROZAL, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-76, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) UNITS (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 16...	1025	13	439	7.6	26.0	3.0	6.4	79	<10	30000	K19000
FEB 17...	1150	7.2	447	8.1	25.5	1.2	6.2	76	<10	K60	K100
JUN 15...	1200	12	388	7.8	27.5	4.1	7.6	97	<10	K1700	K1700
AUG 18...	1140	7.8	381	8.0	28.0	5.1	7.5	97	<10	3000	800

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 16...	160	41	15	20	.7	3.6	150	<.5	20	31
FEB 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
JUN 15...	150	37	13	19	.7	3.9	130	--	16	25
AUG 18...	140	36	12	20	.7	3.9	130	<1.0	14	27

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 16...	.11	31	251	9.00	5	1.00	.010	1.00	.020	.20
FEB 17...	--	--	--	--	2	2.03	.067	2.10	.100	.30
JUN 15...	.15	26	218	7.11	4	1.99	.013	2.00	.020	--
AUG 18...	.24	30	221	4.66	10	2.18	.018	2.20	.050	.36

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 16...	.20	1.1	5.0	.070	<1	<100	30	<1	4	<10
FEB 17...	.40	2.5	11	.330	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 15...	<.20	--	--	.210	<1	<100	40	<1	<1	15
AUG 18...	.41	2.6	12	.350	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO CIBUCO BASIN
50039500 RIO CIBUCO AT VEGA BAJA, PR--Continued

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039500 RIO CIBUCO AT VEGA BAJA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 14...	1145	79	422	7.8	25.5	20	4.5	55	13	4000	2200
FEB 18...	0830	31	482	7.9	24.5	5.9	6.2	74	<10	2000	K1200
MAY 20...	1330	335	340	7.5	26.0	92	6.5	80	24	K18000	7800
AUG 27...	1525	41	416	7.7	28.0	15	6.0	76	<10	K1600	4800

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 14...	170	57	7.7	14	.5	4.3	150	<.5	22	21
FEB 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
MAY 20...	140	43	6.7	10	.4	4.9	120	--	19	16
AUG 27...	160	51	8.9	16	.5	4.2	160	<1.0	15	22

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 14...	.15	17	233	49.8	22	3.00	.170	3.20	.730	.92
FEB 18...	--	--	--	--	5	1.77	.032	1.80	.040	.25
MAY 20...	.13	14	187	170	228	2.36	.040	2.40	.170	1.2
AUG 27...	.11	19	231	25.3	18	1.28	.019	1.30	.060	.55

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 14...	1.6	4.8	21	1.00	<1	<100	40	<1	2	<10
FEB 18...	.29	2.1	9.3	.150	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 20...	1.4	3.8	17	.340	<1	<100	20	<1	16	29
AUG 27...	.61	1.9	8.5	.320	--	--	--	--	--	--

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Figure 16. Río de la Plata basin.

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50039990 LAGO CARITE AT GATE TOWER NEAR CAYEY, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'46", long 66°05'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on top of a concrete tower at diversion tunnel on Carite Reservoir, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) northwest from Escuela Carite Chino, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northeast from Central Hidroeléctrica de Carite Num. 1 and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northeast from Escuela Segunda Unidad.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.20 mi² (21.24 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1989 to current year. Prior to October 1994, published as Lago Carite at Gate Tower.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Carite Dam was completed in 1913. The operation of the reservoir is controlled by the utilization of water to meet the demands for domestic, industrial and agricultural purposes in the Guayama Area. The dam is an earthfill with crest elevation of 1,806 ft (550 m) above mean sea level, with a structural height of 104 ft (32 m) and a length of 500 ft (152 m). The dam has a capacity of approximately 11,310 acre-feet (13.9 hm³). The Dam is operated by the Puerto Rico Electric and Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 1,789.62 ft (545.48 m), Sep. 21, 1998; minimum elevation, 1,761.22 ft (536.81 m), May 28, 1995.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation 1,789.62 ft (545.48 m), Sep. 21; minimum elevation, 1,769.39 ft (539.10 m), Oct. 1.

Capacity Table

(based on Data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
1,746	0	1,775	6,194
1,760	2,471	1,780	7,704
1,769	4,561	1,790	11,048

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1769.39	1781.43	1781.27	1779.67	1781.38	1781.31	1781.59	1781.52	1781.57	1781.17	1780.01	1781.53
2	1769.48	1781.41	1781.24	1779.68	1781.35	1781.31	1781.62	1781.51	1781.52	1781.12	1779.92	1781.62
3	1769.48	1781.42	1781.16	1779.77	1781.34	1781.34	1781.59	1781.51	1781.49	1781.13	1779.84	1781.67
4	1769.50	1781.41	1781.11	1779.88	1781.39	1781.39	1781.55	1781.55	1781.47	1781.19	1779.76	1781.62
5	1769.49	1781.40	1781.07	1779.98	1782.13	1781.32	1781.54	1781.54	1781.50	1781.18	1779.67	1781.56
6	1769.48	1781.39	1781.00	1780.71	1781.79	1781.29	1781.50	1781.49	1781.45	1781.15	A	1781.64
7	1769.45	1781.37	1780.95	1781.06	1781.64	1781.66	1781.64	1781.46	1781.49	1781.09	1779.53	1781.70
8	1769.50	1781.37	1780.88	1781.27	1781.64	1781.65	1781.58	1781.50	1781.47	1781.09	1779.63	1781.71
9	1769.49	1781.70	1780.83	1781.41	1781.57	1781.56	1781.52	1781.59	1781.46	1781.04	1779.66	1781.69
10	1769.47	1782.19	1780.76	1781.52	1781.48	1781.51	1781.50	1781.52	1781.47	1780.99	1779.58	1781.53
11	1769.66	1781.78	1780.71	1781.52	1781.51	1781.48	1781.70	1781.50	1781.39	1780.95	1779.50	1781.55
12	1769.70	1781.63	1780.65	1781.51	1781.51	1781.45	1781.79	1781.49	1781.42	1780.93	1779.53	1781.51
13	1774.24	1781.57	1780.59	1781.54	1781.46	1781.42	1781.67	1781.96	1781.36	1780.87	1779.48	1781.54
14	1781.23	1781.52	1780.53	1781.51	1781.61	1781.42	1781.62	1781.82	1781.34	1780.83	1779.38	1781.52
15	1782.30	1781.50	1780.47	1781.50	1781.58	1781.42	1781.58	1781.74	1781.33	1780.77	1779.34	1781.59
16	1781.99	1781.49	1780.42	1781.47	1781.53	1781.40	1781.58	1781.68	1781.38	1780.73	1779.29	1781.54
17	1781.94	1781.49	1780.40	1781.47	1781.51	1781.38	1781.57	1781.61	1781.36	1780.64	1779.28	1781.48
18	1781.79	1781.47	1780.32	1781.46	1781.48	1781.36	1781.56	1781.54	1781.28	1780.61	1779.24	1781.46
19	1781.69	1781.45	1780.24	1781.42	1781.46	1781.36	1781.55	1781.52	1781.32	1780.56	1779.23	1781.50
20	1781.64	1781.44	1780.22	1781.41	1781.45	1781.65	1781.56	1781.47	1781.31	1780.71	1779.15	1781.47
21	1781.58	1781.46	1780.18	1781.39	1781.43	1781.67	1781.56	1781.45	1781.46	1780.64	1779.23	1789.62
22	1781.56	1781.48	1780.14	1781.38	1781.42	1781.73	1781.54	1781.42	1781.48	1780.58	1780.75	A
23	1781.53	1781.52	1780.09	1781.37	1781.41	1781.63	1781.51	1781.44	1781.43	1780.50	1780.84	A
24	1781.50	1781.52	1780.00	1781.40	1781.39	1781.56	1781.51	1781.44	1781.38	1780.47	1784.06	A
25	1781.50	1781.49	1779.95	1781.45	1781.39	1781.55	1781.50	1781.42	1781.37	1780.42	1782.60	A
26	1781.48	1781.46	1779.86	1781.44	1781.38	1781.51	1781.50	1781.77	1781.34	1780.34	1782.06	A
27	1781.45	1781.41	1779.81	1781.42	1781.36	1781.56	1781.54	1781.75	1781.31	1780.34	1781.81	A
28	1781.45	1781.36	1779.74	1781.42	1781.34	1781.54	1781.55	1781.62	1781.26	1780.32	1781.68	A
29	1781.45	1781.33	1779.67	1781.42	---	1781.53	1781.55	1781.57	1781.22	1780.25	1781.71	A
30	1781.42	1781.32	1779.65	1781.41	---	1781.78	1781.53	1781.68	1781.21	1780.17	1781.63	A
31	1781.42	---	1779.64	1781.40	---	1781.69	---	1781.63	---	1780.09	1781.58	---
MAX	1782.30	1782.19	1781.27	1781.54	1782.13	1781.78	1781.79	1781.96	1781.57	1781.19	---	---
MIN	1769.39	1781.32	1779.64	1779.67	1781.34	1781.29	1781.50	1781.42	1781.21	1780.09	---	---

A No gage-height record

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT PROYECTO LA PLATA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 30...	0800	35	427	8.0	26.0	6.2	7.0	88	<10	320	290
FEB 26...	0840	19	494	7.8	24.5	.40	7.0	87	<10	210	K130
MAY 19...	1155	57	309	7.4	30.0	3.8	7.6	104	<10	3400	K82
AUG 20...	1220	14	387	8.2	30.0	4.1	10.4	143	<10	K40	K20

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 30...	150	37	15	33	1	2.9	150	<.5	24	33
FEB 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
MAY 19...	100	25	9.3	22	1	2.3	100	--	12	23
AUG 20...	130	27	16	12	.5	2.4	130	<1.0	11	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 30...	.10	26	261	24.6	7	1.59	.014	1.60	.020	.26
FEB 26...	--	--	--	--	2	1.20	.010	1.20	.030	.26
MAY 19...	.22	21	174	27.0	5	1.57	.035	1.60	.040	.29
AUG 20...	.10	22	179	6.77	8	1.38	.024	1.40	.070	.35

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 30...	.28	1.9	8.3	.200	<1	<100	50	<1	<1	<10
FEB 26...	.30	1.5	6.5	.080	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 19...	.33	1.9	8.5	.170	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
AUG 20...	.42	1.8	8.1	.150	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN
50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1989 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1989 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-77 sediment sampler since 1989. Automatic sediment sampler since 1989.

REMARKS.--Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a week basis. During high flow events sediment samples were collected by local observer.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 8,800 mg/L Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 950,000 tons (862,000 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.04 tons (0.04 tonne) November 28, 1994.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 6,060 mg/L September 22, 1998 ; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 583,000 tons (530,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.07 tons (0.06tonne) August 6, 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCEN-		DISCHARGE	CONCEN-		DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	
	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)
		(MG/L)			(MG/L)			(MG/L)	
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	14	8	.29	58	10	1.5	56	6	.98
2	12	8	.27	59	8	1.3	50	6	.86
3	26	8	.55	57	7	1.1	47	8	.97
4	16	8	.35	57	7	1.0	46	9	1.2
5	17	8	.36	56	6	.95	45	11	1.3
6	16	8	.34	56	7	1.1	43	10	1.2
7	16	8	.34	53	13	1.9	42	10	1.1
8	195	110	211	50	20	2.8	40	10	1.0
9	109	79	32	51	20	2.8	40	9	.98
10	28	31	2.3	2340	1090	10800	40	9	.94
11	20	31	1.7	339	215	210	40	8	.89
12	50	49	8.4	150	64	28	40	8	.83
13	117	89	38	105	17	4.9	38	7	.68
14	6890	2480	83700	88	16	3.9	37	6	.57
15	2390	1050	7470	76	17	3.4	37	5	.50
16	1030	536	1700	69	16	2.9	36	5	.48
17	775	384	1450	68	12	2.2	38	5	.51
18	672	388	854	69	9	1.6	40	5	.55
19	244	148	101	65	8	1.3	36	6	.61
20	153	73	31	62	9	1.6	34	8	.72
21	122	37	12	61	12	2.0	42	10	1.1
22	105	18	5.1	66	14	2.4	44	15	1.8
23	92	9	2.2	72	10	1.9	37	23	2.3
24	82	8	1.8	74	7	1.4	35	29	2.7
25	77	8	1.7	69	5	1.0	34	17	1.6
26	73	11	2.1	59	6	1.0	33	10	.87
27	69	15	2.7	55	8	1.1	32	7	.62
28	66	18	3.2	54	9	1.3	32	8	.72
29	64	16	2.7	53	8	1.1	34	9	.86
30	63	14	2.3	55	7	1.1	32	11	.93
31	60	12	1.9	---	---	---	33	11	.99
TOTAL	13663	---	95639.60	4546	---	11088.55	1213	---	31.36

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	31	8	.71	26	13	.90	29	4	.34
2	28	6	.49	27	14	1.0	28	6	.42
3	30	5	.41	26	16	1.1	28	7	.56
4	35	5	.47	33	17	1.8	36	8	.83
5	44	5	.60	4590	1610	31600	31	7	.59
6	210	534	847	444	268	369	31	6	.48
7	168	578	296	152	104	44	33	5	.46
8	135	105	40	563	218	1180	60	34	7.9
9	97	59	15	634	445	990	53	26	3.8
10	134	83	33	141	84	33	39	9	.93
11	80	62	14	90	35	8.8	32	9	.79
12	62	44	7.3	68	19	3.5	28	10	.75
13	107	102	31	58	25	4.0	26	11	.76
14	141	103	41	52	36	5.1	26	11	.76
15	77	57	12	76	38	7.8	26	10	.73
16	55	38	5.7	65	20	3.6	27	10	.73
17	47	37	4.7	53	10	1.5	23	10	.63
18	42	38	4.4	49	6	.82	21	10	.57
19	39	36	3.8	44	6	.76	23	10	.62
20	37	26	2.5	42	7	.75	29	10	.79
21	36	18	1.7	39	7	.73	142	80	38
22	33	13	1.2	36	7	.64	66	45	8.2
23	32	12	1.0	35	6	.59	71	25	4.7
24	32	11	.94	34	6	.56	55	15	2.3
25	31	11	.93	33	7	.60	42	15	1.7
26	32	15	1.3	32	7	.64	35	15	1.4
27	34	21	2.0	31	7	.61	33	15	1.3
28	32	26	2.2	30	5	.43	39	15	1.6
29	30	19	1.6	---	---	---	53	30	11
30	29	14	1.1	---	---	---	292	567	801
31	27	12	.83	---	---	---	392	697	1270
TOTAL	1947	---	1374.88	7503	---	34262.23	1849	---	2164.64
DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	88	76	18	34	11	.95	66	50	8.9
2	58	63	9.9	35	11	1.1	56	55	8.9
3	54	54	7.7	51	12	1.7	44	61	7.2
4	44	50	6.1	35	12	1.2	43	48	5.5
5	35	47	4.5	36	13	1.2	39	40	4.2
6	31	52	4.3	37	13	1.3	41	35	3.9
7	32	77	6.7	32	13	1.1	45	29	3.5
8	62	64	11	228	239	565	36	29	2.8
9	49	52	6.9	160	358	226	33	32	2.9
10	38	51	5.2	84	22	5.2	35	35	3.3
11	34	50	4.7	50	2	.31	34	39	3.5
12	188	137	85	38	2	.21	31	43	3.5
13	135	119	44	34	2	.18	29	40	3.1
14	78	80	17	179	137	193	33	22	2.0
15	58	55	8.8	407	282	411	26	12	.83
16	59	42	6.6	115	139	44	24	17	1.1
17	65	31	5.5	85	101	23	25	32	2.2
18	58	24	3.8	64	94	16	31	51	4.2
19	50	20	2.6	109	86	26	30	49	4.0
20	44	16	1.9	73	63	13	21	46	2.6
21	62	13	2.3	179	129	73	20	36	1.9
22	61	14	2.3	159	116	57	45	26	4.0
23	48	15	1.9	68	56	10	52	26	3.9
24	42	15	1.7	53	47	6.8	30	10	.79
25	39	12	1.3	43	47	5.3	20	10	.53
26	39	9	.95	42	45	5.0	18	10	.51
27	37	9	.89	125	62	24	19	12	.60
28	36	9	.88	109	75	23	18	14	.68
29	38	9	.93	68	46	8.5	16	18	.79
30	36	10	.94	56	42	6.4	19	20	1.0
31	---	---	---	71	50	10	---	---	---
TOTAL	1698	---	274.29	2859	---	1760.45	979	---	92.83

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 Río DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	17	17	.78	13	3	.12	79	40	8.6
2	15	15	.59	13	3	.10	190	98	140
3	18	17	.88	12	3	.09	397	225	245
4	22	20	1.2	11	3	.08	424	230	280
5	43	25	3.2	12	2	.08	182	83	44
6	25	9	.65	11	2	.07	112	22	6.7
7	21	28	1.6	16	2	.09	148	20	8.0
8	17	26	1.2	28	21	1.8	161	20	8.7
9	15	23	.93	52	42	6.9	125	19	6.4
10	13	21	.76	34	34	3.1	110	14	4.3
11	13	19	.64	30	27	2.2	87	10	2.5
12	13	18	.61	20	22	1.2	68	8	1.5
13	12	20	.64	17	18	.87	58	8	1.2
14	12	22	.69	16	17	.72	74	7	1.5
15	12	23	.76	14	16	.61	73	12	3.8
16	15	21	.87	13	15	.52	102	48	15
17	16	19	.79	16	15	.63	66	8	1.4
18	16	17	.72	21	17	1.1	57	5	.77
19	18	16	.76	26	19	1.4	60	5	.81
20	32	25	2.9	23	10	.62	68	5	.88
21	116	205	91	25	5	.34	4830	1400	222000
22	36	26	2.6	634	510	1560	26900	6060	583000
23	20	9	.53	421	329	524	2410	657	5710
24	16	4	.18	1040	388	5200	652	234	430
25	16	3	.13	4270	902	13300	353	140	134
26	16	2	.10	991	526	1550	260	122	86
27	16	2	.09	312	142	129	319	145	246
28	21	3	.15	180	45	22	426	255	355
29	18	3	.16	135	42	15	411	258	434
30	16	4	.16	113	41	13	270	178	133
31	14	4	.14	81	41	8.9	---	---	---
TOTAL	670	---	116.41	8600	---	22344.54	39472	---	813309.06
YEAR	84999		982458.84						

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
NOV					
10...	0700	4970	2500	33500	96
JAN					
13...	0930	125	173	58	98
FEB					
05...	1215	6920	2520	47100	83
MAR					
31...	0630	461	792	986	56
APR					
03...	0800	46	54	6.7	90
MAY					
14...	0745	106	378	108	98
JUN					
02...	0715	52	35	4.9	85

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)
NOV 10...	0700	4970	2500	33500	48	60	73
MAR 31...	0630	461	792	986	21	26	32

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN 1.00 MM (70335)
NOV 10...	85	93	96	99	100	100	100
MAR 31...	39	49	56	73	86	96	99

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044000 RIO DE LA PLATA NEAR COMERIO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'33", long 66°12'28", at bridge on Highway 156, 0.56 mi (0.9 km) upstream from dam, about 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northeast of Comerio plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--139 mi² (360 km²), excludes 8.2 mi² (21.1 km²) upstream from Carite Reservoir, the flow of which is diverted to Rio Guamani.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
NOV 05...	0845	47	428	8.0	25.5	11	7.4	91	<10	K780	240
MAR 02...	1355	29	447	8.5	24.5	2.2	7.2	88	<10	240	210
JUN 01...	1350	72	363	8.2	30.0	4.5	8.4	114	<10	K840	K150
AUG 17...	1130	22	382	8.2	30.0	10	8.4	114	<10	K36	490

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 05...	160	52	6.3	18	.6	.90	150	<.5	30	10
MAR 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
JUN 01...	110	27	11	23	1	2.8	120	--	12	25
AUG 17...	120	29	12	26	1	4.2	140	<1.0	15	28

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NO3) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 05...	.20	23	230	29.2	53	--	<.010	.910	.030	.19
MAR 02...	--	--	--	--	2	--	<.010	.370	.040	.17
JUN 01...	.12	23	196	37.8	8	.936	.014	.950	.040	.30
AUG 17...	.15	29	228	13.6	18	--	<.010	.190	.030	.31

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 05...	.22	1.1	5.0	.140	<1	<100	10	<1	<1	<10
MAR 02...	.21	.58	2.6	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 01...	.34	1.3	5.7	.090	<1	<100	50	<1	<1	<10
AUG 17...	.34	.53	2.3	.090	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044850 RIO GUADIANA NEAR NARANJITO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'39", long 66°13'28", at steel-cross-bridge 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northwest of Highway 164, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from mouth and about 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northeast of Naranjito plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.0 mi² (10.3 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
NOV 05...	1200	3.5	441	8.1	28.5	2.7	7.6	96	<10	230	520
MAR 03...	0940	3.0	464	8.1	24.5	.34	6.0	72	<10	260	200
MAY 29...	1015	6.1	406	8.1	27.5	.53	8.3	106	<10	560	670
AUG 18...	1500	4.0	444	7.8	28.0	2.9	6.3	81	<10	K840	700

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD CACO3 (MG/L AS) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 05...	140	43	7.0	11	.4	1.3	150	<.5	7.8	8.7
MAR 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
MAY 29...	160	36	17	20	.7	2.8	140	--	22	26
AUG 18...	170	40	17	21	.7	3.2	150	<1.0	29	28

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 05...	<.10	20	189	2.04	--	--	<.010	2.00	.020	--
MAR 03...	--	--	--	--	1	--	<.010	2.20	.030	.24
MAY 29...	<.10	24	232	3.80	3	.828	.012	.840	.020	.25
AUG 18...	.12	27	254	2.75	1	1.59	.012	1.60	.020	--

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 05...	<.20	--	--	.220	2	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
MAR 03...	.27	2.5	11	.130	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 29...	.27	1.1	4.9	.120	2	<100	50	<1	<1	<10
AUG 18...	<.20	--	--	.160	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045000 LAGO LA PLATA AT DAMSITE NEAR TOA ALTA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'40", long 66°14'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.9 mi (4.7 km) at northeast of Plaza de Naranjito, 2.7 mi (4.3 km) West of Road 167, km 15.3, Buena Vista, Bayamón, 5.2 mi (8.4 km) east of Plaza de Corozal.

DRAINAGE AREA.--181 mi² (469 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1989 to current year. Prior to October 1994, published as Lago La Plata at Damsite.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago La Plata first construction phase was completed in 1974 and the second construction phase to provide the spillway with bascule gates was completed in October 1989. The maximum storage is 37,000 ac-ft (45.6 hm³) and its purpose is the supply of water for domestic and industrial use. La Plata Dam is a concrete gravity structure located across the Rio de la Plata, the dam has an overall length of 774 ft (236 m) and a maximum height of about 131 ft (40 m). The dam spillway is provided with 6 bascule gates. The spillway crest has a total clear length of 690 ft (210 m), an elevation of 155 ft (47 m). The Dam is owned and operated by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 170.90 ft (52.09 m), Sept. 10, 1996; minimum elevation, 107.95 ft (32.90 m), Feb. 21, 1995.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 168.13 ft (51.24 m), Nov. 10; minimum elevation, 126.88 ft (38.67 m), Oct. 8.

Capacity Table

(based on data from Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
98.43	2,760	164.05	28,550
131.24	11,360	170.61	33,160
154.60	22,720	175.52	37,040

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	128.79	164.67	164.74	157.62	155.48	164.95	164.00	163.34	165.06	160.09	152.83	164.96
2	128.38	164.52	164.57	157.35	155.18	164.74	163.99	163.10	165.28	159.87	152.48	164.96
3	127.96	164.36	164.40	A	154.87	164.54	163.90	162.94	165.38	159.64	152.12	165.43
4	127.55	164.18	164.20	156.86	156.36	164.33	163.79	162.72	165.41	159.41	151.76	165.31
5	127.44	164.01	164.01	156.69	160.46	164.16	163.63	162.48	165.30	159.22	151.39	165.36
6	127.35	163.83	163.80	157.19	162.11	163.98	163.44	162.28	165.12	159.25	A	165.50
7	127.06	163.64	163.59	158.35	162.54	163.80	163.32	162.06	164.96	159.03	151.30	165.63
8	127.47	163.43	163.37	158.69	164.87	163.68	163.31	162.52	164.78	158.76	151.23	165.13
9	128.51	163.21	163.16	158.76	166.85	163.59	163.22	162.95	164.70	158.48	151.18	165.23
10	128.37	166.39	162.94	158.93	167.22	163.42	163.09	162.94	164.52	158.23	151.05	165.25
11	128.11	166.80	162.54	158.95	167.31	163.22	162.89	162.79	164.32	157.93	150.83	165.19
12	128.08	167.11	162.52	158.83	167.29	163.00	163.36	162.57	164.11	157.62	150.59	165.08
13	128.63	166.70	162.28	159.18	167.22	162.78	163.70	162.34	163.92	157.30	150.28	164.92
14	166.00	166.69	162.08	159.66	167.23	162.65	163.73	163.49	163.73	156.95	149.96	164.79
15	166.62	166.66	161.83	159.69	167.25	162.43	163.70	165.09	163.50	156.63	149.64	164.56
16	166.02	166.58	161.60	159.56	167.23	162.21	165.19	165.32	163.26	156.30	149.28	164.45
17	166.48	166.46	161.37	159.39	167.13	161.99	165.28	165.43	163.13	156.01	149.04	164.33
18	165.85	166.40	161.15	159.20	167.02	161.75	165.22	165.38	A	155.72	148.73	164.17
19	166.14	166.31	160.91	158.99	166.88	161.52	165.11	165.53	162.78	155.41	148.41	164.01
20	165.97	166.16	160.66	158.77	166.74	161.45	165.01	165.55	162.53	155.38	148.15	162.71
21	166.15	166.03	160.42	158.53	166.55	161.72	164.94	165.75	162.40	155.63	148.05	166.23
22	166.16	165.91	160.23	158.26	166.36	161.68	164.91	165.99	162.24	155.48	149.38	160.38
23	165.75	165.82	159.99	157.98	166.17	161.60	164.81	165.93	162.14	155.25	151.12	162.92
24	165.68	165.75	159.72	157.71	165.98	161.48	164.64	165.79	161.95	155.00	A	164.46
25	165.60	165.68	159.48	157.43	165.78	161.34	164.48	165.60	161.72	154.68	163.94	164.95
26	165.49	A	159.22	157.16	165.60	161.13	164.28	165.43	161.45	154.40	165.08	164.32
27	165.35	165.39	158.94	156.89	165.41	160.92	164.17	165.44	161.18	154.28	164.72	164.95
28	165.24	165.23	158.67	156.61	165.19	160.74	163.97	165.53	160.92	154.03	165.24	164.82
29	165.10	165.06	A	156.34	---	160.92	163.77	165.45	160.65	153.77	165.17	164.25
30	164.97	164.89	158.12	156.06	---	162.37	163.57	165.30	160.36	153.47	165.13	164.18
31	164.81	---	157.86	155.78	---	163.87	---	165.15	---	153.15	165.06	---
MAX	166.62	---	---	---	167.31	164.95	165.28	165.99	---	160.09	---	166.23
MIN	127.06	---	---	---	154.87	160.74	162.89	162.06	---	153.15	---	160.38

A No gage-height record

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'45", long 66°14'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) west of Road 167, km 15.3, Buena Vista, Bayamón, 5.0 mi (8.0 km) east of Plaza de Corozal, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northeast of Plaza de Naranjito.

DRAINAGE AREA.--173 m² (448 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage 164 ft (30 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Regulation at all stages by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir upstream from gage. Gage-height satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2.0	7.2	2.0	.00	.18	.04	1.0	1.8	4.1	1.6	1.4	2.8
2	2.0	7.3	2.0	.00	.39	.04	1.6	2.0	4.7	1.3	1.3	8.2
3	1.6	5.6	2.1	.00	.43	.16	1.6	2.1	3.8	1.7	1.2	195
4	1.6	5.5	1.9	.00	2.2	.42	1.7	2.0	2.0	1.7	.96	427
5	1.6	6.0	1.8	.00	6570	.28	2.4	1.3	2.4	1.6	.22	136
6	2.0	6.0	1.7	.05	.55	.23	1.6	1.1	2.5	2.5	.01	3.0
7	2.2	5.9	1.1	.12	.09	.24	2.3	1.1	2.6	1.8	1.1	2.9
8	2.2	5.4	.82	.03	.02	.31	3.2	1.6	2.5	1.6	.68	300
9	2.2	5.0	.73	.01	170	.32	2.9	2.0	2.5	1.6	.03	3.5
10	2.0	1820	.90	.01	.01	.84	2.7	2.0	2.6	1.5	.00	2.6
11	2.0	293	1.2	.02	.00	.91	2.5	1.7	2.0	1.5	.00	2.8
12	2.4	4.8	1.2	.06	.91	1.3	3.8	1.3	2.1	1.6	.00	2.5
13	2.5	144	1.0	.08	.10	1.3	5.2	1.2	2.2	1.8	.02	2.5
14	853	3.1	.91	.13	.00	1.2	4.8	2.0	2.3	2.0	.00	2.4
15	e11	3.0	.60	.08	.00	.89	2.2	2.0	1.8	2.5	.00	48
16	e2.0	3.1	.24	.46	.00	.83	89	2.2	2.2	2.4	.00	42
17	e134	3.0	.27	.55	.00	1.2	2.4	2.5	3.0	2.8	.04	1.8
18	e.11	3.6	.58	.55	.00	1.2	1.8	2.6	2.1	2.8	.01	1.9
19	e.05	4.3	.42	.57	.00	1.8	1.8	2.4	2.0	2.4	.00	1.9
20	e2.8	4.4	.28	.63	.00	1.2	1.9	.64	2.2	2.6	.00	399
21	e11	4.5	.25	.66	.00	1.1	2.0	.60	2.3	2.3	.01	3930
22	10	2.8	.18	.66	.00	1.1	1.9	.72	1.8	2.3	.00	e75700
23	85	2.4	.12	.66	.00	1.1	2.0	.87	1.7	2.7	.00	e25300
24	8.5	2.0	.13	.66	.00	.97	2.2	.94	1.6	2.7	.25	e777
25	7.0	2.2	.25	.66	.02	1.1	2.1	.97	1.8	2.1	2880	e646
26	7.2	2.4	.27	.65	.04	1.8	2.2	1.5	2.0	1.4	1100	e688
27	7.1	3.2	.27	.60	.23	1.2	2.0	1.5	2.0	2.0	642	e69
28	7.2	4.2	.29	.72	.04	1.1	1.4	2.0	1.7	1.4	330	e937
29	6.8	2.2	.02	.81	---	1.2	1.4	2.2	1.5	1.1	141	e1160
30	6.8	2.0	.00	.85	---	1.3	1.4	2.8	1.8	1.3	46	e729
31	7.0	---	.00	.70	---	1.8	---	4.8	---	1.4	3.7	---
TOTAL	1192.86	2368.1	23.53	10.98	6745.21	28.48	155.0	54.44	69.8	60.0	5149.93	111521.8
MEAN	38.5	78.9	.76	.35	241	.92	5.17	1.76	2.33	1.94	166	3717
MAX	853	1820	2.1	.85	6570	1.8	89	4.8	4.7	2.8	2880	75700
MIN	.05	2.0	.00	.00	.00	.04	1.0	.60	1.5	1.1	.00	1.8
AC-FT	2370	4700	47	22	13380	56	307	108	138	119	10210	221200
CFSM	.22	.46	.00	.00	1.39	.01	.03	.01	.01	.01	.96	21.5
IN.	.26	.51	.01	.00	1.45	.01	.03	.01	.02	.01	1.11	24.01

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998		
MEAN	171	75.2	35.5	216	59.6	15.9	31.4	109	38.4	64.9	43.4	1386
MAX	1107	225	161	1581	241	83.2	231	494	220	384	166	8046
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1998	1990	1993	1993	1993	1993	1998	1996
MIN	.048	.004	.000	.19	.14	.022	.011	.000	.002	.037	.020	.001
(WY)	1992	1995	1995	1990	1995	1995	1995	1994	1994	1994	1989	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	4251.13	127380.13	
ANNUAL MEAN	11.6	349	190
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			714
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			8.62
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1820	Nov 10	75700
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	Jun 29	.00
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	Jun 28	.00
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			122000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			34.16
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	8430	252700	137300
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.067	2.02	1.10
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	.92	27.42	14.90
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.7	8.3	152
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.97	1.8	1.2
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.16	.02	.00

e Estimated

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN
50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR--Continued

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1989 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- Automatic sediment sampler since 1989.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 4,390 mg/L September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 1,810,000 tons (1,640,000 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.0 ton several days 1999.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 524,000 tons (475,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0 ton several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 2,470 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0 mg/L several days .

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	2.0	10	.05	7.2	19	.37	2.0	2	.01
2	2.0	10	.05	7.3	18	.35	2.0	2	.01
3	1.6	10	.04	5.6	16	.25	2.1	2	.01
4	1.6	10	.04	5.5	15	.23	1.9	2	.01
5	1.6	10	.04	6.0	13	.21	1.8	3	.01
6	2.0	10	.05	6.0	3	.05	1.7	3	.01
7	2.2	10	.06	5.9	2	.03	1.1	3	.01
8	2.2	10	.06	5.4	2	.03	.82	4	.01
9	2.2	10	.06	5.0	2	.03	.73	4	.01
10	2.0	10	.05	1820	49	372	.90	4	.01
11	2.0	8	.04	293	21	32	1.2	3	.01
12	2.4	6	.04	4.8	11	.15	1.2	3	.01
13	2.5	6	.04	144	16	18	1.0	3	.01
14	853	31	119	3.1	8	.07	.91	3	.01
15	e11	12	e45	3.0	7	.05	.60	2	<.01
16	e2.0	10	e.05	3.1	5	.05	.24	2	<.01
17	e134	22	e11	3.0	5	.04	.27	2	<.01
18	e.11	10	e.01	3.6	4	.04	.58	2	<.01
19	e.05	10	e.01	4.3	3	.04	.42	2	<.01
20	e2.8	11	e.08	4.4	3	.03	.28	2	<.01
21	e11	11	e.32	4.5	2	.03	.25	2	<.01
22	10	11	.30	2.8	2	.01	.18	1	<.01
23	85	31	18	2.4	1	.01	.12	1	<.01
24	8.5	3	.08	2.0	1	.01	.13	1	<.01
25	7.0	2	.04	2.2	1	.01	.25	1	<.01
26	7.2	2	.04	2.4	1	.01	.27	1	<.01
27	7.1	6	.11	3.2	1	.01	.27	1	<.01
28	7.2	18	.36	4.2	1	.01	.29	1	<.01
29	6.8	20	.38	2.2	1	.01	.02	1	<.01
30	6.8	20	.37	2.0	2	.01	.00	0	.00
31	7.0	19	.37	---	---	---	.00	0	.00
TOTAL	1192.86	---	196.14	2368.1	---	424.14	23.53	---	0.29

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR--Continued
 SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	.00	0	.00	.18	1	<.01	.04	1	<.01
2	.00	0	.00	.39	1	<.01	.04	1	<.01
3	.00	0	.00	.43	1	<.01	.16	1	<.01
4	.00	0	.00	2.2	2	.07	.42	1	<.01
5	.00	0	.00	6570	223	10100	.28	1	<.01
6	.05	1	<.01	.55	3	<.01	.23	1	<.01
7	.12	1	<.01	.09	2	<.01	.24	1	<.01
8	.03	2	<.01	.02	1	<.01	.31	1	<.01
9	.01	2	<.01	170	32	35	.32	1	<.01
10	.01	2	<.01	.01	1	<.01	.84	1	<.01
11	.02	2	<.01	.00	1	.00	.91	1	<.01
12	.06	2	<.01	.91	1	<.01	1.3	1	<.01
13	.08	2	<.01	.10	1	<.01	1.3	1	<.01
14	.13	2	<.01	.00	1	.00	1.2	1	<.01
15	.08	2	<.01	.00	0	.00	.89	1	<.01
16	.46	2	<.01	.00	0	.00	.83	1	<.01
17	.55	2	<.01	.00	0	.00	1.2	1	<.01
18	.55	2	<.01	.00	0	.00	1.2	1	<.01
19	.57	2	<.01	.00	0	.00	1.8	1	<.01
20	.63	2	<.01	.00	0	.00	1.2	1	<.01
21	.66	2	<.01	.00	0	.00	1.1	1	<.01
22	.66	1	<.01	.00	1	.00	1.1	1	<.01
23	.66	1	<.01	.00	0	.00	1.1	1	<.01
24	.66	1	<.01	.00	1	.00	.97	1	<.01
25	.66	1	<.01	.02	1	<.01	1.1	1	<.01
26	.65	1	<.01	.04	1	<.01	1.8	1	<.01
27	.60	1	<.01	.23	1	<.01	1.2	1	<.01
28	.72	1	<.01	.04	1	<.01	1.1	1	<.01
29	.81	1	<.01	---	---	---	1.2	1	<.01
30	.85	1	<.01	---	---	---	1.3	1	<.01
31	.70	1	<.01	---	---	---	1.8	1	<.01
TOTAL	10.98	---	0.26	6745.21	---	10135.20	28.48	---	0.31

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	1.0	1	<.01	1.8	6	.03	4.1	2	.03
2	1.6	1	<.01	2.0	6	.03	4.7	3	.03
3	1.6	1	<.01	2.1	6	.04	3.8	3	.03
4	1.7	2	.01	2.0	6	.04	2.0	3	.01
5	2.4	3	.02	1.3	7	.02	2.4	3	.02
6	1.6	5	.02	1.1	7	.02	2.5	3	.02
7	2.3	9	.06	1.1	6	.02	2.6	3	.02
8	3.2	13	.12	1.6	6	.03	2.5	3	.02
9	2.9	13	.10	2.0	5	.03	2.5	3	.02
10	2.7	13	.09	2.0	5	.03	2.6	3	.02
11	2.5	12	.08	1.7	5	.02	2.0	3	.02
12	3.8	12	.12	1.3	4	.01	2.1	3	.02
13	5.2	11	.16	1.2	4	.01	2.2	3	.02
14	4.8	11	.14	2.0	4	.02	2.3	3	.02
15	2.2	10	.06	2.0	3	.02	1.8	3	.01
16	89	17	6.2	2.2	3	.02	2.2	3	.02
17	2.4	9	.06	2.5	3	.02	3.0	3	.02
18	1.8	8	.04	2.6	3	.02	2.1	3	.01
19	1.8	7	.03	2.4	2	.01	2.0	3	.01
20	1.9	6	.03	.64	2	<.01	2.2	3	.01
21	2.0	5	.03	.60	2	<.01	2.3	3	.02
22	1.9	5	.02	.72	2	<.01	1.8	3	.01
23	2.0	4	.02	.87	2	<.01	1.7	2	.01
24	2.2	4	.02	.94	2	<.01	1.6	2	.01
25	2.1	4	.03	.97	2	.01	1.8	2	.01
26	2.2	5	.03	1.5	2	.01	2.0	2	.01
27	2.0	5	.03	1.5	2	.01	2.0	2	.01
28	1.4	5	.02	2.0	2	.01	1.7	2	.01
29	1.4	5	.02	2.2	2	.01	1.5	2	.01
30	1.4	5	.02	2.8	2	.02	1.8	2	.01
31	---	---	---	4.8	2	.03	---	---	---
TOTAL	155.0	---	7.61	54.44	---	0.59	69.8	---	0.49

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR--Continued
 SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	1.6	2	.01	1.4	6	.02	2.8	9	.07
2	1.3	2	.01	1.3	6	.02	8.2	10	.40
3	1.7	2	.01	1.2	6	.02	---	22	14
4	1.7	2	.01	.96	6	.01	419	17	32
5	1.6	2	.01	.22	6	<.01	133	12	4.6
6	2.5	2	.01	.01	6	<.01	.46	10	.08
7	1.8	2	.01	1.1	6	.02	.42	9	.07
8	1.6	2	.01	.68	6	.01	296	10	117
9	1.6	2	.01	.03	6	<.01	.70	13	.12
10	1.5	2	.01	.00	0	.00	.29	12	.08
11	1.5	2	.01	.00	0	.00	.37	11	.08
12	1.6	2	.01	.00	6	.00	.28	10	.07
13	1.8	2	.01	.02	6	<.01	.28	9	.06
14	2.0	2	.01	.00	0	.00	.24	9	.05
15	2.5	2	.01	.00	0	.00	47	14	3.2
16	2.4	2	.01	.00	0	.00	40	19	2.4
17	2.8	2	.02	.04	6	<.01	.05	10	.05
18	2.8	3	.02	.01	6	<.01	.06	6	.03
19	2.4	3	.02	.00	6	.00	.04	5	.03
20	2.6	3	.02	.00	6	.00	398	9	35
21	2.3	4	.02	.01	6	<.01	3930	106	8050
22	2.3	4	.03	.00	6	.00	e75700	2470	e524000
23	2.7	4	.03	.00	0	.00	e25300	749	e175000
24	2.7	5	.04	.25	6	<.01	e777	41	e362
25	2.1	6	.03	2880	51	606	e646	35	e301
26	1.4	6	.02	1100	11	587	e688	29	e320
27	2.0	7	.04	642	11	291	e69	15	e6.2
28	1.4	7	.03	330	10	133	e937	29	e491
29	1.1	7	.02	141	10	45	e1160	37	e587
30	1.3	7	.02	46	10	10	e729	32	e382
31	1.4	6	.03	3.7	10	.10	---	---	---
TOTAL	60.0	---	0.55	5149.93	---	1672.28	---	---	709708.59

e Estimated

< Actual value is known to be less than the value shown

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-	SEDI-	SED.
		CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)
NOV				
03...	1100	5.5	80	1.2
APR				
16...	1843	370	24	24
SEP				
03...	1146	123	26	8.6
04...	1931	1180	32	102
20...	2315	3840	54	560
21...	0644	3830	27	279
23...	1315	24800	704	47200

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR TOA ALTA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°15'39", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at downstream side of bridge on Highway 2, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) downstream from Rio Lajas, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Toa Alta, 11.3 mi (18.2 km) downstream from Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 mi² (539 km²), excludes 8.2 mi² (21.2 km²) upstream from Lago Carite, flow from which is diverted to Rio Guamaní. Area at site used prior to September 25, 1984, 200 mi² (518 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1959 (measurement only), January 1960 to current year. Prior to October 1984, published as Rio de la Plata at Toa Alta, PR; October 1984 to September 1988 published as 50046900.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 9.15 ft (2.789 m), above mean sea level. Prior to October, 1984, at site about 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream at mean sea level datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Regulation at all stages by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir upstream from gage. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Flow affected by water extraction for La Virgencita water treatment plant by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority of about 3.99 ft³/s (0.11 m³/s). Located about 1,000 ft upstream from station.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate discharges and elevations of major floods, as pointed out by local residents are as follows: Sept. 13, 1928, 120,000 ft³/s (3,400 m³/s), gage height, 37.4 ft (11.40 m); June 16, 1943, 82,000 ft³/s (2,322 m³/s), gage height, 34.4 ft (10.48 m), at site 1.0 mi upstream and different datum.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	39	29	26	25	22	24	37	19	21	34	22	69
2	41	35	24	23	22	23	29	20	24	34	20	63
3	33	42	24	26	21	22	24	20	27	30	18	172
4	142	45	24	22	38	22	21	21	25	e70	14	272
5	165	44	24	22	9370	23	21	21	21	34	13	482
6	95	31	25	60	670	23	19	20	23	55	e14	102
7	51	32	25	157	100	23	22	23	21	73	e62	72
8	40	28	25	39	68	23	55	26	38	28	110	252
9	49	27	24	33	279	22	27	22	46	24	33	255
10	35	1510	24	30	64	25	24	18	46	27	76	57
11	58	911	23	37	51	23	22	18	26	25	52	43
12	246	62	23	43	50	21	29	19	26	21	22	40
13	206	183	22	105	47	22	42	19	29	20	19	40
14	675	69	22	86	50	28	28	34	29	20	16	28
15	3110	67	21	33	52	28	23	91	25	21	16	27
16	3460	52	21	28	39	23	575	47	45	23	16	80
17	858	33	20	24	33	30	172	63	57	33	19	44
18	1750	32	20	24	30	26	45	77	289	66	35	30
19	425	54	19	24	28	26	41	31	89	53	31	28
20	213	29	19	22	26	23	41	26	35	65	19	25
21	182	176	19	24	27	25	55	24	35	66	36	2660
22	62	39	19	23	25	23	37	22	44	26	25	47100
23	140	30	18	21	25	21	33	87	34	19	23	7990
24	79	33	19	22	24	20	32	52	29	46	82	594
25	38	28	21	23	23	21	39	28	30	24	3710	914
26	39	28	23	23	22	21	46	24	31	20	e1010	692
27	39	28	25	22	24	21	42	22	31	29	1420	295
28	37	27	25	22	23	20	e26	22	33	24	1120	886
29	33	28	25	23	---	54	e19	22	34	19	627	717
30	32	26	23	23	---	37	e19	21	34	20	174	805
31	31	---	25	20	---	216	---	21	---	22	95	---
TOTAL	12403	3758	697	1109	11253	959	1645	980	1277	1071	8949	64834
MEAN	400	125	22.5	35.8	402	30.9	54.8	31.6	42.6	34.5	289	2161
MAX	3460	1510	26	157	9370	216	575	91	289	73	3710	47100
MIN	31	26	18	20	21	20	19	18	21	19	13	25
AC-FT	24600	7450	1380	2200	22320	1900	3260	1940	2530	2120	17750	128600
CFSM	2.00	.63	.11	.18	2.01	.15	.27	.16	.21	.17	1.44	10.8
IN.	2.31	.70	.13	.21	2.10	.18	.31	.18	.24	.20	1.67	12.07

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1960 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1960	1961	1962	1963	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998																						
MEAN	456	415	308	183	133	96.7	178	332	157	143	243	444	4813	2015	1352	929	409	468	723	1939	847	690	1677	3173	1971	1985	1971	1992	1989	1969	1987	1985	1970	1961	1979	1996	18.8	18.4	14.8	16.9	16.0	8.31	5.07	7.63	11.4	13.2	16.5	19.2	1975	1995	1995	1995	1984	1983	1986	1984	1984	1977	1994	1976	1991

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR TOA ALTA, PR--Continued

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1998 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1960 - 1998	
ANNUAL TOTAL	37439		108935			
ANNUAL MEAN	103		298		255	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					824	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					31.5	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	3460	Oct 16	47100	Sep 22	68100	Sep 10 1996
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	11	Sep 6	13	Aug 5	2.7	Apr 17 1984
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	12	Sep 5	18	Jul 31	2.9	Apr 15 1984
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			104000	Sep 22	Not determined	Sep 10 1996
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			26.14	Sep 22	27.33	Sep 10 1996
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	74260		216100		185000	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.51		1.49		1.28	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	6.97		20.28		17.36	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	149		192		473	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	32		29		81	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	20		20		18	

e Estimated

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT HWY 2 NR TOA ALTA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°15'39", at Highway 2, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) downstream from Río Lajas, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Toa Alta, 11.3 mi (18.2 km) downstream from Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 mi² (539 km²), exclude 8.2 mi² (21.2 km²) upstream from Lago Carite, flow from which is diverted to Río Guamani.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 27...	1340	37	467	7.6	29.5	1.3	5.4	70	<10	K1500	860
FEB 18...	1135	31	514	7.7	27.0	2.2	10.6	132	11	2100	<10
JUN 15...	1500	25	501	7.7	31.5	.46	7.0	95	<10	K730	K20
SEP 03...	1205	60	494	7.9	30.0	3.8	2.2	29	13	2100	540

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 27...	180	53	11	23	.8	3.2	170	<.5	17	32
FEB 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
JUN 15...	180	56	11	26	.8	3.1	180	--	17	40
SEP 03...	190	56	12	23	.7	3.9	190	<1.0	16	34

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 27...	.11	19	260	26.2	5	1.14	.062	1.20	.070	.49
FEB 18...	--	--	--	--	2	.414	.076	.490	.020	.68
JUN 15...	.15	16	276	18.3	1	.592	.028	.620	.060	.69
SEP 03...	.11	20	279	45.0	8	.510	.120	.630	.420	.68

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 27...	.56	1.8	7.8	.100	1	<100	60	<1	<1	<10
FEB 18...	.70	1.2	5.3	.060	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 15...	.75	1.4	6.1	.080	1	<100	40	<1	<1	12
SEP 03...	1.1	1.7	7.7	.070	--	--	--	--	--	--

Figure 17. Río Hondo to Río Puerto Nuevo basins.

RIO HONDO BASIN

50047530 RIO HONDO AT FLOOD CHANNEL NEAR CATANO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'13", long 66°09'36", at Río Hondo Channel, 800 ft (245 m) below junction with Río Hondo, 0.9 mi (1.5 km) downstream from bridge on de Diego Expressway and 1.1 mi (1.8 km) above mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TURBIDITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLIFORM, FECCAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECCAL, PER (31679)
NOV 07...	1000	27000	7.2	28.0	5.8	3.7	47	110	4600	390
MAR 09...	0845	14100	7.4	24.5	5.4	3.0	36	57	K1700	820
JUN 10...	1215	1530	7.3	31.0	6.9	3.1	42	<10	500000	14000
SEP 15...	1345	441	8.2	31.0	4.7	6.0	80	<10	E3000	K11400

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO (00931)	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 07...	2800	200	570	4690	38	69	160	<.5	1200	9200
MAR 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
JUN 10...	97	27	7.3	13	.6	3.1	90	--	17	14
SEP 15...	130	31	12	27	1	3.2	150	<1.0	16	27

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)
NOV 07...	.45	5.6	16100	89	.068	.042	.110	1.10	.50	1.6
MAR 09...	--	--	--	14	.436	.064	.500	.660	.30	.96
JUN 10...	.10	19	156	7	.223	.047	.270	.390	.91	1.3
SEP 15...	.10	26	232	4	--	.014	<.020	.060	.78	.84

DATE	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)	IRON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS FE) (01045)
NOV 07...	1.7	7.6	.230	2	<100	1900	<5	2	33	610
MAR 09...	1.5	6.5	.110	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 10...	1.6	6.9	.260	<1	<100	860	<5	<1	20	440
SEP 15...	--	--	.090	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047535 RIO DE BAYAMON AT ARENAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'11", long 66°07'18", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left bank, 2.61 mi (4.20 km) southeast of plaza de Cidra, 0.56 mi (0.90 km) southwest from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Bayamón, and 2.70 mi (4.34 km) northeast from Central Cayey.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.45 mi² (1.16 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1992 to September 1993, October 1995 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 1,378 ft (420 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair, except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.08	.10	.08	.03	e.05	.10	.76	.05	.11	.04	.03	.09
2	.14	.09	.09	.05	e.05	.09	.58	.05	.09	.04	.19	.77
3	.10	.09	.08	.05	e.04	.10	.36	.09	.09	.05	.04	.49
4	.09	.09	.08	.07	e.55	.09	.28	.09	.09	.22	.03	4.4
5	.08	.09	.07	.08	e49	.09	.24	.06	.09	.06	.02	.41
6	.08	.10	.07	1.8	e1.4	.10	.14	.05	.07	.04	.09	.22
7	.15	.09	.06	2.3	e.61	.25	.16	.05	.06	.04	.10	.16
8	.11	.09	.06	.81	e7.0	.18	.16	1.6	.05	.04	.15	.19
9	.12	.09	.05	.44	e2.3	.08	.11	.32	.06	.04	.16	.23
10	.16	4.1	.05	.33	e.64	.09	.11	.14	.06	.03	.05	.23
11	.12	.57	.04	.21	.51	.11	.15	.08	.05	.03	.05	.11
12	.10	.23	.05	1.1	.46	.12	.29	.06	.28	.03	.05	.08
13	10	.16	.04	2.8	.37	.14	.22	.06	.18	.03	.04	.12
14	25	.12	.05	1.3	.56	.27	.12	.07	.07	.03	.03	.13
15	4.0	.10	.04	.35	.52	.23	.11	.08	.06	.04	.02	2.0
16	1.7	.12	.04	.21	.36	.17	.11	.08	.07	.04	.02	.37
17	8.0	.11	.04	.16	.43	.14	.82	.07	.31	.04	.03	.12
18	1.7	.10	.04	.05	.31	.10	.24	.06	.21	.07	.07	.08
19	.43	.11	.04	.04	.20	.09	.20	.17	.08	.07	.04	.09
20	.19	.09	.04	.03	.18	1.9	.28	.06	.05	1.1	.03	.11
21	.14	.36	.05	.03	.17	.90	.11	.06	.10	.29	.23	81
22	.12	.63	.04	.03	.14	.64	.09	.06	.31	.07	4.1	97
23	.10	.58	.03	.04	.15	.33	.07	.05	.09	.04	.50	4.0
24	.11	.54	.03	e.04	.11	.21	.07	.06	.08	.05	18	.79
25	.13	.22	.03	e.04	.09	.25	.09	.05	.07	.03	10	.43
26	.11	.14	.03	e.04	.13	.16	.14	.57	.06	.02	1.8	.37
27	.10	.11	.03	e.04	.13	.56	.19	1.3	.06	.10	.56	.33
28	.10	.09	.03	e.04	.13	.43	.17	.53	.06	.09	.38	.22
29	.10	.08	.03	e.04	---	7.7	.08	.29	.06	.04	.24	.18
30	.10	.08	.04	e.04	---	3.6	.06	.29	.05	.03	.14	.16
31	.10	---	.03	e.04	---	1.0	---	.18	---	.02	.11	---
TOTAL	53.56	9.47	1.48	12.63	66.59	20.22	6.51	6.73	3.07	2.86	37.30	194.88
MEAN	1.73	.32	.048	.41	2.38	.65	.22	.22	.10	.092	1.20	6.50
MAX	25	4.1	.09	2.8	49	7.7	.82	1.6	.31	1.1	18	97
MIN	.08	.08	.03	.03	.04	.08	.06	.05	.05	.02	.02	.08
AC-FT	106	19	2.9	25	132	40	13	13	6.1	5.7	74	387
CFSM	3.84	.70	.11	.91	5.28	1.45	.48	.48	.23	.21	2.67	14.4
IN.	4.43	.78	.12	1.04	5.50	1.67	.54	.56	.25	.24	3.08	16.11

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003
MEAN	.67	.66	.29	.55	.81	.27	.22	.62	.75	1.00	1.01	3.06
MAX	1.73	1.30	.63	.63	2.38	.65	.45	2.02	1.79	2.12	1.87	6.50
(WY)	1998	1993	1993	1996	1998	1998	1993	1993	1996	1993	1996	1998
MIN	.30	.32	.048	.41	.16	.097	.095	.10	.10	.092	.46	.20
(WY)	1997	1998	1998	1998	1993	1993	1997	1997	1998	1998	1992	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	147.05	415.30	
ANNUAL MEAN	.40	1.14	.86
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			1.16
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.31
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	25	Oct 14	97
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.02	Jul 3	.02
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.03	Jun 28	.03
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1150
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			7.89
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			.02
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	292	824	626
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.90	2.53	1.92
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	12.16	34.33	26.11
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.51	.78	1.0
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.11	.10	.16
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.04	.04	.06

e Estimated

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN
50047535 RIO DE BAYAMON AT ARENAS, PR--Continued

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047540 RIO SABANA AT VISTA MONTE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'28", long 66°08'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left bank, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southeast of Plaza de Cidra, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southwest from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Bayamón, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) upstream from Lago de Cidra.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.80 mi² (2.07 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1992 to September 1993, October 1995 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 1,345 ft (410 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.18	.50	.31	e.30	.28	.34	.70	.31	.29	.18	.21	.49
2	.20	.50	.31	e.31	.27	.34	.55	.30	.28	.18	.23	2.5
3	.17	.56	.31	e.30	.24	.36	.44	.42	.27	.18	.21	2.0
4	.16	.49	.29	e.31	1.1	.37	.40	.36	.28	.32	.22	4.3
5	.16	.61	.32	e.32	67	.36	.39	.32	.28	.20	.22	1.2
6	.16	.47	.29	e.62	2.6	.34	.38	.31	.25	.18	.36	.86
7	.45	.46	.29	e1.0	1.3	.43	3.1	.32	.25	.18	.38	.75
8	.25	.46	.29	e.39	9.8	.37	.61	2.4	.24	.16	.33	.76
9	.19	.61	.28	e.32	3.3	.29	.41	1.1	.30	.15	.38	.62
10	.19	10	.29	e.31	1.3	.31	.37	.62	.24	.14	.28	.60
11	.30	.87	.29	e.30	.93	.34	.55	.54	.23	.12	.26	.50
12	.22	.65	.30	e.30	.77	.36	.67	.47	.64	.10	.34	.45
13	13	.56	.32	e.45	.68	.36	.50	.56	.43	.09	.25	.43
14	54	.51	.32	e.44	.87	.43	.45	.61	.29	.09	.24	.41
15	11	.47	.32	e.33	.75	.35	.45	.48	.26	.25	.41	.88
16	4.5	.46	.33	e.30	.67	.34	.59	.43	.26	.17	.24	.45
17	37	.46	.36	.29	.71	.30	.82	.41	.36	.16	.31	.41
18	6.5	.48	.32	.27	.60	.34	.64	.53	.28	1.2	.85	.40
19	2.2	.45	.31	.26	.56	.29	.58	.46	.28	.24	.35	.41
20	1.5	.46	.33	.26	.53	2.0	.52	.42	.25	5.5	.47	.48
21	1.1	.54	.36	.26	.52	.59	.42	.38	.47	.84	1.7	138
22	.94	.86	.34	.26	.48	.43	.41	.37	.43	.37	9.7	219
23	.83	.97	e.31	.26	.47	.36	.39	.43	.27	.76	1.3	20
24	.70	.96	e.31	.26	.48	.35	.35	.37	.25	.53	23	5.4
25	.66	.50	e.30	.29	.44	.38	.34	.38	.23	.27	17	3.2
26	.62	.47	e.30	.26	.42	.32	.49	1.2	.23	.23	6.5	3.4
27	.55	.39	e.30	.24	.34	.55	.42	1.6	.22	.96	2.4	5.2
28	.53	.35	e.30	.24	.49	.35	.38	.47	.22	.82	1.9	3.1
29	.51	.33	e.30	.24	---	3.9	.33	.53	.22	.29	1.1	2.1
30	.49	.33	e.30	.22	---	14	.32	.38	.20	.25	.76	1.7
31	.49	---	e.30	.24	---	1.6	---	.32	---	.22	.54	---
TOTAL	139.75	25.73	9.60	10.15	97.90	31.45	16.97	17.80	8.70	15.33	72.44	420.00
MEAN	4.51	.86	.31	.33	3.50	1.01	.57	.57	.29	.49	2.34	14.0
MAX	54	10	.36	1.0	67	14	3.1	2.4	.64	5.5	23	219
MIN	.16	.33	.28	.22	.24	.29	.32	.30	.20	.09	.21	.40
AC-FT	277	51	19	20	194	62	34	35	17	30	144	833
CFSM	5.64	1.07	.39	.41	4.37	1.27	.71	.72	.36	.62	2.92	17.5
IN.	6.50	1.20	.45	.47	4.55	1.46	.79	.83	.40	.71	3.37	19.53

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003
MEAN	1.72	1.13	.69	.73	1.38	.56	.66	.93	.66	1.49	1.47	6.63
MAX	4.51	1.56	1.11	1.01	3.50	1.01	1.23	2.26	1.21	3.02	2.34	16.7
(WY)	1998	1993	1993	1997	1998	1998	1993	1993	1996	1993	1998	1996
MIN	.76	.86	.31	.33	.33	.15	.37	.42	.25	.29	.48	.25
(WY)	1997	1998	1998	1998	1993	1993	1996	1997	1997	1997	1997	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	322.70	865.82	
ANNUAL MEAN	.88	2.37	1.61
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			2.37
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.63
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	54	Oct 14	219
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.16	Oct 4	.09
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.17	Sep 30	.12
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2060
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			11.24
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			.08
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	640	1720	1160
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.11	2.97	2.01
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	15.01	40.26	27.29
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.0	1.8	1.4
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.43	.38	.47
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.19	.23	.20

e Estimated

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN
50047540 RIO SABANA AT VISTA MONTE, PR--Continued

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047550 LAGO CIDRA AT DAMSITE NEAR CIDRA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°11'57", long 66°08'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at Lago de Cidra Dam on Río de Bayamón, 1.9 mi (3.0 km) northeast of Plaza de Cidra and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad de Bayamón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.26 mi² (21.39 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago de Cidra was completed in 1946. The maximum storage is 5,300 ac-ft (6.53 hm³) and provides supplemental water to metropolitan San Juan. The dam is a concrete gravity and earthfill structure approximately 541 ft (165 m) long between abutments with a maximum structural height of about 78.7 ft (24.0 m). The spillway portion of the dam, length 131 ft (40 m) and crest elevation 1,322 ft (403 m), is an ungated ogee crest located 131 ft (40 m) from the right abutment. This dam is owned by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 1,328.09 ft (404.80 m), Sep. 10, 1996; minimum elevation 1,295.86 ft (394.98 m), April 22, 1995.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 1,325.07 ft (403.88 m), Sep. 22; minimum elevation, 1,304.37 ft (397.57 m), Aug. 20, 21.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
1,295	860	1,319	4,400
1,305	1,970	1,322	5,200
1,309	2,610	1,328	6,920
1,312	3,100		

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1313.57	1320.53	1318.23	1313.50	1312.50	1316.66	1317.01	1315.86	1312.62	1306.88	1306.95	1309.12
2	1313.62	1320.45	1318.13	1313.37	1312.30	1316.56	1317.01	1315.72	1312.45	1306.75	1306.87	1309.26
3	1313.64	1320.39	1318.01	A	1312.10	1316.48	1317.01	1315.61	1312.29	1306.71	1306.80	1309.13
4	1313.64	A	1317.91	1313.15	1312.23	1316.44	1317.01	1315.44	1312.00	1306.73	1306.68	1309.28
5	1313.65	A	1317.77	1313.01	1316.89	1316.47	1317.02	1315.31	1311.75	1306.71	1306.51	1309.06
6	1313.61	A	1317.61	A	1316.86	1316.38	1317.00	1315.19	1311.51	1306.71	A	1308.85
7	1313.64	1320.08	1317.44	1313.88	1316.72	1316.39	1317.31	1315.11	1311.16	1306.61	1306.42	1308.64
8	1313.67	1319.98	1317.28	1313.91	1317.58	1316.33	1317.30	1315.33	1310.91	1306.60	1306.30	1308.60
9	1313.69	1319.90	1317.16	1313.96	1317.52	1316.27	1317.27	1315.29	1310.49	1306.60	1306.18	1308.58
10	1313.71	1320.46	1316.92	1313.92	1317.47	1316.17	1317.22	1315.19	1310.28	1306.48	1306.03	1308.47
11	1313.82	A	1316.78	1313.90	1317.56	1316.02	1317.24	1315.08	1309.98	1306.35	1305.93	1308.33
12	1313.80	A	1316.62	1313.93	1317.52	1315.95	1317.24	1315.00	1309.79	1306.20	1305.84	1308.17
13	1315.58	A	1316.45	1314.01	1317.46	1315.90	1317.20	1314.89	1309.50	1306.11	1305.64	1308.05
14	1319.51	A	1316.27	1313.90	1317.56	1315.84	1317.16	A	1309.19	1305.90	1305.42	1307.95
15	1319.92	A	1316.08	1313.78	1317.44	1315.76	1317.11	A	1308.88	1305.74	1305.22	1308.12
16	1319.99	A	1315.90	1313.67	1317.37	1315.67	1317.11	A	1308.64	1305.66	1305.01	1307.99
17	1321.57	A	1315.77	1313.55	1317.32	1315.57	1317.10	A	1308.48	1305.63	1304.83	1307.80
18	1321.61	A	1315.63	1313.43	1317.24	1315.45	1317.06	1314.51	A	1305.82	1304.70	1307.56
19	1321.56	1319.57	1315.49	1313.31	1317.20	1315.34	1316.99	A	1308.13	1305.76	1304.52	1307.31
20	1321.46	1319.46	1315.35	1313.28	1317.16	1315.72	1316.91	1314.31	1307.94	1306.59	1304.37	1306.97
21	1321.38	1319.36	1315.23	1313.26	1317.13	1315.71	1316.81	1314.19	1307.76	1306.60	1304.52	1319.66
22	1321.31	1319.28	1315.07	1313.23	1317.09	1315.66	1316.69	1314.08	1307.56	1306.64	1305.66	1323.43
23	1321.20	1319.15	1314.91	1313.20	1317.05	1315.61	1316.60	1313.98	1307.44	1306.68	1305.64	1322.65
24	1321.12	1319.08	1314.75	1313.16	1316.96	1315.53	1316.51	1313.89	1307.48	1306.71	1308.30	1322.52
25	1321.04	1318.99	1314.59	1313.15	1316.89	1315.47	1316.35	1313.65	1307.31	1306.74	1309.51	1322.49
26	1320.96	1318.90	1314.43	1313.12	1316.86	1315.40	1316.37	1313.60	1307.37	1306.76	1309.81	1322.54
27	1320.87	1318.76	1314.29	1313.05	1316.79	1315.39	1316.28	1313.53	1307.27	1306.95	1309.76	1322.47
28	1320.80	1318.63	1314.13	1312.98	1316.74	1315.33	1316.21	1313.33	1307.12	1307.03	1309.78	1322.37
29	1320.73	1318.49	1314.00	1312.89	---	1315.86	1316.12	1313.14	1307.05	1307.03	1309.67	1322.26
30	1320.66	1318.35	1313.80	1312.86	---	1316.92	1316.00	1312.94	1306.88	1307.03	1309.58	1322.07
31	1320.59	---	1313.65	1312.72	---	1316.99	---	1312.78	---	1307.00	1309.39	---
MAX	1321.61	---	1318.23	---	1317.58	1316.99	1317.31	---	---	1307.03	---	1323.43
MIN	1313.57	---	1313.65	---	1312.10	1315.33	1316.00	---	---	1305.63	---	1306.97

A No gage-height record

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'04", long 66°08'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) downstream of Lago Cidra Dam on right bank, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) northwest of Plaza de Cidra.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.31 mi² (21.5 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 1,279 ft (390 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Regulation at all stages by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir upstream from gage. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.6	9.6	15	17	e32	25	18	e25	24	11	10	30
2	8.0	10	14	18	e28	25	19	27	23	11	9.4	32
3	8.2	10	14	18	e24	25	e17	27	23	11	10	25
4	8.7	10	15	18	e20	26	e16	25	27	10	14	22
5	8.3	10	18	17	e15	25	16	23	32	9.9	17	21
6	8.1	11	20	18	e16	26	e17	23	32	e9.8	e17	20
7	8.3	11	21	16	e20	28	16	21	30	10	17	20
8	8.2	14	20	13	e27	30	14	21	31	11	17	19
9	8.0	17	15	13	e13	29	e13	19	26	10	16	18
10	8.2	17	16	12	e15	29	e13	20	24	10	13	23
11	8.1	15	17	13	e14	29	e17	21	24	10	13	26
12	7.9	17	19	19	e20	23	e14	21	25	11	14	25
13	11	17	21	25	e24	23	e13	19	24	11	20	25
14	12	15	21	26	e27	26	e13	18	26	10	20	21
15	5.7	15	20	22	31	26	e15	17	23	11	20	22
16	5.7	15	21	24	30	27	e15	18	19	10	20	24
17	10	15	18	23	31	22	e15	18	19	13	19	27
18	16	15	18	18	29	27	e16	21	19	16	20	34
19	15	15	17	18	26	28	e16	25	19	16	19	34
20	16	15	18	17	25	26	e14	24	19	17	19	37
21	13	16	18	17	26	27	e16	20	19	16	14	105
22	12	22	18	18	25	28	e19	19	18	13	14	2050
23	12	26	18	19	25	28	e19	17	14	10	13	234
24	12	20	18	19	25	28	19	23	11	10	16	35
25	13	16	17	18	24	29	19	31	11	10	8.9	20
26	13	17	17	18	25	27	e27	32	11	9.7	6.4	21
27	11	18	17	17	24	26	e23	33	11	11	14	28
28	10	19	18	18	25	25	e25	31	11	10	7.5	26
29	9.8	20	17	22	---	28	e24	29	11	10	16	32
30	9.3	19	17	16	---	26	e23	26	11	10	24	33
31	9.8	---	18	24	---	19	---	25	---	10	25	---
TOTAL	313.9	466.6	551	571	666	816	521	719	617	348.4	483.2	3089
MEAN	10.1	15.6	17.8	18.4	23.8	26.3	17.4	23.2	20.6	11.2	15.6	103
MAX	16	26	21	26	32	30	27	33	32	17	25	2050
MIN	5.7	9.6	14	12	13	19	13	17	11	9.7	6.4	18
AC-FT	623	926	1090	1130	1320	1620	1030	1430	1220	691	958	6130
CFSM	1.22	1.87	2.14	2.21	2.86	3.16	2.09	2.79	2.47	1.35	1.87	12.4
IN.	1.40	2.09	2.46	2.55	2.98	3.65	2.33	3.21	2.76	1.56	2.16	13.81

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002
MEAN	14.0	21.9	15.6	18.4	18.4	17.5	13.7	11.2	11.3	14.2	13.7	49.6
MAX	22.7	41.2	30.4	59.6	36.5	26.3	24.5	23.2	20.6	39.6	29.2	233
(WY)	1997	1992	1992	1992	1991	1998	1996	1998	1998	1993	1996	1996
MIN	3.74	8.85	4.36	5.45	7.24	11.4	5.72	4.13	3.47	1.56	1.18	1.64
(WY)	1995	1995	1994	1995	1994	1994	1997	1993	1994	1994	1995	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1991 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	3776.3	9162.1	
ANNUAL MEAN	10.3	25.1	18.2
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			36.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			5.93
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	27	Feb 15	2050
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.7	May 13	5.7
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.5	May 11	8.1
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			4210
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			19.83
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	7490	18170	13180
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.24	3.02	2.19
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	16.88	40.97	29.70
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	18	28	27
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.5	18	12
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.2	10	2.8

e Estimated

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN
50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA, PR--Continued

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1991 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: November 1990 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1990.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediment samples were collected by a local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,670 mg/L Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 3 mg/L November 27, 1993 and June 27-28, 1997.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 27,700 tons (25,100 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.02 ton (0.02 tonne) November 21, 1993.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 801 mg/L September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 4 mg/L October 3, 1997.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 3,810 tons (3,460 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.09 tons (0.08 tonne) October 3, 1997.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	7.6	33	.67	9.6	49	1.3	15	36	1.4
2	8.0	11	.24	10	52	1.4	14	33	1.2
3	8.2	4	.09	10	50	1.4	14	31	1.1
4	8.7	6	.13	10	47	1.3	15	30	1.2
5	8.3	8	.18	10	45	1.2	18	30	1.4
6	8.1	11	.24	11	42	1.3	20	30	1.6
7	8.3	15	.34	11	36	1.0	21	31	1.7
8	8.2	21	.49	14	76	3.2	20	31	1.7
9	8.0	20	.45	17	104	4.7	15	32	1.3
10	8.2	18	.42	17	100	4.5	16	31	1.3
11	8.1	17	.37	15	96	3.8	17	30	1.4
12	7.9	23	.50	17	84	3.9	19	29	1.5
13	11	81	2.1	17	72	3.4	21	27	1.5
14	12	54	2.6	15	62	2.6	21	20	1.1
15	5.7	34	.53	15	58	2.4	20	14	.79
16	5.7	25	.38	15	57	2.3	21	13	.75
17	10	68	2.9	15	56	2.2	18	14	.65
18	16	193	8.4	15	57	2.3	18	14	.68
19	15	182	7.3	15	58	2.3	17	15	.73
20	16	160	6.7	15	59	2.3	18	17	.85
21	13	141	4.8	16	57	2.5	18	20	.95
22	12	137	4.3	22	55	3.3	18	22	1.1
23	12	134	4.5	26	53	3.8	18	25	1.2
24	12	144	4.7	20	51	2.7	18	28	1.3
25	13	133	4.6	16	49	2.2	17	27	1.2
26	13	116	4.2	17	47	2.2	17	25	1.1
27	11	100	3.0	18	45	2.3	17	22	1.0
28	10	78	2.2	19	43	2.2	18	20	.96
29	9.8	59	1.6	20	41	2.1	17	17	.78
30	9.3	45	1.1	19	38	1.9	17	14	.65
31	9.8	45	1.2	---	---	---	18	11	.53
TOTAL	313.9	---	71.23	466.6	---	74.0	551	---	34.62

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	17	10	.44	e32	16	e2.7	25	15	1.0
2	18	12	.57	e28	18	e2.1	25	17	1.1
3	18	16	.77	e24	22	e1.9	25	18	1.2
4	18	21	1.0	e20	35	e1.3	26	19	1.3
5	17	22	.98	e15	61	e1.3	25	18	1.2
6	18	21	1.1	e16	107	e1.3	26	16	1.2
7	16	21	.94	e20	170	e1.3	28	15	1.1
8	13	25	.89	e27	168	e2.0	30	15	1.2
9	13	32	1.1	e13	157	e1.1	29	15	1.2
10	12	40	1.3	e15	146	e1.3	29	15	1.2
11	13	39	1.4	e14	128	e1.2	29	15	1.2
12	19	36	1.8	e20	97	e1.3	23	14	.85
13	25	34	2.3	e24	69	e1.6	23	13	.83
14	26	31	2.2	e27	47	e2.0	26	16	1.1
15	22	29	1.7	31	46	3.9	26	19	1.4
16	24	26	1.7	30	45	3.7	27	24	1.8
17	23	25	1.7	31	46	3.8	22	29	1.7
18	18	22	1.1	29	50	4.0	27	36	2.6
19	18	20	.99	26	57	3.9	28	44	3.3
20	17	18	.78	25	64	4.4	26	75	5.3
21	17	17	.75	26	70	4.9	27	67	4.9
22	18	18	.85	25	52	3.5	28	40	3.0
23	19	17	.83	25	33	2.3	28	24	1.8
24	19	15	.78	25	19	1.3	28	15	1.1
25	18	14	.69	24	11	.71	29	15	1.2
26	18	16	.80	25	7	.46	27	19	1.4
27	17	19	.88	24	8	.54	26	23	1.6
28	18	22	1.1	25	11	.78	25	34	2.4
29	22	20	1.2	---	---	---	28	53	4.0
30	16	17	.72	---	---	---	26	120	10
31	24	15	.95	---	---	---	19	64	3.3
TOTAL	571	---	34.31	666	---	60.59	816	---	66.48
FEBRUARY									
MARCH									
APRIL									
1	18	51	2.4	e25	20	e1.9	24	35	2.2
2	19	40	2.0	27	23	1.7	23	43	2.7
3	e17	33	e1.3	27	23	1.7	23	53	3.3
4	e16	25	e1.3	25	24	1.6	27	62	4.5
5	16	23	1.0	23	23	1.4	32	39	3.4
6	e17	33	e1.3	23	20	1.3	32	22	1.9
7	16	51	2.2	21	18	1.0	30	25	2.0
8	14	77	2.9	21	16	.90	31	32	2.6
9	e13	80	e1.1	19	16	.81	26	28	2.0
10	e13	75	e1.1	20	15	.84	24	21	1.4
11	e17	69	e1.2	21	15	.84	24	17	1.1
12	e14	61	e1.2	21	15	.86	25	17	1.1
13	e13	53	e.80	19	15	.77	24	18	1.2
14	e13	44	e1.1	18	15	.72	26	18	1.2
15	e15	41	e1.1	17	17	.78	23	17	1.1
16	e15	38	e1.3	18	19	.94	19	17	.89
17	e15	40	e1.3	18	19	.91	19	17	.90
18	e16	44	e1.3	21	18	1.0	19	18	.91
19	e16	52	e1.3	25	17	1.1	19	18	.92
20	e14	62	e1.2	24	11	.74	19	19	.95
21	e16	66	e1.3	20	7	.38	19	18	.92
22	e19	76	e1.3	19	10	.53	18	17	.83
23	e19	77	e1.3	17	20	.91	14	13	.51
24	19	60	e1.3	23	22	1.3	11	10	.30
25	19	42	e1.3	31	20	1.7	11	11	.33
26	e27	31	e2.0	32	19	1.6	11	15	.45
27	e23	21	e2.0	33	18	1.7	11	18	.56
28	e25	16	e2.0	31	18	1.5	11	17	.49
29	e24	13	e1.9	29	20	1.6	11	16	.44
30	e23	16	e1.9	26	23	1.7	11	18	.51
31	---	---	---	25	28	1.9	---	---	---
TOTAL	521	---	44.70	719	---	36.63	617	---	41.61
MAY									
JUNE									

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA , PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	11	21	.62	10	19	.50	30	82	6.7
2	11	24	.72	9.4	21	.54	32	58	5.0
3	11	20	.60	10	26	.73	25	39	2.6
4	10	15	.43	14	31	1.2	22	32	1.9
5	9.9	13	.35	17	27	1.2	21	29	1.7
6	e9.8	12	e.32	e17	22	1.0	20	29	1.6
7	10	11	.31	17	19	.88	20	30	1.6
8	11	14	.42	17	17	.77	19	31	1.6
9	10	17	.47	16	15	.66	18	27	1.3
10	10	20	.53	13	14	.49	23	24	1.5
11	10	22	.62	13	12	.43	26	32	2.2
12	11	19	.58	14	12	.44	25	44	3.0
13	11	15	.44	20	12	.65	25	46	3.1
14	10	13	.37	20	11	.59	21	46	2.5
15	11	12	.35	20	10	.56	22	45	2.7
16	10	12	.34	20	11	.61	24	36	2.4
17	13	11	.38	19	13	.68	27	28	2.0
18	16	10	.43	20	14	.76	34	21	1.9
19	16	9	.40	19	14	.71	34	16	1.5
20	17	72	3.8	19	12	.62	37	12	1.2
21	16	36	1.5	14	11	.42	105	801	1150
22	13	22	.78	14	103	3.8	2050	787	3810
23	10	18	.50	13	64	2.2	234	344	231
24	10	21	.58	16	46	2.8	35	241	23
25	10	26	.74	8.9	49	1.2	20	183	10
26	9.7	27	.72	6.4	72	1.3	21	145	8.4
27	11	35	1.2	14	109	4.3	28	170	13
28	10	28	.78	7.5	120	2.4	26	229	16
29	10	25	.68	16	123	5.3	32	304	26
30	10	22	.59	24	109	7.1	33	340	30
31	10	20	.55	25	95	6.5	---	---	---
TOTAL	348.4	---	21.10	483.2	---	51.34	3089	---	5365.4
YEAR	9162.1		5902.01						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
18...	1415	15	204	8.3	98
NOV					
08...	1515	16	108	4.7	96
FEB					
21...	1630	29	74	5.8	97
MAR					
30...	1625	24	285	18	28
APR					
23...	1100	16	85	3.7	87
JUL					
20...	1200	18	233	11	98
AUG					
29...	0850	8.0	127	2.7	95
SEP					
21...	2230	558	3080	4640	97
22...	0730	3150	667	5670	97

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA , PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)	
SEP 22...	0315	2280	1130	6960	39	56	71	
DATE	TIME	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70335)
SEP 22...	77	82	90	96	99	100	100	

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047600 RIO DE BAYAMON NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'39", long 66°08'39", at bridge on Highway 156, and 2.9 mi (4.7 km) west of Aguas Buenas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.5 mi² (47.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-65, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 30...	1000	13	274	8.1	24.0	1.5	7.5	91	11	200	780
FEB 26...	1045	24	244	7.7	23.5	8.8	7.9	96	<10	210	450
MAY 19...	1435	26	260	7.4	27.5	2.5	7.6	100	<10	470	K110
AUG 20...	1430	27	270	8.1	29.0	8.6	7.8	105	<10	K710	K1700

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 30...	39	8.6	4.3	13	.9	.90	98	<.5	6.6	16
FEB 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	87	--	--	--
MAY 19...	91	22	9.0	16	.7	2.7	96	--	7.5	18
AUG 20...	130	32	10	17	.7	4.6	98	<1.0	15	25

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 30...	.10	23	131	4.60	4	--	<.010	.750	<.010	--
FEB 26...	--	--	--	--	3	--	<.010	.680	.020	.19
MAY 19...	.13	21	153	10.7	4	.530	.010	.540	.020	.25
AUG 20...	.10	22	193	14.1	9	--	<.010	.560	.040	.26

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 30...	.26	1.0	4.5	.050	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
FEB 26...	.21	.89	3.9	<.020	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 19...	.27	.81	3.6	<.020	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
AUG 20...	.30	.86	3.8	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047850 RIO BAYAMON NR BAYAMON, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'08", long 66°08'13", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at rock quarry near Highway 174, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) south of colonia Santa Rosa and 4.7 mi (7.6 km) south of Bayamón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--41.8 mi² (108.3 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1964 to October 1970, June 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 98 ft (30 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Diversion to the Guaynabo water treatment plant, for municipal supply, made upstream from station (at Represa de San Juan). Flow is regulated by storage and release of water at Lago de Cidra (capacity 5,220 acre-ft), 10.5 mi (16.9 km) upstream. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	77	e5.1	e4.9	e2.7	e4.2	7.2	10	7.9	6.2	5.3	9.0	12
2	38	e5.2	e4.5	e2.5	e4.4	7.0	8.7	7.2	6.2	6.8	8.2	12
3	16	e5.1	e4.2	e2.6	e4.3	6.9	8.0	7.7	6.4	11	7.7	17
4	14	e5.1	e4.1	e3.1	e5.4	6.7	7.5	7.8	7.9	9.1	7.4	13
5	200	e4.9	e4.0	e4.0	e700	8.1	7.3	7.8	9.9	6.7	6.6	12
6	209	e4.9	e3.8	e38	e80	8.9	6.9	7.6	8.5	63	7.7	14
7	71	e4.7	e3.7	e27	e25	8.4	8.2	7.6	6.9	16	73	11
8	109	e4.5	e3.5	e22	e90	9.1	11	28	6.9	7.8	44	12
9	74	e4.5	e3.5	e16	e100	7.0	7.3	16	12	6.7	19	11
10	35	e200	e3.5	e22	e24	6.6	6.6	10	8.1	7.3	18	8.8
11	179	e36	e3.5	e13	e14	6.4	6.6	8.4	6.5	6.5	15	8.2
12	e155	e15	e3.5	e10	e11	6.3	10	7.8	6.0	6.2	16	8.1
13	e300	e9.6	e3.4	e17	e9.4	6.2	11	7.7	5.7	5.7	15	8.3
14	e900	e7.8	e3.3	e23	e8.6	10	8.1	87	6.4	5.5	13	8.1
15	35	e6.8	e3.3	e13	e12	8.3	8.1	34	6.2	5.6	13	8.8
16	e20	e6.2	e3.2	e9.0	e10	6.9	104	12	6.2	6.9	13	10
17	e16	e6.1	e3.4	e7.6	e9.0	7.0	22	11	61	8.0	24	8.9
18	e14	e6.1	e3.5	e6.8	e8.6	7.5	11	8.7	23	7.6	28	8.5
19	e13	e5.8	e3.2	e6.3	8.5	6.6	9.6	8.4	8.1	8.8	22	7.9
20	e12	e5.5	e3.0	e6.0	8.5	10	9.1	7.8	7.1	62	17	8.2
21	e11	e5.4	e3.7	e5.8	8.4	33	8.5	8.2	16	71	87	547
22	e9.4	e5.8	e3.8	e5.3	7.7	8.0	8.7	7.7	12	9.6	53	e3640
23	e8.2	e6.4	e3.3	e5.2	7.6	6.9	9.5	7.4	7.9	31	38	603
24	e7.4	e6.6	e3.1	e5.2	7.5	6.6	7.5	7.9	7.8	29	369	183
25	e6.8	e6.2	e3.0	e5.0	7.4	7.3	9.7	8.4	12	15	469	87
26	e6.6	e5.2	e2.9	e5.2	7.8	7.2	8.9	7.1	6.6	12	38	69
27	e6.2	e4.8	e2.8	e5.3	8.2	6.8	8.5	7.4	6.0	19	123	108
28	e5.8	e4.7	e2.8	e5.2	8.0	7.8	8.3	7.2	5.9	14	299	67
29	e5.6	e4.7	e3.0	e4.9	---	94	7.8	7.1	5.7	11	41	226
30	e5.6	e4.8	e2.8	e4.7	---	154	7.9	6.8	5.5	10	18	156
31	e5.3	---	e2.9	e4.4	---	46	---	6.4	---	10	13	---
TOTAL	2564.9	403.5	107.1	307.8	1199.5	528.7	366.3	382.0	300.6	494.1	1924.6	5893.8
MEAN	82.7	13.4	3.45	9.93	42.8	17.1	12.2	12.3	10.0	15.9	62.1	196
MAX	900	200	4.9	38	700	154	104	87	61	71	469	3640
MIN	5.3	4.5	2.8	2.5	4.2	6.2	6.6	6.4	5.5	5.3	6.6	7.9
AC-FT	5090	800	212	611	2380	1050	727	758	596	980	3820	11690
CFSM	1.98	.32	.08	.24	1.02	.41	.29	.29	.24	.38	1.49	4.70
IN.	2.28	.36	.10	.27	1.07	.47	.33	.34	.27	.44	1.71	5.25

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998			
MEAN	33.5	42.0	38.8	34.7	23.2	17.7	20.5	37.9	18.4	21.1	41.7	67.9																										
MAX	129	174	263	159	75.3	52.9	72.7	131	60.8	46.6	137	360																										
(WY)	1991	1970	1966	1969	1989	1990	1971	1966	1970	1970	1970	1996																										
MIN	4.30	7.91	3.45	5.30	4.75	3.58	5.36	4.85	3.68	4.01	7.47	6.02																										
(WY)	1969	1965	1968	1968	1965	1965	1965	1994	1994	1994	1994	1967																										

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1998 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1964 - 1998	
ANNUAL TOTAL	8132.4		14472.9			
ANNUAL MEAN	22.3		39.7		33.2	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					59.7	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					10.9	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	900	Oct 14	3640	Sep 22	8640	Sep 10 1996
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.8	Dec 27	2.5	Jan 2	2.2	Apr 19 1965
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.9	Dec 25	2.8	Dec 28	2.4	Apr 14 1965
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			17000		65000	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			19.36		29.07	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	16130		28710		24040	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.53		.95		.79	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	7.24		12.88		10.79	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	31		65		55	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.8		8.0		13	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.8		4.4		4.9	

e Estimated

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN
50047850 RIO BAYAMON NR BAYAMON, PR--Continued

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047990 RIO GUAYNABO NEAR BAYAMON, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'32", long 66°07'59", at bridge on Highway 833, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Río de Bayamón, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) southeast of Bayamón plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--73.2 mi² (189.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1964, 1971-73, 1976, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TURBIDITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (31679)
OCT 30...	0930	517	7.1	27.0	4.0	4.2	<10	5700	690
FEB 19...	0830	481	7.3	25.0	6.5	3.5	<10	2900	K1800
JUN 01...	0800	471	7.1	27.5	3.5	2.2	10	42000	4600
AUG 24...	0730	496	6.8	27.5	4.0	1.8	17	56000	51000

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO (00931)	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 30...	200	70	5.1	9.7	.3	3.3	192	<.5	7.7	16
FEB 19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	200	--	--	--
JUN 01...	170	46	13	30	1	3.4	180	--	11	35
AUG 24...	160	42	14	30	1	4.0	210	<1.0	17	34

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG C, SUSPENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)
OCT 30...	<.10	7.9	232	4	.802	.098	.900	.160	.36	.52
FEB 19...	--	--	--	27	.780	.150	.930	.240	.53	.77
JUN 01...	.18	28	275	12	.610	.130	.740	.200	.31	.51
AUG 24...	.16	28	294	11	.260	.050	.310	1.20	.60	1.8

DATE	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC, TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)	IRON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS FE) (01045)
OCT 30...	1.4	6.3	.190	2	<100	40	<1	<1	<10	250
FEB 19...	1.7	7.5	.230	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 01...	1.3	5.5	.240	2	<100	70	<1	<1	<10	370
AUG 24...	2.1	9.3	.330	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50048510 RIO DE BAYAMON AT FLOOD CHANNEL AT BAYAMON, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'29", long 66°09'04", at bridge on Highway 890, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) downstream from bridge on Highway 2, and 3.2 mi (5.1 km) above mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--71.9 mi² (186.2 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

REMARKS.--Prior to 1979 sampling site was 0.8 mile (1.3 km) downstream but was changed because of flood channel construction.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 30...	1200	20	492	7.4	29.5	3.8	8.9	116	<10	5100	230
FEB 19...	1030	20	462	7.2	25.0	7.6	7.5	89	<10	K18000	K1800
JUN 01...	1130	23	467	7.2	29.0	13	7.2	93	<10	K6400	60
AUG 24...	0915	33	429	6.8	28.5	9.6	5.9	75	11	36000	4800

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 30...	190	46	15	18	.6	2.3	195	<.5	45	20
FEB 19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
JUN 01...	180	46	15	27	.9	2.6	180	--	13	31
AUG 24...	140	36	13	27	1	2.8	180	<1.0	14	28

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 30...	<.10	20	285	15.4	40	.260	.020	.280	.100	.28
FEB 19...	--	--	--	--	6	.324	.036	.360	.160	.31
JUN 01...	<.10	28	269	17.0	25	.230	.030	.260	.070	.35
AUG 24...	.18	27	255	21.6	23	.350	.100	.450	.410	.49

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 30...	.38	.66	2.9	.070	1	<100	40	<1	<1	<10
FEB 19...	.47	.83	3.7	.080	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 01...	.42	.68	3.0	.080	<1	<100	40	<1	1	<10
AUG 24...	.90	1.4	6.0	.150	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048680 LAGO LAS CURIAS AT DAMSITE NEAR RIO PIEDRAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'23", long 66°03'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010005 at Lago Las Curias Dam on Río Piedras, 4.15 mi (6.67 km) south of University of Puerto Rico Tower, 1.6 mi (2.57 km) northwest from Escuela José F. Díaz and 0.8 mi (1.28 km) north of Escuela Cupey Alto.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.97 mi² (2.51 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1997 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Las Curias was completed in 1946. The reservoir has a capacity of 1,135 ac-ft (1.40 km³) at spillway crest elevation 315.78 ft (96.25 m) for water supply. The dam is earthfill and has a crest elevation of 327.3 ft (99.75 m). Masonry parapet walls continuous from abutment on each side of the 25 ft (7.62 m) wide crest. The dam is about 82.0 ft (25.0 m) high and 984.2 ft (300.0 m) long. The morning-glory inlet conduit spillway is located along the left abutment of the dam and has an uncontrolled capacity of about 5,000 ft³/s (141.6 m³/s) at reservoir elevation 321.5 ft (98.0 m). This dam is operated by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 317.01 ft (96.62 m), Aug. 11, 1998; minimum elevation, 314.15 ft (95.75 m), Sept. 30, 1998.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 317.01 ft (96.62 m), Aug. 11; minimum elevation, 314.15 ft (95.75 m), Sept. 30.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
284.7	154	314.3	1,078
298.2	462	317.5	1,232
307.1	770		

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	315.87	315.80	315.79	315.57	315.68	315.71	315.82	315.75	315.74	315.67	315.82	314.99
2	315.95	315.79	315.78	315.59	315.67	315.70	315.81	315.74	315.72	315.66	315.79	315.53
3	315.85	315.80	315.77	315.60	315.66	315.70	315.80	315.73	315.71	315.72	315.78	315.56
4	315.84	315.81	315.76	315.60	A	315.69	315.78	315.73	315.69	315.84	315.77	315.59
5	315.84	315.81	315.75	315.60	319.21	315.71	315.77	315.70	315.87	315.81	315.78	315.61
6	315.85	315.81	315.75	315.72	A	315.71	315.75	315.69	315.83	315.81	A	316.04
7	315.85	315.80	315.74	315.81	A	315.73	315.76	315.68	315.81	315.80	315.89	315.93
8	315.95	315.79	315.73	315.80	A	315.71	315.75	315.68	315.80	315.79	315.86	315.91
9	315.87	315.78	315.72	315.79	A	315.69	315.73	315.66	315.88	315.78	315.84	315.91
10	315.85	315.80	315.73	315.80	A	315.68	315.72	315.65	315.83	315.79	315.90	315.90
11	315.85	315.80	315.73	315.79	A	315.67	315.71	315.62	315.80	315.77	315.99	315.91
12	315.91	315.81	315.71	315.78	A	315.66	315.86	315.60	315.80	315.76	315.90	315.93
13	316.21	315.80	315.70	315.90	A	315.65	315.83	315.59	315.78	315.74	315.87	315.93
14	315.89	315.80	315.69	315.83	A	315.72	315.81	315.74	315.76	315.75	315.85	315.91
15	315.87	315.85	A	315.82	A	315.71	315.85	315.74	315.74	315.76	315.84	315.92
16	315.86	315.83	A	315.81	A	315.70	315.88	315.73	315.76	315.92	315.83	315.92
17	315.86	315.82	A	315.81	A	315.69	315.84	315.73	315.83	315.89	315.83	315.96
18	315.86	315.83	A	315.87	A	315.68	315.83	315.73	315.83	315.88	315.91	315.82
19	315.85	315.82	A	315.84	A	315.67	315.82	315.74	315.80	315.86	315.85	315.52
20	315.85	315.81	A	315.84	A	315.66	315.87	315.74	315.78	315.92	315.87	315.23
21	315.84	315.83	A	315.83	A	315.65	315.86	315.75	315.78	315.86	315.75	316.60
22	315.84	315.81	A	315.81	A	315.63	315.84	315.75	315.77	315.85	315.47	316.09
23	315.82	315.80	A	315.80	A	315.62	315.82	315.80	315.75	315.86	315.16	315.82
24	315.82	315.82	A	315.79	315.74	315.60	315.80	315.79	315.74	315.86	315.54	315.60
25	315.82	315.81	A	315.78	315.74	315.59	315.82	315.78	315.75	315.85	315.67	315.36
26	315.81	315.81	A	315.77	315.74	315.57	315.81	315.82	315.74	315.84	315.38	315.13
27	315.80	315.80	A	315.76	315.73	315.56	315.82	315.80	315.73	315.84	315.70	314.87
28	315.80	315.80	A	315.74	315.72	315.56	315.80	315.81	315.72	315.84	315.96	314.62
29	315.79	315.80	315.59	315.73	---	315.80	315.80	315.80	315.70	315.84	315.69	314.39
30	315.80	315.80	315.57	315.69	---	315.81	315.78	315.78	315.69	315.84	315.41	314.15
31	315.80	---	315.57	315.69	---	315.83	---	315.77	---	315.83	315.12	---
MAX	316.21	315.85	---	315.90	---	315.83	315.88	315.82	315.88	315.92	---	316.60
MIN	315.79	315.78	---	315.57	---	315.56	315.71	315.59	315.69	315.66	---	314.15

A No gage-height record

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'51", long 66°03'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, in the Riberas of Señorial Housing area, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) west of Highway 176 and 2.7 mi (4.3 km) southwest of Río Piedras Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.49 mi² (19.40 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.--March 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 98.4 ft (30.0 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Low flow is affected by discharges from water treatment plant of PRASA and others dispersed pollution points directly to the river. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14	e17	15	14	68	12	8.0	6.6	e11	e7.3	e7.8	13
2	13	e12	14	25	23	13	10	6.7	e7.1	e6.9	e7.4	16
3	14	e34	11	17	15	17	8.4	15	e6.9	e6.9	e7.3	14
4	9.1	e18	13	13	16	16	7.9	7.2	e6.9	e6.9	e7.3	13
5	9.1	e75	10	16	15	23	7.7	6.7	e6.8	e8.0	e6.9	12
6	13	e22	11	12	12	13	7.3	6.5	e6.6	e9.7	e6.9	12
7	e43	e11	10	11	13	14	7.1	6.7	e6.9	e12	e7.1	11
8	e25	19	10	11	14	16	7.2	6.5	e6.9	e19	e16	11
9	e22	15	11	9.7	26	13	6.9	6.6	e7.0	e11	e10	10
10	e49	18	13	9.1	15	12	6.9	6.5	e7.1	e9.9	e16	10
11	e27	14	17	23	17	11	6.9	6.4	e13	e12	e10	9.9
12	e17	30	12	10	29	13	7.0	6.6	e7.1	e7.3	e15	11
13	e60	122	12	8.7	20	12	6.9	7.5	e6.7	e5.3	e32	26
14	e54	25	11	8.9	15	11	6.7	6.5	e6.2	e5.1	e44	33
15	e23	26	10	8.6	13	11	6.6	6.4	e6.3	e7.2	e18	16
16	e22	27	12	8.6	14	11	6.7	8.5	e6.1	e11	e25	13
17	e18	37	10	8.5	12	11	6.9	6.3	e5.9	e5.6	e26	12
18	e17	31	9.9	11	11	31	6.9	6.0	e5.9	e12	e22	12
19	e16	24	10	10	14	11	6.6	5.8	e7.6	e11	e17	11
20	e12	23	10	9.4	e13	9.3	7.1	75	e5.7	e49	e18	10
21	e27	22	15	70	e21	10	7.1	e82	e5.8	e15	e68	12
22	e15	102	11	81	22	11	7.0	e17	e5.9	e6.6	e130	13
23	e19	20	12	63	12	8.4	6.5	e8.8	e9.9	e5.0	28	24
24	e13	21	37	55	21	8.6	6.6	e19	e12	e4.6	55	22
25	e16	13	13	24	20	8.7	6.5	e20	e6.8	e7.2	26	15
26	e70	10	108	16	19	10	6.5	e8.7	e6.1	e6.9	18	37
27	e38	15	36	12	12	8.3	7.0	e8.8	e6.2	e4.6	18	18
28	e199	13	52	15	11	9.2	6.4	e8.1	e6.3	e8.2	15	17
29	e83	10	74	14	---	30	6.5	e7.1	e7.9	e4.8	15	45
30	e33	36	50	12	---	9.9	6.5	e6.9	e19	e27	13	18
31	e35	---	19	15	---	8.6	---	e6.9	---	e12	23	---
TOTAL	1025.2	862	658.9	621.5	513	403.0	212.3	403.3	229.6	325.0	728.7	496.9
MEAN	33.1	28.7	21.3	20.0	18.3	13.0	7.08	13.0	7.65	10.5	23.5	16.6
MAX	199	122	108	81	68	31	10	82	19	49	130	45
MIN	9.1	10	9.9	8.5	11	8.3	6.4	5.8	5.7	4.6	6.9	9.9
AC-FT	2030	1710	1310	1230	1020	799	421	800	455	645	1450	986
CFSM	4.42	3.84	2.84	2.68	2.45	1.74	.94	1.74	1.02	1.40	3.14	2.21
IN.	5.09	4.28	3.27	3.09	2.55	2.00	1.05	2.00	1.14	1.61	3.62	2.47

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1988 - 1997, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997		
MEAN	24.4	21.6	14.9	14.8	12.8	11.0	11.9	15.1	11.6	14.7	21.7	27.6
MAX	57.3	59.8	40.5	24.4	23.6	19.5	23.9	47.2	24.8	38.0	66.9	71.8
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1991	1990	1993	1992	1989	1993	1992	1996
MIN	8.48	5.93	4.32	6.95	2.70	1.85	2.83	3.38	2.66	4.22	6.60	6.90
(WY)	1992	1996	1996	1995	1996	1996	1995	1994	1994	1994	1990	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1996 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1997 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1988 - 1997

ANNUAL TOTAL	6443.02	6479.4	
ANNUAL MEAN	17.6	17.8	16.6
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			24.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			7.76
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1650	Sep 10	1650
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.92	Jul 4	.84
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.97	Jun 30	.97
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		2170	5390
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		11.48	15.46
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	12780	12850	12030
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.35	2.37	2.22
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	32.00	32.18	30.12
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	34	33	34
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.5	12	7.5
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.3	6.6	2.4

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	46	11	11	7.6	3.0	4.5	5.2	4.3	3.5	3.8	5.1	e8.3
2	56	9.2	11	7.4	3.1	4.5	4.8	4.1	3.3	4.4	4.8	23
3	23	9.9	11	9.8	3.1	5.1	4.3	4.4	3.4	13	4.8	7.5
4	17	9.1	11	7.9	58	4.5	4.3	4.7	3.4	20	4.8	6.6
5	18	11	10	8.5	72	18	4.6	4.3	24	4.6	6.2	7.0
6	22	9.6	10	28	9.4	4.3	4.4	4.1	5.3	4.1	e8.0	201
7	18	9.9	10	33	7.7	8.9	5.7	4.2	4.6	7.8	e39	30
8	69	10	10	5.8	29	4.5	5.9	5.0	6.1	3.6	e11	14
9	24	11	10	5.4	13	4.0	4.5	4.2	28	4.1	e15	14
10	18	12	10	5.0	6.4	3.8	4.3	3.9	9.3	9.3	e37	11
11	28	11	9.9	4.5	6.6	3.7	4.4	3.9	4.3	4.1	e84	10
12	25	11	8.7	4.9	5.8	3.7	36	3.8	7.4	3.6	e31	11
13	52	12	8.9	30	5.3	3.7	9.6	3.7	3.8	3.6	e10	16
14	123	11	8.7	13	18	36	4.4	26	3.5	11	8.7	9.9
15	19	32	8.5	5.6	8.9	5.1	9.5	7.0	3.6	8.2	7.4	12
16	16	16	8.1	4.9	6.4	4.2	60	3.7	9.6	75	6.3	14
17	14	9.7	8.1	4.6	5.6	4.2	12	6.9	19	21	e6.0	20
18	13	16	7.6	17	5.2	5.8	6.1	4.4	11	22	e60	22
19	12	12	7.2	6.7	5.6	4.1	5.5	6.7	4.9	6.6	e15	16
20	11	11	7.1	4.9	5.0	3.8	12	6.0	4.4	22	e10	16
21	11	22	8.0	4.7	4.8	3.9	7.7	6.3	8.4	10	e28	e714
22	11	13	6.7	4.2	4.7	3.9	5.4	4.0	5.4	7.6	e11	e1030
23	10	12	6.6	3.9	4.7	3.9	5.2	29	5.0	8.2	e7.0	e49
24	10	14	6.5	3.8	4.2	3.9	5.0	4.9	4.7	17	e61	22
25	11	12	6.1	3.7	4.2	3.9	10	4.3	7.7	5.3	e50	17
26	11	13	6.3	3.7	4.4	3.7	5.5	9.1	4.3	5.5	e7.5	47
27	10	11	6.7	3.7	4.5	3.8	7.9	7.1	4.6	9.8	e30	22
28	10	11	6.3	3.6	4.5	4.5	5.1	8.8	4.6	8.1	e55	15
29	9.6	11	6.5	3.5	---	36	4.8	4.3	4.3	6.2	e18	25
30	9.5	11	6.2	3.5	---	10	4.7	3.7	3.9	7.1	e9.3	13
31	9.7	---	6.7	3.4	---	10	---	3.5	---	7.2	e8.4	---
TOTAL	736.8	374.4	259.4	256.2	313.1	223.9	268.8	200.3	215.3	343.8	659.3	2423.3
MEAN	23.8	12.5	8.37	8.26	11.2	7.22	8.96	6.46	7.18	11.1	21.3	80.8
MAX	123	32	11	33	72	36	60	29	28	75	84	1030
MIN	9.5	9.1	6.1	3.4	3.0	3.7	4.3	3.5	3.3	3.6	4.8	6.6
AC-FT	1460	743	515	508	621	444	533	397	427	682	1310	4810
CFSM	3.17	1.67	1.12	1.10	1.49	.96	1.20	.86	.96	1.48	2.84	10.8
IN.	3.66	1.86	1.29	1.27	1.56	1.11	1.34	.99	1.07	1.71	3.27	12.04

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1988 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	
MEAN	24.3	20.7	14.2	14.1	12.6	10.6	11.6	14.3	11.2	14.3	21.7	32.5
MAX	57.3	59.8	40.5	24.4	23.6	19.5	23.9	47.2	24.8	38.0	66.9	80.8
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1991	1990	1993	1992	1989	1993	1992	1998
MIN	8.48	5.93	4.32	6.95	2.70	1.85	2.83	3.38	2.66	4.22	6.60	6.90
(WY)	1992	1996	1996	1995	1996	1996	1995	1994	1994	1994	1990	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1988 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	5303.9	6274.6	
ANNUAL MEAN	14.5	17.2	16.7
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			24.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			7.76
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	130	Aug 22	1030
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	4.6	Jul 24	3.0
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	5.9	Jul 23	3.3
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			4700
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			14.75
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	10520	12450	12070
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.94	2.30	2.22
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	26.34	31.16	30.23
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	24	27	33
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	7.7	7.5
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.5	3.9	2.5

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1988 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: April 1988 to September 30, 1998.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- Automatic sediment sampler since 1988.

REMARKS.-- During high flow sediment samples were collected by automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 24,600 mg/L Sep. 18, 1989; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L November 18, 1988.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e165,000tons (e150,000tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.02 ton (0.02 tonne) June 9, 1994.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1997-1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,870 mg/L May 20, 1997; Minimum daily mean, 9 mg/L January 16-17, 1997.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 2,140 tons (1,940 tonnes) November 22, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.21 ton (0.19 tonne) January 16-17, 1997.

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,420 mg/L July 16, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 6 mg/L February 3, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 165,000 tons (150,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.05 ton (0.04 tonne) February 3, 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	14	130	5.2	e17	38	e9.4	15	158	9.0
2	13	115	4.3	e12	37	e4.3	14	124	5.0
3	14	124	8.2	e34	36	e66	11	86	2.6
4	9.1	480	1.7	e18	35	e15	13	114	4.5
5	9.1	69	1.7	e75	34	e187	10	77	2.1
6	13	115	5.5	e22	33	e18	11	79	2.3
7	e43	75	e72	e11	32	e4.0	10	81	2.3
8	e25	73	e26	19	30	1.5	10	83	2.3
9	e22	71	e18	15	27	1.1	11	85	2.5
10	e49	500	e91	18	179	24	13	126	7.6
11	e27	67	e32	14	141	6.1	17	181	9.8
12	e17	66	e6.1	30	513	93	12	109	3.7
13	e60	900	e176	122	1090	1710	12	91	2.8
14	e54	569	e146	25	291	20	11	82	2.4
15	e23	60	e20	26	318	27	10	73	2.0
16	e22	59	e18	27	423	48	12	54	2.1
17	e18	57	e15	37	516	69	10	17	.46
18	e17	56	e9.4	31	415	37	9.9	16	.43
19	e16	54	e5.2	24	134	8.5	10	15	.41
20	e12	53	e4.3	23	42	2.6	10	14	.41
21	e27	51	e27	22	36	2.2	15	100	4.8
22	e15	50	e5.8	102	912	2140	11	75	2.2
23	e19	49	e15	20	203	12	12	107	3.8
24	e13	47	e4.8	21	237	15	37	485	101
25	e16	46	e5.2	13	113	4.2	13	127	4.4
26	e70	750	e197	10	72	2.0	108	1090	1480
27	e38	460	e69	15	141	8.9	36	445	64
28	e199	985	e1760	13	108	4.4	52	569	146
29	e83	41	e197	10	63	1.7	74	753	187
30	e33	40	e64	36	466	75	50	730	208
31	e35	39	e69	---	---	---	19	168	8.6
TOTAL	1025.2	---	3079.4	862	---	4616.9	658.9	---	2274.51

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	14	118	4.6	68	899	529	12	20	.63
2	25	300	24	23	284	20	13	54	2.2
3	17	198	11	15	137	5.5	17	121	6.8
4	13	107	3.7	16	172	9.9	16	118	5.9
5	16	170	10	15	139	6.0	23	235	19
6	12	96	3.0	12	99	3.2	13	23	.77
7	11	84	2.6	13	113	4.2	14	87	4.1
8	11	79	2.2	14	138	6.5	16	125	7.1
9	9.7	74	2.0	26	339	45	13	54	2.0
10	9.1	70	1.7	15	121	4.8	12	24	.74
11	23	298	72	17	194	13	11	19	.57
12	10	89	2.5	29	358	44	13	16	.52
13	8.7	49	1.2	20	116	7.1	12	13	.43
14	8.9	27	.65	15	69	3.2	11	13	.36
15	8.6	15	.35	13	12	.41	11	12	.35
16	8.6	9	.22	14	25	1.7	11	12	.33
17	8.5	9	.21	12	10	.34	11	11	.34
18	11	63	4.4	11	10	.29	31	319	119
19	10	98	2.8	14	10	.38	11	12	.35
20	9.4	66	1.7	e13	11	e.39	9.3	11	.27
21	70	1030	276	e21	168	e13	10	10	.31
22	81	826	198	22	248	19	11	12	.34
23	63	911	201	12	35	1.2	8.4	17	.38
24	55	666	104	21	232	16	8.6	27	.63
25	24	257	18	20	176	12	8.7	44	1.0
26	16	136	5.8	19	146	11	10	89	2.6
27	12	110	3.7	12	23	.76	8.3	67	1.5
28	15	131	5.6	11	20	.62	9.2	111	3.2
29	14	138	5.8	---	---	---	30	997	302
30	12	105	3.5	---	---	---	9.9	106	2.9
31	15	153	8.6	---	---	---	8.6	87	2.0
TOTAL	621.5	---	980.83	513	---	778.49	403.0	---	488.62
DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	8.0	71	1.5	6.6	21	.38	e11	14	e7.0
2	10	140	7.0	6.7	21	.38	e7.1	15	e.99
3	8.4	133	3.1	15	185	25	e6.9	15	e.99
4	7.9	57	1.2	7.2	27	.51	e6.9	15	e.99
5	7.7	54	1.1	6.7	26	.47	e6.8	15	e.99
6	7.3	53	1.0	6.5	25	.45	e6.6	16	e.99
7	7.1	51	.99	6.7	25	.44	e6.9	17	e.99
8	7.2	50	.96	6.5	24	.42	e6.9	18	e.99
9	6.9	46	.86	6.6	23	.42	e7.0	19	e.99
10	6.9	41	.77	6.5	23	.40	e7.1	20	e.99
11	6.9	37	.68	6.4	22	.38	e13	21	e2.0
12	7.0	33	.63	6.6	22	.38	e7.1	23	e.99
13	6.9	29	.55	7.5	35	.97	e6.7	24	e.99
14	6.7	26	.48	6.5	28	.49	e6.2	24	e.99
15	6.6	23	.42	6.4	24	.41	e6.3	24	e.99
16	6.7	21	.38	8.5	92	3.6	e6.1	24	e.99
17	6.9	21	.39	6.3	24	.41	e5.9	24	e.37
18	6.9	21	.39	6.0	23	.37	e5.9	24	e.37
19	6.6	21	.38	5.8	21	.33	e7.6	25	e1.1
20	7.1	21	.40	75	1870	1530	e5.7	29	e.37
21	7.1	21	.41	e82	2580	e197	e5.8	35	e.37
22	7.0	21	.39	e17	171	e25	e5.9	41	e.37
23	6.5	21	.37	e8.8	35	e2.0	e9.9	49	e2.9
24	6.6	21	.38	e19	340	e11	e12	58	e2.0
25	6.5	21	.37	e20	335	e12	e6.8	69	e.86
26	6.5	21	.37	e8.7	81	e2.0	e6.1	82	e.86
27	7.0	21	.40	e8.8	78	e2.0	e6.2	88	e.86
28	6.4	21	.36	e8.1	78	e3.1	e6.3	86	e.86
29	6.5	21	.37	e7.1	40	e.99	e7.9	36	e.99
30	6.5	21	.37	e6.9	15	e.99	e19	200	e25
31	---	---	---	e6.9	14	e.99	---	---	---
TOTAL	212.3	---	26.97	403.3	---	1823.28	229.6	---	60.12

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

DAY	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997								
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	e7.3	51	e.99	e7.8	50	e.99	13	45	1.6
2	e6.9	46	e.99	e7.4	48	e.99	16	164	11
3	e6.9	43	e.99	e7.3	51	e.99	14	47	1.7
4	e6.9	44	e.99	e7.3	47	e.99	13	39	1.4
5	e8.0	45	e3.1	e6.9	43	e.99	12	47	1.5
6	e9.7	46	e.27	e6.9	49	e.99	12	57	1.8
7	e12	55	e7.0	e7.1	50	e.99	11	69	2.1
8	e19	59	e25	e16	160	e11	11	84	2.6
9	e11	60	e7.0	e10	70	e2.1	10	75	2.1
10	e9.9	32	e7.0	e16	150	e11	10	74	2.0
11	e12	58	e7.0	e10	65	e2.1	9.9	73	2.0
12	e7.3	51	e.97	e15	130	e2.0	11	109	3.7
13	e5.3	35	e.37	e32	750	e56	26	318	40
14	e5.1	30	e.37	e44	900	e380	33	423	56
15	e7.2	27	e.97	e18	181	e2.9	16	135	5.9
16	e11	60	e7.0	e25	351	e28	13	85	2.9
17	e5.6	40	e.37	e26	348	e28	12	58	1.9
18	e12	41	e7.0	e22	351	e28	12	41	1.3
19	e11	57	e7.0	e17	150	e11	11	36	1.0
20	e49	44	e380	e18	145	e11	10	32	.89
21	e15	33	e2.0	e68	925	e201	12	122	4.4
22	e6.6	25	e.97	e130	1000	e1700	13	128	5.4
23	e5.0	19	e.97	28	308	23	24	1150	344
24	e4.6	16	e.97	55	1530	524	22	351	34
25	e7.2	19	e.99	26	149	12	15	131	5.2
26	e6.9	24	e.99	18	59	2.9	37	842	341
27	e4.6	30	e.37	18	134	7.8	18	181	8.6
28	e8.2	38	e3.1	15	49	2.0	17	171	8.1
29	e4.8	48	e.37	15	49	2.0	45	900	382
30	e27	200	e23	13	49	1.8	18	194	9.6
31	e12	125	e1.8	23	194	23	---	---	---
TOTAL	325.0	---	499.91	728.7	---	3079.53	496.9	---	1285.69
YEAR	6479.4		18994.25						
e	Estimated								

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SED- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
NOV					
13...	0400	167	1800	812	92
22...	1420	365	10100	9950	55
DEC					
26...	1945	304	5500	4510	84
29...	1315	188	1040	528	83
JAN					
24...	1129	44	299	36	99
FEB					
01...	1145	170	6590	3030	68
01...	1248	446	6180	7440	83
MAR					
29...	1240	259	11100	7760	96
MAY					
20...	1831	211	6390	3640	92
JUN					
27...	1157	6.1	56	.92	97
JUL					
30...	2141	70	3870	731	91
AUG					
14...	1516	130	6350	2230	95
SEP					
26...	1016	178	6090	2930	93
29...	1400	100	8120	2190	94

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997

PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)
NOV							
12...	1155	125	5830	1970	39	46	55
22...	1500	1380	11600	43100	25	30	33
DEC							
26...	2030	996	10100	27200	18	25	34
MAR							
18...	1423	168	5560	2520	30	38	43
MAY							
20...	1516	274	9470	7000	22	39	49
JUN							
30...	1415	205	5310	2940	23	31	49
JUL							
30...	1713	79	5250	1120	35	45	58
SEP							
23...	1811	186	43100	21700	6	9	12

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN 1.00 MM (70335)
NOV							
12...	67	78	97	99	100	100	100
22...	41	48	59	72	85	96	99
DEC							
26...	45	57	72	83	90	95	98
MAR							
18...	60	75	86	94	98	99	100
MAY							
20...	65	78	91	97	99	99	100
JUN							
30...	65	79	94	96	98	100	100
JUL							
30...	72	83	97	99	100	100	100
SEP							
23...	19	29	58	75	91	98	100

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998									
DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE
	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	46	2050	1580	11	57	3.7	11	28	.81
2	56	992	445	9.2	10	.24	11	27	.77
3	23	434	28	9.9	26	.88	11	26	.74
4	17	242	11	9.1	10	.23	11	25	.71
5	18	265	15	11	51	2.0	10	24	.67
6	22	379	31	9.6	10	.26	10	23	.62
7	18	273	14	9.9	10	.27	10	22	.60
8	69	1400	1350	10	10	.27	10	21	.57
9	24	495	33	11	10	.29	10	20	.55
10	18	259	12	12	97	3.5	10	20	.55
11	28	534	109	11	24	.70	9.9	47	1.5
12	25	451	46	11	20	.61	8.7	18	.42
13	52	706	923	12	20	.61	8.9	17	.40
14	123	874	856	11	19	.56	8.7	15	.36
15	19	52	2.8	32	717	305	8.5	15	.33
16	16	19	.85	16	166	12	8.1	14	.30
17	14	18	.71	9.7	20	.51	8.1	13	.28
18	13	18	.60	16	114	14	7.6	12	.25
19	12	17	.52	12	23	.71	7.2	12	.23
20	11	16	.47	11	20	.59	7.1	12	.23
21	11	15	.44	22	271	31	8.0	12	.26
22	11	14	.41	13	34	1.2	6.7	12	.22
23	10	14	.38	12	34	1.1	6.6	12	.21
24	10	13	.36	14	112	5.7	6.5	12	.21
25	11	12	.35	12	34	1.1	6.1	12	.20
26	11	12	.33	13	61	2.5	6.3	12	.20
27	10	11	.31	11	33	1.0	6.7	12	.22
28	10	11	.29	11	32	.93	6.3	12	.20
29	9.6	11	.28	11	31	.91	6.5	12	.21
30	9.5	10	.27	11	29	.85	6.2	12	.20
31	9.7	10	.27	---	---	---	6.7	12	.22
TOTAL	736.8	---	5462.64	374.4	---	393.22	259.4	---	13.24

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998									
DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE
	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	7.6	12	.25	3.0	7	.06	4.5	43	.52
2	7.4	12	.24	3.1	7	.06	4.5	40	.49
3	9.8	70	2.5	3.1	6	.05	5.1	37	.51
4	7.9	56	1.7	58	1770	3250	4.5	32	.39
5	8.5	70	2.4	72	1970	1350	18	244	85
6	28	583	114	9.4	108	2.8	4.3	39	.46
7	33	759	151	7.7	83	1.7	8.9	130	8.6
8	5.8	37	.61	29	948	382	4.5	48	.60
9	5.4	24	.35	13	176	7.4	4.0	23	.25
10	5.0	23	.31	6.4	42	.74	3.8	23	.24
11	4.5	22	.27	6.6	39	.69	3.7	23	.23
12	4.9	27	.39	5.8	41	.64	3.7	23	.23
13	30	607	121	5.3	43	.61	3.7	23	.23
14	13	158	7.4	18	302	26	36	880	458
15	5.6	15	.23	8.9	130	3.4	5.1	63	.90
16	4.9	11	.15	6.4	103	1.8	4.2	36	.41
17	4.6	11	.13	5.6	96	1.5	4.2	35	.39
18	17	328	83	5.2	90	1.3	5.8	71	2.3
19	6.7	48	.98	5.6	84	1.3	4.1	48	.64
20	4.9	12	.16	5.0	79	1.1	3.8	22	.23
21	4.7	11	.14	4.8	74	.96	3.9	17	.18
22	4.2	11	.12	4.7	69	.87	3.9	12	.13
23	3.9	10	.11	4.7	64	.81	3.9	9	.09
24	3.8	10	.10	4.2	60	.68	3.9	7	.08
25	3.7	9	.09	4.2	56	.63	3.9	7	.08
26	3.7	9	.09	4.4	53	.62	3.7	7	.08
27	3.7	9	.09	4.5	49	.59	3.8	8	.08
28	3.6	8	.08	4.5	46	.56	4.5	8	.09
29	3.5	8	.08	---	---	---	36	1230	618
30	3.5	8	.07	---	---	---	10	138	9.7
31	3.4	7	.07	---	---	---	10	144	4.9
TOTAL	256.2	---	488.11	313.1	---	5038.87	223.9	---	1194.03

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998									
DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE
	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	5.2	70	.99	4.3	28	.33	3.5	39	.37
2	4.8	61	.80	4.1	23	.26	3.3	37	.34
3	4.3	56	.64	4.4	19	.22	3.4	36	.33
4	4.3	51	.58	4.7	15	.19	3.4	34	.32
5	4.6	46	.56	4.3	12	.14	24	499	181
6	4.4	42	.50	4.1	10	.12	5.3	59	.90
7	5.7	62	1.4	4.2	10	.11	4.6	38	.47
8	5.9	91	1.5	5.0	10	.13	6.1	65	1.8
9	4.5	79	.97	4.2	10	.11	28	551	212
10	4.3	76	.89	3.9	9	.10	9.3	137	4.9
11	4.4	73	.87	3.9	9	.10	4.3	40	.47
12	36	545	273	3.8	9	.09	7.4	98	3.7
13	9.6	117	4.7	3.7	9	.09	3.8	35	.36
14	4.4	41	.48	26	509	165	3.5	33	.31
15	9.5	117	35	7.0	74	1.9	3.6	33	.32
16	60	1280	533	3.7	32	.32	9.6	156	16
17	12	150	5.6	6.9	84	5.5	19	376	106
18	6.1	65	1.1	4.4	43	.72	11	138	5.1
19	5.5	59	.87	6.7	82	2.9	4.9	47	.63
20	12	159	15	6.0	68	2.4	4.4	43	.51
21	7.7	86	2.9	6.3	71	3.3	8.4	102	3.9
22	5.4	53	.77	4.0	33	.37	5.4	56	.82
23	5.2	49	.69	29	492	140	5.0	50	.67
24	5.0	46	.63	4.9	58	.77	4.7	45	.56
25	10	133	7.4	4.3	49	.58	7.7	141	5.9
26	5.5	56	.83	9.1	124	9.9	4.3	44	.52
27	7.9	97	2.9	7.1	84	3.3	4.6	36	.45
28	5.1	53	.73	8.8	132	14	4.6	35	.43
29	4.8	43	.56	4.3	44	.51	4.3	34	.40
30	4.7	35	.45	3.7	42	.42	3.9	33	.36
31	---	---	---	3.5	41	.39	---	---	---
TOTAL	268.8	---	896.31	200.3	---	354.27	215.3	---	549.84

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998									
DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	DISCHARGE
	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	3.8	33	.34	5.1	48	.66	e8.3	14	e7.4
2	4.4	32	.38	4.8	46	.59	23	13	145
3	13	248	57	4.8	44	.57	7.5	15	1.5
4	20	440	153	4.8	42	.55	6.6	16	1.0
5	4.6	137	1.7	6.2	69	1.7	7.0	18	1.1
6	4.1	91	1.0	e8.0	62	e2.7	201	20	5230
7	7.8	96	4.1	e39	65	e273	30	22	53
8	3.6	39	.38	e11	68	e27	14	24	7.6
9	4.1	35	.39	e15	71	e57	14	27	9.4
10	9.3	122	8.5	e37	74	e273	11	30	3.6
11	4.1	45	.52	e84	3400	e4220	10	33	3.2
12	3.6	34	.34	e31	80	e212	11	37	4.8
13	3.6	34	.33	e10	83	e57	16	40	14
14	11	199	27	8.7	77	1.8	9.9	45	2.8
15	8.2	106	7.4	7.4	70	1.4	12	50	4.8
16	75	3420	4220	6.3	64	1.1	14	55	12
17	21	387	34	e6.0	58	e1.6	20	61	32
18	22	479	100	e60	1900	e1350	22	69	29
19	6.6	78	1.4	e15	48	e57	16	92	9.2
20	22	348	34	e10	44	e5.1	16	126	9.6
21	10	146	4.1	e28	40	e212	e714	171	e162000
22	7.6	83	1.7	e11	36	e5.1	e1030	233	e165000
23	8.2	107	3.2	e7.0	33	e1.7	e49	318	167
24	17	259	26	e61	1900	e1350	22	339	20
25	5.3	52	.75	e50	1200	e533	17	282	13
26	5.5	64	1.1	e7.5	25	e2.0	47	916	421
27	9.8	166	7.8	e30	23	e212	22	343	22
28	8.1	99	2.7	e55	1200	e533	15	205	8.2
29	6.2	67	1.6	e18	19	e106	25	433	74
30	7.1	74	1.7	e9.3	17	e8.5	13	205	2.6
31	7.2	85	2.0	e8.4	15	e8.5	---	---	---
TOTAL	343.8	---	4704.43	659.3	---	9515.57	2423.3	---	333308.8
YEAR	6274.6	---	361919.33						

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
02...	1728	390	7250	7630	72
02...	1828	165	3110	1390	82
08...	1811	205	4930	2730	53
14...	0501	149	886	356	81
NOV					
15...	1638	144	8330	3240	94
MAR					
29...	1834	162	10800	4720	97
MAY					
14...	2014	173	7590	3550	99
JUL					
16...	1425	306	18000	1490	93
SEP					
18...	1123	12	67	2.2	97

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)
OCT							
01...	1636	228	14900	9170	19	24	32
NOV							
15...	1553	382	11800	12200	16	22	30
JAN							
18...	1600	188	5730	2910	28	38	50
FEB							
08...	1841	170	4900	2250	21	31	43
MAR							
14...	1200	240	3840	2490	35	45	60
JUN							
09...	1651	251	3670	2490	30	45	63
JUL							
16...	1554	414	40100	44800	13	17	23

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN 1.00 MM (70335)
OCT							
01...	42	55	62	79	94	99	100
NOV							
15...	36	39	43	48	95	99	100
JAN							
18...	67	84	91	96	98	100	100
FEB							
08...	56	66	71	80	95	100	100
MAR							
14...	74	80	83	92	97	99	100
JUN							
09...	79	92	95	99	100	100	100
JUL							
16...	32	45	51	65	82	96	99

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048800 RIO PIEDRAS NEAR RIO PIEDRAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'15", long 66°03'40", at bridge on Winston Churchill Avenue in the El Señorial Housing area, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) west of Highway 176, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) southwest of Río Piedras plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.17 mi² (20.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TURBIDITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLIFORM, FECA, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)
NOV 05...	1240	8.0	409	7.4	28.0	7.1	5.6	72	<10	K62000 22000
MAR 02...	1130	4.8	475	7.4	25.5	2.4	5.4	66	13	K660000 45000
JUN 08...	0815	3.9	444	7.2	26.0	8.0	6.1	75	<10	22000 5400
SEP 03...	1215	13	413	6.9	29.5	6.6	6.6	86	11	K100000 30000

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORPTION RATIO (00931)	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD CACO3 (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 05...	150	57	6.4	12	.6	3.5	156	<.5	12	12
MAR 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
JUN 08...	150	40	13	28	1	2.8	180	--	13	35
SEP 03...	150	38	13	24	.9	3.1	140	<1.0	20	30

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 05...	.10	25	218	4.71	15	.640	.110	.750	.420	.52
MAR 02...	--	--	--	--	2	.510	.220	.730	1.70	.20
JUN 08...	.15	30	270	2.86	16	.590	.100	.690	.350	.25
SEP 03...	.14	26	239	8.27	18	.881	.039	.920	.350	.63

DATE	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 05...	.94	1.7	7.5	.180	1	<100	40	<1	<1	20
MAR 02...	1.9	2.6	12	.310	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 08...	.60	1.3	5.7	.140	<5	<100	60	<1	<1	<10
SEP 03...	.98	1.9	8.4	.140	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049100 RIO PIEDRAS AT HATO REY, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'34", long 66°04'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at bridge on Avenida Pifeiro near Expreso Las Américas (Luis A. Ferré), and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southwest of Hato Rey.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.4 mi² (39.9 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1970 to December 1987 (discharge measurements only), 1972 to December 1982 (maximum discharge only), January 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 16 ft (5 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Mean daily discharge affected by sewage discharges (approximately 2.0 ft³/s (0.06 m³/s)), 20 ft (6 m) upstream from gaging station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	95	e40	e27	e10	6.9	e12	e11	e7.0	11	e14	e16	e30
2	295	e30	e27	e21	6.9	e10	e8.7	e9.3	10	e18	e15	e173
3	81	e34	e27	e21	6.6	28	e6.7	e11	9.3	e49	e15	e23
4	39	e31	e27	11	206	21	e7.0	e13	8.9	e62	e15	e35
5	18	e75	e29	49	609	109	e8.0	e10	123	e20	e13	82
6	18	34	27	147	75	46	e8.0	e8.5	e28	e18	e18	543
7	9.3	27	24	307	53	78	e12	e9.5	11	e35	e30	156
8	e311	26	21	33	149	25	e13	e16	53	e17	e21	140
9	35	26	20	33	75	20	e8.0	e9.5	148	e42	e11	86
10	13	67	21	24	38	16	e7.2	e7.0	52	e41	e57	70
11	212	22	22	23	45	14	e7.1	e7.0	20	e20	e255	65
12	50	22	21	20	37	14	e204	e6.1	56	e17	e129	71
13	101	22	21	91	28	15	e28	e5.6	19	e16	e38	98
14	513	19	20	25	e73	105	e7.7	e195	17	e223	e23	114
15	27	153	20	12	e43	55	e26	90	16	e220	e18	104
16	25	77	19	11	31	11	e219	36	33	e202	e15	93
17	29	26	26	10	29	11	e37	119	40	e78	e13	112
18	e30	82	20	28	25	15	e15	12	45	e97	e96	442
19	e28	41	17	13	23	24	e12	e21	19	e15	e47	191
20	e25	21	17	10	27	16	e34	e39	15	e126	e16	190
21	e23	293	19	10	e20	12	e20	e12	e28	e33	e53	926
22	e24	35	20	9.8	16	11	e11	e8.5	e18	e19	e36	2140
23	e25	22	30	9.1	12	12	e10	e52	e15	e25	e28	322
24	e26	26	18	9.1	9.8	12	e9.3	e12	e15	e51	e203	e213
25	e33	21	17	9.7	e8.0	17	e35	e34	e27	e17	e255	e186
26	e29	25	18	8.6	e14	16	e27	e103	e14	e17	e28	e286
27	e27	e17	17	8.3	e16	17	e46	e31	e16	e29	e73	e208
28	e28	e17	e16	8.9	e15	17	e9.8	63	e16	e25	e166	e180
29	e33	e39	e15	9.5	---	210	e12	e14	e16	e19	e29	e247
30	e37	e31	e19	7.9	---	e29	e7.9	e12	e14	e21	e17	e205
31	e37	---	e20	7.2	---	e29	---	43	---	e22	e14	---
TOTAL	2276.3	1401	662	997.1	1697.2	1027	867.4	1016.0	913.2	1608	1763	7731
MEAN	73.4	46.7	21.4	32.2	60.6	33.1	28.9	32.8	30.4	51.9	56.9	258
MAX	513	293	30	307	609	210	219	195	148	223	255	2140
MIN	9.3	17	15	7.2	6.6	10	6.7	5.6	8.9	14	11	23
AC-FT	4520	2780	1310	1980	3370	2040	1720	2020	1810	3190	3500	15330
CFSM	4.83	3.07	1.40	2.12	3.99	2.18	1.90	2.16	2.00	3.41	3.74	17.0
IN.	5.57	3.43	1.62	2.44	4.15	2.51	2.12	2.49	2.23	3.94	4.31	18.92

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1972 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	
MEAN	67.0	73.8	47.4	45.6	43.9	37.4	54.1	44.7	41.2	49.3	57.1	103																
MAX	134	235	168	97.4	86.9	78.5	150	97.5	81.9	97.4	84.2	261																
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1993	1995	1972	1972	1992	1995	1993	1988	1996																
MIN	16.6	23.9	18.8	12.9	10.8	11.5	13.6	4.12	20.0	12.8	20.2	26.3																
(WY)	1992	1991	1992	1973	1992	1994	1995	1972	1994	1994	1993	1972																

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1972 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	17493.6	21959.2																										
ANNUAL MEAN	47.9	60.2																										
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN										54.7																		
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN										84.0																		1993
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN										28.7																		1994
LOWEST DAILY MEAN																												
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM				518	Jul 20		2140	Sep 22		4550	Sep 10	1996																
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW				9.3	Mar 27		5.6	May 13		1.2	Jun 28	1972																
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE				12	Jun 4		7.7	Jan 28		1.2	Jul 5	1972																
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)							5700	Sep 21		10500	Sep 10	1996																
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)							17.58	Sep 21		22.11	Sep 10	1996																
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)				34700			43560			39630																		
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS				3.15			3.96			3.60																		
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS				42.81			53.74			48.90																		
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS				110			151			122																		
				25			24			22																		
				12			9.6			9.6																		

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50049100 RIO PIEDRAS AT HATO REY, PR--Continued

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049100 RIO PIEDRAS AT HATO REY, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'34", long 66°04'10", at bridge on Avenida Pifiero at Expreso Las Américas, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southwest of Hato Rey.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.4 mi² (39.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1971 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH CENT) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
NOV 05...	1515	25	309	7.4	28.0	18	4.5	57	10	58000	67000
MAR 02...	1315	9.9	476	7.5	26.0	1.0	4.6	57	13	K780000	25000
JUN 08...	1220	54	257	7.0	28.5	35	5.7	73	10	230000	65000
SEP 03...	1040	25	365	7.2	29.0	22	6.2	80	12	350000	210000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD CACO3 (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 05...	140	41	8.1	15	.6	5.2	110	<.5	25	22
MAR 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
JUN 08...	39	8.6	4.3	13	.9	.90	98	--	6.6	16
SEP 03...	130	37	9.0	21	.8	3.1	130	<1.0	14	24

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 05...	.10	16	198	13.4	74	.654	.096	.750	.940	.66
MAR 02...	--	--	--	--	7	.810	.160	.970	1.60	.10
JUN 08...	.10	16	198	13.4	74	.561	.059	.620	.460	.84
SEP 03...	.15	22	208	13.9	46	.758	.082	.840	.780	.72

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 05...	1.6	2.3	10	.280	1	<100	40	<1	1	<10
MAR 02...	1.7	2.7	12	.320	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 08...	1.3	1.9	8.5	.250	1	<100	50	<1	2	<10
SEP 03...	1.5	2.3	10	.200	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049820 LAGUNA SAN JOSE NO. 2 AT SAN JUAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'46", long 66°02'10", 0.2 mi (0.3 km) east of Caño de Martín Peña, and 650 ft (200 m) south of Isla Guachinango.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND- ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TRANS- PAR- ENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN) (00077)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SOLVED SATUR- ATION) (00300)	OXYGEN, COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML) (31616)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, FECAL, PER (COLS. 100 ML) (31679)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD MG/L AS CACO3 (00410)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	
NOV 12...	0945	22600	7.1	29.5	47.0	2.0	26	5500	550	93	10
MAR 09...	1000	18500	7.5	25.5	33.0	4.0	48	23000	800	90	22
JUN 12...	0930	19500	8.0	30.5	26.0	5.6	74	58000	860	84	8
SEP 15...	1030	16300	8.1	30.1	21.0	4.5	60	2000	K54	75	26

DATE	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	CARBON, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS C) (00680)
NOV 12...	--	<.010	<.020	.680	.92	1.6	--	--	.310	6.5
MAR 09...	.010	.030	.040	2.00	.30	2.3	2.3	10	.160	5.3
JUN 12...	.010	.090	.100	.820	1.1	1.9	2.0	8.9	.180	7.1
SEP 15...	--	.010	<.020	.160	1.3	1.5	--	--	.210	3.7

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049920 BAHIA DE SAN JUAN NO. 5 AT SAN JUAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION--Lat 18°26'37", long 66°05'11", 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Puente de la Constitución, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) south from U.S. Naval Reservation.

DRAINAGE--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD--Water years 1974 to present.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND- ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TRANS- PAR- ENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN) (00077)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, SATUR- ATION (00301)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML) (31616)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER (31679)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD MG/L AS CACO3 (00410)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (00530)
NOV 12...	1130	49500	7.3	29.0	16.0	4.0	52	K6700	2000	150	37
MAR 09...	1145	40800	7.4	27.0	24.0	2.5	31	K64000	5500	130	31
JUN 12...	1130	33000	7.6	30.0	15.0	2.9	38	280000	36000	140	13
SEP 15...	1200	17300	7.6	29.0	14.0	.3	4	600000	K140000	140	26

DATE	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	CARBON, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS C) (00680)
NOV 12...	--	.014	<.020	1.80	.80	2.6	--	--	.410	4.6
MAR 09...	.022	.028	.050	2.00	.10	2.1	2.2	9.5	.300	8.6
JUN 12...	.100	.070	.170	1.30	.70	2.0	2.2	9.6	.920	5.9
SEP 15...	.054	.060	.110	2.9	.60	3.5	3.6	16	.510	2.5

Figure 18. Río Grande de Loíza basin.

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050300 QUEBRADA BLASINA NEAR CAROLINA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'27", long 65°58'28", at bridge on Highway 3, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) south of Valle Arriba Heights housing area, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) west-southwest of Carolina plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.96 mi² (7.67 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1973 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)
OCT 28...	0945	4.2	520	7.4	26.5	1.5	6.7	82	<10	K6900	3400
MAR 25...	1030	3.8	461	7.1	26.5	1.2	3.0	37	23	K170000	22000
JUN 09...	1105	5.5	435	7.2	27.5	2.3	4.6	58	10	24000	45000
SEP 08...	1025	11	470	7.0	28.0	62	2.8	36	13	600000	700000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 28...	190	60	9.1	29	.9	3.3	205	<.5	10	42
MAR 25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--
JUN 09...	140	46	5.2	15	.5	.73	170	--	26	7.8
SEP 08...	140	44	7.8	26	.9	4.2	210	<1.0	12	35

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 28...	.29	29	306	3.49	<1	.470	.170	.640	1.90	.20
MAR 25...	--	--	--	--	8	.200	.010	.210	.020	.20
JUN 09...	.30	25	236	3.53	--	.610	.210	.820	.600	.50
SEP 08...	.11	22	277	8.51	134	.580	.100	.680	7.10	.90

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 28...	2.1	2.7	12	.400	1	<100	60	<1	<1	<10
MAR 25...	.02	.24	1.1	.020	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 09...	1.1	1.9	8.5	.260	1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
SEP 08...	8.0	8.7	38	.850	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050900 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT QUEBRADA ARENAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'10", long 65°59'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at intersection of Highways 181 and 9990, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from confluence with Río Emajagua and about 7.1 mi (11.4 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.00 mi² (15.54 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1977 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 640 ft (195 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	22	18	19	23	15	12	27	14	16	8.7	10	18
2	62	17	17	15	14	12	42	14	16	10	9.7	24
3	26	18	17	28	14	e15	24	15	14	12	9.6	36
4	22	17	16	55	15	13	19	16	13	28	9.3	33
5	20	16	16	44	368	12	46	15	15	25	9.0	19
6	19	15	16	476	30	12	21	16	20	12	e27	122
7	18	14	15	200	19	551	20	14	19	21	11	60
8	21	14	15	102	22	75	19	26	16	16	22	105
9	18	26	15	70	23	28	16	17	15	15	32	135
10	18	472	15	115	16	21	15	14	14	11	23	45
11	33	31	15	35	16	18	20	12	e14	9.8	14	26
12	73	25	17	43	16	17	77	12	e20	9.5	14	21
13	460	22	15	35	15	16	18	21	e25	9.5	12	67
14	e769	21	15	29	67	19	14	34	e15	9.6	11	42
15	e207	23	14	25	27	17	13	31	e14	9.1	10	69
16	e90	21	21	23	18	15	37	23	e15	11	11	25
17	e51	21	30	22	21	14	51	17	24	10	106	20
18	41	19	16	21	17	14	83	15	19	15	20	19
19	34	20	15	19	16	16	52	14	16	17	15	18
20	30	20	15	19	15	237	128	14	14	54	18	e21
21	27	26	21	18	15	42	31	14	14	27	24	e4360
22	25	25	15	18	14	29	24	13	31	13	111	e4690
23	24	26	14	17	14	22	21	13	14	12	27	157
24	23	22	13	19	13	19	19	14	12	27	593	77
25	22	20	13	21	13	27	19	12	12	14	433	47
26	21	35	13	21	13	22	18	56	11	11	108	41
27	20	24	13	18	13	28	19	48	11	14	39	139
28	19	20	13	17	12	24	20	14	12	23	28	45
29	18	19	13	17	---	116	16	25	11	12	33	32
30	18	22	13	16	---	153	15	51	9.5	12	23	29
31	18	---	13	16	---	45	---	27	---	11	21	---
TOTAL	2269	1089	488	1597	871	1661	944	641	471.5	489.2	1833.6	10542
MEAN	73.2	36.3	15.7	51.5	31.1	53.6	31.5	20.7	15.7	15.8	59.1	351
MAX	769	472	30	476	368	551	128	56	31	54	593	4690
MIN	18	14	13	15	12	12	13	12	9.5	8.7	9.0	18
AC-FT	4500	2160	968	3170	1730	3290	1870	1270	935	970	3640	20910
CFSM	12.2	6.05	2.62	8.59	5.18	8.93	5.24	3.45	2.62	2.63	9.86	58.6
IN.	14.07	6.75	3.03	9.90	5.40	10.30	5.85	3.97	2.92	3.03	11.37	65.36

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1978 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	
MEAN	41.2	44.0	24.5	20.9	19.5	15.7	14.6	29.8	37.6	36.5	35.1	61.4										
MAX	123	122	55.2	56.1	38.0	53.6	31.5	77.5	122	92.3	90.0	351										
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1992	1982	1998	1998	1985	1979	1993	1979	1998										
MIN	13.1	8.34	6.65	8.16	6.36	5.07	4.64	9.56	11.3	12.5	9.30	11.8										
(WY)	1990	1990	1990	1990	1979	1979	1979	1988	1985	1986	1991	1981										

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1978 - 1998

	1997 CALENDAR YEAR	1998 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1978 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	10236.1	22896.3	
ANNUAL MEAN	28.0	62.7	31.7
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			62.7
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			14.5
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	769	Oct 14	4690
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6.6	May 6	8.7
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	6.9	Apr 30	9.8
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			45000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			26.37
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			7.9
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	20300	45410	23000
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	4.67	10.5	5.29
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	63.46	141.96	71.90
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	40	64	51
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	16	19	15
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.3	12	7.2

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50050900 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT QUEBRADA ARENAS, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'40", long 65°58'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from bridge on Highway 181, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.25 mi² (8.42 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 459 ft (140 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	3.2	3.8	3.2	2.4	2.7	2.7	4.1	2.5	2.5	1.8	1.4	1.9
2	22	3.1	3.1	2.7	2.7	2.7	12	2.4	2.3	1.8	1.4	4.5
3	6.7	3.0	3.0	2.7	2.7	3.1	5.5	3.0	2.2	2.3	1.5	3.7
4	4.4	2.8	2.9	2.8	4.7	3.0	4.1	e3.2	2.2	5.3	1.4	3.5
5	3.5	2.8	2.9	2.8	44	2.8	3.8	e2.8	3.6	2.8	1.3	1.8
6	2.9	2.8	2.9	29	8.5	2.7	3.3	e2.3	3.3	1.9	1.3	2.3
7	2.4	2.6	2.9	39	5.4	e164	3.4	e2.2	2.3	1.7	1.3	4.1
8	3.4	2.5	2.8	15	12	18	3.3	15	2.5	1.7	4.1	22
9	2.8	3.8	2.8	14	8.1	e11	3.1	4.8	2.3	1.6	4.2	11
10	3.2	29	2.8	14	4.1	e6.7	3.0	3.0	2.2	1.6	2.7	10
11	4.7	4.7	2.7	7.2	3.1	e4.9	3.6	2.5	2.0	1.6	6.7	3.2
12	11	3.6	2.8	5.7	2.6	e4.3	12	2.3	3.4	1.5	2.2	2.0
13	56	3.4	2.8	10	2.5	e4.0	4.6	5.2	2.3	1.5	1.7	4.0
14	e126	3.1	2.8	6.8	13	e4.9	3.7	7.6	2.1	1.6	1.5	2.0
15	22	3.0	2.8	4.6	6.8	4.3	3.4	e7.7	2.0	1.6	1.4	38
16	16	2.9	2.8	4.1	4.5	e4.1	8.3	e4.1	2.5	1.8	1.5	12
17	15	3.1	3.3	3.9	4.3	3.8	9.5	3.2	2.3	1.8	3.6	5.5
18	12	2.9	2.8	3.6	3.7	3.9	14	e2.9	2.1	4.5	2.3	3.5
19	8.4	3.0	2.7	3.3	3.4	4.4	e7.1	e2.9	2.5	2.8	1.7	e3.2
20	6.4	2.8	2.7	3.1	3.3	34	13	e3.4	2.1	22	2.0	e3.0
21	5.9	3.9	3.2	2.9	3.1	9.7	7.1	e2.5	2.7	6.0	3.2	e182
22	6.2	5.4	2.6	3.0	2.9	5.7	5.2	2.4	5.4	2.1	21	214
23	5.3	7.2	2.6	2.9	2.9	4.4	4.2	2.5	2.2	1.6	6.2	24
24	4.6	5.8	2.5	3.1	2.7	4.2	3.7	2.5	2.0	1.8	63	16
25	4.9	4.1	2.6	3.5	2.7	4.5	3.5	2.2	2.1	1.6	63	13
26	4.0	4.4	2.5	3.3	2.7	4.0	3.5	2.6	2.0	1.4	23	9.5
27	4.1	3.7	2.5	3.0	2.4	7.3	3.2	6.8	2.0	1.4	13	8.3
28	3.8	3.5	2.5	2.9	2.9	4.6	3.4	2.8	2.1	2.3	7.4	7.1
29	3.5	3.3	2.4	2.8	---	6.9	2.9	3.2	1.9	1.6	5.1	6.3
30	3.4	3.4	2.5	2.7	---	6.0	2.7	6.5	1.8	1.5	3.1	5.8
31	3.3	---	2.5	2.7	---	4.6	---	3.0	---	1.5	2.3	---
TOTAL	381.0	133.4	85.9	209.5	164.4	351.2	164.2	120.0	72.9	86.0	255.5	627.2
MEAN	12.3	4.45	2.77	6.76	5.87	11.3	5.47	3.87	2.43	2.77	8.24	20.9
MAX	126	29	3.3	39	44	164	14	15	5.4	22	63	214
MIN	2.4	2.5	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.7	2.7	2.2	1.8	1.4	1.3	1.8
AC-FT	756	265	170	416	326	697	326	238	145	171	507	1240
CFSM	3.78	1.37	.85	2.08	1.81	3.49	1.68	1.19	.75	.85	2.54	6.43
IN.	4.36	1.53	.98	2.40	1.88	4.02	1.88	1.37	.83	.98	2.92	7.18

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	10.2	14.2	6.52	4.95	4.31	4.46	2.54	6.51	5.97	6.06	7.23	10.5			
MAX	47.8	36.9	30.1	9.94	8.21	20.7	5.47	31.5	21.3	15.0	20.2	27.7			
(WY)	1986	1985	1988	1992	1989	1989	1998	1985	1987	1993	1988	1996			
MIN	2.75	2.49	1.49	1.74	1.32	1.64	.75	.62	2.12	2.02	1.95	1.36			
(WY)	1993	1990	1985	1995	1985	1993	1994	1994	1994	1986	1994	1990			

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1984 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	1971.5	2651.2		
ANNUAL MEAN	5.40	7.26	6.96	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			12.3	1988
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			2.50	1990
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	126	Oct 14	214	Sep 22
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.1	Jul 3	1.3	Aug 5
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.3	Jul 9	1.4	Aug 1
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2970	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			10.38	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			1.2	Aug 4
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	3910	5260	5040	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.66	2.23	2.14	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	22.57	30.35	29.10	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	12	12	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.1	3.2	2.7	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.8	1.9	1.1	

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1985 to 1986 and water year 1989 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1984 to September 1986 and from October 1989 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1989.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediment samples were collected with automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 7,300 mg/L Oct. 06, 1985; Minimum daily mean, <1 mg/L several days in 1996.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 4,940 tons (4,480 tonnes) May 17, 1985; Minimum daily mean, <0.01 ton (<0.01 tonne) several years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,100 mg/L October 14, 1997; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 2,480 tons (2,250 tonnes) September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, <0.01 ton (<0.01 tonne) several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION		DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION		DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	
	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	3.2	4	.04	3.8	6	.06	3.2	9	.08
2	22	80	6.9	3.1	7	.06	3.1	9	.07
3	6.7	18	.35	3.0	8	.06	3.0	9	.07
4	4.4	8	.10	2.8	6	.04	2.9	6	.05
5	3.5	4	.04	2.8	4	.03	2.9	4	.04
6	2.9	3	.02	2.8	4	.03	2.9	6	.05
7	2.4	3	.02	2.6	3	.02	2.9	10	.08
8	3.4	9	.13	2.5	3	.02	2.8	16	.12
9	2.8	4	.03	3.8	14	.97	2.8	15	.12
10	3.2	12	.19	29	631	131	2.8	14	.10
11	4.7	6	.30	4.7	11	.13	2.7	12	.09
12	11	18	2.2	3.6	7	.07	2.8	10	.08
13	56	203	157	3.4	8	.07	2.8	7	.05
14	e126	1100	e1130	3.1	9	.08	2.8	4	.03
15	22	182	11	3.0	10	.08	2.8	2	.02
16	16	49	2.2	2.9	10	.08	2.8	2	.01
17	15	44	1.9	3.1	11	.09	3.3	2	.02
18	12	43	1.4	2.9	10	.08	2.8	1	.01
19	8.4	32	e.74	3.0	9	.07	2.7	1	.01
20	6.4	23	e.40	2.8	8	.06	2.7	1	.01
21	5.9	10	e.15	3.9	12	.14	3.2	2	.02
22	6.2	5	.08	5.4	14	.23	2.6	3	.02
23	5.3	9	.12	7.2	22	.58	2.6	3	.02
24	4.6	13	.17	5.8	13	.24	2.5	2	.01
25	4.9	8	.11	4.1	17	.19	2.6	2	.02
26	4.0	4	.04	4.4	15	.18	2.5	3	.02
27	4.1	2	.03	3.7	14	.14	2.5	4	.03
28	3.8	3	.03	3.5	13	.12	2.5	6	.04
29	3.5	3	.03	3.3	11	.10	2.4	8	.06
30	3.4	4	.04	3.4	10	.09	2.5	9	.06
31	3.3	5	.04	---	---	---	2.5	9	.06
TOTAL	381.0	---	1315.80	133.4	---	135.11	85.9	---	1.47

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	2.4	10	.06	2.7	3	.02	2.7	2	.01
2	2.7	11	.08	2.7	3	.02	2.7	3	.02
3	2.7	11	.08	2.7	5	.04	3.1	3	.02
4	2.8	10	.08	4.7	10	.38	3.0	2	.02
5	2.8	10	.08	44	216	42	2.8	1	.01
6	29	267	54	8.5	25	.60	2.7	1	.01
7	39	182	25	5.4	15	.22	e164	918	e2390
8	15	48	2.1	12	37	3.8	18	64	3.5
9	14	74	3.5	8.1	20	.63	e11	35	e.97
10	14	50	2.3	4.1	3	.04	e6.7	10	e.18
11	7.2	15	.29	3.1	2	.02	e4.9	2	e.02
12	5.7	8	.13	2.6	3	.02	e4.3	1	e.01
13	10	32	2.8	2.5	5	.04	e4.0	2	e.02
14	6.8	17	.37	13	64	6.4	e4.9	2	e.03
15	4.6	11	.14	6.8	16	.32	4.3	2	.02
16	4.1	15	.17	4.5	6	.08	e4.1	2	e.02
17	3.9	13	.13	4.3	8	.09	3.8	2	.02
18	3.6	10	.10	3.7	12	.12	3.9	3	.03
19	3.3	8	.07	3.4	10	.09	4.4	8	.10
20	3.1	4	.04	3.3	7	.06	34	248	75
21	2.9	2	.02	3.1	4	.03	9.7	29	.85
22	3.0	5	.04	2.9	2	.01	5.7	10	.16
23	2.9	10	.08	2.9	1	.01	4.4	6	.07
24	3.1	11	.09	2.7	1	.01	4.2	5	.06
25	3.5	9	.09	2.7	2	.01	4.5	9	.12
26	3.3	8	.07	2.7	2	.01	4.0	5	.06
27	3.0	5	.04	2.4	1	.01	7.3	9	.28
28	2.9	2	.02	2.9	1	.01	4.6	2	.12
29	2.8	3	.02	---	---	---	6.9	9	.49
30	2.7	4	.03	---	---	---	6.0	16	.29
31	2.7	4	.03	---	---	---	4.6	10	.13
TOTAL	209.5	---	92.05	164.4	---	55.09	351.2	---	2472.64
DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	4.1	1	.02	2.5	1	.01	2.5	3	.02
2	12	49	5.5	2.4	2	.01	2.3	2	.01
3	5.5	12	.19	3.0	5	.05	2.2	1	.01
4	4.1	5	.05	e3.2	6	e.05	2.2	1	.01
5	3.8	2	.02	e2.8	3	e.02	3.6	7	.14
6	3.3	1	.01	e2.3	2	e.01	3.3	7	.07
7	3.4	3	.03	e2.2	1	e.01	2.3	4	.03
8	3.3	7	.06	15	245	87	2.5	5	.04
9	3.1	6	.05	4.8	18	.23	2.3	2	.01
10	3.0	4	.03	3.0	14	.11	2.2	1	.01
11	3.6	2	.02	2.5	11	.07	2.0	1	<.01
12	12	32	1.5	2.3	9	.06	3.4	3	.03
13	4.6	8	.10	5.2	15	.31	2.3	1	.01
14	3.7	7	.07	7.6	36	2.2	2.1	1	.01
15	3.4	7	.06	e7.7	14	e.42	2.0	1	.01
16	8.3	30	1.5	e4.1	3	e.03	2.5	4	.03
17	9.5	22	.83	3.2	3	.03	2.3	2	.01
18	14	260	53	e2.9	3	e.02	2.1	1	.01
19	e7.1	18	e.38	e2.9	3	e.02	2.5	4	.03
20	13	59	5.8	e3.4	7	e.08	2.1	3	.02
21	7.1	16	.34	e2.5	3	e.02	2.7	6	.04
22	5.2	3	.05	2.4	1	.01	5.4	13	.25
23	4.2	2	.02	2.5	2	.01	2.2	4	.02
24	3.7	1	.01	2.5	4	.02	2.0	3	.02
25	3.5	2	.01	2.2	6	.04	2.1	2	.01
26	3.5	3	.03	2.6	6	.04	2.0	1	.01
27	3.2	4	.04	6.8	21	.54	2.0	1	<.01
28	3.4	2	.02	2.8	3	.03	2.1	1	.01
29	2.9	1	.01	3.2	1	.01	1.9	1	<.01
30	2.7	1	.01	6.5	19	.57	1.8	1	.01
31	---	---	---	3.0	6	.05	---	---	---
TOTAL	164.2	---	69.76	120.0	---	92.08	72.9	---	0.91

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN			MEAN			MEAN		
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	1.8	2	.01	1.4	2	.01	1.9	2	.01
2	1.8	1	.01	1.4	1	<.01	4.5	8	.29
3	2.3	3	.02	1.5	1	<.01	3.7	7	.08
4	5.3	4	.22	1.4	1	<.01	3.5	5	.06
5	2.8	3	.05	1.3	1	<.01	1.8	2	.01
6	1.9	2	.01	1.3	1	<.01	2.3	3	.03
7	1.7	5	.02	1.3	1	<.01	4.1	4	.06
8	1.7	12	.05	4.1	2	.24	22	80	6.9
9	1.6	14	.06	4.2	6	.12	11	22	1.1
10	1.6	15	.06	2.7	5	.04	10	29	1.1
11	1.6	11	.05	6.7	18	.55	3.2	8	.07
12	1.5	7	.03	2.2	3	.02	2.0	5	.03
13	1.5	5	.02	1.7	2	.01	4.0	11	.21
14	1.6	3	.01	1.5	2	.01	2.0	3	.02
15	1.6	2	.01	1.4	2	.01	38	384	136
16	1.8	1	.01	1.5	3	.01	12	12	.47
17	1.8	1	<.01	3.6	8	.09	5.5	3	.04
18	4.5	14	.38	2.3	3	.02	3.5	2	.02
19	2.8	7	.05	1.7	1	.01	e3.2	2	.02
20	22	78	9.2	2.0	1	<.01	e3.0	2	.02
21	6.0	15	.32	3.2	3	.03	e182	982	2480
22	2.1	4	.02	21	100	12	214	1040	968
23	1.6	3	.01	6.2	14	.30	24	69	5.4
24	1.8	4	.02	63	745	279	16	13	.53
25	1.6	3	.01	63	313	88	13	4	.14
26	1.4	2	.01	23	38	3.0	9.5	9	.22
27	1.4	1	<.01	13	7	.24	8.3	12	.26
28	2.3	3	.03	7.4	3	.05	7.1	13	.24
29	1.6	1	.01	5.1	2	.03	6.3	7	.12
30	1.5	1	.01	3.1	2	.02	5.8	3	.05
31	1.5	2	.01	2.3	2	.01	---	---	---
TOTAL	86.0	---	10.74	255.5	---	383.89	627.2	---	3601.50
YEAR	2651.2		8231.04						

e Estimated

< Actual value is known to be less than the value shown

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DISCHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DISCHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
10...	1515	10	86	2.3	97
NOV					
10...	1100	12	93	3.0	95
JAN					
07...	1715	20	161	8.7	92
MAR					
07...	1840	632	4320	7370	82
AUG					
24...	1615	53	282	40	96
24...	2350	132	3900	1390	80
SEP					
22...	0340	393	1850	1960	73

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)
		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)
MAR 07...	1710	1440	4370	17000	24	30	41
AUG 24...	1351	205	8350	4620	26	32	41
SEP 21...	2150	576	5000	7780	32	43	59
MAR 07...	52	62	69	81	91	98	100
AUG 24...	50	56	60	78	87	91	94
SEP 21...	71	75	79	90	97	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'24", long 65°58'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left downstream side of bridge on Highway 181, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.74 mi² (9.69 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 330 ft (100 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e2.0	2.7	1.9	1.6	1.1	1.4	1.5	1.2	1.4	1.1	.62	2.4
2	e14	2.2	1.8	1.9	1.0	1.4	2.8	1.2	1.4	1.1	.60	3.1
3	e3.8	2.1	1.8	1.8	.95	1.5	3.1	1.5	1.4	1.1	.60	3.1
4	e2.8	2.1	1.7	1.9	9.7	1.6	1.6	1.5	1.3	2.1	.58	2.8
5	e2.3	2.1	1.7	2.4	101	1.7	1.5	1.4	1.4	2.1	.56	2.3
6	e1.8	2.1	1.6	67	5.0	1.8	1.4	1.3	1.8	1.2	e.57	2.5
7	e1.4	2.0	1.6	66	3.2	329	1.4	1.3	1.3	1.2	e1.0	2.6
8	2.0	2.0	1.6	8.5	44	7.4	1.4	12	1.3	1.1	1.2	8.3
9	1.8	e8.1	1.5	4.9	11	2.8	1.3	2.6	1.3	1.0	1.1	4.3
10	2.0	e7.4	1.5	4.3	3.1	2.2	1.2	1.7	1.2	1.0	.91	4.3
11	2.0	3.0	1.5	3.6	2.4	1.9	1.2	1.5	1.2	.99	.94	2.6
12	3.0	2.5	1.5	2.9	2.1	1.7	2.2	1.4	1.5	1.0	.85	2.4
13	e336	2.5	1.6	7.4	1.9	1.7	1.4	1.6	1.5	.91	.75	4.2
14	e97	2.3	1.7	5.2	11	1.7	1.3	2.7	1.3	.87	.69	2.9
15	13	2.4	1.6	3.1	4.2	1.6	1.3	2.6	1.2	.90	.69	7.3
16	8.0	2.3	1.6	2.6	2.6	1.6	2.0	1.6	1.5	1.2	.86	3.3
17	e8.2	2.5	2.1	2.3	2.4	1.6	2.3	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.1	3.0
18	6.4	2.3	1.7	2.1	2.2	1.7	2.0	1.9	e1.3	1.4	.96	3.1
19	4.3	2.2	1.8	1.9	2.0	2.1	e1.7	1.8	e1.4	1.4	.81	3.4
20	3.5	2.1	1.6	1.8	1.9	14	4.3	1.6	1.3	30	.84	4.9
21	3.1	2.2	1.9	1.7	1.8	3.4	2.4	1.4	1.7	2.1	1.2	434
22	2.8	3.3	1.7	1.6	1.7	2.2	2.1	1.3	2.0	1.0	5.3	810
23	2.7	3.6	2.1	1.6	1.6	1.8	1.5	1.4	1.4	.75	1.3	100
24	2.6	2.6	1.9	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.2	.85	105	19
25	2.8	2.2	1.8	1.6	1.6	1.7	1.4	1.2	1.2	.72	91	4.6
26	2.5	3.4	1.7	1.6	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.2	.68	11	5.5
27	2.3	2.6	1.7	1.4	1.5	1.9	1.4	3.5	1.1	.66	4.6	6.7
28	2.3	2.1	1.6	1.3	1.5	1.7	1.6	1.6	1.2	.82	3.4	7.7
29	2.2	2.0	1.6	1.3	---	4.8	1.4	1.6	1.1	.71	3.0	11
30	2.1	2.0	e1.6	1.2	---	2.2	1.3	1.9	1.1	.65	2.7	10
31	2.2	---	1.7	1.1	---	1.6	---	1.7	---	.63	2.5	---
TOTAL	542.9	82.9	52.7	209.2	225.65	404.8	52.8	62.2	40.4	62.44	247.23	1481.3
MEAN	17.5	2.76	1.70	6.75	8.06	13.1	1.76	2.01	1.35	2.01	7.98	49.4
MAX	336	8.1	2.1	67	101	329	4.3	12	2.0	30	105	810
MIN	1.4	2.0	1.5	1.1	.95	1.4	1.2	1.2	1.1	.63	.56	2.3
AC-FT	1080	164	105	415	448	803	105	123	80	124	490	2940
CFSM	4.68	.74	.45	1.80	2.15	3.49	.47	.54	.36	.54	2.13	13.2
IN.	5.40	.82	.52	2.08	2.24	4.03	.53	.62	.40	.62	2.46	14.73

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	9.31	11.4	4.87	5.05	3.64	3.69	2.37	5.92	6.18	5.43	6.32	18.0			
MAX	36.2	33.4	22.8	23.4	10.3	17.4	6.60	35.8	17.5	20.5	14.5	76.5			
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1992	1984	1989	1985	1985	1996	1993	1996	1996			
MIN	2.31	2.72	1.17	1.16	1.23	1.15	.66	.86	.92	1.45	1.51	1.88			
(WY)	1987	1990	1990	1990	1990	1992	1995	1995	1997	1994	1994	1990			

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1984 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	1610.92	3464.52	
ANNUAL MEAN	4.41	9.49	6.86
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			12.4
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			3.19
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	336	Oct 13	810
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.48	Jul 2	.56
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.51	Jun 28	.59
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			4930
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			14.88
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	3200	6870	4970
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.18	2.54	1.83
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	16.02	34.46	24.93
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.7	5.9	9.6
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.9	1.7	2.0
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.85	1.1	.93

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986 and water years 1989 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1984 to September 1986 and from October 1989 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1989.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow sediment samples were collected by local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 7,300 mg/L Oct. 06, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 33,000 tons (29,900 tonnes) Sep. 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, <0.01 ton (<0.01 tonne) several years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.-

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,590 september 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 6,110 tons (5,540 tonnes) September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, <0.01 (<0.01) several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION		DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION		DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	
	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)
OCTOBER									
1	e2.0	4	e.02	2.7	5	.03	1.9	4	.02
2	e14	50	e1.7	2.2	4	.03	1.8	3	.01
3	e3.8	9	e.12	2.1	4	.02	1.8	2	.01
4	e2.8	8	e.06	2.1	4	.03	1.7	3	.01
5	e2.3	7	e.04	2.1	5	.03	1.7	5	.02
6	e1.8	6	e.03	2.1	8	.05	1.6	6	.03
7	e1.4	5	e.02	2.0	11	.06	1.6	7	.03
8	2.0	4	.02	2.0	11	.06	1.6	8	.04
9	1.8	4	.02	e8.1	45	e3.3	1.5	10	.04
10	2.0	4	.02	e7.4	90	e3.1	1.5	10	.04
11	2.0	6	.03	3.0	7	.06	1.5	5	.02
12	3.0	8	.07	2.5	5	.03	1.5	2	.01
13	e336	687	e2320	2.5	8	.05	1.6	2	.01
14	e97	1280	e708	2.3	12	.07	1.7	2	.01
15	13	50	1.7	2.4	11	.07	1.6	2	.01
16	8.0	24	.54	2.3	9	.05	1.6	7	.03
17	e8.2	18	e.43	2.5	7	.05	2.1	23	.13
18	6.4	17	.29	2.3	5	.03	1.7	24	.11
19	4.3	11	.13	2.2	4	.02	1.8	19	.09
20	3.5	7	.07	2.1	7	.04	1.6	11	.05
21	3.1	4	.03	2.2	14	.08	1.9	6	.03
22	2.8	2	.02	3.3	10	.09	1.7	3	.02
23	2.7	5	.03	3.6	6	.06	2.1	4	.02
24	2.6	7	.05	2.6	5	.03	1.9	5	.02
25	2.8	4	.03	2.2	8	.05	1.8	4	.02
26	2.5	2	.01	3.4	13	.13	1.7	3	.01
27	2.3	1	.01	2.6	10	.07	1.7	5	.02
28	2.3	1	.01	2.1	7	.04	1.6	8	.04
29	2.2	2	.01	2.0	6	.03	1.6	12	.05
30	2.1	3	.02	2.0	5	.03	e1.6	8	e.04
31	2.2	5	.03	---	---	---	1.7	5	.02
TOTAL	542.9	---	3033.56	82.9	---	7.79	52.7	---	1.01

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	1.6	3	.01	1.1	2	<.01	1.4	2	.01
2	1.9	2	.01	1.0	1	<.01	1.4	2	.01
3	1.8	5	.02	.95	2	.01	1.5	3	.01
4	1.9	11	.06	9.7	118	61	1.6	6	.03
5	2.4	24	.15	101	1210	656	1.7	3	.01
6	67	466	350	5.0	41	.60	1.8	1	.01
7	66	777	233	3.2	22	.19	329	1540	5390
8	8.5	110	2.8	44	363	211	7.4	121	4.2
9	4.9	26	.34	11	176	11	2.8	9	.07
10	4.3	12	.14	3.1	8	.07	2.2	3	.02
11	3.6	7	.07	2.4	4	.02	1.9	2	.01
12	2.9	4	.04	2.1	2	.01	1.7	2	.01
13	7.4	64	4.6	1.9	2	.01	1.7	1	<.01
14	5.2	66	1.2	11	84	6.7	1.7	1	.01
15	3.1	7	.06	4.2	29	.40	1.6	2	.01
16	2.6	2	.02	2.6	4	.03	1.6	3	.01
17	2.3	3	.02	2.4	2	.01	1.6	2	.01
18	2.1	5	.03	2.2	1	.01	1.7	1	<.01
19	1.9	8	.04	2.0	1	<.01	2.1	2	.01
20	1.8	4	.02	1.9	1	<.01	14	353	35
21	1.7	2	.01	1.8	1	<.01	3.4	36	.35
22	1.6	2	.01	1.7	1	<.01	2.2	11	.06
23	1.6	3	.01	1.6	1	<.01	1.8	3	.01
24	1.6	5	.02	1.6	1	<.01	1.6	1	.01
25	1.6	8	.03	1.6	1	<.01	1.7	1	<.01
26	1.6	12	.05	1.6	1	<.01	1.5	2	.01
27	1.4	5	.02	1.5	1	<.01	1.9	3	.01
28	1.3	1	<.01	1.5	1	<.01	1.7	3	.01
29	1.3	2	.01	---	---	---	4.8	183	11
30	1.2	3	.01	---	---	---	2.2	23	.14
31	1.1	3	.01	---	---	---	1.6	6	.03
TOTAL	209.2	---	592.82	225.65	---	947.18	404.8	---	5441.10

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	1.5	2	.01	1.2	7	.02	1.4	4	.02
2	2.8	14	.19	1.2	6	.02	1.4	3	.01
3	3.1	18	.16	1.5	4	.02	1.4	2	.01
4	1.6	12	.05	1.5	3	.01	1.3	5	.02
5	1.5	13	.05	1.4	3	.01	1.4	11	.04
6	1.4	12	.05	1.3	5	.02	1.8	9	.04
7	1.4	8	.03	1.3	5	.02	1.3	5	.02
8	1.4	4	.01	1.2	323	78	1.3	3	.01
9	1.3	2	.01	2.6	36	.26	1.3	5	.02
10	1.2	2	.01	1.7	23	.11	1.2	7	.02
11	1.2	2	.01	1.5	15	.06	1.2	6	.02
12	2.2	30	.19	1.4	8	.03	1.5	4	.02
13	1.4	22	.09	1.6	5	.02	1.5	4	.01
14	1.3	11	.04	2.7	42	1.1	1.3	3	.01
15	1.3	6	.02	2.6	58	.54	1.2	3	.01
16	2.0	23	.21	1.6	8	.04	1.5	3	.01
17	2.3	19	.17	1.5	6	.02	1.2	3	.01
18	2.0	10	.08	1.9	16	.12	e1.3	5	e.02
19	e1.7	10	e.05	1.8	32	.16	e1.4	9	e.03
20	4.3	135	5.5	1.6	18	.08	1.3	8	.03
21	2.4	24	.16	1.4	13	.05	1.7	6	.03
22	2.1	13	.08	1.3	11	.04	2.0	5	.03
23	1.5	8	.03	1.4	12	.04	1.4	5	.02
24	1.4	5	.02	1.4	14	.05	1.2	5	.02
25	1.4	4	.01	1.2	16	.05	1.2	6	.02
26	1.4	3	.01	1.3	12	.04	1.2	8	.02
27	1.4	3	.01	3.5	38	.54	1.1	7	.02
28	1.6	2	.01	1.6	15	.06	1.2	7	.02
29	1.4	2	.01	1.6	18	.08	1.1	6	.02
30	1.3	4	.01	1.9	13	.06	1.1	6	.02
31	---	---	---	1.7	7	.03	---	---	---
TOTAL	52.8	---	7.28	62.2	---	81.70	40.4	---	0.60

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	1.1	7	.02	.62	14	.02	2.4	6	.04
2	1.1	8	.02	.60	9	.01	3.1	20	.25
3	1.1	11	.03	.60	6	.01	3.1	17	.14
4	2.1	33	.18	.58	4	.01	2.8	13	.10
5	2.1	49	.30	.56	2	<.01	2.3	15	.10
6	1.2	19	.06	e.57	5	e.01	2.5	20	.14
7	1.2	13	.04	e1.0	9	e.03	2.6	26	.18
8	1.1	11	.03	1.2	11	.04	8.3	278	17
9	1.0	8	.02	1.1	12	.04	4.3	84	1.8
10	1.0	5	.01	.91	13	.03	4.3	41	.52
11	.99	5	.01	.94	8	.02	2.6	13	.09
12	1.0	5	.01	.85	5	.01	2.4	10	.06
13	.91	6	.01	.75	4	.01	4.2	66	1.1
14	.87	6	.01	.69	4	.01	2.9	31	.24
15	.90	6	.01	.69	4	.01	7.3	579	33
16	1.2	7	.02	.86	7	.01	3.3	22	.19
17	1.2	7	.02	1.1	9	.03	3.0	13	.11
18	1.4	7	.03	.96	7	.02	3.1	10	.08
19	1.4	7	.03	.81	5	.01	3.4	9	.09
20	30	424	75	.84	5	.01	4.9	31	.56
21	2.1	38	.23	1.2	5	.02	434	1260	6110
22	1.0	18	.05	5.3	194	15	810	1590	6050
23	.75	8	.02	1.3	12	.05	100	105	43
24	.85	7	.02	105	955	734	19	18	.95
25	.72	8	.01	91	869	453	4.6	12	.15
26	.68	9	.02	11	128	6.4	5.5	9	.14
27	.66	9	.02	4.6	23	.28	6.7	9	.16
28	.82	5	.01	3.4	12	.11	7.7	9	.18
29	.71	3	<.01	3.0	8	.06	11	8	.25
30	.65	6	.01	2.7	6	.04	10	8	.23
31	.63	16	.03	2.5	4	.03	---	---	---
TOTAL	62.44	---	76.29	247.23	---	1209.34	1481.3	---	12260.85
YEAR	3464.52		23659.52						

e Estimated

< Actual value is known to be less than the value shown

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
JAN					
07...	1510	173	913	426	97
07...	1700	52	327	46	98
13...	2100	31	449	38	98
MAR					
07...	1830	1070	3090	8930	83
20...	1600	14	350	13	99
29...	1700	36	1820	177	98
JUL					
20...	1515	43	2710	315	100
AUG					
22...	0437	44	3770	448	100
25...	2250	66	549	98	92
SEP					
21...	2310	2670	4140	29800	67
22...	0455	572	1300	2010	85

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)	
JAN								
07...	1426	378	2370	2420	33	42	54	
MAR								
07...	1545	968	4760	12400	21	29	36	
AUG								
24...	1600	53	665	95	54	69	80	
SEP								
15...	0829	21	245	14	26	40	60	
21...	1910	586	4040	6390	38	50	64	
DATE		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70335)
JAN								
07...	66	78	85	94	99	100	100	
MAR								
07...	46	59	71	85	94	98	100	
AUG								
24...	88	97	98	100	100	100	100	
SEP								
15...	77	86	91	98	99	100	100	
21...	76	83	87	94	97	98	100	

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'13", long 65°57'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at downstream side of bridge on Highway 912, at Barrio Cerro Gordo, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) south of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--10.2 mi² (26.4 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1977 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 490 ft (150 m), from topographic map. Prior to Oct. 1, 1983, at site 2,000 ft (610 m) downstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Sand removal at a commercial level is practiced at times during the year. This takes place about one hundred feet downstream from the low water control. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	37	46	e37	74	e29	e21	e37	e21	e26	14	22	38
2	216	28	e34	57	e26	e21	e41	e22	e22	17	18	48
3	62	41	e34	65	e25	e24	e37	e25	e20	22	15	68
4	65	34	e32	107	e29	e23	e30	e26	20	60	15	54
5	34	e37	e33	84	e620	e21	e35	e24	22	66	31	36
6	28	e34	e32	591	e64	e21	e30	e23	25	20	e133	69
7	30	e30	e31	e517	e54	e960	e28	e22	22	37	31	161
8	33	e28	e30	e213	e120	e66	e28	e56	37	23	22	332
9	43	e54	e31	158	e82	e33	e26	e39	30	43	45	165
10	37	e400	e30	321	e41	e27	e24	e27	28	21	36	e135
11	81	e43	e30	95	e31	e24	e25	e23	22	16	43	82
12	140	e35	e32	52	e27	e23	e56	e22	52	14	31	66
13	406	e34	33	70	e26	e22	e30	e32	69	18	26	97
14	1750	e31	29	71	e130	e24	e26	e37	25	21	24	122
15	223	e32	37	46	e52	e25	e24	e43	28	14	26	502
16	134	e31	44	e40	e35	e22	e35	e31	30	16	29	e68
17	93	e32	68	e32	e33	e21	e42	e26	48	14	331	e52
18	60	e30	42	e36	e29	e20	e47	e23	34	35	82	e50
19	50	e30	34	36	e28	e22	e36	e22	30	25	32	e52
20	47	e29	33	28	e26	e110	e66	e21	23	144	53	e50
21	51	e54	69	25	e25	e50	e50	e19	27	73	88	e2900
22	41	e60	55	36	e23	e35	e38	e19	61	23	250	e4100
23	38	e64	48	31	e22	e29	e30	e23	24	16	75	e140
24	37	e49	47	36	e21	e26	e28	e21	19	58	742	e94
25	38	e41	43	e40	e21	e30	e27	e18	21	22	e860	e80
26	36	e58	38	e36	e21	e29	e26	86	20	20	e90	e70
27	29	e49	30	30	e19	e34	e27	117	21	39	e90	e78
28	31	e40	31	31	e22	e31	e30	21	21	65	e78	e70
29	35	e38	32	44	---	e50	e25	24	15	29	e84	e62
30	39	e40	42	48	---	e86	e22	141	15	27	e70	e56
31	37	---	30	34	---	e58	---	26	---	22	e41	---
TOTAL	3981	1552	1171	3084	1681	1988	1006	1080	857	1034	3513	9897
MEAN	128	51.7	37.8	99.5	60.0	64.1	33.5	34.8	28.6	33.4	113	330
MAX	1750	400	69	591	620	960	66	141	69	144	860	4100
MIN	28	28	29	25	19	20	22	18	15	14	15	36
AC-FT	7900	3080	2320	6120	3330	3940	2000	2140	1700	2050	6970	19630
CFSM	12.6	5.07	3.70	9.75	5.89	6.29	3.29	3.42	2.80	3.27	11.1	32.3
IN.	14.52	5.66	4.27	11.25	6.13	7.25	3.67	3.94	3.13	3.77	12.81	36.09

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1977 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992
MEAN	62.3	68.3	44.2	33.3	30.8	24.2	21.0	42.9	44.6	43.5	51.9	81.1				
MAX	176	196	163	99.5	74.1	64.1	46.0	155	140	118	202	330				
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1998	1997	1998	1985	1985	1979	1979	1979	1998				
MIN	14.4	19.2	12.5	14.6	11.0	11.3	10.7	9.68	10.9	15.4	14.5	16.9				
(WY)	1992	1982	1992	1990	1992	1992	1980	1990	1994	1994	1991	1980				

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1977 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	18902.5	30844	
ANNUAL MEAN	51.8	84.5	45.7
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			89.7
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			18.6
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1750	Oct 14	4100 Sep 22
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	8.4	May 6	14 Jul 1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	10	May 3	16 Jul 11
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			12700 Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			23.26 Sep 21
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	37490	61180	33100
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	5.08	8.28	4.48
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	68.94	112.49	60.87
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	95	96	70
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	29	34	25
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	12	21	13

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°11'09", long 65°57'42", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at upstream side of bridge on Highway 183 by-pass, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) south from Plaza de San Lorenzo, 1.4 mi (2.2 km), southwest from Escuela Rafael Colón García and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northwest from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Carlos Zayas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--25.0 mi² (64.8 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 262 ft (80 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated discharges, which are poor. Water purification plant located about 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from gage. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	84	93	72	71	e78	57	121	55	61	39	36	77
2	195	86	66	69	e74	54	136	56	54	39	34	79
3	96	87	64	67	e71	63	124	64	53	42	33	107
4	91	88	62	114	e84	61	101	67	54	108	31	103
5	80	86	63	94	e1600	54	118	62	54	89	31	73
6	73	81	61	711	e220	55	101	59	69	46	e61	116
7	68	79	58	695	e130	1460	92	55	56	51	50	151
8	71	79	58	332	e400	236	93	141	57	48	73	265
9	74	101	60	287	e300	116	86	98	58	48	86	197
10	70	647	57	386	e120	96	81	71	54	42	70	149
11	111	129	57	187	e90	83	83	58	47	38	62	94
12	162	106	61	162	e82	79	187	56	68	35	47	82
13	954	104	59	169	70	75	101	79	84	33	43	124
14	3120	94	58	169	151	85	86	93	53	41	36	122
15	376	94	57	129	126	88	81	108	47	35	36	337
16	249	93	57	123	85	75	117	78	53	40	36	126
17	217	95	89	114	83	72	140	67	77	36	175	98
18	173	90	60	109	78	70	155	60	e61	58	74	92
19	139	89	57	104	72	77	e119	57	61	62	49	96
20	124	87	54	103	71	380	217	55	51	215	55	e94
21	117	105	77	98	69	165	131	51	55	110	81	e3700
22	111	113	60	96	65	118	93	50	91	54	211	e5020
23	108	101	58	98	63	98	76	57	52	46	95	603
24	102	93	54	99	60	89	72	53	47	63	903	401
25	104	79	52	104	58	103	69	46	45	52	1160	336
26	97	110	50	104	61	99	67	99	46	43	330	296
27	93	94	50	94	60	114	68	132	46	46	144	332
28	91	76	50	90	59	103	75	61	50	64	111	302
29	90	72	49	92	---	182	64	72	43	48	119	261
30	87	76	53	e83	---	289	57	125	40	43	93	240
31	88	---	52	e80	---	200	---	86	---	41	83	---
TOTAL	7615	3327	1835	5233	4480	4896	3111	2271	1687	1755	4448	14073
MEAN	246	111	59.2	169	160	158	104	73.3	56.2	56.6	143	469
MAX	3120	647	89	711	1600	1460	217	141	91	215	1160	5020
MIN	68	72	49	67	58	54	57	46	40	33	31	73
AC-FT	15100	6600	3640	10380	8890	9710	6170	4500	3350	3480	8820	27910
CFSM	9.83	4.44	2.37	6.75	6.40	6.32	4.15	2.93	2.25	2.26	5.74	18.8
IN.	11.33	4.95	2.73	7.79	6.67	7.29	4.63	3.38	2.51	2.61	6.62	20.94

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	137	129	85.5	109	82.1	61.9	43.9	64.5	109
MAX	266	223	110	192	160	158	104	186	290
(WY)	1991	1992	1993	1992	1998	1998	1998	1992	1992
MIN	77.6	69.2	59.2	50.1	21.0	17.4	16.8	25.2	42.3
(WY)	1993	1996	1998	1995	1992	1992	1992	1995	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	33576	54731	
ANNUAL MEAN	92.0	150	108
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			154
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			67.8
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	3120	Oct 14	5020
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	21	Jul 3	31
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	24	Jun 28	36
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			36600
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			30.14
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	66600	108600	78520
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.68	6.00	4.34
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	49.96	81.44	58.90
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	133	213	176
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	63	81	63
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	34	48	26

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water year 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: February 1990 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1990.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediment samples were collected by a local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,080 mg/L November 10, 1997; Minimum daily mean, 5 mg/L Several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 80,600 tons (73,100 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.20 ton (0.18 tonne) May 05, 1992.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,080 mg/l November 10, 1997; Minimum daily mean, 11 mg/l March 11, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 56,000 tons (50,800 tonnes) September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1.8 tons (1.6 tonnes) April 30, 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	84	102	23	93	39	9.7	72	49	9.6
2	195	564	459	86	39	9.1	66	72	13
3	96	121	31	87	42	10	64	94	16
4	91	121	30	88	64	15	62	83	14
5	80	124	27	86	82	19	63	68	12
6	73	125	25	81	43	9.5	61	42	6.9
7	68	113	21	79	23	4.8	58	23	3.6
8	71	105	20	79	21	4.5	58	16	2.5
9	74	107	21	101	64	23	60	30	4.9
10	70	110	21	647	3080	11100	57	50	7.7
11	111	314	184	129	281	99	57	34	5.2
12	162	536	407	106	142	41	61	21	3.5
13	954	1390	20000	104	97	27	59	23	3.7
14	3120	2760	49200	94	74	19	58	28	4.4
15	376	165	169	94	83	21	57	36	5.5
16	249	74	50	93	100	25	57	62	9.6
17	217	188	128	95	114	29	89	92	25
18	173	273	129	90	109	26	60	52	8.5
19	139	205	77	89	102	25	57	51	7.8
20	124	151	51	87	101	24	54	50	7.2
21	117	108	34	105	153	46	77	49	10
22	111	83	25	113	155	48	60	48	7.8
23	108	86	25	101	139	38	58	43	6.7
24	102	93	26	93	122	31	54	38	5.5
25	104	103	29	79	121	26	52	34	4.8
26	97	113	30	110	168	50	50	32	4.3
27	93	117	30	94	67	18	50	34	4.5
28	91	92	23	76	25	5.0	50	36	4.9
29	90	70	17	72	28	5.5	49	38	5.0
30	87	52	12	76	37	7.6	53	38	5.5
31	88	40	9.5	---	---	---	52	37	5.2
TOTAL	7615	---	71333.5	3327	---	11815.7	1835	---	234.8

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	71	83	18	e78	70	e17	57	18	2.8
2	69	92	17	e74	66	e18	54	20	2.9
3	67	89	16	e71	52	e15	63	30	5.2
4	114	159	50	e84	32	e16	61	51	8.4
5	94	142	37	e1600	173	e15100	54	87	13
6	711	1350	6300	e220	888	e230	55	123	18
7	695	923	2030	e130	660	e53	1460	2070	25200
8	332	459	448	e400	278	e594	236	340	260
9	287	299	240	e300	121	e321	116	109	35
10	386	514	661	e120	82	e53	96	35	9.2
11	187	163	85	e90	69	e24	83	11	2.6
12	162	125	58	e82	98	e13	79	16	3.4
13	169	280	110	70	121	23	75	34	6.8
14	169	176	87	151	181	119	85	33	7.6
15	129	56	20	126	153	57	88	27	6.4
16	123	26	8.7	85	42	9.6	75	23	4.6
17	114	32	9.9	83	39	8.7	72	33	6.4
18	109	43	13	78	53	11	70	54	10
19	104	56	16	72	82	16	77	83	17
20	103	50	14	71	122	23	380	538	1070
21	98	41	11	69	130	24	165	270	128
22	96	34	8.8	65	129	23	118	100	32
23	98	29	7.6	63	113	19	98	37	9.8
24	99	36	9.5	60	56	9.1	89	30	7.1
25	104	49	14	58	27	4.3	103	29	8.1
26	104	67	19	61	20	3.3	99	29	7.8
27	94	74	19	60	18	2.9	114	108	35
28	90	77	19	59	18	2.8	103	144	40
29	92	78	19	---	---	---	182	200	196
30	e83	77	e14	---	---	---	289	318	601
31	e80	74	e18	---	---	---	200	241	160
TOTAL	5233	---	10397.5	4480	---	16809.7	4896	---	27914.1

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	121	58	19	55	13	2.0	61	58	9.6
2	136	107	53	56	21	3.1	54	31	4.6
3	124	103	37	64	36	6.3	53	21	3.0
4	101	54	15	67	59	11	54	39	5.8
5	118	106	40	62	56	9.3	54	83	12
6	101	87	24	59	84	13	69	83	15
7	92	60	15	55	67	9.9	56	68	10
8	93	46	12	141	431	456	57	59	9.2
9	86	36	8.3	98	163	44	58	88	14
10	81	28	6.1	71	92	18	54	134	19
11	83	22	4.9	58	59	9.2	47	97	12
12	187	463	340	56	63	9.6	68	77	18
13	101	72	20	79	120	26	84	80	27
14	86	43	10	93	167	42	53	61	8.8
15	81	33	7.2	108	214	61	47	36	4.5
16	117	90	40	78	162	34	53	58	8.4
17	140	182	75	67	108	20	77	89	20
18	155	394	282	60	73	12	e61	79	e9.6
19	e119	181	e54	57	58	8.8	61	116	19
20	217	251	220	55	47	7.0	51	111	15
21	131	235	65	51	35	4.9	55	100	15
22	93	108	28	50	27	3.6	91	125	32
23	76	53	11	57	33	5.1	52	75	11
24	72	33	6.4	53	45	6.3	47	50	6.4
25	69	29	5.4	46	58	7.2	45	46	5.7
26	67	30	5.4	99	92	40	46	46	5.7
27	68	29	5.3	132	190	78	46	41	5.1
28	75	19	3.7	61	99	16	50	36	4.8
29	64	12	2.0	72	83	17	43	31	3.7
30	57	12	1.8	125	100	63	40	35	3.8
31	---	---	---	86	96	68	---	---	---
TOTAL	3111	---	1416.5	2271	---	1111.3	1687	---	337.7

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 Rio GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	39	42	4.4	36	36	3.5	77	85	18
2	39	48	5.0	34	46	4.2	79	109	24
3	42	58	6.8	33	56	4.9	107	122	43
4	108	96	46	31	50	4.2	103	123	35
5	89	82	32	31	59	4.9	73	95	19
6	46	55	6.9	e61	61	e9.6	116	342	200
7	51	41	5.6	50	90	12	151	117	61
8	48	34	4.5	73	127	36	265	518	644
9	48	27	3.6	86	136	32	197	463	407
10	42	22	2.5	70	68	13	149	220	96
11	38	25	2.6	62	81	14	94	82	21
12	35	31	2.9	47	118	15	82	70	16
13	33	38	3.4	43	103	12	124	143	68
14	41	47	5.2	36	78	7.5	122	100	35
15	35	58	5.5	36	61	5.9	337	455	860
16	40	71	7.7	36	55	5.2	126	137	48
17	36	77	7.5	175	97	241	98	110	29
18	58	77	18	74	160	32	92	112	28
19	62	90	15	49	156	21	96	114	29
20	215	470	458	55	196	29	e94	117	26
21	110	665	199	81	225	49	e3700	1270	e56000
22	54	552	80	211	146	82	e5020	2300	e49100
23	46	367	46	95	145	39	603	122	225
24	63	227	38	903	1800	10800	401	48	52
25	52	124	18	1160	977	5020	336	34	31
26	43	65	7.5	330	438	477	296	51	41
27	46	42	5.3	144	215	84	332	193	272
28	64	79	16	111	177	53	302	141	127
29	48	55	7.3	119	142	54	261	49	35
30	43	36	4.2	93	113	29	240	48	32
31	41	31	3.4	83	69	16	---	---	---
TOTAL	1755	---	1067.8	4448	---	17209.9	14073	---	108622
YEAR	54731		268270.5						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-	SEDI-	SEDI-	SED.
		CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
NOV					
10...	1050	398	2540	2730	98
JAN					
07...	1630	495	728	973	87
MAR					
07...	1500	2180	7900	46500	58
07...	1900	3600	6010	58400	70
AUG					
24...	1530	894	2450	5910	88
SEP					
21...	2015	5920	2300	36800	73
22...	0815	8840	3340	79700	62

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 Rio GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)
		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)
SEP 22...	0100	13200	5600	200000	19	26	37
SEP 22...	47	59	67	80	92	99	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'35", long 66°02'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank at Highway 765, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of Villa Borinquen, 8.1 mi (13.0 km) upstream from Río Grande de Loiza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.14 mi² (18.49 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 492 ft (150 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12	e17	e15	e11	11	e12	21	14	15	9.3	9.9	12
2	24	e15	e14	e13	11	e12	48	14	14	8.8	9.2	13
3	14	e14	13	e13	11	12	e32	17	14	14	9.8	21
4	13	e13	13	e14	20	e12	e23	16	13	33	9.4	25
5	12	e13	13	e13	149	e12	21	15	14	13	9.1	13
6	12	e13	13	e110	30	12	19	14	16	11	11	14
7	12	e12	13	e150	20	81	18	14	13	11	19	15
8	15	e11	12	e60	29	57	18	38	13	11	36	48
9	14	e17	12	e56	26	29	17	23	13	10	23	30
10	13	e120	12	e56	e18	24	17	18	12	10	18	20
11	21	e21	12	e26	e13	21	18	16	11	9.8	13	14
12	39	e17	13	e22	e12	21	32	15	16	9.6	12	12
13	274	e16	12	30	e11	21	19	23	15	9.6	11	31
14	486	e15	12	27	e56	22	17	24	11	9.3	10	16
15	113	e14	12	19	e28	21	16	23	11	9.6	13	95
16	75	e13	e13	18	e15	20	18	19	12	10	11	27
17	85	e14	e15	17	e14	20	19	16	13	9.5	36	19
18	60	e13	e13	15	16	19	17	21	e11	12	15	22
19	39	e14	e12	13	15	19	17	16	11	12	12	19
20	31	e13	12	13	14	82	31	15	11	34	12	23
21	28	e19	14	13	14	42	19	14	11	17	21	e827
22	25	e25	13	13	14	29	17	14	16	12	109	e1190
23	24	e33	12	12	13	23	17	14	11	11	21	166
24	22	e25	12	13	e13	20	17	14	10	12	197	94
25	21	e19	e12	14	e13	21	17	14	10	11	189	70
26	20	e20	e12	13	e13	20	17	32	10	10	72	57
27	e19	e17	e12	12	12	28	17	43	10	11	26	57
28	e17	e16	e12	12	12	21	18	18	11	12	20	48
29	e18	e15	e11	11	---	35	15	18	10	11	17	62
30	e16	e16	e12	11	---	38	15	21	9.9	10	15	43
31	e15	---	e12	11	---	29	---	16	---	10	13	---
TOTAL	1589	600	390	831	623	835	607	589	367.9	383.5	999.4	3103
MEAN	51.3	20.0	12.6	26.8	22.3	26.9	20.2	19.0	12.3	12.4	32.2	103
MAX	486	120	15	150	149	82	48	43	16	34	197	1190
MIN	12	11	11	11	11	12	15	14	9.9	8.8	9.1	12
MED	21	16	12	13	14	21	18	16	12	11	15	26
AC-FT	3150	1190	774	1650	1240	1660	1200	1170	730	761	1980	6150
CFSM	7.18	2.80	1.76	3.75	3.12	3.77	2.83	2.66	1.72	1.73	4.52	14.5
IN.	8.28	3.13	2.03	4.33	3.25	4.35	3.16	3.07	1.92	2.00	5.21	16.17

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	27.3	23.2	17.0	23.0	17.7	13.6	10.0	15.1	25.4
MAX	51.3	37.9	23.1	47.5	25.0	26.9	20.2	31.9	67.9
(WY)	1998	1992	1991	1992	1997	1998	1993	1996	1996
MIN	10.3	18.6	10.6	7.85	8.93	7.35	6.18	6.11	9.59
(WY)	1994	1996	1994	1990	1990	1993	1990	1994	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	7243.8	10917.8	
ANNUAL MEAN	19.8	29.9	23.2
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			38.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			12.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	486	Oct 14	1190
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6.3	Jul 4	8
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	6.8	Jun 28	9.6
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			13100
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			21.62
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			8.3
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	14370	21660	16790
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.78	4.19	3.25
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	37.74	56.88	44.09
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	28	40	35
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	13	15	12
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.1	11	6.1

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water year 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1990 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1990.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediments samples were collected by local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 9,230 mg/L September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L Several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 80,900 tons (73,400 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 ton (0.01 tonne) Several days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, e50,900 tons (46,200 tonnes) September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.06 ton (0.05 tonne), July 19, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e5,790 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 2 severals days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	12	62	2.0	e17	2	e.09	e15	9	e.33
2	24	83	6.6	e15	2	e.09	e14	9	e.32
3	14	21	.81	e14	2	e.09	13	8	.29
4	13	15	.51	e13	2	e.09	13	7	.24
5	12	13	.44	e13	2	e.09	13	5	.19
6	12	12	.37	e13	3	e.09	13	4	.15
7	12	11	.33	e12	3	e.09	13	5	.16
8	15	28	2.2	e11	3	e.09	12	6	.20
9	14	45	1.7	e17	3	e.19	12	8	.25
10	13	27	.99	e120	3	e113	12	9	.29
11	21	61	6.5	e21	3	e.15	12	10	.34
12	39	86	36	e17	3	e.19	13	11	.39
13	274	982	5140	e16	4	e.19	12	8	.25
14	486	1180	4470	e15	4	e.09	12	4	.14
15	113	304	112	e14	4	e.09	12	2	.08
16	75	156	34	e13	4	e.09	e13	2	e.06
17	85	364	143	e14	4	e.09	e15	4	e.57
18	60	73	14	e13	5	e.09	e13	10	e.57
19	39	13	1.4	e14	5	e.09	e12	17	e.57
20	31	11	.93	e13	5	e.09	12	16	.55
21	28	9	.68	e19	5	e.19	14	16	.60
22	25	6	.40	e25	6	e.40	13	12	.43
23	24	4	.22	e33	6	e.93	12	9	.30
24	22	2	.13	e25	6	e.40	12	6	.21
25	21	3	.15	e19	7	e.24	e12	5	e.15
26	20	4	.19	e20	7	e.24	e12	5	e.15
27	e19	5	e.24	e17	7	e.33	e12	7	e.15
28	e17	4	e.19	e16	8	e.33	e12	9	e.15
29	e18	3	e.14	e15	8	e.33	e11	13	e.15
30	e16	2	e.09	e16	8	e.31	e12	17	e.15
31	e15	2	e.09	---	---	---	e12	24	e.15
TOTAL	1589	---	9976.30	600	---	118.77	390	---	8.53

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	e11	33	e.15	11	5	.16	e12	12	e.38
2	e13	46	e.57	11	5	.14	e12	9	e.28
3	e13	64	e.57	11	6	.17	12	6	.20
4	e14	89	e.60	20	17	28	e12	4	e.13
5	e13	123	e.57	149	80	392	e12	4	e.11
6	e110	170	e112	30	81	7.1	12	3	.10
7	e150	163	e112	20	17	.96	81	9	178
8	e60	193	e14	29	69	18	57	53	41
9	e56	169	e35	26	56	5.1	29	55	4.4
10	e56	79	e35	e18	4	e.17	24	16	1.0
11	e26	56	e4.4	e13	3	e.14	21	11	.63
12	e22	53	e.20	e12	3	e.13	21	8	.44
13	30	92	13	e11	3	e.12	21	6	.31
14	27	60	5.2	e56	4	e41	22	4	.25
15	19	12	.62	e28	5	e5.0	21	5	.31
16	18	6	.31	e15	8	e.36	20	7	.40
17	17	4	.16	e14	8	e.36	20	9	.50
18	15	5	.19	16	6	.26	19	10	.52
19	13	8	.27	15	7	.27	19	10	.52
20	13	11	.40	14	8	.30	82	281	110
21	13	10	.36	14	9	.33	42	16	1.9
22	13	9	.31	14	10	.37	29	13	1.0
23	12	8	.27	13	10	.37	23	13	.80
24	13	7	.23	e13	8	e.27	20	12	.66
25	14	6	.23	e13	6	e.20	21	9	.54
26	13	7	.25	e13	4	e.16	20	7	.37
27	12	9	.27	12	6	.20	28	5	.39
28	12	10	.30	12	9	.29	21	5	.29
29	11	8	.26	---	---	---	35	14	23
30	11	7	.21	---	---	---	38	100	15
31	11	6	.18	---	---	---	29	54	4.6
TOTAL	831	---	338.08	623	---	501.93	835	---	388.03

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	21	23	1.3	14	8	.31	15	14	.55
2	48	116	35	14	7	.26	14	8	.32
3	e32	55	e4.7	17	8	.38	14	7	.27
4	e23	34	e2.1	16	10	.41	13	10	.38
5	21	21	1.2	15	11	.44	14	11	.41
6	19	13	.68	14	7	.28	16	29	1.3
7	18	8	.41	14	7	.24	13	13	.44
8	18	6	.26	38	102	24	13	9	.30
9	17	5	.23	23	72	4.5	13	10	.34
10	17	5	.22	18	23	1.1	12	12	.40
11	18	12	.82	16	8	.32	11	14	.41
12	32	85	9.3	15	5	.21	16	26	1.9
13	19	12	.60	23	11	6.8	15	17	.73
14	17	9	.40	24	42	4.1	11	12	.36
15	16	8	.36	23	50	3.3	11	10	.30
16	18	18	.93	19	25	1.3	12	13	.51
17	19	47	2.6	16	21	.92	13	20	.71
18	17	19	.86	21	14	5.2	e11	18	.52
19	17	18	.88	16	10	.41	11	10	.31
20	31	104	16	15	13	.52	11	5	.16
21	19	21	1.1	14	17	.67	11	5	.15
22	17	18	.83	14	9	.32	16	32	1.7
23	17	16	.71	14	4	.16	11	11	.33
24	17	13	.60	14	4	.15	10	8	.21
25	17	11	.49	14	4	.15	10	10	.28
26	17	9	.42	32	114	15	10	16	.44
27	17	11	.50	43	126	28	10	22	.63
28	18	12	.61	18	17	.79	11	16	.47
29	15	14	.57	18	29	3.1	10	11	.31
30	15	11	.44	21	42	2.5	9.9	14	.38
31	---	---	---	16	22	.99	---	---	---
TOTAL	607	---	85.12	589	---	106.83	367.9	---	15.52

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	9.3	20	.51	9.9	24	.63	12	8	.27
2	8.8	21	.50	9.2	14	.36	13	18	1.6
3	14	37	2.3	9.8	8	.20	21	68	4.3
4	33	120	18	9.4	9	.22	25	122	7.3
5	13	31	1.1	9.1	22	.56	13	80	2.8
6	11	15	.45	11	33	.94	14	31	1.4
7	11	8	.23	19	31	6.7	15	19	.80
8	11	10	.31	36	141	46	48	108	54
9	10	16	.44	23	81	5.0	30	9	.76
10	10	19	.53	18	34	1.7	20	8	.44
11	9.8	23	.60	13	15	.53	14	8	.29
12	9.6	17	.45	12	10	.33	12	7	.24
13	9.6	12	.31	11	8	.25	31	8	34
14	9.3	9	.22	10	8	.22	16	9	.37
15	9.6	11	.28	13	33	1.7	95	338	319
16	10	13	.36	11	29	1.0	27	11	.77
17	9.5	6	.16	36	17	43	19	10	.54
18	12	2	.07	15	17	.66	22	33	2.9
19	12	2	.06	12	14	.46	19	22	1.1
20	34	106	17	12	13	.42	23	50	4.2
21	17	43	2.3	21	15	4.4	e827	3390	e50900
22	12	21	.65	109	21	473	e1190	5790	e35600
23	11	18	.51	21	26	4.3	166	25	11
24	12	13	.44	197	38	1540	94	20	5.1
25	11	10	.31	189	385	644	70	11	2.1
26	10	11	.30	72	163	48	57	6	1.0
27	11	11	.33	26	28	2.0	57	33	7.7
28	12	13	.43	20	16	.86	48	9	1.2
29	11	15	.42	17	10	.46	62	11	2.0
30	10	18	.49	15	9	.36	43	9	1.1
31	10	21	.58	13	9	.31	---	---	---
TOTAL	383.5	---	50.64	999.4	---	2828.57	3103	---	86968.28
YEAR	10917.8		101386.60						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
14...	0445	792	1410	1510	87
15...	1230	108	100	29	98
AUG					
20...	1214	13	165	5.8	98
SEP					
03...	1520	23	83	5.2	97

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)	
OCT 14...	0030	1590	5050	21700	18	26	35	
DATE	TIME	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70335)
OCT 14...	45	45	55	62	72	84	95	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'33", long 66°00'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank 250 ft (76 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 189, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) downstream from Río Turabo, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) east of Plaza de Caguas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--89.8 mi² (232.6 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1959 (low-flow measurement only), February to November 1959 (monthly measurements only), December 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 143.28 ft (43.672 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	98	127	98	67	79	78	171	83	78	42	49	154
2	337	120	92	89	73	74	204	85	68	43	46	157
3	140	111	85	78	71	79	217	92	67	44	42	261
4	113	115	84	135	84	78	139	100	68	143	41	271
5	88	105	80	125	2390	132	147	95	81	120	37	161
6	75	103	79	1780	334	85	139	86	103	63	e51	188
7	66	94	75	1600	195	2250	139	84	73	58	e155	319
8	66	89	73	513	597	661	143	293	71	61	97	628
9	104	92	72	e395	449	204	116	197	74	56	180	368
10	91	1280	74	e583	174	146	107	109	74	54	115	345
11	188	178	69	250	135	132	105	79	59	45	82	197
12	371	139	70	217	123	116	275	70	95	45	72	168
13	752	124	76	243	105	110	145	79	125	40	59	232
14	6490	117	71	299	248	112	112	128	73	43	51	283
15	1070	116	70	177	280	120	102	157	62	41	54	733
16	640	117	69	153	143	104	140	105	66	45	59	314
17	747	110	120	143	128	88	201	84	116	49	241	221
18	527	103	88	129	116	86	203	77	e76	61	140	190
19	323	107	78	119	107	87	e178	80	e75	97	74	204
20	258	101	67	114	98	749	305	70	61	418	73	192
21	213	106	96	112	98	349	253	69	73	241	137	e3490
22	206	179	86	106	91	168	169	61	124	85	536	e8930
23	190	161	74	104	85	134	115	64	74	64	210	1150
24	179	129	73	107	82	113	107	71	60	83	1630	575
25	175	120	66	114	73	131	102	60	58	81	2430	462
26	163	171	64	119	79	124	100	131	55	59	720	399
27	147	165	62	102	84	148	105	251	53	61	339	374
28	144	112	60	98	78	135	109	94	59	98	258	456
29	131	100	58	86	---	374	e99	87	54	76	269	337
30	125	104	62	85	---	464	87	180	49	54	202	292
31	121	---	60	80	---	409	---	114	---	54	165	---
TOTAL	14338	4795	2351	8322	6599	8040	4534	3335	2224	2524	8614	22051
MEAN	463	160	75.8	268	236	259	151	108	74.1	81.4	278	735
MAX	6490	1280	120	1780	2390	2250	305	293	125	418	2430	8930
MIN	66	89	58	67	71	74	87	60	49	40	37	154
AC-FT	28440	9510	4660	16510	13090	15950	8990	6610	4410	5010	17090	43740
CFSM	5.15	1.78	.84	2.99	2.62	2.89	1.68	1.20	.83	.91	3.09	8.19
IN.	5.94	1.99	.97	3.45	2.73	3.33	1.88	1.38	.92	1.05	3.57	9.13

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1960 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1960	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1995	1974	1975	1974	1974	1994	1967
MEAN	358	311	217	148	113	95.5	91.3	223	243	225	266	328	
MAX	1910	1131	714	559	291	306	355	863	1283	660	949	1438	
(WY)	1971	1988	1988	1992	1984	1989	1978	1985	1979	1961	1979	1960	
MIN	44.2	64.9	33.6	45.3	35.6	23.2	30.6	33.7	34.1	21.8	51.4	37.4	
(WY)	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1995	1974	1975	1974	1994	1967	

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1960 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	55612	87727		
ANNUAL MEAN	152	240		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			216	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			526	1979
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN			82.3	1967
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6490	Oct 14	8930	Sep 22
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	23	Jul 4	37	Aug 5
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	28	Jun 29	44	Jul 11
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			49000	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			25.64	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS LOW STAGE			35	Aug 6
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	110300	174000	156500	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.70	2.68	2.41	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	23.04	36.34	32.68	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	229	372	360	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	88	107	106	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	43	60	40	

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1983 to September 1995.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-49 sediment sampler since October 1983. Sediment pumping sampler since 1984.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 14,500 mg/L Nov. 27, 1987; Minimum daily mean, 8 mg/L January 23, 1992.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 396,000 tons (359,000 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.65 tons (0.59 tonnes) May 25, 1995.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 6,300 mg/L September 22, 1998 ; minimum daily mean, 13 mg/L January 2, 3, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 254,000 tons (230,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; minimum daily 2.7 ton (2.4 tonnes) December 27, 28, 1997.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (PER-CENT SATUR-LEVEL) (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)
OCT 15...	1000	1010	152	6.6	25.5	80	7.4	90	16	31000	22000
MAR 10...	0935	161	238	7.0	25.0	17	7.2	87	<10	K16000	2000
JUN 02...	0900	70	271	6.8	29.5	14	6.7	88	<10	3400	K170
SEP 04...	0830	489	202	6.3	27.5	290	6.6	84	<10	31000	49000

DATE	HARD-NESS (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET CACO3 (MG/L AS) (00410)	SULFIDE (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 15...	42	11	3.9	12	.8	2.1	39	<.5	8.9	13
MAR 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	82	--	--	--
JUN 02...	71	18	6.2	20	1	2.1	78	--	13	17
SEP 04...	59	14	5.9	17	1	2.2	79	<1.0	8.4	14

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 15...	.10	23	96	263	124	.470	.010	.480	.020	.41
MAR 10...	--	--	--	--	10	.880	.020	.900	.100	.14
JUN 02...	.12	30	154	29.0	25	.314	.016	.330	.070	.25
SEP 04...	.11	26	135	178	700	.320	.060	.380	.290	1.0

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 15...	.43	.91	4.0	.070	<1	<100	30	<1	1	13
MAR 10...	.24	1.1	5.0	.090	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 02...	.32	.65	2.9	.060	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
SEP 04...	1.3	1.7	7.4	.260	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE) (01045)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB) (01051)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN) (01055)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG) (71900)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE) (01147)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG) (01077)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN) (01092)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN) (00720)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L) (32730)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L) (38260)
OCT 15...	3600	2	290	<.10	<1	<1	30	<.010	<1	.07
MAR 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 02...	740	<1	150	<.10	<1	<1	10	<.010	<1	.18
SEP 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	98	79	22	127	40	14	98	32	8.4
2	337	112	305	120	33	11	92	54	13
3	140	78	32	111	27	8.2	85	100	23
4	113	72	24	115	24	7.3	84	101	23
5	88	133	31	105	33	9.4	80	83	18
6	75	217	44	103	51	14	79	59	13
7	66	167	30	94	37	9.3	75	41	8.3
8	66	104	18	89	24	5.8	73	28	5.6
9	104	72	20	92	27	6.9	72	26	5.0
10	91	53	13	1280	1140	9060	74	26	5.2
11	188	154	94	178	142	75	69	44	8.1
12	371	227	288	139	64	24	70	80	15
13	752	501	7110	124	40	13	76	76	16
14	6490	2650	123000	117	35	11	71	59	11
15	1070	303	887	116	33	10	70	46	8.8
16	640	134	238	117	32	10	69	43	8.1
17	747	277	1010	110	30	9.0	120	58	20
18	527	203	359	103	31	8.6	88	30	7.3
19	323	26	23	107	36	10	78	22	4.6
20	258	21	14	101	77	21	67	20	3.6
21	213	28	16	106	69	21	96	19	5.0
22	206	44	24	179	127	61	86	19	4.4
23	190	42	21	161	108	49	74	19	3.7
24	179	34	16	129	73	26	73	18	3.6
25	175	27	13	120	87	28	66	18	3.1
26	163	22	9.6	171	84	60	64	17	2.9
27	147	18	7.1	165	104	48	62	17	2.7
28	144	19	7.6	112	47	14	60	17	2.7
29	131	23	8.1	100	35	9.5	58	23	3.6
30	125	31	10	104	33	9.2	62	31	5.1
31	121	42	14	---	---	---	60	22	3.6
TOTAL	14338	---	133708.4	4795	---	9663.2	2351	---	265.4

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	67	15	2.7	79	55	12	78	49	10
2	89	13	3.2	73	50	10	74	50	10
3	78	13	2.6	71	48	9.2	79	76	16
4	135	62	27	84	49	13	78	36	7.7
5	125	59	20	2390	1360	12600	132	84	54
6	1780	940	10700	334	155	163	85	173	40
7	1600	657	3140	195	73	38	2250	1920	39400
8	513	494	794	597	231	1190	661	309	806
9	e395	263	e286	449	353	655	204	52	30
10	e583	344	e600	174	256	118	146	30	12
11	250	102	72	135	234	86	132	27	9.7
12	217	62	44	123	115	39	116	25	7.9
13	243	181	127	105	48	14	110	25	7.4
14	299	183	171	248	52	202	112	30	9.3
15	177	96	46	280	89	167	120	36	12
16	153	87	36	143	94	37	104	43	12
17	143	100	38	128	50	17	88	43	10
18	129	110	38	116	26	8.3	86	41	9.6
19	119	71	23	107	30	8.7	87	41	9.5
20	114	44	13	98	43	11	749	367	1770
21	112	42	13	98	39	10	349	356	398
22	106	66	19	91	30	7.4	168	83	39
23	104	66	19	85	27	6.1	134	24	8.7
24	107	58	17	82	42	9.2	113	38	11
25	114	51	16	73	60	12	131	71	25
26	119	49	16	79	58	12	124	59	20
27	102	61	17	84	55	12	148	39	16
28	98	77	20	78	52	11	135	33	12
29	86	74	17	---	---	---	374	188	425
30	85	66	15	---	---	---	464	363	869
31	80	60	13	---	---	---	409	328	577
TOTAL	8322	---	16365.5	6599	---	15477.9	8040	---	44643.8
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	171	67	32	83	34	7.7	78	53	11
2	204	53	100	85	35	8.1	68	37	6.9
3	217	84	96	92	37	9.2	67	28	5.0
4	139	100	38	100	39	11	68	40	7.6
5	147	105	44	95	40	10	81	45	13
6	139	87	34	86	40	9.4	103	97	27
7	139	94	38	84	36	8.0	73	90	18
8	143	157	61	293	273	656	71	80	15
9	116	121	38	197	187	113	74	57	11
10	107	100	29	109	76	23	74	41	8.2
11	105	86	24	79	50	11	59	40	6.3
12	275	109	169	70	37	7.0	95	161	18
13	145	75	31	79	40	8.8	125	113	31
14	112	41	12	128	77	32	73	53	10
15	102	30	8.3	157	83	51	62	38	6.4
16	140	41	45	105	79	22	66	36	6.3
17	201	87	83	84	66	15	116	80	30
18	203	186	101	77	56	12	e76	56	e76
19	e178	134	e71	80	56	12	e75	51	e75
20	305	121	159	70	40	7.6	61	46	7.6
21	253	163	121	69	39	7.3	73	49	9.8
22	169	169	79	61	41	6.8	124	60	30
23	115	125	39	64	41	7.2	74	56	11
24	107	97	28	71	41	7.8	60	43	7.0
25	102	75	21	60	40	6.5	58	38	5.9
26	100	59	16	131	68	37	55	42	6.3
27	105	47	13	251	211	161	53	46	6.5
28	109	41	12	94	67	17	59	42	6.7
29	e99	37	9.8	87	51	13	54	40	5.9
30	87	35	8.2	180	78	69	49	53	7.0
31	---	---	---	114	81	25	---	---	---
TOTAL	4534	---	1560.3	3335	---	1391.4	2224	---	485.4

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN		MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN		MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN	
		CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)		CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)		CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER			
1	42	71	8.1	49	86	11	154	75	31
2	43	75	8.7	46	67	8.3	157	94	42
3	44	58	6.9	42	54	6.1	261	187	133
4	143	38	46	41	60	6.7	271	171	128
5	120	52	28	37	70	7.0	161	148	49
6	63	95	16	e51	72	e5.9	188	167	75
7	58	93	14	e155	77	e62	319	188	199
8	61	82	13	97	82	19	628	419	1080
9	56	77	12	180	87	68	368	314	282
10	54	74	11	115	71	22	345	208	215
11	45	78	9.5	82	77	17	197	131	70
12	45	84	10	72	90	17	168	120	54
13	40	87	9.3	59	87	14	232	163	118
14	43	74	8.6	51	82	11	283	158	128
15	41	64	7.1	54	94	14	733	197	1650
16	45	71	8.6	59	111	18	314	124	114
17	49	71	9.5	241	240	331	221	71	42
18	61	35	8.5	140	126	50	190	74	38
19	97	44	18	74	103	21	204	78	43
20	418	437	1200	73	89	18	192	82	42
21	241	236	179	137	111	45	e3490	1830	e98200
22	85	106	25	536	565	1290	e8930	6300	e254000
23	64	60	10	210	146	94	1150	199	743
24	83	53	12	1630	780	8180	575	80	125
25	81	52	11	2430	1010	10200	462	47	59
26	59	52	8.2	720	188	368	399	41	44
27	61	51	8.5	339	132	121	374	55	67
28	98	66	18	258	96	67	456	251	349
29	76	69	14	269	162	124	337	150	137
30	54	57	8.3	202	124	68	292	96	75
31	54	71	10	165	80	36	---	---	---
TOTAL	2524	---	1756.8	8614	---	21320.0	22051	---	358332
YEAR	87727		604970.1						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
17...	2215	1230	991	3290	98
NOV					
10...	0800	2200	1490	8850	99
JAN					
06...	1330	5740	2780	43100	96
07...	0630	2820	866	6600	99
FEB					
05...	0300	1500	1590	6440	99
05...	1500	2660	1410	10100	96
09...	0045	1340	1390	5030	100
MAR					
20...	1745	1710	1110	5100	100
AUG					
25...	1255	1990	376	2000	99
SEP					
21...	2115	20800	9070	510000	97

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)
FEB							
05...	0730	6550	3830	67700	37	52	68
05...	1125	2780	1640	12300	45	59	73
SEP							
08...	1215	841	818	1860	55	68	80

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70335)
FEB							
05...	84	93	96	99	100	100	100
05...	84	92	97	100	100	100	100
SEP							
08...	87	96	98	99	100	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 RIO CAGÜITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'48", long 66°05'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank 450 ft (137 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 777, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) southeast from Aguas Buenas, 3.9 mi (6.3 km) northwest from Caguas, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) southwest from Las Carolinas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.30 mi² (13.72 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 394 ft (120 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2.7	5.4	4.4	3.4	2.4	2.3	3.9	2.7	2.7	4.4	6.2	7.2
2	2.6	4.3	4.3	3.6	2.3	2.1	3.3	2.6	2.9	7.9	6.5	10
3	2.0	4.7	4.2	3.5	2.3	2.2	3.0	3.1	3.1	9.0	5.6	11
4	1.7	4.7	4.4	3.6	12	2.2	2.8	2.9	5.8	6.2	5.6	14
5	1.7	4.5	4.4	4.2	73	12	3.0	2.8	4.0	4.7	5.6	11
6	3.0	4.7	4.4	14	8.3	6.4	3.5	2.6	3.6	6.5	e6.4	11
7	3.1	4.0	4.4	27	4.8	17	5.4	2.7	3.3	6.3	e10	9.5
8	2.5	4.1	4.4	7.3	39	9.4	4.2	4.0	3.2	4.4	9.1	18
9	2.3	4.4	4.4	4.2	22	4.8	3.3	3.8	4.2	4.0	9.3	11
10	2.1	7.5	4.4	4.0	8.1	3.9	3.2	3.3	4.0	4.0	7.0	9.5
11	2.5	4.8	4.4	3.4	6.0	3.6	3.9	3.3	3.1	3.9	6.2	8.1
12	5.2	4.4	4.2	3.4	4.6	3.4	5.1	3.3	7.8	3.9	6.4	7.4
13	22	4.4	4.1	6.7	4.1	3.4	5.1	3.4	6.3	4.1	5.7	7.0
14	200	4.3	4.0	6.4	8.2	3.7	3.9	5.9	4.3	4.2	5.0	7.0
15	19	4.6	4.0	3.1	5.5	3.4	3.9	4.1	3.0	4.5	5.5	9.0
16	17	5.7	3.9	2.8	4.5	3.3	8.6	2.7	2.7	5.1	5.3	7.3
17	18	6.2	4.1	2.9	3.7	3.1	4.7	2.6	8.2	4.5	7.1	6.8
18	13	5.4	4.3	2.8	3.5	3.1	3.6	2.7	4.7	11	11	7.4
19	8.7	5.0	4.1	3.1	3.2	2.8	3.5	4.1	3.1	5.7	7.4	8.2
20	6.9	4.4	4.2	3.3	3.1	20	4.8	5.6	2.9	30	10	8.1
21	6.1	4.4	5.4	3.8	3.0	9.4	4.2	3.3	5.5	7.4	18	262
22	5.5	4.5	4.2	3.2	2.6	4.1	3.6	2.7	5.9	5.1	28	663
23	5.2	4.8	4.0	3.0	2.6	3.4	3.3	2.8	3.3	7.0	14	43
24	5.0	4.7	3.9	2.8	2.7	2.7	3.1	2.6	12	5.8	71	22
25	5.0	4.7	3.7	3.6	2.4	2.7	3.1	2.8	6.5	5.6	46	17
26	4.8	5.9	3.5	3.1	2.5	2.3	3.1	4.3	5.4	4.2	14	22
27	4.3	5.4	3.4	2.8	2.4	3.7	3.4	5.3	4.9	9.2	25	19
28	4.0	4.4	3.4	2.7	2.4	2.4	2.9	3.0	4.5	12	13	19
29	4.0	5.2	3.4	2.6	---	23	2.7	3.2	4.3	7.5	9.4	17
30	4.1	4.9	3.4	2.4	---	10	2.6	2.8	4.1	6.3	7.8	14
31	4.1	---	3.4	2.4	---	5.2	---	2.8	---	6.3	7.0	---
TOTAL	388.1	146.4	126.7	145.1	241.2	181.0	114.7	103.8	139.3	210.7	394.1	1286.5
MEAN	12.5	4.88	4.09	4.68	8.61	5.84	3.82	3.35	4.64	6.80	12.7	42.9
MAX	200	7.5	5.4	27	73	23	8.6	5.9	12	30	71	663
MIN	1.7	4.0	3.4	2.4	2.3	2.1	2.6	2.6	2.7	3.9	5.0	6.8
AC-FT	770	290	251	288	478	359	228	206	276	418	782	2550
CFSM	2.36	.92	.77	.88	1.63	1.10	.72	.63	.88	1.28	2.40	8.09
IN.	2.72	1.03	.89	1.02	1.69	1.27	.81	.73	.98	1.48	2.77	9.03

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	8.50	6.92	6.13	8.05	5.23	4.70	4.50	5.13	4.27
MAX	20.9	12.3	13.4	16.7	8.61	8.87	13.1	18.0	8.05
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1998	1990	1993	1993	1993
MIN	3.17	2.66	2.34	2.48	2.96	2.09	1.84	2.00	1.84
(WY)	1996	1995	1995	1995	1995	1996	1995	1997	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	1631.4	3477.6	
ANNUAL MEAN	4.47	9.53	7.04
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			11.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			4.31
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	200	Oct 14	663
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.0	Aug 1	1.7
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.3	Sep 5	2.3
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2860
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			18.06
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			1.2
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	3240	6900	5100
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.84	1.80	1.33
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	11.45	24.41	18.04
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.1	12	9.5
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.6	4.4	4.2
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.6	2.7	1.9

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055100 RIO CAGÜITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 Río CAGÜITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: February 1990 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1990.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediment samples were collected by hydrologic technician and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 5,300 mg/L September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L severals days during 1997-98.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 24,500 tons (22,200 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 ton (0.01 tonnes)severals days during 1997-98 . .

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 4,000 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L January 4-5, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 8,080 tons (7,340 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 ton (0.01 tonnes) January 4-5, 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	2.7	15	.11	5.4	11	.16	4.4	8	.09
2	2.6	18	.13	4.3	12	.14	4.3	10	.11
3	2.0	20	.11	4.7	9	.11	4.2	12	.14
4	1.7	18	.08	4.7	6	.08	4.4	10	.12
5	1.7	16	.07	4.5	4	.05	4.4	8	.09
6	3.0	33	.81	4.7	4	.05	4.4	6	.07
7	3.1	17	.14	4.0	4	.04	4.4	5	.06
8	2.5	19	.13	4.1	4	.04	4.4	4	.05
9	2.3	26	.16	4.4	4	.05	4.4	4	.05
10	2.1	36	.20	7.5	40	1.9	4.4	4	.05
11	2.5	48	.33	4.8	38	.49	4.4	4	.05
12	5.2	50	.70	4.4	31	.37	4.2	4	.05
13	22	1390	1320	4.4	24	.29	4.1	4	.05
14	200	2500	4930	4.3	19	.22	4.0	5	.05
15	19	88	4.6	4.6	14	.17	4.0	5	.05
16	17	77	3.5	5.7	29	.64	3.9	5	.05
17	18	290	19	6.2	14	.23	4.1	6	.06
18	13	41	1.5	5.4	16	.24	4.3	6	.07
19	8.7	27	.63	5.0	20	.27	4.1	7	.07
20	6.9	17	.32	4.4	24	.29	4.2	7	.08
21	6.1	11	.19	4.4	18	.22	5.4	8	.11
22	5.5	9	.14	4.5	12	.15	4.2	10	.11
23	5.2	13	.18	4.8	8	.11	4.0	12	.13
24	5.0	19	.25	4.7	6	.08	3.9	15	.16
25	5.0	22	.29	4.7	6	.08	3.7	11	.11
26	4.8	14	.18	5.9	23	.61	3.5	7	.07
27	4.3	9	.10	5.4	9	.13	3.4	5	.04
28	4.0	8	.08	4.4	8	.09	3.4	4	.04
29	4.0	7	.08	5.2	7	.10	3.4	5	.05
30	4.1	7	.08	4.9	6	.08	3.4	6	.05
31	4.1	9	.10	---	---	---	3.4	7	.06
TOTAL	388.1	---	6284.19	146.4	---	7.48	126.7	---	2.34

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 Río CAGÜITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	3.4	5	.04	2.4	11	.07	2.3	4	.03
2	3.6	3	.03	2.3	13	.08	2.1	4	.02
3	3.5	2	.02	2.3	14	.09	2.2	3	.02
4	3.6	1	.01	12	309	128	2.2	3	.02
5	4.2	1	.01	73	1770	756	12	479	63
6	14	163	11	8.3	19	.43	6.4	86	1.6
7	27	339	27	4.8	17	.22	17	243	22
8	7.3	91	2.0	39	1120	506	9.4	285	8.7
9	4.2	26	.30	22	379	29	4.8	38	.50
10	4.0	17	.18	8.1	90	2.0	3.9	19	.20
11	3.4	16	.15	6.0	57	.93	3.6	11	.11
12	3.4	16	.15	4.6	43	.54	3.4	12	.11
13	6.7	62	3.0	4.1	37	.41	3.4	14	.13
14	6.4	78	1.7	8.2	70	2.2	3.7	16	.16
15	3.1	25	.21	5.5	58	.94	3.4	12	.12
16	2.8	12	.09	4.5	28	.33	3.3	9	.08
17	2.9	7	.05	3.7	16	.16	3.1	7	.06
18	2.8	8	.06	3.5	10	.09	3.1	7	.06
19	3.1	10	.09	3.2	7	.06	2.8	7	.05
20	3.3	11	.10	3.1	5	.05	20	594	74
21	3.8	6	.06	3.0	4	.03	9.4	234	6.6
22	3.2	5	.05	2.6	4	.03	4.1	53	.60
23	3.0	5	.04	2.6	5	.04	3.4	19	.17
24	2.8	4	.03	2.7	6	.04	2.7	11	.08
25	3.6	19	.21	2.4	6	.04	2.7	11	.08
26	3.1	18	.15	2.5	7	.05	2.3	10	.06
27	2.8	8	.06	2.4	6	.04	3.7	30	.50
28	2.7	4	.03	2.4	5	.03	2.4	21	.13
29	2.6	5	.04	---	---	---	23	494	132
30	2.4	7	.05	---	---	---	10	171	5.2
31	2.4	9	.06	---	---	---	5.2	65	.94
TOTAL	145.1	---	46.97	241.2	---	1427.90	181.0	---	317.33
APRIL									
1	3.9	37	.39	2.7	4	.03	2.7	16	.12
2	3.3	23	.20	2.6	4	.03	2.9	11	.08
3	3.0	15	.12	3.1	5	.05	3.1	4	.03
4	2.8	10	.08	2.9	8	.06	5.8	45	1.8
5	3.0	8	.06	2.8	9	.06	4.0	9	.10
6	3.5	9	.09	2.6	5	.04	3.6	8	.08
7	5.4	39	1.1	2.7	4	.03	3.3	11	.10
8	4.2	48	.58	4.0	7	.07	3.2	15	.13
9	3.3	23	.20	3.8	7	.07	4.2	14	.16
10	3.2	16	.14	3.3	7	.06	4.0	13	.14
11	3.9	11	.12	3.3	7	.06	3.1	11	.09
12	5.1	23	.45	3.3	6	.05	7.8	84	2.3
13	5.1	26	.40	3.4	6	.05	6.3	45	1.1
14	3.9	11	.12	5.9	41	1.6	4.3	13	.15
15	3.9	10	.11	4.1	44	.49	3.0	12	.10
16	8.6	49	1.9	2.7	29	.21	2.7	11	.08
17	4.7	3	.04	2.6	22	.16	8.2	92	3.6
18	3.6	4	.04	2.7	19	.14	4.7	36	.48
19	3.5	6	.06	4.1	44	.89	3.1	20	.17
20	4.8	11	.14	5.6	62	1.1	2.9	12	.09
21	4.2	13	.15	3.3	25	.23	5.5	32	.82
22	3.6	16	.15	2.7	14	.11	5.9	48	.94
23	3.3	17	.15	2.8	11	.09	3.3	17	.15
24	3.1	14	.12	2.6	9	.06	12	501	62
25	3.1	11	.09	2.8	7	.05	6.5	19	.34
26	3.1	9	.08	4.3	6	.07	5.4	17	.25
27	3.4	7	.06	5.3	59	.95	4.9	16	.21
28	2.9	5	.04	3.0	48	.39	4.5	15	.19
29	2.7	4	.03	3.2	33	.29	4.3	14	.16
30	2.6	4	.03	2.8	23	.18	4.1	9	.10
31	---	---	---	2.8	19	.15	---	---	---
TOTAL	114.7	---	7.24	103.8	---	7.82	139.3	---	76.06
MAY									
JUNE									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 Río CAGÜITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	4.4	7	.08	6.2	27	.45	7.2	29	.57
2	7.9	90	5.0	6.5	20	.34	10	88	3.3
3	9.0	108	4.4	5.6	14	.22	11	152	4.6
4	6.2	50	.87	5.6	11	.16	14	304	20
5	4.7	35	.44	5.6	10	.15	11	162	5.7
6	6.5	58	1.6	e6.4	10	e.18	11	130	4.0
7	6.3	13	.22	e10	102	e5.9	9.5	116	3.0
8	4.4	12	.15	9.1	108	3.3	18	432	36
9	4.0	15	.16	9.3	29	.73	11	98	3.1
10	4.0	17	.18	7.0	28	.53	9.5	27	.70
11	3.9	18	.19	6.2	26	.43	8.1	24	.53
12	3.9	14	.15	6.4	22	.37	7.4	25	.49
13	4.1	10	.10	5.7	19	.30	7.0	24	.45
14	4.2	7	.07	5.0	20	.26	7.0	17	.33
15	4.5	4	.05	5.5	20	.30	9.0	14	.34
16	5.1	3	.04	5.3	20	.28	7.3	16	.31
17	4.5	3	.04	7.1	20	.39	6.8	18	.32
18	11	27	1.5	11	190	11	7.4	17	.34
19	5.7	10	.15	7.4	107	2.2	8.2	16	.36
20	30	1750	380	10	147	4.9	8.1	16	.34
21	7.4	214	5.0	18	142	6.8	262	1710	6610
22	5.1	45	.60	28	193	15	663	4000	8080
23	7.0	52	1.2	14	175	6.8	43	655	95
24	5.8	19	.29	71	739	229	22	43	2.7
25	5.6	17	.25	46	331	50	17	16	.77
26	4.2	17	.19	14	58	2.4	22	151	22
27	9.2	106	4.9	25	1470	190	19	298	16
28	12	162	5.9	13	248	9.4	19	290	18
29	7.5	88	1.8	9.4	38	.97	17	178	8.5
30	6.3	59	1.0	7.8	32	.69	14	206	7.9
31	6.3	40	.67	7.0	31	.59	---	---	---
TOTAL	210.7	---	417.19	394.1	---	544.04	1286.5	---	14945.65
YEAR	3477.6		24084.21						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
MAR					
29...	2045	46	1300	161	96
30...	0626	11	237	7.0	99
JUL					
20...	1530	35	3120	295	98
21...	1630	4.4	181	2.2	98
AUG					
18...	1638	24	865	56	99
24...	1400	191	1160	598	98
27...	1645	81	2350	514	95
SEP					
03...	0620	9.6	852	22	99
22...	0330	1660	3460	15500	74

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 Río CAGÜITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)
		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)
JAN							
07...	0530	94	1110	282	71	81	90
MAR							
20...	1815	75	3060	620	55	69	82
JUL							
20...	1830	130	10400	3650	51	63	76
SEP							
21...	1915	268	5290	3830	37	52	69
JAN							
07...	95	97	97	98	100	100	100
MAR							
20...	92	95	97	99	100	100	100
JUL							
20...	86	93	95	98	99	100	100
SEP							
21...	80	84	90	96	99	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGÜITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'55", long 66°01'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at C. 4 street Villa Blanca housing area at Caguas, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) upstream from Río Grande de Loiza, and 0.95 mi (1.53 km) northeast from Caguas Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--11.71 mi² (30.33 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 164 ft (50 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Low-flow affected by pluvial discharges above 50 ft (15.24 m), upstream from station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e16	24	14	7.7	6.0	9.3	e16	7.1	7.1	6.2	6.3	43
2	e54	16	13	9.7	6.0	8.6	e19	7.2	7.5	6.1	5.0	95
3	e23	26	12	10	6.0	14	e20	12	7.7	40	4.5	53
4	e18	e19	12	12	99	9.4	e12	11	99	22	4.2	145
5	e14	e16	10	15	663	186	e13	6.9	53	9.1	4.7	32
6	e12	e15	9.7	313	60	37	e12	7.3	15	20	e30	47
7	e11	e14	9.5	282	26	428	e11	5.9	6.4	12	e137	26
8	e16	e13	9.8	57	291	141	e12	62	5.5	5.9	103	123
9	12	e14	12	49	234	37	e10	7.2	8.2	4.8	53	58
10	10	e190	9.9	17	47	26	e9.4	5.8	7.5	4.6	16	27
11	62	e18	8.3	12	29	18	e9.2	5.5	7.2	5.8	10	17
12	64	e15	7.7	50	24	16	e25	6.3	113	4.5	7.9	16
13	159	e13	8.0	90	19	16	e12	6.5	38	4.7	5.9	63
14	698	e12	8.8	53	168	22	e10	45	5.8	5.3	5.7	19
15	158	44	10	19	56	15	e9.1	11	5.3	8.9	5.3	88
16	121	16	11	13	21	11	e14	6.8	7.1	7.8	5.0	26
17	197	12	14	10	19	9.0	e18	87	246	8.7	61	23
18	116	12	10	9.5	15	e8.9	11	11	28	163	86	21
19	54	12	9.3	8.9	12	e8.8	11	6.9	9.7	25	13	29
20	43	13	11	8.5	12	e68	28	14	8.0	420	53	54
21	31	14	31	7.9	11	e27	12	27	54	107	109	e1210
22	25	17	10	7.3	11	e15	e10	7.0	36	17	337	e3970
23	21	16	9.6	6.7	10	e13	e9.0	6.3	9.3	13	94	880
24	20	14	10	7.3	10	e11	e8.2	7.1	81	15	866	567
25	20	14	9.1	10	11	e14	e8.2	6.0	15	10	821	469
26	22	42	9.6	8.3	13	e12	e9.0	28	9.6	7.1	e149	433
27	18	17	9.2	8.0	11	e14	e10	30	8.0	92	195	321
28	15	14	9.1	7.6	10	e13	e8.6	8.6	7.4	103	94	386
29	14	14	9.3	7.1	---	e36	8.1	7.6	6.6	10	39	233
30	13	14	8.4	6.8	---	e42	8.6	9.7	7.0	5.5	28	123
31	18	---	8.3	6.5	---	e36	---	9.0	---	5.0	24	---
TOTAL	2075	690	333.6	1129.8	1900.0	1322.0	373.4	478.7	918.9	1169.0	3372.5	9597
MEAN	66.9	23.0	10.8	36.4	67.9	42.6	12.4	15.4	30.6	37.7	109	320
MAX	698	190	31	313	663	428	28	87	246	420	866	3970
MIN	10	12	7.7	6.5	6.0	8.6	8.1	5.5	5.3	4.5	4.2	16
MED	21	15	9.8	10	17	15	11	7.3	8.1	9.1	30	61
AC-FT	4120	1370	662	2240	3770	2620	741	950	1820	2320	6690	19040
CFSM	5.72	1.96	.92	3.11	5.79	3.64	1.06	1.32	2.62	3.22	9.29	27.3
IN.	6.59	2.19	1.06	3.59	6.04	4.20	1.19	1.52	2.92	3.71	10.71	30.49

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	30.8	32.4	20.6	37.8	24.9	18.3	16.0	23.1
MAX	66.9	56.8	58.4	120	67.9	42.6	39.8	59.8
(WY)	1998	1993	1993	1992	1998	1998	1993	1996
MIN	18.7	12.2	8.87	14.2	10.8	7.54	5.49	3.35
(WY)	1996	1995	1995	1995	1992	1994	1994	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1991 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	9765.6	23359.9	
ANNUAL MEAN	26.8	64.0	36.7
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			64.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			11.9
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	698	Oct 14	3970
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	7.7	Dec 12	Sep 22
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	9.0	Dec 25	4.2
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			5.0
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			Jul 30
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	19370		11200
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.28		Sep 22
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	31.02		18.87
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	43		Sep 22
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	18		23.89
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10		Sep 10 1996

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055225 RIO CAGÜITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGÜITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water year 1991 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: December 1990 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1991.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples collected by local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediments samples were collected by local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 5,940 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 3 mg/L August 2, 1997.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e110,000 tons (e99,900 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, e0.03 ton (e0.02 tonne) June 15, 1994.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 5,940 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 8 mg/L August 15, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e110,000 tons (e99,900 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.21 tons (0.19 tonne), August 2, 3 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	e16	60	e1.1	24	41	4.3	14	27	1.1
2	e54	62	e18	16	24	1.0	13	23	.76
3	e23	63	e2.2	26	55	6.3	12	19	.61
4	e18	63	e1.6	e19	50	e1.6	12	17	.55
5	e14	58	e1.1	e16	32	e1.1	10	17	.47
6	e12	51	e.82	e15	24	e1.7	9.7	16	.43
7	e11	46	e.59	e14	19	e1.1	9.5	19	.48
8	e16	54	e1.1	e13	16	e.96	9.8	21	.57
9	12	27	.91	e14	19	e1.1	12	24	.75
10	10	23	.62	e190	25	e512	9.9	21	.56
11	62	74	38	e18	31	e1.6	8.3	17	.38
12	64	103	38	e15	30	e1.7	7.7	14	.29
13	159	259	627	e13	27	e.96	8.0	12	.25
14	698	773	2860	e12	24	e.82	8.8	14	.32
15	158	144	62	44	37	7.3	10	17	.47
16	121	47	17	16	35	1.5	11	19	.61
17	197	643	901	12	28	.93	14	31	1.3
18	116	170	79	12	26	.86	10	23	.62
19	54	24	3.5	12	24	.80	9.3	21	.53
20	43	24	2.8	13	22	.76	11	21	.78
21	31	24	2.0	14	21	.81	31	28	4.6
22	25	23	1.6	17	23	1.2	10	19	.51
23	21	20	1.2	16	29	1.3	9.6	19	.50
24	20	18	.95	14	17	.68	10	20	.56
25	20	17	.91	14	27	1.1	9.1	18	.45
26	22	18	1.1	42	50	17	9.6	16	.43
27	18	21	1.0	17	28	1.4	9.2	15	.37
28	15	21	.84	14	20	.77	9.1	13	.33
29	14	20	.78	14	26	.95	9.3	12	.30
30	13	19	.67	14	31	1.1	8.4	11	.25
31	18	34	2.2	---	---	---	8.3	12	.27
TOTAL	2075	---	4669.59	690	---	574.70	333.6	---	20.40

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGÜITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	7.7	13	.26	6.0	20	.32	9.3	12	.29
2	9.7	13	.35	6.0	26	.42	8.6	13	.31
3	10	14	.39	6.0	33	.53	14	15	.60
4	12	23	1.2	99	119	316	9.4	19	.49
5	15	64	1.9	663	1480	4000	186	949	1870
6	313	366	557	60	134	26	37	130	10
7	282	264	210	26	36	2.7	428	681	2050
8	57	153	29	291	613	1860	141	213	137
9	49	60	9.5	234	386	356	37	49	5.0
10	17	35	1.7	47	75	9.9	26	26	1.9
11	12	25	.80	29	27	2.1	18	14	.74
12	50	52	20	24	27	1.7	16	11	.49
13	90	81	32	19	29	1.5	16	10	.44
14	53	75	12	168	114	94	22	28	2.5
15	19	47	2.4	56	42	7.4	15	36	1.4
16	13	33	1.2	21	29	1.7	11	29	.90
17	10	25	.69	19	22	1.1	9.0	26	.63
18	9.5	20	.50	15	18	.70	e8.9	24	e.48
19	8.9	16	.38	12	15	.47	e8.8	38	e.48
20	8.5	14	.32	12	12	.39	e68	59	e36
21	7.9	17	.35	11	11	.33	e27	86	e4.2
22	7.3	18	.35	11	13	.40	e15	65	e1.7
23	6.7	18	.32	10	18	.49	e13	39	e.96
24	7.3	19	.37	10	18	.51	e11	29	e.59
25	10	19	.53	11	18	.53	e14	39	e1.1
26	8.3	15	.34	13	18	.62	e12	54	e.82
27	8.0	15	.32	11	15	.46	e14	75	e1.1
28	7.6	15	.31	10	13	.36	e13	105	e.96
29	7.1	15	.29	---	---	---	e36	145	e6.8
30	6.8	15	.27	---	---	---	e42	183	e8.4
31	6.5	16	.28	---	---	---	e36	89	e6.8
TOTAL	1129.8	---	885.32	1900.0	---	6686.63	1322.0	---	4153.08
FEBRUARY									
MARCH									
APRIL									
1	e16	33	e1.1	7.1	19	.37	7.1	20	.39
2	e19	14	e1.6	7.2	18	.36	7.5	20	.40
3	e20	15	e1.6	12	24	1.3	7.7	19	.39
4	e12	18	e.82	11	25	.92	99	48	51
5	e13	22	e.96	6.9	19	.35	53	54	24
6	e12	22	e.82	7.3	21	.45	15	21	1.4
7	e11	22	e.59	5.9	19	.31	6.4	13	.22
8	e12	22	e.82	62	53	25	5.5	16	.23
9	e10	22	e.62	7.2	21	.41	8.2	18	.67
10	e9.4	22	e.61	5.8	18	.29	7.5	21	.43
11	e9.2	22	e.47	5.5	22	.33	7.2	23	.45
12	e25	22	e3.0	6.3	22	.38	113	59	34
13	e12	22	e.82	6.5	23	.40	38	35	5.8
14	e10	21	e.62	45	43	18	5.8	20	.31
15	e9.1	17	e.49	11	34	.82	5.3	18	.25
16	e14	14	e1.1	6.8	16	.29	7.1	16	.30
17	e18	11	e1.6	87	57	56	246	271	579
18	11	11	.31	11	35	.88	28	34	3.0
19	11	10	.30	6.9	20	.38	9.7	30	.77
20	28	23	3.6	14	22	2.8	8.0	30	.65
21	12	24	.92	27	37	4.8	54	70	23
22	e10	36	e.62	7.0	29	.55	36	45	6.2
23	e9.0	27	e.53	6.3	27	.46	9.3	31	.79
24	e8.2	21	e.43	7.1	18	.36	81	74	39
25	e8.2	17	e.43	6.0	19	.35	15	88	3.8
26	e9.0	14	e.53	28	59	8.8	9.6	60	1.5
27	e10	16	e.62	30	41	8.6	8.0	42	.91
28	e8.6	22	e.55	8.6	23	.55	7.4	34	.69
29	8.1	23	.50	7.6	22	.45	6.6	28	.50
30	8.6	21	.49	9.7	24	.77	7.0	21	.40
31	---	---	---	9.0	19	.62	---	---	---
TOTAL	373.4	---	27.47	478.7	---	136.35	918.9	---	780.45
MAY									
JUNE									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGÜITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN		MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN		MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN		SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
		CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)		CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)		CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	
JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER				
1	6.2	17	.28	6.3	22	.41	43	43	6.9	
2	6.1	18	.33	5.0	15	.21	95	53	19	
3	40	56	7.9	4.5	14	.21	53	61	10	
4	22	32	2.2	4.2	19	.22	145	96	64	
5	9.1	22	.60	4.7	17	.22	32	37	3.2	
6	20	25	3.3	e30	25	e4.5	47	42	6.7	
7	12	28	.97	e137	49	e70	26	37	2.6	
8	5.9	22	.35	103	71	33	123	105	61	
9	4.8	24	.31	53	69	11	58	74	13	
10	4.6	21	.26	16	33	1.5	27	47	3.7	
11	5.8	19	.29	10	18	.50	17	37	1.8	
12	4.5	21	.25	7.9	14	.29	16	37	1.6	
13	4.7	25	.32	5.9	11	.18	63	50	12	
14	5.3	23	.34	5.7	10	.15	19	31	2.2	
15	8.9	19	.72	5.3	8	.12	88	98	46	
16	7.8	63	1.3	5.0	10	.13	26	42	3.0	
17	8.7	47	1.1	61	41	24	23	22	1.3	
18	163	63	47	86	75	52	21	38	2.2	
19	25	49	3.7	13	24	1.9	29	59	6.3	
20	420	800	1990	53	49	16	54	78	38	
21	107	165	110	109	83	34	e1210	4590	e61300	
22	17	42	2.2	337	195	276	e3970	5940	e110000	
23	13	39	1.4	94	128	36	880	52	134	
24	15	36	1.6	866	1490	6650	567	35	53	
25	10	28	.86	821	512	1490	469	33	42	
26	7.1	20	.39	e149	70	e31	433	56	81	
27	92	102	45	195	123	123	321	92	111	
28	103	99	51	94	89	24	386	199	539	
29	10	58	1.5	39	50	5.2	233	43	30	
30	5.5	47	.68	28	41	3.1	123	24	8.0	
31	5.0	31	.42	24	35	2.3	---	---	---	
TOTAL	1169.0	---	2276.57	3372.5	---	8891.14	9597	---	172602.5	
YEAR	23359.9		201704.20							

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
11...	1550	113	117	36	97
JAN					
07...	0645	461	146	182	96
FEB					
05...	0515	1430	2020	7800	96
05...	1115	581	1080	1690	98
MAR					
05...	1945	254	385	264	99
21...	1635	27	98	7.1	98
AUG					
25...	1200	809	324	708	99
SEP					
21...	1900	1670	11000	49600	99
22...	0645	3520	9610	91300	99

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGÜITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)
		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)
OCT							
17...	1800	813	2930	6430	38	54	75
JAN							
06...	1545	279	524	395	74	89	99
FEB							
05...	0030	1150	4600	14300	51	68	87
SEP							
22...	0200	9820	17700	469000	24	38	63
DATE							
OCT							
17...	90	96	97	99	100	100	100
JAN							
06...	99	99	99	99	100	100	100
FEB							
05...	95	97	97	99	100	100	100
SEP							
22...	86	96	97	99	99	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055250 RIO CAGÜITAS AT HIGHWAY 30 AT CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'11", long 66°01'26", at Highway 30 bridge, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) east of Caguas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--14.1 mi² (36.5 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 21...	0830	14	563	7.2	26.0	5.2	4.2	52	<10	44000	3000
FEB 20...	0800	10	551	7.1	24.0	2.0	4.9	58	<10	24000	K1400
MAY 26...	0825	12	432	7.0	28.0	62	3.0	38	19	58000	42000
AUG 17...	0915	5.8	583	6.8	28.7	4.7	2.8	36	<10	35000	K1500

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CaCO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl) (00940)
OCT 21...	210	54	17	30	.9	3.4	200	<1.0	48	40
FEB 20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
MAY 26...	130	35	11	30	1	3.5	140	--	26	32
AUG 17...	200	52	16	36	1	3.5	190	<1.0	50	44

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 21...	.17	37	350	13.6	5	.450	.010	.460	.020	.20
FEB 20...	--	--	--	--	2	.350	.220	.570	2.00	.40
MAY 26...	.10	27	249	7.87	16	.067	.033	.100	2.90	.40
AUG 17...	.15	41	357	5.61	14	.043	.037	.080	2.90	.00

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'32", long 66°02'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, in the Bairoa Housing Area, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Plaza de Caguas, 4.1 mi (6.6 km) east of Plaza de Aguas Buenas, and 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northwest of Escuela Pepita Garriga.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.08 mi² (13.15 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 131 ft (40 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Mean daily discharge affected by domestic discharge from school nearby station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e4.3	e4.9	e3.0	e3.0	e3.5	4.1	3.3	3.6	3.7	2.9	2.9	3.5
2	e4.8	e3.9	e2.9	e3.2	e3.4	4.0	3.5	4.3	3.4	11	3.1	5.4
3	e3.6	e4.6	e2.7	e3.0	e3.4	4.7	3.3	4.8	3.5	5.9	2.8	6.0
4	e3.6	e4.6	e2.8	e3.1	e15	4.2	3.2	4.6	8.6	4.1	2.7	14
5	e3.6	e4.3	e2.7	e3.4	e60	6.1	3.2	4.2	3.5	3.3	2.9	9.5
6	e4.6	e4.1	e2.7	e14	6.2	4.8	3.1	4.1	3.4	15	e3.2	5.3
7	e4.8	e3.9	e2.8	e24	5.0	19	4.2	4.2	3.2	5.3	15	3.6
8	e3.9	e3.8	e2.9	e10	30	7.1	4.1	6.0	3.1	3.5	31	9.2
9	e3.6	e3.8	e2.8	e6.0	13	4.8	3.3	4.9	3.0	3.3	5.6	4.3
10	e3.3	e5.4	e2.8	e5.6	6.4	4.3	3.2	4.2	3.0	3.3	3.3	3.6
11	e4.0	e3.8	e2.8	e5.0	5.6	4.0	3.2	3.6	3.5	3.5	2.8	3.4
12	e5.2	e3.9	e2.7	e5.0	5.1	4.1	3.6	3.6	4.3	2.9	3.7	3.3
13	e30	e3.8	e2.6	e10	4.8	4.1	4.6	3.6	5.1	3.1	3.1	3.8
14	e180	e3.7	e2.6	e9.0	10	4.2	3.3	14	4.0	2.6	2.9	3.5
15	e17	e3.8	e2.6	e4.5	6.5	4.4	3.7	6.1	3.7	3.0	3.0	4.5
16	e15	e3.7	e2.6	e4.1	4.8	4.4	8.4	3.4	4.7	3.2	3.0	3.6
17	e16	e3.7	e2.8	e4.3	4.7	4.0	4.2	6.6	e5.6	3.0	4.3	3.6
18	e11	e3.6	e2.7	e4.2	4.5	4.1	3.6	3.3	e4.0	14	11	3.2
19	e7.8	e3.6	e2.8	e4.6	4.3	4.1	3.5	3.1	e3.0	3.8	3.8	3.4
20	e6.2	e3.4	e3.8	e4.9	4.1	8.7	3.8	6.7	e2.8	25	3.8	5.2
21	e5.4	e3.3	e5.0	e5.6	4.4	5.6	4.6	4.4	e4.1	5.0	12	139
22	e4.9	e3.2	e4.0	e5.0	4.2	4.2	3.8	3.1	e4.2	3.2	14	532
23	e4.6	e3.0	e3.8	e4.5	4.5	3.8	3.9	3.1	3.2	13	4.9	e35
24	e4.4	e3.0	e3.6	e4.2	4.2	4.0	3.6	3.5	19	4.3	80	e17
25	e4.5	e3.1	e3.4	e5.4	4.3	6.3	3.6	3.2	4.4	2.9	60	e14
26	e4.3	e4.2	e3.3	e4.6	4.4	4.3	3.7	5.5	3.0	2.8	7.7	e17
27	e3.8	e3.1	e3.2	e4.1	4.3	5.0	4.2	4.6	3.0	11	36	e15
28	e3.6	e2.8	e3.2	e4.0	4.2	4.5	3.7	3.8	3.3	5.8	9.7	e15
29	e3.6	e3.1	e3.2	e3.8	---	28	3.6	3.9	3.0	3.0	5.4	e13
30	e3.7	e3.1	e3.2	e3.5	---	5.8	3.6	4.0	2.7	2.7	4.3	e11
31	e3.6	---	e3.2	e3.5	---	3.5	---	4.0	---	2.9	3.8	---
TOTAL	378.7	112.2	95.2	179.1	234.8	184.2	114.6	142.0	129.0	178.3	351.7	909.9
MEAN	12.2	3.74	3.07	5.78	8.39	5.94	3.82	4.58	4.30	5.75	11.3	30.3
MAX	180	5.4	5.0	24	60	28	8.4	14	19	25	80	532
MIN	3.3	2.8	2.6	3.0	3.4	3.5	3.1	3.1	2.7	2.6	2.7	3.2
AC-FT	751	223	189	355	466	365	227	282	256	354	698	1800
CFSM	2.40	.74	.60	1.14	1.65	1.17	.75	.90	.85	1.13	2.23	5.97
IN.	2.77	.82	.70	1.31	1.72	1.35	.84	1.04	.94	1.31	2.58	6.66

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002
MEAN	9.94	9.27	8.12	8.68	5.97	4.51	4.79	5.86	5.16	7.77	9.10	21.6
MAX	25.3	22.2	19.7	14.7	8.81	5.94	9.23	12.5	8.64	16.5	17.7	76.9
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1996	1997	1998	1996	1993	1993	1991	1996	1996
MIN	4.30	3.74	3.07	4.12	3.42	2.87	2.61	2.91	2.72	4.35	4.09	4.50
(WY)	1992	1998	1998	1995	1994	1994	1992	1994	1995	1994	1991	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	2526.0	3009.7	
ANNUAL MEAN	6.92	8.25	8.39
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			14.5
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			4.52
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	180	Oct 14	532
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.6	Dec 13	2.6
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.7	Dec 12	2.7
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1610
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			12.39
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	5010	5970	6080
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.36	1.62	1.65
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	18.50	22.04	22.45
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.8	11	12
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.7	4.0	4.5
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.3	3.0	2.8

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water year 1991 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1994 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1991.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly. During high flows events sediment samples were collected and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 7,040 mg/L September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L severals days 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 37,900 tons (34,300 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.02 ton (0.01 tonne) Several years.

EXTREME FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean,1,610 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 2,970 tons (2,700 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.02 ton (0.01 tonne) March 18-19, 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	e4.3	40	e.16	e4.9	13	e.19	e3.0	13	e.09
2	e4.8	15	e.18	e3.9	14	e.13	e2.9	13	e.07
3	e3.6	2	e.11	e4.6	14	e.17	e2.7	10	e.06
4	e3.6	2	e.08	e4.6	14	e.17	e2.8	11	e.07
5	e3.6	4	e.08	e4.3	8	e.16	e2.7	13	e.06
6	e4.6	8	e.18	e4.1	4	e.15	e2.7	8	e.06
7	e4.8	14	e.18	e3.9	2	e.13	e2.8	4	e.07
8	e3.9	22	e.13	e3.8	3	e.11	e2.9	2	e.07
9	e3.6	18	e.08	e3.8	8	e.11	e2.8	2	e.07
10	e3.3	12	e.10	e5.4	12	e.28	e2.8	1	e.07
11	e4.0	11	e.14	e3.8	14	e.11	e2.8	1	e.06
12	e5.2	10	e.28	e3.9	7	e.13	e2.7	2	e.06
13	e3.0	10	e57	e3.8	3	e.11	e2.6	2	e.06
14	e180	16	e1000	e3.7	2	e.11	e2.6	2	e.06
15	e17	29	e20	e3.8	3	e.11	e2.6	2	e.06
16	e15	24	e9.0	e3.7	3	e.11	e2.6	3	e.06
17	e16	14	e15	e3.7	4	e.11	e2.8	4	e.07
18	e11	9	e2.9	e3.6	6	e.08	e2.7	6	e.06
19	e7.8	5	e.58	e3.6	10	e.08	e2.8	8	e.07
20	e6.2	3	e.31	e3.4	5	e.09	e3.8	7	e.11
21	e5.4	5	e.28	e3.3	1	e.10	e5.0	4	e.25
22	e4.9	8	e.19	e3.2	2	e.10	e4.0	3	e.14
23	e4.6	12	e.17	e3.0	6	e.09	e3.8	5	e.11
24	e4.4	15	e.16	e3.0	16	e.09	e3.6	8	e.08
25	e4.5	15	e.17	e3.1	29	e.10	e3.4	15	e.09
26	e4.3	13	e.16	e4.2	43	e.16	e3.3	23	e.10
27	e3.8	12	e.11	e3.1	13	e.10	e3.2	8	e.10
28	e3.6	12	e.08	e2.8	2	e.07	e3.2	3	e.10
29	e3.6	12	e.08	e3.1	2	e.10	e3.2	2	e.10
30	e3.7	12	e.11	e3.1	5	e.10	e3.2	2	e.10
31	e3.6	13	e.08	---	---	---	e3.2	6	e.10
TOTAL	378.7	---	1108.08	112.2	---	3.65	95.2	---	2.63

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	e3.0	16	e.09	e3.5	5	e.10	4.1	7	.08
2	e3.2	15	e.10	e3.4	5	e.09	4.0	5	.05
3	e3.0	11	e.09	e3.4	3	e.09	4.7	3	.04
4	e3.1	8	e.10	e15	2	e9.0	4.2	2	.03
5	e3.4	7	e.09	e60	19	e82	6.1	14	.38
6	e14	10	e4.3	6.2	13	.24	4.8	10	.13
7	e24	17	e33	5.0	12	.17	19	88	20
8	e10	19	e2.5	30	66	44	7.1	28	.60
9	e6.0	18	e.30	13	68	3.0	4.8	17	.22
10	e5.6	12	e.28	6.4	27	.47	4.3	13	.14
11	e5.0	7	e.25	5.6	16	.25	4.0	9	.10
12	e5.0	5	e.25	5.1	5	.07	4.1	7	.08
13	e10	10	e2.5	4.8	3	.04	4.1	5	.06
14	e9.0	21	e1.7	10	34	1.6	4.2	4	.05
15	e4.5	22	e.17	6.5	25	.47	4.4	4	.04
16	e4.1	19	e.15	4.8	15	.20	4.4	3	.04
17	e4.3	35	e.16	4.7	11	.14	4.0	3	.03
18	e4.2	58	e.16	4.5	8	.10	4.1	2	.02
19	e4.6	19	e.17	4.3	6	.07	4.1	2	.02
20	e4.9	5	e.19	4.1	4	.05	8.7	27	1.1
21	e5.6	11	e.28	4.4	6	.07	5.6	19	.31
22	e5.0	3	e.25	4.2	9	.10	4.2	8	.09
23	e4.5	3	e.17	4.5	11	.14	3.8	4	.04
24	e4.2	3	e.16	4.2	7	.08	4.0	11	.13
25	e5.4	5	e.28	4.3	6	.08	6.3	17	.33
26	e4.6	6	e.17	4.4	14	.16	4.3	4	.05
27	e4.1	6	e.15	4.3	11	.13	5.0	8	.12
28	e4.0	7	e.14	4.2	9	.10	4.5	6	.07
29	e3.8	6	e.11	---	---	---	28	144	40
30	e3.5	5	e.10	---	---	---	5.8	70	1.2
31	e3.5	5	e.10	---	---	---	3.5	24	.23
TOTAL	179.1	---	48.46	234.8	---	143.01	184.2	---	65.78
APRIL									
1	3.3	15	.13	3.6	12	.12	3.7	11	.11
2	3.5	10	.09	4.3	14	.17	3.4	7	.07
3	3.3	7	.06	4.8	15	.25	3.5	4	.04
4	3.2	7	.06	4.6	9	.11	8.6	23	1.9
5	3.2	7	.06	4.2	5	.06	3.5	9	.08
6	3.1	8	.07	4.1	4	.05	3.4	10	.09
7	4.2	13	.22	4.2	4	.04	3.2	14	.12
8	4.1	14	.16	6.0	17	.36	3.1	17	.14
9	3.3	11	.10	4.9	17	.23	3.0	14	.11
10	3.2	9	.08	4.2	8	.09	3.0	11	.09
11	3.2	11	.09	3.6	4	.04	3.5	9	.09
12	3.6	13	.13	3.6	4	.04	4.3	7	.09
13	4.6	16	.23	3.6	5	.05	5.1	8	.12
14	3.3	8	.07	14	34	4.6	4.0	10	.11
15	3.7	10	.17	6.1	83	.49	3.7	16	.16
16	8.4	17	.87	3.4	52	.11	4.7	104	1.4
17	4.2	14	.16	6.6	33	1.9	e5.6	401	e.28
18	3.6	10	.10	3.3	20	.10	e4.0	245	e.14
19	3.5	8	.08	3.1	13	.09	e3.0	41	e.09
20	3.8	12	.12	6.7	23	1.4	e2.8	21	e.07
21	4.6	15	.28	4.4	26	.32	e4.1	17	e.15
22	3.8	12	.13	3.1	16	.14	e4.2	13	e.16
23	3.9	8	.09	3.1	10	.09	3.2	13	.11
24	3.6	5	.05	3.5	6	.06	19	82	18
25	3.6	5	.05	3.2	4	.03	4.4	25	.30
26	3.7	4	.04	5.5	19	.40	3.0	17	.13
27	4.2	15	.17	4.6	7	.09	3.0	13	.11
28	3.7	11	.11	3.8	8	.09	3.3	17	.15
29	3.6	8	.08	3.9	15	.16	3.0	22	.18
30	3.6	9	.09	4.0	14	.15	2.7	19	.14
31	---	---	---	4.0	13	.14	---	---	---
TOTAL	114.6	---	4.14	142.0	---	11.97	129.0	---	24.73
MAY									
JUNE									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	2.9	16	.13	2.9	9	.07	3.5	11	.10
2	11	11	4.7	3.1	11	.10	5.4	18	.39
3	5.9	10	.40	2.8	5	.04	6.0	20	.41
4	4.1	10	.17	2.7	4	.03	14	222	11
5	3.3	9	.11	2.9	3	.03	9.5	25	1.4
6	15	104	22	e3.2	3	e.10	5.3	19	.28
7	5.3	29	.45	15	30	3.3	3.6	14	.13
8	3.5	20	.19	31	26	70	9.2	58	2.7
9	3.3	15	.13	5.6	17	.33	4.3	20	.24
10	3.3	11	.10	3.3	12	.10	3.6	15	.15
11	3.5	11	.13	2.8	10	.08	3.4	11	.10
12	2.9	10	.08	3.7	9	.09	3.3	7	.06
13	3.1	9	.08	3.1	7	.06	3.8	14	.16
14	2.6	11	.08	2.9	5	.04	3.5	7	.07
15	3.0	12	.10	3.0	6	.05	4.5	14	.19
16	3.2	15	.14	3.0	7	.06	3.6	10	.10
17	3.0	24	.19	4.3	24	.41	3.6	10	.09
18	14	52	3.9	11	42	3.5	3.2	10	.09
19	3.8	20	.21	3.8	16	.18	3.4	15	.12
20	25	127	26	3.8	13	.17	5.2	41	.55
21	5.0	36	.52	12	53	2.1	139	348	794
22	3.2	19	.16	14	19	3.1	532	1610	2970
23	13	55	4.7	4.9	13	.25	e35	311	e150
24	4.3	23	.30	80	445	229	e17	53	e20
25	2.9	10	.08	60	308	82	e14	24	e4.3
26	2.8	10	.09	7.7	27	.57	e17	16	e20
27	11	43	2.6	36	387	150	e15	11	e9.0
28	5.8	23	.40	9.7	146	4.0	e15	8	e9.0
29	3.0	14	.11	5.4	65	.95	e13	7	e6.0
30	2.7	12	.09	4.3	27	.31	e11	6	e2.9
31	2.9	10	.08	3.8	12	.13	---	---	---
TOTAL	178.3	---	68.42	351.7	---	551.15	909.9	---	4003.53
YEAR	3009.7		6035.55						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
AUG					
18...	1520	102	206	57	97
24...	2055	170	947	435	99
25...	1045	64	493	85	99
27...	1955	63	1390	236	99
SEP					
21...	1830	91	274	67	98
22...	0300	1180	2920	9300	74

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued
 WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)
		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)
AUG							
24...	1640	252	2340	1590	56	71	85
SEP							
21...	2210	653	1790	3160	50	63	74
AUG							
24...	93	97	97	99	99	100	100
SEP							
21...	84	91	93	98	100	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055400 RIO BAIROA NEAR CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'28", long 66°02'13", at bridge on Highway 1, about 2.5 mi (4.0 km) upstream from Río Grande de Loíza, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) north of Caguas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.4 mi² (14.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1962-66, 1973-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT											
21...	1115	5.4	469	7.2	26.0	1.6	4.9	61	22	18000	500
FEB											
20...	0935	5.0	461	7.2	24.0	1.0	3.8	45	<10	26000	2400
MAY											
26...	1100	3.2	449	7.2	28.5	2.3	2.2	28	17	67000	28000
AUG											
20...	0755	4.4	389	6.9	26.0	3.8	3.5	44	<10	12000	6400

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD CACO3 (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT										
21...	180	49	13	30	1	3.4	180	<1.0	17	39
FEB										
20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
MAY										
26...	150	36	14	28	1	5.1	160	--	14	38
AUG										
20...	140	34	13	22	.8	4.8	130	<1.0	13	29

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT										
21...	.10	33	274	3.99	5	.440	.030	.470	.110	.89
FEB										
20...	--	--	--	--	3	1.46	.340	1.80	.570	.40
MAY										
26...	.15	28	260	2.27	11	.074	.036	.110	2.00	.50
AUG										
20...	.14	28	222	2.61	9	1.75	.150	1.90	.220	.40

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'02", long 65°53'07", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, 2.43 mi (3.91 km) northeast of Plaza de Juncos, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) southeast of Escuela La Placita and 0.35 mi (0.56 km) southwest of El Mango.

DRAINAGE AREA.--22.3 mi² (57.8 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 230 ft (70 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Low-flow is affected by sewage discharges from a water treatment plant, 0.60 mi (0.96 m) upstream from gaging station since 1990.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	13	12	22	6.8	6.9	6.9	7.6	5.0	25	4.8	7.1	17
2	359	11	15	8.9	7.0	6.8	11	4.9	12	4.7	6.6	104
3	58	10	12	10	6.6	7.1	13	5.1	9.9	6.0	6.0	90
4	17	9.3	11	13	6.6	6.7	8.1	10	8.7	45	5.8	31
5	12	9.5	10	18	254	6.3	7.0	9.4	8.1	16	5.8	17
6	8.8	10	9.6	227	29	6.3	6.8	6.2	8.6	7.7	6.1	55
7	7.0	9.1	9.2	430	16	7.4	6.6	5.7	11	16	35	54
8	47	9.1	8.6	64	51	8.0	6.4	21	25	10	21	68
9	18	17	8.3	69	132	6.0	6.2	26	16	7.1	36	52
10	8.3	408	8.2	78	22	5.5	6.0	15	12	6.4	25	19
11	9.9	29	7.6	133	15	4.9	6.5	8.7	8.5	6.1	9.9	12
12	79	16	7.3	39	15	5.0	7.5	6.9	48	11	9.5	9.6
13	319	15	7.6	29	13	5.1	9.9	8.5	58	5.9	7.6	13
14	1680	12	6.9	24	24	5.4	8.1	22	13	5.6	6.5	77
15	95	13	7.9	16	31	7.4	7.2	14	9.1	19	6.0	128
16	74	12	7.8	14	15	7.8	18	15	9.4	80	30	56
17	61	12	12	12	14	6.0	15	20	11	19	152	19
18	38	12	15	11	11	5.2	8.6	9.8	17	25	29	90
19	30	16	11	11	10	4.5	7.4	7.1	23	59	71	108
20	24	11	8.2	11	9.6	6.0	6.9	6.5	9.8	234	76	26
21	21	11	12	10	9.0	7.6	7.0	12	29	83	136	2250
22	19	13	10	9.4	8.6	7.8	8.3	9.4	26	32	159	e2260
23	16	11	34	8.5	8.1	7.1	6.5	13	9.8	42	34	e93
24	15	11	16	8.3	8.0	5.5	5.8	11	7.5	115	914	e46
25	14	10	9.7	7.8	7.8	6.1	6.7	8.9	6.9	32	792	e35
26	14	462	8.4	7.6	7.7	5.5	6.4	30	7.1	13	325	e37
27	13	43	8.0	7.5	7.3	7.0	6.1	99	5.8	11	125	e27
28	12	20	7.7	7.1	7.0	7.5	6.0	16	5.4	40	56	e34
29	11	21	7.2	7.1	---	13	5.7	13	5.2	18	230	e34
30	11	32	6.6	7.0	---	15	5.2	74	5.3	9.9	48	e31
31	11	---	6.8	6.9	---	16	---	84	---	8.1	26	---
TOTAL	3115.0	1287.0	331.6	1311.9	752.2	222.4	237.5	597.1	451.1	992.3	3396.9	5892.6
MEAN	100	42.9	10.7	42.3	26.9	7.17	7.92	19.3	15.0	32.0	110	196
MAX	1680	462	34	430	254	16	18	99	58	234	914	2260
MIN	7.0	9.1	6.6	6.8	6.6	4.5	5.2	4.9	5.2	4.7	5.8	9.6
AC-FT	6180	2550	658	2600	1490	441	471	1180	895	1970	6740	11690
CFSM	4.51	1.92	.48	1.90	1.20	.32	.36	.86	.67	1.44	4.91	8.81
IN.	5.20	2.15	.55	2.19	1.25	.37	.40	1.00	.75	1.66	5.67	9.83

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	50.8	63.8	27.4	39.3	31.6	11.4	8.54	25.9	45.2
MAX	161	109	59.0	103	66.7	18.1	11.0	123	117
(WY)	1991	1992	1991	1996	1995	1991	1993	1992	1992
MIN	4.01	13.6	10.7	6.34	10.4	5.63	5.29	4.83	14.7
(WY)	1993	1996	1998	1995	1993	1993	1995	1990	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	11223.9	18587.6	
ANNUAL MEAN	30.8	50.9	41.6
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			52.3
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			22.0
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1680	Oct 14	2260
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	4.1	May 4	4.5
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.5	Apr 30	5.3
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			15400
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			22.72
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	22260	36870	30160
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.38	2.28	1.87
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	18.72	31.01	25.36
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	44	76	69
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	11	11
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.6	6.1	4.6

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR--Continued

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water Year 1990 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: March 1990 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.--USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1990.

REMARKS:-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediment samples were collected with automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 2,400 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L May 5,1997.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 51,000 tons (46,300 tonnes) September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.05 ton (0.3 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 2,400 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 5 mg/L April 25, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 51,000 tons (46,300 tonnes) September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.10 ton (0.09 tonne) April 25, 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	13	32	1.2	12	44	1.5	22	60	3.7
2	359	512	1260	11	53	1.6	15	57	2.3
3	58	200	42	10	59	1.6	12	57	1.9
4	17	63	2.9	9.3	65	1.6	11	72	2.1
5	12	63	2.0	9.5	76	2.0	10	88	2.4
6	8.8	62	1.5	10	88	2.5	9.6	80	2.1
7	7.0	62	1.2	9.1	70	1.7	9.2	70	1.7
8	47	170	57	9.1	45	1.1	8.6	61	1.4
9	18	64	3.6	17	56	2.8	8.3	58	1.3
10	8.3	27	.61	408	642	2710	8.2	55	1.2
11	9.9	36	1.2	29	79	6.6	7.6	53	1.1
12	79	198	139	16	58	2.5	7.3	51	1.0
13	319	275	1810	15	56	2.3	7.6	50	1.0
14	1680	1540	19700	12	32	1.1	6.9	49	.91
15	95	72	18	13	27	1.1	7.9	49	1.0
16	74	105	21	12	32	1.1	7.8	55	1.1
17	61	166	32	12	21	.69	12	60	1.9
18	38	245	25	12	13	.43	15	55	2.2
19	30	173	14	16	76	3.3	11	49	1.5
20	24	127	8.1	11	88	2.7	8.2	51	1.1
21	21	94	5.3	11	91	2.6	12	54	1.8
22	19	86	4.4	13	74	2.6	10	55	1.5
23	16	81	3.6	11	58	1.7	34	111	17
24	15	59	2.4	11	46	1.3	16	59	2.9
25	14	43	1.6	10	34	.96	9.7	30	.78
26	14	38	1.4	462	812	2320	8.4	27	.61
27	13	34	1.2	43	121	15	8.0	27	.58
28	12	26	.85	20	66	3.7	7.7	27	.55
29	11	19	.57	21	62	4.4	7.2	27	.51
30	11	15	.43	32	84	7.3	6.6	26	.43
31	11	24	.69	---	---	---	6.8	26	.48
TOTAL	3115.0	---	23162.75	1287.0	---	5107.78	331.6	---	60.05

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	6.8	26	.48	6.9	43	.80	6.9	7	.13
2	8.9	26	.63	7.0	38	.71	6.8	7	.13
3	10	35	1.0	6.6	30	.54	7.1	9	.18
4	13	46	1.7	6.6	23	.41	6.7	13	.24
5	18	58	3.0	254	385	595	6.3	13	.23
6	227	522	693	29	44	3.4	6.3	12	.20
7	430	853	2420	16	52	2.3	7.4	14	.34
8	64	173	36	51	103	112	8.0	45	.98
9	69	152	52	132	354	287	6.0	41	.66
10	78	184	81	22	47	2.8	5.5	39	.58
11	133	166	144	15	44	1.9	4.9	37	.49
12	39	27	3.3	15	46	1.8	5.0	35	.48
13	29	18	1.7	13	50	1.7	5.1	33	.46
14	24	9	.56	24	81	8.5	5.4	31	.45
15	16	11	.46	31	92	8.9	7.4	29	.58
16	14	10	.38	15	47	1.9	7.8	26	.54
17	12	9	.31	14	49	1.9	6.0	19	.31
18	11	9	.26	11	58	1.7	5.2	14	.20
19	11	8	.24	10	51	1.4	4.5	11	.13
20	11	8	.24	9.6	40	1.0	6.0	8	.13
21	10	9	.24	9.0	31	.75	7.6	6	.13
22	9.4	9	.24	8.6	28	.65	7.8	7	.14
23	8.5	10	.23	8.1	27	.59	7.1	8	.15
24	8.3	11	.24	8.0	31	.68	5.5	8	.11
25	7.8	12	.25	7.8	38	.79	6.1	7	.12
26	7.6	13	.27	7.7	32	.66	5.5	8	.12
27	7.5	20	.41	7.3	23	.46	7.0	10	.19
28	7.1	35	.68	7.0	10	.19	7.5	12	.23
29	7.1	43	.82	---	---	---	13	12	.40
30	7.0	45	.86	---	---	---	15	25	2.6
31	6.9	47	.88	---	---	---	16	52	2.8
TOTAL	1311.9	---	3445.38	752.2	---	1040.43	222.4	---	14.43
APRIL									
1	7.6	17	.35	5.0	17	.23	25	78	5.7
2	11	21	.84	4.9	16	.22	12	36	1.2
3	13	29	1.0	5.1	15	.20	9.9	30	.80
4	8.1	18	.39	10	16	1.0	8.7	28	.65
5	7.0	18	.34	9.4	20	.79	8.1	26	.57
6	6.8	20	.36	6.2	22	.37	8.6	24	.56
7	6.6	15	.26	5.7	20	.31	11	28	1.1
8	6.4	10	.18	21	74	13	25	41	4.9
9	6.2	8	.14	26	93	8.1	16	44	1.9
10	6.0	7	.12	15	67	1.9	12	35	1.1
11	6.5	6	.11	8.7	60	.67	8.5	27	.63
12	7.5	5	.11	6.9	54	.43	48	111	35
13	9.9	12	.37	8.5	48	.72	58	192	43
14	8.1	10	.21	22	43	4.1	13	49	1.7
15	7.2	7	.13	14	38	1.7	9.1	46	1.1
16	18	45	4.7	15	34	1.9	9.4	44	1.1
17	15	52	2.3	20	31	3.3	11	41	1.3
18	8.6	28	.64	9.8	27	.84	17	46	2.2
19	7.4	23	.47	7.1	25	.47	23	56	4.2
20	6.9	20	.37	6.5	24	.42	9.8	25	.66
21	7.0	19	.35	12	31	1.0	29	74	11
22	8.3	18	.40	9.4	13	.33	26	100	7.4
23	6.5	13	.22	13	10	1.5	9.8	60	1.6
24	5.8	8	.13	11	10	1.1	7.5	36	.74
25	6.7	6	.10	8.9	10	.70	6.9	30	.56
26	6.4	8	.13	30	61	18	7.1	28	.55
27	6.1	12	.19	99	328	144	5.8	27	.42
28	6.0	13	.20	16	52	2.3	5.4	25	.37
29	5.7	12	.19	13	38	1.3	5.2	26	.37
30	5.2	14	.20	74	188	61	5.3	28	.40
31	---	---	---	84	241	72	---	---	---
TOTAL	237.5	---	15.50	597.1	---	343.90	451.1	---	132.78
MAY									
JUNE									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)		SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)		SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)		SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
		CONCENTRATION	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE			CONCENTRATION	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE			CONCENTRATION	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE	
			JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER			
1	4.8	29	.38		7.1	10	.19		17	63	3.0	
2	4.7	28	.35		6.6	10	.18	104	279	160		
3	6.0	25	.40		6.0	10	.16	90	227	60		
4	45	161	25	5.8	5.8	10	.16	31	108	9.2		
5	16	64	3.0		5.8	11	.17	17	66	3.2		
6	7.7	33	.70		6.1	12	.20	55	153	44		
7	16	41	2.3		35	85	32	54	168	24		
8	10	18	.56		21	102	7.5	68	112	20		
9	7.1	9	.18		36	101	15	52	75	11		
10	6.4	8	.14		25	87	7.5	19	55	2.8		
11	6.1	9	.14		9.9	32	.87	12	45	1.5		
12	11	42	1.3		9.5	30	.76	9.6	37	.96		
13	5.9	28	.45		7.6	27	.55	13	41	2.1		
14	5.6	16	.24		6.5	25	.43	77	185	72		
15	19	36	7.3		6.0	22	.36	128	296	131		
16	80	186	45		30	68	24	56	85	13		
17	19	30	2.0		152	415	306	19	53	2.8		
18	25	41	6.2		29	85	8.9	90	277	184		
19	59	160	27		71	203	136	108	170	54		
20	234	568	677		76	224	59	26	85	6.1		
21	83	186	56		136	159	63	2250	1850	51000		
22	32	70	18		159	355	166	e2260	2400	e32000		
23	42	113	18		34	156	17	e93	250	e64		
24	115	161	96		914	1220	6990	e46	167	e21		
25	32	11	.95		792	1430	3970	e35	112	e11		
26	13	11	.39		325	656	924	e37	90	e9.1		
27	11	11	.34		125	353	136	e27	89	e8.1		
28	40	93	12		56	196	32	e34	88	e8.1		
29	18	27	1.6		230	643	681	e34	87	e8.0		
30	9.9	10	.27		48	158	21	e31	87	e7.4		
31	8.1	10	.22		26	99	7.2	---	---	---		
TOTAL	992.3	---	1003.41		3396.9	---	13607.13	5892.6	---	83941.36		
YEAR	18587.6		131874.90									

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
11...	1315	9.0	96	2.3	95
NOV					
10...	0743	324	427	374	99
26...	0658	1260	1120	3810	96
DEC					
10...	1200	82	51	11	92
JAN					
21...	1800	10	78	2.1	71
AUG					
21...	1448	176	123	58	99
22...	0731	258	488	340	99
SEP					
18...	1832	217	298	175	98
19...	0511	140	11900	4500	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)	
NOV 10...	0230	484	1470	1920	68	79	91	
MAY 27...	0515	333	1530	1380	57	71	83	
DATE		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70335)
NOV 10...	95	96	99	100	100	100	100	100
MAY 27...	91	97	98	100	100	100	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'58", long 65°55'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank at Highway 919, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Quebrada Don Víctor, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from Río Gurabo and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) south of Juncos.

DRAINAGE AREA.--16.4 mi² (42.5 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1971 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 320 ft (98 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Minor diversion from public water supply tank, 0.5 mi (0.80 km) upstream, during low flow. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate discharges (no stages were recorded) of major floods are as follows: Sept. 6, 1960, 37,100 ft³/s (1,050 m³/s), Oct. 9, 1970, 18,200 ft³/s (515 m³/s).

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	41	e18	e35	21	13	11	24	8.7	27	7.8	8.6	18
2	263	e17	e29	46	13	10	21	8.8	15	8.2	7.7	24
3	32	e15	e19	34	12	12	15	9.1	13	8.4	7.7	51
4	19	e14	e17	35	18	11	12	25	11	77	7.2	54
5	14	e15	e16	39	234	9.8	13	19	14	21	6.8	20
6	12	e15	e15	580	42	9.5	e12	8.2	19	10	e7.7	198
7	10	e14	e14	739	28	220	e11	7.4	9.9	18	8.4	58
8	11	e14	e14	137	147	69	e11	14	24	10	9.0	355
9	12	e30	e13	186	92	21	e11	18	13	13	51	80
10	12	e680	12	100	39	14	e10	11	10	8.3	38	46
11	23	e35	12	79	31	13	e11	8.2	8.4	7.1	12	26
12	54	e25	12	41	29	12	e13	8.2	23	10	16	21
13	493	e24	12	43	25	11	e17	13	13	7.2	12	78
14	2480	e19	13	46	99	19	e14	15	9.6	11	8.3	75
15	151	e20	12	30	70	17	e12	7.3	8.2	14	8.6	157
16	113	e19	15	27	36	10	e42	7.8	14	23	9.6	82
17	e77	e19	30	24	29	10	36	7.5	11	12	37	49
18	e56	e19	31	23	21	8.7	14	6.4	e34	57	16	76
19	e42	e25	17	21	17	9.1	9.8	6.0	40	39	11	e92
20	e33	e17	16	20	15	14	12	7.4	12	298	37	53
21	e29	e17	30	19	15	11	36	7.9	32	67	90	e1410
22	e26	e20	17	20	13	11	34	5.8	43	21	107	e4680
23	e23	e17	37	21	14	9.0	15	9.7	11	17	20	e351
24	e21	e17	24	20	12	8.3	13	20	9.3	28	856	e115
25	e20	e16	19	20	11	21	12	9.4	34	19	752	e82
26	e18	e720	18	17	11	12	14	25	25	13	141	e76
27	e18	e100	17	17	11	24	13	90	10	15	72	e64
28	e17	e31	17	16	11	18	16	14	9.8	30	41	e59
29	e16	e33	18	16	---	64	10	20	9.2	13	123	e54
30	e16	e50	21	17	---	197	9.3	546	8.4	11	27	e49
31	e14	---	22	13	---	73	---	73	---	10	20	---
TOTAL	4166	2075	594	2467	1108	959.4	493.1	1036.8	520.8	904.0	2568.6	8553
MEAN	134	69.2	19.2	79.6	39.6	30.9	16.4	33.4	17.4	29.2	82.9	285
MAX	2480	720	37	739	234	220	42	546	43	298	856	4680
MIN	10	14	12	13	11	8.3	9.3	5.8	8.2	7.1	6.8	18
AC-FT	8260	4120	1180	4890	2200	1900	978	2060	1030	1790	5090	16960
CFSM	8.19	4.22	1.17	4.85	2.41	1.89	1.00	2.04	1.06	1.78	5.05	17.4
IN.	9.45	4.71	1.35	5.60	2.51	2.18	1.12	2.35	1.18	2.05	5.83	19.40

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1971 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	73.9	86.3	51.4	26.6	20.2	19.0	15.2	46.8	50.3	47.1	62.5	90.8
MEAN	73.9	86.3	51.4	26.6	20.2	19.0	15.2	46.8	50.3	47.1	62.5	90.8
MAX	293	461	550	79.6	47.9	39.7	41.7	268	188	163	231	285
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1998	1984	1973	1985	1985	1979	1981	1979	1998
MIN	19.9	16.8	11.0	11.4	7.21	7.01	5.17	5.02	4.95	4.61	4.71	10.8
(WY)	1993	1996	1990	1976	1974	1977	1995	1990	1994	1994	1994	1987

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1998 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1971 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	14767.8	25445.7	
ANNUAL MEAN	40.5	69.7	49.4
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			121
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			17.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2480	Oct 14	9100
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.9	Jun 18	1.4
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.6	Jun 29	1.7
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			40000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			25.63
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	29290	50470	35770
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.47	4.25	3.01
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	33.50	57.72	40.91
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	49	85	72
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15	18	18
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.5	9.1	7.0

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1983 to 1986 and water year 1989 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1994 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- Automatic sediment sampler since 1984.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow event sediment samples were collected by a local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 8,340 mg/L September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 263,000 tons (238,000 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 ton (0.01 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 5,310 mg/L September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 6 mg/L March 19-21, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 65,400 tons (59,400 tonnes) October 14, 1997; Minimum daily mean, 0.15 tons (0.14 tonne) March 19, 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	41	199	39	e18	208	e4.4	e35	36	e14
2	263	492	915	e17	40	e3.6	e29	47	e14
3	32	59	5.7	e15	12	e3.4	e19	62	e5.1
4	19	15	.81	e14	18	e3.2	e17	75	e3.6
5	14	10	.38	e15	29	e3.4	e16	73	e3.5
6	12	9	.29	e15	47	e3.4	e15	69	e3.4
7	10	8	.22	e14	75	e3.2	e14	52	e3.2
8	11	17	.54	e14	113	e3.2	e14	50	e3.2
9	12	76	2.2	e30	112	e15	e13	66	e2.2
10	12	68	2.4	e680	101	e5780	12	51	1.7
11	23	100	11	e35	96	e19	12	39	1.3
12	54	235	80	e25	100	e8.5	12	28	.90
13	493	2400	17200	e24	106	e8.2	12	22	.74
14	2480	4380	65400	e19	112	e5.1	13	20	.72
15	151	523	221	e20	124	e5.8	12	18	.61
16	113	300	90	e19	139	e5.1	15	25	1.2
17	e77	598	e94	e19	156	e5.1	30	95	16
18	e56	473	e80	e19	153	e5.1	31	139	18
19	e42	149	e31	e25	102	e8.5	17	108	5.1
20	e33	47	e16	e17	67	e3.6	16	92	5.6
21	e29	18	e14	e17	55	e3.6	30	160	15
22	e26	14	e8.8	e20	48	e5.8	17	66	3.1
23	e23	12	e7.9	e17	53	e3.6	37	167	26
24	e21	9	e6.8	e17	60	e3.6	24	137	8.6
25	e20	8	e5.8	e16	57	e3.5	19	78	4.0
26	e18	9	e4.4	e720	53	e7100	18	64	3.2
27	e18	9	e4.4	e100	49	e151	17	53	2.5
28	e17	10	e3.6	e31	44	e16	17	48	2.1
29	e16	16	e3.5	e33	40	e16	18	54	2.6
30	e16	217	e3.5	e50	36	e59	21	63	3.7
31	e14	861	e3.2	---	---	---	22	78	4.7
TOTAL	4166	---	84255.44	2075	---	13258.9	594	---	179.57

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	21	99	5.6	13	65	2.3	11	80	2.3
2	46	133	35	13	51	1.8	10	76	2.1
3	34	130	13	12	59	2.0	12	72	2.2
4	35	62	5.7	18	101	16	11	68	2.0
5	39	48	5.1	234	3870	3290	9.8	65	1.7
6	580	3580	7320	42	268	31	9.5	61	1.6
7	739	3320	10500	28	188	14	220	1700	4690
8	137	602	243	147	1630	2230	69	590	150
9	186	710	640	92	345	117	21	87	5.3
10	100	495	151	39	154	16	14	33	1.3
11	79	358	83	31	118	10	13	37	1.3
12	41	218	24	29	94	7.4	12	45	1.5
13	43	193	30	25	84	5.6	11	53	1.6
14	46	175	33	99	1400	973	19	105	7.0
15	30	94	7.7	70	380	83	17	172	8.2
16	27	35	2.5	36	142	14	10	90	2.5
17	24	35	2.3	29	89	7.0	10	51	1.4
18	23	37	2.3	21	103	5.8	8.7	17	.41
19	21	39	2.2	17	118	5.5	9.1	6	.15
20	20	39	2.1	15	126	5.3	14	6	.23
21	19	34	1.8	15	130	5.1	11	6	.19
22	20	31	1.6	13	120	4.2	11	7	.21
23	21	37	2.1	14	110	4.1	9.0	8	.20
24	20	47	2.5	12	104	3.4	8.3	9	.21
25	20	59	3.1	11	99	2.9	21	106	7.9
26	17	75	3.4	11	94	2.9	12	78	2.5
27	17	87	3.9	11	89	2.7	24	89	12
28	16	80	3.5	11	84	2.6	18	164	5.5
29	16	77	3.2	---	---	---	64	1670	1120
30	17	111	6.0	---	---	---	197	690	778
31	13	92	3.2	---	---	---	73	362	89
TOTAL	2467	---	19141.8	1108	---	6864.6	959.4	---	6898.50
DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	24	107	7.1	8.7	66	1.6	27	82	6.6
2	21	86	5.3	8.8	65	1.6	15	26	1.1
3	15	90	3.4	9.1	64	1.6	13	34	1.2
4	12	82	2.1	25	76	12	11	52	1.6
5	13	74	2.9	19	1240	69	14	81	4.0
6	e12	68	e1.7	8.2	534	12	19	77	5.5
7	e11	281	e2.1	7.4	227	4.5	9.9	22	.61
8	e11	74	e2.1	14	157	7.6	24	69	11
9	e11	16	e2.1	18	194	10	13	31	1.1
10	e10	13	e1.7	11	146	4.2	10	19	.54
11	e11	12	e2.1	8.2	88	1.9	8.4	15	.33
12	e13	12	e2.6	8.2	53	1.2	23	122	11
13	e17	12	e3.6	13	72	4.0	13	23	.89
14	e14	17	e3.2	15	77	3.8	9.6	22	.57
15	e12	55	e2.1	7.3	34	.68	8.2	38	.86
16	e42	234	e31	7.8	35	.73	14	60	3.0
17	36	306	35	7.5	35	.70	11	53	2.1
18	14	125	4.9	6.4	35	.61	e34	96	e18
19	9.8	136	1.6	6.0	36	.58	40	454	71
20	12	186	3.6	7.4	36	.93	12	113	3.7
21	36	935	429	7.9	36	1.0	32	87	29
22	34	195	21	5.8	29	.46	43	82	36
23	15	82	3.3	9.7	35	1.8	11	76	2.2
24	13	77	2.7	20	41	6.4	9.3	67	1.7
25	12	71	2.3	9.4	48	1.4	34	196	67
26	14	69	3.2	25	106	14	25	566	45
27	13	44	1.5	90	605	173	10	236	6.6
28	16	68	3.9	14	438	17	9.8	155	4.1
29	10	68	1.9	20	377	20	9.2	105	2.6
30	9.3	67	1.7	546	1620	4240	8.4	76	1.7
31	---	---	---	73	292	61	---	---	---
TOTAL	493.1	---	590.7	1036.8	---	4675.29	520.8	---	340.60

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	7.8	70	1.5	8.6	37	.86	18	44	2.2
2	8.2	65	1.4	7.7	19	.40	24	92	11
3	8.4	61	1.4	7.7	13	.26	51	276	39
4	77	328	97	7.2	19	.38	54	451	71
5	21	117	8.1	6.8	31	.56	20	200	11
6	10	131	1.7	e7.7	41	e.82	198	1110	1690
7	18	145	6.3	8.4	50	1.1	58	310	59
8	10	162	1.6	9.0	52	1.3	355	2800	6010
9	13	180	3.1	51	315	136	80	559	103
10	8.3	200	1.1	38	276	57	46	245	33
11	7.1	223	.81	12	39	1.2	26	63	4.6
12	10	248	1.8	16	72	3.8	21	38	2.2
13	7.2	276	.83	12	80	2.7	78	339	149
14	11	307	2.3	8.3	30	.68	75	371	84
15	14	342	6.7	8.6	14	.31	157	807	788
16	23	90	7.9	9.6	13	.32	82	246	53
17	12	78	2.1	37	172	31	49	131	17
18	57	86	94	16	154	4.1	76	352	90
19	39	95	24	11	147	1.8	e92	142	e145
20	298	1600	2620	37	140	29	53	50	7.1
21	67	152	44	90	134	145	e1410	5310	e31000
22	21	65	3.7	107	430	230	e4680	2300	e42100
23	17	51	2.4	20	126	7.1	e351	88	e119
24	28	91	14	856	2430	11800	e115	21	e5.5
25	19	84	5.5	752	1130	3700	e82	20	e4.5
26	13	78	2.5	141	770	383	e76	19	e3.7
27	15	72	3.7	72	260	78	e64	17	e2.9
28	30	66	16	41	208	25	e59	14	e2.2
29	13	61	2.7	123	166	333	e54	12	e1.8
30	11	56	1.9	27	133	11	e49	---	e1.7
31	10	52	1.7	20	107	5.8	---	---	---
TOTAL	904.0	---	2981.74	2568.6	---	16991.49	8553	---	82610.4
YEAR	25445.7		238789.03						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
02...	0900	926	1300	3250	95
17...	1650	77	1110	231	98
JAN					
06...	1345	695	1240	2330	91
09...	1835	287	1190	922	86
FEB					
05...	0330	323	9550	8330	85
05...	1245	375	1200	1220	68
08...	2215	643	2940	5100	57
14...	1745	367	8830	8750	87
MAY					
30...	0600	2620	3820	27000	84
AUG					
22...	0445	466	1430	1800	94
SEP					
22...	0830	4530	4430	54200	80

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SESPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)
OCT							
13...	2100	302	12700	10400	34	43	55
FEB							
05...	0700	437	6560	7740	39	49	63
MAR							
07...	2115	519	2680	3760	52	64	79
29...	1700	233	7720	4860	14	18	26
SEP							
21...	2200	5770	8930	139000	11	17	25

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70335)
OCT							
13...	68	78	86	94	99	100	100
FEB							
05...	75	82	83	86	99	100	100
MAR							
07...	89	95	96	98	99	100	100
29...	38	54	71	87	99	100	100
SEP							
21...	32	44	56	76	91	98	99

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water year 1985 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1983 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 and USD-77 sediment sampler, since 1984. Automatic sediment sampler, since 1984.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediments samples were collected by local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 9,220 mg/L Nov 27, 1987; Minimum daily mean, 3 mg/L August 09, 1994.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 686,000 tons (622,340 tonnes) Nov 27, 1987; Minimum daily mean, 0.08 tons (0.07 tonne) August 09, 1994.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,510 mg/L November 26, 1997 ; minimum daily mean, 5 mg/L December 5, 1997.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 32,300 tons (29,300 tonnes) October 14, 1997; minimum daily, 0.30 ton (0.27 tonne) December 21, 1997.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	41	67	7.3	e23	20	e1.3	25	31	2.1
2	514	353	977	e22	18	e1.1	24	21	1.3
3	102	164	29	e21	17	e.97	24	13	.85
4	46	87	10	e22	15	e.92	23	10	.60
5	34	41	3.8	e23	16	e1.0	23	7	.47
6	29	20	1.5	e28	18	e1.3	23	7	.43
7	25	12	.84	e27	19	e1.4	23	7	.43
8	36	20	3.7	e30	29	e2.9	22	7	.42
9	49	45	6.6	e47	34	e4.7	22	7	.44
10	45	19	2.3	e424	273	e542	22	8	.48
11	90	59	20	e39	117	e13	21	10	.57
12	169	157	106	e32	88	e4.2	20	13	.70
13	349	508	1630	e26	68	e4.6	20	11	.57
14	7580	990	32300	33	51	4.5	21	7	.41
15	e199	183	e105	47	51	8.6	21	5	.30
16	e130	116	e41	29	49	3.8	22	6	.37
17	e149	111	e54	25	43	2.9	31	13	1.0
18	e70	77	e15	24	37	2.4	33	17	1.9
19	e46	44	e5.5	23	33	2.1	29	22	1.8
20	e36	28	e2.7	22	34	2.0	22	11	.69
21	e31	22	e1.8	22	16	.91	32	35	3.1
22	e29	19	e1.5	22	15	.86	25	40	2.7
23	e27	21	e1.6	20	18	1.0	48	49	9.1
24	e26	24	e1.7	20	23	1.2	40	68	7.5
25	e25	16	e1.1	20	25	1.3	24	55	3.6
26	e24	10	e.65	e347	1510	e1700	22	44	2.5
27	e23	7	e.42	78	94	26	20	32	1.7
28	e22	11	e.63	28	48	3.6	20	23	1.2
29	e21	19	e1.1	25	36	2.4	19	20	1.1
30	e20	21	e1.1	34	39	3.8	18	19	.93
31	e19	22	e1.1	---	---	---	18	17	.85
TOTAL	10006	---	35333.94	1583	---	2346.76	757	---	50.11

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	19	15	.80	31	14	1.2	29	7	.56
2	25	16	1.1	30	19	1.5	28	7	.53
3	25	18	1.2	30	12	.96	29	7	.58
4	26	19	1.4	34	21	3.3	29	8	.62
5	34	21	1.9	e361	253	e192	35	26	3.2
6	e395	244	e471	82	126	28	30	34	2.8
7	604	438	1080	52	72	10	67	67	26
8	e154	133	e58	e109	80	e63	76	75	19
9	124	133	42	e165	147	e67	35	36	3.4
10	130	219	41	65	59	10	30	25	2.1
11	e173	223	e76	51	34	4.8	27	17	1.3
12	75	152	31	47	22	2.7	26	12	.85
13	72	79	16	45	14	1.7	25	9	.64
14	76	75	16	86	59	26	26	10	.69
15	51	42	5.8	96	95	27	33	10	.86
16	45	24	2.9	52	50	7.1	32	9	.80
17	42	15	1.7	49	29	3.9	27	9	.66
18	40	12	1.3	44	18	2.1	25	9	.61
19	38	14	1.5	41	24	2.6	24	9	.61
20	37	17	1.7	39	37	3.9	25	10	.66
21	36	18	1.8	37	25	2.5	29	9	.74
22	35	18	1.7	35	13	1.2	26	9	.60
23	35	18	1.7	35	8	.72	26	9	.61
24	35	18	1.7	33	9	.77	23	12	.76
25	35	18	1.7	32	10	.82	26	18	1.3
26	35	17	1.5	33	8	.74	27	17	1.3
27	33	11	1.0	31	7	.61	28	18	1.4
28	34	8	.69	30	7	.57	31	31	2.6
29	33	7	.63	---	---	---	61	56	13
30	33	7	.65	---	---	---	82	87	26
31	30	10	.80	---	---	---	87	97	26
TOTAL	2559	---	1866.17	1775	---	466.69	1104	---	140.78
APRIL									
1	34	69	6.3	15	10	.40	e93	54	e18
2	32	45	3.8	15	11	.44	e36	26	e2.5
3	35	24	2.3	16	13	.54	e28	25	e1.9
4	26	16	1.1	23	24	1.7	e25	23	e1.6
5	23	13	.82	29	32	2.5	e23	22	e1.3
6	25	12	.77	19	19	.95	e24	21	e1.3
7	24	14	.89	16	17	.76	e27	19	e1.4
8	23	17	1.0	30	32	3.6	e42	18	e2.1
9	20	12	.66	56	58	9.4	e46	17	e2.1
10	20	8	.42	37	49	5.1	e30	16	e1.3
11	19	12	.61	22	39	2.3	e23	16	e1.1
12	34	32	2.9	18	36	1.8	e38	26	e3.4
13	26	19	1.3	17	32	1.5	e155	128	e63
14	24	15	.93	32	37	3.3	e43	43	e5.2
15	21	13	.74	23	30	1.9	e29	24	e1.9
16	30	26	3.0	24	25	1.7	e28	29	e2.2
17	63	67	11	26	31	2.2	e35	37	e3.5
18	28	38	3.0	20	34	1.8	e49	56	e7.6
19	28	36	2.7	16	29	1.3	e62	106	e20
20	38	46	4.9	14	25	.96	e40	54	e6.1
21	69	65	22	18	22	1.0	e38	42	e5.5
22	53	66	11	16	19	.81	e90	99	e25
23	21	47	2.7	15	18	.72	e43	60	e7.0
24	18	42	2.0	21	25	1.4	e36	69	e6.6
25	18	33	1.6	15	15	.63	32	66	5.7
26	18	25	1.2	e19	49	e2.2	51	59	8.8
27	18	20	.95	e139	264	e53	30	26	2.1
28	17	18	.87	29	82	2.8	28	22	1.6
29	18	17	.82	26	31	2.3	26	20	1.4
30	15	13	.53	e122	102	e48	25	18	1.2
31	---	---	---	e157	133	e66	---	---	---
TOTAL	838	---	92.81	1045	---	223.01	1275	---	212.4
MAY									
JUNE									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	24	18	1.1	38	19	2.0	53	51	7.3
2	23	22	1.4	39	30	3.4	90	99	29
3	23	26	1.6	36	43	4.1	122	287	36
4	82	77	22	35	29	2.7	89	209	51
5	64	77	14	33	20	1.8	57	89	14
6	36	44	4.4	35	19	1.8	171	157	150
7	36	40	3.9	123	88	74	118	139	49
8	46	26	3.2	106	97	29	262	257	289
9	48	20	2.6	63	66	11	123	129	48
10	46	18	2.2	93	85	24	69	56	11
11	43	19	2.2	47	43	5.5	52	36	5.1
12	48	22	2.8	47	32	4.0	46	25	3.1
13	43	24	2.8	45	28	3.4	56	40	9.0
14	43	26	3.0	38	26	2.7	109	148	45
15	47	31	4.0	36	27	2.7	209	172	135
16	92	87	22	36	29	2.8	116	133	43
17	67	67	12	150	118	73	74	105	21
18	62	62	11	83	84	20	100	99	40
19	95	127	33	61	65	13	162	138	64
20	e405	752	e1820	113	108	34	81	87	19
21	178	309	206	179	191	107	e1930	679	e12000
22	64	66	11	202	160	104	3520	1030	10500
23	73	55	11	84	82	19	356	421	435
24	115	110	39	e1040	466	e2580	211	102	60
25	68	65	12	e1520	714	e3630	171	25	11
26	52	47	6.6	552	401	883	158	17	7.1
27	50	34	4.5	148	145	61	146	15	6.0
28	67	51	10	96	126	33	134	13	4.8
29	59	62	10	319	231	357	123	9	2.9
30	44	49	5.9	84	116	27	117	6	1.8
31	40	30	3.3	61	73	12	---	---	---
TOTAL	2183	---	2288.5	5542	---	8127.9	9025	---	24097.1
YEAR	37692		75246.17						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L) (80154)	SED- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
13...	1500	155	221	92	98
14...	0400	31300	1660	140000	96
14...	1115	2320	709	4440	96
17...	1845	504	210	286	98
NOV					
26...	0945	454	1170	1430	90
26...	1500	380	393	403	99
26...	1915	392	2070	2190	88
MAY					
27...	1445	110	432	128	98
JUL					
20...	1700	992	3140	8410	98
21...	0100	516	928	1290	98

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS- PENDEDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)
		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)
OCT							
12...	2100	516	465	648	45	53	63
14...	1040	3240	1240	10800	49	59	68
NOV							
26...	0600	888	5500	13200	39	48	59
DATE							
OCT							
12...	72	80	85	95	99	100	100
14...	77	84	87	95	99	100	100
NOV							
26...	70	80	84	94	98	99	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057025 RIO GURABO NEAR GURABO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'56", long 65°59'04", at bridge on Highway 941, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) west-northwest from gaging station 50057000, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) northwest of Gurabo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--62.8 mi² (162.7 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)		
OCT	15...	1150	--	200	6.6	26.0	88	5.7	69	23	46000	K14000
FEB	18...	0855	19	341	7.1	26.0	10	4.4	55	<10	2000	380
MAY	26...	0945	6.9	391	7.0	30.0	10	5.3	70	<10	2100	K120
AUG	17...	0745	90	399	6.5	29.0	25	4.2	55	<10	4900	K1900

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)	
OCT	15...	58	14	5.8	14	.8	3.5	56	<0.5	11	15
FEB	18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
MAY	26...	120	27	13	32	1	3.9	130	--	15	35
AUG	17...	130	29	13	28	1	5.0	140	<1.0	16	31

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	
OCT	15...	.12	20	116	--	108	.770	.060	.830	.130	.35
FEB	18...	--	--	--	--	7	1.03	.068	1.10	.200	.47
MAY	26...	.17	32	236	4.40	22	.691	.059	.750	.050	.82
AUG	17...	.14	34	240	58.4	46	.758	.062	.820	.190	.68

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)	
OCT	15...	.48	1.3	5.8	.040	<1	<100	30	<1	3	<10
FEB	18...	.67	1.8	7.8	.220	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY	26...	.87	1.6	7.2	.130	1	<100	50	<1	<1	<10
AUG	17...	.87	1.7	7.5	.620	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT RIO CAÑAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'41", long 66°02'44", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at right bank, off road 798, upstream side of bridge on Highway 52, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) northeast from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Francisco Valdés, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) north of La Barra.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.53 mi² (19.50 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 164 ft (50 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.2	6.6	9.5	11	4.1	5.2	3.7	2.6	3.7	e3.0	4.0	5.8
2	12	6.6	9.5	7.0	4.2	4.9	3.6	2.5	3.8	e3.8	3.9	7.1
3	4.3	6.5	9.3	7.0	4.1	5.3	3.4	2.6	3.7	e6.2	3.9	7.3
4	3.2	6.7	10	7.1	60	5.3	3.4	2.5	4.6	e5.0	3.7	9.8
5	3.0	6.7	9.7	7.7	79	5.7	3.3	2.4	10	e3.7	3.7	7.5
6	20	6.2	9.5	29	8.9	5.1	3.3	2.3	4.1	e27	e4.4	8.8
7	5.3	5.8	9.8	29	8.3	8.1	5.0	2.2	3.7	e9.5	51	6.4
8	7.2	5.3	9.4	10	33	6.2	4.0	4.4	3.6	e4.3	7.5	7.3
9	4.3	5.2	9.2	9.9	16	4.9	3.3	3.0	7.4	e3.6	4.5	5.3
10	3.5	7.1	8.8	9.2	9.4	4.8	3.2	2.7	4.1	e3.9	4.1	4.8
11	6.2	5.3	8.5	8.7	8.8	4.6	3.2	2.6	3.6	e3.5	3.9	4.4
12	30	5.6	8.2	8.1	7.9	4.5	5.9	2.5	3.4	e3.3	3.9	4.3
13	42	4.9	8.1	21	7.2	4.3	4.7	2.4	3.4	e3.1	3.7	5.3
14	227	4.8	8.4	13	15	11	3.8	41	3.3	e2.8	3.6	4.2
15	20	75	9.2	7.2	10	4.4	3.9	6.8	3.3	e2.8	3.6	7.1
16	18	17	8.9	7.2	7.7	3.7	12	4.5	3.1	e3.6	3.4	4.7
17	15	10	8.7	8.5	7.2	4.1	4.0	4.3	55	e4.3	7.8	4.5
18	14	9.7	8.0	6.5	6.2	4.0	3.6	4.2	9.8	e3.9	35	5.5
19	13	11	8.0	5.9	5.9	3.6	3.3	4.4	6.3	e4.6	5.8	4.5
20	11	9.9	8.0	5.3	5.6	3.8	3.3	4.3	5.8	e28	5.0	5.7
21	9.1	9.9	8.6	5.3	5.5	4.2	3.2	4.2	13	e11	12	264
22	8.1	10	7.7	5.2	5.5	3.5	3.1	4.1	e6.8	5.4	10	1060
23	7.6	10	7.4	4.9	5.3	3.4	3.0	4.0	e4.4	9.4	5.4	172
24	7.3	9.7	7.2	4.9	5.3	3.5	2.8	4.5	e4.4	7.9	51	86
25	9.4	9.5	7.0	5.0	5.2	3.8	2.9	4.3	e6.8	4.9	52	77
26	8.0	11	7.0	4.7	5.5	3.4	3.0	4.2	e3.7	4.4	7.2	115
27	7.5	10	7.0	4.5	5.3	3.4	3.4	4.3	e3.4	5.5	21	83
28	7.2	10	7.2	4.3	5.2	3.6	3.0	4.3	e3.5	7.9	166	57
29	6.7	9.9	7.7	4.1	---	16	2.7	4.1	e3.3	4.6	15	57
30	7.0	9.5	7.4	4.0	---	5.1	2.7	4.2	e3.4	4.4	8.0	49
31	6.6	---	7.9	4.1	---	4.9	---	3.9	---	4.3	e6.5	---
TOTAL	550.7	315.4	260.8	269.3	351.3	158.3	113.7	150.3	198.4	199.6	520.5	2140.3
MEAN	17.8	10.5	8.41	8.69	12.5	5.11	3.79	4.85	6.61	6.44	16.8	71.3
MAX	227	75	10	29	79	16	12	41	55	28	166	1060
MIN	3.0	4.8	7.0	4.0	4.1	3.4	2.7	2.2	3.1	2.8	3.4	4.2
AC-FT	1090	626	517	534	697	314	226	298	394	396	1030	4250
CFSM	2.36	1.40	1.12	1.15	1.67	.68	.50	.64	.88	.86	2.23	9.47
IN.	2.72	1.56	1.29	1.33	1.74	.78	.56	.74	.98	.99	2.57	10.57

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	
MEAN	15.4	13.6	11.3	11.3	10.3	5.24	5.37	8.26	7.49	8.42	15.7	27.8
MAX	39.4	36.2	29.9	24.5	18.8	7.97	11.1	19.5	20.0	24.9	36.8	81.6
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1995	1997	1993	1992	1993	1993	1996	1996
MIN	4.60	7.18	5.55	4.48	4.29	2.48	3.24	2.50	1.78	3.40	4.36	4.25
(WY)	1992	1991	1994	1994	1994	1994	1995	1994	1994	1990	1990	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	3335.6	5228.6	
ANNUAL MEAN	9.14	14.3	12.2
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			17.7
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			5.77
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	382	Aug 22	1060
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.3	Jun 28	2.2
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.5	Jun 12	2.4
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2490
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			18.19
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			2.2
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	6620	10370	8820
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.21	1.90	1.62
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	16.48	25.83	21.97
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	12	15	18
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.4	5.5	5.1
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.1	3.3	2.7

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT RIO CAÑAS, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT CAÑAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water year 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1994 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1990.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediment samples were collected by local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 12,900 mg/L September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 95,000 tons (86,200 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 ton (0.01 tonne) January 08, 1995.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,560 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L December 26, 1997.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 12,000 tons (10,900 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.02 ton (0.02 tonne) several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	7.2	203	17	6.6	36	.63	9.5	34	.87
2	12	238	20	6.6	29	.51	9.5	17	.43
3	4.3	47	.56	6.5	23	.41	9.3	7	.19
4	3.2	26	.23	6.7	19	.34	10	6	.17
5	3.0	19	.16	6.7	17	.30	9.7	7	.18
6	20	957	408	6.2	15	.26	9.5	6	.14
7	5.3	39	.58	5.8	14	.22	9.8	4	.11
8	7.2	296	24	5.3	17	.24	9.4	3	.08
9	4.3	28	.33	5.2	41	.57	9.2	3	.07
10	3.5	13	.13	7.1	58	1.2	8.8	3	.07
11	6.2	47	1.3	5.3	19	.28	8.5	5	.12
12	30	519	283	5.6	48	.81	8.2	10	.22
13	42	400	725	4.9	71	.95	8.1	9	.20
14	227	1690	3260	4.8	48	.62	8.4	6	.14
15	20	102	5.8	75	2230	2050	9.2	4	.11
16	18	54	2.6	17	341	43	8.9	6	.14
17	15	52	2.1	10	91	2.5	8.7	8	.19
18	14	54	2.1	9.7	70	1.8	8.0	6	.14
19	13	57	2.0	11	127	4.5	8.0	4	.10
20	11	60	1.8	9.9	36	.97	8.0	4	.09
21	9.1	47	1.2	9.9	28	.76	8.6	5	.11
22	8.1	33	.72	10	31	.87	7.7	6	.11
23	7.6	18	.38	10	33	.93	7.4	6	.12
24	7.3	10	.19	9.7	34	.88	7.2	7	.13
25	9.4	56	2.4	9.5	26	.65	7.0	4	.07
26	8.0	68	1.5	11	18	.51	7.0	2	.04
27	7.5	36	.71	10	14	.37	7.0	3	.06
28	7.2	10	.19	10	47	1.4	7.2	5	.10
29	6.7	13	.23	9.9	73	1.9	7.7	9	.19
30	7.0	22	.41	9.5	50	1.3	7.4	16	.32
31	6.6	36	.65	---	---	---	7.9	17	.35
TOTAL	550.7	---	4765.27	315.4	---	2119.68	260.8	---	5.36

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT CAÑAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	11	80	3.1	4.1	5	.05	5.2	8	.11
2	7.0	67	1.3	4.2	5	.06	4.9	8	.10
3	7.0	38	.72	4.1	4	.04	5.3	5	.08
4	7.1	24	.47	60	1140	2270	5.3	3	.05
5	7.7	16	.33	79	1600	1130	5.7	6	.78
6	29	551	105	8.9	44	1.1	5.1	10	.14
7	29	905	98	8.3	23	.53	8.1	40	3.2
8	10	97	2.8	33	489	165	6.2	46	.83
9	9.9	30	3.2	16	168	9.0	4.9	13	.18
10	9.2	10	.25	9.4	28	.72	4.8	5	.06
11	8.7	10	.23	8.8	9	.20	4.6	4	.05
12	8.1	10	.22	7.9	12	.25	4.5	4	.05
13	21	88	30	7.2	25	.49	4.3	4	.05
14	13	90	3.8	15	25	13	11	193	29
15	7.2	17	.34	10	19	.53	4.4	26	.32
16	7.2	10	.20	7.7	16	.34	3.7	11	.11
17	8.5	169	11	7.2	10	.19	4.1	9	.09
18	6.5	24	.42	6.2	6	.09	4.0	8	.09
19	5.9	14	.22	5.9	4	.06	3.6	8	.08
20	5.3	10	.14	5.6	3	.05	3.8	9	.09
21	5.3	9	.13	5.5	3	.05	4.2	9	.10
22	5.2	4	.05	5.5	3	.04	3.5	9	.09
23	4.9	5	.06	5.3	3	.04	3.4	9	.08
24	4.9	8	.10	5.3	3	.04	3.5	9	.08
25	5.0	12	.17	5.2	3	.05	3.8	8	.08
26	4.7	20	.25	5.5	5	.07	3.4	8	.07
27	4.5	29	.35	5.3	6	.09	3.4	7	.06
28	4.3	38	.44	5.2	7	.10	3.6	6	.06
29	4.1	16	.18	---	---	---	16	27	28
30	4.0	4	.05	---	---	---	5.1	53	.75
31	4.1	4	.04	---	---	---	4.9	20	.56
TOTAL	269.3	---	263.56	351.3	---	3592.18	158.3	---	65.39
FEBRUARY									
MARCH									
APRIL									
1	3.7	11	.10	2.6	3	.02	3.7	3	.03
2	3.6	9	.09	2.5	5	.03	3.8	6	.06
3	3.4	8	.08	2.6	9	.06	3.7	10	.10
4	3.4	8	.07	2.5	13	.09	4.6	28	.45
5	3.3	7	.07	2.4	7	.05	10	268	33
6	3.3	7	.06	2.3	4	.02	4.1	48	.54
7	5.0	25	1.1	2.2	3	.02	3.7	19	.19
8	4.0	22	.26	4.4	285	2.0	3.6	9	.08
9	3.3	13	.11	3.0	16	.13	7.4	17	2.4
10	3.2	12	.10	2.7	7	.05	4.1	28	.31
11	3.2	11	.09	2.6	3	.02	3.6	25	.24
12	5.9	33	2.6	2.5	3	.02	3.4	23	.22
13	4.7	32	.44	2.4	4	.03	3.4	23	.21
14	3.8	10	.10	41	1510	1320	3.3	22	.20
15	3.9	10	.21	6.8	103	2.2	3.3	22	.19
16	12	104	10	4.5	54	.65	3.1	21	.18
17	4.0	30	.33	4.3	45	.52	55	1450	1040
18	3.6	19	.19	4.2	37	.42	9.8	112	3.2
19	3.3	12	.11	4.4	34	.44	6.3	43	.74
20	3.3	15	.13	4.3	19	.23	5.8	33	.51
21	3.2	19	.16	4.2	12	.13	13	50	9.6
22	3.1	17	.14	4.1	11	.12	e6.8	48	e.95
23	3.0	11	.09	4.0	11	.12	e4.4	15	e.18
24	2.8	7	.05	4.5	22	.33	e4.4	13	e.19
25	2.9	7	.05	4.3	40	.46	e6.8	25	e.72
26	3.0	7	.06	4.2	22	.25	e3.7	10	e.10
27	3.4	8	.07	4.3	14	.16	e3.4	9	e.08
28	3.0	6	.05	4.3	9	.10	e3.5	6	e.06
29	2.7	5	.04	4.1	6	.06	e3.3	4	e.04
30	2.7	4	.03	4.2	4	.05	e3.4	5	e.04
31	---	---	---	3.9	4	.04	---	---	---
TOTAL	113.7	---	16.98	150.3	---	1328.82	198.4	---	1094.81
MAY									
JUNE									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT CAÑAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	e3.0	6	e.05	4.0	5	.06	5.8	21	.32
2	e3.8	4	e.04	3.9	5	.05	7.1	67	1.9
3	e6.2	3	e.05	3.9	5	.05	7.3	76	1.4
4	e5.0	4	e.05	3.7	4	.04	9.8	150	2.7
5	e3.7	5	e5.0	3.7	3	.03	7.5	123	1.4
6	e27	341	e83	e4.4	3	e.04	8.8	79	3.1
7	e9.5	120	e4.1	51	731	574	6.4	55	.98
8	e4.3	25	e.29	7.5	74	2.1	7.3	69	1.5
9	e3.6	26	e.25	4.5	29	.37	5.3	24	.34
10	e3.9	29	e.30	4.1	7	.08	4.8	8	.10
11	e3.5	32	e.30	3.9	7	.07	4.4	8	.10
12	e3.3	35	e.31	3.9	7	.08	4.3	11	.13
13	e3.1	36	e.30	3.7	8	.08	5.3	32	.66
14	e2.8	31	e.23	3.6	9	.09	4.2	13	.15
15	e2.8	25	e.19	3.6	9	.09	7.1	53	2.0
16	e3.6	23	e.23	3.4	9	.08	4.7	23	.29
17	e4.3	22	e.26	7.8	16	3.0	4.5	16	.19
18	e3.9	21	e.22	35	509	351	5.5	19	.77
19	e4.6	20	e.26	5.8	31	.56	4.5	28	.39
20	e28	137	e169	5.0	24	.45	5.7	43	.88
21	e11	106	e6.3	12	182	6.5	264	1120	4190
22	5.4	28	.41	10	81	4.6	1060	3560	12000
23	9.4	580	3.6	5.4	264	.65	172	1070	611
24	7.9	192	1.8	51	862	279	86	143	34
25	4.9	34	.45	52	904	286	77	20	4.2
26	4.4	31	.36	7.2	39	.83	115	1330	1390
27	5.5	25	.68	21	295	51	83	936	279
28	7.9	69	2.3	166	1750	3480	57	34	5.2
29	4.6	26	.33	15	177	7.6	57	312	63
30	4.4	14	.16	8.0	56	1.2	49	24	3.2
31	4.3	8	.09	e6.5	24	.42	---	---	---
TOTAL	199.6	---	280.91	520.5	---	5050.12	2140.3	---	18598.90
YEAR	5228.6		37181.98						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-	SEDI-	SED.	
		CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
FEB					
05...	0318	261	5770	4070	82
JUL					
23...	1530	18	1500	73	98
AUG					
28...	1810	180	4280	2080	88
SEP					
22...	0200	1640	3820	16900	72

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT CAÑAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)
		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)
OCT							
06...	1630	240	12700	8230	24	37	52
12...	1415	370	9270	9260	35	45	57
FEB							
04...	2248	666	10200	18300	26	34	45
MAY							
14...	2049	170	10100	4640	43	56	72
JUN							
17...	1858	265	7420	5310	39	50	63
AUG							
28...	1600	1460	9720	38300	38	48	61
DATE							
OCT							
06...	65	80	87	96	99	100	100
12...	68	77	79	88	96	99	100
FEB							
04...	56	64	68	79	88	95	99
MAY							
14...	85	93	97	99	100	100	100
JUN							
17...	76	86	90	96	99	100	100
AUG							
28...	72	81	83	91	96	99	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059000 LAGO LOIZA AT DAMSITE NEAR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'49", long 66°01'00", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at pumpsite at damsite, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) south of Trujillo Alto plaza.

DRANAIGE AREA.--208 mi² (539 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1987 to current year. Prior to October 1994, published as Lago Loiza at Damsite.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lake is formed by Loiza Dam, a concrete structure completed in 1954. Useable capacity of impoundment is 30,000 acre-ft (37.0 hm³). Out flow from lake is controlled by five slide gates in powerplant and pump intake structure, four sluiceways, and concrete spillway with eight radial gates. Lake is used for municipal water supply and intermittent power generation. Gage-height satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 147.42 ft (44.93 m), Sept. 18, 1989; minimum elevation, 108.52 ft (33.08 m), July 18, 1994.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation 136.59 ft (41.63 m), Oct. 13; minimum elevation, 124.12 ft (37.83 m), Sept. 22.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents in acre-feet
98.4	5,000	128.6	18,000
111.5	8,900	137.8	26,000
120.4	13,000	147.6	35,000

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	134.70	134.21	134.75	130.82	133.04	133.83	134.94	134.08	134.70	127.64	131.54	132.23
2	134.41	134.20	134.70	130.76	132.81	133.67	134.67	133.92	134.61	127.37	131.33	131.60
3	134.82	134.16	134.59	130.71	132.62	133.54	A	133.80	134.51	127.14	131.08	132.34
4	134.89	134.13	134.46	130.80	133.35	133.43	134.53	133.75	126.68	127.54	130.81	132.13
5	134.86	134.12	134.35	130.95	134.78	133.96	134.52	133.68	126.62	127.71	130.54	132.41
6	134.80	134.09	134.23	134.52	134.81	133.92	134.49	133.54	126.73	127.81	A	131.66
7	134.71	134.02	134.10	134.86	134.94	134.69	134.59	133.42	126.60	127.54	132.34	132.62
8	134.79	133.94	133.96	134.77	134.98	134.97	134.61	134.12	126.48	127.28	132.54	132.52
9	134.79	133.90	133.81	134.51	134.97	134.80	134.53	134.50	126.50	127.04	132.90	132.27
10	134.71	134.32	133.67	134.51	134.89	134.82	134.43	134.53	126.37	126.82	132.72	132.05
11	134.54	134.52	133.51	134.80	134.65	134.80	134.34	134.41	126.17	126.54	132.80	132.27
12	134.57	134.50	133.36	134.72	134.70	134.77	134.84	134.22	126.26	126.23	132.72	132.47
13	136.34	134.48	133.20	134.36	134.69	134.70	134.75	134.07	126.76	125.91	132.58	132.04
14	134.64	134.38	133.07	134.61	134.55	134.72	134.71	134.52	126.63	125.59	132.38	132.55
15	134.55	134.86	132.91	134.75	134.92	134.73	134.66	134.67	126.39	125.31	132.19	132.79
16	134.93	134.27	132.79	134.83	134.79	134.68	134.84	134.62	126.17	125.62	132.00	132.41
17	134.10	134.27	132.82	134.88	134.87	134.60	134.84	134.63	128.66	125.87	132.91	131.78
18	134.64	134.28	132.76	134.90	134.86	134.50	135.03	134.51	128.84	126.51	132.60	132.18
19	134.47	134.23	132.66	134.84	134.81	134.40	134.79	134.36	128.85	127.06	132.58	131.91
20	134.77	134.21	132.51	134.74	134.76	134.45	134.73	134.23	128.70	130.19	132.85	132.29
21	134.46	134.18	132.49	134.69	134.72	134.82	134.79	134.12	128.89	131.49	132.42	125.52
22	134.51	134.40	132.39	134.60	134.62	134.91	134.90	133.92	129.21	131.51	132.39	130.16
23	134.48	134.62	132.36	134.45	134.52	134.90	134.87	133.73	129.14	131.62	132.53	131.84
24	134.45	134.64	132.31	134.31	134.42	134.82	134.79	133.58	129.16	131.93	132.34	132.69
25	134.39	134.63	132.14	134.18	134.29	134.81	134.73	133.38	129.02	131.94	132.81	132.85
26	134.31	134.20	131.96	134.04	134.20	134.79	134.66	133.45	128.89	131.79	132.89	132.75
27	134.19	134.59	131.76	133.88	134.08	134.86	134.59	134.34	128.65	131.89	132.13	132.48
28	134.16	134.64	131.56	133.71	133.97	134.87	134.51	134.31	128.45	132.12	131.98	132.37
29	134.17	134.66	A	133.60	---	134.87	134.39	134.26	128.21	132.12	132.37	131.97
30	134.18	134.72	131.13	133.46	---	134.92	134.24	134.91	127.94	131.96	132.78	132.52
31	134.17	---	130.95	133.25	---	134.81	---	134.70	---	131.76	132.43	---
MAX	136.34	134.86	---	134.90	134.98	134.97	---	134.91	134.70	132.12	---	132.85
MIN	134.10	133.90	---	130.71	132.62	133.43	---	133.38	126.17	125.31	---	125.52

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'33", long 66°00'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank of Highway 175, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) downstream of Lago Loiza Dam.

DRAINAGE AREA.--209 mi² (541 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1986 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 32 ft (10 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Flow regulated by Lago Loiza Dam. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.5	7.8	42	e5.1	3.5	4.9	9.2	e5.8	11	1.3	1.4	238
2	833	8.0	44	e5.8	3.6	4.8	121	e5.5	5.3	1.3	1.3	377
3	4.0	8.4	45	e7.1	3.4	4.8	e43	e5.2	5.6	1.9	1.2	137
4	3.5	8.2	45	e8.2	8.9	4.9	e52	e5.1	e3330	4.1	1.8	443
5	3.5	8.1	46	e9.6	2460	7.3	7.8	e5.6	43	2.8	3.0	1.2
6	3.4	8.0	46	e1070	184	5.5	7.7	e5.4	5.8	4.8	2.1	716
7	3.3	7.6	46	e2120	18	3230	9.1	e5.1	3.9	1.9	4.2	11
8	5.1	7.8	46	526	613	426	8.5	e5.5	4.4	2.1	188	1150
9	3.7	7.8	45	448	589	105	7.8	e5.2	6.5	3.0	1.6	564
10	3.5	1890	45	435	89	6.9	7.7	e5.1	5.9	1.6	162	412
11	141	39	45	233	87	7.1	7.5	e5.0	3.4	1.4	38	1.2
12	284	39	44	153	10	7.0	11	e5.0	3.3	1.3	1.7	1.4
13	288	38	44	339	6.7	6.6	41	e4.8	2.8	1.3	.99	255
14	33500	38	42	120	218	6.3	7.5	e21	2.8	1.6	.54	178
15	747	39	39	22	109	6.0	7.0	6.6	1.6	2.0	.92	933
16	369	187	41	14	63	6.0	15	5.1	1.2	4.5	1.1	600
17	870	30	45	13	4.9	6.1	65	13	1.2	3.5	1.1	451
18	135	7.7	e42	15	4.7	5.8	8.2	5.7	e3.2	2.7	367	1.9
19	160	7.4	e29	14	4.6	5.5	e76	5.2	e1.3	2.3	.86	440
20	23	7.4	e19	12	4.3	285	110	5.2	1.1	5.3	1.0	1.2
21	127	7.6	e12	13	3.9	85	92	7.7	1.4	6.1	588	10700
22	49	7.2	e8.7	12	3.7	4.2	50	5.3	1.6	2.3	967	65900
23	50	6.7	e9.5	12	3.9	4.2	6.3	5.7	1.7	2.4	159	2500
24	52	6.1	e9.0	13	4.3	4.2	5.7	5.1	1.2	4.0	5380	1070
25	52	6.2	e9.0	12	4.5	4.1	5.2	5.0	1.2	3.7	8260	853
26	52	848	e9.0	11	4.8	4.0	4.7	5.3	1.2	3.7	1530	753
27	52	70	e9.3	3.7	4.7	4.1	4.6	5.3	1.2	4.0	998	768
28	31	41	e8.5	3.4	4.8	4.4	4.8	5.7	1.2	4.0	850	866
29	9.1	43	e8.5	3.5	---	313	e5.1	5.3	1.2	1.8	488	e670
30	8.8	42	e8.0	3.4	---	290	e5.3	473	1.3	1.7	.92	174
31	8.1	---	e4.4	3.4	---	304	---	345	---	1.5	120	---
TOTAL	37878.5	3472.0	935.9	5660.2	4519.2	5162.7	805.7	998.5	3456.5	85.9	20120.73	91165.9
MEAN	1222	116	30.2	183	161	167	26.9	32.2	115	2.77	649	3039
MAX	33500	1890	46	2120	2460	3230	121	473	3330	6.1	8260	65900
MIN	3.3	6.1	4.4	3.4	3.4	4.0	4.6	4.8	1.1	1.3	.54	1.2
AC-FT	75130	6890	1860	11230	8960	10240	1600	1980	6860	170	39910	180800
CFSM	5.85	.55	.14	.87	.77	.80	.13	.15	.55	.01	3.11	14.5
IN.	6.74	.62	.17	1.01	.80	.92	.14	.18	.62	.02	3.58	16.23

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	313	461	312	154	76.8	55.0	29.1	80.8	166	147	236	919
MAX	1222	2732	2603	733	242	299	112	367	784	672	718	4255
(WY)	1998	1988	1988	1992	1989	1989	1987	1992	1987	1993	1988	1996
MIN	44.7	37.6	17.2	2.49	4.52	5.19	1.20	1.03	1.96	1.62	2.21	29.7
(WY)	1992	1996	1994	1995	1990	1997	1995	1995	1994	1994	1994	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1987 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	50355.9	174261.73	
ANNUAL MEAN	138	477	247
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			652
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			37.8
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	33500	Oct 14	65900
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.8	Jul 15	.54
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.3	Jun 29	1.2
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			196000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			47.01
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	99880		345600
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.66		2.28
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	8.96		31.02
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	47		479
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.2		7.7
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.1		1.6

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water year 1987 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: December 1986 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- Automatic sediment sampler, since 1987.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 4,290 mg/L September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 1,500,000 tons (1,360,000 tonnes) September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, <0.01 tons (<0.01 tonne) several years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,350 mg/L September 22, 1998; minimum daily mean, 7 mg/L October 9-10, 1997.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 1,030,000 tons (935,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; minimum daily mean, 0.03 ton (0.02 tonne) June 20, 1998.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	7.5	28	.56	7.8	101	2.1	42	137	15
2	833	195	1220	8.0	99	2.1	44	150	18
3	4.0	71	.78	8.4	96	2.2	45	160	19
4	3.5	49	.46	8.2	94	2.1	45	156	19
5	3.5	31	.29	8.1	92	2.0	46	150	18
6	3.4	19	.17	8.0	90	1.9	46	144	18
7	3.3	12	.11	7.6	88	1.8	46	139	17
8	5.1	8	.11	7.8	85	1.8	46	134	16
9	3.7	7	.07	7.8	83	1.8	45	129	16
10	3.5	7	.06	1890	128	936	45	124	15
11	141	55	167	39	170	18	45	120	14
12	284	172	482	39	191	20	44	115	14
13	288	126	814	38	215	22	44	111	13
14	33500	736	106000	38	222	23	42	107	12
15	747	572	1530	39	159	17	39	103	11
16	369	334	397	187	161	107	41	99	11
17	870	296	949	30	154	12	45	95	12
18	135	227	94	7.7	152	3.2	e42	92	e10
19	160	190	111	7.4	151	3.0	e29	91	e7.2
20	23	221	14	7.4	150	3.0	e19	91	e4.8
21	127	189	87	7.6	149	3.1	e12	90	e3.0
22	49	179	24	7.2	148	2.9	e8.7	90	e2.2
23	50	127	17	6.7	147	2.6	e9.5	89	e2.3
24	52	124	17	6.1	143	2.4	e9.0	89	e2.2
25	52	120	17	6.2	125	2.1	e9.0	88	e2.2
26	52	117	16	848	95	221	e9.0	88	e2.1
27	52	114	16	70	97	16	e9.3	87	e2.2
28	31	111	9.3	41	106	12	e8.5	87	e2.0
29	9.1	109	2.7	43	116	13	e8.5	86	e2.0
30	8.8	106	2.5	42	126	14	e8.0	85	e1.8
31	8.1	104	2.3	---	---	---	e4.4	85	e1.0
TOTAL	37878.5	---	111991.41	3472.0	---	1471.1	935.9	---	303.0

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	e5.1	84	e1.2	3.5	71	.67	4.9	28	.37
2	e5.8	84	e1.3	3.6	68	.66	4.8	25	.33
3	e7.1	83	e1.6	3.4	64	.58	4.8	24	.32
4	e8.2	83	e1.8	8.9	67	3.3	4.9	30	.39
5	e9.6	82	e2.1	2460	149	917	7.3	38	.78
6	e1070	69	e275	184	162	139	5.5	49	.72
7	e2120	229	e1550	18	128	6.1	3230	173	2830
8	526	246	395	613	151	593	426	228	716
9	448	228	287	589	195	486	105	556	198
10	435	174	224	89	193	50	6.9	411	7.6
11	233	156	114	87	126	47	7.1	340	6.5
12	153	140	71	10	106	2.9	7.0	287	5.4
13	339	142	269	6.7	97	1.8	6.6	242	4.3
14	120	139	77	218	103	112	6.3	204	3.5
15	22	174	10	109	121	47	6.0	173	2.8
16	14	159	6.1	63	96	20	6.0	146	2.4
17	13	152	5.4	4.9	92	1.2	6.1	123	2.0
18	15	144	5.9	4.7	83	1.0	5.8	104	1.6
19	14	137	5.3	4.6	75	.92	5.5	87	1.3
20	12	130	4.4	4.3	68	.79	285	127	294
21	13	124	4.3	3.9	62	.65	85	148	61
22	12	118	3.9	3.7	56	.56	4.2	176	2.0
23	12	112	3.6	3.9	50	.53	4.2	166	1.9
24	13	107	3.6	4.3	46	.53	4.2	154	1.7
25	12	101	3.4	4.5	41	.51	4.1	134	1.5
26	11	96	2.9	4.8	37	.48	4.0	116	1.3
27	3.7	92	.92	4.7	34	.43	4.1	100	1.1
28	3.4	87	.81	4.8	31	.40	4.4	86	1.0
29	3.5	83	.79	---	---	---	313	110	209
30	3.4	79	.71	---	---	---	290	120	137
31	3.4	75	.68	---	---	---	304	105	109
TOTAL	5660.2	---	3332.71	4519.2	---	2435.01	5162.7	---	4604.81

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	9.2	84	2.1	e5.8	19	e.29	11	84	2.6
2	121	98	47	e5.5	16	e.24	5.3	77	1.1
3	e43	85	e10	e5.2	14	e.20	5.6	73	1.1
4	e52	56	e17	e5.1	12	e.17	e3330	160	e5740
5	7.8	68	1.4	e5.6	10	e.16	43	71	8.4
6	7.7	84	1.7	e5.4	9	e.13	5.8	53	.84
7	9.1	103	2.6	e5.1	9	e.12	3.9	40	.42
8	8.5	123	2.8	e5.5	9	e.13	4.4	30	.36
9	7.8	117	2.5	e5.2	9	e.12	6.5	23	.40
10	7.7	107	2.2	e5.1	8	e.12	5.9	17	.27
11	7.5	97	2.0	e5.0	8	e.11	3.4	13	.12
12	11	89	2.7	e5.0	8	e.11	3.3	10	.09
13	41	94	11	e4.8	8	e.11	2.8	10	.08
14	7.5	95	1.9	e21	33	e6.2	2.8	10	.08
15	7.0	90	1.7	6.6	80	1.4	1.6	10	.04
16	15	86	3.5	5.1	73	1.0	1.2	10	.04
17	65	94	18	13	96	4.0	1.2	10	.04
18	8.2	87	1.9	5.7	133	2.1	e3.2	11	e.08
19	e76	95	e22	5.2	120	1.7	e1.3	11	e.04
20	110	88	34	5.2	109	1.5	1.1	11	.03
21	92	93	27	7.7	100	2.1	1.4	11	.04
22	50	91	13	5.3	95	1.4	1.6	11	.05
23	6.3	69	1.2	5.7	91	1.4	1.7	11	.05
24	5.7	53	.83	5.1	87	1.2	1.2	11	.04
25	5.2	45	.63	5.0	83	1.1	1.2	11	.04
26	4.7	39	.50	5.3	80	1.1	1.2	11	.04
27	4.6	34	.42	5.3	76	1.1	1.2	11	.04
28	4.8	29	.38	5.7	73	1.1	1.2	11	.04
29	e5.1	25	e.35	5.3	70	1.0	1.2	12	.04
30	e5.3	22	e.31	473	140	561	1.3	12	.04
31	---	---	---	345	88	117	---	---	---
TOTAL	805.7	---	232.62	998.5	---	709.41	3456.5	---	5756.55

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	1.3	12	.04	1.4	12	.04	238	97	103
2	1.3	12	.04	1.3	11	.04	377	161	325
3	1.9	12	.06	1.2	11	.04	137	63	51
4	4.1	12	.13	1.8	11	.05	443	61	134
5	2.8	12	.09	3.0	11	.09	1.2	49	.16
6	4.8	12	.16	2.1	10	.06	716	77	257
7	1.9	12	.06	4.2	10	.12	11	80	2.3
8	2.1	12	.07	188	28	57	1150	105	491
9	3.0	13	.10	1.6	58	.26	564	86	236
10	1.6	13	.05	162	80	109	412	86	165
11	1.4	13	.05	38	96	21	1.2	81	.27
12	1.3	13	.05	1.7	59	.26	1.4	63	.24
13	1.3	13	.05	.99	56	.15	255	58	111
14	1.6	13	.06	.54	54	.08	178	79	46
15	2.0	13	.07	.92	51	.13	933	83	368
16	4.5	13	.16	1.1	49	.14	600	91	244
17	3.5	13	.13	1.1	47	.14	451	70	181
18	2.7	13	.10	367	65	148	1.9	18	.09
19	2.3	14	.09	.86	54	.13	440	270	1430
20	5.3	14	.20	1.0	50	.14	1.2	77	.25
21	6.1	14	.23	588	72	183	10700	1830	138000
22	2.3	14	.09	967	431	3430	65900	3350	1030000
23	2.4	14	.09	159	69	163	2500	699	4670
24	4.0	14	.15	5380	239	7180	1070	653	1860
25	3.7	13	.13	8260	490	12100	853	610	1420
26	3.7	13	.13	1530	207	1520	753	570	1160
27	4.0	13	.14	998	93	354	768	533	1110
28	4.0	13	.14	850	98	289	866	498	1140
29	1.8	12	.06	488	71	152	e670	465	e815
30	1.7	12	.05	.92	49	.12	174	446	210
31	1.5	12	.05	120	57	133	---	---	---
TOTAL	85.9	---	3.02	20120.73	---	25840.99	91165.9	---	1184530.31
YEAR	174261.73		1341210.94						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
02...	1747	2170	843	492	99
02...	2032	1420	1020	3910	99
12...	1742	1730	890	4160	99
15...	1045	71	539	103	99
15...	1957	1660	515	2310	100
17...	2132	2400	454	2940	85
NOV					
10...	0907	4270	120	1380	92
JAN					
09...	2207	1720	228	1060	100
FEB					
05...	1708	1830	191	944	99
15...	1103	1750	204	964	100
MAR					
10...	0847	6.5	412	7.2	100
20...	2258	1720	351	1630	97
AUG					
25...	1458	3380	546	4980	98
26...	1028	3210	372	3220	99
SEP					
02...	1510	233	1120	704	100
19...	0746	3510	1580	15000	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- MENT, CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- MENT, CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)
OCT							
14...	0207	134000	1190	430000	63	76	88
15...	1544	1780	957	4600	17	22	32
FEB							
05...	0315	1620	897	3900	55	67	77
MAR							
07...	2148	3020	851	6940	62	74	85
SEP							
21...	2031	10600	2480	71000	73	88	95

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN 1.00 MM (70335)
OCT							
14...	90	93	93	95	97	99	100
15...	49	76	89	96	97	99	100
FEB							
05...	84	91	94	97	99	100	100
MAR							
07...	91	95	95	97	97	98	98
SEP							
21...	96	98	99	100	100	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059100 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW TRUJILLO ALTO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'35", long 66°00'15", 100 ft (30 m) downstream of Highway 181 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northwest of Trujillo Alto plaza, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northeast of Lago Loiza Reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--213 mi² (552 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1981 to current year.

REMARKS: Flow controlled by Lago Loiza reservoir.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
NOV 05...	1030	17	318	7.6	27.5	49	7.5	97	<10	K80 420
MAR 10...	1130	9.3	250	7.0	26.0	150	5.4	66	15	K840 2100
JUN 02...	1115	9.5	373	7.2	31.0	2.0	7.9	106	<10	560 30
SEP 08...	0835	E4340	315	6.8	28.0	51	5.5	70	<10	5700 2200

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 05...	70	17	6.4	7.2	.4	2.2	115	<.5	8.2	11
MAR 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	94	--	--	--
JUN 02...	120	30	11	27	1	2.6	131	--	16	27
SEP 08...	100	26	9.9	20	.8	2.8	130	<1.0	13	19

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 05...	<.10	17	134	6.15	52	.926	.014	.940	.040	.37
MAR 10...	--	--	--	--	116	1.16	.039	1.20	.190	.59
JUN 02...	.14	28	220	5.65	6	.326	.014	.340	.030	.33
SEP 08...	.13	24	192	E2250	84	.873	.017	.890	.080	.61

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 05...	.41	1.4	6.0	.110	<1	<100	40	<1	<1	<10
MAR 10...	.78	2.0	8.8	.240	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 02...	.36	.70	3.1	.060	1	<100	50	<1	<1	<10
SEP 08...	.69	1.6	7.0	.180	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50061800 RIO CANOVANAS NEAR CAMPO RICO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'08", long 65°53'21", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at upstream side of bridge, on paved secondary road, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of junction of Highways 185 and 186, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) south of Campo Rico, and 4.4 mi (7.1 km) south of Loíza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.84 mi² (25.48 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1967 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 225 ft (68 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	13	9.0	15	8.3	14	8.2	9.0	5.5	7.0	3.3	4.8	18
2	37	8.7	12	9.5	9.2	7.8	28	5.4	6.6	3.2	4.4	76
3	29	8.4	10	13	9.0	7.8	14	5.9	6.4	3.5	4.1	51
4	16	8.4	9.6	14	13	7.8	8.3	11	9.7	4.5	3.8	32
5	14	8.6	9.8	12	314	7.4	6.8	8.5	6.6	4.9	3.5	30
6	12	8.5	9.3	39	20	8.0	6.2	6.3	6.6	3.5	4.4	22
7	12	8.3	9.2	197	13	7.5	6.2	5.9	6.2	5.5	39	30
8	14	7.9	8.8	22	34	9.2	7.8	118	8.5	4.9	33	28
9	21	8.0	8.7	25	36	7.5	6.2	33	14	4.0	19	23
10	14	136	9.1	25	14	7.0	5.7	21	11	3.2	13	19
11	46	15	8.9	30	12	6.8	5.8	10	7.1	3.0	6.8	16
12	32	11	8.4	15	15	6.5	7.4	7.9	14	3.0	5.4	14
13	174	9.8	8.3	34	11	6.2	18	7.1	30	2.6	5.2	17
14	666	9.1	8.4	32	13	6.7	8.1	10	9.0	3.1	4.3	27
15	31	8.9	8.5	16	16	8.4	6.3	9.3	6.6	5.2	4.9	74
16	28	12	8.2	13	11	9.0	65	8.1	6.4	5.5	40	29
17	23	10	11	12	10	7.4	18	7.9	8.1	4.0	53	18
18	16	13	11	11	9.5	6.9	10	7.8	12	4.8	16	17
19	15	17	9.0	11	9.3	6.6	15	7.4	7.5	7.9	16	19
20	13	11	8.3	11	8.7	7.8	12	6.6	6.0	12	20	18
21	13	14	11	10	8.3	10	9.4	11	6.1	11	104	2060
22	12	12	9.7	9.8	7.7	8.8	8.3	7.2	9.1	5.3	41	1600
23	12	11	8.1	9.7	7.5	8.4	7.2	6.4	6.4	5.7	19	127
24	11	11	8.9	9.5	7.3	7.3	6.7	6.3	5.5	50	554	e70
25	10	9.7	7.9	9.3	7.5	7.1	6.9	6.4	4.9	13	536	e55
26	10	138	7.0	8.9	11	6.8	6.8	6.5	4.8	7.1	108	44
27	9.8	27	6.7	9.2	9.1	7.2	7.6	9.3	4.2	11	39	38
28	9.5	15	6.7	8.9	8.7	7.7	6.5	6.9	3.8	15	30	34
29	9.5	13	6.7	8.5	---	11	6.0	7.7	3.5	15	63	31
30	9.1	16	6.4	8.3	---	34	5.7	9.4	3.3	7.2	26	29
31	9.0	---	6.9	10	---	23	---	10	---	5.4	20	---
TOTAL	1340.9	595.3	277.5	651.9	658.8	281.8	334.9	389.7	240.9	237.3	1840.6	4666
MEAN	43.3	19.8	8.95	21.0	23.5	9.09	11.2	12.6	8.03	7.65	59.4	156
MAX	666	138	15	197	314	34	65	118	30	50	554	2060
MIN	9.0	7.9	6.4	8.3	7.3	6.2	5.7	5.4	3.3	2.6	3.5	14
AC-FT	2660	1180	550	1290	1310	559	664	773	478	471	3650	9260
CFSM	4.40	2.02	.91	2.14	2.39	.92	1.13	1.28	.82	.78	6.03	15.8
IN.	5.07	2.25	1.05	2.46	2.49	1.07	1.27	1.47	.91	.90	6.96	17.64

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1967 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978
MEAN	40.7	44.1	31.9	25.1	19.8	13.9	14.9	27.2	17.6	18.7	26.5	41.8
MAX	273	125	116	62.4	48.4	36.2	53.2	93.2	63.7	63.7	137	196
(WY)	1971	1985	1971	1969	1988	1969	1971	1969	1970	1979	1979	1996
MIN	6.74	6.66	5.82	6.66	4.04	3.54	4.36	4.28	2.80	3.72	5.69	5.20
(WY)	1968	1981	1968	1977	1977	1977	1994	1974	1974	1974	1991	1967

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1967 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	7266.6	11515.6		
ANNUAL MEAN	19.9	31.5		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN				27.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN				58.0
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	666	Oct 14	2060	Sep 21
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.8	Jun 22	2.6	Jul 13
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.0	Jun 28	3.4	Jul 8
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			17300	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			15.90	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			2.4	Jul 14
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	14410	22840		19650
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.02	3.21		2.76
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	27.47	43.53		37.45
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	30	34		43
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	13	9.4		12
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.7	5.5		5.2

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50061800 RIO CANOVANAS NEAR CAMPO RICO, PR--Continued

Figure 19. Northeastern river basins -- Río Herrera to Río Antón Ruíz basins.

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063440 QUEBRADA SONADORA NEAR EL VERDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'24", long 65°49'03", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, in Caribbean National Forest, at El Yunque, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) upstream from Río Espiritu Santo, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Highway 186, and about 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of El Verde.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.01 mi² (2.62 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 1,230 ft (375 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

CORRECTIONS.--The maximum discharge for the water year 1996 is 963.0 ft³/s (27.2 m³/s), Apr. 4, 1996, gage-height, 8.09 ft (2.46 m); The previously published figure was not the maximum. The maximum discharge for the period of record is 2,230 ft³/s (63.1 m³/s), Dec. 7, 1987, gage-height, 9.42 ft (2.87 m). The previously published figure in the report for 1997 was not the maximum for the period of record.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e2.2	4.1	e2.0	5.3	1.0	.34	3.9	1.6	1.7	e1.5	e1.8	e3.8
2	e15	1.4	1.5	3.9	.93	.33	11	1.4	1.4	e1.7	e1.8	e21
3	e2.6	1.2	1.3	24	.72	.33	3.0	3.3	1.2	e4.0	e2.1	e9.4
4	e2.0	2.2	1.3	17	12	.30	2.1	9.6	1.2	e6.8	e2.2	e7.0
5	e2.0	2.2	1.3	12	e16	.25	e1.8	2.1	1.1	e2.5	e2.1	e10
6	e1.6	2.6	1.2	62	e1.3	.61	e1.5	1.3	1.5	e1.8	e4.3	e12
7	e1.5	1.4	1.2	e90	e.52	e200	e1.8	1.2	1.2	e4.2	e17	e39
8	e1.7	1.1	1.1	e4.9	e1.1	e11	e3.1	9.6	1.5	e5.4	e9.0	e11
9	e2.1	18	1.1	e3.7	e3.2	e3.8	e1.9	2.2	e16	e9.2	e8.2	e8.6
10	e1.5	e20	1.1	e3.8	e.60	e1.8	e1.6	1.1	e4.0	e2.2	e3.1	e4.5
11	e4.3	e2.3	1.2	e2.1	e.42	e1.6	e1.4	1.0	e1.8	e2.1	e2.3	e3.5
12	e3.8	e1.4	1.1	e1.5	e1.4	e1.6	e3.4	.93	e39	e1.6	e2.9	e3.1
13	e10	e1.3	1.1	e4.4	e.42	e1.5	e6.0	7.2	e5.4	e1.7	e2.8	e14
14	e29	e1.2	1.1	e5.2	e.60	e2.1	e2.7	9.1	e2.4	e1.9	e1.7	e10
15	e3.8	e2.7	1.2	e1.9	e1.4	e3.0	e2.8	9.5	e1.8	e4.2	e3.1	e54
16	e2.3	e4.4	1.0	e1.4	e.42	e2.7	e50	4.4	e4.3	e4.6	e11	e8.0
17	e1.9	e3.8	1.8	e1.2	e.42	e2.1	e6.0	1.7	e2.1	e3.7	e17	e5.2
18	e1.5	e4.1	1.5	e1.2	e.42	e2.2	e6.6	1.2	e6.0	e3.7	e8.2	e6.0
19	e1.5	e4.2	1.2	e1.2	e.38	e1.5	e41	1.1	e2.1	e11	e24	e9.5
20	e1.3	e3.5	1.3	e1.1	e.38	19	e8.0	1.2	e1.6	e18	e12	e7.0
21	e1.4	e5.4	3.7	e1.0	e.38	4.6	e5.4	1.4	e2.7	e6.0	e32	e240
22	e1.3	e2.9	1.3	e1.0	e.38	3.1	3.8	1.0	e3.4	e2.3	e12	e160
23	e1.3	e1.8	1.0	e1.0	e.38	2.5	3.1	.95	e1.9	e10	e5.8	e15
24	e1.4	e2.7	.97	e1.0	e.34	1.7	2.6	1.1	e1.8	e27	e83	e8.0
25	e1.4	e1.5	.87	e1.0	e.39	2.5	2.5	1.8	e1.8	e4.2	e54	e6.0
26	e1.5	e21	.81	e1.0	.41	4.6	2.4	15	e1.6	e2.8	e17	e5.2
27	e1.3	e4.1	.83	e.88	.40	7.9	7.3	9.8	e1.6	e4.7	e12	e4.5
28	e1.1	e2.8	.82	e.88	.45	4.2	3.9	6.6	e1.9	e5.8	e13	e3.9
29	e1.0	e2.3	.69	e.80	---	3.4	2.1	17	e1.5	e2.9	e14	e3.6
30	e1.1	e3.0	.61	e.75	---	9.2	1.7	16	e1.4	e2.4	e5.0	e3.3
31	e1.3	---	.84	.80	---	4.5	---	3.7	---	e2.7	e4.4	---
TOTAL	105.7	130.6	38.04	257.91	46.76	304.26	194.4	145.08	116.9	162.6	388.8	696.1
MEAN	3.41	4.35	1.23	8.32	1.67	9.81	6.48	4.68	3.90	5.25	12.5	23.2
MAX	29	21	3.7	90	16	200	50	17	39	27	83	240
MIN	1.0	1.1	.61	.75	.34	.25	1.4	.93	1.1	1.5	1.7	3.1
AC-FT	210	259	75	512	93	603	386	288	232	323	771	1380
CFSM	3.38	4.31	1.21	8.24	1.65	9.72	6.42	4.63	3.86	5.19	12.4	23.0
IN.	3.89	4.81	1.40	9.50	1.72	11.21	7.16	5.34	4.31	5.99	14.32	25.64

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1983 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	5.42	9.32	7.46	7.02	5.88	5.01	4.66	7.38	5.80	6.37	7.03	7.93				
MAX	16.8	19.8	20.9	11.1	11.9	14.3	9.76	14.3	13.7	12.7	14.2	23.2				
(WY)	1986	1985	1988	1996	1988	1990	1987	1992	1987	1983	1988	1998				
MIN	.22	2.47	.92	3.42	1.56	1.53	.90	2.51	.98	2.33	.50	2.45				
(WY)	1993	1991	1990	1985	1992	1993	1997	1996	1985	1991	1993	1986				

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063440 QUEBRADA SONADORA NEAR EL VERDE, PR--Continued

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1998 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1983 - 1998	
ANNUAL TOTAL	1472.42	2587.15		
ANNUAL MEAN	4.03	7.09	6.55	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			9.32	1988
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			3.91	1994
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	46 Jan 22	240 Sep 21	346	Sep 10 1996
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.31 May 3	.25 Mar 5	.00	Aug 14 1993
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.32 Apr 30	.34 Feb 27	.01	Mar 31 1994
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		614 Sep 21	2230	Dec 7 1987
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		7.39 Sep 21	9.42	Dec 7 1987
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		.22 Mar 5	.00	Aug 13 1993
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	2920	5130	4750	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.99	7.02	6.49	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	54.23	95.29	88.14	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10	13	16	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.7	2.2	2.5	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.73	.88	.47	

e Estimated

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063800 RIO ESPIRITU SANTO NEAR RIO GRANDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'37", long 65°48'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on downstream side of bridge on Highway 966, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Jlménez, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km), southeast of Río Grande.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.62 mi² (22.33 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to April 1963 (annual low-flow and occasional measurements only), August 1966 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 40 ft (12 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	36	44	55	77	13	13	30	18	29	15	18	38
2	237	26	44	48	12	12	66	15	21	17	18	214
3	43	17	39	112	12	12	33	30	17	29	20	98
4	32	22	36	91	14	12	29	98	15	67	22	70
5	32	28	36	80	282	20	24	33	13	27	21	99
6	26	33	33	271	40	20	21	20	15	18	e43	114
7	25	25	30	468	15	1270	24	17	16	40	e172	393
8	28	18	28	79	33	e143	42	89	19	52	90	112
9	34	67	27	59	57	50	27	50	164	92	81	88
10	25	279	27	61	17	e23	22	19	51	22	34	50
11	71	37	27	36	12	e21	19	15	18	21	23	36
12	62	22	24	25	25	e21	42	14	390	16	29	31
13	174	21	24	71	12	e20	82	26	97	17	28	142
14	456	19	23	84	17	e29	37	119	24	19	17	101
15	45	58	23	30	25	e40	38	83	18	41	25	534
16	38	123	26	21	12	e36	677	56	43	46	102	88
17	31	106	40	18	12	28	82	30	21	37	166	53
18	25	115	44	18	12	29	90	17	60	37	82	60
19	25	118	37	18	11	20	558	18	23	99	232	e97
20	21	98	31	17	11	88	120	15	16	176	121	e70
21	22	152	79	16	11	33	48	40	25	65	323	e2380
22	21	76	37	16	11	23	39	24	34	23	144	e1680
23	21	51	31	16	11	22	29	24	19	79	59	e151
24	22	76	33	16	e9.7	22	28	21	18	274	840	80
25	22	42	30	16	e11	24	25	30	18	48	550	61
26	23	588	28	16	12	29	25	127	16	28	167	53
27	21	113	28	14	12	38	58	131	16	43	124	46
28	17	76	28	14	13	27	37	66	19	57	135	40
29	16	63	26	13	---	27	23	129	15	29	139	37
30	17	85	26	12	---	57	19	199	14	24	51	33
31	21	---	26	12	---	34	---	67	---	27	45	---
TOTAL	1689	2598	1026	1845	734.7	2243	2394	1640	1264	1585	3921	7049
MEAN	54.5	86.6	33.1	59.5	26.2	72.4	79.8	52.9	42.1	51.1	126	235
MAX	456	588	79	468	282	1270	677	199	390	274	840	2380
MIN	16	17	23	12	9.7	12	19	14	13	15	17	31
AC-FT	3350	5150	2040	3660	1460	4450	4750	3250	2510	3140	7780	13980
CFSM	6.32	10.0	3.84	6.90	3.04	8.39	9.26	6.14	4.89	5.93	14.7	27.3
IN.	7.29	11.21	4.43	7.96	3.17	9.68	10.33	7.08	5.45	6.84	16.92	30.42

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1966 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	59.6	85.7	71.0	55.2	50.4	39.6	44.3	65.7	45.7	52.1	62.4	64.9
MEAN	59.6	85.7	71.0	55.2	50.4	39.6	44.3	65.7	45.7	52.1	62.4	64.9
MAX	202	196	179	119	117	153	119	185	120	114	126	235
(WY)	1971	1985	1971	1969	1982	1990	1981	1979	1970	1983	1998	1998
MIN	12.3	29.1	16.8	18.5	10.8	9.53	6.27	14.9	10.0	11.1	18.5	17.7
(WY)	1969	1982	1994	1987	1983	1996	1984	1973	1975	1975	1994	1971

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1966 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	22521	27988.7		
ANNUAL MEAN	61.7	76.7	58.2	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			98.6	1979
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			21.6	1994
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	923	Aug 22	2380	Sep 21
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	11	Jun 9	9.7	Feb 24
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	12	Jun 6	11	Feb 19
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			13500	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			12.87	Sep 21
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	44670	55520	42140	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	7.16	8.90	6.75	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	97.19	120.79	91.69	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	114	130	123	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	34	30	26	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	17	15	10	

e Estimated

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063800 RIO ESPIRITU SANTO NEAR RIO GRANDE, PR--Continued

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063800 RIO ESPIRITU SANTO NEAR RIO GRANDE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1961-66, 1968 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 28...	1300	17	115	7.4	27.0	.40	7.3	92	<10	310	360
MAR 25...	0845	24	115	6.8	24.5	2.1	8.2	98	<10	4800	2700
JUN 09...	0910	17	89	6.7	26.0	2.0	8.0	98	<10	340	310
AUG 24...	1400	506	31	6.2	24.5	71	8.1	97	15	5800	K14000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 28...	39	8.6	4.3	8.4	.6	.73	40	<.5	1.8	10
MAR 25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	44	--	--	--
JUN 09...	27	5.9	3.0	7.0	.6	.43	33	--	1.7	8.5
AUG 24...	8	1.8	.92	3.2	.5	.46	82	<1.0	1.4	4.2

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 28...	<.10	22	80	3.61	<1	--	<.010	.060	.020	--
MAR 25...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<.010	.020	.020	.41
JUN 09...	<.10	18	64	3.01	3	--	<.010	.060	.010	--
AUG 24...	<.10	5.0	66	90.3	146	.060	.010	.070	.060	1.4

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 28...	<.20	--	--	.030	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
MAR 25...	.43	.43	1.9	.030	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 09...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	30	2	<1	<10
AUG 24...	1.5	1.6	6.9	.110	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50064200 RIO GRANDE NEAR EL VERDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'42", long 65°50'30", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank 250 ft (7.6 m) upstream side of bridge at Hwy 960, 0.05 mi (0.08 km) southwest of junction of Highways 956 and 960, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) west of El Verde, and 2.7 mi (4.3 km) south of Rio Grande.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.31 mi² (18.93 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1967 to December 1970, January 1972 to September 1982, August 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 131 ft (40 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17	e18	e18	e78	18	7.1	16	9.7	23	8.5	12	e30
2	120	e11	e14	e45	13	7.1	54	9.2	14	8.3	9.8	e143
3	37	e7.0	e13	e110	12	6.7	e18	11	12	12	9.1	e95
4	20	e9.3	e12	e90	19	6.5	e12	47	11	23	8.6	e61
5	16	e11	e12	e80	313	7.5	9.3	20	11	17	8.7	e61
6	13	e13	e11	e300	29	9.0	8.2	10	20	11	e22	e43
7	13	e9.1	e9.4	e470	15	212	8.9	9.2	18	41	e94	e60
8	13	e7.0	e8.2	e80	45	55	13	98	12	21	60	e58
9	19	e29	e7.6	e60	57	16	8.0	44	64	26	55	e45
10	12	e119	e6.4	e64	17	11	7.3	18	40	15	38	e36
11	25	e15	e6.0	e35	14	10	7.9	13	14	12	16	e28
12	33	e6.8	e5.5	e26	34	10	15	12	150	9.6	18	e25
13	146	e6.1	e5.4	e72	14	9.5	56	21	79	8.9	17	e59
14	455	e5.5	e5.5	e86	16	13	14	65	20	8.7	11	e72
15	46	13	e5.6	e30	24	19	19	30	14	24	14	219
16	48	33	e5.3	e21	12	17	361	36	17	25	47	60
17	34	31	e18	e19	11	14	49	24	18	16	113	35
18	21	50	e20	e19	10	10	31	15	39	19	43	e34
19	17	45	e17	e19	9.8	10	49	13	15	52	116	67
20	15	25	e14	e18	9.4	49	23	11	12	91	71	e49
21	12	66	e36	e17	9.9	28	16	20	18	48	221	1440
22	11	25	e17	e17	9.0	22	14	11	28	15	114	833
23	9.7	e17	e14	e17	8.7	15	13	9.7	13	32	43	119
24	8.7	e25	e15	17	7.2	9.8	11	11	11	201	563	79
25	e8.0	e14	e13	16	7.1	10	12	13	10	42	e492	66
26	e7.3	e275	e12	16	9.1	13	13	37	9.9	19	e144	62
27	e6.5	e37	e11	15	8.1	26	22	69	9.5	42	e71	50
28	e6.5	e24	e11	14	7.4	17	16	22	12	60	e58	44
29	e6.4	e20	e10	13	---	17	12	53	9.8	31	e90	41
30	e6.8	e28	e9.9	12	---	98	10	44	9.1	16	e43	37
31	e7.9	---	e9.8	12	---	45	---	52	---	18	e32	---
TOTAL	1210.8	994.8	372.6	1888	758.7	800.2	918.6	857.8	733.3	973.0	2654.2	4051
MEAN	39.1	33.2	12.0	60.9	27.1	25.8	30.6	27.7	24.4	31.4	85.6	135
MAX	455	275	36	470	313	212	361	98	150	201	563	1440
MIN	6.4	5.5	5.3	12	7.1	6.5	7.3	9.2	9.1	8.3	8.6	25
AC-FT	2400	1970	739	3740	1500	1590	1820	1700	1450	1930	5260	8040
CFSM	5.34	4.54	1.64	8.33	3.71	3.53	4.19	3.79	3.34	4.29	11.7	18.5
IN.	6.16	5.06	1.90	9.61	3.86	4.07	4.67	4.37	3.73	4.95	13.51	20.62

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1967 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	
MEAN	54.9	66.2	45.4	43.8	30.8	20.9	27.0	49.5	30.5	36.5	44.6	52.4											
MAX	392	172	140	151	76.4	54.4	119	203	86.5	109	90.0	153											
(WY)	1971	1970	1971	1969	1969	1978	1969	1968	1968	1969	1968	1975											
MIN	8.45	14.3	12.0	10.1	5.80	4.50	6.29	10.2	6.22	8.66	7.39	12.4											
(WY)	1969	1981	1998	1977	1977	1977	1995	1974	1975	1994	1991	1967											

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1967 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	10408.8	16213.0																					
ANNUAL MEAN	28.5	44.4								40.3													
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN										87.1		1969											
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN										17.3		1994											
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	455	Oct 14	1440	Sep 21	3470	May 21	1969																
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.6	May 5	5.3	Dec 16	2.2	Aug 15	1991																
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.0	Apr 30	5.7	Dec 10	2.5	Aug 10	1991																
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			22000	Sep 21	22000	Sep 21	1998																
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			19.30	Sep 21	19.30	Sep 21	1998																
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW					1.6	Mar 13	1977																
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	20650	32160	29190																				
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.90	6.08	5.51																				
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	52.97	82.51	74.90																				
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	57	79	78																				
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	16	17	17																				
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.8	8.6	6.6																				

e Estimated

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN
50064200 RIO GRANDE NEAR EL VERDE, PR--Continued

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'46", long 65°45'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 988, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) west of Sabana, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) downstream from Río de la Mina, and 3.2 mi (5.1 km) southeast of Mameyes.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.88 mi² (17.82 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1967 to December 1973, June 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 275 ft (84 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28	33	38	63	18	20	47	26	69	22	e24	39
2	e380	16	30	52	19	18	96	23	49	22	e25	129
3	e58	15	27	79	17	18	38	57	39	30	e32	59
4	e42	22	25	83	19	17	29	93	35	110	e30	44
5	e33	23	24	68	334	18	29	39	32	34	e31	55
6	e26	36	21	233	42	34	25	31	36	32	e70	65
7	e23	17	20	392	31	260	40	28	29	59	e166	284
8	76	42	18	77	48	64	50	113	40	69	104	105
9	68	116	18	62	49	23	26	50	106	88	103	84
10	34	270	18	83	29	18	23	31	48	38	47	49
11	192	35	18	42	29	16	24	27	32	29	33	39
12	85	25	16	29	34	15	65	26	332	26	38	39
13	264	24	15	63	26	15	64	56	113	23	35	139
14	490	22	15	47	38	69	34	177	51	28	28	69
15	77	47	14	25	34	32	29	108	42	59	28	225
16	58	107	14	22	26	21	377	67	71	47	78	70
17	45	84	24	21	27	22	81	45	39	35	97	49
18	66	107	21	19	25	23	110	36	e62	27	54	55
19	41	73	15	19	24	17	128	43	e45	75	65	63
20	32	61	21	19	23	96	126	42	34	82	54	58
21	28	87	45	18	23	35	67	40	41	37	151	1480
22	25	49	21	17	22	40	46	32	41	20	83	699
23	23	38	17	17	21	28	39	29	31	29	45	126
24	21	64	14	18	20	20	35	28	29	123	415	82
25	20	40	13	18	19	31	33	30	26	30	277	65
26	19	526	12	18	19	32	31	125	25	22	112	56
27	17	80	16	18	20	46	51	91	28	26	82	46
28	16	53	13	18	20	32	42	56	38	34	59	40
29	15	61	11	18	---	54	29	194	26	25	52	39
30	16	58	11	18	---	107	26	297	23	28	41	35
31	16	---	15	18	---	48	---	106	---	32	37	---
TOTAL	2334	2231	600	1694	1056	1289	1840	2146	1612	1341	2496	4387
MEAN	75.3	74.4	19.4	54.6	37.7	41.6	61.3	69.2	53.7	43.3	80.5	146
MAX	490	526	45	392	334	260	377	297	332	123	415	1480
MIN	15	15	11	17	17	15	23	23	23	20	24	35
AC-FT	4630	4430	1190	3360	2090	2560	3650	4260	3200	2660	4950	8700
CFSM	10.9	10.8	2.81	7.94	5.48	6.04	8.91	10.1	7.81	6.29	11.7	21.3
IN.	12.62	12.06	3.24	9.16	5.71	6.97	9.95	11.60	8.72	7.25	13.50	23.72

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1967 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	
MEAN	64.0	80.0	56.9	54.3	42.1	37.5	40.9	64.5	54.8	49.4	53.8	64.1											
MAX	240	191	164	105	68.0	79.7	83.1	147	112	93.4	81.4	166											
(WY)	1971	1985	1971	1969	1988	1990	1973	1970	1970	1969	1988	1989											
MIN	20.3	36.3	16.6	25.0	21.7	18.1	14.5	18.7	12.4	20.3	20.4	26.6											
(WY)	1969	1974	1990	1985	1968	1968	1984	1973	1985	1994	1994	1986											

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1967 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	17732	23026	
ANNUAL MEAN	48.6	63.1	55.8
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			78.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			33.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	526	Nov 26	1480
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	11	Dec 29	11
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	13	Dec 24	13
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			12600
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			11.03
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			10
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	35170	45670	40430
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	7.06	9.17	8.11
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	95.88	124.50	110.20
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	80	109	100
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	34	35	33
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	18	18	16

e Estimated

RIO MAMEYES BASIN
50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR--Continued

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1992 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1992 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler, since 1993.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 484 mg/L September 10, 1996; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 5,390 tons (4,890 tonnes) September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.03 tons (0.02 tonne) October 05, 1994.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 463 mg/L March 7, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days .

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 5,390 tons (4,890 tonnes) September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.05 tons (0.04 tonne) October 27-28, 1997.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	28	2	.16	33	5	1.2	38	70	7.2
2	e380	139	e412	16	6	.20	30	43	3.6
3	e58	17	e.38	15	7	.17	27	26	1.9
4	e42	6	e1.7	22	9	.44	25	20	1.4
5	e33	1	e.90	23	12	.43	24	17	1.1
6	e26	1	e.54	36	15	1.3	21	13	.78
7	e23	1	e.29	17	19	.24	20	11	.60
8	76	27	19	42	25	4.9	18	11	.53
9	68	52	7.9	116	48	29	18	11	.50
10	34	4	.39	270	226	523	18	10	.49
11	192	104	232	35	12	1.1	18	10	.49
12	85	62	14	25	4	.27	16	9	.38
13	264	80	223	24	1	.09	15	8	.35
14	490	57	257	22	1	.06	15	13	.54
15	77	3	.61	47	18	5.1	14	11	.42
16	58	2	.38	107	41	15	14	8	.29
17	45	3	.34	84	23	9.4	24	8	.49
18	66	30	8.5	107	22	24	21	7	.45
19	41	16	1.8	73	22	5.3	15	7	.16
20	32	13	1.1	61	35	7.8	21	7	1.1
21	28	7	.56	87	15	8.5	45	6	3.0
22	25	4	.28	49	9	1.2	21	18	1.0
23	23	2	.14	38	2	.24	17	23	1.1
24	21	2	.11	64	34	7.9	14	21	.82
25	20	2	.10	40	15	1.9	13	19	.70
26	19	1	.08	526	136	514	12	18	.58
27	17	1	.05	80	37	8.1	16	16	.69
28	16	1	.05	53	23	3.3	13	10	.35
29	15	1	.06	61	47	12	11	6	.19
30	16	2	.07	58	96	15	11	4	.12
31	16	2	.08	---	---	---	15	4	.18
TOTAL	2334	---	1183.57	2231	---	1201.14	600	---	31.50

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
		MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	
1	63	36	19	18	4	.18	20	8	.41	
2	52	26	3.4	19	6	.32	18	7	.34	
3	79	27	9.9	17	5	.23	18	6	.31	
4	83	28	9.6	19	8	5.4	17	6	.27	
5	68	29	4.9	334	233	508	18	6	.31	
6	233	296	270	42	12	1.5	34	8	1.4	
7	392	129	357	31	3	.24	260	463	2780	
8	77	47	10	48	14	5.2	64	25	5.8	
9	62	18	4.1	49	43	2.7	23	7	.43	
10	83	40	11	29	29	.71	18	4	.18	
11	42	19	1.6	29	20	.76	16	3	.14	
12	29	15	.70	34	14	1.1	15	4	.15	
13	63	12	7.4	26	10	.56	15	4	.17	
14	47	10	2.5	38	11	1.5	69	6	9.5	
15	25	8	.57	34	12	1.1	32	7	1.0	
16	22	7	.44	26	7	.52	21	4	.26	
17	21	6	.36	27	5	.34	22	2	.13	
18	19	5	.29	25	3	.20	23	2	.10	
19	19	5	.25	24	2	.14	17	1	.06	
20	19	4	.21	23	3	.18	96	6	16	
21	18	4	.19	23	4	.25	35	7	1.2	
22	17	4	.19	22	6	.33	40	7	1.8	
23	17	3	.15	21	8	.44	28	8	.67	
24	18	3	.15	20	11	.58	20	8	.32	
25	18	3	.14	19	11	.58	31	9	.90	
26	18	3	.13	19	10	.53	32	9	1.2	
27	18	2	.12	20	9	.49	46	10	2.2	
28	18	2	.11	20	8	.44	32	11	.92	
29	18	2	.10	---	---	---	54	21	5.0	
30	18	2	.10	---	---	---	107	23	26	
31	18	3	.13	---	---	---	48	13	1.9	
TOTAL	1694	---	714.73	1056	---	534.52	1289	---	2859.07	

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
		MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	
1	47	20	2.3	26	12	.86	69	46	4.9	
2	96	18	14	23	10	.61	49	21	2.2	
3	38	14	1.4	57	29	7.4	39	10	1.1	
4	29	11	.87	93	34	13	35	8	.75	
5	29	9	.70	39	12	1.3	32	8	.70	
6	25	7	.49	31	10	.86	36	8	.77	
7	40	15	4.3	28	9	.65	29	8	.63	
8	50	36	3.0	113	10	49	40	9	1.6	
9	26	24	.55	50	16	2.5	106	49	41	
10	23	15	.42	31	26	.81	48	21	2.9	
11	24	10	.47	27	40	.62	32	10	.86	
12	65	28	8.1	26	64	.56	332	162	370	
13	64	35	5.9	56	102	11	113	62	24	
14	34	7	.60	177	70	145	51	13	1.9	
15	29	6	.58	108	78	14	42	4	.51	
16	377	243	512	67	45	4.9	71	25	6.2	
17	81	34	8.0	45	26	1.8	39	15	1.6	
18	110	22	30	36	15	1.1	e62	13	4.1	
19	128	57	52	43	8	1.2	e45	12	1.8	
20	126	51	19	42	7	1.3	34	11	1.0	
21	67	21	4.1	40	3	.33	41	11	1.8	
22	46	8	.95	32	2	.21	41	10	1.5	
23	39	3	.29	29	5	.41	31	6	.51	
24	35	2	.15	28	12	.88	29	3	.22	
25	33	1	.10	30	11	.79	26	4	.28	
26	31	3	.28	125	15	27	25	6	.38	
27	51	11	1.8	91	22	16	28	8	.57	
28	42	12	1.4	56	30	4.1	38	8	1.4	
29	29	18	1.5	194	84	84	26	3	.20	
30	26	15	1.1	297	216	138	23	2	.10	
31	---	---	---	106	100	12	---	---	---	
TOTAL	1840	---	676.35	2146	---	542.19	1612	---	475.48	

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	22	1	.08	e24	17	e.37	39	14	1.7
2	22	1	.07	e25	22	e.46	129	27	25
3	30	4	.63	e32	26	e.85	59	8	1.5
4	110	28	34	e30	33	e.75	44	2	.26
5	34	23	1.0	e31	38	e.80	55	16	2.9
6	32	19	1.6	e70	44	e6.2	65	22	4.2
7	59	15	4.1	e166	43	e41	284	127	263
8	69	12	9.5	104	53	18	105	34	13
9	88	40	14	103	46	15	84	31	7.4
10	38	12	1.2	47	22	2.8	49	18	2.4
11	29	8	.65	33	18	1.7	39	14	1.5
12	26	6	.41	38	15	1.5	39	16	2.5
13	23	4	.26	35	13	1.2	139	52	33
14	28	7	.63	28	11	.79	69	35	4.7
15	59	31	7.3	28	9	.67	225	120	144
16	47	12	2.6	78	14	13	70	20	4.1
17	35	11	1.2	97	35	14	49	6	.80
18	27	11	.67	54	19	2.9	55	16	3.4
19	75	30	9.1	65	29	8.5	63	19	4.0
20	82	33	13	54	20	3.0	58	22	3.2
21	37	9	1.1	151	17	38	1480	309	5390
22	20	1	.07	83	29	8.8	699	180	580
23	29	5	1.3	45	18	2.2	126	53	18
24	123	53	24	415	128	312	82	32	7.2
25	30	13	1.0	277	44	56	65	23	4.0
26	22	8	.46	112	42	14	56	20	2.9
27	26	5	.33	82	24	7.1	46	17	1.9
28	34	8	.82	59	22	3.3	40	15	1.4
29	25	10	.54	52	20	2.5	39	13	1.3
30	28	12	.67	41	18	1.5	35	11	1.0
31	32	15	.90	37	13	1.4	---	---	---
TOTAL	1341	---	133.19	2496	---	580.29	4387	---	6530.26
YEAR	23026		15462.29						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
13...	2153	1840	722	3590	81
14...	0043	2050	288	1590	72
NOV					
26...	0420	4210	1080	12300	87
26...	0510	1750	357	1690	91
APR					
16...	1140	1320	972	3460	86
AUG					
17...	1418	340	106	97	96

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50066000 RIO MAMEYES AT MAMEYES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'27", long 65°45'50", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, at bridge on Highway 3, 3.1 mi (5.0 km), southwest from Luquillo, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) downstream from Quebrada Anón, and 2.9 mi (4.7 km) east from Escuela Juan González.

DRAINAGE AREA.--13.4 mi² (34.7 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1997 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 16.4 ft (5.0m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Discharges above 5,000 ft³/s (141.6 m³/s), are based on a rating curve extension and are rated poor. Low flow affected by water supply intake about 1,000 ft (305 m), upstream from station. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1											e27	53
2											24	44
3											28	30
4											52	39
5											36	23
6											29	19
7											30	19
8											29	18
9											26	57
10											119	29
11											39	16
12											32	19
13											37	67
14											25	170
15											25	223
16											57	52
17											64	35
18											71	63
19											32	37
20											26	29
21											24	45
22											591	95
23											74	79
24										e37	90	69
25										43	84	267
26										57	41	700
27										39	39	82
28										33	33	55
29										27	27	54
30										e62	25	45
31										e45	38	---
TOTAL										---	1874	2533
MEAN										---	60.5	84.4
MAX										---	591	700
MIN										---	24	16
AC-FT										---	3720	5020

e Estimated

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50066000 RIO MAMEYES AT MAMEYES, PR--Continued

RIO MAMEYES BASIN
50066000 RIO MAMEYES AT MAMEYES, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	29	33	42	58	26	20	54	35	204	25	29	49
2	560	20	33	37	28	20	131	31	97	25	23	205
3	60	17	29	64	24	19	46	67	71	39	21	94
4	45	23	26	64	27	19	32	131	60	198	19	62
5	34	27	25	57	557	66	30	50	54	30	19	82
6	29	38	23	380	55	66	27	35	59	e16	65	99
7	26	23	21	669	34	869	34	33	48	e52	190	560
8	100	43	20	106	51	161	72	172	59	85	146	207
9	97	140	19	73	79	50	29	80	144	174	149	159
10	29	476	19	94	30	36	25	40	88	33	63	74
11	443	48	20	50	26	30	25	33	49	23	34	55
12	114	29	18	35	34	29	67	30	500	16	36	47
13	568	28	16	73	25	27	108	43	200	14	37	224
14	1100	24	16	82	32	94	43	311	68	16	26	123
15	87	47	15	35	48	57	35	169	50	45	30	446
16	61	141	14	31	30	32	809	102	188	41	96	127
17	48	115	20	30	30	34	131	50	52	32	160	83
18	63	138	17	29	28	40	155	37	101	24	88	75
19	43	117	13	28	25	25	235	43	64	97	109	113
20	33	80	11	27	27	120	230	36	43	139	114	83
21	29	121	45	27	26	58	119	41	50	72	261	2660
22	27	53	17	27	24	50	71	30	58	32	148	1830
23	26	40	15	27	22	45	57	27	37	37	71	228
24	23	83	12	28	21	31	50	25	34	246	e500	126
25	21	41	9.5	31	19	44	47	26	33	62	e350	94
26	21	1000	8.1	28	19	37	45	164	32	37	205	85
27	19	122	9.6	28	19	59	66	138	34	39	155	70
28	17	65	8.2	29	20	51	56	61	48	49	93	59
29	16	63	7.7	28	---	106	41	615	33	35	98	56
30	17	66	13	27	---	143	35	1130	28	32	57	50
31	18	---	8.9	25	---	61	---	219	---	37	58	---
TOTAL	3803	3261	571.0	2327	1386	2499	2905	4004	2586	1802	3450	8225
MEAN	123	109	18.4	75.1	49.5	80.6	96.8	129	86.2	58.1	111	274
MAX	1100	1000	45	669	557	869	809	1130	500	246	500	2660
MIN	16	17	7.7	25	19	19	25	25	28	14	19	47
AC-FT	7540	6470	1130	4620	2750	4960	5760	7940	5130	3570	6840	16310

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1997 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1997	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1997	1998
MEAN	123	109	18.4	75.1	49.5	80.6	96.8	129	86.2	58.1	85.9	179
MAX	123	109	18.4	75.1	49.5	80.6	96.8	129	86.2	58.1	111	274
(WY)	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998
MIN	123	109	18.4	75.1	49.5	80.6	96.8	129	86.2	58.1	60.5	84.4
(WY)	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1997	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1997 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	36819.0	
ANNUAL MEAN	101	101
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN		101
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN		101
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2660	2660
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	7.7	7.7
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	9.3	9.3
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	18400	18400
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	14.18	14.18
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	73030	73080
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	180	170
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	44	43
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	19	20

e Estimated

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50066000 RIO MAMEYES AT MAMEYES, PR--Continued

RIO SABANA BASIN

50067000 RIO SABANA AT SABANA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'52", long 65°43'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank along Highway 988, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) north of junction of Highways 988 and 983 in Sabana, and 3.3 mi (5.3 km) south of Luquillo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.96 mi² (10.26 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1979 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (80 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Low-flow affected by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority Water Intake 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream, and purification plant 0.2 mi (0.32 km). Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e61	11	12	11	6.5	6.6	9.3	5.6	50	7.9	4.8	9.8
2	e328	7.2	11	12	6.8	6.0	13	5.5	26	8.3	4.2	47
3	e28	6.8	10	10	6.3	6.0	6.8	6.7	20	12	3.8	21
4	e17	12	9.6	17	13	5.6	5.3	12	17	77	3.7	12
5	e13	8.9	9.2	18	226	11	8.5	6.3	15	15	3.3	16
6	e10	11	8.4	120	16	16	6.1	5.2	17	9.6	6.5	13
7	e9.7	6.9	7.9	194	13	71	15	6.3	13	13	16	108
8	22	30	7.1	29	26	14	16	48	14	17	17	35
9	26	81	7.3	19	22	5.5	6.0	11	65	25	12	46
10	28	178	7.2	25	11	4.4	4.9	5.4	22	e11	6.1	18
11	56	18	7.1	16	9.8	4.1	6.7	4.6	13	e9.7	5.0	14
12	53	11	5.8	14	9.8	e4.2	19	4.9	99	e21	4.3	13
13	242	9.5	5.9	20	9.1	e4.2	22	6.7	58	e11	5.4	41
14	339	7.7	6.0	20	11	20	8.0	160	21	e8.4	5.5	26
15	37	14	5.4	12	10	9.8	6.1	67	17	e18	5.0	65
16	28	64	5.2	11	8.8	5.3	246	31	40	e11	5.4	26
17	23	26	6.9	10	9.9	8.4	27	12	17	e12	24	15
18	26	31	5.0	10	8.5	9.4	22	9.0	e24	e10	9.5	13
19	19	24	4.3	9.9	7.0	4.3	13	8.9	19	e25	7.0	20
20	16	17	4.2	9.6	6.9	22	27	8.4	14	e16	7.5	15
21	14	24	12	9.4	6.0	10	20	9.4	16	e12	24	472
22	13	14	6.6	8.3	5.8	6.2	9.4	9.4	15	e8.6	14	296
23	12	12	5.0	8.3	5.5	7.6	8.4	7.2	12	e8.7	7.1	25
24	11	38	3.8	8.4	e5.4	6.2	8.0	6.3	12	e24	244	18
25	10	15	3.4	8.4	e4.9	4.9	7.0	6.2	11	e9.3	128	16
26	9.5	421	3.0	8.0	e4.9	4.8	6.9	60	10	e6.8	28	14
27	9.0	36	3.6	7.6	5.3	7.8	9.0	29	9.9	e8.6	23	13
28	8.4	22	3.2	7.2	5.1	6.3	8.2	27	10	e8.6	16	12
29	7.8	17	3.0	6.8	---	49	6.0	136	8.4	6.2	22	12
30	7.6	16	2.8	7.0	---	20	5.5	401	8.7	5.3	12	9.1
31	7.1	---	3.7	6.7	---	11	---	53	---	5.3	11	---
TOTAL	1491.1	1190.0	195.6	673.6	480.3	371.6	576.1	1169.0	694.0	441.3	685.1	1460.9
MEAN	48.1	39.7	6.31	21.7	17.2	12.0	19.2	37.7	23.1	14.2	22.1	48.7
MAX	339	421	12	194	226	71	246	401	99	77	244	472
MIN	7.1	6.8	2.8	6.7	4.9	4.1	4.9	4.6	8.4	5.3	3.3	9.1
AC-FT	2960	2360	388	1340	953	737	1140	2320	1380	875	1380	2900
CFSM	12.1	10.0	1.59	5.49	4.33	3.03	4.85	9.52	5.84	3.59	5.58	12.3
IN.	14.01	11.18	1.84	6.33	4.51	3.49	5.41	10.98	6.52	4.15	6.44	13.72

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1980 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	23.8	32.9	24.1	15.9	13.2	11.4	11.7	31.6	20.6	16.6	18.1	25.2							
MAX	66.4	79.7	64.1	48.5	23.2	36.0	33.5	63.9	50.6	36.0	39.9	74.2							
(WY)	1986	1988	1982	1996	1997	1987	1990	1982	1987	1996	1995	1996							
MIN	6.48	8.15	3.92	6.12	2.94	2.71	2.20	4.65	3.64	5.84	3.09	7.23							
(WY)	1983	1981	1990	1986	1983	1994	1984	1994	1997	1986	1994	1987							

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1980 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	7427.5	9428.6		
ANNUAL MEAN	20.3	25.8	20.5	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			31.9	1996
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			7.85	1994
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	421	Nov 26	472	Sep 21
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.6	Jul 1	2.8	Dec 30
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.0	Jun 29	3.2	Dec 25
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			4580	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			15.86	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW				19.74
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	14730	18700	.86	Apr 17 1983
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	5.14	6.52	5.17	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	69.77	88.57	70.19	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	33	43	38	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.2	11	8.9	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.4	5.3	2.8	

e Estimated

RIO SABANA BASIN
5006700 RIO SABANA AT SABANA, PR--Continued

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50070500 RIO FAJARDO ABOVE FAJARDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'21", long 65°43'18", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, 4.1 mi (6.6 km) from Plaza de Naguabo, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) northeast from Escuela Sonadora, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southwest of Colonia Paraíso, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) north from Escuela Segunda Unidad Mariana.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.69 mi² (9.56 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Oct. 1, 1995 to Nov. 8, 1995 (estimated discharge). Nov. 9, 1995 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 328 ft (100 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12	12	22	45	10	10	19	19	32	18	14	31
2	90	10	20	36	10	9.9	18	18	26	19	13	67
3	12	9.9	18	42	9.2	10	16	22	24	20	13	35
4	12	12	17	41	18	9.9	15	24	23	37	12	30
5	12	14	16	40	63	9.9	18	17	23	20	12	33
6	14	17	15	88	17	14	16	15	25	19	e17	30
7	15	11	14	111	16	13	17	14	23	24	21	64
8	46	33	14	53	22	12	19	26	24	23	17	43
9	21	36	14	60	18	10	16	15	37	22	22	33
10	17	85	14	70	15	10	16	12	25	21	14	28
11	28	16	14	40	15	9.9	17	12	22	18	13	27
12	22	14	13	34	15	10	23	e11	75	17	13	27
13	91	12	13	49	14	10	21	15	40	16	14	40
14	115	12	14	37	14	18	18	23	30	20	14	31
15	23	14	13	28	14	14	18	e32	28	25	15	78
16	19	27	14	25	13	11	64	e26	34	21	20	34
17	16	26	19	23	13	10	26	e13	27	20	23	29
18	24	32	16	22	13	10	34	e12	e31	18	20	33
19	14	19	15	20	12	10	26	e12	23	24	24	38
20	12	16	e16	19	11	19	28	e23	22	20	24	31
21	11	19	e28	18	11	13	25	e35	26	18	37	e270
22	11	17	19	17	11	15	22	e21	22	17	29	139
23	10	16	22	16	11	13	22	21	20	18	25	55
24	9.9	25	19	15	10	12	22	20	20	42	128	46
25	9.9	23	19	14	10	13	21	20	20	19	93	42
26	9.6	144	19	13	10	15	21	47	19	17	e57	39
27	9.7	32	21	12	10	15	25	38	19	16	50	36
28	9.6	25	20	12	10	15	23	26	21	15	37	34
29	9.5	23	20	11	---	15	20	42	19	15	35	33
30	9.7	25	20	11	---	29	19	70	18	14	33	32
31	9.8	---	22	10	---	18	---	34	---	15	31	---
TOTAL	724.7	776.9	540	1032	415.2	403.6	665	735	798	628	890	1488
MEAN	23.4	25.9	17.4	33.3	14.8	13.0	22.2	23.7	26.6	20.3	28.7	49.6
MAX	115	144	28	111	63	29	64	70	75	42	128	270
MIN	9.5	9.9	13	10	9.2	9.9	15	11	18	14	12	27
AC-FT	1440	1540	1070	2050	824	801	1320	1460	1580	1250	1770	2950
CFSM	6.34	7.02	4.72	9.02	4.02	3.53	6.01	6.43	7.21	5.49	7.78	13.4
IN.	7.31	7.83	5.44	10.40	4.19	4.07	6.70	7.41	8.04	6.33	8.97	15.00

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1996 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007
MEAN	22.4	33.5	24.0	40.5	22.1	13.4	15.4	22.3	29.7	25.9	29.5	67.3
MAX	23.4	54.6	28.4	49.9	33.6	14.5	22.2	30.2	50.3	42.4	41.1	121
(WY)	1998	1997	1996	1996	1997	1997	1998	1996	1996	1996	1996	1996
MIN	20.4	20.1	17.4	33.3	14.8	12.6	10.1	12.9	12.2	15.1	18.7	31.9
(WY)	1997	1996	1998	1998	1998	1996	1997	1997	1997	1997	1997	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1996 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	7688.6	9096.4	
ANNUAL MEAN	21.1	24.9	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			28.8
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			37.5
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	430	Sep 26	23.9
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	7.0	Apr 21	1997
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	7.2	Apr 20	1997
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			7.0
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			7.2
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			7.0
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	15250	18040	1996
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	5.71	6.75	1997
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	77.51	91.70	1998
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	29	40	1999
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15	19	2000
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.4	11	2001

e Estimated

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50070500 RIO FAJARDO ABOVE FAJARDO, PR--Continued

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50070500 RIO FAJARDO ABOVE FAJARDO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1996 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1995 to current year .

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 1995.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,020 mg/L September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e5,320 tons (e4,803 tonnes) September 21, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 tons (0.01 tonnes) several years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,020 mg/L September 21, 1998; minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days .

SEDIMENT LOADS : Maximum daily mean, e5,320 tons (e4,803 tonnes) September 21, 1998; minimum daily mean .03 ton (.02 tonne) several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	12	1	.04	12	2	.05	22	1	.06
2	90	222	246	10	1	.03	20	2	.10
3	12	3	.09	9.9	1	.03	18	4	.20
4	12	3	.10	12	2	.07	17	4	.19
5	12	5	.15	14	3	.08	16	3	.14
6	14	5	.18	17	7	.16	15	2	.09
7	15	2	.09	11	3	.09	14	1	.05
8	46	61	59	33	23	7.7	14	1	.04
9	21	9	.57	36	18	3.7	14	1	.04
10	17	5	.25	85	102	92	14	1	.04
11	28	19	5.6	16	3	.13	14	2	.06
12	22	12	1.0	14	2	.07	13	2	.07
13	91	98	72	12	2	.07	13	2	.08
14	115	212	248	12	1	.04	14	3	.10
15	23	2	.15	14	2	.13	13	3	.10
16	19	2	.09	27	4	.74	14	2	.09
17	16	1	.05	26	10	1.0	19	2	.10
18	24	9	.77	32	19	3.4	16	1	.06
19	14	5	.19	19	9	.55	15	1	.05
20	12	1	.04	16	2	.06	e16	2	e.13
21	11	1	.03	19	1	.06	e28	11	e1.0
22	11	1	.04	17	1	.05	19	1	.06
23	10	3	.07	16	1	.05	22	4	.27
24	9.9	4	.11	25	4	.41	19	1	.06
25	9.9	3	.07	23	5	.62	19	1	.05
26	9.6	2	.04	144	106	77	19	1	.05
27	9.7	1	.03	32	1	.12	21	4	.24
28	9.6	1	.03	25	1	.07	20	3	.15
29	9.5	1	.03	23	1	.06	20	1	.06
30	9.7	2	.04	25	1	.42	20	2	.08
31	9.8	2	.05	---	---	---	22	3	.16
TOTAL	724.7	---	634.90	776.9	---	188.96	540	---	3.97

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50070500 RIO FAJARDO ABOVE FAJARDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	45	35	11	10	2	.06	10	2	.04
2	36	8	.96	10	3	.07	9.9	1	.03
3	42	9	1.6	9.2	8	.20	10	1	.03
4	41	8	1.2	18	72	108	9.9	1	.03
5	40	2	.18	63	115	72	9.9	1	.04
6	88	78	29	17	3	.12	14	4	.20
7	111	68	36	16	2	.10	13	2	.07
8	53	17	2.5	22	7	.86	12	2	.05
9	60	34	6.2	18	4	.24	10	2	.06
10	70	39	8.1	15	2	.06	10	2	.05
11	40	10	1.1	15	1	.05	9.9	2	.05
12	34	3	.29	15	2	.06	10	2	.05
13	49	16	2.7	14	2	.07	10	2	.05
14	37	3	.40	14	2	.09	18	5	.38
15	28	2	.11	14	1	.08	14	4	.18
16	25	1	.08	13	1	.04	11	1	.04
17	23	1	.09	13	2	.05	10	1	.03
18	22	4	.23	13	2	.06	10	1	.03
19	20	8	.41	12	1	.04	10	1	.03
20	19	5	.24	11	1	.04	19	7	.49
21	18	3	.14	11	2	.05	13	3	.10
22	17	2	.11	11	3	.08	15	4	.19
23	16	2	.09	11	3	.09	13	4	.12
24	15	3	.13	10	2	.05	12	2	.06
25	14	5	.19	10	1	.04	13	1	.04
26	13	5	.20	10	3	.08	15	1	.04
27	12	2	.08	10	5	.14	15	2	.11
28	12	1	.04	10	3	.08	15	2	.08
29	11	2	.05	---	---	---	15	2	.08
30	11	2	.06	---	---	---	29	15	2.5
31	10	3	.08	---	---	---	18	4	.22
TOTAL	1032	---	103.56	415.2	---	182.90	403.6	---	5.47
	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	19	4	.18	19	1	.05	32	15	1.5
2	18	4	.18	18	1	.05	26	19	1.3
3	16	4	.19	22	4	.28	24	12	.79
4	15	3	.11	24	9	.64	23	3	.20
5	18	2	.21	17	4	.18	23	1	.06
6	16	2	.09	15	1	.04	25	1	.07
7	17	5	.34	14	1	.04	23	1	.06
8	19	16	.86	26	13	2.7	24	1	.06
9	16	4	.17	15	4	.16	37	13	2.7
10	16	1	.05	12	3	.09	25	3	.23
11	17	1	.05	12	2	.06	22	2	.12
12	23	8	.58	e11	2	e.07	75	162	99
13	21	3	.17	15	5	.37	40	13	2.0
14	18	1	.06	23	15	2.5	30	3	.24
15	18	1	.07	e32	29	e8.3	28	3	.22
16	64	53	13	e26	10	e1.1	34	5	.48
17	26	5	.35	e13	2	e.07	27	1	.08
18	34	16	2.3	e12	1	e.05	e31	1	e.81
19	26	6	.40	e12	4	e.13	23	1	.06
20	28	6	.54	e23	14	e1.9	22	1	.06
21	25	3	.22	e35	17	e1.7	26	4	.34
22	22	2	.14	e21	7	e.39	22	2	.14
23	22	2	.10	21	4	.24	20	1	.07
24	22	1	.06	20	3	.15	20	1	.05
25	21	1	.08	20	2	.11	20	1	.05
26	21	2	.10	47	44	9.1	19	1	.05
27	25	4	.24	38	13	3.0	19	1	.05
28	23	2	.12	26	3	.24	21	1	.06
29	20	1	.06	42	22	6.2	19	1	.05
30	19	1	.05	70	59	16	18	1	.05
31	---	---	---	34	11	1.0	---	---	---
TOTAL	665	---	21.07	735	---	56.91	798	---	110.95

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50070500 RIO FAJARDO ABOVE FAJARDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	18	1	.05	14	2	.06	31	9	.80
2	19	2	.11	13	1	.04	67	45	11
3	20	4	.20	13	1	.04	35	11	1.1
4	37	17	2.9	12	1	.03	30	4	.34
5	20	4	.22	12	1	.03	33	5	.89
6	19	2	.11	e17	4	e.19	30	7	.65
7	24	8	.58	21	11	1.1	64	62	23
8	23	7	.43	17	3	.15	43	25	3.8
9	22	2	.30	22	2	.14	33	10	.93
10	21	6	.34	14	2	.07	28	5	.41
11	18	4	.17	13	1	.05	27	4	.26
12	17	2	.08	13	1	.04	27	7	.50
13	16	1	.05	14	1	.04	40	16	2.3
14	20	3	.24	14	1	.04	31	6	.51
15	25	8	.55	15	1	.04	78	50	28
16	21	4	.28	20	2	.27	34	14	1.3
17	20	4	.23	23	6	.45	29	11	.86
18	18	2	.11	20	6	.31	33	12	1.2
19	24	1	.09	24	9	.77	38	18	2.1
20	20	2	.13	24	6	.41	31	7	.60
21	18	2	.12	37	18	2.5	e270	1020	e5320
22	17	2	.09	29	5	.38	139	139	89
23	18	6	.30	25	2	.14	55	6	.85
24	42	23	4.2	128	142	107	46	4	.46
25	19	12	.61	93	28	22	42	3	.34
26	17	10	.46	e57	9	e1.3	39	3	.32
27	16	6	.27	50	8	1.1	36	3	.29
28	15	1	.05	37	7	.70	34	3	.28
29	15	1	.04	35	7	.70	33	3	.27
30	14	2	.06	33	8	.68	32	3	.26
31	15	2	.08	31	8	.67	---	---	---
TOTAL	628	---	13.45	890	---	141.44	1488	---	5492.62
YEAR	9096.4		6956.20						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
16...	0101	515	949	1320	66
NOV					
10...	0315	190	258	132	90
26...	0434	347	424	397	85
26...	1330	164	68	30	74
JAN					
07...	0129	395	618	659	90
07...	0700	127	25	8.6	92
FEB					
05...	0044	224	950	575	82
MAY					
29...	2315	162	185	81	91
SEP					
15...	1315	190	322	165	92

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50070500 RIO FAJARDO ABOVE FAJARDO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)	
FEB 04...	2359	876	4270	10100	20	25	36	
DATE		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70335)
FEB 04...	46	59	67	88	97	98	99	

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1982 to September 1986 and October 1995 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Automatic sediment sampler since October 1983.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 2,210 mg/L October 6, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 22,100 tons (20,000 tonnes) October 6, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 tons (0.01 tonnes) May 06, 1996.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 354 mg/L November 10, 1997; minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e2,110 tons (e1,910 tonnes) September 21, 1998; minimum daily 0.04 tons (0.03 tonnes) February 26 and March 4, 1998.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)
OCT 27...	1000	31	127	7.3	27.0	.57	7.5	93	<10	210
MAR 30...	0915	22	117	6.6	24.0	3.0	8.8	106	<10	K1800
JUN 03...	0930	37	104	6.9	26.0	2.1	8.0	99	<10	40
AUG 25...	1010	278	60	6.2	24.5	21	8.0	96	<10	2400

DATE	STREP-TOCOCCHI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)
OCT 27...	860	34	7.5	3.7	12	.9	1.1	39	<.5	3.3
MAR 30...	40	--	--	--	--	--	--	44	--	--
JUN 03...	70	27	5.8	3.0	9.5	.8	.95	34	--	3.1
AUG 25...	4900	14	3.0	1.5	5.7	.7	1.3	13	<1.0	2.7

DATE	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 27...	13	<.10	25	89	7.46	<1	<.010	.080	<.010	--
MAR 30...	--	--	--	--	--	<1	<.010	.180	.020	<.02
JUN 03...	11	<.10	24	78	7.68	3	<.010	.170	<.010	--
AUG 25...	7.5	<.10	12	41	31.0	18	<.010	.230	.060	.35

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 27...	.33	.41	1.8	.040	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
MAR 30...	<.20	.33	1.5	<.020	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 03...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
AUG 25...	.41	.64	2.8	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE) (01045)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB) (01051)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN) (01055)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG) (71900)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS SE) (01147)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG) (01077)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN) (01092)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN) (00720)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L) (32730)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L) (38260)
OCT 27...	220	<1	12	<.10	<1	<1	<10	<.010	3	.04
MAR 30...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 03...	170	<1	10	<.10	<1	<1	<10	<.010	<1	<.02
AUG 25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	13	7	.24	27	17	1.2	109	6	1.8
2	575	228	1020	21	16	.92	91	6	1.5
3	37	13	1.6	18	15	.74	88	6	1.5
4	22	4	.22	24	15	1.0	82	7	1.5
5	15	8	.33	32	16	1.4	74	7	1.4
6	14	12	.44	43	21	2.5	69	7	1.3
7	13	15	.54	23	17	1.0	66	7	1.3
8	152	64	80	199	75	103	63	7	1.2
9	58	26	4.6	515	128	214	62	7	1.2
10	18	18	.85	868	354	1800	59	8	1.2
11	71	31	21	50	22	3.2	56	8	1.2
12	66	28	9.1	29	11	.92	50	8	1.1
13	688	173	738	20	6	.32	49	8	1.1
14	1250	189	1660	16	6	.25	49	8	1.1
15	236	5	3.2	23	17	1.9	49	9	1.1
16	144	5	1.9	144	49	35	45	9	2.0
17	91	3	.82	95	20	8.9	75	9	5.3
18	147	29	17	163	35	52	50	9	2.4
19	71	33	6.7	58	17	4.3	45	10	2.0
20	49	9	1.2	23	6	.35	42	10	1.8
21	42	11	1.2	26	8	.62	111	10	12
22	38	21	2.1	21	5	.27	69	10	4.5
23	37	19	1.9	17	6	.26	67	10	4.8
24	32	16	1.4	65	25	6.1	54	11	2.8
25	30	15	1.2	19	16	.86	43	11	1.8
26	30	15	1.2	1700	155	737	41	11	1.7
27	27	15	1.1	349	54	59	47	11	2.2
28	22	16	.96	171	10	4.7	41	12	1.6
29	22	17	.97	126	6	2.0	35	12	1.2
30	21	17	.96	156	12	6.0	33	12	1.1
31	20	18	.95	---	---	---	34	13	1.2
TOTAL	4051	---	3581.68	5041	---	3049.71	1848	---	67.9

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	197	58	99	12	9	.29	15	3	.11
2	42	30	5.3	14	12	.44	14	4	.14
3	50	26	6.9	12	8	.26	13	2	.08
4	37	20	2.4	24	6	3.5	13	1	.04
5	35	11	1.2	707	289	1040	12	1	.05
6	521	134	372	68	9	2.0	47	24	4.5
7	775	223	671	39	3	.32	341	122	247
8	97	21	6.8	208	38	93	41	6	.84
9	214	59	65	152	67	45	21	2	.12
10	356	80	111	44	4	.47	17	2	.09
11	52	10	1.7	33	2	.18	15	2	.09
12	38	6	.62	33	2	.18	13	2	.08
13	75	20	7.1	27	2	.14	12	3	.09
14	58	23	4.5	27	3	.21	145	46	38
15	32	14	1.2	31	4	.36	74	32	7.5
16	26	7	.49	23	3	.21	35	7	.83
17	24	4	.24	23	4	.27	17	4	.18
18	22	6	.35	24	6	.41	15	4	.16
19	22	11	.63	21	5	.26	12	4	.13
20	21	8	.43	19	3	.15	97	37	19
21	20	4	.20	18	2	.08	29	11	.89
22	18	3	.15	17	1	.05	33	11	1.4
23	18	3	.16	16	1	.06	23	16	1.0
24	18	6	.28	15	2	.07	15	8	.31
25	17	11	.51	13	2	.05	15	8	.33
26	15	9	.39	13	1	.04	25	15	1.3
27	15	6	.26	13	1	.05	32	13	1.2
28	14	4	.17	13	2	.07	26	7	.54
29	13	3	.12	---	---	---	44	20	3.6
30	13	4	.14	---	---	---	262	101	164
31	14	6	.22	---	---	---	101	57	20
TOTAL	2869	---	1360.46	1659	---	1188.12	1574	---	513.60
DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	78	13	3.5	19	15	.76	114	23	12
2	51	14	2.3	16	12	.52	54	5	.75
3	34	17	1.6	32	13	1.5	36	4	.41
4	26	12	.87	57	23	5.0	28	4	.30
5	161	59	63	24	19	1.3	23	4	.25
6	44	16	2.1	17	7	.33	30	12	1.0
7	45	13	3.8	20	5	.26	21	11	.64
8	67	33	7.7	152	36	38	20	9	.48
9	28	9	.66	51	13	2.7	129	38	35
10	26	8	.57	21	6	.33	41	23	3.1
11	26	10	.69	16	6	.26	17	6	.28
12	78	28	7.4	14	5	.21	421	170	445
13	86	19	7.0	29	11	1.4	240	71	76
14	31	11	.94	208	74	87	61	19	3.3
15	27	21	1.5	253	69	102	51	9	1.2
16	659	128	297	137	51	34	168	56	38
17	89	12	3.8	36	10	1.0	51	9	1.4
18	165	47	52	25	6	.42	e101	34	e10
19	54	11	1.8	26	4	.31	e46	12	e1.7
20	64	32	6.3	48	14	4.9	36	6	.60
21	61	16	4.0	55	31	5.2	81	17	6.9
22	30	5	.44	22	12	.72	55	20	3.2
23	26	6	.41	21	5	.29	31	7	.63
24	26	6	.45	20	8	.42	29	4	.35
25	21	7	.39	20	16	.84	27	3	.24
26	22	6	.35	189	235	283	23	3	.21
27	36	5	.45	238	57	108	21	4	.23
28	31	5	.40	55	13	2.9	31	10	.94
29	21	6	.33	198	104	77	21	4	.25
30	20	9	.50	674	96	185	17	3	.12
31	---	---	---	134	36	13	---	---	---
TOTAL	2133	---	472.25	2827	---	958.57	2024	---	644.48

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	15	2	.09	18	5	.26	28	17	1.3
2	17	4	.18	14	6	.24	378	112	176
3	21	6	.36	13	10	.35	99	28	11
4	243	81	124	12	15	.49	37	6	.62
5	43	7	.96	11	10	.29	41	10	1.7
6	25	2	.13	e46	22	e1.7	36	20	2.0
7	65	12	3.2	e74	45	e7.2	315	109	178
8	56	25	5.1	40	11	1.4	162	65	43
9	47	12	1.7	94	11	9.4	80	15	3.2
10	42	10	1.4	29	12	.99	39	16	1.7
11	23	3	.18	17	8	.34	28	13	.95
12	43	14	3.1	15	7	.28	23	11	.71
13	20	8	.51	17	4	.20	112	36	22
14	26	5	.95	15	2	.10	60	34	6.6
15	99	7	10	15	2	.10	491	132	362
16	67	10	5.1	36	13	2.3	114	66	22
17	53	14	3.2	65	27	7.2	48	28	3.8
18	41	17	1.8	29	8	.75	64	30	7.5
19	101	20	10	45	12	4.7	192	68	54
20	54	22	3.0	46	11	1.7	58	22	3.6
21	41	8	1.0	143	50	33	e762	293	e2110
22	26	4	.35	50	6	.74	e452	139	e239
23	36	15	1.8	28	4	.26	e109	36	e11
24	329	88	114	833	337	1650	e92	31	e11
25	56	4	.72	493	156	138	e84	29	e3.2
26	31	3	.27	102	34	11	e80	27	e3.2
27	24	5	.34	219	69	84	e73	26	e1.4
28	22	6	.34	61	11	2.1	e69	24	e3.8
29	20	4	.25	58	17	3.1	63	22	3.8
30	19	4	.21	34	6	.52	57	21	3.2
31	22	4	.26	37	9	.85	---	---	---
TOTAL	1727	---	294.50	2709	---	1963.56	4246	---	3291.28
YEAR	32708		17386.11						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT			
		DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
NOV					
09...	0930	840	177	401	100
26...	1340	1940	231	1210	95
MAY					
08...	1545	71	98	19	96
29...	1915	490	181	239	99
30...	1845	598	60	97	98
AUG					
24...	1718	3880	1230	12900	88

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50072500 RIO FAJARDO BELOW FAJARDO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'35", long 65°38'47", 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southwest of Playa de Fajardo, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) east of Fajardo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--23.4 mi² (60.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD) (00400)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TURBIDITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 27...	1235	21	154	7.4	29.0	.60	8.8	114	<10	470	200
MAR 30...	1045	31	129	6.8	25.5	36	8.4	102	<10	2400	2200
JUN 03...	1100	50	125	7.0	28.5	3.6	8.6	111	<10	340	80
AUG 25...	1200	304	73	7.1	26.5	52	7.3	91	<10	6000	5700

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORPTION RATIO (00931)	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD CACO3 (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 27...	42	9.2	4.6	14	.9	1.3	46	<.5	4.9	16
MAR 30...	--	--	--	--	--	--	48	--	--	--
JUN 03...	33	7.1	3.8	11	.8	1.2	39	--	4.0	13
AUG 25...	16	3.5	1.8	6.9	.7	1.6	45	<1.0	3.6	8.8

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 27...	<.10	19	96	5.40	<1	--	<.010	.060	.020	--
MAR 30...	--	--	--	--	17	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 03...	<.10	22	85	11.6	2	--	<.010	.180	.010	--
AUG 25...	<.10	13	66	53.9	40	.219	.011	.230	.060	.41

DATE	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 27...	<.20	--	--	.040	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
MAR 30...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 03...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
AUG 25...	.47	.70	3.1	.070	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO BLANCO BASIN

50074950 QUEBRADA GUABA NEAR NAGUABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'02", long 65°47'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, off Highway 191 at El Yunque Caribbean National Forest, 4.8 mi (7.7 km) southeast of Campamento Eliza Colberg, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) southeast of Mt. Britton, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northwest of Pico del Este and 7.3 mi (11.7 km) southeast of Río Grande Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.05 mi² (0.13 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1992 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 2,100 ft (640 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.35	e.55	.48	.92	.35	.13	.18	.12	.31	.18	.23	.43
2	2.3	e.41	.45	.61	.32	.11	.35	.13	.27	.18	.21	1.1
3	.57	e.44	.41	.91	.28	.10	.13	.25	.28	.22	.21	.42
4	.44	e.50	.37	.70	1.3	.09	.11	.51	.24	.32	.20	.37
5	.43	e.56	.39	.60	1.7	.09	.11	.17	.24	.20	.20	.38
6	.34	e.62	.35	1.6	.37	.10	.08	.16	.27	.26	e.45	.43
7	.34	e.37	.34	3.4	.30	.29	.14	.18	.19	.35	e.68	1.0
8	1.7	e.84	.34	.85	.45	.20	.14	.80	.20	.28	.40	.44
9	.54	e1.0	.33	.95	.34	.12	.09	.32	.55	.32	.55	.40
10	.41	e2.5	.27	1.1	.27	.10	.08	.19	.22	.24	.30	.35
11	1.3	e.40	.25	.63	.30	.09	.10	.17	.15	.22	.24	.33
12	.80	e.30	.27	.52	.27	.09	.40	.17	1.4	.21	.28	.39
13	4.4	.28	.27	.64	.24	.09	.23	.79	.30	.19	.25	1.0
14	4.0	.26	.27	.58	.21	.25	.12	.91	.22	.36	.22	.54
15	e.80	.28	.23	.57	.18	.18	.11	.70	.20	.63	.22	1.4
16	e.76	.45	.23	.49	.16	.12	1.9	.46	.23	.34	.32	.48
17	e.70	.46	.30	.46	.14	.10	.21	.40	.26	.32	.26	.41
18	e.78	.67	.40	.46	.14	.10	.25	.30	e.35	.29	.23	.46
19	e.70	.40	.29	.41	.11	.10	.39	.28	.25	.44	.85	.45
20	e.68	.31	.34	.41	.11	.47	.23	e.42	.24	.35	.34	.50
21	e.67	.57	.41	.38	.11	.16	.14	e.25	.29	.30	.77	14
22	e.65	.35	.27	.35	.10	.18	.12	e.22	.25	.25	.38	6.0
23	e.60	.30	.52	.31	.10	.13	.11	e.24	.23	.33	.28	.86
24	e.54	.38	.39	.31	.08	.10	.10	e.25	.22	1.6	2.9	.68
25	e.45	.31	.35	.30	.09	.15	.12	e.31	.21	.37	1.5	.65
26	e.43	3.3	.30	.28	.10	.20	.13	.92	.20	.32	.52	.62
27	e.40	.50	.28	.30	.12	.30	.22	.50	.22	.31	.48	.64
28	e.40	.41	.25	.29	.13	.16	.18	.29	.22	.29	.41	.61
29	e.38	.47	.22	.29	---	.12	.14	.78	.19	.27	.45	.51
30	e.40	.61	.22	.33	---	.23	.15	.67	.18	.27	.41	.53
31	e.39	---	.37	.40	---	.16	---	.48	---	.32	.38	---
TOTAL	27.65	18.80	10.16	20.35	8.37	4.81	6.76	12.34	8.58	10.53	15.12	36.38
MEAN	.89	.63	.33	.66	.30	.16	.23	.40	.29	.34	.49	1.21
MAX	4.4	3.3	.52	3.4	1.7	.47	1.9	.92	1.4	1.6	2.9	14
MIN	.34	.26	.22	.28	.08	.09	.08	.12	.15	.18	.20	.33
AC-FT	55	37	20	40	17	9.5	13	24	17	21	30	72
CFSM	7.43	5.22	2.73	5.47	2.49	1.29	1.88	3.32	2.38	2.83	4.06	10.1
IN.	8.57	5.83	3.15	6.31	2.59	1.49	2.10	3.83	2.66	3.26	4.69	11.28

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	.42	.51	.39	.50	.41	.26	.27
MAX	.89	.76	.61	.67	.60	.30	.33
(WY)	1998	1993	1993	1997	1994	1995	1994
MIN	.25	.32	.22	.28	.30	.16	.21
(WY)	1993	1995	1994	1994	1998	1995	1996

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	162.95	179.85	
ANNUAL MEAN	.45	.49	.42
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			.49
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.32
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	5.3 Jun 2	14 Sep 21	23 Sep 10 1996
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.08 May 5	.08 Feb 24	.08 May 5 1997
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.09 Apr 30	.10 Feb 20	.09 Apr 30 1997
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		104 Sep 21	104 Sep 21 1998
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		10.78 Sep 21	10.78 Sep 21 1998
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			.05 May 1 1997
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	323	357	301
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.72	4.11	3.47
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	50.51	55.75	47.11
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.70	.79	.71
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.34	.32	.29
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.16	.12	.15

e Estimated

RIO BLANCO BASIN

50074950 QUEBRADA GUABA NEAR NAGUABO, PR--Continued

RIO BLANCO BASIN

50075000 RIO ICACOS NEAR NAGUABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'38", long 65°47'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, in Caribbean National Forest, at Highway 191, at El Yunque, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream from confluence with Río Cubuy, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) north of Florida, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) northwest of Naguabo Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.26 mi² (3.26 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1945 to March 1953 (operated by Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority), annual maximum, water years 1953-62, annual low-flow measurements 1962-66, October 1979 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder, crest-stage gage and sharp-crested weir. Elevation of gage is 2,020 ft (616 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	6.4	11	11	32	5.7	4.7	10	5.8	12	4.5	6.0	14
2	81	6.1	9.0	17	5.7	4.6	21	5.5	8.9	4.3	5.6	54
3	11	6.7	8.0	28	5.7	4.6	7.6	11	7.7	6.0	5.2	15
4	8.0	8.8	6.8	25	20	4.5	5.7	21	6.9	21	5.0	11
5	6.6	9.9	6.4	18	92	4.4	5.1	7.1	6.7	9.0	5.0	14
6	5.8	12	5.7	65	8.8	5.1	4.5	6.0	10	15	19	e26
7	6.1	5.5	5.7	131	6.6	27	7.2	5.7	6.9	22	36	e103
8	70	17	5.1	23	16	9.0	6.8	33	9.8	17	25	e32
9	21	23	5.1	26	9.7	5.8	4.5	11	32	19	34	e44
10	10	87	5.1	39	6.2	5.7	4.2	8.7	10	11	13	e22
11	41	7.4	4.8	15	8.8	5.4	4.1	7.5	6.7	6.6	8.7	e12
12	16	6.0	4.5	14	8.6	5.4	21	8.2	85	5.0	11	13
13	132	5.8	4.7	22	6.5	5.9	10	29	22	4.7	9.3	52
14	152	5.7	4.8	17	9.6	17	4.6	31	10	14	7.1	32
15	16	7.8	4.5	11	7.2	10	5.1	23	7.3	28	6.6	70
16	15	23	4.6	9.5	6.4	6.7	92	12	12	21	20	e17
17	12	26	7.7	9.0	6.3	6.0	11	9.4	7.9	16	18	11
18	18	35	11	8.5	6.0	5.9	18	6.9	14	14	9.6	17
19	12	15	4.1	8.8	5.7	5.7	32	7.4	6.9	24	31	e15
20	11	10	8.4	8.2	5.7	30	15	17	6.0	21	15	18
21	11	27	15	8.0	5.7	8.2	7.2	9.4	12	13	39	254
22	10	11	4.9	8.0	5.4	8.9	6.1	6.5	8.6	11	17	158
23	8.5	7.9	9.8	7.3	5.1	5.4	7.2	7.1	6.0	14	6.5	24
24	7.2	16	4.8	7.2	5.1	4.5	5.8	7.5	5.8	72	117	16
25	7.2	11	4.3	7.2	4.9	7.4	5.9	9.4	6.0	12	e72	15
26	7.0	139	4.0	7.0	4.8	9.4	5.8	42	6.4	8.3	e25	14
27	6.4	14	4.2	6.6	4.5	11	14	19	7.4	7.7	23	12
28	6.4	11	4.4	6.4	4.6	5.9	10	6.6	7.8	7.8	14	11
29	6.0	16	4.5	6.4	---	4.5	6.5	36	5.1	6.4	14	10
30	6.2	18	4.5	5.9	---	22	6.1	40	4.7	6.3	12	10
31	6.0	---	8.5	6.0	---	7.8	---	25	---	10	10	---
TOTAL	732.8	599.6	195.9	603.0	287.3	268.4	364.0	474.7	358.5	451.6	639.6	1116
MEAN	23.6	20.0	6.32	19.5	10.3	8.66	12.1	15.3	11.9	14.6	20.6	37.2
MAX	152	139	15	131	92	30	92	42	85	72	117	254
MIN	5.8	5.5	4.0	5.9	4.5	4.4	4.1	5.5	4.7	4.3	5.0	10
AC-FT	1450	1190	389	1200	570	532	722	942	711	896	1270	2210
CFSM	18.8	15.9	5.02	15.4	8.14	6.87	9.63	12.2	9.48	11.6	16.4	29.5
IN.	21.64	17.70	5.78	17.80	8.48	7.92	10.75	14.01	10.58	13.33	18.88	32.95

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1945 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	15.6	19.1	15.2	14.2	14.3	10.5	12.1	16.4	12.7	13.8	14.9	18.7
MAX	32.1	46.9	31.3	28.4	44.0	26.2	34.4	26.6	23.7	39.0	24.5	51.7
(WY)	1986	1951	1988	1996	1950	1949	1950	1948	1996	1952	1945	1996
MIN	4.78	8.03	4.99	6.65	4.86	3.90	4.77	6.84	5.19	7.21	5.91	7.03
(WY)	1993	1948	1990	1994	1983	1951	1984	1994	1985	1994	1993	1986

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1945 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL		6106.0		6091.4	
ANNUAL MEAN		16.7		16.7	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN				14.8	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN				21.1	1952
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN				8.00	1994
LOWEST DAILY MEAN				7.37	Sep 10 1996
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	172	Jun 2		4.0	Dec 26
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.7	Jul 11		4.4	Dec 24
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.2	Jul 6		2180	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW				8.14	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE				3.5	Apr 10
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW					
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	12110			12080	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	13.3			13.2	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	180.27			179.84	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	31			31	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10			9.0	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.8			5.0	

e Estimated

RIO BLANCO BASIN
50075000 RIO ICACOS NEAR NAGUABO, PR

66°06'33"

66°53'19"

EXPLANATION

- 0920 ▲ SURFACE-WATER STATION AND NUMBER
- 0920-Q ▼ QUALITY-OF-WATER STATION AND NUMBER
- HW-TW-01 ● WELL AND WELL NUMBER
- 093050 △ LAKE-ELEVATION STATION AND NUMBER

- TOWN OR CITY
- TUNNEL FLOW DIRECTION
- CHANNELS FLOW DIRECTION
- - - DRAINAGE BASIN BOUNDARY

Figure 20. Southeastern river basins -- Río Humacao to Quebrada Aguas Verdes basins.

RIO HUMACAO BASIN

50081000 RIO HUMACAO AT LAS PIEDRAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'27", long 65°52'11", Hydrologic unit 21010005, on left bank at downstream side of bridge on Highway 921, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) southeast of junction with Highway 30, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) downstream from Quebrada Blanca and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) south of Las Piedras.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.65 mi² (17.22 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1958 to December 1967 (monthly discharge measurements), July 1974 to September 1977, October 1987 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (79 m), from topographic map. Prior to July 1974, crest-stage gage at different datum. July 1974 to September 1977 at site 90 ft (27 m) upstream at present datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, and above 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s), which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17	20	20	15	18	13	14	9.8	11	10	9.6	19
2	112	19	17	20	18	13	13	9.5	12	9.6	9.2	20
3	24	19	16	16	18	14	12	11	9.9	11	9.2	28
4	21	18	16	20	19	13	12	13	10	27	9.1	22
5	19	18	16	15	168	13	13	12	10	21	9.1	19
6	18	18	16	166	23	13	12	11	10	12	9.0	93
7	18	18	15	211	18	27	12	11	9.7	13	9.2	29
8	17	19	15	54	19	18	12	12	12	12	9.2	118
9	17	26	15	71	19	13	11	12	12	23	15	38
10	17	170	14	85	18	12	10	11	11	12	12	e31
11	17	25	14	32	17	12	10	10	11	11	12	22
12	40	22	15	38	e16	12	13	11	16	12	12	e20
13	104	28	14	29	e16	12	10	12	14	11	11	68
14	567	21	14	27	e18	14	9.6	11	11	14	11	56
15	50	20	14	24	e17	13	9.4	9.8	10	14	12	72
16	33	21	15	23	e17	12	13	10	11	11	13	42
17	27	20	17	22	e17	12	11	9.5	11	13	50	31
18	25	19	18	22	e17	11	9.5	9.8	e31	16	21	32
19	24	20	14	21	e16	12	11	9.6	e21	16	14	36
20	23	20	14	21	e16	13	18	14	13	89	23	37
21	22	23	15	21	e16	13	12	11	15	26	20	e316
22	21	28	14	21	e15	12	11	10	19	14	34	591
23	21	20	14	20	e15	12	10	16	12	12	16	90
24	21	21	15	20	e14	11	9.9	12	11	16	228	e63
25	22	19	13	20	e14	13	9.6	9.7	19	12	e235	e54
26	20	146	13	20	e14	12	10	11	14	11	e59	52
27	20	28	12	19	14	13	10	17	12	13	28	50
28	19	21	12	19	14	12	17	10	12	18	21	49
29	19	20	12	19	---	13	11	12	11	12	51	45
30	19	20	13	19	---	33	10	157	10	11	22	43
31	19	---	12	19	---	24	---	17	---	11	20	---
TOTAL	1413	907	454	1149	621	440	346.0	501.7	391.6	513.6	1013.6	2186
MEAN	45.6	30.2	14.6	37.1	22.2	14.2	11.5	16.2	13.1	16.6	32.7	72.9
MAX	567	170	20	211	168	33	18	157	31	89	235	591
MIN	17	18	12	15	14	11	9.4	9.5	9.7	9.6	9.0	19
AC-FT	2800	1800	901	2280	1230	873	686	995	777	1020	2010	4340
CFSM	6.85	4.55	2.20	5.57	3.34	2.13	1.73	2.43	1.96	2.49	4.92	11.0
IN.	7.90	5.07	2.54	6.43	3.47	2.46	1.94	2.81	2.19	2.87	5.67	12.23

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1974 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	
MEAN	29.7	36.4	28.9	20.2	16.2	11.8	9.75	14.1	17.2	19.5	20.9	38.9														
MAX	74.9	126	112	37.1	22.2	16.4	15.1	42.2	41.1	38.1	34.7	121														
(WY)	1975	1988	1988	1988	1997	1989	1997	1992	1996	1993	1996	1996														
MIN	12.8	13.4	11.5	10.5	11.0	8.87	5.88	7.26	5.91	7.95	9.45	10.0														
(WY)	1995	1996	1992	1995	1977	1996	1977	1990	1977	1990	1974	1990														

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1998 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1974 - 1998	
ANNUAL TOTAL	7598.6		9936.5			
ANNUAL MEAN	20.8		27.2		22.1	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					37.6	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					12.1	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	567	Oct 14	591	Sep 22	2010	Sep 10 1996
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6.3	Jul 15	9.0	Aug 6	2.2	Jul 15 1974
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	7.0	Jun 29	9.1	Aug 2	2.8	Jul 19 1974
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2180		20800	Sep 6 1960
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			6.57		34.40	Sep 6 1960
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	15070		19710		16020	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.13		4.09		3.32	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	42.51		55.58		45.18	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	25		39		32	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15		16		13	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.1		10		7.3	

e Estimated

RIO HUMACAO BASIN

50081000 RIO HUMACAO AT LAS PIEDRAS, PR--Continued

RIO HUMACAO BASIN

50082000 RIO HUMACAO AT HIGHWAY 3 AT HUMACAO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°08'49", long 65°49'37", at bridge on Highway 3, 300 ft (91 m) downstream from Quebrada Mariana, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) south of Humacao.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.3 mi² (44.8 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-66, 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TURBIDITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)
NOV 06...	1150	26	321	6.9	28.5	73	7.0	90	<10	4500 3800
MAR 09...	1120	22	300	7.1	27.0	19	7.6	95	<10	420 520
MAY 18...	1120	10	379	7.0	29.0	3.1	7.0	91	<10	K6100 270
AUG 18...	1020	23	237	6.6	27.7	59	6.7	85	<10	K15000 2400

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO (00931)	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 06...	100	29	8.0	9.2	.4	2.5	106	<.5	18	10
MAR 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
MAY 18...	110	33	7.9	30	1	1.8	120	--	12	42
AUG 18...	67	19	5.1	18	1	3.3	79	<1.0	8.3	26

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 06...	<.10	28	162	11.4	42	.584	.026	.610	.080	.13
MAR 09...	--	--	--	--	38	.700	.010	.710	.060	.19
MAY 18...	.18	41	240	6.54	<1	.328	.012	.340	.010	--
AUG 18...	<.10	29	155	9.80	62	.494	.026	.520	.100	.40

DATE	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 06...	.21	.82	3.6	1.70	<1	<100	60	<1	<1	<10
MAR 09...	.25	.96	4.2	.070	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 18...	<.20	--	--	.050	<1	<100	40	<1	<1	<10
AUG 18...	.50	1.0	4.5	.080	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50083500 RIO GUAYANES AT YABUCOA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'33", long 65°54'03", at bridge on Highway 182, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) west-northwest of Yabucoa plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.2 mi² (44.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-62, 1968-70, 1980 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	
NOV 06...	1010	39	187	6.8	24.5	4.9	7.2	86	10	2800
MAR 06...	0930	30	190	7.0	23.5	4.7	7.4	87	<10	4000
MAY 18...	0925	22	189	7.0	26.0	9.0	6.9	84	<10	K860
AUG 28...	1045	63	157	6.6	26.0	14	6.5	81	<10	2200

DATE	STREP-TOCOCCHI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)
NOV 06...	K1500	88	26	5.7	9.5	.4	2.3	80	<.5	8.0
MAR 06...	K16000	--	--	--	--	--	--	77	--	--
MAY 18...	790	58	15	5.1	16	.9	1.6	75	--	5.0
AUG 28...	7100	47	12	4.1	13	.8	1.8	56	<1.0	4.0

DATE	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS STO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 06...	12	<.10	25	151	16.0	14	<.010	.440	.040	.22
MAR 06...	--	--	--	--	--	4	<.010	.440	.030	--
MAY 18...	14	.16	35	136	7.98	18	<.010	.310	<.010	--
AUG 28...	12	<.10	32	113	19.4	28	<.010	.460	.020	.23

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 06...	.26	.70	3.1	.080	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	12
MAR 06...	<.20	--	--	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 18...	.25	.56	2.5	.030	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
AUG 28...	.25	.71	3.1	.070	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50086500 RIO GUAYANES ABOVE MOUTH AT PLAYA DE GUAYANES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'45", long 65°49'42", at old railroad crossing, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) from mouth, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Playa de Guayanes, and 3.5 mi (5.6 km) northeast of Yabucoa plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--34.0 mi² (88.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TURBIDITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLIFORM, FECCAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECCAL, PER (31679)
NOV 13...	1215	471	7.4	28.0	4.3	7.2	92	<10	5100	2400
MAR 06...	1040	200	7.2	24.5	4.9	7.1	85	<10	9900	810
MAY 19...	1115	253	6.8	29.5	15	4.0	52	<10	4300	430
AUG 18...	0845	225	6.4	26.5	21	3.9	48	<10	3000	5200

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO (00931)	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 13...	170	48	13	30	1	3.7	187	<.5	12	35
MAR 06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	72	--	--	--
MAY 19...	110	17	5.9	25	1	2.9	97	--	5.8	23
AUG 18...	54	13	5.0	21	1	4.8	82	<1.0	6.2	22

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)
NOV 13...	.17	27	280	6	.700	.130	.830	.240	.42	.66
MAR 06...	--	--	--	<1	--	<.010	.470	.020	--	<.20
MAY 19...	.16	31	217	14	.222	.018	.240	.060	.38	.44
AUG 18...	.14	3.1	126	40	.247	.013	.260	.060	.72	.78

DATE	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)	IRON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS FE) (01045)
NOV 13...	1.5	6.6	.270	2	<100	40	<1	<1	<10	340
MAR 06...	--	--	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 19...	.68	3.0	.140	<1	<100	40	<1	<1	<10	1300
AUG 18...	1.0	4.6	.130	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO MAUNABO BASIN

50090500 RIO MAUNABO AT LIZAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'38", long 65°56'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, off Highway 759 at Lizas, about 1.0 mi (1.6km) downstream from Quebrada Coroco, and about 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northwest of Maunabo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.38 mi² (13.93 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1971 to January 1985, February 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 230 ft (70 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12	25	29	30	15	12	8.8	11	11	6.6	7.7	16
2	212	22	21	20	14	11	9.2	11	10	6.9	6.9	17
3	31	22	18	28	14	12	9.4	12	11	8.5	6.5	18
4	24	20	18	30	13	11	9.6	11	11	21	6.2	15
5	20	19	18	35	40	10	18	10	11	9.8	6.1	14
6	18	20	17	220	19	10	11	15	21	7.7	e14	24
7	16	20	16	240	16	45	12	12	47	27	e6.9	27
8	15	20	16	70	25	30	11	13	21	12	6.2	37
9	15	39	17	51	33	14	9.5	12	20	9.9	7.6	45
10	14	72	17	66	18	11	9.3	11	26	7.9	7.2	22
11	14	24	16	33	15	10	9.9	11	14	7.5	6.7	16
12	24	20	17	29	14	9.8	35	11	21	6.6	15	14
13	57	21	18	31	14	9.7	12	12	16	6.8	7.8	38
14	532	20	18	26	30	12	10	12	13	12	6.7	27
15	163	23	17	23	24	11	10	12	11	10	7.1	38
16	63	25	20	22	16	9.4	29	12	22	20	7.5	21
17	41	23	30	22	15	8.8	16	12	16	11	15	17
18	34	21	22	20	15	8.4	11	12	e17	13	8.5	24
19	29	39	20	20	14	9.8	15	12	e14	21	7.7	17
20	26	29	19	20	14	40	30	12	13	14	11	17
21	24	28	30	19	14	17	12	11	12	13	11	289
22	22	33	20	19	13	13	11	11	19	8.4	40	670
23	20	41	27	20	13	9.9	11	12	9.9	7.5	12	73
24	20	36	21	20	12	8.3	11	14	9.0	9.4	302	47
25	19	23	19	e25	12	11	13	11	10	11	315	37
26	19	38	18	21	12	9.8	13	87	8.6	7.9	122	32
27	19	28	20	18	12	10	12	73	8.2	35	36	65
28	19	22	19	17	12	10	12	14	8.3	28	24	34
29	19	44	19	19	---	9.5	11	10	7.7	12	27	28
30	19	102	19	16	---	9.5	11	30	7.1	9.6	19	26
31	20	---	22	15	---	10	---	27	---	11	17	---
TOTAL	1580	919	618	1245	478	412.9	402.7	536	445.8	392.0	1093.3	1765
MEAN	51.0	30.6	19.9	40.2	17.1	13.3	13.4	17.3	14.9	12.6	35.3	58.8
MAX	532	102	30	240	40	45	35	87	47	35	315	670
MIN	12	19	16	15	12	8.3	8.8	10	7.1	6.6	6.1	14
AC-FT	3130	1820	1230	2470	948	819	799	1060	884	778	2170	3500
CFSM	9.47	5.69	3.71	7.46	3.17	2.48	2.50	3.21	2.76	2.35	6.56	10.9
IN.	10.92	6.35	4.27	8.61	3.31	2.85	2.78	3.71	3.08	2.71	7.56	12.20

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1971 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	27.9	31.1	17.8	14.4	12.8	9.96	7.49	13.0	17.8	17.4	23.2	30.0																
MAX	52.6	88.9	35.2	40.2	24.5	18.9	13.4	25.1	47.1	40.2	131	94.6																
(WY)	1979	1978	1978	1998	1982	1976	1998	1979	1993	1993	1979	1996																
MIN	10.4	7.46	8.74	7.79	6.10	4.32	3.92	5.13	4.40	3.70	6.18	7.99																
(WY)	1994	1982	1994	1981	1979	1979	1979	1974	1974	1974	1974	1980																

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1971 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	6449.8	9887.7	
ANNUAL MEAN	17.7	27.1	18.7
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			36.7
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.8
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	532	Oct 14	670
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.3	Jul 4	6.1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.7	Jul 2	7.5
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2550
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			10.47
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	12790	19610	13520
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.28	5.04	3.47
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	44.60	68.37	47.13
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	29	37	33
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10	16	11
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.2	8.9	5.3

e Estimated

RIO MAUNABO BASIN
50090500 RIO MAUNABO AT LIZAS, PR--Continued

RIO MAUNABO BASIN

50091000 RIO MAUNABO AT MAUNABO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'24", long 65°54'19", at bridge on Highway 3, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) southwest of Maunabo plaza, and 1.3 mi (2.1 km) upstream from mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.4 mi² (32.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-66, 1975 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)
NOV 13...	1030	48	475	7.2	27.5	25	6.6	84	<10	4200	3300
MAR 09...	0925	15	248	7.2	24.0	4.0	7.3	87	<10	3900	2100
MAY 19...	0940	9.3	263	7.0	28.0	13	7.6	97	<10	K1500	9200
AUG 28...	0900	41	223	6.6	26.5	6.4	7.0	87	<10	K1900	5400

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 13...	170	58	6.1	19	.6	.90	178	<.5	46	8.0
MAR 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	92	--	--	--
MAY 19...	110	20	7.6	22	1	1.3	97	--	8.7	21
AUG 28...	65	16	6.1	18	1	1.4	75	<1.0	9.1	19

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 13...	.20	24	258	33.0	23	.570	.190	.760	1.70	.40
MAR 09...	--	--	--	--	11	--	<.010	.630	.020	--
MAY 19...	.15	37	217	5.45	6	--	<.010	.190	.030	--
AUG 28...	<.10	34	149	16.5	17	--	<.010	.780	.020	.19

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 13...	2.1	2.9	13	.340	2	<100	40	<1	<1	<10
MAR 09...	<.20	--	--	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 19...	<.20	--	--	.040	<1	<100	10	<1	<1	<10
AUG 28...	.21	.99	4.4	.060	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO CHICO BASIN

50091800 RIO CHICO AT PROVIDENCIA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'16", long 66°00'18", at flat low bridge 200 ft (61 m) south of Highway 3, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) above mouth, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southeast of Patillas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.9 mi² (12.8 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)
OCT 16...	1200	46	263	6.7	27.0	27	5.1	64	11	8200	K15000
MAR 05...	0915	1.5	448	7.2	26.5	3.0	5.9	73	36	20	64
MAY 21...	0915	.68	415	6.8	31.0	.60	6.6	89	<10	930	320
AUG 19...	0915	.78	445	6.2	31.0	2.0	5.0	67	32	2000	3700

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 16...	70	16	7.3	23	1	1.5	69	.7	14	27
MAR 05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
MAY 21...	42	9.6	4.3	12	.8	.60	46	--	8.1	11
AUG 19...	63	15	5.9	55	3	10	56	<1.0	26	56

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 16...	.14	31	161	20.1	32	1.20	.050	1.30	.200	.62
MAR 05...	--	--	--	--	5	3.90	.400	4.30	4.00	--
MAY 21...	<.10	21	95	.17	7	9.11	.390	9.50	.270	2.7
AUG 19...	.16	25	227	.48	10	8.28	.220	8.50	.150	2.2

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 16...	.83	2.1	9.4	1.80	<1	<100	40	<1	<1	<10
MAR 05...	3.8	8.1	36	2.10	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 21...	3.0	13	55	3.10	<1	<100	110	<1	<1	<10
AUG 19...	2.3	11	48	3.40	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'04", long 66°01'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, off Highway 184, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from Lago Patillas Dam and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest of Patillas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.3 mi² (47.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to October 1965 (annual low-flow and occasional measurements only), January 1966 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 235 ft (72 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	29	39	37	e32	28	22	38	27	35	20	25	25
2	99	35	34	e42	26	22	44	27	32	20	24	28
3	61	34	33	e37	25	25	43	26	30	21	24	43
4	52	34	32	e64	26	24	33	31	27	35	24	40
5	37	32	31	e60	233	22	49	26	26	33	24	30
6	31	31	31	e400	66	21	39	26	40	22	e31	69
7	27	30	30	e360	41	353	47	23	35	23	e27	111
8	28	33	30	145	39	144	42	22	31	21	32	72
9	28	49	29	95	44	43	34	25	33	21	43	83
10	26	436	29	113	33	33	32	27	31	19	38	67
11	37	73	28	66	30	29	51	19	26	18	27	48
12	38	51	30	56	28	28	157	19	33	19	36	43
13	487	43	29	49	27	27	61	61	37	19	30	87
14	1320	40	29	45	52	28	45	52	26	19	26	63
15	544	38	28	38	49	29	39	64	24	20	24	76
16	256	40	28	36	34	27	42	49	43	23	26	56
17	143	39	35	34	34	25	47	34	39	20	67	e49
18	107	35	29	32	31	25	51	29	e29	25	31	e42
19	81	37	29	30	28	26	46	26	e28	32	25	e48
20	68	37	29	30	27	129	56	25	26	53	25	e49
21	60	38	35	29	27	58	42	24	34	52	26	e2390
22	54	44	30	29	26	54	39	23	49	31	190	e4500
23	50	56	29	28	25	44	35	23	33	24	33	e2000
24	46	53	28	31	24	35	33	25	29	30	705	e600
25	44	44	27	40	24	39	34	25	30	28	751	e500
26	42	41	27	42	24	36	32	145	30	25	175	e400
27	40	40	29	32	22	42	33	160	28	33	59	e370
28	38	36	28	30	22	40	31	51	26	39	39	e460
29	37	35	27	36	---	47	29	38	25	31	36	e330
30	37	45	29	29	---	51	27	46	22	28	30	e290
31	35	---	29	27	---	58	---	62	---	27	28	---
TOTAL	3982	1618	928	2117	1095	1586	1331	1260	937	831	2681	12969
MEAN	128	53.9	29.9	68.3	39.1	51.2	44.4	40.6	31.2	26.8	86.5	432
MAX	1320	436	37	400	233	353	157	160	49	53	751	4500
MIN	26	30	27	27	22	21	27	19	22	18	24	25
AC-FT	7900	3210	1840	4200	2170	3150	2640	2500	1860	1650	5320	25720
CFSM	7.02	2.95	1.64	3.73	2.14	2.80	2.42	2.22	1.71	1.46	4.73	23.6
IN.	8.09	3.29	1.89	4.30	2.23	3.22	2.71	2.56	1.90	1.69	5.45	26.36

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1966 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998			
MEAN	96.9	87.9	49.5	35.3	29.0	25.3	22.4	50.2	63.3	63.3	70.0	98.1																								
MAX	593	393	152	125	94.6	51.2	44.4	172	200	164	231	432																								
(WY)	1971	1978	1971	1992	1982	1998	1998	1969	1979	1979	1979	1998																								
MIN	14.4	16.1	8.63	14.0	7.09	6.74	9.98	10.3	13.1	14.1	17.2	12.1																								
(WY)	1968	1968	1968	1973	1973	1968	1968	1974	1974	1974	1994	1967																								

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1966 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	15685	31335					
ANNUAL MEAN	43.0	85.8	57.1				
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			117				
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			19.8				
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1320	Oct 14	4500	Sep 22	4780	Sep 16	1975
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	10	Jul 1	18	Jul 11	4.8	May 9	1968
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	12	Jun 27	19	Jul 9	5.0	Apr 10	1968
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			Not determined	Sep 21	30900	Jan 5	1992
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			24.36	Sep 21	unknown	Jan 5	1992
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			18	Jul 11	4.6	May 13	1968
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	31110	62150	41400				
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.35	4.69	3.12				
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	31.88	63.70	42.43				
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	60	85	96				
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	28	33	28				
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	14	24	12				

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN
50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR--Continued

RIO PATILLAS BASIN

50093045 LAGO PATILLAS AT DAMSITE NEAR PATILLAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'15", long 66°01'19", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank, in a concrete tower at Damsite, 1.05 mi (1.69 km) northeast from Patillas plaza, 0.45 mi (0.72 km) northeast from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Real and 2.30 mi (3.70 km) from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Jesús María Rodríguez.

DRAINAGE AREA.--25.2 mi² (65.3 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1995 to current year.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Patillas was completed in 1914. The dam is a semihydraulic earthfill structure about 147 ft (45 m) height, a top width of 15 ft (4.6 m), maximum pool elevation of 230 ft (70.1 m), a base width of 625 ft (190 m), a crest length of 1,067 ft (325 m) and has maximum pool storage of 17,073 ac-ft (21.05 hm³). The Patillas Dam is owned by the Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority (P.R.E.P.A) and its primary purpose is for irrigation of lands served by the Patillas irrigation canal. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 225.92 ft (68.86 m), Sept. 10, 1996; minimum elevation, 211.19 ft (64.37 m), May 29, 1995, July 19, 1997.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 225.49 ft (68.73 m), Sept. 21; minimum elevation, 216.97 ft (66.13 m), Sept. 21.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
143	0	200	7,752
190	5,492	225	15,005
		230	16,773

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	A	221.75	221.52	221.13	221.47	221.31	221.71	221.25	221.81	A	221.42	221.13
2	221.20	221.69	221.16	221.14	221.43	221.25	221.84	221.18	221.68	A	221.30	221.41
3	221.03	221.61	221.03	221.36	221.43	A	221.89	221.13	221.66	A	221.19	221.80
4	221.01	221.52	221.00	221.80	221.46	A	221.81	221.17	221.67	A	221.09	221.84
5	220.90	221.45	220.99	221.95	221.55	A	221.88	221.16	221.69	A	221.00	221.57
6	220.92	221.46	220.99	222.09	221.22	A	221.83	221.19	221.88	221.63	221.02	221.76
7	220.95	221.44	221.00	222.06	221.40	A	221.92	221.19	221.90	A	220.97	221.62
8	221.00	221.58	221.01	221.56	221.63	A	221.82	221.20	221.74	221.59	220.96	221.77
9	221.06	221.80	220.99	221.30	221.83	221.05	221.69	221.26	221.64	221.51	221.08	221.86
10	221.09	222.01	220.98	A	221.85	221.19	221.54	221.34	221.55	221.42	221.12	221.55
11	221.14	221.79	220.96	A	221.82	221.24	221.69	221.34	221.51	221.33	221.08	221.82
12	221.29	221.42	220.96	A	221.78	221.23	221.57	221.35	221.61	221.21	221.20	221.94
13	222.14	221.31	220.98	A	221.74	221.22	221.29	221.69	221.72	A	221.18	221.62
14	222.26	221.47	220.97	221.44	222.06	221.29	221.39	221.90	221.72	221.05	221.11	221.03
15	222.27	221.65	220.97	221.62	221.79	221.31	221.47	221.97	221.71	221.03	221.03	221.64
16	221.27	221.83	221.04	221.77	221.47	221.30	221.61	221.83	221.99	221.02	220.97	221.92
17	221.83	221.93	221.13	221.86	221.18	221.26	221.77	221.59	221.85	221.00	221.29	221.92
18	221.94	221.89	221.13	221.87	221.28	221.27	221.91	221.50	221.62	221.05	221.33	221.97
19	221.69	221.89	221.12	221.83	221.33	221.29	221.87	221.50	221.56	221.13	221.32	221.81
20	221.38	221.81	221.13	221.78	221.38	222.11	A	221.50	221.58	221.44	221.30	220.11
21	221.20	221.77	221.20	221.71	221.43	221.35	221.70	221.49	221.69	221.62	221.34	222.64
22	221.22	221.87	221.20	221.66	221.45	221.05	221.67	221.47	221.91	221.58	220.79	221.45
23	221.47	221.87	221.24	221.60	221.46	220.93	221.64	221.47	221.87	221.51	220.70	222.19
24	221.63	221.68	221.22	221.58	221.47	220.96	221.59	221.48	221.77	221.56	222.17	221.83
25	221.79	221.62	221.19	221.64	221.48	221.15	221.58	221.46	221.71	221.55	221.98	221.66
26	221.89	221.81	221.18	221.71	221.44	221.27	221.55	221.75	221.62	221.47	221.73	222.01
27	221.89	221.91	221.17	221.67	221.38	221.47	221.51	221.42	221.58	221.62	221.76	222.00
28	221.86	221.89	221.15	221.61	221.35	221.64	221.46	221.22	221.56	221.75	221.33	221.31
29	221.81	221.89	221.09	221.66	---	221.83	221.39	221.35	221.52	221.70	220.99	221.85
30	221.76	221.85	221.09	221.60	---	222.00	221.33	221.67	221.46	221.62	220.75	222.01
31	221.72	---	221.06	221.53	---	221.80	---	221.94	---	221.54	220.91	---
MAX	---	222.01	221.52	---	222.06	---	---	221.97	221.99	---	222.17	222.64
MIN	---	221.31	220.96	---	221.18	---	---	221.13	221.46	---	220.70	220.11

A No gage-height record

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Figure 21. South coast river basins -- Río Salinas to Río Jacaguas basins.

RIO SALINAS BASIN

50100200 RIO LAPAS NEAR RABO DEL BUEY, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'36", long 66°14'28", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 1, Km 9.7, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) north of Rabo del Buey, and 4.4 mi (7.1 km) northeast of Salinas Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.92 mi² (25.69 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1953-63 (annual low-flow measurements only), September 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 394 ft (120 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.01	2.8	4.5	2.0	.13	e.96	e1.8	e1.4	e1.4	e.56	e.28	e6.8
2	.02	2.4	4.2	2.0	.11	e.90	e1.3	e1.2	e1.1	e.56	e.31	e10
3	.43	2.2	4.1	2.4	.10	e1.1	e3.0	e1.3	e.76	e.70	e.29	e38
4	.00	2.1	3.7	2.7	.10	e1.4	e1.2	e1.3	e.70	e1.1	e.29	e56
5	.00	2.3	3.7	2.4	201	e1.3	e.96	e1.1	e.72	e1.4	e.29	e22
6	.00	2.5	3.5	2.9	15	e1.1	e.84	e1.1	e.98	e.94	e.56	e16
7	.00	2.5	3.6	2.9	5.5	e1.0	e21	e1.1	e1.1	e.92	e2.0	e16
8	.61	2.5	3.5	2.9	5.0	e.90	e11	e1.0	e.86	e.84	e2.3	e14
9	.00	49	3.5	2.4	7.0	e.80	e2.2	e2.8	e.84	e1.0	e2.2	e12
10	.00	e353	2.7	2.3	3.9	e.76	e1.2	e2.0	e1.0	e.84	e1.0	e9.8
11	.00	34	2.8	2.0	2.6	e.76	e2.2	e1.6	e.94	e.82	e.78	e6.8
12	.00	22	2.6	1.8	2.3	e.68	e20	e2.0	e.90	e.70	e.60	e5.8
13	631	14	2.6	1.9	2.0	e.68	e12	e3.0	e1.2	e.54	e.58	e5.8
14	791	11	2.5	2.0	2.1	e.68	e1.4	e7.4	e1.4	e.60	e.45	e5.0
15	122	8.4	2.5	1.8	2.1	e.64	e1.1	e4.1	e1.3	e.52	e.38	e5.0
16	44	8.6	2.5	1.6	1.8	e.64	e.95	e3.1	e1.5	e.60	e.38	e4.7
17	20	8.2	2.7	1.7	e1.9	e.64	e1.0	e2.8	e1.1	e.54	e.50	e3.3
18	24	7.5	2.7	1.9	e1.7	e.56	e1.1	e3.8	e.78	e.52	e.72	e3.6
19	14	6.8	2.6	2.0	e1.5	e.46	e1.2	e3.6	e.90	e.88	e.56	e4.6
20	11	6.7	2.6	1.7	e1.4	e.76	e1.3	e1.8	e1.1	e.62	e.47	e2.6
21	9.0	6.5	3.3	1.6	e1.3	e1.0	e2.5	e.92	e1.0	e.68	e.58	e540
22	7.4	6.1	2.7	1.3	e1.2	e.76	e2.8	e.82	e3.4	e.45	e16	e560
23	6.6	5.8	2.6	1.1	e1.1	e.80	e4.7	e.78	e.90	e.32	e5.2	e120
24	6.3	5.3	2.4	.92	e1.0	e.46	e4.3	e.78	e.60	e.40	e82	e66
25	5.8	5.4	2.2	.96	e.98	e.41	e2.7	e.76	e.54	e.33	e160	e42
26	5.3	5.1	2.0	.69	e.98	e.42	e2.6	e2.1	e.56	e.28	e42	e36
27	5.0	5.0	2.2	.42	e.98	e.46	e2.2	e4.2	e.60	e.27	e20	e32
28	4.8	4.7	2.1	.31	e.98	e.88	e2.0	e1.5	e.56	e.44	e12	e30
29	4.6	4.6	2.2	.24	---	e.70	e1.7	e1.0	e.56	e.60	e23	e27
30	4.1	4.4	2.0	.20	---	e22	e1.5	e1.0	e.56	e.45	e13	e24
31	3.4	---	2.0	.15	---	e11	---	e4.8	---	e.38	e9.0	---
TOTAL	1720.37	601.4	88.8	51.19	265.76	55.61	125.45	66.16	29.86	19.80	397.72	1724.8
MEAN	55.5	20.0	2.86	1.65	9.49	1.79	4.18	2.13	1.00	.64	12.8	57.5
MAX	791	353	4.5	2.9	201	22	21	7.4	3.4	1.4	160	560
MIN	.00	2.1	2.0	.15	.10	.41	.84	.76	.54	.27	.28	2.6
AC-FT	3410	1190	176	102	527	110	249	131	59	39	789	3420
CFSM	5.55	2.00	.29	.17	.95	.18	.42	.21	.10	.06	1.28	5.75
IN.	6.40	2.24	.33	.19	.99	.21	.47	.25	.11	.07	1.48	6.42

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1988 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	
MEAN	17.7	6.78	2.14	8.14	3.42	1.03	1.35	4.42	2.19	1.79	3.41	21.9
MAX	76.1	28.4	6.09	68.8	12.4	2.08	4.18	36.6	10.4	7.80	12.8	81.2
(WY)	1991	1991	1991	1992	1991	1992	1998	1992	1993	1993	1998	1996
MIN	1.46	1.07	.75	.47	.49	.44	.28	.086	.036	.009	.001	.052
(WY)	1992	1994	1995	1994	1990	1990	1990	1994	1994	1994	1994	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1988 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	2524.84	5146.92	
ANNUAL MEAN	6.92	14.1	6.19
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			14.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.57
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	791	791	1900
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	.00	.00
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	.07	.00
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		7320	18100
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		14.30	18.65
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	5010	10210	4480
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.69	1.41	.62
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	9.39	19.15	8.41
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.8	14	6.0
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.40	1.8	1.1
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.02	.45	.12

e Estimated

RIO SALINAS BASIN

50100200 RIO LAPAS NEAR RABO DEL BUEY, PR--Continued

RIO SALINAS BASIN

50100450 RIO MAJADA AT LA PLENA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'40", long 66°12'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank, upstream side of bridge on Hwy 712, about 0.3 mi (0.5 km), southwest of La Plena.

DRAINAGE AREA.--16.7 mi² (43.3 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1973 to April 1979 (montly measurements only), September 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 410 ft (125 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.-Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Some regulation at low-flow upstream from station by local residents for agricultural purposes.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e.00	e10	11	6.1	1.3	2.3	2.6	e2.1	4.3	1.8	.86	7.4
2	e.00	e9.3	11	6.7	1.2	2.2	19	e1.9	3.4	1.8	1.0	12
3	e.00	e9.0	9.9	4.7	.88	2.8	4.9	e2.0	2.4	2.2	.91	49
4	e.00	e8.8	9.1	3.6	.74	3.5	1.8	e2.0	2.2	3.5	.91	84
5	e.00	e9.5	8.9	3.3	36	3.0	1.4	e1.7	2.3	4.7	.91	24
6	e.00	e10	8.2	4.1	13	2.6	1.2	1.6	3.1	3.0	1.7	16
7	e.00	e11	7.5	4.7	6.0	2.5	32	1.6	3.5	2.9	6.6	15
8	e.00	e11	7.3	4.1	4.3	2.1	15	1.5	2.8	2.6	7.4	14
9	e.00	e42	7.0	3.9	6.9	1.9	3.2	4.2	2.7	3.2	7.1	12
10	e.00	e400	7.0	3.5	4.5	1.8	1.8	3.1	3.3	2.7	3.2	9.3
11	e.00	e35	6.6	3.5	3.9	1.8	3.3	2.3	3.0	2.6	2.4	7.2
12	e.00	e30	6.2	3.8	3.6	1.6	30	2.9	2.8	2.2	1.9	6.7
13	e.00	e29	6.2	3.9	3.3	1.6	17	4.4	3.8	1.7	1.8	6.5
14	e547	e27	6.2	3.5	6.2	1.6	2.0	11	4.4	1.9	1.4	6.1
15	e98	e51	6.1	2.8	9.2	1.5	1.6	6.2	4.0	1.6	1.2	6.2
16	e50	e43	5.7	2.5	5.4	1.5	1.4	4.4	4.9	2.0	1.2	5.7
17	e33	e36	8.1	2.2	4.5	1.5	1.5	4.0	3.7	1.7	1.7	4.7
18	e36	e32	6.6	2.2	4.2	1.3	1.7	5.6	2.4	1.6	2.3	4.9
19	e25	e31	6.7	2.2	3.6	1.1	1.8	5.3	2.9	2.8	1.8	5.7
20	e22	e28	5.8	2.2	3.4	1.7	e1.9	3.3	3.6	1.9	1.5	4.1
21	e18	23	6.4	2.2	3.2	2.4	e3.7	2.8	3.4	2.2	2.0	e965
22	e17	24	6.7	2.2	3.0	1.8	e4.3	2.5	11	1.4	50	1080
23	e15	24	5.7	2.1	2.8	1.9	e7.1	2.4	2.8	1.0	16	224
24	e14	20	5.3	2.0	2.6	1.1	e6.4	2.4	1.9	1.3	151	139
25	e14	16	5.6	2.1	2.4	.96	e4.1	2.3	1.7	1.0	315	81
26	e13	15	5.7	2.3	2.4	1.0	e3.9	7.0	1.8	.87	60	69
27	e12	14	5.7	2.0	2.4	1.1	e3.3	13	1.9	.85	26	61
28	e11	13	5.7	1.6	2.4	2.1	e3.0	4.6	1.8	1.4	11	57
29	e11	12	5.7	1.6	---	1.6	e2.6	3.1	1.8	1.9	25	52
30	e11	12	6.2	1.5	---	32	e2.3	3.1	1.8	1.4	14	45
31	e11	---	5.7	1.3	---	16	---	15	---	1.2	8.8	---
TOTAL	958.00	1035.6	215.5	94.4	143.32	101.86	185.8	129.3	95.4	62.92	726.59	3073.5
MEAN	30.9	34.5	6.95	3.05	5.12	3.29	6.19	4.17	3.18	2.03	23.4	102
MAX	547	400	11	6.7	36	32	32	15	11	4.7	315	1080
MIN	.00	8.8	5.3	1.3	.74	.96	1.2	1.5	1.7	.85	.86	4.1
AC-FT	1900	2050	427	187	284	202	369	256	189	125	1440	6100
CFSM	1.85	2.07	.42	.18	.31	.20	.37	.25	.19	.12	1.40	6.13
IN.	2.13	2.31	.48	.21	.32	.23	.41	.29	.21	.14	1.62	6.85

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1973 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	14.4	9.33	3.61	9.07	3.27	2.06	1.90	3.82	3.18	3.09	4.29	28.2														
MAX	76.4	34.5	9.67	68.8	12.1	3.92	6.19	25.5	12.1	12.9	23.4	109														
(WY)	1991	1998	1991	1992	1991	1991	1998	1992	1992	1993	1998	1996														
MIN	1.43	1.53	.62	.37	.63	.59	.30	.21	.042	.012	.010	.008														
(WY)	1992	1994	1995	1995	1990	1990	1995	1994	1994	1997	1994	1997														

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1973 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	2335.44	6822.19	
ANNUAL MEAN	6.40	18.7	7.17
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			18.7
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.81
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	547 Oct 14	1080 Sep 22	2270 Sep 10 1996
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00 Jul 19	.00 Oct 1	.00 Oct 3 1994
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00 Jul 19	.00 Oct 1	.00 Oct 8 1994
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		12800 Sep 21	17700 Sep 10 1996
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		15.63 Sep 21	19.69 Sep 10 1996
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	4630	13530	5200
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.38	1.12	.43
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	5.20	15.20	5.84
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	27	8.9
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.47	3.5	1.8
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	1.3	.17

e Estimated

RIO SALINAS BASIN

50100450 RIO MAJADA AT LA PLENA, PR--Continued

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106100 RIO COAMO AT COAMO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'00", long 66°21'16", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on Highway 14 bridge, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northeast from Parque Atlético, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southeast from (W.C.P.R.) Antena de Radio.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.5 mi² (112.7 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1987 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 335 ft (110 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Low-flow is affected by domestic discharges about 200 ft (65.6 m), upstream from gaging station. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. The gage-height recovered for the instantaneous peak stage produced by Hurricane Georges was affected by backwater caused by the Hwy. 14 bridge which is about 100 ft.(30.40 m), downstream from gage.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2.0	8.8	8.1	5.3	7.1	9.5	11	10	12	5.1	2.0	15
2	2.0	9.0	7.7	5.0	6.4	8.8	37	10	9.0	4.6	2.2	37
3	12	8.2	7.5	4.5	6.2	8.8	9.6	14	9.0	4.5	2.3	75
4	3.4	7.7	7.3	4.9	6.2	10	5.8	12	38	4.6	2.1	149
5	2.0	e7.5	6.7	4.8	328	8.7	5.3	10	10	5.9	2.1	21
6	2.3	e7.4	6.6	4.5	42	7.3	4.9	9.6	8.2	4.0	3.2	70
7	1.8	e7.2	6.5	6.3	12	7.1	31	13	7.3	3.6	35	63
8	42	e7.2	6.1	5.9	12	6.1	11	11	7.3	3.2	53	44
9	49	e18	5.6	5.5	43	5.8	5.7	11	6.9	3.4	14	35
10	13	e26	5.6	5.5	26	5.2	5.4	12	6.7	3.7	8.2	27
11	23	e11	5.5	5.8	22	4.6	14	8.8	6.3	3.9	6.2	22
12	16	e9.4	5.3	19	20	4.0	126	7.3	5.9	3.8	5.7	20
13	78	e9.0	5.3	11	16	3.7	46	10	6.2	3.8	4.9	18
14	351	e8.6	5.1	10	15	3.5	22	39	6.3	3.6	4.4	16
15	200	e18	5.0	11	13	4.0	17	75	6.3	4.6	3.9	16
16	113	e14	5.0	11	12	3.5	14	29	7.2	4.0	4.2	14
17	60	e12	5.2	9.0	12	3.4	13	17	7.4	4.0	4.6	12
18	51	e11	4.8	13	13	2.8	41	38	7.6	4.2	4.1	14
19	43	e10	5.0	13	14	2.6	30	43	6.7	4.5	4.1	15
20	34	e9.6	5.0	9.7	13	2.5	26	89	6.1	4.1	4.0	13
21	28	e9.2	5.2	8.5	11	3.6	24	212	6.8	4.7	4.2	e1550
22	23	e9.1	5.6	8.5	9.7	3.3	25	200	12	3.0	75	e4530
23	16	e9.0	5.6	8.2	9.2	3.0	20	131	7.1	2.6	23	e694
24	17	e9.0	5.6	8.6	8.4	2.5	20	93	6.2	2.4	107	e283
25	15	e9.0	5.6	9.0	7.7	2.4	25	67	5.8	2.2	348	e189
26	13	12	5.6	9.7	10	2.7	21	54	5.8	2.3	64	e176
27	12	17	5.6	8.5	10	2.3	18	58	5.6	2.8	37	e177
28	11	11	5.6	7.7	9.5	2.6	14	30	5.4	2.7	30	e172
29	10	8.5	5.8	6.9	---	3.6	13	20	5.5	2.9	27	e144
30	9.0	8.5	5.7	6.7	---	12	12	16	5.2	2.7	20	e116
31	9.0	---	5.3	6.2	---	26	---	13	---	2.8	16	---
TOTAL	1261.5	321.9	180.1	253.2	714.4	175.9	667.7	1362.7	245.8	114.2	921.4	8727
MEAN	40.7	10.7	5.81	8.17	25.5	5.67	22.3	44.0	8.19	3.68	29.7	291
MAX	351	26	8.1	19	328	26	126	212	38	5.9	348	4530
MIN	1.8	7.2	4.8	4.5	6.2	2.3	4.9	7.3	5.2	2.2	2.0	12
AC-FT	2500	638	357	502	1420	349	1320	2700	488	227	1830	17310
CFSM	.94	.25	.13	.19	.59	.13	.51	1.01	.19	.08	.68	6.69
IN.	1.08	.28	.15	.22	.61	.15	.57	1.17	.21	.10	.79	7.46

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	54.1	25.7	16.6	17.4	10.6	5.84	11.5	18.1	13.7	6.97	10.5	50.6
MAX	274	62.9	83.8	79.0	25.5	9.79	27.6	69.6	76.1	15.5	29.7	291
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1992	1998	1988	1987	1992	1987	1988	1998	1998
MIN	10.3	4.91	3.72	2.71	3.17	3.09	2.49	1.66	1.99	.78	1.28	1.61
(WY)	1989	1995	1989	1995	1989	1987	1995	1989	1989	1989	1994	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1998 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1987 - 1998	
ANNUAL TOTAL	3056.1		14945.8			
ANNUAL MEAN	8.37		40.9		19.9	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					40.9	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					4.52	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	351	Oct 14	4530	Sep 22	4530	Sep 22 1998
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.4	Sep 12	1.8	Oct 7	.67	Aug 2 1989
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.4	Sep 16	2.3	Jul 30	.70	Jul 27 1989
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			52700		52700	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			25.94		25.94	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	6060		29640		14380	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.19		.94		.46	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	2.61		12.78		6.20	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	12		50		35	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.6		9.0		6.9	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.8		3.5		2.2	

e Estimated

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106100 RIO COAMO AT COAMO, PR--Continued

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106500 RIO COAMO NEAR COAMO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'52", long 66°22'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on Highway 153 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) above Río de la Mina, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) south of Coamo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--46.0 mi² (119.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1978 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-ATION) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
NOV 04...	1240	9.1	638	8.8	30.0	4.5	8.6	88	<10	210	K190
MAR 13...	1010	6.3	672	7.8	26.5	.28	8.2	102	<10	K130	50
MAY 20...	1110	20	464	7.6	30.0	1.5	7.7	102	<10	K1900	K160
AUG 26...	0930	99	384	7.0	26.0	8.5	7.3	91	20	2400	K1700

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 04...	240	24	44	13	.4	1.6	218	<.5	21	16
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--
MAY 20...	170	45	14	26	.9	.23	170	--	25	28
AUG 26...	200	31	30	16	.5	2.1	150	<1.0	18	17

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 04...	.10	33	286	7.03	39	1.78	.022	1.80	.030	.39
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	1	2.58	.017	2.60	.030	.28
MAY 20...	.38	31	272	14.5	2	1.58	.018	1.60	.040	--
AUG 26...	.20	33	270	6.63	12	--	<.010	2.50	.020	.32

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 04...	.42	2.2	9.8	.210	<1	<100	80	<1	<1	<10
MAR 13...	.31	2.9	13	.150	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 20...	<.20	--	--	.150	<1	<100	50	<1	<1	<10
AUG 26...	.34	2.8	13	.260	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO DESCALABRADO BASIN

50108000 RIO DESCALABRADO NEAR LOS LLANOS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'08", long 66°25'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 14, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) west of Los Llanos, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) east of Juana Díaz.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.9 mi² (33.4 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1959-65 (annual low-flow measurements only), 1965 (annual maximum discharge), January 1966 to June 1969, July to December 1969 (maximum discharge only), February 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 220 ft (67 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Some regulation at low-flow by local resident upstream from station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	4.2	1.7	e1.3	.44	e.39	1.0	e14	1.6	e4.4	e1.7	e.58	e5.6
2	1.6	1.7	e1.2	.42	e.35	1.0	e1.5	1.8	e3.2	e1.6	e.64	e14
3	2.2	1.8	e1.2	.49	e.34	.94	e1.4	2.0	e3.3	e1.6	e.66	e29
4	1.7	1.7	e1.1	.46	e.34	.92	e1.3	1.7	e14	e1.6	e.62	e54
5	1.5	1.8	e1.1	.40	e60	.87	e1.3	1.7	e3.6	e2.0	e.62	e8.0
6	1.4	1.8	e1.1	.45	e5.4	.87	e1.3	1.7	e3.0	e1.4	e.82	e26
7	1.4	1.7	e1.0	.43	e1.8	.90	e46	3.8	e2.7	e1.3	e9.6	e23
8	27	1.8	e1.0	.56	e1.8	.82	e4.8	2.5	e2.7	e1.1	e14	e17
9	38	3.4	.90	.49	e6.4	.87	e3.2	1.9	e2.5	e1.2	e3.7	e13
10	39	e6.9	.91	.49	e3.8	.93	e2.7	1.8	e2.5	e1.3	e2.2	e10
11	e108	e2.1	.91	.45	e3.3	.93	e5.2	1.7	e2.3	e1.4	e1.7	e8.2
12	e16	e2.2	.85	1.9	e2.9	.91	e43	2.0	e2.2	e1.3	e1.7	e7.6
13	e159	e2.1	.79	1.0	e2.4	.91	e5.0	e2.1	e2.3	e1.3	e1.5	e6.8
14	e398	e2.0	.77	.67	e2.3	.88	e3.0	e10	e2.3	e1.3	e1.5	e6.0
15	91	e1.9	.73	.59	e2.0	.91	3.1	e18	e2.3	e1.7	e1.4	e6.0
16	22	e1.9	.72	.54	e1.8	e.88	3.2	e7.0	e2.7	e1.1	e1.6	e5.4
17	16	e1.9	.76	.51	e1.8	e.84	3.4	e4.0	e2.8	e1.1	e1.8	e4.6
18	9.8	e1.8	.80	.52	e2.0	e.82	18	e9.0	e2.8	e1.2	e1.8	e5.2
19	5.3	1.8	.74	.54	e2.1	e.80	3.0	e11	e2.5	e1.3	e1.9	e5.6
20	4.5	1.7	.72	e.70	e1.9	e.80	2.1	e21	e2.2	e1.2	e2.0	e5.0
21	4.1	1.4	.80	e.47	e1.6	e.82	3.5	e50	e2.5	e1.4	e2.2	e200
22	3.7	1.5	.70	e.47	e1.4	e.80	2.6	e47	e4.5	e.86	e20	e1700
23	3.4	1.4	.66	e.45	e1.3	e.78	1.8	e30	e2.6	e.72	e6.1	e260
24	3.0	1.2	.62	e.48	e1.2	e.78	1.8	e23	e2.2	e.70	e30	e106
25	2.8	1.2	.59	e.50	1.2	e.80	1.7	e18	e2.0	e.65	e92	e70
26	2.4	1.1	.57	e.54	1.1	e.78	1.9	e13	e2.0	e.66	e25	e66
27	2.2	1.0	.56	e.47	1.1	e.80	1.8	e14	e1.9	e.80	e14	e66
28	2.0	1.0	.58	e.43	1.1	e.78	1.8	e11	e1.8	e.80	e11	e65
29	1.9	.99	.54	e.38	---	e.86	1.7	e7.2	e1.9	e.83	e10	e55
30	1.9	.99	.49	e.37	---	e1.2	1.6	e5.6	e1.8	e.74	e7.4	e44
31	2.0	---	.48	e.35	---	e.97	---	e4.7	---	e.74	e6.0	---
TOTAL	977.0	55.48	25.19	16.96	113.12	27.17	186.7	329.8	89.5	36.60	274.04	2892.0
MEAN	31.5	1.85	.81	.55	4.04	.88	6.22	10.6	2.98	1.18	8.84	96.4
MAX	398	6.9	1.3	1.9	60	1.2	46	50	14	2.0	92	1700
MIN	1.4	.99	.48	.35	.34	.78	1.3	1.6	1.8	.65	.58	4.6
AC-FT	1940	110	50	34	224	54	370	654	178	73	544	5740
CFSM	2.44	.14	.06	.04	.31	.07	.48	.82	.23	.09	.69	7.47
IN.	2.82	.16	.07	.05	.33	.08	.54	.95	.26	.11	.79	8.34

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1966 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	26.9	14.1	4.77	4.60	3.67	1.92	4.33	14.6	4.87	2.61	4.25	38.3
MAX	117	41.0	24.5	36.4	23.9	8.93	18.8	62.2	25.2	10.5	13.1	395
(WY)	1986	1985	1988	1992	1995	1996	1985	1985	1987	1991	1996	1996
MIN	2.02	1.04	.19	.057	.020	.012	.000	.032	.000	.000	.19	.063
(WY)	1968	1995	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1967	1967	1990	1967

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1966 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	1451.39	5023.56	
ANNUAL MEAN	3.98	13.8	11.0
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			41.7
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			1.69
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	398	Oct 14	1700
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.11	Sep 20	.34
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.12	Sep 3	.36
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			9180
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			16.15
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	2880	9960	7960
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.31	1.07	.85
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	4.19	14.49	11.57
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.4	18	14
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.62	1.8	1.4
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.15	.58	.06

e Estimated

RIO DESCALABRADO BASIN
50108000 RIO DESCALABRADO NEAR LOS LLANOS, PR--Continued

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'37", long 66°27'24", Hydrologic unit 21010004, on right bank, off a dirt road about 0.3 mi (0.5 km) from road 553, 2.4 mi (3.9 km) southeast from Villalba Plaza, and 0.2 mi (0.3 km) downstream from confluence with Quebrada Limón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--14.2 mi² (36.77 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 525 ft (160 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17	7.3	3.5	1.9	1.6	1.9	16	7.4	18	5.4	7.1	14
2	16	7.0	3.3	2.0	1.6	1.8	31	7.3	17	4.8	12	30
3	13	6.6	3.0	2.1	1.5	2.5	15	7.8	21	4.4	7.4	93
4	12	6.4	2.9	1.9	2.0	2.5	5.5	7.5	45	5.6	3.4	153
5	10	6.1	2.9	1.7	93	2.2	2.9	7.5	53	5.8	2.5	37
6	9.8	5.9	2.9	1.6	4.5	2.0	2.1	16	34	4.2	4.1	150
7	11	5.7	2.8	2.4	2.2	2.0	86	11	29	4.6	19	92
8	75	7.0	2.8	2.2	24	2.5	53	13	28	4.5	31	49
9	44	7.4	2.4	2.0	33	1.9	28	15	26	4.3	19	35
10	29	24	2.3	1.7	8.3	1.5	17	9.5	25	4.7	11	28
11	66	7.5	2.3	1.6	4.5	1.5	17	7.7	23	4.6	13	47
12	55	6.1	2.1	1.8	3.0	1.4	217	7.0	23	4.5	18	34
13	71	5.2	2.1	3.0	2.4	1.4	58	22	22	4.9	13	23
14	236	4.7	1.9	3.5	3.0	1.4	26	67	19	10	6.2	18
15	129	4.7	2.0	2.2	3.7	1.4	17	74	18	15	3.4	18
16	68	5.0	2.0	1.7	2.6	1.5	13	36	27	12	3.0	34
17	53	4.7	2.4	1.5	2.6	1.5	11	29	40	9.8	10	19
18	36	4.3	2.4	15	2.5	1.6	10	124	25	9.5	3.3	41
19	26	4.0	2.4	14	2.1	1.7	9.0	42	14	7.6	3.9	37
20	22	3.9	2.0	3.9	2.1	1.7	8.6	243	11	9.5	14	26
21	15	3.9	2.0	2.8	1.9	2.0	11	456	11	11	9.0	1050
22	13	4.0	1.7	2.4	2.0	2.6	11	165	18	6.5	122	e1740
23	11	3.8	2.6	2.2	1.8	1.9	14	87	10	4.8	33	e224
24	10	3.5	2.4	2.2	2.0	2.0	13	62	9.2	4.7	455	e115
25	9.3	3.3	2.3	2.3	1.8	2.5	9.7	45	9.0	4.8	146	e85
26	8.6	3.2	2.2	2.5	1.8	2.7	9.0	43	8.4	3.8	52	e73
27	8.2	3.1	2.1	1.9	1.8	2.2	7.7	31	7.2	5.9	34	e63
28	7.9	3.0	2.1	1.8	1.9	2.1	7.0	27	6.9	4.7	24	e59
29	7.9	3.0	2.0	1.8	---	1.7	6.3	24	6.3	4.1	19	e93
30	7.7	4.3	1.9	1.6	---	13	6.8	22	6.0	3.6	16	e86
31	7.5	---	1.8	1.6	---	4.0	---	20	---	3.2	14	---
TOTAL	1104.9	168.6	73.5	90.8	215.2	72.6	738.6	1735.7	610.0	192.8	1128.3	4566
MEAN	35.6	5.62	2.37	2.93	7.69	2.34	24.6	56.0	20.3	6.22	36.4	152
MAX	236	24	3.5	15	93	13	217	456	53	15	455	1740
MIN	7.5	3.0	1.7	1.5	1.5	1.4	2.1	7.0	6.0	3.2	2.5	14
AC-FT	2190	334	146	180	427	144	1470	3440	1210	382	2240	9060
CFSM	2.51	.40	.17	.21	.54	.16	1.73	3.94	1.43	.44	2.56	10.7
IN.	2.89	.44	.19	.24	.56	.19	1.93	4.55	1.60	.51	2.96	11.96

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998		
MEAN	41.5	15.9	6.46	9.19	5.70	3.37	9.79	23.1	11.2	6.64	9.86	44.5
MAX	109	40.1	12.4	43.1	12.6	5.01	26.3	76.1	35.4	14.4	36.4	152
(WY)	1991	1991	1993	1992	1996	1996	1993	1995	1992	1992	1998	1998
MIN	4.61	2.19	1.42	1.79	2.38	1.67	1.46	1.42	1.23	.71	2.74	3.21
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1995	1990	1990	1990	1997	1990	1990	1990	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1989 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	2278.47	10697.0		
ANNUAL MEAN	6.24	29.3		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			15.9	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			29.3	1998
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	236	Oct 14	1740	Sep 22
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.57	Jul 25	1.4	Mar 12
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.64	Jul 22	1.4	Mar 10
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			Not determined	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			20.60	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			.59	Apr 1
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	4520	21220	11500	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.44	2.06	1.12	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	5.97	28.02	15.19	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.9	54	33	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.4	7.2	4.3	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.1	1.9	1.4	

e Estimated

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1988 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: April 1988 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 and automatic sediment sampler since 1988.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediment samples were collected by a local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 11,800 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several years.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e93,300 tons (e84,700 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, <0.01 ton (<0.01 tonne) several years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 11,800 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e93,300 tons (e84,700 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 tons (0.01 tonne) several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION		DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION		DISCHARGE	CONCENTRATION	
	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	(MG/L)	(TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	17	95	4.3	7.3	205	4.0	3.5	16	.16
2	16	89	3.9	7.0	231	4.3	3.3	17	.15
3	13	84	3.0	6.6	263	4.7	3.0	16	.13
4	12	79	2.5	6.4	293	5.0	2.9	15	.12
5	10	75	2.0	6.1	254	4.2	2.9	10	.08
6	9.8	70	1.8	5.9	205	3.2	2.9	6	.04
7	11	130	3.2	5.7	164	2.5	2.8	3	.03
8	75	1390	1040	7.0	131	2.4	2.8	3	.02
9	44	494	60	7.4	108	2.4	2.4	2	.01
10	29	328	26	24	350	37	2.3	2	.01
11	66	655	203	7.5	41	.87	2.3	2	.01
12	55	598	91	6.1	8	.13	2.1	3	.01
13	71	709	226	5.2	2	.02	2.1	3	.02
14	236	2350	2990	4.7	3	.03	1.9	3	.02
15	129	456	183	4.7	9	.11	2.0	4	.02
16	68	471	91	5.0	24	.33	2.0	4	.02
17	53	476	127	4.7	14	.17	2.4	5	.03
18	36	271	28	4.3	4	.05	2.4	5	.03
19	26	72	5.2	4.0	1	.01	2.4	6	.04
20	22	21	1.2	3.9	1	.01	2.0	6	.03
21	15	33	e1.4	3.9	1	.01	2.0	7	.04
22	13	86	2.9	4.0	1	.01	1.7	8	.04
23	11	210	6.4	3.8	3	.03	2.6	9	.06
24	10	229	6.3	3.5	8	.08	2.4	10	.06
25	9.3	200	5.0	3.3	12	.11	2.3	11	.07
26	8.6	175	4.1	3.2	4	.04	2.2	12	.07
27	8.2	168	3.7	3.1	5	.04	2.1	14	.08
28	7.9	165	3.5	3.0	5	.04	2.1	15	.09
29	7.9	163	3.5	3.0	7	.06	2.0	17	.09
30	7.7	174	3.6	4.3	11	.13	1.9	19	.10
31	7.5	188	3.8	---	---	---	1.8	18	.09
TOTAL	1104.9	---	5136.3	168.6	---	71.98	73.5	---	1.77

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	1.9	17	.09	1.6	7	.03	1.9	31	.16
2	2.0	16	.09	1.6	6	.03	1.8	38	.19
3	2.1	15	.08	1.5	5	.02	2.5	46	.31
4	1.9	14	.07	2.0	9	.07	2.5	44	.29
5	1.7	13	.06	93	1610	1230	2.2	38	.23
6	1.6	12	.05	4.5	124	1.8	2.0	32	.18
7	2.4	12	.08	2.2	27	.16	2.0	17	.09
8	2.2	11	.06	24	184	87	2.5	8	.05
9	2.0	10	.05	33	214	29	1.9	4	.02
10	1.7	10	.04	8.3	42	.96	1.5	3	.01
11	1.6	9	.04	4.5	29	.35	1.5	3	.01
12	1.8	8	.04	3.0	19	.15	1.4	3	.01
13	3.0	8	.06	2.4	11	.07	1.4	4	.02
14	3.5	7	.07	3.0	6	.05	1.4	6	.02
15	2.2	7	.04	3.7	4	.04	1.4	8	.03
16	1.7	7	.03	2.6	6	.04	1.5	11	.04
17	1.5	6	.03	2.6	11	.08	1.5	14	.06
18	15	106	34	2.5	22	.15	1.6	18	.08
19	14	87	6.7	2.1	21	.12	1.7	22	.10
20	3.9	10	.10	2.1	16	.09	1.7	26	.12
21	2.8	10	.08	1.9	12	.06	2.0	30	.17
22	2.4	10	.07	2.0	10	.05	2.6	25	.13
23	2.2	10	.06	1.8	12	.06	1.9	18	.10
24	2.2	10	.06	2.0	16	.09	2.0	14	.08
25	2.3	10	.06	1.8	23	.11	2.5	16	.10
26	2.5	10	.07	1.8	38	.18	2.7	20	.14
27	1.9	10	.05	1.8	35	.17	2.2	23	.14
28	1.8	10	.05	1.9	28	.14	2.1	17	.10
29	1.8	10	.05	---	---	---	1.7	11	.05
30	1.6	9	.04	---	---	---	13	158	11
31	1.6	8	.04	---	---	---	4.0	42	.59
TOTAL	90.8	---	42.41	215.2	---	1351.07	72.6	---	14.62
DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	16	335	69	7.4	32	.64	18	5	.25
2	31	394	86	7.3	43	.85	17	10	.46
3	15	206	9.2	7.8	48	1.0	21	110	11
4	5.5	69	1.1	7.5	53	1.1	45	297	88
5	2.9	23	.19	7.5	53	1.1	53	836	464
6	2.1	11	.06	16	84	19	34	73	6.9
7	86	1680	1290	11	87	2.7	29	30	2.3
8	53	130	22	13	168	3.4	28	29	2.2
9	28	26	2.0	15	138	5.8	26	28	2.0
10	17	32	1.4	9.5	61	1.6	25	28	1.9
11	17	62	3.5	7.7	38	.81	23	27	1.7
12	217	2230	2060	7.0	28	.53	23	27	1.7
13	58	685	111	22	176	27	22	26	1.6
14	26	384	28	67	933	429	19	26	1.3
15	17	215	9.8	74	727	176	18	26	1.2
16	13	121	4.3	36	73	7.6	27	121	12
17	11	68	2.0	29	34	2.7	40	246	65
18	10	39	1.1	124	2030	3300	25	217	14
19	9.0	39	.95	42	560	98	14	130	4.8
20	8.6	46	1.1	243	2160	6340	11	87	2.7
21	11	78	2.6	456	2560	10200	11	56	1.7
22	11	109	2.6	165	254	142	18	37	1.8
23	14	127	5.5	87	105	24	10	24	.67
24	13	91	3.3	62	127	21	9.2	16	.39
25	9.7	40	1.0	45	147	18	9.0	10	.25
26	9.0	28	.69	43	88	10	8.4	7	.15
27	7.7	24	.49	31	37	3.2	7.2	5	.09
28	7.0	18	.35	27	4	.31	6.9	7	.14
29	6.3	6	.10	24	2	.15	6.3	15	.25
30	6.8	12	.22	22	3	.15	6.0	28	.45
31	---	---	---	20	3	.16	---	---	---
TOTAL	738.6	---	3719.55	1735.7	---	20837.80	610.0	---	690.90

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	5.4	21	.30	7.1	28	3.7	14	9	.32
2	4.8	12	.15	12	75	8.3	30	224	47
3	4.4	7	.08	7.4	60	1.4	93	621	257
4	5.6	5	.08	3.4	22	.20	153	700	678
5	5.8	5	.07	2.5	16	.11	37	32	3.0
6	4.2	5	.05	4.1	22	.32	150	337	363
7	4.6	4	.05	19	103	20	92	77	23
8	4.5	3	.04	31	230	37	49	15	2.0
9	4.3	3	.04	19	211	12	35	7	.69
10	4.7	3	.04	11	80	2.5	28	4	.27
11	4.6	3	.04	13	92	6.2	47	240	63
12	4.5	3	.04	18	148	7.0	34	247	35
13	4.9	3	.04	13	57	2.1	23	35	2.2
14	10	3	.09	6.2	23	.40	18	4	.20
15	15	3	.12	3.4	15	.14	18	4	.19
16	12	3	.10	3.0	13	.23	34	246	44
17	9.8	3	.08	10	80	4.0	19	283	8.3
18	9.5	3	.08	3.3	27	.24	41	448	84
19	7.6	3	.07	3.9	19	.20	37	379	40
20	9.5	4	.10	14	167	6.9	26	226	16
21	11	4	.13	9.0	106	2.5	1050	6200	52000
22	6.5	5	.09	122	93	e252	e1740	11800	e93300
23	4.8	6	.07	33	128	e42	e224	1110	e4920
24	4.7	6	.08	455	131	e10200	e115	345	e252
25	4.8	7	.09	146	80	e252	e85	115	e252
26	3.8	8	.08	52	24	3.7	e73	77	e429
27	5.9	9	.14	34	9	.85	e63	60	e199
28	4.7	10	.13	24	6	.36	e59	47	e199
29	4.1	12	.13	19	3	.18	e93	37	e252
30	3.6	13	.13	16	4	.17	e86	28	e252
31	3.2	15	.13	14	6	.22	---	---	---
TOTAL	192.8	---	2.86	1128.3	---	10866.92	4566	---	153722.17
YEAR	10697.0		196458.35						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
OCT					
15...	1500	212	942	539	98
15...	1600	224	882	533	91
APR					
02...	1615	64	1980	342	99
07...	1520	437	9410	11100	66
MAY					
18...	1645	1020	31700	87300	61
20...	2015	1530	18300	75600	39
21...	2330	327	537	474	89
SEP					
06...	1645	1390	881	3310	83
11...	1645	279	4700	3540	67

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PEN- DED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PEN- DED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)	
DATE		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70335)
OCT								
08...	1600	363	8780	8610	27	37	51	
MAR								
30...	1645	23	959	60	63	77	90	
APR								
07...	1425	534	6870	9910	30	39	50	
MAY								
20...	1815	1500	14400	58300	14	19	25	
21...	1630	2790	22800	172000	14	20	26	
21...	1815	2080	11100	62300	7	9	11	
SEP								
04...	0230	428	7670	8860	22	29	39	
OCT								
08...	65	81	87	96	99	100	100	
MAR								
30...	97	97	99	100	100	100	100	
APR								
07...	59	63	68	82	95	100	100	
MAY								
20...	30	37	41	53	73	92	98	
21...	33	40	44	55	73	90	97	
21...	14	17	18	24	37	62	86	
SEP								
04...	50	61	64	81	93	98	100	

RIO TOA VACA BASIN

50111210 LAGO TOA VACA AT DAMSITE NEAR VILLALBA, PR--Continued

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	489.90	499.32	500.12	499.88	---	501.45	497.88	500.21	506.24	504.44	500.90	502.02
2	489.89	499.33	500.12	499.85	499.70	501.32	498.04	500.09	506.16	504.33	500.79	502.03
3	489.89	499.34	500.11	499.85	499.65	501.22	497.97	499.97	506.10	504.20	500.67	502.52
4	489.88	499.34	500.10	499.83	499.71	501.09	497.87	499.84	506.12	504.11	500.53	503.80
5	489.86	499.36	500.09	499.81	501.90	500.96	497.74	499.72	506.26	504.00	500.41	503.86
6	489.84	499.36	500.08	499.81	501.94	500.83	497.62	499.73	506.19	503.92	---	504.73
7	489.85	499.38	500.07	499.84	501.95	500.70	498.89	499.66	506.12	---	500.35	504.99
8	490.58	499.41	500.06	499.82	---	500.57	498.91	499.58	506.05	---	500.34	505.03
9	490.76	499.54	500.06	499.82	502.32	500.43	498.81	499.49	505.98	---	500.24	505.02
10	490.81	499.68	500.05	499.81	502.30	500.29	498.71	499.38	505.89	---	500.12	504.99
11	491.35	499.70	500.03	499.81	502.30	500.14	498.67	499.26	505.79	---	500.02	505.11
12	491.51	499.72	500.02	499.81	502.29	500.01	501.53	499.15	505.70	---	499.92	505.20
13	492.56	499.73	500.02	499.81	502.28	499.87	501.73	499.21	505.61	---	499.80	505.20
14	495.73	499.72	500.02	499.80	502.31	499.74	501.72	499.63	505.51	---	499.67	505.14
15	497.35	500.11	500.01	499.80	502.31	499.60	501.67	499.96	505.40	---	499.55	505.11
16	497.82	500.13	499.99	499.78	502.30	499.47	501.58	499.96	505.34	---	499.41	505.21
17	498.45	500.14	500.00	499.76	502.29	499.32	501.50	499.90	505.80	---	499.38	505.15
18	498.68	500.14	499.99	499.77	502.31	499.18	501.49	500.79	505.76	---	499.26	505.23
19	498.83	500.15	500.00	499.78	---	499.04	501.40	501.11	505.66	---	499.13	505.24
20	498.94	500.15	499.98	499.78	502.28	498.93	501.30	503.14	505.56	---	499.01	505.20
21	499.02	500.14	499.99	499.77	---	498.80	501.21	505.82	505.52	---	498.89	512.73
22	499.08	500.14	499.98	499.83	502.26	498.68	501.13	506.35	505.46	---	499.23	529.60
23	499.13	500.14	499.98	499.80	502.21	498.54	501.05	506.55	505.35	---	499.31	531.01
24	499.16	500.14	499.97	499.78	502.12	498.41	500.97	506.58	505.24	---	500.62	530.58
25	499.20	500.13	499.95	499.79	501.98	498.29	500.88	506.58	505.13	---	502.29	528.79
26	499.23	500.13	499.93	499.77	501.85	498.15	500.78	506.58	505.02	---	502.37	526.73
27	499.25	500.13	499.92	499.75	501.72	498.02	500.70	506.55	504.90	---	502.42	526.17
28	499.27	500.13	499.92	499.75	501.59	497.89	500.58	506.50	504.79	---	502.36	526.52
29	499.29	500.12	499.91	499.74	---	497.77	500.45	506.44	504.67	---	502.30	526.74
30	499.30	500.11	499.90	499.73	---	497.87	500.34	506.38	504.55	---	502.21	526.89
31	499.31	---	499.88	499.71	---	497.76	---	506.31	---	500.92	502.11	---
TOTAL	15353.72	14995.06	15500.25	15493.64	---	15484.34	15003.12	15570.42	15167.87	---	---	15356.54
MAX	499.31	500.15	500.12	499.88	---	501.45	501.73	506.58	506.26	---	---	531.01
MIN	489.84	499.32	499.88	499.71	---	497.76	497.62	499.15	504.55	---	---	502.02

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50111300 LAGO GUAYABAL AT DAMSITE NEAR JUANA DIAZ, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'17", long 66°30'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Damsite, 2.30 mi (3.70 km) northeast from Juana Díaz Plaza, 0.70 mi (1.13 km) northeast from Escuela Salvador Bousquets and 2.45 mi (3.94 km) southeast from Escuela Zoilo Gracia.

DRAINAGE AREA.--21.0 mi² (54.4 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1995 to current year.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Guayabal was completed in 1913. The dam is a reinforced concrete, flatslab and buttress-type structure about 130 ft (40 m) height, a net crest length at the right side of the dam of 693 ft (211 m) and a crest elevation of 331 ft (101 m). It has a maximum storage capacity of 7,600 acre-feet (9.37 km³). The Guayabal Dam is owned by the Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority (P.R.E.P.A) and its primary purpose is for irrigation of lands served by the Juana Díaz Canal. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 341.55 ft (104.10 m), Sept. 10, 1996; minimum elevation, 325.99 ft (99.36 m), Sept. 29, 1997.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 341.42 ft (104.06 m), May 21; minimum elevation, 328.59 ft (100.20 m), Oct. 5.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
305	366	330	3,885
321	2,010	341	7,360

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	328.90	340.35	339.52	335.67	333.66	335.75	333.68	340.37	340.73	340.72	340.64	340.78
2	328.87	340.23	339.40	335.52	333.46	335.66	334.39	340.32	340.71	340.72	340.77	340.92
3	328.79	340.20	339.31	335.33	333.34	335.63	334.52	340.32	340.71	340.70	340.81	341.00
4	328.65	340.18	339.25	335.13	333.45	335.56	334.44	340.38	340.91	340.70	340.79	340.88
5	328.63	340.15	339.17	334.99	335.81	335.45	334.36	340.42	340.84	340.66	340.79	340.86
6	328.77	340.21	338.98	334.79	336.17	335.34	334.38	340.70	340.71	340.83	340.88	340.94
7	329.25	340.25	338.82	334.72	336.23	335.13	339.26	340.83	340.67	340.69	340.90	340.83
8	331.23	340.30	338.75	334.64	336.81	334.94	339.59	340.87	340.74	340.63	340.98	340.89
9	331.91	340.52	338.68	334.78	337.34	334.85	339.61	340.81	340.76	340.68	340.84	340.90
10	332.44	340.82	338.59	334.82	337.55	334.73	339.57	340.77	340.77	340.69	340.84	340.92
11	333.33	340.78	338.49	334.89	337.70	334.61	339.63	340.80	340.76	340.56	340.93	340.95
12	334.02	340.79	338.38	335.07	337.87	334.48	340.97	340.79	340.75	340.49	340.89	340.87
13	337.44	340.79	338.19	335.32	337.78	334.37	340.79	341.06	340.67	340.51	340.86	340.98
14	340.99	340.80	338.02	335.49	337.68	334.13	340.74	340.99	340.61	340.88	340.84	340.92
15	340.91	340.89	337.96	335.65	337.60	333.96	340.77	340.91	340.67	340.83	340.75	340.87
16	340.83	340.75	337.88	335.77	337.50	333.93	340.79	340.86	340.78	340.80	340.75	340.94
17	340.81	340.77	337.86	335.80	337.41	333.80	340.78	340.83	340.88	340.80	340.92	340.82
18	340.78	340.77	337.83	335.88	337.35	333.69	340.86	340.96	340.83	340.72	340.91	340.95
19	340.74	340.74	337.75	336.04	337.25	333.56	340.79	340.88	340.77	340.67	340.87	340.95
20	340.81	340.71	337.60	335.84	337.11	333.50	340.91	341.00	340.69	340.71	340.85	340.91
21	340.80	340.75	337.47	335.67	336.89	333.33	340.87	340.85	340.74	340.73	340.88	A
22	340.79	340.70	337.35	335.68	336.69	333.19	340.85	340.80	340.80	340.79	340.86	A
23	340.79	340.68	337.20	335.48	336.58	333.06	340.83	340.86	340.72	340.80	340.81	A
24	340.80	340.57	337.07	335.25	336.54	332.98	340.84	340.79	340.72	340.78	341.07	A
25	340.66	340.49	336.87	335.00	336.46	332.92	340.78	340.80	340.70	340.67	340.91	A
26	340.62	340.37	336.72	334.94	336.35	332.83	340.78	340.83	340.73	340.61	340.87	A
27	340.64	340.16	336.53	334.82	336.13	332.79	340.82	340.83	340.68	340.59	340.94	A
28	340.71	340.00	336.34	334.59	335.94	332.59	340.69	340.84	340.66	340.55	340.87	A
29	340.72	339.78	336.20	334.39	---	332.46	340.58	340.83	340.71	340.51	340.85	A
30	340.60	339.61	336.04	334.13	---	333.25	340.43	340.80	340.73	340.45	340.85	341.01
31	340.51	---	335.86	333.89	---	333.38	---	340.78	---	340.45	340.85	---
MAX	340.99	340.89	339.52	336.04	337.87	335.75	340.97	341.06	340.91	340.88	341.07	---
MIN	328.63	339.61	335.86	333.89	333.34	332.46	333.68	340.32	340.61	340.45	340.64	---

A No gage-height record

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50111500 RIO JACAGUAS AT JUANA DIAZ, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'16", long 66°30'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on Highway 14 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Juana Díaz plaza, and 4.0 mi (6.4 km) downstream from Lago Guayabal.

DRAINAGE AREA.--49.8 mi² (129.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 131 ft (40 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Flow regulation from Lago Guayabal. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1.2	20	e6.6	e2.9	1.5	3.5	16	36	60	11	6.0	131
2	1.1	19	e5.5	e4.0	1.4	3.1	10	12	40	9.4	6.8	92
3	1.1	17	e5.2	e2.2	1.3	3.8	5.2	9.6	30	10	15	379
4	1.1	13	e5.2	e2.0	1.4	4.4	3.6	9.1	80	11	20	611
5	.96	11	e11	e1.3	127	3.7	2.9	8.7	233	10	14	289
6	.84	9.7	e15	e2.0	34	3.2	2.6	8.5	112	52	e37	314
7	.99	9.2	e12	e2.0	14	3.8	14	8.6	53	54	162	250
8	1.1	9.6	e11	e1.9	9.9	3.4	35	16	33	13	147	179
9	6.8	9.6	e9.8	e1.5	12	2.7	32	24	39	6.8	124	223
10	5.2	39	e9.3	e2.1	9.0	2.1	24	14	38	8.3	73	224
11	55	50	e9.7	e2.1	7.4	2.1	18	9.8	35	7.4	75	253
12	9.1	37	e8.6	e1.7	6.7	2.0	186	9.0	31	4.1	105	277
13	38	37	e7.6	e1.6	5.8	1.9	153	9.4	22	3.2	83	218
14	363	37	e6.9	e1.5	6.1	1.9	96	128	11	7.2	62	230
15	397	72	e6.3	e1.2	7.5	2.0	66	125	8.2	99	41	230
16	228	75	e5.7	e1.2	5.8	1.9	53	90	11	85	20	228
17	355	42	e7.1	e1.2	5.0	1.8	51	52	111	67	43	242
18	198	40	e6.4	e1.4	5.3	1.7	53	44	92	39	83	189
19	113	36	e6.7	e1.6	5.8	1.7	61	88	63	15	75	263
20	95	23	e6.8	e1.5	5.5	1.6	40	153	31	9.2	59	262
21	103	19	e4.9	e3.3	5.3	2.0	81	425	15	12	51	1230
22	97	25	e3.2	e1.2	5.6	2.0	66	218	36	14	285	8530
23	89	19	e3.4	1.2	5.4	1.9	51	159	35	12	124	863
24	84	15	e3.1	1.4	6.5	1.9	49	136	17	15	427	959
25	73	e11	e2.6	1.5	4.4	2.6	45	115	15	11	828	1030
26	55	e11	e2.2	1.3	4.1	2.3	27	111	12	5.2	291	938
27	44	e9.7	e2.8	1.3	3.8	2.0	24	110	14	4.8	233	715
28	38	e8.3	e2.2	1.3	3.4	2.0	55	101	8.4	6.3	232	230
29	40	e7.9	e1.7	1.2	---	2.0	42	92	7.3	4.9	185	219
30	36	e7.4	e1.5	1.3	---	25	40	91	9.2	4.9	165	199
31	25	---	e2.2	1.2	---	7.3	---	84	---	5.1	145	---
TOTAL	2555.49	739.4	192.2	53.1	310.9	103.3	1402.3	2496.7	1302.1	616.8	4216.8	19997
MEAN	82.4	24.6	6.20	1.71	11.1	3.33	46.7	80.5	43.4	19.9	136	667
MAX	397	75	15	4.0	127	25	186	425	233	99	828	8530
MIN	.84	7.4	1.5	1.2	1.3	1.6	2.6	8.5	7.3	3.2	6.0	92
AC-FT	5070	1470	381	105	617	205	2780	4950	2580	1220	8360	39660
CFSM	1.66	.49	.12	.03	.22	.07	.94	1.62	.87	.40	2.73	13.4
IN.	1.91	.55	.14	.04	.23	.08	1.05	1.87	.97	.46	3.15	14.94

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	114	81.6	32.5	23.0	9.04	5.03	13.2	66.5	38.6	21.7	26.9	81.8			
MAX	445	287	151	144	16.9	8.60	46.7	215	198	82.4	136	667			
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1992	1991	1996	1998	1985	1987	1987	1998	1998			
MIN	4.31	7.57	6.20	1.71	1.98	1.95	1.84	1.46	.93	1.04	1.59	.76			
(WY)	1995	1995	1998	1998	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994	1997			

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1998 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1984 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	5482.05	33986.09	
ANNUAL MEAN	15.0	93.1	44.1
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			93.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			6.23
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	397	8530	8530
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.37	.84	.24
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.51	1.0	.51
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		37600	40000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		28.71	29.42
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	10870	67410	31940
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.30	1.87	.89
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	4.10	25.39	12.03
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	33	218	93
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.3	13	8.2
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.84	1.7	2.2

e Estimated

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50111500 RIO JACAGUAS AT JUANA DIAZ, PR--Continued

Figure 22. South coast river basins -- Río Inabón to Río Loco basins.

RIO INABON BASIN

50112500 RIO INABON AT REAL ABAJO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'10", long 66°33'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on private road, off Highway 511 at Hacienda La Concordia, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) upstream from diversion canal, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) north of Real Abajo, and 6.1 mi (9.8 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.70 mi² (25.12 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1962-63 (annual low-flow measurements only), February to June 1964 (monthly measurements only), July 1964 to July 1970, April 1971 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 410 ft (125 m), from topographic map. Prior to April 1971 non-recording gage and crest-stage gage at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.8	13	7.5	3.6	3.1	4.1	e21	28	22	15	17	13
2	6.6	14	8.5	3.8	3.1	4.3	e22	28	22	14	22	28
3	5.0	16	6.7	4.0	3.1	4.1	e22	28	26	15	17	78
4	4.4	15	6.2	4.2	12	4.2	20	29	41	15	13	79
5	3.8	14	5.4	3.9	e104	3.5	15	29	67	14	12	38
6	3.6	13	5.3	3.9	11	3.1	12	35	41	23	18	46
7	e30	13	5.3	7.6	5.6	e7.1	e100	35	29	20	26	37
8	e18	e13	5.0	6.2	14	e11	88	39	25	14	39	30
9	e27	e15	4.6	4.0	e16	5.7	37	38	24	15	23	26
10	e22	e27	4.5	4.4	6.9	4.2	30	31	23	e20	18	22
11	16	12	4.5	4.1	5.0	3.9	26	28	21	e16	19	26
12	13	10	4.3	8.1	4.2	3.8	54	27	20	15	17	24
13	79	9.2	4.6	6.3	3.6	3.7	43	32	19	e15	13	e32
14	290	7.6	4.3	4.3	4.1	e5.8	30	75	20	35	11	33
15	105	22	4.8	3.5	6.0	e26	24	51	21	e29	10	32
16	53	e16	4.6	3.4	4.8	19	21	32	24	18	8.6	44
17	179	10	4.2	3.4	4.9	10	19	25	35	15	12	47
18	87	8.0	4.5	4.0	3.8	7.2	46	21	e22	14	12	44
19	32	7.5	5.1	7.3	4.2	5.7	e36	18	17	19	11	40
20	22	7.7	4.6	6.4	4.6	6.3	52	34	16	25	10	36
21	17	7.2	5.2	3.9	5.3	e6.6	46	36	e16	23	14	e166
22	15	7.6	4.8	4.2	5.6	6.5	34	24	e19	21	21	e416
23	13	6.6	3.8	3.8	5.5	7.4	31	25	17	21	18	137
24	11	6.4	3.5	3.5	4.4	5.3	49	22	17	15	116	e88
25	11	6.3	3.4	3.6	3.4	6.0	46	21	16	13	e198	70
26	10	6.8	3.5	3.8	3.3	8.6	38	21	16	12	40	61
27	11	7.6	3.4	3.4	3.5	5.7	33	21	16	11	44	66
28	12	6.1	3.4	3.4	3.4	5.3	30	19	15	12	33	55
29	13	11	3.6	3.4	---	e4.6	27	19	15	11	22	49
30	13	13	e3.5	3.6	---	e36	26	20	15	12	17	49
31	13	---	3.5	3.3	---	e30	---	21	---	14	13	---
TOTAL	1143.2	341.6	146.1	136.3	258.4	264.7	1078	912	697	531	864.6	1912
MEAN	36.9	11.4	4.71	4.40	9.23	8.54	35.9	29.4	23.2	17.1	27.9	63.7
MAX	290	27	8.5	8.1	104	36	100	75	67	35	198	416
MIN	3.6	6.1	3.4	3.3	3.1	3.1	12	18	15	11	8.6	13
AC-FT	2270	678	290	270	513	525	2140	1810	1380	1050	1710	3790
CFSM	3.80	1.17	.49	.45	.95	.88	3.70	3.03	2.40	1.77	2.88	6.57
IN.	4.38	1.31	.56	.52	.99	1.02	4.13	3.50	2.67	2.04	3.32	7.33

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	45.0	32.5	12.0	8.48	5.86	5.82	8.90	19.5	15.9	11.8	17.3	33.8
MAX	148	77.9	26.5	45.5	13.1	16.4	35.9	76.7	49.8	32.7	46.1	119
(WY)	1986	1978	1966	1992	1996	1972	1998	1969	1969	1979	1979	1975
MIN	14.5	8.32	4.43	4.11	3.05	1.85	2.76	1.94	2.75	1.77	4.47	6.16
(WY)	1994	1977	1977	1989	1977	1977	1975	1967	1967	1990	1974	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1964 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	3289.3	8284.9	
ANNUAL MEAN	9.01	22.7	17.9
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			30.9
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			7.44
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	290	Oct 14	416
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.7	May 25	3.1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.0	May 14	3.3
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			3470
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			17.94
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	6520	16430	13000
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.93	2.34	1.85
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	12.61	31.77	25.13
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15	44	39
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.7	15	9.0
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.7	3.8	3.2

e Estimated

RIO INABON BASIN

50112500 RIO INABON AT REAL ABAJO, PR--Continued

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50113800 RIO CERRILLOS ABOVE LAGO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'01", long 66°36'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) downstream from confluence with Rio San Patricio, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) southwest of Hwy 139 and 2.4 mi (3.7 km) northwest of Mayagüez.

DRAINAGE AREA.-- 15.4 mi² (39.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 720 ft (210 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.1	14	14	7.9	6.1	6.3	61	e13	20	17	27	61
2	7.4	14	14	7.8	5.8	6.4	68	e13	19	29	39	86
3	6.9	13	13	7.4	5.6	6.4	e40	e13	29	21	25	127
4	6.4	13	12	7.4	22	6.7	e21	e13	50	18	19	160
5	6.1	13	11	7.3	96	6.1	16	e13	87	17	17	112
6	6.0	12	11	8.6	18	5.7	14	e31	57	19	23	123
7	65	12	10	14	11	14	341	e20	33	18	41	112
8	59	12	10	9.7	31	9.6	75	e35	27	16	73	89
9	45	33	9.8	7.7	32	6.5	29	e28	24	15	83	79
10	62	43	10	7.5	14	5.8	19	e19	22	19	106	67
11	60	15	10	7.3	11	5.5	19	e18	20	17	142	76
12	64	13	10	8.3	9.7	5.4	79	e18	19	14	111	74
13	151	11	10	7.8	8.7	5.3	58	e37	18	14	89	80
14	261	11	9.9	7.6	9.8	11	28	103	18	45	69	68
15	203	41	9.8	6.9	11	34	21	114	17	69	60	62
16	104	30	9.6	6.7	8.7	15	18	74	33	66	56	91
17	178	18	9.6	6.6	8.1	9.1	16	49	78	53	59	113
18	118	15	12	6.8	7.9	7.2	19	37	65	46	51	107
19	65	14	11	7.8	7.5	6.2	18	31	42	39	46	93
20	44	13	9.5	7.0	7.3	7.3	32	43	29	36	45	72
21	34	13	11	6.5	7.2	8.1	26	48	27	28	65	e384
22	28	12	9.8	6.7	7.0	e6.8	18	36	36	23	107	2510
23	24	12	9.5	6.3	6.9	e7.9	18	44	25	31	82	271
24	22	11	9.0	6.3	7.2	e6.4	39	35	32	25	302	177
25	20	15	8.8	6.6	6.6	e6.1	e36	28	26	21	309	150
26	19	18	8.6	6.7	7.3	e8.7	25	26	21	19	109	132
27	18	14	8.6	6.2	6.6	7.3	e22	24	20	19	111	122
28	17	12	8.6	6.8	6.2	7.0	e17	22	19	20	104	109
29	16	27	8.4	7.2	---	16	14	21	18	18	e81	97
30	15	18	8.4	6.7	---	47	13	21	18	17	65	90
31	15	---	8.4	6.1	---	28	---	20	---	18	67	---
TOTAL	1747.9	512	315.3	230.2	386.2	328.8	1220	1047	949	827	2583	5894
MEAN	56.4	17.1	10.2	7.43	13.8	10.6	40.7	33.8	31.6	26.7	83.3	196
MAX	261	43	14	14	96	47	341	114	87	69	309	2510
MIN	6.0	11	8.4	6.1	5.6	5.3	13	13	17	14	17	61
AC-FT	3470	1020	625	457	766	652	2420	2080	1880	1640	5120	11690
CFSM	4.74	1.43	.85	.62	1.16	.89	3.42	2.84	2.66	2.24	7.00	16.5
IN.	5.46	1.60	.99	.72	1.21	1.03	3.81	3.27	2.97	2.59	8.07	18.42

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998		
MEAN	64.5	31.7	15.1	15.8	12.3	11.0	16.4	25.0	23.5	15.8	33.7	69.3
MAX	154	59.3	26.2	59.0	26.1	27.5	40.7	68.2	46.4	26.7	83.3	196
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1996	1989	1998	1993	1996	1991	1998	1998
MIN	24.6	9.77	8.10	6.59	6.34	4.77	5.01	4.58	4.14	3.37	11.3	13.1
(WY)	1992	1994	1995	1995	1990	1990	1997	1990	1997	1994	1994	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1998

	1997 CALENDAR YEAR	1998 WATER YEAR	1989 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	5019.4	16040.4	
ANNUAL MEAN	13.8	43.9	27.7
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			43.9
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			9.94
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	261	2510	2510
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.1	5.3	3.0
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.3	6.3	3.2
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		16200	16200
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		12.42	12.42
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		5.1	3.0
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	9960	31820	20060
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.16	3.69	2.33
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	15.69	50.14	31.61
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	22	92	61
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.5	18	14
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.0	6.8	4.8

e Estimated

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50113800 RIO CERRILLOS ABOVE LAGO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR--Continued

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50113950 LAGO CERRILLOS AT DAMSITE NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'41", long 66°34'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank west from intake house of dam, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) southwest from Iglesia San Mateo at Real Abajo, 3.2 mi (5.1 km) northeast from Hospital de Distrito de Ponce, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest from Escuela Yuca.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.4 mi² (45.1 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1992 to current year .

REVISED RECORDS.--WDR PR-94-1: 1993,1994.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lake is formed by Cerrillos Dam, a rockfilled ungated structure completed in 1992. Elevation of crest is 611 ft (186 m) above mean sea level, with a structural height of 323 ft (98 m) and a length of 1,555 ft (474 m). The dam has a capacity of approximately 47,900 ac-ft (59.1 hm³). The dam is operated by U.S. Army Corps of Engineers and its purpose is for flood control, water supply, power generation, and recreation. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 602.84 ft (183.74 m), Sept. 22, 1998; minimum elevation, 416.63 ft (126.99 m), Oct. 1, 1992, (Revised).

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 602.84 ft (183.74 m), Sept. 22; minimum elevation, 551.69 ft (168.15 m), Feb. 26.

Capacity Table

(based on data from U.S. Army Corps of Engineers)

Elevation , in feet	Contents in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents in acre-feet
328	0	558	25,786
426	3,206	590	37,509
492	10,621	611	42,520
525	16,990		

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	558.71	568.57	565.39	559.86	553.97	551.71	553.69	563.49	569.31	572.33	572.49	573.00
2	558.49	568.43	565.24	559.66	553.71	551.70	554.14	563.53	569.39	572.44	572.73	573.22
3	558.31	568.29	565.08	559.49	553.52	551.71	554.22	563.59	569.52	572.50	572.80	574.59
4	558.13	568.15	564.91	559.27	554.14	551.73	554.43	563.64	569.87	572.57	572.85	573.91
5	557.93	568.04	564.75	559.07	554.52	551.73	554.49	563.70	570.65	572.60	572.87	573.36
6	557.73	567.88	564.58	558.93	554.38	551.73	554.56	563.88	570.87	572.82	572.97	571.54
7	558.11	567.75	564.41	558.79	554.25	551.78	558.82	564.00	571.02	572.90	573.17	568.84
8	558.48	567.62	564.23	558.64	554.33	551.80	559.31	564.26	571.13	572.92	573.90	568.93
9	558.66	567.84	564.03	558.43	554.27	551.79	559.50	564.38	571.24	572.94	574.45	569.31
10	558.98	567.80	563.88	558.25	554.13	551.79	559.61	564.47	571.31	573.02	574.88	569.58
11	559.37	567.68	563.69	558.06	553.97	551.81	559.88	564.53	571.38	573.06	575.45	570.05
12	559.58	567.57	563.48	557.94	553.77	551.81	560.60	564.58	571.45	573.08	575.36	570.40
13	562.28	567.43	563.31	557.75	553.62	551.81	560.91	564.98	571.51	573.06	575.05	570.87
14	564.20	567.30	563.14	557.49	553.48	551.86	561.10	566.14	571.57	573.19	572.94	571.06
15	565.98	567.54	562.93	A	553.38	552.04	561.22	566.77	571.65	573.41	572.40	571.38
16	566.39	567.49	562.75	557.13	553.18	552.09	561.33	567.10	571.78	573.62	572.40	572.11
17	568.97	567.40	562.57	556.92	552.99	552.10	561.42	567.30	572.47	573.73	572.48	572.83
18	569.51	567.27	562.45	556.72	552.84	552.11	561.61	567.43	572.79	573.81	572.28	573.05
19	569.72	567.12	562.27	556.51	552.64	552.12	561.73	567.57	572.93	573.83	572.20	572.90
20	569.77	566.95	562.08	556.30	551.85	552.14	561.93	567.91	572.92	573.81	572.17	572.64
21	569.77	566.81	561.92	556.08	551.62	552.14	562.09	568.07	A	573.59	572.34	574.61
22	569.73	566.65	A	555.88	551.40	552.19	562.18	568.24	572.71	573.38	572.71	600.03
23	569.64	566.51	561.55	555.66	551.75	552.20	562.28	568.51	572.67	573.21	572.81	589.57
24	569.57	566.33	561.36	555.47	551.72	552.19	562.71	568.65	572.77	573.01	577.46	583.59
25	569.48	566.16	561.18	555.26	551.70	552.25	562.94	568.75	572.70	572.78	575.11	577.11
26	569.36	566.03	560.96	555.05	551.71	552.33	563.12	568.87	572.63	572.55	573.78	575.08
27	569.25	565.90	560.80	554.89	551.71	552.34	563.23	568.96	572.57	572.60	574.16	573.58
28	569.13	565.74	560.63	554.74	551.70	552.35	563.33	569.03	572.47	572.58	574.07	572.98
29	568.99	565.66	560.43	554.55	---	552.46	563.39	569.08	572.37	572.46	573.87	573.10
30	568.85	565.53	560.28	554.37	---	553.01	563.44	569.18	572.28	572.36	573.54	572.77
31	568.72	---	560.07	554.14	---	553.18	---	569.24	---	572.41	573.28	---
MAX	569.77	568.57	---	---	554.52	553.18	563.44	569.24	---	573.83	577.46	600.03
MIN	557.73	565.53	---	---	551.40	551.70	553.69	563.49	---	572.33	572.17	568.84

A No gage-height record

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114000 RIO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'15", long 66°34'51", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank off Highway 139, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) below Lago Cerrillos Dam, 2.3 mi (3.7 km) upstream from Quebrada Ausubo and 4.6 mi (7.4 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.8 mi² (46.1 km²), excludes 17.4 mi² (45.1 km²), upstream from Lago Cerrillos Dam.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February to April 1964 (monthly measurements only), May 1964 to June 1985, July 1985 to April 1991 (semi-monthly measurements only), May 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 253.10 ft (77.145 m), above mean sea level. Prior to March 22, 1977 at site 0.15 mi (0.24 km) upstream and datum 9.90 ft (3.018 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Flow regulated by Lago Cerrillos Dam since May 1991. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Prior to June 1985 some low-flow regulation by construction upstream. Maximum discharge prior to regulation, 22,400 ft³/s (6.34 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage-height, 11.2 ft (3.414 m), site and datum then in use from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 150 ft³/s (4.25 m³/s), on basis of slope-area measurements of peak flow; minimum discharge prior to regulation, 2.2 ft³/s (0.062 m³/s), May 28, 1967.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	4.2	5.1	5.6	4.4	4.0	e4.4	4.3	4.1	4.8	17	4.0	114
2	4.3	5.1	5.6	4.4	4.0	e4.4	5.5	4.1	4.9	4.0	3.9	114
3	4.4	5.1	5.5	4.1	4.0	e4.4	4.6	4.1	5.2	3.8	3.9	114
4	4.6	4.9	5.5	3.9	5.7	e4.2	4.5	4.1	5.3	3.7	4.0	206
5	4.7	4.9	5.5	4.0	9.9	e4.2	4.4	4.1	5.0	3.7	4.0	147
6	4.7	4.7	5.5	3.9	5.0	e4.2	4.5	4.0	5.0	3.8	4.7	240
7	4.9	4.9	5.5	4.0	4.9	e4.1	e4.4	4.0	5.1	3.8	4.1	298
8	5.6	4.9	5.5	4.0	5.2	e4.2	e5.0	4.0	5.3	3.8	4.5	102
9	5.9	5.0	5.5	5.0	4.9	e4.0	e4.5	3.9	5.5	4.0	4.3	8.7
10	5.3	6.1	5.5	5.4	5.1	e3.8	e4.4	3.9	5.8	3.9	45	8.4
11	5.1	5.9	5.4	5.6	4.7	e3.8	e6.8	3.9	5.7	4.0	94	8.5
12	5.1	5.7	5.3	5.5	3.9	e4.0	e13	4.0	5.5	4.0	130	8.3
13	5.7	5.7	5.3	5.3	3.8	4.1	e5.6	4.1	5.4	17	132	8.4
14	7.2	5.5	5.1	4.8	3.9	4.2	e5.8	4.1	5.3	33	257	8.4
15	7.3	5.6	5.2	4.5	3.8	4.2	e6.6	4.1	5.3	33	161	8.6
16	6.6	5.9	5.2	4.1	3.8	4.2	e7.0	4.1	5.5	33	31	8.5
17	7.1	5.7	5.0	4.1	3.9	4.3	e6.6	4.1	5.8	32	31	8.5
18	6.5	5.5	4.9	4.1	4.0	4.4	e6.0	4.1	e5.3	32	63	53
19	6.2	5.5	4.8	3.9	4.0	4.3	e5.4	4.1	e14	32	62	106
20	6.1	5.8	4.7	3.9	4.1	4.4	e5.2	4.3	29	54	30	106
21	5.3	5.7	4.8	4.2	4.2	4.5	e6.2	4.2	29	68	30	169
22	5.6	5.9	4.7	4.6	4.1	4.4	e6.6	4.1	29	67	30	528
23	5.9	5.9	4.6	4.8	e8.5	4.4	e6.5	4.7	28	65	30	578
24	5.9	5.9	4.4	4.4	e8.5	4.6	e6.6	4.3	31	65	85	519
25	5.7	5.9	4.5	4.9	e4.7	4.6	e6.0	4.2	32	66	327	329
26	5.7	5.8	4.7	4.6	e4.7	4.5	e5.0	4.3	32	66	270	177
27	5.7	5.8	4.7	4.2	e4.5	4.6	e4.6	4.3	32	25	115	176
28	5.5	5.9	4.7	4.3	e4.4	4.6	e4.4	4.4	31	20	115	95
29	5.3	5.9	4.6	4.0	---	4.5	e4.2	4.6	31	32	115	38
30	5.3	5.7	4.6	4.2	---	7.1	4.1	4.7	31	32	115	78
31	5.3	---	4.5	4.0	---	4.6	---	4.7	---	14	115	---
TOTAL	172.7	165.9	156.9	137.1	136.2	136.2	168.3	129.7	444.7	845.5	2420.4	4363.3
MEAN	5.57	5.53	5.06	4.42	4.86	4.39	5.61	4.18	14.8	27.3	78.1	145
MAX	7.3	6.1	5.6	5.6	9.9	7.1	13	4.7	32	68	327	578
MIN	4.2	4.7	4.4	3.9	3.8	3.8	4.1	3.9	4.8	3.7	3.9	8.3
AC-FT	343	329	311	272	270	270	334	257	882	1680	4800	8650
CFSM	.31	.31	.28	.25	.27	.25	.32	.24	.83	1.53	4.39	8.17
IN.	.36	.35	.33	.29	.28	.28	.35	.27	.93	1.77	5.06	9.12

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998					
MEAN	68.4	52.5	21.2	14.5	9.47	9.85	15.0	36.2	25.9	23.6	33.2	62.7																												
MAX	202	124	49.1	74.2	20.0	20.3	106	221	88.9	71.1	82.4	256																												
(WY)	1971	1978	1966	1992	1969	1969	1985	1985	1969	1968	1968	1975																												
MIN	4.93	5.21	4.81	4.42	4.37	4.39	4.93	4.14	3.69	4.75	5.26	4.52																												
(WY)	1996	1996	1995	1998	1993	1998	1979	1967	1995	1995	1995	1997																												

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1998

	1997 CALENDAR YEAR	1998 WATER YEAR	1964 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	2888.8	9276.9	
ANNUAL MEAN	7.91	25.4	30.5
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			53.9
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			5.35
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	329	Mar 21	578
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.8	Sep 16	3.7
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.9	Sep 16	3.8
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			931
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			6.73
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	5730	18400	22130
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.44	1.43	1.72
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	6.04	19.39	23.32
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	7.5	65	73
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.5	5.1	13
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.7	4.0	4.9

e Estimated

RIO BUCANA BASIN
50114000 RIO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR--Continued

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114000 RIO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'15", long 66°34'51", Hydrologic unit 21010004, on right bank off Highway 139, 2.3 mi (3.7 km) upstream from Quebrada Ausubo and 4.6 mi (7.4 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.8 mi² (46.1 km²)

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)
OCT 20...	1130	6.1	371	7.3	27.5	.40	8.8	111	<10	K190 50
MAR 12...	1045	4.1	341	7.7	25.5	.47	9.3	114	<10	K150 40
MAY 28...	1145	4.6	341	7.8	28.0	.47	8.8	113	<10	30 30
AUG 27...	1045	115	255	7.0	25.5	.90	7.2	88	<10	370 K1700

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 20...	150	52	5.8	16	.5	.70	140	<.5	42	8.5
MAR 12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
MAY 28...	150	50	5.3	15	.5	.75	140	--	28	7.6
AUG 27...	110	20	15	6.5	.3	1.5	110	<1.0	8.5	7.1

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 20...	.28	26	235	3.85	<1	.490	.010	.500	.020	.38
MAR 12...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<.010	.090	.020	--
MAY 28...	.21	22	214	2.66	3	--	<.010	.110	<.010	--
AUG 27...	.10	29	166	51.5	<1	--	<.010	.070	.260	.17

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 20...	.40	.90	4.0	.040	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	<10
MAR 12...	<.20	--	--	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 28...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	10	<1	<1	<10
AUG 27...	.43	.50	2.2	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114390 RIO BUCANA AT HWY 14 BRIDGE NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'29", long 66°34'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, 200 ft (61 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 14 and 4.0 mi (6.4 km) downstream from Lago Cerrillos Dam, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) northeast of Degetau Plaza in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--24.9 mi² (64.5 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986 (maximum only), published as "Río Bucana Floodway Channel at Highway 14 bridge", October 1986 to July 1987 (maximum only), August 1987 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 116.4 ft (35.50 m) above mean sea level. Prior to Oct. 1, 1986, crest-stage gage located at Highway 14 bridge, at elevation of mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Flow regulated by Lago Cerrillos Dam 4.0 mi upstream. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.5	6.3	5.4	5.4	6.8	6.1	7.2	5.5	5.3	47	9.6	e541
2	5.0	7.0	5.6	5.3	6.8	5.6	9.8	5.6	5.0	4.8	8.2	521
3	5.1	7.4	5.6	5.9	6.6	5.4	7.2	5.6	5.0	5.1	7.6	517
4	5.9	6.1	5.7	5.9	6.7	5.2	5.7	5.4	4.8	7.2	7.5	e1070
5	5.6	5.7	5.9	5.6	176	6.1	5.4	5.3	4.4	4.7	8.5	e714
6	4.9	5.6	5.9	11	8.3	5.6	6.0	5.0	4.4	4.3	e7.3	e1270
7	4.6	4.9	6.0	12	7.4	5.2	7.6	5.3	3.9	4.1	e5.0	e1610
8	14	6.7	6.1	9.2	9.2	4.9	8.2	5.7	e4.5	3.6	8.4	e460
9	23	6.9	6.1	8.4	8.9	4.9	6.4	5.8	e10	3.5	5.7	e5.4
10	16	11	6.3	8.1	9.2	4.8	6.0	5.0	e13	3.3	52	e5.8
11	25	8.0	6.1	7.9	9.2	5.1	7.7	4.3	e15	3.5	204	e6.3
12	14	7.4	5.9	9.4	8.7	5.1	18	4.1	e7.6	4.0	463	e6.7
13	20	7.5	6.1	9.2	7.9	4.6	7.6	4.9	e10	6.5	560	e7.2
14	270	6.9	6.6	8.4	8.9	5.6	8.0	5.3	e10	e36	1600	e7.8
15	110	9.1	6.7	7.8	8.8	6.2	9.3	4.7	e13	61	1500	e8.3
16	36	8.5	7.0	7.3	8.2	6.2	10	5.3	e15	67	174	e8.4
17	165	7.5	7.1	7.3	8.4	5.7	9.5	4.6	e18	85	103	e7.2
18	155	6.8	6.3	7.3	8.3	5.3	8.6	4.4	e10	99	182	e15
19	18	6.8	5.9	7.3	8.5	5.2	e7.9	4.4	e7.6	87	323	e476
20	12	6.5	5.7	7.0	9.1	5.7	7.4	4.4	33	126	131	e484
21	10	5.9	6.9	6.8	8.2	5.2	8.2	5.2	42	216	128	856
22	9.8	6.0	6.7	6.8	7.2	5.8	9.3	4.6	48	215	110	e3510
23	8.6	5.9	5.8	6.6	7.3	5.4	9.1	7.0	42	201	120	e3280
24	8.8	6.0	5.7	6.6	8.3	5.0	9.6	6.2	50	200	380	e2930
25	8.7	5.9	5.7	6.7	6.7	6.4	8.7	4.7	59	206	2280	e1800
26	7.7	5.9	5.6	6.8	6.3	5.3	7.2	4.7	58	208	1880	e892
27	8.3	6.1	5.7	6.6	7.0	5.2	6.5	4.9	56	142	e523	e879
28	8.0	5.6	5.9	8.2	6.1	5.1	6.3	4.7	55	27	527	e419
29	7.4	5.7	5.8	7.3	---	5.2	5.9	4.8	58	99	532	e68
30	6.6	5.7	10	7.0	---	59	5.8	5.2	59	100	540	e306
31	6.2	---	5.7	6.8	---	26	---	5.4	---	73	541	---
TOTAL	1004.7	201.3	191.5	231.9	389.0	242.1	240.1	158.0	726.5	2349.6	12920.8	22681.1
MEAN	32.4	6.71	6.18	7.48	13.9	7.81	8.00	5.10	24.2	75.8	417	756
MAX	270	11	10	12	176	59	18	7.0	59	216	2280	3510
MIN	4.6	4.9	5.4	5.3	6.1	4.6	5.4	4.1	3.9	3.3	5.0	5.4
AC-FT	1990	399	380	460	772	480	476	313	1440	4660	25630	44990
CFSM	1.30	.27	.25	.30	.56	.31	.32	.20	.97	3.04	16.7	30.4
IN.	1.50	.30	.29	.35	.58	.36	.36	.24	1.09	3.51	19.30	33.89

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	114	56.1	16.0	40.6	10.4	13.8	13.3	22.4	23.9	22.8	72.1	131
MAX	527	222	49.1	337	19.3	48.0	42.5	94.9	80.5	75.8	417	756
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1992	1995	1989	1992	1992	1989	1998	1998	1998
MIN	6.34	5.09	5.03	4.51	4.10	4.49	4.74	4.29	4.90	4.37	4.06	5.66
(WY)	1996	1994	1996	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994	1994	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1998 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1987 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	4204.8	41336.6	
ANNUAL MEAN	11.5	113	46.0
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			113
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			7.43
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	664	Mar 21	3510
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	4.2	May 16	3.3
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.4	May 13	3.8
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			5410
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			14.41
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	8340	81990	17400
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.46	4.55	13.48
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	6.28	61.76	13.48
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10	207	33290
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.1	7.2	1.85
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.9	5.0	25.08

e Estimated

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114390 RIO BUCANA AT HWY 14 BRIDGE NEAR PONCE, PR--Continued

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50114900 RIO PORTUGUES AT TIBES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'00", long 66°38'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.6 mi (2.6 km), north from Escuela Segunda Unidad of Corral Viejo, 0.3 mi (0.50 km) south from Hacienda Burenes and 6.0 mi (9.6 km) north-east from Peñuelas Plaza Church.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.27 mi² (18.83 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1997 to September.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 918 ft (280 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Some low-flow regulation due to PRASA intakes (2) 0.85 mi (1.36 km) upstream from station . Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e1.9	5.9	5.6	3.3	2.8	e4.0	e34	7.7	9.1	6.6	15	16
2	e1.4	5.8	5.3	3.3	e2.9	e3.6	24	7.1	8.6	17	17	32
3	e1.7	5.7	5.2	3.3	2.9	4.2	e16	7.2	9.4	8.7	17	38
4	e2.0	5.6	5.0	3.2	5.7	4.8	e7.8	7.0	31	7.4	16	76
5	e1.2	5.5	e4.8	3.1	25	4.8	7.4	7.0	23	6.8	15	18
6	e1.1	5.4	e4.6	e3.5	6.9	5.0	6.9	9.0	13	6.6	e15	45
7	e2.5	5.3	4.5	3.7	5.5	7.7	66	8.5	10	6.4	21	42
8	e26	5.7	4.4	3.4	e10	4.9	50	10	9.4	6.1	41	25
9	e15	13	4.2	3.2	9.3	3.5	25	9.8	8.9	5.9	37	18
10	e20	e16	4.0	3.1	6.2	3.1	e18	8.8	8.5	9.1	29	14
11	e13	e7.9	4.0	3.3	e5.4	2.8	17	8.5	7.8	7.4	45	e21
12	e56	e6.9	3.8	3.3	4.9	2.7	50	8.4	7.4	6.6	35	30
13	e13	6.5	3.8	3.1	e4.4	3.5	34	9.3	6.9	6.2	21	e25
14	e24	e6.3	3.8	3.1	e4.5	e3.5	24	56	6.5	8.1	18	23
15	e48	11	3.8	3.0	4.4	4.4	14	79	6.1	41	17	22
16	23	8.5	3.8	3.0	e4.0	3.9	11	13	8.3	43	16	37
17	36	7.0	3.7	2.9	4.0	2.8	10	9.3	20	26	17	32
18	23	6.6	3.7	3.0	3.9	e2.6	e9.8	8.7	11	28	16	e40
19	13	e6.3	3.7	3.0	3.8	e2.7	e9.8	8.0	7.4	26	16	e39
20	11	6.1	3.6	e2.9	3.7	2.9	10	7.6	9.0	29	20	e29
21	9.6	e6.0	e3.7	2.9	3.5	3.0	8.5	16	7.9	24	27	135
22	8.7	5.9	3.6	2.9	3.4	e3.1	8.0	11	9.5	19	37	e3000
23	8.1	5.8	3.5	3.0	e3.2	3.0	8.1	16	7.4	25	21	e230
24	7.7	5.7	3.5	e2.9	3.5	3.0	8.5	11	17	19	78	e100
25	7.2	5.9	3.5	e2.9	3.4	3.2	8.4	9.4	6.5	17	130	e66
26	6.7	6.0	e3.5	2.9	3.5	2.8	8.1	8.4	7.0	16	e48	e48
27	6.5	5.8	3.4	2.7	e3.8	2.6	8.4	8.1	7.3	16	30	e100
28	6.3	5.7	3.4	2.8	3.7	2.5	8.5	8.4	7.1	16	20	e49
29	6.2	7.3	e3.4	2.9	---	3.0	7.7	8.6	6.9	15	19	e35
30	6.1	6.2	e3.4	2.8	---	3.0	7.4	8.7	6.8	15	15	e22
31	5.9	---	e3.3	2.8	---	2.4	---	8.9	---	15	14	---
TOTAL	411.8	207.3	123.5	95.2	148.2	109.0	526.3	404.4	304.7	498.9	883	4407
MEAN	13.3	6.91	3.98	3.07	5.29	3.52	17.5	13.0	10.2	16.1	28.5	147
MAX	56	16	5.6	3.7	25	7.7	66	79	31	43	130	3000
MIN	1.1	5.3	3.3	2.7	2.8	2.4	6.9	7.0	6.1	5.9	14	14
AC-FT	817	411	245	189	294	216	1040	802	604	990	1750	8740
CFSM	1.83	.95	.55	.42	.73	.48	2.41	1.79	1.40	2.21	3.92	20.2
IN.	2.11	1.06	.63	.49	.76	.56	2.69	2.07	1.56	2.55	4.52	22.55

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1998 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998
MEAN	13.3	6.91	3.98	3.07	5.29	3.52	17.5	13.0	10.2	16.1	28.5	147
MAX	13.3	6.91	3.98	3.07	5.29	3.52	17.5	13.0	10.2	16.1	28.5	147
(WY)	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998
MIN	13.3	6.91	3.98	3.07	5.29	3.52	17.5	13.0	10.2	16.1	28.5	147
(WY)	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

ANNUAL TOTAL	8119.3
ANNUAL MEAN	22.2
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	3000 Sep 22
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.1 Oct 6
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.7 Oct 1
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	10000 Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	22.46 Sep 21
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	16100
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.06
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	41.55
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	33
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	7.4
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.0

e Estimated

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN
50114900 RIO PORTUGUES AT TIBES, PR--Continued

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50114900 RIO PORTUGUES AT TIBES, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- October, 1997 to current water year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October, 1997 to current water year.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USDH-48 sediment sampler and automatic sediment sampler since 11997.

REMARKS.-- Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis. During high flow events sediments samples were collected by local observer and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, e17,500 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L March 1, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e143,000 tons (e130,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.03 ton (0.02 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, e17,500 mg/L September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L March 1, 1998.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e143,000 tons (e130,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily mean, 0.03 ton (0.02 tonne) several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	e1.9	15	e.10	5.9	21	.33	5.6	61	.93
2	e1.4	15	e.10	5.8	30	.47	5.3	65	.94
3	e1.7	15	e.10	5.7	44	.67	5.2	75	1.0
4	e2.0	15	e.10	5.6	65	.99	5.0	86	1.1
5	e1.2	15	e.10	5.5	44	.66	e4.8	92	e1.2
6	e1.1	15	e.10	5.4	24	.34	e4.6	87	e1.1
7	e2.5	15	e.10	5.3	21	.30	4.5	46	.56
8	e26	1250	e36	5.7	73	1.3	4.4	23	.28
9	e15	330	e52	13	6240	696	4.2	20	.22
10	e20	116	e95	e16	1360	e68	4.0	19	.21
11	e13	201	e20	e7.9	275	e5.9	4.0	28	.30
12	e56	351	e2010	e6.9	231	e4.3	3.8	35	.36
13	e13	610	e22	6.5	168	3.0	3.8	18	.19
14	e24	1060	e50	e6.3	127	e2.2	3.8	12	.12
15	e48	1850	e332	11	454	23	3.8	28	.29
16	23	531	78	8.5	261	6.1	3.8	66	.67
17	36	1340	312	7.0	220	4.2	3.7	73	.73
18	23	531	73	6.6	210	3.7	3.7	73	.73
19	13	614	19	e6.3	159	e2.7	3.7	74	.74
20	11	415	11	6.1	117	1.9	3.6	74	.73
21	9.6	35	.90	e6.0	85	e1.4	e3.7	66	e.66
22	8.7	47	1.1	5.9	62	.98	3.6	52	.50
23	8.1	64	1.4	5.8	33	.51	3.5	31	.29
24	7.7	86	1.8	5.7	19	.29	3.5	17	.17
25	7.2	88	1.7	5.9	30	.49	3.5	10	.09
26	6.7	69	1.2	6.0	60	.98	e3.5	6	e.06
27	6.5	54	.94	5.8	32	.50	3.4	7	.07
28	6.3	42	.71	5.7	12	.19	3.4	20	.18
29	6.2	32	.54	7.3	126	3.8	e3.4	37	e.34
30	6.1	27	.44	6.2	108	1.8	e3.4	12	e.11
31	5.9	14	.23	---	---	---	e3.3	25	e.22
TOTAL	411.8	---	3121.66	207.3	---	837.00	123.5	---	15.09

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50114900 RIO PORTUGUES AT TIBES, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	3.3	61	.53	2.8	5	.04	e4.0	2	e.03
2	3.3	61	.54	e2.9	5	e.04	e3.6	3	e.03
3	3.3	48	.42	2.9	6	.04	4.2	10	.12
4	3.2	39	.34	5.7	152	13	4.8	38	.48
5	3.1	45	.38	25	2660	301	4.8	30	.39
6	e3.5	55	e.53	6.9	728	14	5.0	13	.17
7	3.7	63	.64	5.5	510	7.6	7.7	82	5.7
8	3.4	52	.47	e10	863	e57	4.9	18	.24
9	3.2	43	.38	9.3	654	19	3.5	14	.13
10	3.1	52	.44	6.2	78	1.3	3.1	11	.09
11	3.3	64	.58	e5.4	46	e.67	2.8	9	.07
12	3.3	77	.70	4.9	29	.38	2.7	9	.06
13	3.1	60	.50	e4.4	22	e.26	3.5	27	.27
14	3.1	34	.29	e4.5	17	e.21	e3.5	71	e.67
15	3.0	13	.11	4.4	12	.14	4.4	56	.66
16	3.0	6	.05	e4.0	9	e.10	3.9	39	.41
17	2.9	13	.10	4.0	13	.14	2.8	27	.21
18	3.0	18	.14	3.9	18	.19	e2.6	20	e.14
19	3.0	22	.18	3.8	16	.16	e2.7	18	e.13
20	e2.9	21	e.16	3.7	13	.13	2.9	20	.16
21	2.9	18	.14	3.5	10	.10	3.0	32	.26
22	2.9	17	.13	3.4	6	.06	e3.1	53	e.45
23	3.0	15	.12	e3.2	4	e.03	3.0	89	.70
24	e2.9	15	e.12	3.5	5	.05	3.0	148	1.2
25	e2.9	15	e.12	3.4	7	.06	3.2	198	1.7
26	2.9	15	.12	3.5	5	.05	2.8	121	.93
27	2.7	15	.11	e3.8	3	e.04	2.6	74	.53
28	2.8	15	.11	3.7	3	.03	2.5	62	.42
29	2.9	13	.10	---	---	---	3.0	54	.43
30	2.8	7	.05	---	---	---	3.0	48	.38
31	2.8	4	.03	---	---	---	2.4	44	.28
TOTAL	95.2	---	8.63	148.2	---	415.82	109.0	---	17.44
DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	e34	2460	e757	7.7	42	.88	9.1	45	1.1
2	24	4920	618	7.1	71	1.4	8.6	62	1.4
3	e16	824	e40	7.2	52	1.0	9.4	1290	43
4	e7.8	272	6.0	7.0	31	.59	31	1730	445
5	7.4	191	3.8	7.0	26	.49	23	800	78
6	6.9	175	3.2	9.0	1770	76	13	302	11
7	66	6680	2640	8.5	265	6.1	10	51	1.5
8	50	2460	362	10	1110	52	9.4	62	1.6
9	25	531	36	9.8	413	11	8.9	98	2.4
10	e18	368	e17	8.8	355	8.5	8.5	98	2.2
11	17	1230	92	8.5	305	7.0	7.8	91	1.9
12	50	3460	794	8.4	262	5.9	7.4	77	1.5
13	34	2660	254	9.3	337	8.6	6.9	62	1.2
14	24	466	32	56	6090	2990	6.5	51	.89
15	14	330	12	79	3740	1100	6.1	42	.69
16	11	290	8.6	13	325	13	8.3	342	15
17	10	257	7.0	9.3	702	17	20	1470	237
18	e9.8	251	e6.7	8.7	922	22	11	423	22
19	e9.8	251	e6.6	8.0	384	8.5	7.4	86	1.9
20	10	173	4.7	7.6	103	2.1	9.0	36	.88
21	8.5	107	2.4	16	842	153	7.9	34	.72
22	8.0	106	2.3	11	216	7.2	9.5	25	.66
23	8.1	63	1.4	16	687	73	7.4	18	.37
24	8.5	78	1.8	11	265	8.4	17	810	126
25	8.4	55	1.2	9.4	112	2.8	6.5	152	2.7
26	8.1	36	.78	8.4	108	2.4	7.0	91	1.7
27	8.4	32	.78	8.1	112	2.4	7.3	89	1.8
28	8.5	14	.32	8.4	115	2.6	7.1	93	1.8
29	7.7	16	.33	8.6	62	1.4	6.9	68	1.3
30	7.4	24	.48	8.7	26	.60	6.8	49	.90
31	---	---	---	8.9	28	.68	---	---	---
TOTAL	526.3	---	5712.39	404.4	---	4586.54	304.7	---	1008.11

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50114900 RIO PORTUGUES AT TIBES, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	6.6	44	.78	15	16	.64	16	870	63
2	17	1310	252	17	17	.79	32	2320	586
3	8.7	207	5.3	17	17	.79	38	592	65
4	7.4	60	1.2	16	18	.76	76	2200	1020
5	6.8	49	.90	15	19	.75	18	727	44
6	6.6	50	.88	e15	19	e.81	45	1780	518
7	6.4	52	.90	21	889	97	42	377	44
8	6.1	54	.90	41	3110	720	25	203	14
9	5.9	52	.83	37	1590	196	18	242	13
10	9.1	440	32	29	1870	130	14	164	6.3
11	7.4	185	3.8	45	5580	1350	e21	867	e102
12	6.6	71	1.3	35	2320	283	30	1200	106
13	6.2	58	.97	21	58	3.6	e25	29	e2.0
14	8.1	972	42	18	18	.90	23	28	1.7
15	41	3430	873	17	21	.94	22	26	1.6
16	43	2260	387	16	19	.80	37	1360	256
17	26	1970	154	17	15	.69	32	1820	159
18	28	1950	168	16	16	.71	e40	729	e128
19	26	1390	99	16	20	.84	e39	86	e8.3
20	29	2110	220	20	798	70	e29	28	e2.2
21	24	319	22	27	2020	315	135	1910	15100
22	19	103	5.4	37	3980	440	e3000	17500	e143000
23	25	3100	539	21	1150	65	e230	12500	e2450
24	19	242	13	78	3060	2500	e100	2200	e1300
25	17	26	1.2	130	2200	1330	e66	4430	e919
26	16	28	1.2	e48	681	e86	e48	1780	e518
27	16	33	1.4	30	1420	139	e100	2220	e1300
28	16	29	1.3	20	999	53	e49	1780	e518
29	15	23	.95	19	1030	60	e35	1360	e256
30	15	26	1.1	15	728	30	e22	203	e14
31	15	18	.73	14	632	24	---	---	---
TOTAL	498.9	---	2832.04	883	---	7901.02	4407	---	168515.1
YEAR	8119.3		194970.84						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-	SEDI-	SEDI-	SED.
		CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
NOV					
10...	1145	E14	2400	E91	94
FEB					
05...	0900	25	2150	145	99
07...	0900	5.7	594	9.1	98
APR					
07...	1700	273	26600	19600	83
MAY					
06...	1758	23	13600	844	99
08...	1915	24	6000	389	96
JUN					
04...	2248	30	501	41	91
AUG					
08...	2000	154	19400	8070	100
08...	2245	68	1280	235	99
11...	1645	187	15100	7620	98
21...	1648	107	13200	3800	100
24...	2123	335	8660	7830	98
25...	0308	211	4650	2650	98
25...	1036	137	1220	451	99
25...	2049	72	528	103	100
SEP					
02...	1722	89	24500	5890	100
04...	0614	73	1220	240	100
04...	1029	73	843	166	99
06...	2051	67	944	171	99
16...	1640	117	8280	2620	99
18...	1930	E82	4120	E912	100
18...	2035	69	2390	445	100
21...	2210	367	2370	2350	100
21...	2240	453	2700	3300	100

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50114900 RIO PORTUGUES AT TIBES, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .002 MM (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .004 MM (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .008 MM (70328)
NOV							
10...	1145	E14	2400	E91	41	55	71
FEB							
05...	0900	25	2150	145	42	56	73
07...	0900	5.7	594	9.1	--	--	--
APR							
07...	1700	273	26600	19600	32	43	56
MAY							
06...	1758	23	13600	844	30	51	78
08...	1915	24	6000	389	--	--	--
JUN							
04...	2248	30	501	41	--	--	--
AUG							
08...	2000	154	19400	8070	49	65	82
08...	2245	68	1280	235	--	--	--
11...	1645	187	15100	7620	--	--	--
21...	1648	107	13200	3800	--	--	--
24...	2123	335	8660	7830	36	49	66
25...	0308	211	4650	2650	--	--	--
25...	1036	137	1220	451	--	--	--
25...	2049	72	528	103	--	--	--
SEP							
02...	1722	89	24500	5890	48	64	82
04...	0614	73	1220	240	--	--	--
04...	1029	73	843	166	--	--	--
06...	2051	67	944	171	--	--	--
16...	1640	117	8280	2620	50	64	82
18...	1930	E82	4120	E912	81	92	98
18...	2035	69	2390	445	--	--	--
21...	2210	367	2370	2350	--	--	--
21...	2240	453	2700	3300	77	91	98

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .016 MM (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN .031 MM (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .125 MM (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .250 MM (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .500 MM (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN 1.00 MM (70335)
NOV							
10...	84	89	94	99	100	100	100
FEB							
05...	87	96	99	100	100	100	100
07...	--	--	98	--	--	--	--
APR							
07...	69	79	83	93	99	100	100
MAY							
06...	93	95	99	100	100	100	100
08...	--	--	96	--	--	--	--
JUN							
04...	--	--	91	--	--	--	--
AUG							
08...	95	100	100	100	100	100	100
08...	--	--	99	--	--	--	--
11...	--	--	98	--	--	--	--
21...	--	--	100	--	--	--	--
24...	82	95	98	99	100	100	100
25...	--	--	98	--	--	--	--
25...	--	--	99	--	--	--	--
25...	--	--	100	--	--	--	--
SEP							
02...	96	99	100	100	100	--	100
04...	--	--	100	--	--	--	--
04...	--	--	99	--	--	--	--
06...	--	--	99	--	--	--	--
16...	94	98	99	100	100	100	100
18...	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
18...	--	--	100	--	--	--	--
21...	--	--	100	--	--	--	--
21...	99	100	100	100	100	100	100

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115000 RIO PORTUGUES NEAR PONCE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 20...	0915	20	375	7.2	23.5	72	8.0	95	<10	3100	K1700
MAR 12...	0850	2.9	381	7.8	20.5	3.5	8.6	96	<10	930	670
MAY 28...	1000	9.5	355	7.8	24.5	7.5	8.5	103	<10	500	220
AUG 27...	0900	47	323	6.6	23.0	34	8.2	97	<10	2000	5100

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 20...	170	50	10	11	.4	1.4	150	.6	20	12
MAR 12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
MAY 28...	170	49	10	11	.4	1.3	160	--	14	9.1
AUG 27...	170	--	12	35	1	1.8	150	<1.0	47	26

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 20...	.14	21	215	11.6	80	1.57	.130	1.70	.180	.28
MAR 12...	--	--	--	--	7	--	<.010	.780	.020	.21
MAY 28...	.11	19	210	5.38	10	--	<.010	1.30	.020	--
AUG 27...	.10	21	283	36.0	29	2.39	.012	2.40	.030	.61

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 20...	.46	2.2	9.5	.120	<1	<100	20	1	1	11
MAR 12...	.23	1.0	4.5	.030	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 28...	<.20	--	--	.030	<1	<100	10	<1	<1	<10
AUG 27...	.64	3.0	13	.380	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115900 RIO PORTUGUES AT HIGHWAY 14 AT PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'09", long 66°36'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank upstream from bridge on Highway 14, 1.70 mi (2.74 km) downstream from Rio Chiquito, and 0.6 mi (0.96 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.6 mi² (48.17 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Occasional measurements 1963, annual maximum discharge and peaks above base at different datum, from 1965 to 1972. June 1997 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 67.2 ft (20.48 m), from topographic map. Prior to June 18, 1997 non-recording gage crested-stage gage at same site and different datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Some low-flow regulation due to Río Portugués dam construction activity upstream. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1										1.7	1.6	7.8
2										1.6	1.5	140
3										1.6	30	50
4										1.6	5.7	15
5										1.6	3.0	7.8
6										1.9	2.5	6.0
7										2.1	2.5	4.8
8										2.6	2.8	4.2
9										3.7	2.8	4.1
10										2.7	10	4.0
11										1.8	22	3.9
12										1.9	8.1	4.5
13										4.8	11	6.4
14										2.4	15	5.3
15										1.8	19	5.3
16										2.1	6.8	5.4
17										4.3	5.1	4.7
18									e.97	2.8	6.7	4.5
19									1.4	5.8	4.4	4.5
20									6.0	9.5	3.6	3.8
21									2.5	28	11	4.1
22									1.7	15	3.1	4.9
23									1.5	5.2	3.1	6.7
24									2.1	3.5	4.2	5.5
25									2.3	2.4	3.3	4.7
26									1.5	2.0	3.2	5.2
27									1.6	1.7	3.4	6.3
28									1.7	1.7	3.8	5.9
29									1.7	1.7	4.1	30
30									1.8	1.5	3.8	11
31									---	1.4	3.3	---
TOTAL									---	122.4	210.4	376.3
MEAN									---	3.95	6.79	12.5
MAX									---	28	30	140
MIN									---	1.4	1.5	3.8
AC-FT									---	243	417	746

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1997 - 1997, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	---	3.95	6.79	12.5
MAX	---	3.95	6.79	12.5
(WY)	---	1997	1997	1997
MIN	---	3.95	6.79	12.5
(WY)	---	1997	1997	1997

e Estimated

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115900 RIO PORTUGUES AT HIGHWAY 14 AT PONCE, PR--Continued

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115900 RIO PORTUGUES AT HIGHWAY 14 AT PONCE, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.0	8.7	7.6	5.5	5.0	e3.6	49	5.9	10	10	9.7	47
2	6.2	8.6	6.7	5.7	4.9	3.6	105	5.5	10	9.4	8.7	89
3	7.3	7.8	6.4	6.0	5.1	3.6	e69	5.4	9.5	44	19	229
4	8.7	8.0	6.2	5.7	6.1	e3.7	e21	4.9	30	22	9.5	537
5	4.9	7.5	6.4	5.0	341	e3.7	e8.7	4.6	39	19	11	207
6	4.6	7.1	6.2	24	31	e3.8	e7.0	4.6	39	13	e9.4	218
7	17	7.2	6.0	7.8	12	e4.0	e270	11	18	14	e15	214
8	178	6.9	5.9	7.8	9.3	e6.5	198	9.5	12	12	44	92
9	89	e23	5.8	5.6	50	e4.4	e34	25	12	11	159	57
10	40	e95	6.1	5.4	14	e3.7	e15	9.4	14	10	116	46
11	199	20	5.9	5.2	9.2	3.4	13	7.0	8.4	27	85	34
12	155	12	5.3	10	7.6	3.3	49	6.1	7.5	11	189	61
13	216	11	5.1	6.3	6.6	e3.5	e90	7.3	7.9	9.7	106	46
14	814	9.6	5.5	5.6	6.6	e4.9	25	13	8.2	8.8	47	33
15	407	31	6.1	5.1	7.8	4.2	15	253	8.2	49	41	89
16	185	54	5.7	4.9	6.2	6.7	12	50	19	117	25	92
17	326	17	6.5	4.8	5.5	5.6	14	26	53	79	18	111
18	298	13	6.8	4.8	5.1	4.7	10	16	80	59	45	80
19	55	11	6.4	4.7	4.6	4.6	9.2	16	55	55	29	158
20	29	9.4	5.7	4.5	4.3	4.7	8.8	12	22	31	30	53
21	20	8.5	6.4	4.6	4.3	5.2	8.9	19	24	65	52	85
22	16	8.2	5.8	4.4	4.1	4.6	9.4	39	41	26	175	5580
23	14	7.7	5.6	4.5	3.8	5.2	7.3	54	20	18	138	460
24	12	7.5	5.6	4.4	e4.2	4.8	e7.8	59	20	50	193	198
25	12	7.1	5.5	5.3	e4.5	7.7	e10	23	70	17	1310	123
26	11	e8.6	5.7	5.0	e4.7	6.7	e9.9	19	24	13	213	86
27	10	8.9	5.7	4.8	e4.7	6.0	e8.5	17	16	12	92	e188
28	9.9	7.0	5.7	e5.5	e4.1	5.5	e12	12	14	31	121	91
29	9.6	6.6	5.8	5.4	---	5.4	e8.2	12	13	13	78	64
30	9.1	14	6.0	5.4	---	15	6.6	13	11	12	50	38
31	8.5	---	5.8	5.2	---	13	---	11	---	11	35	---
TOTAL	3179.8	451.9	185.9	188.9	576.3	165.3	1111.3	770.2	715.7	878.9	3473.3	9406
MEAN	103	15.1	6.00	6.09	20.6	5.33	37.0	24.8	23.9	28.4	112	314
MAX	814	95	7.6	24	341	15	270	253	80	117	1310	5580
MIN	4.6	6.6	5.1	4.4	3.8	3.3	6.6	4.6	7.5	8.8	8.7	33
AC-FT	6310	896	369	375	1140	328	2200	1530	1420	1740	6890	18660

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1997 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1997	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1997	1998	1998
MEAN	103	15.1	6.00	6.09	20.6	5.33	37.0	24.8	23.9	16.1	59.4	163
MAX	103	15.1	6.00	6.09	20.6	5.33	37.0	24.8	23.9	28.4	112	314
(WY)	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998
MIN	103	15.1	6.00	6.09	20.6	5.33	37.0	24.8	23.9	3.95	6.79	12.5
(WY)	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1998	1997	1997	1997

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1997 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	21103.5	
ANNUAL MEAN	57.8	57.8
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN		57.8 1998
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN		57.8 1998
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	5580	Sep 22 1998
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.3	Mar 12 1997
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.7	Mar 1 1997
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	16300	Sep 22 1998
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	19.73	Sep 22 1998
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	41860	41890
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	105	89
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10	8.3
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.8	3.3

e Estimated

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115900 RIO PORTUGUES AT HIGHWAY 14 AT PONCE, PR--Continued

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50116200 RIO PORTUGUES AT PONCE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'20", long 66°36'28", 1,300 ft (400 m) south of Las Américas Avenue Bridge, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of CSC 50115900, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) west of Highways 1 and 2 junction, and 0.7 mi (1.1 km) southeast of Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.9 mi² (49.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
NOV 04...	1015	13	494	7.7	29.3	17	7.9	102	<10	36000	4400
MAR 13...	0835	2.9	613	7.1	22.0	.85	4.4	50	<10	4500	650
MAY 20...	0930	13	436	7.4	27.0	21	6.5	81	<10	330	700
SEP 09...	0945	4.0	369	6.6	26.7	35	6.8	85	<10	2600	2000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
NOV 04...	80	19	7.8	20	1	1.9	156	<.5	8.9	18
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--
MAY 20...	180	52	12	21	.7	1.1	200	--	27	18
SEP 09...	150	46	9.2	14	.5	1.4	170	<1.0	15	12

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
NOV 04...	.10	37	213	7.47	5	.640	.200	.840	.570	.53
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	14	.390	.130	.520	.580	.42
MAY 20...	.15	16	267	9.23	39	.426	.014	.440	.040	.24
SEP 09...	.12	21	221	2.32	62	1.27	.029	1.30	.060	.34

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
NOV 04...	1.1	1.9	8.6	.210	<1	<100	80	<1	<1	10
MAR 13...	1.0	1.5	6.7	.110	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 20...	.28	.72	3.2	.040	<1	<100	50	<1	<1	<10
SEP 09...	.40	1.7	7.5	.060	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124200 RIO GUAYANILLA NEAR GUAYANILLA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'40", long 66°47'53", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) north of junction of Highways 2 and 132, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) downstream from Quebrada Consejo, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) north-northwest from Plaza de Guayanilla.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.9 mi² (49.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1981 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 80 ft (24 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e12	19	6.7	4.5	3.5	3.2	70	3.6	9.2	12	17	46
2	e10	18	6.6	4.3	3.4	3.1	44	4.5	8.7	25	25	68
3	e7.6	18	6.5	4.0	3.3	3.1	e22	3.8	8.3	29	24	176
4	e6.6	18	5.8	3.8	3.6	3.4	e14	3.6	70	25	17	156
5	e5.8	18	5.7	3.7	98	3.1	11	3.4	29	18	16	267
6	e5.4	17	5.6	7.4	12	2.9	9.6	6.2	24	20	27	143
7	e49	18	5.4	5.7	7.4	3.5	36	9.5	16	19	e49	104
8	e46	17	5.2	4.3	8.2	2.8	39	56	20	15	80	88
9	e60	21	5.0	3.8	11	2.6	17	31	19	14	52	67
10	e54	39	4.9	3.8	6.5	2.7	11	11	16	16	39	e55
11	e48	20	4.8	3.7	5.5	2.4	9.7	7.8	14	25	32	e60
12	e37	18	4.5	4.0	4.9	2.5	11	6.5	13	15	29	54
13	e130	17	4.4	4.7	4.6	2.5	11	6.4	14	14	24	54
14	e440	16	4.3	3.8	4.9	2.6	8.1	7.3	13	13	28	47
15	e180	24	4.2	3.8	6.0	2.8	6.9	40	12	17	30	53
16	e100	25	4.4	3.8	4.7	3.2	6.5	24	13	15	23	54
17	e280	16	4.3	3.8	4.5	3.1	6.0	13	21	30	25	48
18	e130	13	4.5	4.2	4.4	2.8	5.5	9.6	e23	24	21	45
19	e50	11	4.6	4.7	4.2	2.5	5.6	10	e16	18	19	41
20	e37	10	4.5	3.8	4.0	2.6	5.8	8.5	13	26	62	78
21	e34	9.4	4.8	3.7	4.1	3.1	5.5	19	13	21	50	238
22	30	9.1	4.1	3.5	3.9	2.9	5.6	27	16	16	113	e932
23	28	8.6	3.8	3.3	3.7	2.7	5.0	50	26	19	66	e175
24	26	8.3	3.8	3.4	3.5	2.5	4.6	34	46	22	92	e122
25	25	8.3	3.8	3.7	3.3	3.2	4.5	19	38	16	318	e108
26	24	8.2	4.0	3.5	3.8	3.6	4.8	14	25	14	69	e99
27	23	8.1	4.2	3.5	3.8	2.8	4.9	11	20	35	45	e104
28	22	7.6	4.5	3.6	3.4	2.9	5.2	58	17	36	36	e89
29	21	7.2	4.6	4.3	---	2.8	3.9	43	14	22	28	e83
30	20	7.1	e4.3	4.1	---	26	3.6	16	13	18	23	e73
31	20	---	4.4	3.7	---	18	---	11	---	16	19	---
TOTAL	1961.4	454.9	148.2	125.9	234.1	127.9	397.3	567.7	600.2	625	1498	3727
MEAN	63.3	15.2	4.78	4.06	8.36	4.13	13.2	18.3	20.0	20.2	48.3	124
MAX	440	39	6.7	7.4	98	26	70	58	70	36	318	932
MIN	5.4	7.1	3.8	3.3	3.3	2.4	3.6	3.4	8.3	12	16	41
AC-FT	3890	902	294	250	464	254	788	1130	1190	1240	2970	7390
CFSM	3.35	.80	.25	.21	.44	.22	.70	.97	1.06	1.07	2.56	6.57
IN.	3.86	.90	.29	.25	.46	.25	.78	1.12	1.18	1.23	2.95	7.34

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1981 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	59.7	45.6	17.4	10.2	7.53	6.03	10.0	25.2	14.4	12.2	18.8	44.1						
MAX	167	110	41.9	27.5	11.6	13.2	26.6	80.4	41.0	25.9	48.5	124						
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1992	1996	1989	1983	1985	1987	1986	1988	1998						
MIN	16.0	15.2	4.78	4.06	3.10	2.85	2.76	2.33	2.35	2.45	5.14	3.62						
(WY)	1983	1998	1998	1998	1990	1981	1995	1994	1997	1994	1997	1997						

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1981 - 1998

	1997 CALENDAR YEAR	1998 WATER YEAR	1981 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	4117.0	10467.6	
ANNUAL MEAN	11.3	28.7	22.3
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			33.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			8.94
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	440	932	1500
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.5	2.4	.77
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.6	2.6	1.1
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		18700	18700
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		21.88	21.88
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		2.2	.70
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	8170	20760	16150
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.60	1.52	1.18
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	8.10	20.60	16.03
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	21	60	49
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.2	13	9.6
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.9	3.5	3.2

e Estimated

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124200 RIO GUAYANILLA NEAR GUAYANILLA, PR--Continued

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124700 RIO GUAYANILLA AT CENTRAL RUFINA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'40", long 66°46'49", at dirt road bridge, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) from mouth, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) east of Central Rufina and 0.9 mi (1.4 km) southeast of Guayanilla.

DRAINAGE AREA.--22.8 mi² (59.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960-65, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT	23...	26	402	8.5	29.0	4.9	12.0	155	<10	430	270
MAR	27...	.38	897	7.9	29.0	2.5	8.4	109	16	2300	20
JUN	05...	38	398	7.7	26.5	7.7	7.9	98	<10	4600	K1800
SEP	11...	53	439	7.2	26.5	4.6	8.2	102	<10	38000	320

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)	
OCT	23...	170	46	14	15	.5	1.8	130	<.5	46	20
MAR	27...	--	--	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--
JUN	05...	170	46	14	17	.6	2.6	130	--	35	18
SEP	11...	190	52	15	13	.4	.17	150	<1.0	39	18

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	
OCT	23...	<.10	17	237	16.9	24	1.99	.012	2.00	.020	.36
MAR	27...	--	--	--	--	1	1.54	.060	1.60	.180	2.1
JUN	05...	<.10	19	229	23.4	19	2.29	.010	2.30	.020	.35
SEP	11...	<.10	20	247	35.1	15	2.49	.014	2.50	.030	.25

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)	
OCT	23...	.38	2.4	11	.150	1	<100	30	<1	2	<10
MAR	27...	2.3	3.9	17	.880	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN	05...	.37	2.7	12	.100	1	<100	40	<1	2	<10
SEP	11...	<.28	2.8	12	.250	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO YAUCO BASIN

50125780 LAGO LUCCHETTI AT DAMSITE NEAR YAUCO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'37", long 66°51'54, Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Antonio Lucchetti Dam on Río Yauco, 3.9 mi (6.3 km) north of Yauco.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.4 mi² (45.1 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1989 to current year. Prior to October 1994, published as Lago Lucchetti at Damsite.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Lucchetti was completed in 1952. The dam is on Río Yauco and is a unit of the Southwestern Puerto Rico Project. It provides 16,500 acre-feet (20.3 km³) of usable storage for power generation and irrigation. The dam is a concrete gravity structure with a total length of 591 ft (180 m), a maximum height of 178 ft (54 m), and a maximum width at the base of 150 ft (46 m). An ungated, overflow tipe spillway with a clear length of 171 ft (52 m), and a maximum capacity of 62,800 ft³/s (1,778 m³/s), at a design head of 20 ft (6 m). The dam is owned by Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 577.56 ft (176.04 m), Sept. 22, 1998; minimum elevation, 512.09 ft (156.08 m), Sept. 9, 1994.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 577.56 ft (176.04 m), Sept. 22, minimum elevation, 529.98 ft (161.54 m), Oct 1.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
512	1,505	540	5,165
520	2,385	550	7,020
525	2,965	561	9,600
527	3,255	563	10,125
530	3,695	571	12,125
532	3,975	573	12,645
		578	14,061

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	530.29	562.73	566.26	559.14	565.32	567.87	558.69	555.16	569.09	562.99	561.96	561.23
2	530.73	562.48	564.78	559.23	564.74	567.83	A	555.10	570.14	562.23	561.36	560.46
3	530.41	563.34	563.49	A	565.50	567.79	A	555.08	569.05	562.28	561.38	A
4	530.41	564.73	563.49	559.11	567.05	567.71	A	554.86	569.79	562.28	561.39	558.16
5	530.38	565.01	563.09	557.51	568.36	566.40	558.48	554.62	570.14	562.26	561.39	557.96
6	530.33	565.03	562.73	557.52	568.57	566.40	A	554.91	570.15	562.36	562.14	560.05
7	531.09	564.97	562.73	557.47	568.87	566.36	557.93	554.85	569.68	562.49	563.52	560.48
8	535.35	564.94	562.70	557.75	568.53	566.31	A	555.32	569.60	562.94	564.22	559.69
9	539.05	564.98	562.71	557.83	569.33	566.25	A	555.28	569.84	563.14	564.60	561.18
10	541.08	565.09	562.29	557.79	570.19	566.18	A	555.12	569.79	563.51	564.90	562.60
11	543.72	565.68	562.25	557.74	570.53	564.70	A	554.89	569.89	563.53	565.24	562.15
12	545.56	565.84	562.22	558.17	570.38	564.67	A	554.88	569.60	563.64	565.52	563.06
13	547.52	565.89	562.20	557.19	570.09	564.58	A	554.87	569.50	563.74	565.67	563.65
14	552.51	565.90	562.16	558.40	570.09	564.53	A	554.92	569.32	563.73	565.76	565.00
15	555.39	566.28	562.12	559.13	570.05	564.48	A	555.05	567.84	563.80	565.60	565.40
16	557.37	566.40	562.06	559.53	570.15	563.88	A	555.08	566.51	563.80	565.48	566.01
17	558.95	566.41	562.06	559.52	569.76	563.86	A	555.08	566.13	563.79	565.38	566.30
18	559.87	566.47	562.05	559.48	570.53	563.32	A	555.07	566.48	563.80	565.49	566.13
19	560.27	566.48	561.04	559.45	569.96	562.42	A	555.59	566.73	563.55	565.17	565.98
20	560.46	566.50	560.93	560.33	569.14	562.35	A	558.97	566.70	563.54	565.21	564.85
21	560.63	566.51	560.80	560.45	569.48	562.32	A	563.34	566.79	563.53	564.98	567.09
22	560.74	566.50	560.65	561.17	569.84	562.28	A	564.13	567.04	563.48	565.30	571.68
23	561.09	566.52	560.61	560.88	569.41	561.92	A	564.43	567.73	563.53	565.36	570.61
24	561.08	566.46	560.59	561.02	568.58	A	A	564.61	566.90	563.43	565.66	570.40
25	561.27	566.42	560.55	561.39	568.06	561.55	A	565.33	565.37	563.40	565.99	571.07
26	562.36	566.50	560.51	562.47	568.04	A	A	566.21	564.83	563.34	565.67	570.55
27	562.39	566.52	560.33	563.11	567.99	559.26	A	566.60	565.11	563.35	565.22	570.44
28	562.49	566.26	560.30	564.16	567.94	559.20	A	568.64	565.10	563.13	564.38	A
29	562.56	566.27	560.28	565.21	---	559.16	A	568.85	565.09	563.14	563.54	A
30	562.57	566.25	559.09	565.47	---	558.43	A	568.96	564.31	562.92	562.74	A
31	562.60	---	558.80	565.40	---	558.64	---	569.03	---	562.48	562.08	---
MAX	562.60	566.52	566.26	---	570.53	---	---	569.03	570.15	563.80	565.99	---
MIN	530.29	562.48	558.80	---	564.74	---	---	554.62	564.31	562.23	561.36	---

A No gage-height record

RIO LOCO BASIN

50128900 LAGO LOCO AT DAMSITE NEAR YAUCO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'41", long 66°53'16", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Damsite, 2.60 mi (4.18 km) northwest from Yauco Plaza, 0.45 mi (0.72 km) northeast from Escuela Río Cañas and 0.95 mi (1.53 km) northwest from Escuela Susua Alta.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.40 mi² (21.8 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1995 to current year.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Loco was completed in 1951. The dam is a concrete gravity structure with a total length of 600 ft (183 m), maximum structural height of 72 ft (21.9 m), the ungated overflow spillway is 150 ft (47.7 m), long with crest at elevation of 230 ft (70.1 m). It has a normal storage capacity of 1,950 acre-feet (2.40 km³), as for May 4, 1979. The Loco Dam is owned by the Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority (P.R.E.P.A) and its part of the Southwestern Puerto Rico Project which was developed for electric power generation and irrigation of the lands in the Lajas Valley, some of the Project waters are used for water supply in the Lajas area. The maximum drawdown of the Dam is from 230 ft (70.1 m) to 220 ft (67.1 m) and the Capacity Table provided by P.R.E.P.A includes only that portion of the storage for the dam. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 234.77 ft (71.56 m), Sept. 22, 1998; minimum elevation, 217.77 ft (66.4 m), June 10, 1997.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 234.77 ft (71.56 m), Sept. 22; minimum elevation, 222.74 ft (67.8 m), Mar. 26.

Capacity Table

(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
220	0	230	639
225	299	232	787
		235	1,024

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	225.49	A	A	228.77	223.45	228.11	229.08	229.47	229.14	230.85	230.43	230.98
2	223.93	230.31	230.41	228.97	229.09	227.37	227.41	229.31	228.28	229.89	230.36	230.52
3	229.57	230.72	230.47	A	230.67	226.27	A	229.14	230.29	229.29	229.35	230.98
4	229.39	229.41	229.99	226.83	228.45	224.83	225.88	230.09	229.79	229.20	228.23	231.02
5	229.20	228.33	230.09	230.29	230.97	229.78	225.29	230.05	230.54	229.03	226.83	230.94
6	228.49	230.19	230.31	A	230.54	228.87	224.65	230.15	229.93	228.64	A	231.02
7	227.25	230.32	230.29	230.78	230.88	228.41	227.33	230.20	230.65	229.98	230.44	230.95
8	A	230.97	229.48	228.27	230.48	227.93	226.59	230.13	230.72	230.04	230.37	230.95
9	228.55	230.34	229.98	226.87	230.07	226.89	225.79	230.13	230.61	230.87	230.16	230.18
10	229.28	229.89	230.15	225.99	229.86	225.25	225.66	230.12	229.93	230.15	229.67	230.66
11	230.43	229.55	A	225.02	229.61	230.04	224.67	230.00	230.20	230.91	229.23	230.69
12	230.19	229.09	229.27	224.34	229.26	228.39	223.72	229.52	230.57	230.54	228.84	230.23
13	230.29	228.49	228.97	229.69	A	227.24	226.96	228.84	230.45	230.72	228.48	230.15
14	230.47	228.06	228.67	227.84	A	226.82	224.53	228.06	229.83	230.58	230.43	230.28
15	230.28	A	228.04	225.69	228.90	225.97	228.75	227.64	230.79	230.86	230.51	230.04
16	230.19	228.51	226.71	A	230.49	227.48	227.06	227.45	230.33	230.87	230.77	230.05
17	230.32	A	225.56	227.37	230.66	225.60	230.04	227.55	230.47	230.13	230.40	229.99
18	230.93	229.51	224.28	226.96	A	227.18	229.76	226.76	229.29	229.79	230.29	230.69
19	230.94	230.19	228.48	226.51	230.23	228.89	229.48	225.88	230.87	230.95	230.38	230.64
20	230.40	229.58	229.49	225.15	230.39	227.45	229.20	225.24	230.87	230.78	230.88	230.67
21	A	229.18	229.58	227.62	229.96	226.77	228.37	224.86	229.87	230.92	230.99	230.86
22	230.80	229.63	A	225.46	229.77	226.05	227.82	224.54	230.30	230.38	230.99	230.83
23	230.81	230.18	A	228.95	230.55	226.69	226.79	224.26	230.66	230.32	230.94	230.52
24	230.16	230.01	228.41	230.18	230.51	226.46	226.19	223.88	230.64	230.96	231.09	230.45
25	230.27	230.12	228.00	230.25	230.32	223.94	225.81	224.05	230.64	229.88	231.07	230.60
26	A	A	227.58	228.88	229.50	225.50	225.44	226.13	230.03	230.67	231.02	230.43
27	230.80	229.37	227.83	229.68	228.92	229.55	224.91	227.54	230.09	230.35	231.01	230.44
28	A	230.13	A	227.96	228.52	228.29	224.43	229.46	229.87	230.32	231.01	230.40
29	230.28	229.77	226.18	226.32	---	227.11	226.96	229.90	229.30	230.56	231.02	230.79
30	A	229.40	229.14	225.20	---	229.99	227.64	229.85	230.87	230.84	231.02	230.79
31	230.11	---	229.77	224.36	---	230.19	---	229.70	---	230.87	231.01	---
MAX	---	---	---	---	---	230.19	---	230.20	230.87	230.96	---	231.02
MIN	---	---	---	---	---	223.94	---	223.88	228.28	228.64	---	229.99

A No gage-height record

RIO LOCO BASIN

50129700 RIO LOCO AT GUANICA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'33", long 66°54'52", 0.6 mi (1.0 km) northwest of Guánica and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northeast of Ensenada.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1975 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND- ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR- BID- ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML) (31616)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 23...	1025	314	7.1	29.0	8.4	5.5	71	<10	2000	2100
MAR 27...	0910	18400	7.3	29.0	1.5	3.3	46	93	46000	540
JUN 05...	0815	12500	7.4	29.0	3.7	2.4	32	27	230	220
SEP 11...	0915	315	6.8	26.8	12	5.7	71	<10	350	670

DATE	HARD- NESS TOTAL (MG/L CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 23...	130	30	13	13	.5	2.7	110	<.5	16	15
MAR 27...	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--
JUN 05...	1400	100	268	2110	25	87	130	--	550	3900
SEP 11...	120	28	12	17	.7	3.1	120	<1.0	13	15

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)
OCT 23...	<.10	20	175	11	1.38	.017	1.40	.020	.36	.38
MAR 27...	--	--	--	4	.590	.050	.640	.130	.57	.70
JUN 05...	.29	16	7120	17	.241	.029	.270	.170	.47	.64
SEP 11...	.13	23	183	20	.686	.014	.700	.050	.33	.38

DATE	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE) (01045)
OCT 23...	1.8	7.9	.080	<1	<100	30	<1	3	<10	560
MAR 27...	1.3	5.9	.160	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 05...	.91	4.0	.060	<1	<100	20	<1	2	<10	290
SEP 11...	1.1	4.8	.130	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Figure 23. Río Guanajibo basin.

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50131990 RIO GUANAJIBO AT HWY 119 AT SAN GERMAN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'06", long 67°02'02", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on left bank, at bridge on Hwy 119, 0.6 mi (1.0 km), southwest of junction of Highways 119 and 2, 0.2 mi (0.3 km), northeast of junction of Highways 119 and 102, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) east from public Plaza of San Germán.

DRAINAGE AREA.--34.6 mi² (89.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 148 ft (45 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.3	21	13	7.8	4.7	6.1	3.6	6.6	38	14	14	40
2	6.8	21	13	6.9	4.5	5.7	3.2	6.3	31	165	49	52
3	5.6	20	13	6.2	4.3	5.2	3.2	6.0	32	153	34	221
4	4.8	21	12	6.2	4.2	5.8	3.2	5.1	297	55	16	583
5	6.9	19	11	6.1	9.24	5.2	3.1	5.5	156	26	15	362
6	4.9	19	11	6.3	5.2	5.2	3.1	3.7	106	35	e66	192
7	10	19	11	6.3	2.6	7.5	3.1	4.5	51	62	725	173
8	377	18	10	6.8	2.1	5.3	1.6	1.6	3.7	2.8	4.22	1.03
9	673	18	10	6.4	2.1	4.1	6.0	3.6	5.4	2.2	1.47	80
10	383	21	9.7	6.1	1.6	4.1	3.7	1.4	3.3	2.2	8.7	6.4
11	519	18	10	5.6	1.3	4.1	3.4	8.6	2.6	3.5	9.4	7.7
12	486	33	9.3	1.0	1.2	3.9	3.5	7.4	2.3	1.7	6.4	1.59
13	552	18	9.0	1.1	1.0	4.2	3.6	6.7	2.2	1.5	4.6	1.23
14	1180	17	8.8	7.1	1.0	4.0	3.2	6.1	1.9	1.5	4.2	6.4
15	380	279	8.5	6.2	1.2	7.1	2.8	1.2	1.7	1.4	9.4	5.3
16	233	1.26	8.4	6.2	1.0	5.5	1.2	1.2	1.6	1.3	4.8	5.0
17	282	4.2	8.0	6.2	8.5	5.1	2.37	8.5	1.84	1.4	4.1	4.4
18	218	3.0	9.6	6.8	7.9	1.2	2.3	8.5	9.1	1.6	3.4	6.0
19	11.6	2.5	1.0	6.7	7.9	6.3	9.4	1.43	3.8	2.2	2.9	8.5
20	8.4	2.2	8.8	5.8	7.2	4.7	1.8	1.60	2.7	2.0	3.8	2.17
21	6.2	1.9	9.2	5.2	7.1	4.2	9.8	3.00	2.3	1.7	3.3	2.48
22	5.0	1.8	8.4	5.4	6.6	3.9	7.5	1.96	2.8	1.5	1.09	e17300
23	4.3	1.6	7.5	4.9	6.8	3.6	5.8	5.1	3.4	1.4	5.9	e8830
24	3.8	1.5	7.9	4.8	6.1	3.2	5.1	3.0	5.3	1.5	4.8	e5440
25	3.4	1.6	7.4	4.9	6.7	4.5	7.5	3.22	3.7	1.2	5.07	e5030
26	3.2	3.0	7.2	4.6	7.2	4.0	3.9	2.57	2.6	1.0	1.98	e3490
27	2.9	1.9	7.2	4.5	7.7	3.8	1.3	7.2	2.2	1.8	1.00	e1800
28	2.7	1.5	7.2	4.6	6.1	3.8	1.5	4.19	1.8	3.3	8.0	e842
29	2.6	1.5	7.3	4.6	---	3.5	1.3	3.05	1.6	1.7	6.9	e1380
30	2.4	1.4	7.0	4.6	---	4.7	7.5	9.6	1.6	1.3	5.0	e394
31	2.3	---	9.2	4.4	---	4.2	---	5.4	---	1.2	4.1	---
TOTAL	5919.3	984	289.6	189.2	1268.3	154.5	487.3	2652.3	1571	939	3399	47556
MEAN	191	32.8	9.34	6.10	45.3	4.98	16.2	85.6	52.4	30.3	1.10	1585
MAX	1180	279	1.3	1.1	9.24	1.2	2.37	4.19	2.97	1.65	7.25	17300
MIN	4.8	1.4	7.0	4.4	4.3	3.2	2.8	5.1	1.6	1.0	1.4	4.0
MED	4.3	1.9	9.2	6.2	8.2	4.5	5.9	3.0	3.2	1.7	5.0	1.83
AC-FT	11740	1950	574	375	2520	306	967	5260	3120	1860	6740	94330
CFSM	5.52	.95	.27	.18	1.31	.14	.47	2.47	1.51	.88	3.17	45.8
IN.	6.36	1.06	.31	.20	1.36	.17	.52	2.85	1.69	1.01	3.65	51.13

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	104	66.6	23.1	22.0	22.5	10.7	20.8	45.9
MAX	205	127	52.2	47.5	45.3	25.8	55.9	85.6
(WY)	1993	1997	1993	1997	1998	1995	1996	1998
MIN	20.4	15.8	8.21	6.10	4.32	3.52	7.79	5.11
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1998	1992	1992	1997	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1991 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	11236.9	65409.5	
ANNUAL MEAN	30.8	179	57.7
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			179
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			16.6
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1180	Oct 14	17300
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.1	Jun 10	2.8
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.7	Jun 8	3.2
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			24900
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			19.53
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	22290	129700	41780
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.89	5.18	1.67
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	12.08	70.32	22.65
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	38	217	93
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.3	16	15
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.5	4.6	4.8

e Estimated

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50131990 RIO GUANAJIBO AT HWY 119 AT SAN GERMAN, PR--Continued

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50133600 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR SAN GERMAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'18", long 67°03'56", at bridge on Highway 347, 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest of San Germán.

DRAINAGE AREA.--45.5 mi² (117.8 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 22...	1000	70	535	7.3	25.5	2.1	6.5	79	<10	800	550
MAR 26...	0940	3.7	784	7.2	26.0	.95	4.7	58	15	330	380
JUN 04...	1030	50	331	7.3	27.0	95	6.9	86	<10	K15000	5700
SEP 10...	1030	88	493	7.4	27.5	5.3	7.6	96	<10	2100	580

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 22...	240	23	44	20	.6	2.8	260	.6	24	25
MAR 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--
JUN 04...	150	14	27	12	.4	2.6	140	--	14	15
SEP 10...	180	7.7	13	5.1	.3	1.0	220	<1.0	18	17

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 22...	<.10	35	330	62.1	8	1.42	.180	1.60	.360	.74
MAR 26...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.28	.020	1.30	.020	.52
JUN 04...	<.10	27	196	26.6	120	.764	.096	.860	.180	.67
SEP 10...	<.10	37	230	54.5	12	1.14	.062	1.20	.160	.15

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 22...	1.1	2.7	12	.160	<1	<100	60	<1	9	<10
MAR 26...	.54	1.8	8.1	.210	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 04...	.85	1.7	7.6	.240	<1	<100	60	<1	75	15
SEP 10...	.31	1.5	6.7	.160	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'36", long 67°05'08", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on Highway 348, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) southwest of Rosario Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.3 mi² (47.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 50.0 ft (15.2 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. The gage-height recorded during the Hurricane Georges event was affected by backwater caused by the Hwy. 348 bridge which is about 32 ft. downstream from gage.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e105	38	30	24	20	10	9.2	8.4	16	13	76	59
2	e75	37	30	23	18	11	9.4	8.0	15	62	75	248
3	e61	37	29	19	15	9.3	9.9	7.7	16	114	49	156
4	e51	35	28	19	17	9.2	9.0	9.2	23	41	47	181
5	e42	33	27	20	56	8.9	9.1	9.7	30	21	40	138
6	e39	31	26	22	20	9.2	9.2	20	28	122	54	280
7	e37	31	26	49	15	9.0	27	40	22	e72	165	148
8	e41	30	25	24	20	8.9	27	22	25	e36	159	113
9	175	28	25	19	25	8.6	13	22	35	25	120	99
10	e229	30	24	19	16	8.5	10	19	40	51	142	85
11	e212	46	25	31	14	8.1	9.0	16	31	42	162	85
12	e141	38	24	28	13	7.9	8.9	13	23	28	e112	160
13	e195	34	23	22	13	7.9	8.5	12	22	23	e82	131
14	449	30	23	19	12	15	8.7	12	21	22	e69	88
15	e244	67	22	17	13	22	8.8	14	19	23	64	76
16	165	48	20	17	12	11	8.7	24	26	28	56	75
17	125	34	20	16	12	49	8.8	25	187	31	58	78
18	107	33	24	17	11	53	8.6	39	58	107	49	91
19	89	112	22	18	12	18	11	94	32	72	43	79
20	78	87	22	16	13	13	9.5	68	23	62	64	92
21	70	45	21	17	13	11	9.0	67	20	40	63	120
22	64	37	20	17	12	9.5	12	63	19	32	71	e4420
23	59	33	25	16	12	8.3	8.8	32	20	65	61	422
24	56	31	24	17	12	7.9	8.7	32	19	45	48	287
25	e56	31	22	17	12	8.0	9.8	138	17	36	152	258
26	e55	41	21	16	14	9.9	10	75	16	33	85	244
27	49	34	21	16	11	11	9.7	30	16	92	263	237
28	47	31	21	17	11	9.6	19	31	14	69	130	233
29	44	32	21	17	---	8.9	11	43	13	47	e81	336
30	43	39	21	16	---	8.9	8.4	27	13	38	e68	224
31	40	---	23	15	---	10	---	21	---	42	e64	---
TOTAL	3243	1213	735	620	444	400.5	329.7	1042.0	859	1534	2772	9243
MEAN	105	40.4	23.7	20.0	15.9	12.9	11.0	33.6	28.6	49.5	89.4	308
MAX	449	112	30	49	56	53	27	138	187	122	263	4420
MIN	37	28	20	15	11	7.9	8.4	7.7	13	13	40	59
AC-FT	6430	2410	1460	1230	881	794	654	2070	1700	3040	5500	18330
CFSM	5.72	2.21	1.30	1.09	.87	.71	.60	1.84	1.56	2.70	4.89	16.8
IN.	6.59	2.47	1.49	1.26	.90	.81	.67	2.12	1.75	3.12	5.63	18.79

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1986 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	102	68.5	31.6	22.8	19.4	21.3	23.2	43.7	41.7	42.5	62.3	105	
MAX	206	117	53.7	39.7	37.8	77.0	57.7	122	91.1	75.2	102	308	
(WY)	1986	1990	1995	1997	1995	1989	1989	1993	1993	1989	1989	1998	
MIN	33.2	16.1	9.92	15.1	8.55	10.1	11.0	14.8	12.0	23.2	25.1	32.7	
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1994	1992	1992	1998	1997	1992	1990	1991	1986	

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1986 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	13311.9	22435.2	
ANNUAL MEAN	36.5	61.5	48.8
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			70.6
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			30.8
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	449	Oct 14	4420
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	8.3	May 15	7.7
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	8.7	Jun 5	8.4
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			Not determined
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			18.66
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			7.2
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	26400	44500	35370
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.99	3.36	2.67
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	27.06	45.61	36.25
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	66	121	110
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	25	26	28
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	9.4	11

e Estimated

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN
50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1979 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1985 to current year.

INSTRUMENTATION.--US D-49 Sediment sampler since October 1985. Automatic sediment sampler since 1986.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 15,900 mg/L September 22,1998; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 356,000 tons (323,000 tonnes); September 22,1998 Minimum daily, 0.05 ton (0.04 Tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR 1998.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 15,900 mg/L ; September 22,1998; Minimum daily mean, 2.0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 356,000 tons (323,000 tonnes) September 22, 1998; Minimum daily 0.09 ton (0.08 tonne) several days.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH CENT) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 22...	1150	64	263	7.5	25.0	.98	8.2	99	<10	K740	490
MAR 26...	1135	9.8	284	7.8	26.0	.49	8.7	108	<10	2000	45
JUN 04...	1215	13	261	8.2	29.0	1.0	8.0	104	<10	420	70
SEP 10...	1130	85	253	7.4	26.2	2.7	8.1	100	<10	590	470

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 22...	120	22	16	7.1	.3	1.4	130	<.5	6.5	7.3
MAR 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
JUN 04...	130	23	18	7.2	.3	1.4	130	--	6.8	8.4
SEP 10...	120	21	16	6.6	.3	1.4	110	<1.0	6.5	6.8

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 22...	<.10	29	168	28.9	2	--	<.010	1.10	<.010	--
MAR 26...	--	--	--	--	1	.620	.010	.630	.020	.21
JUN 04...	.10	28	170	6.01	1	--	<.010	.540	.010	.21
SEP 10...	<.10	28	152	34.7	4	1.18	.018	1.20	.030	--

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE) (01045)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB) (01051)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN) (01055)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG) (71900)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS SE) (01147)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG) (01077)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN) (01092)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN) (00720)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L) (32730)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L) (38260)
OCT 22...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	20	<1	7	<10
MAR 26...	.24	.86	3.8	.020	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 04...	.22	.76	3.4	<.020	<1	<100	20	<1	4	<10
SEP 10...	<.20	--	--	.030	--	--	--	--	--	--

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	e105	171	e51	38	7	.70	30	28	2.3
2	e75	41	e8.5	37	3	.27	30	16	1.3
3	e61	25	e4.1	37	6	.60	29	16	1.3
4	e51	25	e3.4	35	17	1.6	28	18	1.4
5	e42	15	e1.8	33	18	1.6	27	8	.58
6	e39	8	e.90	31	11	.94	26	3	.18
7	e37	7	e.69	31	7	.58	26	2	.14
8	e41	7	e.78	30	5	.36	25	2	.14
9	175	1020	1460	28	4	.34	25	4	.26
10	e229	1200	e1240	30	5	.42	24	9	.58
11	e212	822	e560	46	77	19	25	15	.99
12	e141	549	e218	38	80	9.1	24	21	1.3
13	e195	705	e758	34	31	2.9	23	20	1.3
14	449	1730	2880	30	24	2.0	23	17	1.0
15	e244	709	e589	67	215	109	22	18	1.1
16	165	193	94	48	67	9.8	20	19	1.1
17	125	62	21	34	20	1.8	20	9	.48
18	107	47	14	33	17	1.5	24	3	.18
19	89	29	7.0	112	510	643	22	2	.12
20	78	17	3.5	87	226	64	22	2	.12
21	70	10	1.9	45	32	4.0	21	2	.13
22	64	7	1.2	37	16	1.6	20	4	.20
23	59	6	.88	33	17	1.5	25	36	2.5
24	56	8	1.1	31	11	.92	24	6	.44
25	e56	16	e18	31	6	.47	22	2	.14
26	e55	28	e17	41	88	10	21	3	.17
27	49	31	4.0	34	33	3.0	21	4	.21
28	47	14	1.7	31	22	1.8	21	5	.29
29	44	6	.70	32	27	3.3	21	7	.43
30	43	8	.97	39	87	11	21	11	.62
31	40	13	1.4	---	---	---	23	11	.68
TOTAL	3243	---	7964.52	1213	---	907.10	735	---	21.68

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	24	19	1.6	20	13	.67	10	6	.16
2	23	35	2.3	18	11	.52	11	5	.16
3	19	21	1.1	15	12	.47	9.3	5	.13
4	19	15	.75	17	15	.87	9.2	5	.14
5	20	12	.61	56	122	34	8.9	6	.15
6	22	9	.57	20	8	.42	9.2	8	.20
7	49	100	27	15	7	.30	9.0	11	.26
8	24	24	1.8	20	20	1.7	8.9	13	.31
9	19	9	.44	25	44	3.4	8.6	14	.32
10	19	10	.52	16	14	.63	8.5	9	.20
11	31	67	10	14	11	.42	8.1	5	.11
12	28	47	3.8	13	11	.38	7.9	5	.10
13	22	23	1.4	13	10	.36	7.9	4	.09
14	19	13	.65	12	10	.33	15	22	2.9
15	17	7	.33	13	11	.36	22	39	3.1
16	17	6	.27	12	12	.38	11	7	.22
17	16	6	.26	12	12	.39	49	152	97
18	17	7	.30	11	6	.19	53	103	27
19	18	8	.36	12	5	.17	18	16	.81
20	16	9	.38	13	6	.21	13	9	.33
21	17	10	.44	13	6	.21	11	7	.21
22	17	9	.41	12	6	.18	9.5	6	.16
23	16	8	.36	12	5	.17	8.3	6	.14
24	17	8	.36	12	5	.16	7.9	6	.13
25	17	8	.36	12	5	.17	8.0	6	.13
26	16	8	.32	14	6	.21	9.9	6	.16
27	16	7	.31	11	6	.18	11	5	.16
28	17	7	.33	11	6	.18	9.6	5	.13
29	17	8	.36	---	---	---	8.9	6	.14
30	16	10	.45	---	---	---	8.9	7	.17
31	15	14	.56	---	---	---	10	9	.24
TOTAL	620	---	58.70	444	---	47.63	400.5	---	135.46
DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	9.2	11	.27	8.4	4	.09	16	9	.40
2	9.4	8	.19	8.0	4	.09	15	6	.26
3	9.9	5	.12	7.7	4	.09	16	7	.32
4	9.0	4	.11	9.2	5	.12	23	28	2.3
5	9.1	5	.12	9.7	5	.13	30	52	4.8
6	9.2	4	.10	20	33	5.0	28	24	2.0
7	27	44	9.8	40	82	10	22	11	.67
8	27	51	4.7	22	22	1.3	25	33	2.7
9	13	15	.52	22	7	.41	35	71	8.2
10	10	10	.28	19	6	.33	40	57	7.1
11	9.0	8	.20	16	7	.30	31	49	4.4
12	8.9	6	.14	13	7	.25	23	16	1.0
13	8.5	4	.10	12	7	.22	22	15	.86
14	8.7	5	.12	12	7	.22	21	15	.84
15	8.8	7	.16	14	13	.51	19	14	.71
16	8.7	5	.13	24	40	2.6	26	40	4.2
17	8.8	4	.10	25	54	6.4	187	818	1640
18	8.6	4	.09	39	76	8.4	58	135	23
19	11	18	.55	94	399	378	32	59	5.2
20	9.5	13	.34	68	119	24	23	32	2.0
21	9.0	9	.21	67	141	53	20	32	1.9
22	12	27	.90	63	129	27	19	15	.79
23	8.8	18	.44	32	31	3.1	20	23	1.7
24	8.7	10	.24	32	64	16	19	22	1.2
25	9.8	6	.17	138	744	683	17	17	.77
26	10	7	.18	75	197	50	16	9	.38
27	9.7	8	.20	30	28	2.4	16	9	.36
28	19	30	1.6	31	39	5.1	14	10	.39
29	11	20	.64	43	79	10	13	7	.27
30	8.4	6	.13	27	40	3.1	13	5	.20
31	---	---	---	21	15	.90	---	---	---
TOTAL	329.7	---	22.85	1042.0	---	1292.06	859	---	1718.92

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	13	5	.18	76	197	84	59	55	15
2	62	208	112	75	192	47	248	1800	4740
3	114	507	650	49	93	13	156	395	168
4	41	75	11	47	101	16	181	688	447
5	21	18	1.0	40	95	10	138	416	157
6	122	489	505	54	131	27	280	1820	5300
7	e72	163	e38	165	795	1160	148	209	87
8	e36	17	e1.7	159	676	466	113	22	6.9
9	25	12	.80	120	297	125	99	12	3.3
10	51	168	65	142	980	469	85	9	2.1
11	42	72	8.7	162	625	349	85	56	18
12	28	23	1.8	e112	206	e67	160	639	856
13	23	20	1.3	e82	36	e8.2	131	164	64
14	22	26	1.6	e69	16	e3.0	88	19	4.6
15	23	32	2.2	64	93	19	76	28	5.7
16	28	38	3.3	56	122	19	75	46	9.3
17	31	47	5.0	58	92	15	78	116	29
18	107	332	192	49	28	3.8	91	170	54
19	72	137	30	43	12	1.4	79	114	26
20	62	107	23	64	124	32	92	172	80
21	40	59	6.7	63	63	11	120	1140	1240
22	32	17	1.5	71	100	22	e4420	15900	e356000
23	65	189	98	61	36	6.4	422	648	853
24	45	121	16	48	16	2.2	287	151	118
25	36	53	5.1	152	413	185	258	80	56
26	33	30	2.7	85	227	53	244	43	29
27	92	404	342	263	1280	3160	237	24	15
28	69	76	16	130	200	86	233	13	8.4
29	47	17	2.1	e81	15	3.2	336	1120	2540
30	38	9	.90	e68	10	1.8	224	85	55
31	42	37	5.9	e64	7	1.3	---	---	---
TOTAL	1534	---	2150.48	2772	---	6466.3	9243	---	372987.3
YEAR	22435.2		393773.00						

e Estimated

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN .062 MM (70331)
MAY					
25...	1130	32	164	14	99
JUL					
03...	1730	794	3930	8430	94
27...	1730	517	2500	3490	90
AUG					
10...	1930	586	4590	7260	91
11...	1635	233	1180	742	93
SEP					
21...	2315	599	9980	16100	99
23...	1630	360	248	241	92

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L) (80154)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY) (80155)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70326)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70327)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70328)
OCT							
09...	1859	628	8620	14600	27	37	49
NOV							
19...	1850	806	5330	11600	40	50	64
JUN							
17...	1600	1760	7740	36800	37	48	62
AUG							
07...	1645	1040	5460	15300	32	45	60
SEP							
22...	0815	5510	22300	332000	35	51	69

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70329)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. % FINER THAN (70330)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70331)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70332)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70333)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70334)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. % FINER THAN (70335)
OCT							
09...	60	72	76	89	97	100	100
NOV							
19...	75	83	86	94	99	100	100
JUN							
17...	73	82	86	95	99	100	100
AUG							
07...	72	85	89	96	99	100	100
SEP							
22...	82	93	95	99	100	100	100

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°08'36", long 67°08'57", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on Highway 100, 1.4 mi (2.3 km), west of Hormigueros, and 2.0 mi (3.2 km),downstream from Río Rosario.

DRAINAGE AREA.--120 mi² (311 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Annual low-flow measurements 1959, monthly measurements April 1959 to November 1967, January 1973 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is at mean sea level. Previous to Nov. 7, 1980, at site 0.3 mi (0.5 km) upstream at datum 7.36 ft (2.243 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Daily discharges affected by sewage treatment plant about 2.1 mi (3.4 km) upstream from gage.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	216	91	51	35	15	20	16	e17	97	45	93	301
2	115	87	49	42	15	21	14	e16	81	141	256	748
3	89	85	55	28	13	19	14	e15	121	279	289	1550
4	76	83	47	26	17	19	12	e13	293	236	109	1200
5	70	80	44	32	439	19	11	e14	321	95	91	1030
6	64	77	42	28	146	20	11	e96	212	189	112	917
7	90	75	40	56	74	20	13	e120	109	219	462	1050
8	206	73	38	54	63	21	51	e43	91	108	1070	631
9	651	70	37	29	77	19	25	e97	99	84	551	467
10	1120	78	36	26	54	18	16	e35	103	89	420	342
11	1070	77	36	24	46	19	13	e23	84	127	538	246
12	810	104	35	46	41	18	13	e19	64	80	390	658
13	592	81	33	35	36	18	12	e17	67	68	218	1050
14	2770	70	32	28	33	22	11	16	57	64	192	358
15	2510	122	31	27	35	47	e10	19	48	73	324	243
16	1140	299	30	24	33	32	e50	46	48	72	223	214
17	655	113	29	23	28	26	e600	33	362	103	161	200
18	622	88	31	24	25	106	e60	51	329	331	137	238
19	406	121	31	24	24	39	e24	230	126	313	115	273
20	308	234	31	23	24	25	e46	346	86	144	169	248
21	251	98	29	22	22	20	e24	313	71	126	167	343
22	215	79	28	21	22	17	e18	290	74	106	169	e20200
23	168	69	29	19	21	15	e15	95	94	135	172	e6460
24	148	63	36	18	21	14	e13	76	172	111	122	2280
25	135	60	29	18	20	13	e19	452	122	82	1370	1440
26	e130	73	27	17	21	14	e100	565	81	73	847	e1310
27	117	67	26	17	22	15	e33	155	66	171	830	e869
28	e111	56	26	16	21	15	e39	163	58	214	1180	684
29	105	53	25	16	---	14	e33	551	51	139	438	632
30	101	63	25	16	---	14	e19	215	48	98	282	631
31	95	---	29	15	---	21	---	135	---	76	205	---
TOTAL	15156	2789	1067	829	1408	720	1335	4276	3635	4191	11702	46813
MEAN	489	93.0	34.4	26.7	50.3	23.2	44.5	138	121	135	377	1560
MAX	2770	299	55	56	439	106	600	565	362	331	1370	20200
MIN	64	53	25	15	13	13	10	13	48	45	91	200
AC-FT	30060	5530	2120	1640	2790	1430	2650	8480	7210	8310	23210	92850
CFSM	4.07	.77	.29	.22	.42	.19	.37	1.15	1.01	1.13	3.15	13.0
IN.	4.70	.86	.33	.26	.44	.22	.41	1.33	1.13	1.30	3.63	14.51

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1973 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	462	397	123	59.5	51.4	45.6	68.6	167	105	99.9	223	491														
MAX	1254	1518	422	112	119	244	316	636	504	240	757	2075														
(WY)	1986	1978	1976	1997	1996	1989	1989	1980	1979	1984	1988	1975														
MIN	97.5	42.7	15.4	13.8	13.9	10.6	16.1	12.7	9.23	26.4	42.3	78.5														
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1973	1977	1977	1977	1977	1977	1976	1976	1997														

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1998 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1973 - 1998
ANNUAL TOTAL	36049	93921	
ANNUAL MEAN	98.8	257	193
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			402
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			69.6
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2770	20200	Sep 16 1975
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	10	10	Apr 15 1977
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	11	13	Apr 1 1977
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		40600	Sep 22 1975
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		28.03	Sep 22 1975
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			4.6
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	71500	186300	139900
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.82	2.14	1.61
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	11.18	29.12	21.86
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	150	551	419
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	47	71	75
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	19	17	21

e Estimated

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 23...	0840	175	425	7.2	25.5	3.6	5.3	64	<10	580	710
MAR 27...	0750	16	414	7.1	24.5	7.1	6.1	74	<10	22000	330
JUN 11...	1015	83	408	6.6	26.5	59	6.3	79	<10	3400	2900
SEP 11...	0745	250	487	7.0	26.5	31	5.6	69	<10	4500	260

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 23...	190	26	31	14	.4	2.5	180	<.5	16	15
MAR 27...	--	--	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--
JUN 11...	180	26	29	16	.5	2.9	180	--	17	18
SEP 11...	240	44	32	8.4	.2	4.7	200	<1.0	12	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 23...	<.10	30	242	114	9	1.04	.055	1.10	.020	.34
MAR 27...	--	--	--	--	6	.940	.010	.950	.010	.20
JUN 11...	<.10	30	246	55.5	108	.950	.020	.970	.050	.23
SEP 11...	.11	17	250	169	74	--	.011	<.020	.060	.68

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 23...	.36	1.5	6.5	.160	<1	<100	50	<1	7	<10
MAR 27...	.20	1.0	4.5	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 11...	.28	1.3	5.5	.290	<1	100	60	<1	23	13
SEP 11...	.74	--	--	.030	--	--	--	--	--	--

66°45'

67°10'40"

Figure 24. Río Yagüez to Río Grande de Añasco basins.

RIO YAGÜEZ BASIN

50138800 RIO YAGÜEZ NEAR MAYAGÜEZ, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'31", long 67°07'07", at steel-truss bridge on unnumbered paved road about 800 ft (244 m) south of Highway 106, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) west of Highways 106 and 352 junction, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) east-northeast from Mayagüez plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.7 mi² (17.3 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT	22...	1400	13	300	7.6	26.0	1.4	6.5	80	<10	570	3300
MAR	26...	1300	1.5	307	8.0	25.5	.55	9.7	119	<10	340	K140
JUN	04...	1400	2.1	321	7.7	27.5	5.5	7.3	93	<10	K1600	2000
SEP	10...	1320	24	279	7.4	27.0	4.9	8.0	101	<10	K730	820

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)	
OCT	22...	130	35	11	11	.4	2.2	130	<.5	6.9	9.5
MAR	26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
JUN	04...	140	37	11	12	.5	2.6	140	--	9.7	11
SEP	10...	120	32	9.1	9.9	.4	2.2	120	<1.0	6.7	8.5

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	
OCT	22...	<.10	31	183	6.28	1	--	<.010	1.00	.020	--
MAR	26...	--	--	--	--	1	.950	.010	.960	.020	.20
JUN	04...	<.10	31	198	1.14	1	--	<.010	.520	.030	.21
SEP	10...	<.10	30	170	11.1	5	.988	.012	1.00	.020	--

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)	
OCT	22...	<.20	--	--	.020	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
MAR	26...	.23	.86	3.7	.070	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN	04...	.24	.76	3.4	.040	<1	<100	40	<1	1	<10
SEP	10...	<.20	--	--	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50141500 LAGO GUAYO AT DAMSITE NEAR CASTAÑER, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'46", long 66°50'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Guayo Dam on Río Guayo, 1.1 mi (1.8 km), southwest of Lago Yahuecas, 2.6 mi (4.2 km), southwest of Lago Prieto, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) north of Castañer, and 6.0 mi (9.6 km) west of Adjuntas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.60 mi² (24.86 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1980 to January 1985, June 1989 to current year. Prior to October 1994, published as Lago Guayo near Castañer .

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Guayo was completed in 1956. The dam is on Río Guayo and is the largest in the southwestern Puerto Rico project. The maximum storage is 17,400 ac-ft (21.5 hm³), for power and irrigation. The dam is a concrete gravity structure with a total length of 555 ft (169 m), a maximum structural height of 190 ft (58 m), and a maximum width at the base of 145 ft (44 m). The ungated overflow spillway with a crest elevation of 60.00 ft (18.29 m), and a crest length of 220 ft (67 m) was designed to pass a maximum flood of 30,200 ft³/s (855 m³/s) at a reservoir elevation of 70.00 ft (21.34 m). Timber flashboards that were added to increase storage capacity were subsequently removed and their use discontinued. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 1465.35 ft (446.64 m), Sept. 22, 1998; minimum elevation recorded, 1415.43 ft (431.42 m), June 2, 1990, but may have been less during period of no gage-height record June 2-5, 1990.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 1465.35 ft (446.64 m), Sept. 22; minimum elevation 1434.66 ft (437.28 m), Feb 25.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
1,415	3,960	1,460	13,550
1,449	10,660	1,465	15,000

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 2400 HOURS

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1441.69	1451.58	1453.10	1456.35	1444.11	1435.58	1441.53	1448.91	1460.17	1458.63	1444.73	1459.81
2	1441.95	1451.82	1453.33	1456.11	1443.29	1435.76	1442.70	1449.07	1459.21	1459.80	1445.41	1460.30
3	1440.94	1450.73	1453.56	1456.25	1441.27	1435.93	A	1449.22	1459.64	1460.20	1445.91	1460.30
4	1441.16	1449.67	1453.60	1456.38	1440.46	1436.12	1443.52	1449.02	1460.39	1460.17	1446.33	1460.38
5	1441.38	1449.67	1453.81	1456.56	1444.61	1436.28	1443.74	1449.16	1459.86	1460.13	1446.70	1459.92
6	1441.66	1448.89	1454.01	1456.79	1443.74	1436.55	1443.67	1449.52	1460.21	1460.60	1448.03	1460.04
7	1442.91	1447.93	1453.99	1455.88	1442.38	1436.82	1444.94	1449.84	1460.20	1459.66	1452.59	1459.48
8	1444.54	1446.40	1454.19	1455.78	1442.96	1437.00	1445.98	1452.88	1459.93	1458.87	1454.25	1459.19
9	1445.79	1446.66	1454.01	1455.80	1442.46	1437.15	1446.34	1454.06	1459.41	1457.31	1455.11	1458.08
10	1446.67	1447.44	1454.21	1455.95	1441.67	1437.30	1446.43	1454.41	1459.09	1456.55	1455.78	1457.22
11	1448.20	1448.36	1454.30	1456.09	1440.86	1437.45	1446.65	1454.67	1458.75	1455.85	1456.85	1457.87
12	1451.54	1449.06	1454.50	1455.90	1440.13	1437.59	1446.91	1454.86	1457.84	1455.56	1457.65	1459.49
13	1454.24	1449.48	1454.68	1455.72	1440.36	1437.75	1446.69	1455.04	1457.13	1453.79	1458.25	1460.32
14	1458.09	1449.91	1454.87	1454.84	1440.64	1437.85	1446.92	1455.28	1457.46	1452.72	1457.63	1459.48
15	1460.75	1450.23	1455.05	1454.32	1440.92	1438.05	1447.15	1455.83	1457.76	1452.07	1457.33	1460.28
16	1460.41	1450.67	1455.21	1453.42	1440.32	1438.30	1447.37	1456.19	1458.07	1451.21	1457.42	1460.32
17	1460.45	1450.55	1455.28	1453.58	1439.44	1438.74	1446.76	1456.38	1459.62	1451.36	1456.61	1460.33
18	1459.93	1450.87	1455.37	1453.77	1438.10	1438.70	1447.02	1456.64	A	1452.27	1455.76	1460.48
19	1459.90	1450.86	1455.49	1453.94	1437.22	1438.88	1447.27	1458.80	1459.40	1451.97	1455.54	1460.28
20	1458.92	1451.19	1455.39	1453.25	1437.13	1439.03	1447.47	1461.13	1459.11	1451.83	1454.68	1460.32
21	1458.57	1451.49	1455.57	1452.45	1436.80	1439.19	1447.66	1461.31	1459.45	1451.00	1454.33	1462.46
22	1457.99	1451.63	1455.56	1451.89	1436.45	1439.32	1446.96	1460.46	1459.01	1449.71	1453.20	1461.23
23	1457.27	1451.67	1455.74	1451.29	1435.80	1439.45	1447.14	1460.27	1458.21	1450.14	1453.46	1460.83
24	1456.98	1451.33	1455.73	1450.44	1434.90	1439.58	1447.30	1460.24	1458.05	1449.58	1453.18	1460.66
25	1456.43	1451.54	1455.89	1448.32	1434.73	1439.73	1447.52	1460.23	1458.37	1449.99	1456.07	1460.67
26	1455.69	1451.85	1456.05	1447.31	1434.96	1439.88	1447.74	1459.64	1458.65	1450.03	1455.95	1460.49
27	1454.71	1452.12	1456.20	1446.11	1435.18	1440.04	1448.09	1459.51	1457.74	1449.05	1457.44	1460.43
28	1453.29	1452.37	1456.31	1445.08	1435.39	1440.16	1448.49	1458.70	1458.01	1448.53	1458.73	1460.40
29	A	1452.62	1456.45	1444.01	---	1440.38	1448.69	1459.25	1458.26	1447.44	1459.81	1460.42
30	A	1452.87	1456.59	1443.79	---	1440.76	1448.84	1459.76	1458.40	1446.31	1459.85	1460.39
31	1451.95	---	1456.51	1443.96	---	1440.20	---	1460.11	---	1444.65	1459.73	---
MAX	---	1452.87	1456.59	1456.79	1444.61	1440.76	---	1461.31	---	1460.60	1459.85	1462.46
MIN	---	1446.40	1453.10	1443.79	1434.73	1435.58	---	1448.91	---	1444.65	1444.73	1457.22

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50143000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR LARES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'26", long 66°55'00", at bridge on Highway 124, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) downstream from confluence of Río Blanco and Río Prieto, and 3.7 mi (6.0 km) southwest of Lares plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--26.3 mi² (68.1 km²) this does not include 36.2 mi² (93.8 km²) which contributes only during high floods, and 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) which contributes only part of its storm runoff.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959-68, 1970 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 20...	1100	85	269	8.0	25.5	3.0	7.7	93	<10	37000	K160
MAR 05...	0905	10	317	8.0	23.0	1.7	8.3	97	<10	200	K91
JUN 02...	1400	88	251	7.2	28.5	3.2	7.1	94	<10	220	K1100
SEP 09...	1130	100	267	7.7	27.5	4.0	7.5	97	<10	240	200

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 20...	110	30	8.9	10	.4	2.3	100	<.5	16	10
MAR 05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
JUN 02...	110	29	8.9	20	.8	2.3	93	--	9.6	29
SEP 09...	100	26	8.7	19	.8	3.1	98	<1.0	10	26

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 20...	<.10	31	168	38.6	4	1.20	.150	1.40	1.50	.86
MAR 05...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<.010	.420	.030	--
JUN 02...	<.10	25	180	42.7	3	--	<.010	.310	.050	.63
SEP 09...	<.10	28	196	52.9	6	1.79	.010	1.80	.010	--

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 20...	2.4	3.8	17	.940	<1	<100	10	<1	<1	<10
MAR 05...	<.20	--	--	.030	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 02...	.68	.99	4.4	.040	<1	<100	20	<1	<1	12
SEP 09...	<.20	--	--	.020	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50144000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'05", long 67°03'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on left bank, at downstream side of bridge on Highway 108, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) downstream from Quebrada La Zumbadora, 4.4 mi (7.1 km) northwest of Las Marias, 5.4 mi (8.7 km) southwest of San Sebastian.

DRAINAGE AREA.--94.3 mi² (244.2 km²), does not include 36.2 mi² (93.8 km²) which contributes only during high floods, and 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) which contributes only part of its storm runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1963 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 103.72 ft (31.614 m) above mean sea level (Puerto Rico Department of Public Works bench mark). Previous to Oct. 30, 1975, at site 600 ft (180 m) upstream at same datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Transbasin diversion (except during floods) to Rio Yauco basin for hydroelectric power and irrigation above Lago Guayo, Yahuecas, and Prieto, combined useable storage 17,300 acre-ft (21.3 km³). Limited storm runoff is contributed to basin by 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) above Rio Toro Diversion dam. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	384	193	138	88	61	61	139	64	138	103	208	384
2	467	185	131	87	60	59	193	64	208	132	202	4200
3	239	181	126	79	60	58	121	63	185	213	230	1130
4	197	172	120	77	58	56	82	73	142	263	281	1020
5	329	164	115	76	286	76	72	66	426	186	218	800
6	210	160	113	81	121	72	66	97	298	462	167	1910
7	191	157	109	103	81	153	59	190	209	580	2200	816
8	236	154	111	108	90	106	261	190	195	346	1010	636
9	362	150	109	81	153	73	107	338	166	161	1120	574
10	413	151	108	77	94	69	79	118	134	305	1320	488
11	452	159	112	103	78	67	69	85	148	366	931	490
12	564	259	104	143	74	64	65	70	159	636	736	996
13	795	196	102	86	74	64	64	62	507	286	399	829
14	1980	175	101	88	70	73	62	58	198	435	314	612
15	1690	300	100	78	74	144	57	97	157	471	271	449
16	1380	280	98	74	74	100	55	140	709	419	246	1030
17	775	170	95	71	70	88	54	107	560	352	291	591
18	727	155	98	114	67	217	52	177	662	233	263	619
19	461	151	95	85	63	100	e73	496	350	246	213	624
20	384	181	94	76	62	77	75	943	199	197	198	480
21	304	148	93	74	61	68	70	5740	156	195	233	528
22	282	141	93	112	60	65	71	2660	151	156	287	69900
23	264	135	97	74	60	61	62	655	133	368	274	e4200
24	250	140	119	68	59	58	66	400	124	422	216	e2290
25	237	169	94	67	57	62	68	328	272	202	1050	e1450
26	231	311	88	67	66	65	77	420	153	166	419	e1170
27	218	221	86	66	66	68	67	202	201	151	1430	e1110
28	209	164	83	65	62	68	133	159	129	150	838	e916
29	202	165	82	63	---	63	107	258	114	322	435	e1050
30	197	183	82	62	---	116	72	210	108	163	435	e3850
31	196	---	107	61	---	146	---	177	---	411	614	---
TOTAL	14826	5470	3203	2554	2261	2617	2598	14707	7291	9098	17049	105142
MEAN	478	182	103	82.4	80.8	84.4	86.6	474	243	293	550	3505
MAX	1980	311	138	143	286	217	261	5740	709	636	2200	69900
MIN	191	135	82	61	57	56	52	58	108	103	167	384
AC-FT	29410	10850	6350	5070	4480	5190	5150	29170	14460	18050	33820	208500
CFSM	5.07	1.93	1.10	.87	.86	.90	.92	5.03	2.58	3.11	5.83	37.2
IN.	5.85	2.16	1.26	1.01	.89	1.03	1.02	5.80	2.88	3.59	6.73	41.48

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1963 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	660	428	221	141	115	104	143	374	287	268	364	691
MAX	1467	746	482	286	345	271	313	1084	815	657	936	3505
(WY)	1993	1982	1966	1997	1996	1972	1971	1986	1979	1979	1979	1998
MIN	344	182	103	82.4	62.3	54.4	49.3	63.7	71.2	111	152	206
(WY)	1983	1998	1992	1998	1992	1965	1968	1967	1977	1990	1967	1983

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1998 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1963 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	75096	186816										
ANNUAL MEAN	206	512								316		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN										512		1998
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN										189		1967
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1980	Oct 14	69900	Sep 22	69900	Sep 22	1998			32	Apr 18	1965
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	56	Jun 17	52	Apr 18	35	Apr 14	1965			35	Apr 14	1965
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	58	Jun 11	58	Apr 12	163000	Sep 22	1998			163000	Sep 22	1998
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW										34.50	Sep 22	1998
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE										51	Apr 18	1965
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW										31	Apr 19	1965
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	149000	370500								229100		
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.18	5.43								3.35		
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	29.62	73.70								45.56		
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	381	716								654		
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	153	153								184		
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	72	64								74		

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN
50144000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR--Continued

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50144000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1963 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (00301)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)
OCT 21...	1210	312	247	8.1	26.0	4.6	8.0	98	<10	360
FEB 24...	1150	58	264	7.7	24.0	3.0	8.6	101	<10	K90
JUN 03...	0900	145	245	7.5	26.5	17	7.6	95	<10	K1400
SEP 09...	1600	E488	219	7.3	26.5	36	7.7	96	<10	4000

DATE	STREP-TOCOCCHI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	HARD-NESS AS CACO3 (MG/L) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED AS CA (MG/L) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED AS MG (MG/L) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED AS NA (MG/L) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED AS K (MG/L) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED AS SO4 (MG/L) (00945)
OCT 21...	390	110	27	9.6	8.3	.3	1.8	98	--	9.9
FEB 24...	K80	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--
JUN 03...	K600	100	26	8.6	8.8	.4	2.2	100	--	11
SEP 09...	3100	89	22	8.0	8.4	.4	1.9	90	<1.0	8.5

DATE	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 21...	7.5	<.10	29	152	128	7	<.010	1.30	.020	--
FEB 24...	--	--	--	--	--	1	<.010	.390	.020	.23
JUN 03...	8.2	.12	25	150	58.7	26	<.010	.730	.030	.25
SEP 09...	6.7	<.10	27	137	E180	54	<.010	1.30	.030	--

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 21...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	<10	--	1	<10
FEB 24...	.25	.64	2.8	.020	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 03...	.28	1.0	4.5	.040	<1	<100	<10	<1	1	<10
SEP 09...	<.20	--	--	.050	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50146000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR AÑASCO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'00", long 67°08'05", at bridge on Highway 430, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) south of Highway 109 at El Espino and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) east-southeast from Añasco plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--139 mi² (360 km²) this does not include 39.7 mi² (102.8 km²), flow is diverted to south coast.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD) (00400)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TURBIDITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLIFORM, FECA, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT 21...	1415	E600	247	7.6	27.5	9.6	7.5	94	10	210	360
MAR 13...	0920	81	259	7.7	25.0	4.2	6.7	80	<10	K110	K40
JUN 04...	0830	219	237	7.3	27.0	60	6.7	84	<10	K1500	K1600
SEP 10...	1450	E500	220	7.3	27.5	31	7.2	91	<10	39000	2700

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORPTION RATIO (00931)	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD CACO3 (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 21...	100	26	9.5	8.3	.4	1.8	100	<1.0	9.7	7.8
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
JUN 04...	96	25	8.4	8.7	.4	2.3	97	--	8.8	7.8
SEP 10...	89	23	8.0	8.3	.4	1.9	92	<1.0	7.8	6.7

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 21...	<.10	29	153	E248	6	--	<.010	1.10	.020	--
MAR 13...	--	--	--	--	8	--	<.010	.230	.040	.19
JUN 04...	<.10	24	143	84.6	82	--	<.010	.670	.040	.45
SEP 10...	<.10	27	138	E186	50	1.19	.012	1.20	.030	.22

DATE	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOSPHORUS, TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHROMIUM, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOVERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 21...	<.20	--	--	.030	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	10
MAR 13...	.23	.46	2.0	.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 04...	.49	1.2	5.1	.060	<1	<100	20	<1	2	<10
SEP 10...	.25	1.5	6.4	.060	--	--	--	--	--	--

Figure 25. Río Culebrinas basin.

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147600 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'51", long 67°02'40", at bridge on Highway 423, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) south of Quebrada El Salto Bridge on Highway 111, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) west of Central La Plata.

DRAINAGE AREA.--58.2 mi² (150.7 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD) (UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (00301)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER (COLS./100 ML) (31679)	
OCT	22...	0950	104	310	7.8	25.5	2.8	7.9	96	<10	5800	1000
MAR	12...	1205	31	330	7.9	24.5	4.4	7.9	94	<10	450	280
JUN	03...	1430	E1000	194	7.3	26.5	760	6.9	86	19	60000	53000
SEP	10...	0945	246	311	7.6	25.0	56	7.6	91	<10	24000	3500

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)	
OCT	22...	140	45	5.8	11	.4	2.1	130	<1.0	11	11
MAR	12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
JUN	03...	78	26	3.1	6.1	.3	3.9	77	--	13	7.3
SEP	10...	130	45	4.6	8.5	.3	2.3	140	<1.0	11	8.4

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)	
OCT	22...	<.10	29	194	54.6	3	1.17	.030	1.20	.040	--
MAR	12...	--	--	--	--	4	1.28	.017	1.30	.030	.19
JUN	03...	<.10	12	118	E318	1450	.766	.034	.800	.250	3.0
SEP	10...	.10	20	184	123	62	.662	.018	.680	.060	.60

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, TOTAL UNFLTRD (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)	
OCT	22...	<.20	--	--	<.020	<1	<100	<10	<1	<10	30
MAR	12...	.22	1.5	6.7	.080	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN	03...	3.2	4.0	18	.190	<1	<100	<10	<1	10	37
SEP	10...	.66	1.3	5.9	.160	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147800 RIO CULEBRINAS AT HIGHWAY 404 NEAR MOCA, PR--Continued

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50149100 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR AGUADA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'03", long 67°09'40", at bridge on Highway 2, 2.3 mi (3.7 km) northeast of Aguada plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--97.0 mi² (251.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1970 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND (00061)	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS) (00400)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU) (00076)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L) (00340)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML) (31616)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
OCT 22...	0745	--	361	7.1	26.0	18	6.8	83	<10	2300 640
MAR 12...	0915	--	354	8.1	25.0	9.8	6.7	80	<10	K1200 340
JUN 03...	1645	E1500	336	8.2	28.0	160	6.7	85	<10	K12000 4000
SEP 10...	1130	447	292	7.4	26.0	140	6.3	77	<10	51000 5800

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3) (00900)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET (MG/L AS CACO3) (00410)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S) (00745)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
OCT 22...	150	51	6.3	12	.4	2.3	130	<1.0	11	13
MAR 12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
JUN 03...	140	49	5.0	9.5	.3	3.2	140	--	18	11
SEP 10...	130	43	4.6	9.0	.3	2.6	130	<1.0	8.5	9.8

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY) (70302)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
OCT 22...	<.10	29	203	--	29	.848	.012	.860	.050	.19
MAR 12...	--	--	--	--	20	.839	.011	.850	.050	.46
JUN 03...	<.10	17	197	E798	208	.795	.015	.810	.060	.72
SEP 10...	<.10	19	175	211	192	.982	.018	1.00	.080	.38

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS) (01002)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA) (01007)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B) (01022)	CADMIUM, WATER UNFLTRD TOTAL (UG/L AS CD) (01027)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR) (01034)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU) (01042)
OCT 22...	.24	1.1	4.9	.030	<1	<100	30	<1	3	<10
MAR 12...	.51	1.4	6.0	.060	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 03...	.78	1.6	7.0	.050	<1	<100	40	<1	4	<10
SEP 10...	.46	1.5	6.5	.070	--	--	--	--	--	--

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**Discharge at
Partial-Record Stations
in Puerto Rico**

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PUERTO RICO

EXPLANATION

- 043950 ↓ ▲ LOW-FLOW STATION AND NUMBER
- TOWN OR CITY
- DRAINAGE BASIN BOUNDARY
- - - MUNICIPAL BOUNDARY OF COMERÍO

Figure 26. Location of low-flow partial-record stations in Comerio, Puerto Rico.

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

As the number of streams on which streamflow information is likely to be desired far exceeds the number of stream-gaging stations feasible to operate at one time, the Geological Survey collects limited streamflow data at sites other than stream-gaging stations. When limited streamflow data are collected on a systematic basis over a period of years for use in hydrologic analyses, the site at which the data are collected is called a partial-record station. Data collected at these partial-record stations are useable in low-flow or floodflow analyses, depending on the type of data collected. In addition, discharge measurements are made at other sites not included in the partial-record program. These measurements are generally made in times of drought or flood to give better areal coverage to those events. Those measurements and others collected for some special reason are called measurements at miscellaneous sites.

Low-flow partial-record stations

Measurements of streamflow in the areas covered by this report made at low-flow partial-record stations are given in the following table. These measurements were made during periods of base flow when streamflow is primarily from ground-water storage. These measurements, when correlated with the simultaneous discharge of nearby stream when continuous records are available, will give a picture of the low-flow potentiality of stream.

Discharge measurements made at low-flow partial-records stations during water year 1998

PUBLICATION RECORD

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río de La Plata basin						
50043500	Quebrada Prieta at barrio Río Hondo, PR	Lat 18°12'27", long 66°14'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Río Hondo, 0.3 mi (0.5 Km) upstream of Río de La Plata, 1.9 mi (3.0 km) southwest of Cerro Lazo, and 1.4 mi (2.2 km) southwest from Comercio plaza.	1.16 (3.00)	1/29/98	0745	0.14 (0.004)
				3/11/98	1045	0.15 (0.004)
				3/20/98	1425	1.03 (0.029)
				6/09/98	0810	0.20 (0.006)
				6/16/98	1350	0.17 (0.005)
				6/24/98	1050	0.12 (0.003)
				7/14/98	0645	0.07 (0.001)
				1/26/99	1200	0.78 (0.022)
				2/12/99	0820	0.52 (0.015)
				2/24/99	1145	0.61 (0.017)
				3/16/99	1145	0.34 (0.010)
50043575	Río Hondo at Highway 776 at Río Hondo, PR	Lat 18°13'18", long 66°15'07", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Río Hondo on Highway 776, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) north of Escuela Segunda Unidad de Río Hondo, 4.3 mi (6.9 km) northeast of Barranquitas, and 4.4 mi (7.1 km) northeast from Cañón San Cristóbal.	9.07 (23.5)	1/29/98	0820	2.82 (0.080)
				3/11/98	1000	3.43 (0.097)
				3/20/98	1315	8.32 (0.236)
				6/09/98	0840	5.67 (0.160)
				6/16/98	1250	4.92 (0.139)
				6/24/98	1120	4.78 (0.135)
				7/14/98	0805	3.77 (0.107)
				7/15/98	0850	3.73 (0.106)
				1/26/99	1005	13.9 (0.394)
				2/12/99	0930	11.9 (0.337)
				2/24/99	1050	10.4 (0.294)
3/16/99	1045	9.00 (0.255)				
50043600	Río Hondo near Comercio, PR	Lat 18°12'38", long 66°14'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at Highway 156 at barrio Río Hondo, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) upstream of Río La Plata, and 1.3 mi (2.1 km) southwest from Comercio plaza.	10.5 (27.2)	6/25/98	1045	4.97 (0.141)
				7/14/98	0715	3.56 (0.101)
				7/15/98	0810	3.41 (0.096)
				1/26/99	1100	16.1 (0.456)
				2/12/99	0845	13.5 (0.382)
				2/24/99	1000	10.4 (0.294)
				3/16/99	1000	8.23 (0.233)

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río de La Plata basin						
50043790	Quebrada Pifa at Highway 775 at Comerío, PR	Lat 18°13'00", long 66°13'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at Comerío, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream of Río de La Plata, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) west of Cerro Lazo, and 0.3 mi (0.5 km) south from Comerío plaza.	2.31 (5.98)	1/29/98	0935	0.24 (0.007)
				3/11/98	0850	0.32 (0.009)
				3/23/98	1205	0.28 (0.008)
				6/09/98	0720	0.23 (0.006)
				6/15/98	1155	0.16 (0.004)
				6/24/98	1215	0.18 (0.005)
				7/14/98	0905	0.06 (0.002)
				1/26/99	0850	1.77 (0.050)
				2/12/99	1110	0.97 (0.027)
				2/24/99	0845	0.83 (0.024)
				3/16/99	0830	0.54 (0.015)
				50043803	Quebrada Convento at Comerío, PR	Lat 18°13'31", long 66°13'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at Comerío, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) south of Cerro Magueyes, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Río de La Plata, and 0.3 mi (0.5 km) north from Comerío plaza.
3/11/98	0750	0.74 (0.021)				
6/09/98	0935	0.65 (0.018)				
6/11/98	1455	0.46 (0.013)				
6/24/98	1005	0.54 (0.015)				
7/14/98	0930	0.51 (0.016)				
1/26/99	0815	1.05 (0.030)				
2/09/99	1005	1.02 (0.029)				
2/24/99	0805	0.92 (0.026)				
3/16/99	0755	0.84 (0.024)				
50043820	Quebrada Higüero at Highway 780 at barrio Doña Elena, PR	Lat 18°14'37", long 66°14'51", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at (2.4 km) northwest of Cerro Magueyes, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad de Palomas, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) northwest from Comerío plaza.	1.19 (3.08)	2/02/98	1520	0.46 (0.013)
				3/25/98	1035	0.42 (0.012)
				6/17/98	1210	0.81 (0.023)
				6/22/98	1315	0.71 (0.020)
				7/15/98	0625	0.62 (0.018)
				1/25/99	1220	2.06 (0.058)
				2/09/99	1125	2.24 (0.063)
				2/23/99	1150	1.91 (0.054)
				3/15/99	1040	1.71 (0.048)
				50043840	Tributario de Quebrada Higüero at barrio Palomas, PR	Lat 18°14'10", long 66°14'35", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Palomas, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) west of Cerro Magueyes, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad de Palomas, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) from Comerío plaza.
3/10/98	1235	0.15 (0.004)				
3/23/98	1530	0.15 (0.004)				
6/17/98	1310	0.30 (0.008)				
6/22/98	1115	0.33 (0.009)				
7/15/98	0705	0.18 (0.005)				
1/25/99	1315	0.58 (0.016)				
2/09/99	1045	0.63 (0.018)				
2/23/99	1110	0.53 (0.015)				
3/15/99	1130	0.47 (0.013)				

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río de La Plata basin						
50043845	Quebrada Higüero at Highway 156 near Comerío, PR	Lat 18°14'15", long 66°12'55", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Palomas, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northeast of Cerro Magueyes, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) southwest of Cerro La Tiza, and 1.4 mi (2.2 km) northeast from Comerío plaza.	3.65 (9.45)	1/29/98	1125	2.54 (0.072)
				3/10/98	1055	3.05 (0.086)
				3/17/98	1110	2.16 (0.061)
				6/09/98	1030	3.25 (0.092)
				6/11/98	1350	2.53 (0.072)
				6/24/98	0920	2.85 (0.081)
				7/14/98	1050	2.46 (0.070)
				1/25/99	1050	7.77 (0.220)
				2/09/99	0905	7.67 (0.217)
				2/23/99	1000	6.40 (0.181)
3/15/99	0940	5.53 (0.157)				
50043950	Río Arroyata at Highway 7774 near Cidra, PR	Lat 18°12'04", long 66°12'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Vega Redonda on Highway 7774, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northwest of Cerro Almirante, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) north of Cerro Viento Caliente, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southeast of Comerío plaza.	9.42 (24.4)	1/28/98	1130	2.12 (0.060)
				3/16/98	1105	2.49 (0.070)
				6/25/98	0945	1.88 (0.053)
				7/13/98	0915	1.03 (0.029)
				2/04/99	1100	9.28 (0.263)
				2/11/99	1000	7.88 (0.223)
				2/25/99	1035	6.44 (0.182)
3/17/99	1025	4.67 (0.132)				
50043970	Quebrada Cejas at barrio Vega Redonda, PR	Lat 18°12'56", long 66°12'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Vega Redonda, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) east of Cerro Lazo, 2.2 mi (3.5 km) southwest of Cerro La Tiza, and 1.7 mi (2.7 km) southeast from Comerío plaza.	1.29 (3.34)	1/28/98	1310	0.80 (0.023)
				3/16/98	1155	0.95 (0.027)
				3/18/98	1335	0.68 (0.019)
				6/10/98	1625	0.82 (0.023)
				6/25/98	0850	1.56 (0.044)
				7/13/98	0950	0.14 (0.004)
				2/04/99	1010	2.00 (0.057)
				2/11/99	1050	2.03 (0.057)
2/25/99	0940	1.72 (0.049)				
3/17/99	0940	1.44 (0.041)				
50043980	Río Arroyata at barrio Naranjo, PR	Lat 18°13'30", long 66°12'12", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Naranjo, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) northeast of Cerro Lazo, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southwest of Cerro La Tiza, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northeast of Comerío plaza.	12.9 (33.4)	1/28/98	1345	2.55 (0.072)
				3/16/98	1245	3.39 (0.096)
				6/25/98	0805	2.82 (0.080)
				7/13/98	1025	1.19 (0.034)
				2/04/99	0925	12.1 (0.343)
				2/11/99	1130	11.0 (0.312)
2/25/99	0855	9.17 (0.260)				
3/17/99	0850	7.61 (0.216)				

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río de La Plata basin						
50043995	Quebrada Naranjo at barrio Naranjo, PR	Lat 18°13'54", long 66°12'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Naranjo, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northeast of Cerro Lazo, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) southwest of Cerro La Tiza, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) north- east from Comerío plaza.	2.58 (6.68)	1/28/98	1430	1.16 (0.033)
				3/16/98	1330	1.29 (0.036)
				3/18/98	1430	1.08 (0.030)
				6/10/98	1540	0.86 (0.024)
				6/25/98	0720	1.13 (0.032)
				7/13/98	1100	0.85 (0.024)
				2/04/99	0835	4.37 (0.124)
				2/11/99	1215	3.99 (0.113)
				2/25/99	0805	3.43 (0.097)
				3/17/99	0800	3.10 (0.088)
50044050	Quebrada Doña Elena at Highway 167 near Comerío, PR	Lat 18°15'04", long 66°12'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Doña Elena, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream of Río de La Plata, 2.4 mi (3.9 km) south- east of Cerro Avispa, 4.3 mi (6.9 km) southeast from Comerío plaza.	1.28 (3.32)	1/29/98	1220	0.70 (0.020)
				3/10/98	1010	0.86 (0.024)
				3/20/98	1020	0.70 (0.020)
				6/09/98	1200	0.70 (0.020)
				6/11/98	1230	0.67 (0.019)
				6/24/98	0825	0.62 (0.018)
				7/13/98	1145	0.60 (0.017)
				7/15/98	1005	0.54 (0.015)
				1/25/99	0955	1.76 (0.050)
				2/09/99	0820	1.68 (0.048)
2/23/99	0920	1.48 (0.042)				
3/15/99	0905	1.36 (0.038)				

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66°08'45"
18°19'41"

65°59'14"

18°06'20"

Figure 27. Location of low-flow partial-record stations in Caguas, Puerto Rico.

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)				
Río Grande de Loíza basin										
50052925	Río Turabo at barrio San Salvador, PR	Lat 18°08'37", long 66°03'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio San Salvador, 2.7 mi (4.3 km) southwest of Cerro Gregorio, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad de Mercedes Palma, and 2.4 mi (3.9 km) southwest from Villa Borinquen.	1.38 (3.57)	2/24/98	1120	3.23 (0.091)				
				5/13/98	1220	3.16 (0.089)				
				6/16/98	0655	3.20 (0.091)				
				7/01/98	1025	2.59 (0.073)				
				9/17/98	1130	8.35 (0.236)				
				2/19/99	0805	3.99 (0.113)				
				3/05/99	0815	3.15 (0.089)				
				3/19/99	0735	2.60 (0.074)				
				4/19/99	0845	2.05 (0.058)				
				50052950	Quebrada Maracai at barrio San Salvador, PR	Lat 18°08'37", long 66°03'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio San Salvador, 2.7 mi (4.3 km) southwest of Cerro Gregorio, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad de Mercedes Palma, and 2.4 mi (3.9 km) southwest of Villa Borinquen.	2.31 (5.98)	2/24/98	1200	4.09 (0.116)
5/13/98	1140	5.10 (0.144)								
6/16/98	0735	3.77 (0.107)								
7/01/98	1105	3.29 (0.093)								
9/17/98	1210	5.54 (0.157)								
2/19/99	0725	6.49 (0.184)								
3/05/99	0730	5.19 (0.147)								
3/19/99	0700	4.70 (0.133)								
4/19/99	0810	3.45								
50053060	Río Turabo at Highway 765 at barrio Borinquen, PR	Lat 18°10'45", long 66°02'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Borinquen, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) northwest of Cerro Gregorio, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northeast of Cerro Las Piñas, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) from El Naranjito.	8.06 (20.9)					2/24/98	0750	12.2 (0.346)
				3/19/98	1055	15.3 (0.433)				
				5/12/98	1355	13.7 (0.388)				
				7/01/98	0840	9.46 (0.268)				
				2/18/99	1150	15.6 (0.442)				
				3/04/99	1215	12.8 (0.362)				
				3/22/99	1055	10.0 (0.283)				
				4/19/99	1030	8.22 (0.233)				
				50053080	Quebrada Naranjito at barrio Borinquen, PR	Lat 18°10'56", long 66°02'35", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Borinquen, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northwest of Cerro Gregorio, 3.1 mi (5.0 km) northeast of Cerro Las Piñas, and 1.1 mi (1.8 km) northwest from El Naranjito.	2.24 (5.80)	2/24/98	0715	1.14 (0.032)
								3/19/98	1025	0.95 (0.027)
5/12/98	1300	0.91 (0.026)								
7/01/98	0805	0.33 (0.009)								
2/18/99	1240	1.15 (0.032)								
3/04/99	1305	1.17 (0.033)								
3/22/99	1140	0.61 (0.017)								
4/19/99	1115	0.54 (0.015)								

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Grande de Loíza basin						
50053150	Quebrada Sonadora at barrio Beatriz, PR	Lat 18°10'22", long 66°03'42", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Beatriz, 3.6 mi (5.8 km) northwest of Cerro Gregorio, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northeast of Cerro Las Piñas, and 1.4 mi (2.2 km) southeast from Villa Borinquen.	1.20 (3.11)	2/24/98	0900	1.33 (0.038)
				5/14/98	1210	0.98 (0.028)
				6/16/98	0930	0.90 (0.025)
				7/02/98	1130	0.75 (0.021)
				9/17/98	1405	1.98 (0.056)
				2/19/99	1000	1.76 (0.050)
				3/05/99	1000	1.56 (0.044)
				3/19/99	0930	1.27 (0.036)
				4/20/98	1105	1.06 (0.030)
				50053200	Quebrada Beatriz at barrio Beatriz, PR	Lat 18°11'01", long 66°03'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Beatriz, 4.1 mi (6.6 km) northwest of Cerro Gregorio, 2.3 mi (3.7 km) northeast of Cerro Las Piñas, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest from Villa Borinquen.
6/03/98	1045	1.99 (0.056)				
6/16/98	1025	2.43 (0.069)				
7/02/98	1020	2.23 (0.063)				
2/19/99	1050	5.74 (0.162)				
3/05/99	1055	4.75 (0.134)				
3/19/99	1030	3.90 (0.110)				
4/20/99	0955	3.00 (0.085)				
50053950	Quebrada de Las Quebradillas at barrio Beatriz, PR	Lat 18°11'40", long 66°05'25", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Beatriz, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) northwest of Cerro Las Piñas, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northeast of Las Cruces, and 3.4 mi (5.5 km) northwest from Villa Borinquen.	3.85 (9.97)	2/04/98	1205	3.57 (0.101)
				6/04/98	1135	3.01 (0.085)
				6/16/98	1145	3.31 (0.094)
				7/02/98	0915	2.41 (0.068)
				2/18/99	0935	8.14 (0.230)
				3/03/99	1000	6.57 (0.186)
				3/04/99	1010	7.77 (0.220)
				3/22/99	0910	5.40 (0.153)
				4/20/99	0845	4.57 (0.129)
50053975	Quebrada de Las Quebradillas above Dam at barrio Turabo, PR	Lat 18°11'37", long 66°04'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Beatriz, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) northeast of Cerro Las Piñas, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) northwest of Villa Borinquen, and 3.7 mi (6.0 km) southwest from Caguas plaza.	6.27 (16.2)	2/04/98	1050	4.70 (0.133)
				5/26/98	1200	9.15 (0.259)
				6/16/98	1250	4.72 (0.137)
				7/02/98	0845	4.14 (0.117)
				2/18/99	0825	11.5 (0.326)
				3/02/99	0930	12.3 (0.348)
				3/04/99	0850	10.5 (0.297)
				3/22/99	0810	8.57 (0.242)
4/20/99	0730	6.99 (0.198)				

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Grande de Loíza basin						
50054300	Río Turabo at Villa del Rey near Caguas, PR	Lat 18°12'51", long 66°02'30", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Turabo, 2.5 mi (4.0 km) north of Villa Borinquen, 4.8 mi (7.7 km) northwest of Cerro Gregorio, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) southwest from Caguas plaza.	25.0 (64.8)	2/04/98	0945	10.8 (0.306)
				6/02/98	1150	11.0 (0.312)
				6/16/98	1350	9.72 (0.275)
				7/01/98	0650	5.31 (0.150)
				9/17/99	1015	37.1 (1.051)
				2/18/99	1040	27.0 (0.765)
				3/04/99	1110	21.2 (0.600)
				3/19/99	1140	14.1 (0.400)
				4/19/99	1310	12.1 (0.343)
				50055120	Río Cagüitas at Highway 156 near Caguas, PR	Lat 18°14'41", long 66°03'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Cañabón at Highway 156, 3.4 mi (5.5 km) northeast of Los Sumideros, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northeast of Escuela Bunker, and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northwest from Caguas plaza.
3/19/98	0820	1.35 (0.038)				
5/19/98	1010	3.51 (0.099)				
6/30/98	1135	1.73 (0.049)				
8/05/98	1015	3.04 (0.086)				
2/17/99	1200	7.89 (0.223)				
3/08/99	1125	6.62 (0.187)				
3/18/99	1130	5.48 (0.153)				
50055150	Río Cañaboncito at barrio Cañaboncito, PR	Lat 18°12'53", long 66°04'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Cañaboncito, 2.6 mi (4.2 km) southeast of Los Sumideros, 4.1 mi (6.6 km) northeast of Cerro Las Pifias, and 3.0 mi (4.8 km) Southwest from Caguas plaza.	1.61 (4.17)	2/04/98	0845	0.65 (0.018)
				3/19/98	0910	0.83 (0.024)
				5/21/98	1035	0.50 (0.014)
				7/02/98	0715	0.58 (0.016)
				8/05/98	1125	0.64 (0.018)
				9/18/98	1140	0.74 (0.021)
				2/18/99	0715	2.75 (0.078)
				3/04/99	0740	2.46 (0.070)
				3/22/99	0715	1.65 (0.047)
				4/19/99	1225	1.27 (0.036)
50055330	Río Bairoa at barrio Bairoa near Caguas, PR	Lat 18°15'44", long 66°04'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Bairoa, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) northwest of Las Carolinas, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) southwest of Cerro La Marquesa, and 1.9 mi (3.0 km) northeast of Aguas Buenas plaza.	3.03 (7.85)	2/03/98	1050	2.38 (0.067)
				3/19/98	0725	2.89 (0.082)
				5/11/98	1310	2.66 (0.075)
				6/30/98	1045	2.38 (0.067)
				8/05/98	0930	1.91 (0.054)
				9/18/98	1400	3.18 (0.090)
				2/17/99	1250	6.15 (0.174)
				3/08/99	1215	7.27 (0.206)
3/18/99	1215	6.09 (0.172)				
4/21/99	1245	4.60 (0.130)				

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATION
Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Grande de Loíza basin						
50057725	Río Cañas at barrio Jagüeyes near Aguas Buenas, PR	Lat 18°16'54", long 66°04'41", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Jagüeyes, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) east of Cerro La Marquesa, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northwest of Las Carolinas, and 2.3 mi, (3.7 km) northeast of Aguas Buenas plaza.	1.39 (3.60)	2/03/98	0725	0.30 (0.008)
				3/18/98	0900	0.54 (0.015)
				6/30/98	0655	0.37 (0.010)
				2/17/99	0815	1.98 (0.056)
				3/08/99	0835	1.69 (0.048)
				3/18/99	0810	1.61 (0.045)
				4/21/99	0815	1.25 (0.035)
50057750	Tributario de Río Cañas at barrio Río Cañas, PR	Lat 18°17'56", long 66°03'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Río Cañas, 3.3 mi (5.3 km) east of Cerro Marquesa, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) north of Las Carolinas, and 3.1 mi (5.0 km) northeast from Aguas Buenas plaza.	0.68 (1.76)	2/03/98	0815	0.24 (0.007)
				3/18/98	0950	0.24 (0.007)
				6/30/98	0730	0.21 (0.006)
				2/17/99	0900	0.86 (0.024)
				3/08/99	0910	0.90 (0.025)
				3/18/99	0850	0.76 (0.022)
				4/21/99	0855	0.54 (0.015)
50057800	Río Cañas at barrio Jagüeyes near Río Cañas, PR	Lat 18°17'09", long 66°04'21", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Jagüeyes, 2.7 mi (4.3 km) northeast of Cerro Marquesa, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northwest of Las Carolinas, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) northeast from Aguas Buenas plaza.	2.74 (7.10)	2/03/98	0850	0.86 (0.024)
				3/18/98	1025	1.06 (0.030)
				5/05/98	0925	0.94 (0.027)
				6/30/98	0825	0.77 (0.022)
				11/19/98	1155	9.15 (0.259)
				2/17/99	0730	3.72 (0.105)
				3/08/99	0735	2.90 (0.082)
3/18/99	0720	2.97 (0.084)				
5/21/99	0715	2.10 (0.059)				
50058010	Río Cañas at Highway 1 at barrio Río Cañas, PR	Lat 18°17'41", long 66°03'02", Hydrologic unit 21010005, at barrio Río Cañas at Highway 1, 2.7 mi (4.3 km) northeast of Las Carolinas, 4.2 mi (6.8 km) northeast of Cerro Marquesa, and 4.3 mi (6.9 km) northeast from Aguas Buenas plaza.	3.60 (9.32)	2/03/98	0940	1.14 (0.032)
				3/18/98	1115	1.64 (0.046)
				5/05/98	1045	1.11 (0.031)
				6/30/98	0910	1.04 (0.029)
				11/19/98	1425	11.6 (0.328)
				2/17/99	1000	5.24 (0.148)
				3/08/99	0940	4.79 (0.136)
3/18/99	0935	4.31 (0.122)				
4/21/99	0930	4.14 (0.117)				

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66°03'24"

66°52'30"

18°29'58"

18°15'02"

Figure 28. Location of low-flow partial-record stations in Carolina, Puerto Rico.

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Grande de Loíza basin						
50059210	Quebrada Grande at barrio Dos Bocas, PR	Lat 18°21'22", long 65°59'23", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Dos Bocas, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream of Río Grande de Loíza, 4.0 mi (6.4 km) northwest of Cerro Gordo, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northwest from Canto de Sapo.	12.9 (33.4)	2/26/98	0735	5.89 (0.167)
				3/17/98	1420	7.54 (0.214)
				6/29/98	1330	4.19 (0.119)
				8/06/98	1420	8.21 (0.232)
				2/22/99	1350	9.63 (0.273)
				3/09/99	1400	9.60 (0.272)
				3/23/99	1335	7.96 (0.225)
				4/22/99	1340	5.56 (0.157)
50060160	Quebrada Maracuta at barrio Santa Cruz, PR	Lat 18°21'07", long 65°57'00", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Santa Cruz, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Cerro Gordo, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northeast from Canto de Sapo, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northeast from Mariana.	6.31 (16.3)	2/25/98	1030	1.93 (0.055)
				3/17/98	0940	1.77 (0.050)
				6/29/98	0900	1.31 (0.037)
				8/06/98	1010	1.53 (0.046)
				2/22/99	0915	3.37 (0.095)
				3/09/99	0950	3.49 (0.099)
				3/23/99	0925	2.82 (0.080)
				4/22/99	0900	1.90 (0.054)
50060190	Quebrada Pastrana near Mariana at barrio Cacaos, PR	Lat 18°20'23", long 65°57'35", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Cacaos, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northwest of Cerro Gordo, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southeast of Canto de Sapo, and 5.7 mi (9.2 km) northeast from Gurabo plaza.	0.79 (2.05)	2/25/98	0940	0.50 (0.014)
				3/17/98	1025	0.34 (0.010)
				4/07/98	1340	0.35 (0.010)
				6/29/98	0735	0.37 (0.010)
				8/06/98	0940	0.52 (0.015)
				8/07/98	1020	0.56 (0.016)
				2/22/99	0835	0.69 (0.020)
				3/09/99	0910	0.72 (0.020)
3/23/99	0845	0.50 (0.014)				
4/22/98	0820	0.57 (0.016)				
50060195	Quebrada Pastrana near mouth at barrio Cacaos, PR	Lat 18°21'38", long 65°57'40", Hydrologic unit 21010005, at barrio Cacaos, 2.6 mi (4.2 km) northwest of Cerro Gordo, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northeast of Canto de Sapo, and 2.6 mi (4.2 km) southwest from Cambute.	2.04 (5.28)	2/25/98	0835	0.58 (0.016)
				3/17/98	0855	0.63 (0.018)
				4/07/98	1130	0.27 (0.008)
				6/29/98	0750	0.67 (0.019)
				8/05/98	1120	1.92 (0.054)
				8/06/98	0850	1.46 (0.041)
				2/22/99	0750	1.39 (0.039)
				3/09/99	0820	1.30 (0.037)
3/23/99	0805	0.96 (0.027)				
4/22/99	0730	0.86 (0.024)				

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Grande de Loíza basin						
50060200	Quebrada Maracuta at Trujillo Bajo, PR	Lat 18°22'11", long 65°57'28", Hydrologic unit 21010005, at bridge on Highway 853, and 0.3 mi (0.5 km) above Junction with Río Grande de Loíza.	10.2 (26.4)	2/25/98	0735	3.70 (0.105)
				3/17/98	0815	3.49 (0.099)
				6/29/98	0700	2.80 (0.079)
				8/06/98	0800	4.46 (0.126)
				2/22/99	0700	5.40 (0.153)
				3/09/99	0730	5.67 (0.160)
				3/23/99	0715	4.02 (0.114)
				4/97/99	0630	4.97 (0.141)
				50061200	Río Canovanillas at Carruzos, PR	Lat 18°19'03", long 65°54'16", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at bridge on road 500 ft (152 m) off of Highway 185, and 0.7 mi (1.1 km) east of Jesús T. Piñero school.
3/17/98	1310	3.13 (0.089)				
4/17/98	1335	7.46 (0.211)				
6/29/98	1210	1.89 (0.054)				
8/06/98	1310	2.26 (0.064)				
8/14/98	1145	2.45 (0.069)				
2/22/99	1240	6.56 (0.186)				
3/09/99	1255	6.33 (0.179)				
3/23/99	1225	6.32 (0.179)				
4/22/99	1235	3.34 (0.094)				
50061325	Río Canovanillas at barrio Canovanillas, PR	Lat 18°21'51", long 65°55'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at barrio Canovanillas, 3.6 mi (5.8 km) northwest of Cerro Pitahaya, 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northeast of Cerro Gordo, and 1.6 mi (2.8 km) southwest from Canóvanas plaza.	15.0 (38.8)	2/25/98	1120	5.18 (0.147)
				3/17/98	1105	5.53 (0.157)
				4/13/98	1240	15.7 (0.445)
				6/29/98	0950	3.00 (0.085)
				8/06/98	1110	3.29 (0.093)
				8/12/98	1245	4.88 (0.138)
				2/22/99	1010	9.69 (0.274)
				3/09/99	1045	8.57 (0.242)
				3/23/99	1020	7.27 (0.206)
4/22/99	0955	5.34 (0.151)				

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**Water-Quality at
Partial Record Stations
in Puerto Rico**

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATION

Water-quality partial-record stations are particular sites where chemical-quality, biological and or sediment data are collected systematically over a period of years for use in hydrological analysis. The data are collected usually less than quarterly.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	SAM- PLING DEPTH (FEET) (00003)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND- ARDS UNITS) (00400)	TRANS- PAR- ENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN) (00077)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION) (00300)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML) (31616)	
RIO DE GUAJATACA BASIN									
50010720	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS,PR (LAT 18° 22'05"N LONG 66° 54' 36"W)								
DEC 03...	0850	1.00	27.3	273	7.9	37.0	11.8	148	K13
MAR 18...	0900	1.00	26.3	312	8.0	51.0	10.5	132	K20
JUL 29...	0935	1.00	28.7	297	7.6	48.0	6.1	81	K4
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN									
50025110	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO,PR (LAT 18° 19'15"N LONG 66° 40' 11"W)								
DEC 08...	0830	1.00	26.4	238	7.6	37.0	6.7	83	K130
MAR 19...	1000	1.00	27.3	275	8.5	34.0	9.8	123	240
JUL 23...	0915	1.00	29.1	248	8.0	17.0	8.9	117	K120
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN									
50039900	LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY,PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 66° 06' 03"W)								
NOV 25...	0905	1.00	24.8	96	7.6	30.0	7.7	98	K26
MAR 24...	1035	1.00	24.2	121	8.5	42.0	9.0	112	44
JUL 16...	1015	1.00	28.6	114	7.3	40.0	7.53	103	K11
50044400	LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 66° 12' 28"W)								
NOV 20...	1020	1.00	27.4	265	7.6	36.0	9.0	113	K72
MAR 26...	1000	1.00	27.1	408	8.2	42.0	12.8	160	64
JUL 22...	1015	1.00	29.6	422	8.0	15.0	7.2	96	K130
RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN									
50047537	LAGO DE CIDRA NR RIO BAYAMON MOUTH (LAT 18° 11' 02"N LONG 66° 08' 6"W)								
DEC 01...	1015	1.00	25.9	211	7.3	31.0	6.5	83	K8
MAR 23...	1215	1.00	25.8	255	8.4	24.0	9.0	115	56
JUL 21...	0955	1.00	27.8	256	7.4	14.0	5.1	68	550
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN									
50057500	LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18° 16' 51"N LONG 66° 00' 35"W)								
NOV 21...	1130	1.00	28.0	293	7.2	6.00	5.3	68	490
MAR 25...	1030	1.00	27.4	264	6.8	4.00	4.6	57	500
JUL 24...	1035	1.00	29.9	304	7.1	10.0	5.5	73	84

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATION

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	STREP- TOCOCCT FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)	ANC	RESIDUE	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L) AS N) (00620)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L) AS N) (00615)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L) AS N) (00630)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L) AS N) (00610)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L) AS N) (00605)
		WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD CACO3 (00410)	AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L) (00530)					

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN-Continued

50010720 LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS,PR (LAT 18° 22' 05"N LONG 66° 54' 36"W)

DEC 03...	K8	120	<1	--	<.010	<.020	.080	.92
MAR 18...	90	130	1	--	<.010	.210	.060	.56
JUL 29...	K2	146	<1	--	<.010	<.020	.010	.56

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN-Continued

50025110 LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO,PR (LAT 18° 19' 15"N LONG 66° 40' 11"W)

DEC 08...	44	85	--	.533	.017	.550	.080	.36
MAR 19...	K29	90	6	.253	.027	.280	.070	.51
JUL 23...	30	85	9	.406	.020	.430	.030	.64

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN-Continued

50039900 LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY,PR (LAT 18° 05' 04"N LONG 66° 06' 03"W)

NOV 25...	210	31	<1	--	<.010	<.020	.030	.24
MAR 24...	K28	36	58	.010	.010	<.020	.040	.35
JUL 16...	K20	35	7	--	<.010	<.020	.020	--

50044400 LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18° 19' 33"N LONG 66° 12' 28"W)

NOV 20...	44	92	1	.706	.034	.740	.020	.44
MAR 26...	42	140	--	.020	.010	.030	.070	.68
JUL 22...	K10	131	15	.380	.020	.040	.010	.39

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN-Continued

50047537 LAGO DE CIDRA NR RIO BAYAMON MOUTH (LAT 18° 11' 02"N LONG 66° 08' 06"W)

DEC 01...	K15	77	<1	--	<.010	<.020	.020	.65
MAR 23...	K8	84	26	.420	.080	.500	1.20	.50
JUL 21...	690	79	28	.221	.05	.27	.68	.56

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN-Continued

50057500 LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18° 16' 51"N LONG 66° 00' 35"W)

NOV 21...	K120	88	40	--	<.010	1.80	.140	.83
MAR 25...	K170	69	54	.448	.042	.490	.080	
JUL 24...	K110	80	19	1.51	.09	1.6	.35	.75

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATION

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00625)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00600)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3) (71887)	PHOS- TOTAL (MG/L AS P) (00665)	CHLOR-A PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L) (70953)	CHLOR-B PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L) (70954)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS ASH WT (MG/L) (81353)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS DRY WT (MG/L) (81354)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN-Continued								
50010720	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS,PR (LAT 18° 22' 5"N LONG 66° 54' 36"W)							
DEC 03...	1.0	1.1	4.9	.050	11	.1	271	276
MAR 18...	.62	.83	3.7	.020	23	.5	274	284
JUL 29...	.57	.68	3.0	.04	8.5	2.1	536	549
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN-Continued								
50025110	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO,PR (LAT 18° 19' 15"N LONG 66° 40' 11"W)							
DEC 08...	.44	.99	4.4	.030	5.10	.4	260	260
MAR 19...	.58	.86	3.8	.040	8.4	.4	267	274
JUL 23...	.67	1.1	4.9	.11	28	2.8	372	386
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN-Continued								
50039900	LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY,PR (LAT 18° 05' 04"N LONG 66° 06' 03"W)							
NOV 25...	.27	--	--	<.020	3.9	.3	259	264
MAR 24...	--	--	--	--	6.9	.7	278	285
JUL 16...	<.20	--	--	.02	6.5	1.7	611	623
50044400	LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18° 19' 33"N LONG 66° 12' 28"W)							
NOV 20...	.46	1.2	5.3	.070	5.7	.7	265	272
MAR 26...	--	--	--	--	6.1	.4	240	251
JUL 22...	--	--	--	--	6.5	.1	393	403
RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN-Continued								
50047537	LAGO DE CIDRA NR RIO BAYAMON MOUTH (LAT 18° 11' 02"N LONG 66° 08' 06"W)							
DEC 01...	.67	--	--	.050	14	1.4	269	275
MAR 23...	--	--	--	--	14	2.1	272	282
JUL 21...	.66	.93	4.1	.03	8.3	.9	544	558
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN-Continued								
50057500	LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18° 16' 51"N LONG 66° 00' 35"W)							
NOV 21...	.97	2.8	12	.270	17	.9	298	308
MAR 25...	--	--	--	--	1.6	<.1	1420	1460
JUL 24...	1.1	2.7	12	.34	7.6	1.2	567	583

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATION

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	SAM- PLING DEPTH (FEET) (00003)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C) (00010)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM) (00095)	PH WATER FIELD (STAND- ARD UNITS) (00400)	TRANS- PAR- ENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN) (00077)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L) (00300)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION) (00301)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML) (31616)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML) (31679)
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RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN-Continued

50044950 LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18⁰ 20' 18"N LONG 66⁰ 14' 01"W)

NOV										
20...	0915	1.00	27.6	254	7.7	63.0	8.9	112	48	K33
20...	0930	48.0	24.3	185	7.0	--	--	--	--	--
MAR										
26...	0930	1.00	27.3	313	7.1	82.0	8.3	103	44	K15
26...	0935	72.0	23.8	209	6.6	--	--	--	--	--
JUL										
22...	1145	1.00	29.1	341	6.94	113	.2	2	K19	K21
22...	1200	48.0	24.3	249	6.9	--	--	--	--	--

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN-Continued

50047549 LAGO DE CIDRA NR DAM (LAT 18⁰ 11' 52"N LONG 66⁰ 08' 24"W)

DEC										
01...	0945	1.00	26.1	203	7.1	42.0	6.7	86	K14	K4
01...	0950	48.0	23.9	148	7.0	--	--	--	--	--
MAR										
23...	1135	1.00	25.8	242	8.5	32.0	9.2	117	K20	<2
23...	1145	52.0	23.0	174	7.2	--	--	--	--	--
JUL										
21...	0900	1.00	28.0	248	7.3	24.0	3.2	43	K180	100
21...	0910	42.0	23.7	229	7.0	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN-Continued

50058800 LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18⁰ 19' 29"N LONG 66⁰ 00' 47"W)

NOV										
21...	1100	1.00	28.8	254	7.1	9.00	5.4	70	K140	84
21...	1105	36.0	26.1	206	7.1	--	--	--	--	--
MAR										
25...	1000	1.00	27.1	235	6.6	4.00	4.0	50	K32	K150
25...	1005	56.0	25.3	316	6.4	--	--	--	--	--
JUL										
24...	1015	1.00	29.8	332	6.9	17.0	3.9	51	K110	84
24...	1020	35.0	26.8	179	6.8	--	--	--	--	--

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATION

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	HARD- NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS (00900)	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA) (00915)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG) (00925)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA) (00930)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO (00931)	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K) (00935)	ANC WATER UNFLTRD FET FIELD CACO3 (00410)	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4) (00945)	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL) (00940)
	RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN-Continued								
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18° 20' 18"N LONG 66° 14' 01"W)								
NOV									
20...	92	23	8.4	16	.7	2.7	87	13	20
20...	65	17	5.8	11	.6	2.8	56	11	15
MAR									
26...	65	16	6.1	11	.6	2.8	61	9.5	14
26...	78	18	7.0	18	.9	2.4	98	12	21
JUL									
22...	120	27	12	20	.8	2.8	116	12	23
22...	89	22	8.3	13	.6	2.7	123	9.3	15
RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN-Continued									
50047549	LAGO DE CIDRA NR DAM (LAT 18° 11' 52"N LONG 66° 08' 24"W)								
DEC									
01...	61	12	7.3	17	1	3.5	71	5.2	17
01...	74	20	5.8	10	.5	2.4	69	8.7	10
MAR									
23...	70	15	7.6	17	.9	3.0	80	7.1	18
23...	46	9.9	5.1	12	.8	3.5	90	7.5	11
JUL									
21...	75	16	8.6	19	1	2.3	78	7.3	18
21...	64	14	6.9	15	.8	3.2	78	7.1	13
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN-Continued									
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18° 19' 29"N LONG 66° 00'47"W)								
NOV									
21...	80	20	7.5	19	.9	3.4	80	14	21
21...	64	16	6.0	15	.8	3.3	64	11	17
MAR									
25...	61	15	6.7	15	.8	3.3	57	10	14
25...	59	15	5.4	15	.9	2.7	61	11	16
JUL									
24...	94	23	8.7	26	1	3.7	98	14	26
24...	58	15	5.3	14	.8	3.5	99	10	16

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATION

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F) (00950)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2) (00955)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L) (70301)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L) (00530)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00620)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00615)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00630)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00610)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N) (00605)
------	---	--	---	--	---	---	---	---	---

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN-Continued

50044950 LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18° 20'18"N LONG 66° 14' 01"W)

NOV									
20...	.1	18	153	<1	.160	.010	.170	<.010	--
20...	.2	15	112	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR									
26...	.2	23	119	<1	.120	.140	.260	.040	.56
26...	.1	14	151	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
22...	.1	20	188	<1	--	<.010	<.020	.020	--
22...	.1	16	139	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN-Continued

50047549 LAGO DE CIDRA NR DAM (LAT 18° 11' 52"N LONG 66° 08' 24"W)

DEC									
01...	<.1	17	122	1	--	<.010	<.020	.040	.52
01...	<.1	23	120	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR									
23...	<.1	16	133	52	.280	.020	.300	.020	.28
23...	<.1	11	114	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
21...	.1	21	139	9	.114	.030	.140	.480	--
21...	<.1	16	130	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN-Continued

50058800 LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18° 19 '29"N LONG 66° 00' 47"W)

NOV									
21...	.1	25	156	17	--	<.010	1.60	.060	.65
21...	.1	19	126	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR									
25...	.1	17	110	11	.460	<.010	.460	.180	.50
25...	<.1	18	120	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
24...	.1	29	189	7	.776	.080	.860	.140	.70
24...	<.1	19	116	--	--	--	--	--	--

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

PESTICIDE ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL RECORDS STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L) (39516)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L) (39330)	CHLOR- DANE, TECH- NICAL TOTAL (UG/L) (39350)	P,P'- DDD UNFILT RECOVER (UG/L) (39360)	P,P'- DDE, TOTAL RECOVER (UG/L) (39365)	P,P'- DDT UNFILT RECOVER (UG/L) (39370)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L) (39570)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L) (39380)	ENDO- SULFAN I TOTAL (UG/L) (39388)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN-Continued										
50010790		LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS,PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 23' 56"N LONG 66 ⁰ 55' 23"W)								
JUL 29...	1000	<.100	<.010	<.100	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN-Continued										
50020050		LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS,PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 08' 21"N LONG 66 ⁰ 44' 35"W)								
JUL 28...	1200	<.100	<.010	<.100	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010
50027090		LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO,PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 20' 09"N LONG 66 ⁰ 40' 04"W)								
JUL 23...	0945	<.100	<.010	<.100	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN-Continued										
50039950		LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18 ⁰ 04' 39"N LONG 66 ⁰ 06' 19"W)								
JUL 16...	1100	<.100	<.010	<.100	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010
50044950		LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 20' 18"N LONG 66 ⁰ 14' 01"W)								
JUL 22...	1145	<.100	<.010	<.100	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010
RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN-Continued										
50047549		LAGO DE CIDRA NR DAM (LAT 18 ⁰ 11' 52"N LONG 66 ⁰ 08' 24"W)								
JUL 21...	0900	<.100	<.010	<.100	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN-Continued										
50058800		LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 19' 29"N LONG 66 ⁰ 00' 47"W)								
JUL 24...	1015	<.100	<.010	<.100	<.010	<.010	<.010	.018	<.010	<.010

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

PESTICIDE ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL RECORDS STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L) (39390)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L) (39398)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L) (39410)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L) (39420)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L) (39340)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L) (39530)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L) (39480)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L) (39600)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L) (39790)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L) (39755)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN-Continued										
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS,PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 23' 56"N LONG 66 ⁰ 55' 23"W)									
JUL 29...	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	--	<.010
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN-Continued										
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS,PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 08' 21"N LONG 66 ⁰ 44' 35"W)									
JUL 28...	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	--	<.010
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO,PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 20' 09"N LONG 66 ⁰ 40' 04"W)									
JUL 23...	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	--	<.010
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN-Continued										
50039950	LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18 ⁰ 04' 39"N LONG 66 ⁰ 06' 19"W)									
JUL 16...	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	--	<.010
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 20' 18"N LONG 66 ⁰ 14' 01"W)									
JUL 22...	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	--	<.010
RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN-Continued										
50047549	LAGO DE CIDRA NR DAM (LAT 18 ⁰ 11' 52"N LONG 66 ⁰ 08' 24"W)									
JUL 21...	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	--	<.010
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN-Continued										
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 19' 29"N LONG 66 ⁰ 00' 47"W)									
JUL 24...	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	.008	<.010	<.010	--	<.010

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

PESTICIDE ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL RECORDS STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L) (39540)	PCNS UNFILT RECOVER (UG/L) (39250)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L) (39034)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L) (39400)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L) (39786)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L) (39730)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L) (39740)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L) (82183)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L) (39760)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN-Continued									
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS,PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 23' 56"N LONG 66 ⁰ 55' 23"W)								
JUL 29...	<.010	<.100	<.100	<1.00	<.010	.173	<.010	<.010	<.010
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN-Continued									
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS,PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 08' 21"N LONG 66 ⁰ 44' 35"W)								
JUL 28...	<.010	<.100	<.100	<1.00	<.010	.024	<.010	<.010	<.010
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO,PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 20' 09"N LONG 66 ⁰ 40' 04"W)								
JUL 23...	<.010	<.100	<.100	<1.00	<.010	.109	<.010	<.010	<.010
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN-Continued									
50039950	LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18 ⁰ 04' 39"N LONG 66 ⁰ 06' 19"W)								
JUL 16...	<.010	<.100	<.100	<1.00	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 20' 18"N LONG 66 ⁰ 14' 01"W)								
JUL 22...	<.010	<.100	<.100	<1.00	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010	<.010
RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN-Continued									
50047549	LAGO DE CIDRA NR DAM (LAT 18 ⁰ 11' 52"N LONG 66 ⁰ 08' 24"W)								
JUL 21...	<.010	<.100	<.100	<1.00	<.010	.010	<.010	<.010	<.010
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN-Continued									
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18 ⁰ 19' 29"N LONG 66 ⁰ 00' 47"W)								
JUL 24...	<.010	<.100	<.100	<1.00	<.010	.157	<.010	<.010	<.010

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**Ground-Water Records
for Puerto Rico**

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

182925067031100. Local number, OT-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°29'25", long 67°03'11", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.15 mi northwest of Hwy 472, 1.90 mi northwest of the intersection of Hwy 112 with Hwy 2, and 1.32 mi east of Hwy 466. Owner: Otilio Milán, Name: Otilio No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 0-10 ft (0-3.05 m), open hole 10-347 ft (3.05-105.8 m). Depth 347 ft (105.8 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Pressure transducer with integrated electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 295 ft (89.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of the 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.08 ft (0.94 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on May 16, 1997, removed on June 16, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 16, 1997 to September 30, 1998. From June 16, 1998 only tape down measurements.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 292.4 ft (89.1 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 18, 19, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 293.5 ft (89.5 m), below land-surface datum, May 12, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.72	292.92	292.89	292.68
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.74	292.93	292.90	292.65
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.75	292.93	292.91	292.62
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.72	292.94	292.91	292.62
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.72	292.96	292.92	292.60
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.72	292.96	292.91	292.57
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.74	292.96	292.89	292.55
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.76	292.96	292.90	292.54
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.78	292.96	292.91	292.54
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.79	292.95	292.93	292.55
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.80	292.95	292.95	292.55
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.82	292.94	292.97	292.59
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.80	292.93	292.97	292.60
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.79	292.94	292.99	292.61
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.81	292.92	292.99	292.63
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.81	292.91	292.99	292.63
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.88	292.82	292.88	293.00	292.63
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.91	292.83	292.88	293.01	292.63
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.92	292.85	292.86	293.01	292.64
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.84	292.86	292.86	293.00	292.65
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.85	292.89	292.86	293.01	292.67
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.85	292.88	292.86	292.95	292.68
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.72	292.92	292.88	292.90	292.68
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.72	292.90	292.89	292.90	292.69
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.72	292.91	292.89	292.90	292.71
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.72	292.91	292.90	292.88	292.72
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.71	292.91	292.88	292.84	292.74
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.73	292.91	292.88	292.81	292.74
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.73	292.92	292.87	292.77	292.76
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.71	292.94	292.86	292.74	292.75
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.74	---	292.90	292.70	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	292.78	292.82	292.91	292.91	292.64

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 292.82 HIGHEST 292.5 SEPT. 8, 1997 LOWEST 293.04 AUG. 18-21, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	292.74	292.66	292.83	293.08	293.09	292.99	293.28	293.50	293.26	---	---	---
2	292.74	292.67	292.85	293.09	292.97	292.99	293.31	293.51	293.25	---	---	---
3	292.75	292.67	292.87	293.09	292.97	293.00	293.32	293.49	293.22	---	---	---
4	292.75	292.68	292.88	293.06	292.94	293.01	293.35	293.48	293.20	---	---	---
5	292.72	292.69	292.90	293.06	292.93	293.03	293.34	293.49	293.19	---	---	---
6	292.73	292.70	292.90	293.02	292.94	293.05	293.34	293.49	293.21	---	---	---
7	292.75	292.72	292.90	293.03	292.98	293.04	293.32	293.48	293.19	---	---	---
8	292.77	292.71	292.90	293.03	292.96	293.07	293.33	293.48	293.19	---	---	---
9	292.77	292.70	292.91	293.04	292.98	293.06	293.37	293.49	293.17	---	---	---
10	292.76	292.71	292.92	293.04	293.01	293.06	293.37	293.48	293.17	---	---	---
11	292.75	292.70	292.93	293.03	293.03	293.08	293.38	293.50	293.18	---	---	---
12	292.73	292.73	292.94	293.05	293.05	293.09	293.36	293.51	293.18	---	---	---
13	292.69	292.75	292.95	293.06	293.05	293.10	293.35	293.51	293.18	---	---	---
14	292.61	292.76	292.95	293.08	293.05	293.11	293.36	293.49	293.13	---	---	---
15	292.57	292.77	292.97	293.10	293.05	293.13	293.41	293.48	293.05	---	---	---
16	292.50	292.79	292.98	293.11	293.05	293.14	293.44	293.48	---	---	---	---
17	292.49	292.76	292.99	293.10	293.06	293.18	293.44	293.49	---	---	---	---
18	292.47	292.75	293.00	293.11	293.06	293.20	293.42	293.48	---	---	---	---
19	292.48	292.75	293.01	293.10	293.04	293.22	293.43	293.49	---	---	---	---
20	292.48	292.76	293.01	293.10	293.07	293.21	293.43	293.46	---	---	---	---
21	292.48	292.77	293.04	293.10	293.08	293.22	293.44	293.45	---	---	---	---
22	292.48	292.78	293.03	293.11	293.09	293.22	293.43	293.42	---	---	---	---
23	292.50	292.78	293.03	293.09	293.10	293.21	293.42	293.38	---	---	---	---
24	292.52	292.78	293.05	293.08	293.09	293.22	293.43	293.37	---	---	---	---
25	292.55	292.82	293.05	293.09	293.10	293.23	293.42	293.34	---	---	---	---
26	292.56	292.84	293.04	293.09	293.13	293.23	293.41	293.33	---	---	---	---
27	292.59	292.82	293.05	293.09	292.99	293.26	293.43	293.32	---	---	---	---
28	292.61	292.82	293.06	293.10	292.97	293.26	293.45	293.32	---	---	---	---
29	292.62	292.82	293.06	293.10	---	293.26	293.47	293.31	---	---	---	---
30	292.63	292.84	293.07	293.09	---	293.25	293.49	293.30	---	---	---	---
31	292.66	---	293.07	293.10	---	293.26	---	293.30	---	---	---	---
MEAN	292.63	292.75	292.97	293.08	293.03	293.14	293.39	293.44	293.18	---	---	---
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 293.06	HIGHEST 292.45	OCT. 18, 19, 1997	LOWEST 293.55	MAY 12, 1998							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

182422067015100. Local number, 165.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'22", long 67°01'51", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 5.60 mi northeast of Moca plaza, 4.70 mi southeast of Aguadilla US Naval Reservation radio antenna, and 1.63 mi northwest of La Virgen del Rosario Church. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Saltos # 1 (Mateo Pérez).

AQUIFER.--Cibao Formation. Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.40 m), cased 16 in (0.40 m) 0-40.0 ft (0-12.2 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 40-200 ft (12.2-61.0 m). Depth 200 ft (61.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 689 ft (210 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on pump base, 0.50 ft (0.15 m), above land-surface datum. Prior to October 6, 1988, hole on top of pipe on top of pump base, 0.80 ft (0.24 m), above land-surface datum. Prior to November 1985, hole on top of pump base, 1.00 ft (0.30 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 18, 1998. Formerly published as 182421067015000.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1982 to March 1985, November 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 38.36 ft (11.7 m), below land-surface datum, July 12, 1993; lowest water level measured, 70.6 ft (21.5 m), below land-surface datum, June 18, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	39.78	39.66	39.31	39.92	39.61	39.65	40.35	40.36	41.10	40.47	40.32	40.31
2	39.70	39.58	39.32	39.81	39.58	39.57	40.26	40.29	40.98	40.37	40.17	40.05
3	39.55	39.50	39.32	39.71	39.41	39.49	40.14	40.21	40.84	40.28	40.74	40.04
4	39.48	39.44	39.82	39.62	39.24	39.45	40.01	40.71	40.72	40.67	40.62	40.00
5	39.48	39.97	39.71	40.01	39.23	39.44	40.39	40.60	40.65	40.57	40.50	39.87
6	39.43	39.78	39.61	39.85	39.23	39.35	40.22	40.48	40.59	40.48	40.38	39.75
7	39.38	39.66	39.50	39.75	39.81	39.83	40.23	40.38	41.15	40.88	40.28	39.64
8	39.30	39.54	39.47	39.72	39.71	39.70	40.82	40.28	40.98	40.70	40.23	40.18
9	39.30	39.46	39.39	39.65	39.61	39.64	40.60	40.27	40.89	40.62	40.08	40.01
10	39.25	39.41	39.33	39.60	39.59	39.58	40.40	40.40	40.76	40.52	40.57	39.91
11	39.70	39.41	39.88	39.48	40.15	40.04	40.29	40.96	40.66	40.40	40.42	39.73
12	39.47	39.37	39.79	39.43	40.07	39.90	40.16	40.77	40.56	40.83	40.36	39.63
13	39.34	39.88	39.62	39.40	39.93	39.86	40.24	40.68	40.99	40.64	40.24	39.57
14	39.24	39.74	39.54	39.93	39.82	39.94	40.89	40.55	40.78	40.53	40.08	39.54
15	39.12	39.69	39.42	39.78	39.74	39.74	40.64	40.45	40.69	40.44	40.02	39.52
16	39.17	39.58	39.94	39.71	39.72	39.64	40.50	40.92	40.65	40.37	40.31	39.45
17	39.81	39.49	39.82	39.66	39.58	40.25	40.40	40.78	41.22	40.29	40.18	39.96
18	39.73	39.44	39.76	39.53	39.51	40.06	40.30	40.69	40.96	40.68	39.99	39.74
19	39.65	39.40	39.73	39.42	39.51	39.94	40.17	41.22	40.84	40.56	39.83	39.64
20	39.55	39.33	39.63	39.38	40.06	39.81	40.11	41.02	40.71	40.43	40.39	39.98
21	39.46	39.22	39.46	39.94	39.83	39.64	40.07	40.87	40.65	40.36	40.08	39.66
22	39.37	39.22	39.46	39.83	39.79	40.23	40.00	40.73	40.63	40.24	40.02	39.51
23	39.33	39.46	40.00	39.75	39.67	40.07	39.93	40.67	40.56	40.11	39.94	39.50
24	39.30	39.37	39.87	39.70	39.58	40.01	39.92	40.62	40.50	40.04	39.81	39.51
25	39.22	39.30	39.76	39.62	39.50	39.99	40.52	40.68	40.42	40.64	39.80	39.43
26	39.83	39.22	39.70	39.59	39.42	39.90	40.36	41.20	40.40	40.44	40.36	39.35
27	40.33	39.78	39.59	39.47	39.37	40.35	40.23	41.07	40.85	40.29	40.21	39.26
28	40.15	39.70	39.46	39.42	39.88	40.12	40.14	40.94	40.70	40.23	40.02	39.19
29	39.96	39.53	40.14	39.91	---	39.99	40.69	40.78	40.63	40.68	39.98	39.18
30	39.85	39.40	40.04	39.78	---	39.87	40.53	40.70	40.54	40.56	39.90	39.20
31	39.73	---	39.99	39.61	---	39.79	---	40.63	---	40.43	39.85	---
MEAN	39.55	39.52	39.66	39.68	39.65	39.83	40.32	40.67	40.75	40.48	40.18	39.68

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 40.00 HIGHEST 38.93 SEPT. 21, 22, 1998 LOWEST 41.27 MAY 19, JUNE 17, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

182647066552400. Local number, 202.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'47", long 66°55'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 2.22 mi southeast of Quebradillas plaza, 1.29 mi north of Escuela José de Diego, and 1.99 mi northwest of El Calvario Church. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Carmelo Barreto García well.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-296 ft (0-90.2 m), diameter 13 in (0.33 m), cased 13 in (0.33 m) 0-550 ft (0-168 m), perforated 270-529 ft (82.3-161 m). Depth 550 ft (168 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 475 ft (145 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.50 ft (0.46 m), above land-surface datum. Prior July 25, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.30 ft (1.00 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 18, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 409.2 ft (125 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 25, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 453.9 ft (138 m), below land-surface datum, May 14, 15, 16, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	434.72	435.20	436.83	438.57	440.69	442.46	444.16	445.78	445.90	443.29	442.61	442.44
2	434.75	435.23	436.89	438.63	440.74	442.53	444.22	445.85	445.85	443.21	442.61	442.35
3	434.83	435.29	436.91	438.69	440.76	442.59	444.25	445.89	445.77	443.17	442.61	442.32
4	434.90	435.34	436.90	438.75	440.81	442.66	444.29	445.94	445.67	443.14	442.66	442.25
5	434.92	435.39	436.93	438.83	440.94	442.76	444.33	446.01	445.60	443.12	442.69	442.10
6	434.99	435.43	436.96	438.91	441.02	442.80	444.38	446.08	445.54	443.08	442.71	442.00
7	435.01	435.49	437.02	438.96	441.09	442.88	444.49	446.12	445.47	443.04	442.74	441.89
8	435.05	435.53	437.07	439.04	441.14	442.96	444.55	446.17	445.42	443.03	442.79	441.77
9	435.06	435.59	437.10	439.11	441.23	442.98	444.58	446.23	445.39	443.04	442.84	441.66
10	435.07	435.70	437.14	439.19	441.31	443.01	444.61	446.27	445.31	443.03	442.83	441.46
11	435.08	435.74	437.19	439.24	441.36	443.03	444.70	446.33	445.27	442.99	442.88	441.20
12	435.08	435.40	437.24	439.33	441.43	443.09	444.77	446.41	445.21	443.00	442.94	440.99
13	435.08	435.87	437.28	439.42	441.47	443.13	444.87	446.46	445.17	443.00	442.93	440.85
14	435.07	435.91	437.32	439.46	441.55	443.17	444.91	446.51	445.16	443.02	442.92	440.71
15	435.10	435.98	437.40	439.51	441.61	443.18	444.94	446.57	445.07	443.02	442.92	440.58
16	435.19	436.06	437.45	439.61	441.67	443.23	445.03	446.63	444.97	443.00	442.92	440.44
17	435.17	436.10	437.54	439.67	441.72	443.29	445.10	446.70	444.79	442.96	442.87	440.24
18	435.14	436.16	437.60	439.74	441.79	443.33	445.14	446.74	444.59	442.92	442.80	439.97
19	435.11	436.19	437.68	439.80	441.85	443.38	445.19	446.79	444.44	442.89	442.77	439.76
20	435.04	436.23	437.73	439.87	441.90	443.41	445.25	446.81	444.28	442.82	442.77	439.59
21	435.00	436.31	437.78	439.95	441.97	443.46	445.32	446.81	444.15	442.80	442.69	439.40
22	434.98	436.36	437.86	440.01	442.04	443.54	445.35	446.78	444.04	442.74	442.70	439.41
23	434.97	436.41	437.93	440.10	442.09	443.61	445.39	446.75	443.92	442.71	442.68	439.10
24	434.94	436.47	438.00	440.14	442.14	443.69	445.46	446.70	443.83	442.68	442.63	438.40
25	434.94	436.54	438.08	440.21	442.21	443.76	445.51	446.61	443.72	442.67	442.72	437.38
26	434.96	436.61	438.14	440.27	442.29	443.79	445.57	446.54	443.62	442.63	442.69	436.57
27	434.97	436.70	438.18	440.34	442.34	443.86	445.60	446.46	443.54	442.61	442.65	436.06
28	435.01	436.77	438.24	440.41	442.40	443.92	445.64	446.36	443.48	442.63	442.61	435.70
29	435.07	436.79	438.33	440.47	---	443.97	445.70	446.24	443.42	442.60	442.64	435.44
30	435.08	436.79	438.43	440.52	---	444.02	445.75	446.14	443.35	442.60	442.57	435.15
31	435.14	---	438.51	440.59	---	444.11	---	446.02	---	442.60	442.52	---
MEAN	435.01	435.99	437.54	439.59	441.56	443.28	444.97	446.38	444.73	442.90	442.74	439.91

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 441.21 HIGHEST 434.65 OCT. 1, 1997 LOWEST 446.85 MAY 20, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CAMUY BASIN

182723066511200. Local number, Z-4.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'23", long 66°51'12", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.60 mi south of the intersection of Hwy 119 with Hwy 2, 1.35 mi east of Hwy 119 of, and 0.01 mi east of Hwy 486. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority,

Name: Zanja 4.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m). Depth 585 ft (178 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Pressure transducer with integrated electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 360 ft (110 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of the 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Eletronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 25, 1997. Record is poor when the water level is below the level of the pressure transducer which is set at 331 ft (101 m), below land-surface datum.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 25, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 161.8 ft (49.3 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 22, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 331.2 ft (101 m), below land-surface datum, Mar. 11, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	310.79	323.19	329.10	324.09	329.12	329.15	329.17
2	---	---	---	---	---	311.40	323.54	329.12	324.33	329.12	329.15	329.17
3	---	---	---	---	---	311.96	323.85	329.07	326.65	329.12	329.15	329.17
4	---	---	---	---	---	312.56	324.14	329.06	328.29	329.12	329.15	329.17
5	---	---	---	---	---	313.12	324.29	329.07	329.10	329.12	329.15	329.17
6	---	---	---	---	---	313.54	324.51	329.07	329.10	329.12	329.15	329.18
7	---	---	---	---	---	314.13	324.80	329.08	329.10	329.12	329.15	329.18
8	---	---	---	---	---	314.80	325.06	323.38	329.10	329.12	329.16	329.18
9	---	---	---	---	---	315.25	325.36	324.53	329.10	329.12	329.16	329.18
10	---	---	---	---	---	315.61	325.67	325.07	329.10	329.12	329.16	329.18
11	---	---	---	---	---	315.98	325.96	325.32	329.10	329.14	329.16	329.18
12	---	---	---	---	---	316.45	326.23	327.19	329.11	329.13	329.15	329.18
13	---	---	---	---	---	317.02	326.40	328.74	329.11	329.13	329.16	329.18
14	---	---	---	---	---	317.49	326.60	329.08	329.11	329.13	329.16	329.18
15	---	---	---	---	---	317.91	326.81	329.08	329.11	329.13	329.16	329.18
16	---	---	---	---	---	318.30	326.93	329.08	329.11	329.13	329.15	329.18
17	---	---	---	---	---	318.71	327.04	329.08	329.10	329.13	329.16	329.18
18	---	---	---	---	---	319.15	327.11	329.09	329.11	329.13	324.30	329.18
19	---	---	---	---	---	319.52	327.32	329.08	329.11	329.13	329.16	329.18
20	---	---	---	---	---	319.22	327.60	329.08	329.11	329.14	321.29	329.18
21	---	---	---	---	---	318.91	327.87	329.08	329.12	329.14	327.02	329.18
22	---	---	---	---	---	319.74	327.03	329.08	329.12	329.14	309.51	329.18
23	---	---	---	---	---	320.39	327.09	329.08	329.11	329.14	318.41	329.18
24	---	---	---	---	---	320.93	327.65	329.09	329.11	329.14	324.83	329.18
25	---	---	---	---	---	307.11	321.41	328.12	329.09	329.11	329.14	329.18
26	---	---	---	---	---	307.81	321.83	328.50	329.09	329.12	329.14	329.18
27	---	---	---	---	---	309.00	322.11	328.74	328.28	329.12	324.66	329.18
28	---	---	---	---	---	309.98	322.36	328.94	283.86	329.11	329.14	329.18
29	---	---	---	---	---	322.51	329.00	300.94	329.12	329.14	322.89	329.18
30	---	---	---	---	---	322.67	329.07	314.41	329.11	329.15	326.94	329.18
31	---	---	---	---	---	322.92	---	319.78	---	329.15	329.17	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	308.48	317.70	326.48	325.26	328.67	328.99	329.18

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 325.87 HUGHEST 280.21 MAY 28, 1997 LOWEST 329.31 AUG. 25, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CAMUY BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	329.18	329.17	316.73	329.43	330.20	330.89	331.01	330.49	295.49	311.10	323.20	246.03
2	329.18	329.17	322.86	329.46	330.23	330.92	330.86	330.48	288.68	313.36	323.94	271.72
3	304.16	329.17	327.38	329.48	330.25	330.94	330.85	330.47	295.87	314.88	324.70	250.30
4	315.80	329.17	329.26	329.51	330.28	330.97	330.83	330.46	299.54	315.66	325.57	257.91
5	323.70	329.17	329.26	329.53	330.30	330.99	330.82	330.44	304.21	316.37	326.39	270.89
6	301.34	329.17	329.26	329.56	330.42	297.79	330.81	330.43	308.70	318.13	327.12	280.40
7	313.20	329.17	329.25	329.58	330.35	318.15	330.80	330.42	304.28	319.40	327.29	262.91
8	306.01	329.17	329.17	329.61	330.38	300.45	330.79	330.41	306.00	320.14	327.22	269.87
9	315.32	329.17	329.17	329.63	330.40	318.46	330.77	330.39	310.02	321.02	327.15	278.39
10	321.37	329.17	329.16	329.66	330.43	327.41	330.76	330.38	312.72	321.85	304.53	259.25
11	326.50	329.17	329.17	329.68	330.45	331.14	330.75	330.37	315.07	323.00	315.30	272.47
12	329.17	329.17	329.17	329.71	330.48	331.13	330.74	330.36	246.70	322.49	280.84	280.19
13	297.76	329.17	329.16	329.73	330.50	331.11	330.72	330.35	241.90	305.71	242.11	284.48
14	275.36	329.17	329.16	329.75	330.53	331.10	330.71	330.33	227.53	311.21	276.31	255.92
15	285.25	329.17	329.16	329.77	330.55	331.09	330.70	330.32	237.77	316.11	291.87	274.57
16	265.40	329.17	329.16	329.81	330.58	331.08	330.69	324.61	261.57	309.12	299.51	278.48
17	286.14	329.17	329.16	329.82	330.60	331.07	330.45	321.12	273.20	281.93	297.86	281.02
18	299.20	329.17	329.08	329.85	330.63	331.04	330.66	243.14	279.41	297.28	305.32	286.44
19	310.14	329.17	329.11	329.87	330.65	331.04	330.65	248.30	280.08	306.51	309.46	269.29
20	317.02	329.17	329.13	329.90	330.68	331.02	296.67	250.77	288.21	312.21	311.83	280.35
21	321.10	329.17	329.16	329.92	330.70	331.01	314.42	232.17	294.33	314.41	313.35	286.63
22	324.50	329.17	329.18	329.95	330.73	330.99	324.76	262.12	298.65	316.46	296.31	162.04
23	326.89	329.17	329.21	329.97	330.75	330.98	330.69	284.22	301.07	318.14	306.60	190.66
24	328.67	329.17	329.23	330.00	330.78	330.98	330.68	252.10	305.81	316.26	311.53	220.76
25	329.27	329.17	329.26	330.02	330.79	330.97	330.58	279.04	308.88	309.03	277.28	230.14
26	329.27	329.17	329.28	330.05	330.82	330.95	330.55	291.21	309.24	315.14	290.01	243.13
27	329.18	287.98	329.31	330.07	330.84	330.93	330.54	234.99	311.18	317.86	278.31	256.79
28	329.17	266.06	329.33	330.10	330.87	330.92	330.53	262.12	286.29	317.36	290.01	263.65
29	329.18	293.14	329.36	330.13	---	330.91	330.52	278.26	299.02	319.19	237.67	264.95
30	329.17	309.26	329.38	330.15	---	321.31	330.50	283.61	306.83	320.90	268.60	268.40
31	329.17	---	329.41	330.18	---	329.92	---	289.96	---	322.21	282.34	---
MEAN	314.73	323.83	328.55	329.80	330.54	327.67	328.83	299.80	289.94	314.34	300.63	259.93

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 312.36 HIGHEST 161.80 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 331.22 MAR. 11, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CAMUY BASIN

182431066463400. Local number, CA-4.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'31", long 66°46'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.02 mi west of the intersection of Hwy 129 with Hwy 130, 1.68 mi southeast of the intersection of Hwy 130 with Hwy 490, and 3.00 mi east of Río Camuy. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Campo Alegre 4.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m). Depth 220 ft (67.1 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 606.8 ft (185 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of the 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.25 ft (0.99 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on Sept. 27, 1996, replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on Jan. 14, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 27, 1996 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 183.9 ft (56.1 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 3, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 212.6 ft (64.8 m), below land-surface datum, May 28, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	184.12	186.38	187.06	191.42	186.32	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	184.09	186.65	187.06	191.25	186.09	---	190.26	---	---	---	---	---
3	183.98	186.85	187.03	191.08	185.81	---	190.31	---	---	---	---	---
4	184.04	186.53	187.45	190.89	185.61	---	190.47	---	---	---	---	---
5	184.12	186.67	187.22	190.71	185.46	---	190.61	---	---	---	---	---
6	184.17	186.77	187.37	190.51	185.30	---	190.70	---	---	---	---	---
7	184.18	186.78	186.75	190.45	185.17	---	190.77	---	---	---	---	---
8	184.29	186.80	186.80	190.07	185.17	---	190.74	---	---	---	---	---
9	184.31	186.69	186.89	189.93	185.20	---	190.67	---	---	---	---	---
10	184.41	186.55	187.13	189.79	185.27	187.83	190.65	---	---	---	---	---
11	184.42	186.62	187.14	189.68	185.33	187.83	190.79	---	---	---	---	---
12	184.45	186.77	187.17	189.61	185.45	187.84	191.00	---	---	---	---	---
13	184.50	186.90	187.13	189.66	185.68	188.05	191.04	---	---	---	---	---
14	184.50	186.92	187.01	189.58	185.70	187.93	191.18	---	---	---	---	---
15	184.64	186.86	187.04	189.51	185.72	188.10	191.20	---	---	---	---	---
16	184.87	186.90	187.14	189.46	185.75	188.34	191.20	---	---	---	---	---
17	185.02	187.02	187.16	189.41	185.77	188.55	191.15	---	---	---	---	---
18	185.13	187.07	187.43	189.40	185.79	188.75	191.00	---	---	---	---	---
19	185.13	186.78	187.75	189.43	185.81	188.84	190.98	---	---	---	---	---
20	185.17	186.91	188.09	189.60	185.84	188.97	191.13	---	---	---	---	---
21	185.39	186.96	188.42	189.66	185.86	189.00	191.25	---	---	---	---	---
22	185.59	186.98	188.76	189.88	186.00	189.02	191.43	---	---	---	---	---
23	185.63	186.78	189.13	189.78	186.06	---	191.51	---	---	---	---	---
24	185.70	186.87	189.46	189.69	186.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	185.87	187.04	189.81	189.45	186.48	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	186.05	187.08	190.21	188.86	186.63	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	186.22	187.05	190.60	188.70	186.78	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.34
28	186.23	187.03	190.84	188.28	186.96	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.32
29	186.22	187.03	191.15	187.82	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.28
30	186.30	187.03	191.45	187.52	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.26
31	186.38	---	191.51	186.67	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	185.00	186.84	188.23	189.60	185.82	188.39	190.91	---	---	---	---	201.30

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 187.95 HIGHEST 183.96 OCT. 3, 1996 LOWEST 201.38 SEPT. 26, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CAMUY BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	201.20	197.86	196.55	198.33	199.90	202.80	206.32	210.19	211.02	197.01	194.35	192.72
2	201.13	197.74	196.58	198.48	199.99	202.87	206.49	210.28	210.39	196.86	194.26	192.57
3	201.08	197.69	196.73	198.54	200.02	202.93	206.65	210.39	209.80	196.63	194.16	192.53
4	201.26	197.48	196.89	198.55	199.94	202.98	206.81	210.48	209.23	196.37	194.10	192.51
5	200.71	197.30	196.95	198.51	199.85	203.07	206.98	210.57	208.64	196.18	194.10	192.48
6	200.79	197.14	196.94	198.49	199.99	203.19	207.12	210.65	208.10	196.06	194.10	192.46
7	200.89	196.89	197.00	198.46	200.11	203.17	207.26	210.74	207.65	195.94	194.10	192.44
8	200.95	196.65	197.07	198.51	200.33	203.20	207.42	210.81	207.23	195.83	194.10	192.42
9	201.02	196.49	197.17	198.60	200.61	203.34	207.57	210.90	206.78	195.76	194.07	192.39
10	201.07	196.40	197.24	198.70	200.75	203.44	207.70	210.99	206.31	195.70	194.05	192.37
11	201.10	196.42	197.19	198.73	200.94	203.49	207.84	211.07	205.82	195.62	193.96	192.35
12	201.07	196.42	197.31	198.78	201.14	203.60	207.98	211.16	205.29	195.53	193.98	192.33
13	200.99	196.42	197.34	198.88	201.35	203.78	208.11	211.23	204.74	195.44	194.02	192.30
14	200.77	196.42	197.36	198.99	201.47	203.94	208.26	211.31	204.12	195.37	194.02	192.28
15	200.42	196.49	197.37	199.05	201.60	204.09	208.40	211.40	203.57	195.31	193.90	192.26
16	200.30	196.56	197.37	199.14	201.74	204.20	208.52	211.46	203.09	195.29	193.87	192.23
17	200.35	196.55	197.40	199.27	201.84	204.32	208.66	211.54	202.66	195.25	193.90	192.21
18	200.33	196.55	197.46	199.38	201.93	204.28	208.78	211.61	202.16	195.22	193.84	192.19
19	200.24	196.56	197.61	199.43	202.05	204.38	208.91	211.69	201.62	195.15	193.62	192.17
20	200.08	196.53	197.75	199.51	202.17	204.53	209.03	211.76	201.05	195.10	193.44	192.14
21	199.85	196.53	197.78	199.58	202.28	204.68	209.15	211.72	200.52	195.06	193.26	192.12
22	199.66	196.55	197.84	199.70	202.40	204.79	209.26	211.85	200.09	195.04	193.05	190.60
23	199.54	196.61	197.92	199.55	202.49	204.91	209.38	211.99	199.66	195.04	193.05	190.58
24	199.39	196.71	197.94	199.76	202.50	205.10	209.48	212.13	199.26	194.71	192.90	190.55
25	199.21	196.71	198.00	199.96	202.53	205.28	209.59	212.25	198.86	194.70	192.81	190.53
26	199.04	196.67	198.08	200.02	202.62	205.47	209.68	212.38	198.45	194.70	192.85	190.51
27	198.88	196.62	198.09	200.03	202.67	205.63	209.78	212.50	198.03	194.59	192.84	190.49
28	198.74	196.67	198.03	200.03	202.74	205.78	209.89	212.62	197.69	194.46	192.81	190.46
29	198.59	196.73	197.99	199.99	---	205.92	210.00	212.53	197.41	194.40	192.73	190.44
30	198.34	196.65	198.01	199.94	---	206.05	210.08	212.16	197.19	194.38	192.73	190.42
31	198.07	---	198.16	199.88	---	206.17	---	211.63	---	194.38	192.75	---
MEAN	200.16	196.77	197.46	199.19	201.36	204.24	208.37	211.42	203.55	195.39	193.60	191.80
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 200.27	HIGHEST 190.41	SEPT. 30, 1998	LOWEST 212.64	MAY 28, 1998							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

182756066454700. Local number, BARR-1
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'56", long 66°45'47", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.04 mi north of Hwy 653, 1.86 mi west of Hwy 129, and 1.55 mi west of the University of Puerto Rico, Arecibo Campus. Owner: Vaqueria Barreto, Name: Barreto #01.
 AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 300 ft (91.4 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 164 ft (50.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of white PVC cap 3.37 ft (1.03 m), above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on October 24, 1997. Water levels affected by marine tides.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 24, 1997 to September 30, 1998.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 159.6 ft (48.7 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 24-28, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 161.4 ft (49.2 m), below land-surface datum, Jan. 6, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	161.02	161.30	161.23	161.34	161.27	161.04	160.93	160.96	160.95	160.79	160.31
2	---	161.03	161.30	161.22	161.33	161.25	161.00	160.93	160.96	160.96	160.81	160.30
3	---	161.02	161.27	161.26	161.31	161.22	160.98	160.96	160.97	160.98	160.81	160.26
4	---	161.02	161.24	161.27	161.33	161.23	160.96	160.97	160.97	160.97	160.81	160.24
5	---	161.02	161.21	161.32	161.37	161.20	160.98	160.97	160.97	160.96	160.81	160.24
6	---	161.04	161.27	161.36	161.35	161.22	160.98	160.96	161.00	160.96	160.82	160.23
7	---	161.04	161.29	161.37	161.37	161.21	161.00	160.96	160.95	160.97	160.83	160.20
8	---	161.10	161.30	161.36	161.37	161.18	161.00	160.96	160.93	160.99	160.81	160.15
9	---	161.13	161.29	161.35	161.36	161.20	160.96	160.97	160.97	160.99	160.78	160.08
10	---	161.16	161.31	161.38	161.36	161.18	160.94	160.95	160.97	160.97	160.77	160.05
11	---	161.18	161.32	161.36	161.33	161.16	160.97	160.94	160.98	160.96	160.75	160.03
12	---	161.20	161.31	161.36	161.30	161.17	161.02	160.96	160.98	160.93	160.72	160.03
13	---	161.19	161.32	161.34	161.30	161.15	161.04	160.95	160.91	160.92	160.70	160.06
14	---	161.19	161.33	161.32	161.30	161.15	160.98	160.97	160.87	160.91	160.71	160.02
15	---	161.17	161.35	161.30	161.30	161.10	160.96	160.99	160.85	160.89	160.74	160.01
16	---	161.18	161.35	161.31	161.30	161.10	160.93	161.01	160.87	160.87	160.72	159.99
17	---	161.17	161.33	161.31	161.28	161.05	161.01	161.02	160.87	160.86	160.66	159.99
18	---	161.16	161.35	161.30	161.27	161.02	161.01	161.01	160.84	160.84	160.63	159.97
19	---	161.17	161.24	161.29	161.27	161.03	160.98	161.04	160.84	160.84	160.59	159.92
20	---	161.17	161.24	161.31	161.26	161.01	161.04	161.09	160.83	160.82	160.57	159.90
21	---	161.18	161.21	161.32	161.22	161.02	161.07	161.18	160.85	160.84	160.51	159.85
22	---	161.18	161.26	161.32	161.19	161.03	161.07	161.12	160.89	160.83	160.41	159.81
23	---	161.17	161.25	161.33	161.20	161.05	161.06	161.07	160.87	160.83	160.37	159.67
24	---	161.20	161.25	161.34	161.23	161.04	161.08	161.08	160.90	160.82	160.33	159.64
25	160.99	161.21	161.24	161.35	161.21	161.04	161.07	161.06	160.91	160.75	160.35	159.64
26	161.01	161.21	161.23	161.34	161.22	161.03	161.06	161.05	160.93	160.78	160.29	159.66
27	161.01	161.24	161.24	161.34	161.25	160.98	161.04	161.01	160.93	160.79	160.32	159.66
28	161.01	161.26	161.24	161.35	161.28	160.98	161.02	160.95	160.92	160.79	160.37	159.65
29	161.01	161.25	161.25	161.33	---	161.00	160.97	160.95	160.94	160.77	160.33	159.68
30	161.01	161.28	161.26	161.33	---	161.08	160.96	160.98	160.92	160.79	160.33	159.72
31	161.03	---	161.22	161.35	---	161.05	---	160.96	---	160.80	160.34	---
MEAN	161.01	161.15	161.28	161.32	161.29	161.11	161.01	161.00	160.92	160.88	160.61	159.97

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 160.96 HIGHEST 159.61 SEPT. 24-28, 1998 LOWEST 161.40 JAN. 6, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

182737066370900. Local number, 204.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'37", long 66°37'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 5.26 mi west of Barceloneta plaza, 1.58 mi north of Hwy 2 km 63.7, and 3.67 mi southwest of Escuela Agustín Balseiro. Owner: Sucesión Marquez, Name: Gilberto Rivera well.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Abandoned unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 48.0 ft (14.63 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Air hole on pump base, 0.50 ft (0.15 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 7, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 50.0 ft (15.2 m), below land-surface datum, May 14, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 53.1 ft (16.2 m), below land-surface datum, Jan. 29, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	51.93	52.12	52.09	52.18	51.99	52.04	52.29	52.31	51.82	51.89	51.98	51.93
2	51.90	52.10	52.09	52.18	52.01	52.07	52.31	52.27	51.79	51.90	52.00	51.91
3	51.92	52.11	52.15	52.19	52.04	52.11	52.32	52.25	51.79	51.91	52.02	51.85
4	51.90	52.15	52.23	52.15	52.01	52.11	52.38	52.22	51.80	51.91	52.04	51.88
5	51.92	52.16	52.26	52.07	51.94	52.12	52.36	52.21	51.83	51.89	52.06	51.85
6	51.95	52.18	52.21	52.04	51.93	52.09	52.30	52.21	51.84	51.91	52.10	51.84
7	52.02	52.22	52.16	52.04	51.94	52.10	52.27	52.19	51.84	51.91	52.06	51.83
8	52.03	52.14	52.14	52.03	51.94	52.11	52.28	52.20	51.87	51.94	52.01	51.80
9	52.02	52.10	52.15	52.02	51.93	52.14	52.31	52.16	51.88	51.94	52.00	51.74
10	52.02	52.07	52.14	52.01	51.94	52.14	52.34	52.20	51.89	51.89	52.03	51.74
11	52.01	52.07	52.13	51.99	51.98	52.12	52.29	52.22	51.88	51.87	52.03	51.74
12	51.96	52.07	52.15	52.00	52.03	52.12	52.24	52.22	51.89	51.84	52.04	51.81
13	51.89	52.08	52.13	52.01	52.04	52.14	52.20	52.20	51.81	51.81	52.08	51.82
14	51.81	52.08	52.16	52.05	52.03	52.18	52.27	52.18	51.69	51.81	52.12	51.82
15	51.75	52.09	52.13	52.06	52.02	52.20	52.32	52.13	51.63	51.83	52.14	51.84
16	51.71	52.12	52.13	52.05	52.04	52.22	52.32	52.12	51.62	51.84	52.14	51.91
17	51.80	52.12	52.12	52.05	52.06	52.25	52.28	52.10	51.66	51.86	52.12	51.92
18	51.90	52.17	52.13	52.04	52.04	52.28	52.26	52.06	51.72	51.88	52.11	51.89
19	51.97	52.17	52.19	52.03	52.05	52.29	52.27	52.02	51.76	51.89	52.04	51.84
20	52.01	52.17	52.22	52.01	52.07	52.30	52.21	51.99	51.79	51.89	51.98	51.80
21	52.05	52.17	52.21	52.00	52.10	52.28	52.17	51.91	51.81	51.89	51.89	51.78
22	52.09	52.17	52.18	52.00	52.10	52.26	52.16	51.91	51.84	51.90	51.84	51.70
23	52.10	52.17	52.17	51.98	52.10	52.24	52.14	51.88	51.83	51.85	51.81	51.47
24	52.15	52.14	52.18	52.00	52.07	52.26	52.14	51.87	51.84	51.84	51.76	51.39
25	52.17	52.13	52.18	51.98	52.06	52.25	52.12	51.85	51.85	51.86	51.79	51.39
26	52.16	52.12	52.17	52.01	52.05	52.28	52.12	51.82	51.89	51.90	51.71	51.40
27	52.15	52.12	52.16	51.98	52.04	52.31	52.17	51.82	51.89	51.92	51.81	51.43
28	52.15	52.09	52.16	51.98	52.04	52.33	52.22	51.80	51.89	51.93	51.83	51.47
29	52.15	52.09	52.09	51.98	---	52.33	52.26	51.81	51.89	51.94	51.85	51.52
30	52.14	52.10	52.12	51.99	---	52.27	52.28	51.81	51.88	51.97	51.88	51.58
31	52.13	---	52.15	51.99	---	52.26	---	51.83	---	51.96	51.91	---
MEAN	52.00	52.13	52.16	52.04	52.02	52.20	52.25	52.06	51.81	51.89	51.97	51.73
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 52.02	HIGHEST 51.38	SEPT. 24, 25, 1998	LOWEST 52.42	APR. 3, 4, 1998							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

182616066364100. Local number, EN-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'16", long 66°36'41", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 3.00 west of the intersection of Hwy 140 with Hwy 2 (Cruce Davila), 0.32 mi southwest of Hwy 22, 0.15 mi north of Hwy 2, and 0.22 mi northeast of the intersection of Hwy 2 with Hwy 639. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: PRASA Encantada 1.

AQUIFER.--Tertiary Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 312 ft (95.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor 3.40 ft (1.04 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on Aug. 23, 1996, replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on January 13, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 23, 1996 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 312.23 ft (95.2 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 13, 14, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 313.84 ft (95.7 m), below land-surface datum, April 3, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	313.40	313.57	313.56	313.65	313.44	313.51	313.70	313.74	313.25	313.32	313.38	313.26
2	313.37	313.57	313.56	313.66	313.44	313.53	313.71	313.72	313.20	313.33	313.40	313.23
3	313.39	313.57	313.59	313.63	313.46	313.56	313.76	313.69	313.20	313.36	313.41	313.17
4	313.37	313.61	313.66	313.59	313.44	313.56	313.79	313.66	313.22	313.36	313.42	313.16
5	313.39	313.61	313.68	313.53	313.36	313.56	313.76	313.64	313.23	313.33	313.43	313.17
6	313.42	313.63	313.65	313.46	313.36	313.54	313.71	313.64	313.26	313.33	313.46	313.17
7	313.44	313.61	313.59	313.46	313.36	313.54	313.67	313.66	313.25	313.36	313.46	313.15
8	313.46	313.57	313.58	313.46	313.36	313.56	313.69	313.64	313.29	313.37	313.42	313.15
9	313.44	313.54	313.58	313.46	313.36	313.57	313.75	313.64	313.30	313.39	313.42	313.10
10	313.42	313.51	313.59	313.44	313.39	313.59	313.76	313.65	313.32	313.37	313.45	313.10
11	313.40	313.49	313.59	313.44	313.44	313.57	313.71	313.67	313.32	313.34	313.45	313.09
12	313.34	313.51	313.60	313.45	313.48	313.56	313.67	313.67	313.32	313.31	313.44	313.11
13	313.28	313.51	313.61	313.46	313.48	313.59	313.64	313.67	313.26	313.28	313.47	313.12
14	313.22	313.54	313.63	313.50	313.48	313.61	313.70	313.65	313.15	313.28	313.48	313.11
15	313.17	313.55	313.60	313.51	313.46	313.65	313.76	313.59	313.10	313.29	313.49	313.10
16	313.13	313.58	313.61	313.50	313.48	313.67	313.78	313.57	313.08	313.32	313.47	313.11
17	313.24	313.58	313.61	313.50	313.50	313.69	313.70	313.56	313.10	313.32	313.46	313.11
18	313.35	313.61	313.60	313.50	313.48	313.72	313.69	313.53	313.14	313.30	313.46	313.11
19	313.42	313.61	313.63	313.46	313.50	313.76	313.68	313.49	313.14	313.29	313.39	313.06
20	313.47	313.60	313.65	313.45	313.51	313.76	313.60	313.44	313.16	313.29	313.35	313.04
21	313.48	313.60	313.66	313.44	313.54	313.74	313.57	313.29	313.19	313.31	313.29	313.03
22	313.48	313.59	313.65	313.42	313.56	313.71	313.56	313.27	313.23	313.32	313.21	---
23	313.50	313.60	313.61	313.42	313.54	313.68	313.56	313.24	313.25	313.30	313.17	---
24	313.51	313.58	313.61	313.42	313.53	313.70	313.54	313.25	313.25	313.30	313.16	---
25	313.53	313.56	313.61	313.42	313.50	313.70	313.54	313.25	313.28	313.31	313.16	---
26	313.54	313.55	313.61	313.45	313.51	313.72	313.54	313.22	313.31	313.36	313.13	---
27	313.53	313.55	313.61	313.45	313.50	313.76	313.58	313.22	313.32	313.36	313.16	---
28	313.54	313.55	313.61	313.45	313.48	313.76	313.64	313.22	313.32	313.37	313.18	---
29	313.56	313.55	313.60	313.44	---	313.73	313.69	313.24	313.33	313.37	313.19	---
30	313.56	313.56	313.60	313.44	---	313.69	313.70	313.24	313.32	313.39	313.22	---
31	313.57	---	313.61	313.42	---	313.67	---	313.26	---	313.38	313.24	---
MEAN	313.42	313.57	313.61	313.48	313.46	313.64	313.67	313.49	313.24	313.33	313.35	313.13

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 313.46 HIGHEST 312.95 SEPT. 21, 22, 1998 LOWEST 313.84 APR. 3, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

182626066345100. Local number, TI-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'26", long 66°34'51", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.45 mi south of Hwy 682, 1.15 mi northwest of the intersection of Hwy 140 with Hwy 2 (Cruce Dávila), 0.48 mi north of Hwy 2, and approximately 100 feet south of Hwy 22. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Tiburones 1.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m). Depth 320 ft (97.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval. Prior to December 19, 1996, pressure transducer with integrated electronic data logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 295 ft (89.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 4 in (0.10 m) PVC cap, above shelter floor, 3.40 ft (1.04 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Electronic Data Logger (EDL), re-installed on October 27, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 14, 1996 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 290.88 ft (88.7 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 13, 1996; lowest water level measured, 292.79 ft (89.2 m), below land-surface datum, Jan. 17, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	292.11	292.13	292.32	292.06	292.11	292.31	292.35	291.92	291.98	292.10	292.05
2	---	292.09	292.13	292.32	292.07	292.13	292.31	292.34	291.87	292.00	292.11	292.02
3	---	292.14	292.17	292.29	292.11	292.16	292.35	292.31	291.91	292.02	292.12	291.96
4	---	292.18	292.25	292.23	292.07	292.15	292.41	292.27	291.88	292.01	292.13	291.97
5	---	292.18	292.26	292.16	291.95	292.14	292.35	292.27	291.91	291.98	292.16	291.97
6	---	292.20	292.20	292.13	291.94	292.11	292.30	292.25	291.92	291.99	292.18	291.97
7	---	292.19	292.17	292.08	291.98	292.11	292.27	292.23	291.93	292.00	292.16	291.96
8	---	292.14	292.14	292.08	291.95	292.14	292.27	292.22	291.98	292.03	292.14	291.94
9	---	292.11	292.17	292.10	291.97	292.15	292.34	292.20	291.96	292.04	292.13	291.91
10	---	292.06	292.14	292.09	292.00	292.20	292.35	292.25	292.00	292.02	292.16	291.91
11	---	292.04	292.14	292.05	292.04	292.16	292.32	292.26	292.00	291.99	292.16	291.91
12	---	292.08	292.17	292.06	292.10	292.16	292.28	292.29	291.99	291.96	292.17	291.93
13	---	292.07	292.19	292.06	292.11	292.20	292.24	292.29	291.93	291.93	292.20	291.94
14	---	292.09	292.20	292.13	292.07	292.24	292.31	292.27	291.84	291.92	292.23	291.93
15	---	292.12	292.19	292.13	292.06	292.27	292.38	292.17	291.77	291.93	292.24	291.95
16	---	292.14	292.18	292.13	292.07	292.26	292.36	292.16	291.75	291.95	292.24	291.95
17	---	292.18	292.16	292.12	292.09	292.30	292.27	292.16	291.78	291.97	292.22	291.95
18	---	292.18	292.16	292.12	292.10	292.34	292.29	292.12	291.82	291.98	292.20	291.93
19	---	292.19	292.19	292.08	292.09	292.37	292.25	292.07	291.83	291.97	292.15	291.89
20	---	292.16	292.25	292.06	292.13	292.37	292.18	292.04	291.86	291.97	292.10	291.88
21	---	292.17	292.22	292.07	292.12	292.32	292.17	291.97	291.88	291.98	292.03	291.85
22	---	292.19	292.21	292.06	292.15	292.31	292.14	291.94	291.91	291.99	291.96	291.74
23	---	292.18	292.17	292.07	292.14	292.29	292.15	291.92	291.91	291.97	291.92	291.50
24	---	292.13	292.30	292.05	292.14	292.28	292.12	291.92	291.92	291.96	291.90	291.39
25	---	292.11	292.29	292.09	292.10	292.29	292.12	291.93	291.95	291.98	291.91	291.42
26	---	292.12	292.28	292.06	292.10	292.34	292.14	291.90	291.98	292.03	291.88	291.46
27	---	292.13	292.29	292.06	292.10	292.37	292.20	291.91	292.00	292.05	291.92	291.50
28	292.13	292.10	292.29	292.09	292.10	292.33	292.28	291.90	291.99	292.06	291.95	291.52
29	292.11	292.11	292.28	292.06	---	292.33	292.31	291.90	291.99	292.07	291.97	291.57
30	292.14	292.12	292.25	292.06	---	292.28	292.33	291.91	291.98	292.09	292.00	291.62
31	292.11	---	292.27	292.05	---	292.26	---	291.92	---	292.09	292.04	---
MEAN	292.12	292.13	292.21	292.11	292.07	292.24	292.27	292.12	291.91	292.00	292.09	291.82

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 292.09 HIGHEST 291.37 SEPT. 24, 1998 LOWEST 292.46 APR. 5, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

182603066333601. Local number, FA-2.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'03", long 66°33'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.70 south of the intersection of Hwy 140 with Hwy 22, 0.35 mi east of the intersection of Hwy 140 with Hwy 2, and 1.35 mi northeast of the intersection of Hwy 140 with Hwy 666. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Florida Afuera No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 0-270 ft (0-82.3 m), screened 200-270 ft (61.0-82.3 m). Depth 270 ft (82.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 213.3 ft (65.0 m), above mean sea level from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of the 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 4.00 ft (1.22 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on August 23, 1996, replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on January 17, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 23, 1996 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 199.01 ft (60.7 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 11, 12, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 201.63 ft (61.5 m), below land-surface datum, Apr. 10, 11, 12, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.41	201.31	201.37
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.41	201.31	201.37
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.17	201.41	201.31	201.37
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.17	201.41	201.31	201.37
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.18	201.41	201.34	201.37
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.20	201.41	201.34	201.36
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.18	201.41	201.34	201.36
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.20	201.43	201.34	201.27
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.21	201.43	201.32	201.27
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.26	201.41	201.29	201.27
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.30	201.41	201.29	201.29
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.30	201.41	201.31	201.29
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.30	201.40	201.34	201.29
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.30	201.32	201.32	201.30
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.29	201.32	201.35	201.30
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.29	201.32	201.35	201.32
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.30	201.32	201.35	201.32
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.32	201.34	201.35	201.31
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.32	201.31	201.38	201.31
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.17	201.33	201.28	201.38	201.31
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.18	201.33	201.25	201.38	201.37
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.20	201.33	201.25	201.38	201.37
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.20	201.35	201.25	201.38	---
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.18	201.38	201.25	201.38	---
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.17	201.39	201.23	201.38	---
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.39	201.25	201.37	---
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.41	201.25	201.37	---
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.41	201.25	201.37	---
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.14	201.41	201.28	201.37	---
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	201.41	201.29	201.37	---
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.15	---	201.32	201.37	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	201.16	201.29	201.34	201.35	201.33

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 201.20 HIGHEST 199.29 JAN. 23, 24, 1997 LOWEST 201.44 JULY 7, 8, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	201.37	201.47	201.54	201.40	201.47	201.60	201.50	200.86	200.76	200.86	200.61
2	---	201.37	201.47	201.54	201.40	201.47	201.60	201.54	200.86	200.76	200.86	200.63
3	---	201.37	201.47	201.52	201.40	201.45	201.61	201.55	200.86	200.79	200.88	200.57
4	---	201.39	201.50	201.50	201.44	201.47	201.61	201.55	200.86	200.82	200.89	200.56
5	---	201.40	201.51	201.49	201.41	201.48	201.61	201.55	200.86	200.82	200.90	200.55
6	---	201.42	201.50	201.48	201.39	201.45	201.62	201.53	200.90	200.82	200.94	200.56
7	---	201.43	201.50	201.42	201.39	201.48	201.62	201.53	200.88	200.84	200.96	200.56
8	---	201.43	201.50	201.37	201.38	201.48	201.62	201.53	200.88	200.84	200.96	200.49
9	---	201.40	201.51	201.39	201.35	201.48	201.62	201.53	200.88	200.85	200.95	200.47
10	---	201.39	201.51	201.37	201.35	201.49	201.63	201.53	200.81	200.86	200.94	200.46
11	---	201.40	201.51	201.37	201.33	201.54	201.63	201.53	200.81	200.86	200.96	200.45
12	---	201.40	201.53	201.37	201.35	201.54	201.63	201.54	200.81	200.86	200.97	200.44
13	---	201.40	201.51	201.37	201.36	201.53	201.62	201.54	200.81	200.86	200.97	200.43
14	---	201.42	201.51	201.39	201.39	201.51	201.60	201.57	200.66	200.86	200.96	200.37
15	---	201.43	201.53	201.39	201.38	201.51	201.60	201.24	200.42	200.86	200.97	200.37
16	---	201.43	201.53	201.39	201.39	201.53	201.56	201.19	200.42	200.86	200.96	200.38
17	---	201.43	201.53	201.42	201.41	201.52	201.51	201.23	200.42	200.86	200.96	200.38
18	---	201.45	201.51	201.42	201.41	201.54	201.51	200.93	200.42	200.85	200.97	200.40
19	---	201.45	201.51	201.40	201.42	201.58	201.50	200.90	200.43	200.82	200.97	200.38
20	---	201.44	201.51	201.40	201.42	201.62	201.17	200.63	200.46	200.81	200.91	200.37
21	---	201.45	201.51	201.39	201.45	201.61	201.19	200.66	200.51	200.80	200.86	200.34
22	---	201.44	201.52	201.39	201.47	201.61	201.26	200.76	200.57	200.81	200.77	200.35
23	---	201.44	201.52	201.39	201.49	201.59	201.29	200.84	200.64	200.82	200.70	200.34
24	---	201.45	201.52	201.37	201.49	201.59	201.32	200.86	200.67	200.83	200.66	200.31
25	---	201.45	201.52	201.37	201.49	201.59	201.34	200.90	200.70	200.84	200.62	200.30
26	---	201.45	201.52	201.37	201.51	201.61	201.34	200.91	200.72	200.83	200.61	200.29
27	---	201.45	201.54	201.37	201.49	201.61	201.36	200.94	200.73	200.83	200.59	200.29
28	201.32	201.45	201.54	201.39	201.48	201.61	201.39	200.94	200.74	200.81	200.58	200.28
29	201.35	201.44	201.54	201.39	---	201.61	201.43	200.94	200.74	200.81	200.57	200.27
30	201.35	201.45	201.52	201.40	---	201.61	201.48	200.94	200.76	200.83	200.57	200.26
31	201.37	---	201.54	201.40	---	201.61	---	200.91	---	200.84	200.58	---
MEAN	201.35	201.42	201.51	201.41	201.42	201.54	201.50	201.20	200.70	200.83	200.83	200.42

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 201.16 HIGHEST 200.25 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 201.63 APR. 10, 11, 12, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

182209066340600. Local number, FL-1.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'09", long 66°34'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.20 north of the intersection of Hwy 140 with Hwy 642, 1.15 mi south of the intersection of Hwy 140 with Hwy 641, and approximately 100 ft west of Hwy 140. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Florida 1.
 AQUIFER.--Cibao Formation.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m), Depth 200 ft (61.0 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Pressure transducer with an electronic data logger--60-minute interval.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 607 ft (185 m), above mean sea level from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Shelter floor 4.00 ft (1.22 m), above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 12, 1996 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 137.91 ft (42.0 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 22, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 157.63 ft (48.0 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 14, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	151.59	152.33	153.45	153.25	154.60	154.27	152.96	147.98	151.55	153.66	153.64
2	---	151.78	152.43	153.57	153.40	154.72	154.48	150.16	149.30	151.76	153.83	153.86
3	---	151.88	152.53	153.66	152.70	154.82	154.62	152.02	150.24	151.97	153.98	148.21
4	---	151.08	152.62	153.76	153.13	154.89	154.75	152.34	150.88	151.63	154.10	149.29
5	---	151.28	152.72	153.81	146.84	154.94	154.85	152.54	151.34	151.97	154.21	150.25
6	---	151.38	152.82	150.29	148.96	153.15	154.95	152.48	150.50	152.19	154.28	151.00
7	---	151.47	152.92	148.07	149.83	153.53	155.07	150.20	149.54	152.39	154.37	152.13
8	---	151.67	153.02	148.95	150.59	153.37	155.10	152.18	150.49	152.58	153.49	150.12
9	---	151.77	153.11	149.27	148.93	153.73	155.12	148.96	151.52	152.76	153.86	150.47
10	---	151.87	153.21	149.37	150.23	153.99	155.22	150.08	151.88	152.91	153.76	151.38
11	---	151.97	153.21	149.29	151.23	154.21	155.31	149.10	152.15	153.03	154.07	152.42
12	---	151.36	153.31	149.36	151.63	154.40	155.41	150.30	152.39	153.16	154.31	152.86
13	---	151.56	153.41	147.11	152.02	154.53	155.46	150.64	148.64	153.26	154.29	153.06
14	---	151.76	153.51	149.40	152.37	154.65	155.54	149.99	143.93	153.36	154.49	153.15
15	---	151.86	153.60	150.60	152.69	154.76	155.57	149.90	144.98	153.46	154.64	153.36
16	---	151.76	153.70	151.63	152.92	152.67	148.60	149.61	146.27	153.53	154.78	153.58
17	---	151.86	153.71	152.01	153.11	153.21	146.65	148.74	147.32	153.66	150.89	153.78
18	---	151.95	153.83	152.36	153.30	153.63	150.25	148.45	148.09	153.12	152.71	153.98
19	---	151.75	153.94	152.13	153.47	153.73	151.08	147.85	148.80	153.21	152.26	152.64
20	---	151.95	154.04	149.55	153.64	153.86	145.73	144.93	149.44	153.44	152.84	153.10
21	---	152.05	154.12	150.70	153.80	153.74	147.14	145.50	149.95	153.53	147.56	153.37
22	---	152.15	154.24	150.69	153.96	154.00	148.45	146.17	149.07	153.66	148.96	141.97
23	---	152.24	154.35	150.54	154.08	154.21	149.57	147.67	149.83	153.81	150.36	139.67
24	150.30	152.34	154.43	150.51	154.19	154.38	150.46	147.98	150.43	153.48	151.16	142.13
25	150.50	152.44	154.48	149.98	154.30	154.52	150.50	149.09	150.86	153.40	149.06	144.00
26	150.80	152.54	154.53	151.77	154.40	154.62	151.60	150.00	148.67	153.62	150.54	145.04
27	150.99	151.44	154.58	151.96	154.46	154.70	152.06	150.12	149.49	151.17	151.46	145.40
28	151.09	151.73	154.63	151.95	154.55	154.79	152.39	150.83	150.25	152.67	152.70	145.92
29	151.19	151.93	154.69	152.42	---	154.88	150.27	151.25	150.83	153.11	152.34	146.54
30	151.39	152.13	154.73	152.69	---	153.49	152.75	151.60	151.38	153.26	152.89	147.20
31	151.49	---	154.79	153.02	---	153.92	---	148.08	---	153.48	153.31	---
MEAN	150.97	151.82	153.66	151.09	152.43	154.15	152.44	149.73	149.55	152.91	152.75	149.78
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 151.83	HIGHEST 137.91	SEPT. 22, 1998	LOWEST 155.61	APR. 15, 16, 1998							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182757066325600. Local number, 206.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'57", long 66°32'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.84 mi northwest of Barceloneta plaza, 0.64 mi west of Central Plazuela, and 1.96 mi southeast of Escuela Agustín Balseiro. Owner: PR Department of Agriculture, Name: Plazuela No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-85.0 ft (0-25.9 m), open hole 85-101 ft (25.9-30.8 m). Depth 101 ft (30.8 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 7.00 ft (2.1 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 7, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.75 ft (1.14 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 11, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 6.03 ft (1.84 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 15, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.32	5.47	5.44	5.50	5.32	5.42	5.57	5.66	5.20	5.26	5.37	5.28
2	5.30	5.45	5.45	5.49	5.33	5.44	5.61	5.64	5.18	5.29	5.39	5.25
3	5.31	5.46	5.49	5.49	5.38	5.46	5.66	5.61	5.18	5.30	5.40	5.21
4	5.30	5.54	5.55	5.46	5.34	5.47	5.69	5.57	5.19	5.30	5.41	5.21
5	5.31	5.56	5.57	5.41	5.22	5.47	5.67	5.56	5.21	5.27	5.44	5.19
6	5.33	5.56	5.54	5.36	5.25	5.44	5.60	5.56	5.22	5.28	5.46	5.20
7	5.38	5.54	5.49	5.30	5.26	5.46	5.56	5.54	5.19	5.29	5.44	5.19
8	5.39	5.50	5.48	5.30	5.26	5.47	5.56	5.55	5.23	5.31	5.41	5.17
9	5.37	5.47	5.48	5.31	5.26	5.48	5.62	5.53	5.25	5.31	5.39	5.14
10	5.37	5.45	5.48	5.29	5.27	5.49	5.65	5.56	5.25	5.29	5.43	5.14
11	5.35	5.44	5.47	5.28	5.31	5.47	5.58	5.57	5.25	5.26	5.42	5.14
12	5.31	5.45	5.48	5.29	5.38	5.47	5.53	5.56	5.25	5.24	5.43	5.14
13	5.23	5.45	5.48	5.30	5.42	5.48	5.50	5.56	5.21	5.22	5.46	5.17
14	5.16	5.46	5.49	5.38	5.39	5.53	5.57	5.55	5.13	5.21	5.49	5.16
15	5.12	5.47	5.48	5.41	5.36	5.55	5.64	5.44	5.06	5.22	5.51	5.17
16	5.11	5.48	5.48	5.39	5.41	5.56	5.63	5.42	5.06	5.23	5.50	---
17	5.20	5.49	5.48	5.41	5.44	5.59	5.58	5.42	5.09	5.25	5.50	---
18	5.32	5.51	5.48	5.41	5.43	5.63	5.58	5.37	5.13	5.26	5.47	---
19	5.37	5.52	5.51	5.37	5.43	5.64	5.58	5.35	5.14	5.26	5.40	---
20	5.42	5.52	5.54	5.33	5.46	5.65	5.51	5.31	5.16	5.25	5.34	---
21	5.44	5.50	5.54	5.32	5.49	5.61	5.47	5.24	5.18	5.26	5.26	---
22	5.46	5.51	5.51	5.31	5.50	5.58	5.46	5.23	5.22	5.27	5.21	---
23	5.45	5.52	5.48	5.31	5.49	5.58	5.46	5.22	5.22	5.25	5.18	---
24	5.50	5.49	5.50	5.32	5.46	5.59	5.46	5.22	5.22	5.24	5.16	---
25	5.52	5.48	5.50	5.31	5.44	5.59	5.44	5.22	5.24	5.25	5.15	---
26	5.50	5.46	5.50	5.33	5.43	5.61	5.46	5.17	5.26	5.29	5.13	---
27	5.47	5.46	5.49	5.32	5.42	5.64	5.50	5.18	5.28	5.30	5.15	---
28	5.49	5.45	5.48	5.32	5.39	5.64	5.55	5.18	5.27	5.32	5.19	---
29	5.49	5.45	5.45	5.31	---	5.62	5.59	5.19	5.27	5.33	5.20	---
30	5.49	5.46	5.45	5.32	---	5.56	5.62	5.20	5.26	5.34	5.22	---
31	5.48	---	5.47	5.32	---	5.55	---	5.21	---	5.36	5.26	---
MEAN	5.36	5.49	5.49	5.35	5.38	5.54	5.56	5.41	5.20	5.27	5.35	5.18

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 5.39 HIGHEST 5.03 JUNE 16, 1998 LOWEST 5.71 APR. 3, 4, 5, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182710066303700. Local number, 207.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'10", long 66°30'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.92 mi east of Barceloneta plaza, 1.35 mi north of Central Monserrate, and 2.68 mi northeast of Escuela José Cordero. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Cantito La Luisa.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-30.0 ft (0-9.14 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 0-126 ft (0-38.4 m), perforated 80-126 ft (24.4-38.4 m). Depth 126 ft (38.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 59.0 ft (18.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.80 ft (0.85 m), above land-surface datum. Prior to Nov. 20, 1992, hole on side of casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 5, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 36.4 ft (11.1 m), below land-surface datum, May 15, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 89.8 ft (27.4 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 5, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	39.09	39.05	38.76	39.28	39.01	39.00	---	39.22	38.87	39.17	39.28	39.15
2	39.08	39.07	38.77	39.25	39.00	39.01	---	39.25	38.87	39.17	39.28	39.15
3	39.08	39.07	38.80	39.23	39.01	39.03	---	39.25	38.87	39.17	39.27	39.14
4	39.05	39.07	38.84	39.20	39.03	39.06	---	39.25	38.87	39.18	39.27	39.15
5	39.05	38.50	38.86	39.17	38.95	39.08	---	39.25	38.87	39.19	39.30	39.15
6	39.02	38.51	38.86	39.15	38.89	39.07	---	39.26	38.87	39.19	39.31	39.15
7	39.03	38.51	38.85	39.10	38.87	39.08	---	39.26	38.89	39.20	39.33	39.15
8	39.03	38.49	38.87	39.02	38.87	39.10	---	39.26	38.89	39.22	39.31	39.13
9	39.03	38.49	38.90	39.02	38.86	39.13	---	39.26	38.90	39.23	39.31	39.12
10	39.02	38.49	38.91	39.02	38.86	39.15	---	39.27	38.92	39.24	39.32	39.11
11	39.00	38.50	38.93	39.01	38.86	39.16	---	39.27	38.93	39.24	39.32	39.09
12	38.95	38.52	38.95	38.97	38.87	39.16	---	39.26	38.94	39.25	39.31	39.09
13	38.85	38.53	38.97	38.96	38.88	39.17	---	39.29	38.95	39.24	39.32	39.10
14	38.76	38.57	39.00	38.97	38.90	39.19	---	39.29	38.95	39.23	39.33	39.08
15	38.70	38.61	39.00	38.98	38.90	39.21	---	39.09	38.93	39.23	39.33	39.08
16	38.64	38.64	39.00	38.98	38.93	39.22	---	39.07	38.93	39.23	39.33	39.09
17	38.66	38.66	39.02	38.99	38.97	39.24	---	39.04	38.94	39.23	39.32	---
18	38.72	38.68	39.02	39.00	38.98	39.27	---	38.97	38.96	39.24	39.32	---
19	38.76	38.69	39.04	39.00	38.99	39.28	---	38.97	38.97	39.24	39.30	---
20	38.78	38.70	39.06	39.02	38.99	39.32	---	38.96	38.98	39.25	39.29	---
21	38.82	38.70	39.10	39.01	39.03	39.33	---	38.92	39.00	39.25	39.25	---
22	38.85	38.70	39.11	39.00	39.07	39.33	---	38.89	39.04	39.26	39.21	---
23	38.85	38.71	39.12	39.00	39.09	39.33	---	38.88	39.04	39.26	39.18	---
24	38.89	38.72	39.14	38.99	39.12	39.34	---	38.87	39.06	39.26	39.17	---
25	38.92	38.72	39.16	38.99	39.12	39.36	---	38.87	39.07	39.26	39.15	---
26	38.96	38.74	39.18	39.00	39.11	39.37	---	38.87	39.12	39.26	39.12	---
27	38.99	38.76	39.22	39.01	39.06	39.39	---	38.87	39.17	39.27	39.12	---
28	39.01	38.75	39.23	39.02	39.00	39.39	---	38.87	39.17	39.28	39.12	---
29	39.03	38.75	39.23	39.03	---	39.39	39.22	38.87	39.17	39.28	39.12	---
30	39.06	38.76	39.27	39.04	---	39.38	39.21	38.87	39.17	39.28	39.12	---
31	39.06	---	39.28	39.03	---	---	---	38.87	---	39.28	39.14	---
MEAN	38.93	38.69	39.01	39.05	38.97	39.22	39.22	39.08	38.98	39.23	39.25	39.12

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 39.05 HIGHEST 38.48 NOV. 5, 8, 9, 10, 1997 LOWEST 39.39 MAR. 27, 28, 29, 30, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182549066304300. Local number, 166.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'49", long 66°30'43", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.95 mi east of the Rio Grande de Manatí Hwy 2 bridge, 0.40 mi southwest of Central Monserrate, 1.07 mi east of the intersection of Hwy 666 with Hwy 2, 1.20 mi west of the intersection of Hwy 685 with Hwy 2, 0.01 mi north of Hwy 2. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority

Name: Manatí 3.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 0-100 ft (0-39.49 m), diameter 14 in (0.36 m), cased 0-140 ft (0-42.7 m), slotted 80-90 ft (24.7-27.4 m), and 130-140 ft (39.6-42.7 m). Depth 140 ft (42.7 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 29.50 ft (9.0 m), above mean-sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: A hole in the side of the 20 in (0.51 m) diameter well casing, 1.65 ft (0.50 m) above land-surface datum. Prior May 31, 1996, top of 14 in (0.36 m) casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 31, 1996. Formerly published as 182542066305200. From September 9, 1998, monthly measurements only.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1982 to December 1984, discontinued, May 31, 1996 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 22.11 ft (6.74 m), below land-surface datum, Jan. 25, 1997; lowest water level measured, 26.36 ft (8.04 m), below land-surface datum, Feb. 3, 1983.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	24.06	23.97	24.12	24.19	23.87	23.95	24.16	24.06	23.25	23.78	---	---
2	24.03	23.98	24.14	24.18	23.88	23.97	24.19	24.10	23.25	23.75	---	---
3	24.03	24.00	24.13	24.16	24.04	23.99	24.22	24.09	23.23	23.79	---	---
4	23.99	23.98	24.16	24.13	24.11	24.03	24.22	24.10	23.32	23.87	---	---
5	23.97	24.00	24.17	24.11	23.83	24.02	24.25	24.12	23.32	23.88	---	---
6	23.90	24.03	24.16	24.11	23.73	24.02	24.25	24.12	23.34	23.92	---	---
7	23.91	24.02	24.17	23.99	23.63	24.02	24.25	24.09	23.27	23.93	---	---
8	23.91	24.04	24.17	23.92	23.62	23.99	24.22	24.10	23.37	23.99	---	---
9	23.91	24.04	24.16	23.93	23.58	24.04	24.20	24.09	23.46	23.93	---	---
10	23.90	24.05	24.18	23.95	23.62	24.14	24.23	24.07	23.43	23.99	---	---
11	23.90	24.06	24.24	23.91	23.70	24.11	24.24	24.10	23.41	23.95	---	---
12	23.81	24.06	24.19	23.81	23.71	24.10	24.22	24.17	23.41	23.94	---	---
13	23.61	24.07	24.21	23.79	23.76	24.12	24.19	24.12	23.41	23.97	---	---
14	23.47	24.07	24.24	23.77	23.77	24.12	24.30	24.13	23.42	23.99	---	---
15	23.45	24.14	24.14	23.77	23.79	24.10	24.24	23.60	23.36	23.92	---	---
16	23.39	24.14	24.11	23.80	23.84	24.12	24.14	23.53	23.28	23.96	---	---
17	23.39	24.14	24.14	23.85	23.86	24.13	23.99	23.45	23.40	23.98	---	---
18	23.38	24.14	24.13	23.89	23.88	24.16	23.91	23.41	23.44	23.92	---	---
19	23.38	24.08	24.19	23.91	23.91	24.15	23.91	23.37	23.46	23.98	---	---
20	23.38	24.12	24.20	23.88	23.91	24.17	23.85	23.32	23.48	23.91	---	---
21	23.38	24.12	24.18	23.89	23.95	24.18	23.79	23.25	23.51	23.89	---	---
22	23.57	24.14	24.24	23.89	23.98	24.21	23.80	23.19	23.42	23.90	---	---
23	23.63	24.18	24.23	23.91	24.00	24.20	23.83	23.18	23.52	23.95	---	---
24	23.66	24.19	24.22	23.90	24.03	24.19	23.84	23.18	23.57	23.91	---	---
25	23.76	24.17	24.24	23.86	24.04	24.21	23.85	23.22	23.61	23.87	---	---
26	23.78	24.14	24.22	23.85	24.05	24.17	23.87	23.23	23.68	23.87	---	---
27	23.83	24.16	24.24	23.87	24.02	24.19	23.89	23.24	23.65	23.89	---	---
28	23.86	24.14	24.25	23.87	23.98	24.24	23.91	23.29	23.67	---	---	---
29	23.90	24.16	24.24	23.89	---	24.20	23.96	23.33	23.70	---	---	---
30	23.93	24.14	24.22	23.90	---	24.21	24.03	23.25	23.73	---	---	---
31	23.97	---	24.21	23.89	---	24.16	---	23.23	---	---	---	---
MEAN	23.74	24.09	24.19	23.93	23.86	24.12	24.07	23.67	23.45	23.91	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 23.90 HIGHEST 23.10 MAY 22, 1998 LOWEST 24.30 APR. 14, 1998

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182506066280200. Local number, HI-2.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'06", long 66°28'02", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.72 mi southwest of the intersection of Hwy 686 with Hwy 670, 0.73 mi southeast of intersection of Hwy 149 with Hwy 670, and 0.78 mi northeast of Escuela Sabana Seca. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: USGS Hill 2.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), screened 360-410 ft (110-125 m). Depth 410 ft (125 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Pressure transducer with integrated electronic data logger--60 minutes interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 312 ft (95.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.76 ft (1.15 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on May 28, 1996.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 28, 1996 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 267.96 ft (81.7 m), below land-surface datum, Jan. 24, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 293.09 ft (89.3 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 5, 6, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP		
1	288.65	288.66	289.45	290.21	290.27	290.44	290.61	290.41	289.07	288.96	288.70	289.07		
2	288.65	288.72	289.54	290.19	290.28	290.47	290.76	290.42	289.06	288.92	288.67	289.04		
3	288.65	288.74	289.61	290.16	290.19	290.49	290.82	290.41	288.96	288.87	288.71	289.18		
4	288.73	288.81	289.57	290.14	290.12	290.54	290.79	290.39	288.90	288.85	288.80	289.32		
5	288.75	288.86	289.56	290.15	290.19	290.60	290.72	290.43	288.88	288.87	288.83	289.31		
6	288.73	288.85	289.54	290.19	290.29	290.59	290.74	290.44	288.85	288.90	288.83	289.32		
7	288.65	288.80	289.64	290.15	290.25	290.58	290.91	290.41	288.88	288.87	288.82	289.30		
8	288.59	288.82	289.70	290.24	290.17	290.67	291.04	290.39	289.00	288.89	288.86	289.35		
9	288.59	288.91	289.68	290.26	290.20	290.71	291.00	290.43	289.07	288.89	288.83	289.38		
10	288.57	289.05	289.69	290.25	290.27	290.73	290.90	290.44	289.08	288.87	288.82	289.42		
11	288.55	289.09	289.71	290.19	290.32	290.67	290.88	290.39	289.07	288.82	288.88	289.38		
12	288.49	289.13	289.74	290.20	290.32	290.74	290.87	290.40	288.92	288.78	288.93	289.37		
13	288.37	289.14	289.72	290.23	290.27	290.79	291.05	290.41	288.87	288.75	288.89	289.40		
14	287.38	289.15	289.70	289.83	290.25	290.77	291.08	290.36	288.86	288.75	288.86	289.47		
15	286.34	289.21	289.73	289.66	290.27	290.67	291.04	290.24	288.90	288.78	288.88	289.59		
16	287.48	289.26	289.78	289.73	290.30	290.70	290.96	290.25	288.98	288.76	288.95	289.62		
17	287.62	289.30	289.84	289.82	290.21	290.75	290.78	290.29	289.00	288.77	289.00	289.67		
18	287.76	289.35	289.87	289.87	290.21	290.78	290.67	290.28	288.95	288.70	288.96	289.69		
19	287.88	289.35	289.95	289.90	290.24	290.80	290.52	290.23	288.97	288.75	288.93	289.74		
20	287.92	289.32	289.93	289.96	290.29	290.78	290.47	290.04	288.97	288.78	289.03	289.79		
21	288.03	289.39	289.88	290.05	290.31	290.68	290.33	289.88	289.00	288.77	288.92	289.70		
22	288.16	289.39	289.94	290.08	290.39	290.74	290.15	289.74	289.06	288.72	289.04	288.89		
23	288.27	289.41	289.95	290.16	290.36	290.83	290.16	289.71	289.06	288.71	289.10	288.82		
24	288.33	289.40	289.96	290.16	290.36	290.90	290.23	289.72	289.07	288.69	289.07	286.97		
25	288.37	289.36	290.01	290.20	290.39	290.97	290.34	289.69	289.04	288.79	289.13	287.53		
26	288.44	289.37	290.02	290.20	290.42	291.00	290.38	289.69	288.99	288.71	289.16	287.94		
27	288.47	289.38	289.97	290.20	290.44	290.90	290.39	289.76	288.95	288.66	288.97	288.04		
28	288.50	289.48	289.97	290.21	290.46	290.76	290.43	289.73	288.97	288.68	288.84	288.19		
29	288.53	289.45	290.02	290.19	---	290.65	290.51	289.69	289.01	288.68	288.93	288.44		
30	288.54	289.40	290.09	290.15	---	290.54	290.50	289.69	288.98	288.71	288.97	288.63		
31	288.61	---	290.18	290.16	---	290.50	---	289.47	---	288.69	289.07	---		
MEAN	288.28	289.15	289.80	290.10	290.29	290.70	290.67	290.12	288.98	288.79	288.92	289.05		
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 289.57	HIGHEST 285.27	SEPT. 22, 1998	LOWEST 291.10	APR. 14, 1988									

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182308066260400. Local number, 210.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'08", long 66°26'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 4.88 mi southeast of Manatí plaza, 5.24 mi southwest of Vega Baja plaza, and 2.25 mi west of Escuela Evaristo Camacho. Owner: Gelo Martínez, Name: Gelo Martínez well.
 AQUIFER.--Lares Limestone.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 574 ft (174.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.30 ft (1.01 m), above land-surface datum. Prior to January 14, 1993, hole on side of casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m), above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 17, 1997.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 40.56 ft (12.4 m), below land-surface datum, May 22, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 85.50 ft (26.1 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 14, 15, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	80.14	80.95	82.75	85.12	85.72	---	---	82.93	83.00	82.44	79.85	78.30
2	80.14	80.98	82.83	85.15	85.71	---	---	82.93	82.98	82.41	79.72	78.31
3	80.13	81.00	82.90	85.19	85.71	---	---	82.93	82.96	82.38	79.60	78.33
4	80.15	81.01	82.98	85.26	85.69	---	---	82.93	82.95	82.37	79.51	78.38
5	80.19	81.06	83.08	85.31	85.69	---	---	82.93	82.94	82.34	79.39	78.39
6	80.22	81.10	83.15	85.33	85.67	---	---	82.93	82.92	82.31	79.32	78.42
7	80.26	81.12	83.26	85.37	85.67	---	---	82.92	82.91	82.28	79.25	78.43
8	80.29	81.15	83.34	85.38	85.66	---	---	82.92	82.89	82.25	79.20	78.43
9	80.33	81.18	83.42	85.40	85.62	---	---	82.93	82.88	82.18	79.14	78.44
10	80.38	81.22	83.49	85.51	---	---	---	82.93	82.87	82.15	79.08	78.55
11	80.43	81.27	83.57	85.54	---	---	---	82.94	82.83	82.11	79.01	78.58
12	80.48	81.31	83.64	85.58	---	---	---	82.95	82.80	82.07	78.97	78.62
13	80.52	81.34	83.77	85.61	---	---	---	82.98	82.79	82.03	78.92	78.63
14	80.57	81.39	83.85	85.65	---	---	---	82.99	82.77	81.98	78.90	78.64
15	80.58	81.42	83.93	85.69	---	---	---	83.01	82.76	81.93	78.84	78.65
16	80.62	81.46	84.00	85.70	---	---	---	83.04	82.74	81.88	78.80	78.62
17	80.65	81.50	84.08	85.73	---	---	---	83.05	82.74	81.79	78.76	78.66
18	80.68	81.58	84.16	85.74	---	---	---	83.07	82.73	81.76	78.73	78.68
19	80.71	81.67	84.24	85.75	---	---	---	83.08	82.71	81.70	78.70	78.70
20	80.74	81.75	84.31	85.75	---	---	---	83.10	82.69	81.62	78.67	78.73
21	80.76	81.84	84.37	85.76	---	---	---	83.11	82.67	81.53	78.63	78.77
22	80.78	81.95	84.43	85.76	---	---	---	83.11	82.66	81.50	78.58	78.25
23	80.80	82.04	84.49	85.77	---	---	---	83.11	82.63	81.34	78.53	77.90
24	80.82	82.14	84.54	85.78	---	---	---	83.11	82.61	81.17	78.46	77.67
25	80.84	82.22	84.73	85.78	---	---	---	83.10	82.58	81.06	78.42	77.27
26	80.86	82.30	84.80	85.79	---	---	---	83.10	82.56	80.89	78.39	76.72
27	80.88	82.36	84.90	85.79	---	---	---	83.08	82.54	80.71	78.38	76.15
28	80.89	82.46	84.96	85.78	---	---	---	83.07	82.51	80.51	78.35	75.68
29	80.90	82.55	85.03	85.77	---	---	---	83.04	82.49	80.33	78.32	75.35
30	80.91	82.65	85.07	85.74	---	---	82.93	83.03	82.46	80.14	78.31	75.16
31	80.93	---	85.09	85.73	---	---	---	83.01	---	79.98	78.30	---
MEAN	80.57	81.60	83.97	85.59	85.68	---	82.93	83.01	82.75	81.65	78.87	77.98

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 81.91 HIGHEST 75.10 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 85.79 JAN 26, 27, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182548066265700. Local number CS-7

LOCATION. Lat 18°25'48", long 66°26'57", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.92 mi east of the intersection of Hwy 686 with Hwy 670, 0.79 mi south of Hwy 2, 0.27 mi east of the intersection of Hwy 672 with Hwy 670, and 0.01 mi south of Hwy 670. Owner: Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Coto Sur No. 7.

AQUIFER.--Tertiary Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level ,logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 270.0 ft (82.3 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 20 in (0.51 m) casing, 2.30 ft (0.70 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorded (ADR), installed on July 11, 1994, replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on May 15, 1997. From Oct. 15, 1997, monthly measurements only.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 11, 1994 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 254.41 ft (77.54 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 15, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 260.63 ft (79.44 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 14, 15, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level						
Oct. 15	258.90	Dec. 15	259.63	Feb. 17	259.36	June 10	259.35
Oct. 21	258.92	Jan. 15	259.40	Apr. 29	259.54	June 16	259.39
Nov. 17	259.52						

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182614066261500. Local number, PA-2.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'14", long 66°26'15", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.80 mi east of the intersection of Hwy 686 with Hwy 670, 0.30 mi south of Hwy 2, 0.70 mi northeast of Escuela Ramirez de Arellano, and 0.32 mi north of Hwy 670.

Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Palo Alto 2.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), screened 265-310 ft (80.8-94.5 m). Depth 310 ft (94.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Pressure transducer with integrated electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 245.5 ft (74.8 m), above mean sea level, from topographic survey.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.79 ft (1.16 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on May 28, 1996.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 28, 1996 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 221.78 ft (67.6 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 12, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 240.14 ft (73.2 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 18, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	239.43	239.43	239.59	239.80	239.66	239.68	239.92	239.84	239.58	239.93	240.03	239.95
2	239.43	239.44	239.59	239.79	239.65	239.68	239.92	239.86	239.59	239.94	240.04	239.97
3	239.42	239.45	239.61	239.78	239.65	239.70	239.92	239.87	239.59	239.94	240.04	239.97
4	239.42	239.48	239.61	239.76	239.65	239.71	239.93	239.88	239.59	239.95	240.05	239.98
5	239.41	239.49	239.63	239.75	239.49	239.72	239.94	239.89	239.59	239.95	240.06	239.99
6	239.38	239.50	239.63	239.74	239.51	239.73	239.95	239.91	239.61	239.95	240.07	239.99
7	239.37	239.51	239.64	239.72	239.50	239.73	239.95	239.91	239.61	239.96	240.08	239.99
8	239.37	239.51	239.64	239.68	239.49	239.75	239.95	239.92	239.63	239.97	240.09	239.99
9	239.36	239.51	239.65	239.67	239.49	239.76	239.96	239.92	239.65	239.98	240.09	239.98
10	239.36	239.52	239.66	239.66	239.49	239.77	239.96	239.92	239.64	239.99	240.10	239.97
11	239.36	239.52	239.67	239.64	239.50	239.78	239.97	239.91	239.66	239.99	240.10	239.96
12	239.34	239.53	239.68	239.57	239.50	239.79	239.97	239.92	239.68	239.99	240.10	239.96
13	239.30	239.55	239.70	239.56	239.52	239.79	239.97	239.92	239.68	239.99	240.10	239.95
14	239.25	239.56	239.71	239.55	239.54	239.79	239.96	239.93	239.69	239.99	240.11	239.96
15	239.21	239.58	239.72	239.56	239.54	239.80	239.97	239.90	239.69	239.99	240.12	239.96
16	239.16	239.59	239.72	239.56	239.54	239.81	239.93	239.88	239.70	239.99	240.12	239.97
17	239.15	239.60	239.73	239.57	239.57	239.82	239.32	239.86	239.79	240.00	240.12	239.98
18	239.15	239.62	239.72	239.59	239.59	239.84	239.51	239.84	239.79	240.00	240.13	239.99
19	239.17	239.63	239.73	239.59	239.61	239.86	239.62	239.83	239.79	240.00	240.12	240.00
20	239.18	239.63	239.72	239.61	239.62	239.87	239.66	238.61	239.80	240.01	240.12	239.99
21	239.18	239.62	239.73	239.61	239.64	239.88	239.69	239.01	239.81	239.98	240.10	239.98
22	239.20	239.61	239.74	239.62	239.66	239.88	239.70	239.22	239.84	239.98	240.08	236.88
23	239.21	239.60	239.73	239.62	239.68	239.88	239.71	239.35	239.85	239.99	240.06	236.58
24	239.22	239.58	239.74	239.62	239.69	239.88	239.74	239.43	239.87	240.00	240.03	237.35
25	239.25	239.58	239.75	239.62	239.71	239.90	239.75	239.48	239.88	240.01	240.01	237.92
26	239.28	239.58	239.76	239.63	239.72	239.90	239.76	239.52	239.89	240.01	239.98	238.38
27	239.31	239.59	239.76	239.64	239.72	239.92	239.77	239.55	239.90	240.01	239.97	238.70
28	239.33	239.58	239.76	239.66	239.69	239.93	239.79	239.56	239.91	240.02	239.95	238.92
29	239.36	239.58	239.77	239.66	---	239.93	239.81	239.58	239.92	240.02	239.95	239.08
30	239.38	239.58	239.78	239.67	---	239.92	239.83	239.59	239.93	240.02	239.94	239.20
31	239.41	---	239.79	239.66	---	239.92	---	239.59	---	240.03	239.95	---
MEAN	239.30	239.55	239.70	239.65	239.59	239.82	239.83	239.69	239.74	239.99	240.06	239.42

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 239.70 HIGHEST 235.50 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 240.14 AUG. 18, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182712066251700. Local number, TO-3.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'12", long 66°25'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.60 mi north of the intersection of Hwy 687 with Hwy 2, 0.55 mi southeast of the eastern shoreline of Laguna Tortuguero, 0.32 mi east of Laguna Rica, and 0.12 mi west of Hwy 687. Owner: US Geological Survey WRD, Name: USGS Tortuguero TW-3.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), screened 68-218 ft (20.7-66.4 m). Depth 218 ft (66.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 30.0 ft (9.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.40 ft (1.04 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 31, 1996.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 31, 1996 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 23.48 ft (7.16 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 12, 13, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 25.26 ft (7.70 m), below land-surface datum, June 21, 22, 23, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	24.80	24.79	24.78	24.95	24.71	24.74	25.01	25.05	---	---	---	---
2	24.78	24.80	24.79	24.94	24.73	24.75	25.02	25.06	---	---	---	---
3	24.75	24.81	24.81	24.92	24.74	24.77	25.05	25.05	---	---	---	---
4	24.73	24.83	24.84	24.89	24.76	24.79	25.09	25.05	---	---	---	---
5	24.72	24.84	24.85	24.86	24.65	24.80	25.09	25.05	---	---	---	---
6	24.68	24.84	24.84	24.84	24.62	24.80	25.07	25.05	---	---	---	---
7	24.69	24.84	24.83	24.79	24.62	24.82	25.07	25.05	---	---	---	---
8	24.69	24.82	24.82	24.76	24.62	24.83	25.06	25.04	---	---	---	---
9	24.70	24.80	24.83	24.76	24.62	24.84	25.08	25.03	---	---	---	---
10	24.69	24.79	24.84	24.76	24.62	24.86	25.10	25.03	---	---	---	---
11	24.69	24.79	24.84	24.74	24.63	24.86	25.10	25.04	---	---	---	---
12	24.66	24.80	24.85	24.69	24.65	24.86	25.07	---	---	---	---	---
13	24.58	24.81	24.87	24.68	24.67	24.86	25.05	---	---	---	---	---
14	24.47	24.83	24.88	24.68	24.67	24.88	25.06	---	---	---	---	---
15	24.44	24.84	24.87	24.70	24.66	24.90	25.09	25.01	---	---	---	---
16	24.34	24.86	24.88	24.70	24.67	24.93	25.05	24.90	---	---	---	---
17	24.43	24.86	24.89	24.71	24.69	24.94	24.90	24.91	---	---	---	---
18	24.47	24.87	24.88	24.72	24.70	24.97	24.89	24.92	---	---	---	---
19	24.50	24.86	24.89	24.71	24.72	25.00	24.89	24.94	---	---	---	---
20	24.56	24.85	24.89	24.71	24.73	25.01	24.88	24.95	---	---	---	---
21	24.60	24.81	24.91	24.71	24.75	25.00	24.88	24.96	---	---	---	---
22	24.62	24.78	24.91	24.71	24.77	24.99	24.88	24.96	---	---	---	---
23	24.63	24.77	24.91	24.71	24.79	24.99	24.88	24.94	---	---	---	---
24	24.65	24.77	24.91	24.71	24.80	25.01	24.88	24.93	---	---	---	---
25	24.67	24.77	24.91	24.71	24.79	25.03	24.89	24.90	---	---	---	24.45
26	24.68	24.77	24.93	24.72	24.80	25.04	24.91	24.73	---	---	---	24.51
27	24.70	24.77	24.94	24.72	24.77	25.06	24.92	24.50	---	---	---	24.54
28	24.73	24.77	24.94	24.74	24.74	25.07	24.95	24.46	---	---	---	24.55
29	24.75	24.78	24.92	24.74	---	25.06	24.98	---	---	---	---	24.59
30	24.77	24.78	24.94	24.74	---	25.04	25.02	---	---	---	---	24.62
31	24.78	---	24.95	24.73	---	25.02	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	24.64	24.81	24.88	24.76	24.70	24.92	24.99	24.94	---	---	---	24.54

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 24.82 HIGHEST 24.34 OCT. 16, 17, 1997 LOWEST 25.11 APR. 10-11, 15-16, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182615066235300. Local number, 211.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'15", long 66°23'53", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 4.46 mi southeast of Manatí plaza, 5.48 mi southwest of Vega Baja plaza, and 1.22 mi east of Hwy 155 km 58.3. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Rosario No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 14 in (0.36 m) 0-200 ft (0-61.0 m), diameter 12 in (0.30 m) 200-250 ft (61.0-76.2 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-250 ft (0-76.2 m), perforated 210-250 ft (64.0-76.2 m), diameter 10 in (0.25 m) 250-270 ft (76.2-82.3 m), open hole; concrete sealed 0-200 ft (0-61.0 m). Depth 270 ft (82.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 215 ft (65.5 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.10 ft (0.94 m), above land-surface datum. Prior to April 11, 1994, hole on side of casing, 1.15 ft (0.35 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 5, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 191.29 ft (58.3 m), below land-surface datum, May 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 194.1 ft (59.2 m), below land-surface datum, Mar. 31, Apr. 1 to 7, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	193.39	193.38	193.55	193.32	193.34	193.60	193.58	193.28	193.46	193.61	193.53
2	---	193.39	193.38	193.55	193.32	193.34	193.60	193.59	193.29	193.46	193.61	193.53
3	193.36	193.38	193.38	193.55	193.33	193.34	193.60	193.58	193.29	193.47	193.61	193.53
4	193.34	193.38	193.43	193.53	193.34	193.36	193.60	193.58	193.29	193.48	193.61	193.53
5	193.33	193.39	193.45	193.52	193.24	193.38	193.61	193.58	193.30	193.48	193.64	193.53
6	193.31	193.44	193.45	193.50	193.21	193.38	193.61	193.58	193.30	193.48	193.64	193.53
7	193.30	193.44	193.44	193.47	193.21	193.40	193.61	193.57	193.30	193.48	193.65	193.53
8	193.30	193.44	193.44	193.44	193.22	193.41	193.61	193.57	193.30	193.49	193.65	193.53
9	193.30	193.43	193.44	193.43	193.22	193.42	193.61	193.57	193.31	193.54	193.65	193.53
10	193.30	193.42	193.44	193.43	193.22	193.42	193.61	193.56	---	193.54	193.64	193.53
11	193.31	193.42	193.47	193.42	193.22	193.43	193.61	193.56	193.32	193.54	193.64	193.53
12	193.29	193.42	193.46	193.36	193.22	193.43	193.61	193.57	193.32	193.54	193.64	193.53
13	193.24	193.42	193.48	193.35	193.24	193.44	193.60	193.57	193.32	193.54	193.64	193.53
14	193.16	193.44	193.49	193.31	193.25	193.46	193.59	193.58	193.32	193.53	193.64	193.53
15	193.04	193.45	193.49	193.31	193.25	193.48	193.60	193.58	193.32	193.53	193.64	193.53
16	193.02	193.45	193.49	193.31	193.25	193.48	193.61	193.57	193.32	193.53	193.64	193.53
17	193.02	193.45	193.49	193.31	193.27	193.50	193.56	193.56	193.32	193.53	193.64	193.53
18	193.04	193.46	193.49	193.31	193.27	193.52	193.55	193.55	193.32	193.53	193.65	193.53
19	193.06	193.46	193.49	193.31	193.27	193.53	193.55	193.54	193.32	193.53	193.65	193.53
20	193.08	193.46	193.50	193.31	193.28	193.55	193.55	193.45	193.32	193.53	193.65	193.53
21	193.16	193.46	193.50	193.31	193.31	193.56	193.55	193.39	193.34	193.53	193.64	193.53
22	193.20	193.44	193.51	193.31	193.34	193.56	193.55	193.37	193.35	193.53	193.63	193.41
23	193.21	193.38	193.51	193.31	193.34	193.56	193.55	193.37	193.38	193.53	193.55	193.14
24	193.23	193.38	193.51	193.30	193.35	193.56	193.54	193.37	193.38	193.53	193.55	193.10
25	193.28	193.38	193.51	193.30	193.35	193.59	193.54	193.36	193.43	193.53	193.55	193.09
26	193.31	193.38	193.53	193.30	193.35	193.60	193.54	193.35	193.44	193.53	193.54	193.09
27	193.31	193.38	193.53	193.30	193.35	193.60	193.54	193.35	193.44	193.54	193.54	193.09
28	193.39	193.38	193.54	193.30	193.35	193.62	193.54	193.27	193.46	193.54	193.54	193.09
29	193.39	193.37	193.54	193.32	---	193.62	193.53	193.27	193.46	193.54	193.54	193.10
30	193.40	193.38	193.55	193.32	---	193.61	193.54	193.28	193.46	193.54	193.54	193.16
31	193.39	---	193.55	193.32	---	193.61	---	193.28	---	193.61	193.53	---
MEAN	193.24	193.42	193.48	193.38	193.28	193.49	193.58	193.48	193.34	193.52	193.61	193.41

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 193.44 HIGHEST 193.02 OCT. 16, 17, 18, 1997 LOWEST 193.65 AUG. 6-21, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182647066201700. Local number, 70.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'47", long 66°20'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.52 mi north of Vega Alta plaza, 4.78 mi southwest of Dorado plaza, and 2.01 mi northwest of Escuela Industrial para Mujeres. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Sabana Hoyos.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused artesian well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 0-90.0 ft (0-27.4 m), perforated. Depth 90.0 ft (27.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 49.0 ft (14.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of casing wooden cover, 1.30 ft (0.40 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 17, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1960 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 21.33 ft (6.50 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 26, 1976; lowest water level recorded, 31.12 ft (9.48 m), below land-surface datum, May 12, 13, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	29.96	29.52	29.54	29.97	29.45	29.58	30.03	30.05	29.64	29.72	30.09	29.93
2	29.96	29.54	29.55	29.98	29.46	29.60	30.03	30.07	29.63	29.75	30.10	29.93
3	29.96	29.57	29.56	29.98	29.48	29.61	30.03	30.08	29.62	29.77	30.11	29.93
4	29.94	29.59	29.58	29.98	29.50	29.63	30.04	30.09	29.58	29.79	30.12	29.94
5	29.92	29.61	29.59	29.97	29.47	29.65	30.06	30.10	29.56	29.79	30.13	29.94
6	29.87	29.63	29.60	29.95	29.43	29.65	30.07	30.12	29.56	29.80	30.15	29.93
7	29.85	29.64	29.60	29.87	29.38	29.66	30.09	30.13	29.55	29.82	30.16	29.91
8	29.83	29.66	29.60	29.83	29.35	29.68	30.10	30.13	29.55	29.84	30.15	29.90
9	29.81	29.66	29.61	29.80	29.33	29.70	30.12	30.13	29.56	29.85	30.16	29.88
10	29.80	29.68	29.63	29.77	29.32	29.72	30.13	30.14	29.56	29.87	30.16	29.88
11	29.81	29.69	29.64	29.74	29.32	29.73	30.14	30.14	29.56	29.89	30.16	29.88
12	29.79	29.70	29.64	29.65	29.34	29.75	30.14	30.16	29.57	29.91	30.17	29.87
13	29.75	29.71	29.65	29.59	29.35	29.77	30.16	30.18	29.58	29.92	30.17	29.87
14	29.64	29.73	29.67	29.53	29.36	29.80	30.18	30.20	29.58	29.93	30.18	29.87
15	29.59	29.74	29.67	29.46	29.36	29.81	30.19	30.19	29.59	29.95	30.18	29.87
16	29.50	29.76	29.70	29.41	29.37	29.83	30.07	30.16	29.60	29.97	30.18	29.89
17	29.44	29.76	29.72	29.38	29.38	29.86	30.04	30.12	29.61	29.98	30.19	29.90
18	29.41	29.77	29.74	29.35	29.39	29.88	30.00	30.10	29.61	30.00	30.20	29.91
19	29.38	29.75	29.75	29.33	29.41	29.91	29.99	30.08	29.59	30.01	30.19	29.91
20	29.36	29.74	29.77	29.32	29.43	29.93	29.99	30.06	29.59	30.01	30.19	29.91
21	29.34	29.62	29.80	29.33	29.45	29.95	29.98	30.02	29.58	30.01	30.18	29.91
22	29.35	29.59	29.81	29.33	29.47	29.97	29.97	29.99	29.58	30.03	30.16	29.79
23	29.36	29.57	29.82	29.34	29.49	29.99	29.96	29.96	29.59	30.03	30.15	29.55
24	29.37	29.55	29.84	29.36	29.50	30.00	29.96	29.93	29.60	30.04	30.13	29.31
25	29.38	29.54	29.86	29.36	29.53	30.02	29.96	29.91	29.63	30.05	30.08	29.12
26	29.39	29.53	29.87	29.38	29.55	30.05	29.96	29.89	29.64	30.07	30.05	28.97
27	29.42	29.52	29.89	29.39	29.56	30.06	29.97	29.88	29.67	30.06	30.01	28.85
28	29.43	29.52	29.90	29.40	29.57	30.08	29.98	29.85	29.68	30.07	29.98	28.77
29	29.44	29.52	29.92	29.41	---	30.08	30.00	29.84	29.68	30.07	29.96	28.71
30	29.46	29.53	29.94	29.42	---	30.08	30.02	29.72	29.70	30.08	29.93	28.67
31	29.48	---	29.96	29.44	---	30.04	---	29.67	---	30.09	29.93	---
MEAN	29.61	29.63	29.72	29.58	29.43	29.84	30.05	30.04	29.60	29.94	30.12	29.66

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 29.77 HIGHEST 28.66 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWRST 30.20 APR. 15, 16, MAY 14, 15, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182515066194000. Local number, 212.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'15", long 66° 19'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 5.15 mi southwest of Dorado plaza, 0.49 mi north of Vega Alta plaza, and 1.04 mi northwest of Escuela Industrial para Mujeres. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Ponderosa TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone-Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-136 ft (0-41.1 m), perforated 121-131 ft (36.9-39.9 m); bentonite packed 0.5-121 ft (0.15-36.9 m). Depth 136 ft (39.9 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 98.0 ft (29.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 2.55 ft (0.78 m), above land-surface datum. Prior to November 3, 1989, hole on top of shelter floor casing, 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 17, 1998. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 63.05 ft (19.2 m), below land-surface datum, July 15, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 75.33 ft (22.9 m), below land-surface datum, Feb. 27, Mar. 4, 5, 6, 1995

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	69.93	68.76	68.98	70.61	69.60	72.67	73.71	71.24	70.18	69.38	73.09	73.53
2	69.91	68.77	68.96	72.34	69.59	72.71	73.72	72.17	70.07	70.36	73.12	73.53
3	69.88	68.77	68.98	72.72	69.54	72.74	73.74	72.38	70.00	71.54	73.19	73.55
4	69.86	68.78	68.99	70.47	69.53	72.77	73.75	72.54	69.95	70.38	73.23	73.56
5	69.83	68.83	69.00	72.26	69.51	72.84	73.78	72.66	69.88	69.77	73.33	73.58
6	69.77	68.84	69.01	72.71	69.49	72.86	73.79	72.72	69.82	69.74	73.41	73.59
7	69.77	68.86	69.02	70.77	69.46	72.88	73.81	72.78	69.77	71.23	73.44	73.61
8	69.70	68.91	69.06	72.71	69.46	72.92	71.73	72.84	69.72	71.84	73.45	73.63
9	69.66	68.92	69.09	72.82	69.40	72.97	73.59	72.87	69.69	71.51	73.48	73.62
10	69.61	68.95	69.14	72.85	69.39	72.98	73.71	72.90	69.63	72.05	73.50	73.63
11	69.60	68.95	69.15	72.85	69.37	73.02	73.76	72.72	69.59	72.21	73.53	73.64
12	69.56	68.97	69.16	72.78	69.35	73.08	73.77	73.00	69.57	72.31	73.55	73.66
13	69.46	68.98	69.17	72.71	69.34	73.12	71.89	73.05	69.57	72.43	73.56	73.68
14	69.36	68.99	69.18	72.66	69.35	73.14	71.39	73.11	69.53	72.56	73.56	72.88
15	69.26	69.01	69.22	72.59	69.33	73.17	71.50	73.12	69.45	72.66	73.56	73.40
16	69.19	69.06	70.35	72.57	69.32	73.21	71.12	73.12	69.42	72.70	73.57	73.54
17	69.12	69.09	69.98	72.55	69.31	73.31	70.89	73.12	69.40	72.74	73.59	73.63
18	69.02	69.10	69.55	72.52	71.49	73.35	70.76	73.12	69.38	72.78	73.59	73.67
19	68.96	69.10	69.57	72.51	71.77	73.39	70.65	73.12	69.35	72.84	73.70	73.73
20	68.93	69.11	71.76	72.43	71.40	73.44	70.48	73.12	69.32	72.86	73.51	73.80
21	68.88	69.11	71.95	72.44	71.89	73.45	70.42	73.10	71.33	71.35	73.52	73.84
22	68.82	69.03	72.14	72.44	72.07	73.49	70.35	73.02	71.00	72.40	73.69	71.49
23	68.78	69.01	72.29	72.45	72.21	73.53	70.32	73.02	69.89	72.77	73.71	71.25
24	68.77	69.00	72.40	70.21	72.30	71.61	70.25	73.01	69.54	72.86	73.13	71.03
25	68.77	68.97	72.54	69.99	72.39	71.14	70.22	73.01	69.78	72.92	73.52	70.84
26	68.77	68.95	72.59	69.89	72.53	72.69	70.19	73.00	69.42	72.97	73.53	70.73
27	68.77	68.94	72.68	69.80	72.55	73.33	70.17	72.98	69.38	72.76	73.54	70.58
28	68.77	68.94	72.73	69.71	72.59	73.52	70.11	71.08	69.38	72.46	73.54	70.53
29	68.76	68.94	72.82	69.65	---	73.58	70.08	70.73	69.37	72.85	73.53	70.40
30	68.76	68.94	72.86	69.62	---	73.60	70.07	70.47	69.37	72.92	73.53	71.93
31	68.76	---	71.07	69.75	---	73.71	---	70.32	---	73.03	73.53	---
MEAN	69.26	68.95	70.43	71.69	70.48	73.04	71.79	72.56	69.72	72.04	73.48	72.80

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 71.37 HIGHEST 68.76 OCT. 29-1, NOV. 1, 2, 1997 LOWEST 73.84 SEPT. 21, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182330066185700. Local number, 213.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'30", long 66°18'57", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.82 mi southeast of Vega Alta plaza, 4.23 mi west of Toa Alta plaza, and 1.27 mi northwest off the intersection of Hwy 820 with Hwy 823. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Pampano No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Rio Indio Limestone-Lares Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-130 ft (0-39.6 m), diameter 14 in (0.36 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-220 ft (0-67.1 m); open hole 220-330 ft (67.6-101 m). Depth 330 ft (101 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 394 ft (120 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 9.32 ft (2.84 m), above land-surface datum. Prior April 27, 1993, hole on side of casing, 2.95 ft (0.90 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 17, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 34.40 ft (10.5 m), below land-surface datum, Dec. 6, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 65.68 ft (20.0 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 20, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	54.68	53.45	53.95	55.20	54.29	54.10	55.28	---	54.92	55.28	55.79	55.40
2	54.68	53.37	54.00	55.20	54.30	54.11	55.30	---	54.97	55.31	55.77	55.27
3	54.69	53.35	54.04	55.22	54.26	54.13	55.30	---	54.97	55.33	55.79	55.28
4	54.73	53.33	54.05	55.24	54.25	54.18	55.29	---	54.99	55.34	55.82	55.25
5	54.72	53.34	54.10	55.32	54.23	54.36	55.25	---	55.04	55.42	55.82	55.17
6	54.71	53.33	54.12	55.37	54.17	54.39	55.27	---	55.05	55.44	55.82	55.12
7	54.65	53.30	54.19	55.36	54.09	54.41	55.33	---	55.09	55.48	55.82	55.07
8	54.61	53.30	54.23	55.39	54.05	54.50	55.41	---	55.10	55.53	55.84	55.04
9	54.61	53.36	54.30	55.41	54.04	54.56	55.38	---	55.11	55.62	55.82	55.00
10	54.57	53.47	54.34	55.43	54.00	54.60	55.34	---	55.12	55.66	55.80	54.96
11	54.56	53.48	54.38	55.41	53.99	54.61	55.35	---	55.12	55.68	55.81	54.87
12	54.54	53.50	54.42	55.41	53.98	54.71	55.35	---	55.10	55.70	55.83	54.84
13	54.47	53.53	54.45	55.40	53.95	54.76	55.45	---	55.10	55.72	55.83	54.83
14	54.34	53.55	54.53	---	53.92	54.76	55.47	---	55.08	55.77	55.83	54.86
15	54.28	53.60	54.58	54.99	53.92	54.77	55.48	54.85	55.08	55.82	55.84	54.90
16	54.31	53.64	54.59	54.90	53.92	54.78	55.45	54.86	55.10	55.87	55.87	54.89
17	54.28	53.67	54.62	54.82	53.87	54.85	---	54.89	55.12	55.91	55.89	54.88
18	54.27	53.69	54.67	54.67	53.88	54.87	---	54.90	55.11	55.93	55.88	54.88
19	54.25	53.69	54.78	54.56	53.89	54.91	---	54.91	55.11	55.98	55.88	54.89
20	54.16	53.70	54.79	54.48	53.92	54.93	---	54.91	55.10	55.98	55.90	54.91
21	54.18	53.74	54.79	54.45	53.94	54.92	---	54.89	55.11	55.98	55.86	54.84
22	54.17	53.75	54.86	54.42	53.98	54.97	---	54.89	55.13	55.92	55.90	---
23	53.80	53.78	54.88	54.40	53.98	55.01	---	54.92	55.13	55.89	55.96	---
24	53.64	53.80	54.91	54.34	53.98	55.12	---	54.93	55.14	55.88	55.94	---
25	53.50	53.80	54.95	54.33	54.00	55.17	---	54.91	55.14	55.87	55.95	---
26	53.45	53.82	54.98	54.30	54.02	55.21	---	54.91	55.13	55.84	55.92	---
27	53.33	53.85	54.98	54.29	54.05	55.19	---	54.94	55.14	55.79	55.89	---
28	53.29	53.92	55.00	54.29	54.10	55.24	---	54.94	55.17	55.79	55.82	---
29	53.29	53.92	55.04	54.27	---	55.24	---	54.92	55.23	55.78	55.69	---
30	53.76	53.90	55.12	54.25	---	55.25	---	54.93	55.26	55.80	55.61	---
31	53.50	---	55.17	54.25	---	55.28	---	54.94	---	55.80	55.44	---
MEAN	54.19	53.60	54.57	54.85	54.03	54.77	55.36	54.91	55.10	55.71	55.83	55.01

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 54.80 HIGHEST 51.64 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 55.98 JULY 19, 20, 21, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182804066173500. Local number, DA-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°28'04", long 66°17'35", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.04 mi west of Dorado plaza, 1.15 mi north of Hwy 696, and 0.03 mi south of Hwy 693. Owner: Dorado Airport, Name: Dorado Airport Well.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m). Depth 98.0 ft (29.9 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 62.2 ft (18.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic survey.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.88 ft (1.18 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR) replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 21, 1997. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 2, 1995 to July 31, 1998, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 56.7 ft (17.3 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 11, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 59.2 ft (18.0 m), below land-surface datum Apr. 16, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	58.33	58.38	58.22	58.54	58.23	58.24	58.56	58.80	58.32	58.57	---	---
2	58.34	58.37	58.27	58.51	58.27	58.29	58.62	58.76	58.34	58.59	---	---
3	58.37	58.34	58.36	58.43	58.29	58.35	58.69	58.73	58.39	58.63	---	---
4	58.25	58.40	58.42	58.42	58.28	58.38	58.68	58.70	58.33	58.65	---	---
5	58.16	58.40	58.43	58.35	58.08	58.40	58.67	58.71	58.37	58.54	---	---
6	58.19	58.43	58.35	58.29	57.96	58.39	58.66	58.79	58.36	58.59	---	---
7	58.25	58.45	58.35	58.12	58.01	58.35	58.67	58.83	58.35	58.58	---	---
8	58.25	58.42	58.40	58.07	58.02	58.38	58.69	58.73	58.38	58.65	---	---
9	58.27	58.41	58.40	58.11	58.02	58.40	58.73	58.68	58.38	58.62	---	---
10	58.30	58.46	58.38	58.07	58.05	58.45	58.72	58.72	58.33	58.62	---	---
11	58.22	58.41	58.44	58.10	58.09	58.38	58.66	58.74	58.30	58.58	---	---
12	58.21	58.38	58.40	58.04	---	58.39	58.62	58.81	58.29	58.57	---	---
13	58.11	58.33	58.34	58.06	---	58.47	58.64	58.80	58.30	58.57	---	---
14	58.00	58.36	58.34	57.96	---	58.52	58.72	58.73	58.26	58.60	---	---
15	57.86	58.34	58.31	58.02	---	58.54	58.82	58.66	58.24	58.63	---	---
16	57.79	58.30	58.40	58.03	---	58.57	58.72	58.63	58.31	58.67	---	---
17	57.92	58.36	58.36	58.08	58.25	58.61	58.63	58.63	58.39	58.70	---	---
18	58.01	58.40	58.40	58.11	58.26	58.65	58.63	58.63	58.40	58.70	---	---
19	58.07	58.40	58.54	58.11	58.30	58.63	58.64	58.62	58.46	58.71	---	---
20	58.15	58.38	58.56	58.13	58.29	58.59	58.63	58.62	58.51	58.68	---	---
21	58.18	58.42	58.61	58.17	58.34	58.55	58.58	58.55	58.54	58.59	---	---
22	58.22	58.37	58.60	58.15	58.36	58.55	58.59	58.51	58.50	58.55	---	---
23	58.29	58.33	58.55	58.15	58.30	58.57	58.63	58.52	58.48	58.58	---	---
24	58.37	58.30	58.46	58.13	58.31	58.61	58.65	58.47	58.48	58.58	---	---
25	58.43	58.29	58.53	58.14	58.30	58.65	58.63	58.40	58.48	58.59	---	---
26	58.40	58.28	58.53	58.15	58.29	58.65	58.62	58.37	58.50	58.63	---	---
27	58.37	58.25	58.54	58.13	58.24	58.61	58.63	58.32	58.51	58.60	---	---
28	58.42	58.28	58.51	58.20	58.21	58.59	58.64	58.29	58.50	58.64	---	---
29	58.40	58.29	58.46	58.18	---	58.59	58.67	58.28	58.53	58.65	---	---
30	58.36	58.25	58.50	58.13	---	58.48	58.75	58.29	58.50	58.68	---	---
31	58.34	---	58.56	58.17	---	58.50	---	58.33	---	---	---	---
MEAN	58.22	58.36	58.44	58.17	58.21	58.49	58.66	58.60	58.40	58.62	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 58.42 HIGHEST 57.78 OCT. 16, 1997 LOWEST 58.90 APR. 30, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
 RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182526066165001. Local number, SR-2.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'26", long 66°16'50", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 1.03 mi north of Hwy 2, 0.93 mi west of the intersection of Hwy 659 with Hwy 693, and 0.03 mi north of Hwy 659. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Santa Rosa USGS No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-140 ft (0-42.7 m), screened 120-130 ft (36.6-39.6 m). Depth 140 ft (42.7 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 91.8 ft (28.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.31 ft (1.01 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed in February 6, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 2, 1995 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 60.4 ft (18.4 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 20, 1995; lowest water level recorded, 64.9 ft (19.8 m), below land-surface datum, May 2-5, 10-15, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 10	63.51	Jan. 27	63.37	Apr. 9	64.14	July 28	64.08
Nov. 17	63.64	Feb. 23	63.69	May 15	64.09	Sept. 2	64.05
Dec. 10	63.54	Mar. 13	63.99				

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182548066164401. Local number, MA-2
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'48", long 66°16'44", Hydrologic Unit 2101005, 1.47 mi north of Hwy 2, 0.60 mi south of Hwy 695, 0.04 mi south of the intersection of Hwy 694 with 659, and 0.02 mi east of Hwy 659. Owner: US Geological Survey
 WRD, Name: Maguayo USGS No. 2
 AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-110 ft (0-33.5 m), screened 95-105 ft (29.0-32.0 m). Depth 110 ft (33.5 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 39.4 ft (12.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.80 ft (1.16 m), above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 6, 1997.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 22, 1995 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 24.89 ft (7.59 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 18, 19, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 29.05 ft (8.85 m), below land-surface datum, July 20, 21, 22, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28.43	27.96	28.04	28.56	27.89	28.10	28.59	28.56	28.20	28.13	28.50	28.39
2	28.42	27.96	28.04	28.56	27.91	28.12	28.59	28.60	28.18	28.16	28.50	28.40
3	28.42	28.01	28.02	28.56	27.97	28.13	28.60	28.60	28.18	28.20	28.51	28.40
4	28.40	28.04	28.02	28.56	27.97	28.16	28.64	28.59	28.18	28.22	28.51	28.40
5	28.31	28.04	28.04	28.54	27.85	28.18	28.64	28.59	28.17	28.22	28.55	28.38
6	28.22	28.04	28.04	28.52	27.64	28.18	28.67	28.60	28.15	28.22	28.56	28.38
7	28.19	28.09	28.05	28.28	27.67	28.18	28.68	28.62	28.14	28.23	28.57	28.38
8	28.18	28.11	28.08	28.26	27.68	28.18	28.70	28.63	28.14	28.24	28.58	28.38
9	28.17	28.12	28.10	28.24	27.71	28.23	28.70	28.63	28.13	28.26	28.60	28.35
10	28.15	28.16	28.12	28.22	27.71	28.28	28.70	28.63	28.12	28.27	28.60	28.35
11	28.15	28.07	28.11	28.21	27.75	28.30	28.71	28.64	28.12	28.30	28.60	28.35
12	28.14	28.13	28.10	28.06	27.78	28.30	28.70	28.65	28.12	28.31	28.60	28.35
13	27.98	28.16	28.11	28.01	27.80	28.34	28.70	28.68	28.12	28.34	28.60	28.36
14	27.92	28.17	28.14	27.82	27.86	28.34	28.70	28.71	28.12	28.36	28.60	28.36
15	27.78	28.18	28.17	27.75	27.86	28.35	28.72	28.69	28.09	28.36	28.60	28.37
16	27.59	28.20	28.19	27.74	27.89	28.35	28.71	28.69	28.10	28.37	28.62	28.37
17	27.57	28.21	28.22	27.74	27.92	28.39	28.61	28.67	28.03	28.41	28.63	28.37
18	27.57	28.22	28.23	27.73	27.93	28.45	28.59	28.63	28.02	28.42	28.63	28.38
19	27.58	28.23	28.25	27.73	27.97	28.48	28.59	28.62	27.95	28.43	28.63	28.39
20	27.62	28.22	28.26	27.73	27.98	28.51	28.58	28.60	27.91	28.44	28.63	28.39
21	27.63	28.08	28.28	27.73	28.03	28.52	28.54	28.57	27.92	28.45	28.63	28.35
22	27.71	28.02	28.31	27.73	28.05	28.54	28.52	28.54	27.93	28.45	28.63	27.39
23	27.72	28.02	28.32	27.73	28.09	28.57	28.51	28.52	27.93	28.45	28.63	26.81
24	27.73	28.02	28.40	27.74	28.10	28.58	28.50	28.37	27.97	28.47	28.63	26.83
25	27.78	28.01	28.40	27.75	28.10	28.59	28.51	28.32	27.96	28.47	28.57	26.89
26	27.79	28.01	28.41	27.76	28.10	28.62	28.51	28.30	28.01	28.49	28.41	26.89
27	27.82	28.01	28.44	27.80	28.10	28.62	28.51	28.27	28.02	28.50	28.37	26.88
28	27.83	28.01	28.47	27.80	28.10	28.64	28.51	28.20	28.03	28.50	28.36	26.91
29	27.87	28.02	28.52	27.85	---	28.65	28.52	28.22	28.07	28.50	28.34	26.89
30	27.88	28.02	28.54	27.87	---	28.66	28.55	28.23	28.10	28.50	28.34	26.87
31	27.92	---	28.56	27.87	---	28.62	---	28.22	---	28.50	28.35	---
MEAN	27.95	28.08	28.23	28.01	27.91	28.39	28.61	28.53	28.07	28.36	28.54	27.94

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 28.22 HIGHEST 26.80 SEPT. 23, 1998 LOWEST 28.76 APR. 15, 16, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182620066163400. Local number, HG-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'20", long 66°16'34", Hydrologic Unit 2101005, 1.85 mi south of Dorado plaza, 0.70 mi southwest of Laboratorio Dorado, 0.65 mi northwest of the intersection of Hwy 695 with Hwy 693, and 0.09 mi north of Hwy 695.

Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Higuillar No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-490 ft (0-149.4 m), screened 470-480 ft (143.3-146.3 m). Depth 490 ft (149.4 m)

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 49.2 ft (15.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.60 ft (1.10 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 16, 1996, replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 23, 1998. Well screened below freshwater/saltwater interface at approximately 305 ft (93.0 m), below land-surface datum. From May 15, 1998, bi-monthly measurements only.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 16, 1996 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 36.04 ft (11.0 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 15, 16, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 39.89 ft (12.2 m), below land-surface datum, June 2, 3, 4, 9, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1995 TO SEPTEMBER 1996
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.88	39.83	39.61	39.31
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.88	39.81	39.61	39.31
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.88	39.81	39.60	39.33
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.87	39.79	39.59	39.32
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.85	39.81	39.57	39.22
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.79	39.80	39.57	39.22
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.80	39.77	39.56	39.23
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.83	39.62	39.55	39.24
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.84	39.45	39.57	39.16
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.84	39.53	39.57	37.72
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.84	39.56	39.56	36.39
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.87	39.63	39.58	36.37
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.87	39.67	39.57	36.28
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.86	39.68	39.62	36.18
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.85	39.57	39.57	36.12
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.70	39.85	39.39	39.46	36.07
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.70	39.78	39.46	39.33	36.08
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.68	39.69	39.51	39.34	36.11
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.67	39.61	39.52	39.37	36.12
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.68	39.57	39.55	39.37	36.20
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.70	39.60	39.59	39.37	36.30
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.70	39.64	39.62	39.38	36.36
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.75	39.66	39.64	39.43	36.46
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.75	39.68	39.66	39.27	36.50
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.76	39.66	39.65	39.30	36.58
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.75	39.68	39.59	39.35	36.62
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.75	39.72	39.62	39.37	36.68
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.75	39.72	39.64	39.35	36.70
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.77	39.76	39.64	39.31	36.77
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.79	39.78	39.64	39.30	36.82
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.87	---	39.63	39.31	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.74	39.77	39.63	39.46	37.29
WTR YR 1996	MEAN 39.13	HIGHEST 36.04	SEPT. 15, 16, 1996	LOWEST 39.89	JUNE 2, 3, 4, 9, 1996							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	36.84	37.52	36.75	36.96	36.40	36.79	37.41	37.89	38.25	38.62	38.79	38.49
2	36.89	37.55	36.77	36.95	36.42	36.80	37.46	37.95	38.26	38.64	38.78	38.47
3	36.94	37.56	36.76	36.90	36.43	36.81	37.40	38.00	38.27	38.67	38.78	38.45
4	37.02	37.57	36.81	36.86	36.49	36.82	37.41	37.97	38.28	38.68	38.77	38.43
5	37.06	37.58	36.84	36.85	36.51	36.83	37.45	38.03	38.29	38.70	38.78	38.44
6	37.09	37.60	36.84	36.87	36.53	36.84	37.49	38.05	38.33	38.68	38.74	38.43
7	37.14	37.61	36.88	36.88	36.55	36.89	37.54	38.08	38.35	38.68	38.78	38.41
8	37.21	37.56	36.95	36.90	36.55	36.92	37.54	38.10	38.35	38.69	38.77	38.39
9	37.29	37.53	37.01	36.89	36.57	36.93	37.50	38.10	38.39	38.67	38.79	38.41
10	37.31	37.53	37.05	36.88	36.55	36.95	37.56	38.00	38.40	38.69	38.80	38.39
11	37.32	37.54	37.06	36.89	36.54	36.95	37.57	38.04	38.36	38.70	38.76	38.42
12	37.35	37.54	37.01	36.89	36.58	36.96	37.58	38.06	38.40	38.71	38.77	38.43
13	37.35	37.36	37.01	36.91	36.58	36.97	37.61	38.11	38.43	38.68	38.75	38.43
14	37.40	37.24	37.04	36.93	36.61	36.98	37.62	38.12	38.44	38.72	38.77	38.42
15	37.44	37.19	37.07	36.96	36.61	36.99	37.67	38.14	38.44	38.76	38.80	38.42
16	37.48	37.23	37.05	36.97	36.68	37.00	37.67	38.15	38.47	38.77	38.82	38.42
17	37.51	37.26	37.07	36.98	36.70	37.05	37.66	38.18	38.49	38.79	38.78	38.40
18	37.55	37.27	37.12	37.03	36.75	37.09	37.70	38.18	38.53	38.82	38.70	38.41
19	37.59	37.24	37.15	37.09	36.77	37.09	37.77	38.21	38.55	38.83	38.68	38.41
20	37.63	37.27	37.19	37.12	36.80	37.09	37.78	38.24	38.52	38.83	38.68	38.40
21	37.65	37.30	37.23	37.11	36.81	37.15	37.82	38.25	38.54	38.81	38.67	38.41
22	37.71	37.30	37.26	36.82	36.81	37.16	37.83	38.27	38.55	38.79	38.67	38.40
23	37.73	37.16	37.29	36.63	36.82	37.19	37.84	38.30	38.55	38.81	38.54	38.38
24	37.79	37.09	37.30	36.50	36.81	37.22	37.87	38.29	38.52	38.81	38.52	38.37
25	37.79	36.90	37.28	36.40	36.77	37.28	37.90	38.18	38.52	38.77	38.46	38.35
26	37.79	36.87	37.28	36.38	36.79	37.30	37.92	38.14	38.53	38.75	38.46	38.37
27	37.73	36.87	37.16	36.39	36.79	37.30	37.91	38.10	38.54	38.77	38.47	38.38
28	37.75	36.82	37.13	36.38	36.79	37.31	37.91	38.12	38.56	38.83	38.48	38.39
29	37.73	36.82	37.11	36.40	---	37.34	37.91	38.16	38.59	38.85	38.50	38.39
30	37.60	36.81	37.03	36.40	---	37.34	37.93	38.19	38.61	38.83	38.54	38.41
31	37.52	---	37.00	36.39	---	37.38	---	38.23	---	38.82	38.52	---
MEAN	37.43	37.29	37.05	36.79	36.64	37.06	37.67	38.12	38.44	38.75	38.68	38.41
WTR YR 1997	MEAN 37.70	HIGHEST 36.33	JAN. 25, 26, 1997	LOWEST 38.86	JULY 29, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	38.39	37.94	37.95	38.42	37.86	37.90	38.26	---	---	---	---	---
2	38.39	37.94	37.95	38.39	37.87	37.91	38.30	---	---	---	---	---
3	38.39	37.96	37.93	38.37	37.87	37.92	38.32	---	---	---	---	---
4	38.34	37.95	37.92	38.35	37.86	37.98	38.37	---	---	---	---	---
5	38.21	37.94	37.93	38.32	37.72	38.00	38.36	---	---	---	---	---
6	38.12	37.95	37.92	38.28	37.34	37.98	38.41	---	---	---	---	---
7	38.09	37.97	37.94	38.11	37.45	37.98	38.48	---	---	---	---	---
8	38.09	37.98	37.97	38.03	37.52	38.02	38.48	---	---	---	---	---
9	38.09	37.98	37.99	38.02	37.59	38.05	38.45	---	---	---	---	---
10	38.08	38.07	38.00	38.02	37.62	38.09	38.44	---	---	---	---	---
11	38.08	37.89	38.00	38.00	37.68	38.08	38.46	---	---	---	---	---
12	38.04	38.00	38.02	37.91	37.70	38.13	38.45	---	---	---	---	---
13	37.88	38.06	38.04	37.87	37.72	38.16	38.48	---	---	---	---	---
14	37.82	38.08	38.05	37.68	37.77	38.14	38.47	---	---	---	---	---
15	37.69	38.10	38.09	37.60	37.75	38.12	38.46	---	---	---	---	---
16	37.47	38.11	38.09	37.62	37.76	38.15	38.44	---	---	---	---	---
17	37.45	38.11	38.12	37.61	37.76	38.18	38.25	---	---	---	---	---
18	37.44	38.11	38.12	37.60	37.80	38.23	38.21	---	---	---	---	---
19	37.46	38.08	38.13	37.63	37.82	38.23	38.21	---	---	---	---	---
20	37.52	38.06	38.15	37.63	37.84	38.26	38.20	---	---	---	---	---
21	37.55	37.96	38.15	37.65	37.90	38.23	38.19	---	---	---	---	---
22	37.64	37.85	38.20	37.66	37.92	38.27	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	37.66	37.85	38.21	37.68	37.92	38.31	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	37.68	37.85	38.27	37.69	37.94	38.33	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	37.74	37.86	38.28	37.73	37.95	38.39	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	37.77	37.87	38.30	37.74	37.94	38.42	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	37.81	37.88	38.30	37.77	37.93	38.42	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	37.84	37.91	38.36	37.81	37.91	38.43	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	37.87	37.92	38.42	37.84	---	38.40	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	37.87	37.92	38.44	37.84	---	38.36	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	37.89	---	38.45	37.83	---	38.29	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	37.88	37.97	38.12	37.89	37.78	38.17	38.37	---	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 38.01 HIGHEST 37.30 FEB. 6, 1998 LOWEST 38.50 APR. 7, 1998

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
May 15	38.37	July 28	38.25	Sept. 2	38.00

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182620066163403. Local number, HG-4.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'20", long 66°16'34", Hydrologic Unit 2101005, 1.85 mi south of Dorado plaza, 0.70 mi southwest of Laboratorio Dorado, 0.65 mi northwest of the intersection of Hwy 695 with Hwy 693, and 0.09 mi north of Hwy 695.

Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Higuillar No. 4.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-100 ft (0-30.5 m), screened 80-90.0 ft (24.4-27.4 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m)

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 49.2 ft (15.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.60 ft (1.10 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 6, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 23, 1995 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 31.84 ft (9.70 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 11, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 36.15 ft (11.0 m), below land-surface datum, May 1, 11, 13, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	35.09	34.67	34.90	35.24	34.60	34.80	35.25	35.15	34.85	34.74	35.14	35.00
2	35.08	34.68	34.90	35.24	34.69	34.80	35.26	35.16	34.85	34.76	35.14	35.00
3	35.06	34.76	34.90	35.24	34.70	34.81	35.26	35.15	34.85	34.89	35.15	35.00
4	35.01	34.76	34.90	35.24	34.70	34.82	35.27	35.15	34.85	34.89	35.15	35.00
5	34.85	34.77	34.90	35.23	34.69	34.97	35.28	35.15	34.86	34.88	35.16	34.99
6	34.81	34.77	34.90	35.17	34.39	34.97	35.28	35.14	34.86	34.89	35.22	34.99
7	34.80	34.78	34.90	34.89	34.39	34.97	35.29	35.14	34.86	34.89	35.22	34.99
8	34.78	34.79	34.90	34.89	34.40	34.97	35.31	35.14	34.86	34.90	35.23	34.99
9	34.76	34.79	34.90	34.89	34.41	34.99	35.33	35.13	34.86	34.90	35.23	34.99
10	34.75	34.81	34.90	34.89	34.41	34.99	35.34	35.13	34.86	34.90	35.23	34.99
11	34.74	34.77	34.90	34.89	34.43	34.99	35.33	35.22	34.86	34.90	35.24	34.99
12	34.75	34.79	34.90	34.89	34.45	35.00	35.33	35.22	34.86	34.90	35.24	34.98
13	34.57	34.82	34.90	34.89	34.46	35.01	35.32	35.23	34.87	34.91	35.25	34.99
14	34.58	34.82	34.90	34.36	34.52	35.01	35.32	35.22	34.87	34.92	35.25	34.99
15	34.32	34.85	34.90	34.33	34.53	35.02	35.32	35.22	34.87	34.94	35.26	34.99
16	34.30	34.86	34.91	34.33	34.53	35.05	35.30	35.22	34.87	35.06	35.26	34.99
17	34.30	34.91	34.91	34.34	34.56	35.05	35.20	35.22	34.60	35.06	35.26	34.99
18	34.30	34.92	34.91	34.34	34.68	35.07	35.20	35.22	34.60	35.06	35.27	34.99
19	34.30	34.91	34.91	34.35	34.75	35.07	35.19	35.22	34.57	35.06	35.27	34.99
20	34.31	34.91	34.91	34.36	34.75	35.15	35.19	35.22	34.57	35.06	35.28	34.99
21	34.32	34.91	34.91	34.36	34.75	35.16	35.19	35.22	34.58	35.06	35.28	34.98
22	34.34	34.90	34.93	34.36	34.76	35.16	35.18	35.13	34.61	35.06	35.28	33.04
23	34.35	34.90	34.93	34.36	34.78	35.22	35.03	35.11	34.61	35.06	35.29	32.49
24	34.35	34.90	35.06	34.37	34.78	35.24	35.03	34.87	34.62	35.07	35.29	33.09
25	34.39	34.90	35.06	34.37	34.79	35.24	35.02	34.85	34.62	35.07	35.08	33.26
26	34.39	34.90	35.06	34.38	34.79	35.24	35.02	34.85	34.62	35.09	34.95	33.45
27	34.50	34.90	35.06	34.40	34.79	35.25	35.01	34.84	34.70	35.12	34.96	33.45
28	34.52	34.90	35.09	34.43	34.79	35.25	35.01	34.85	34.70	35.12	34.96	33.55
29	34.53	34.90	35.18	34.55	---	35.25	35.01	34.85	34.71	35.12	34.96	33.55
30	34.53	34.90	35.20	34.60	---	35.26	35.14	34.85	34.72	35.13	34.98	33.54
31	34.55	---	35.25	34.60	---	35.25	---	34.85	---	35.13	34.98	---
MEAN	34.59	34.84	34.96	34.67	34.62	35.07	35.21	35.09	34.75	34.99	35.18	34.47

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 34.87 HIGHEST 32.48 SEPT. 23, 1998 LOWEST 35.34 APR. 9, 10, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182657066162700. Local number, SA-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'57", long 66°16'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 1.16 mi south of Dorado plaza, 0.45 mi west of Laboratorio Dorado, 1.79 mi southeast of Dorado airport main gate, and 0.19 mi west of the PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority San Antonio public supply well (San Antonio No. 3). Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: San Antonio No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-290 ft (0-88.4 m), screened 270-280 ft (82.3-85.3 m). Depth 290 ft (88.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 19.6 ft (6.00 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m), casing, 3.20 ft (0.98 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 21, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 19, 1994 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 13.97 ft (4.26 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 11, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 19.56 ft (5.96 m), below land-surface datum, May 3, 4, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17.71	17.34	17.29	17.68	17.04	17.21	17.62	17.78	17.41	17.32	---	---
2	17.70	17.35	17.29	17.69	17.04	17.21	17.63	17.78	17.41	17.32	---	---
3	17.72	17.36	17.29	17.68	17.05	17.23	17.64	17.78	17.41	17.32	---	---
4	17.63	17.35	17.29	17.66	17.05	17.25	17.64	17.78	17.38	17.50	---	---
5	17.48	17.36	17.29	17.67	17.04	17.29	17.71	17.78	17.39	17.49	---	---
6	17.40	17.40	17.30	17.57	16.57	17.29	17.71	17.72	17.38	17.50	---	---
7	17.41	17.42	17.32	17.25	16.57	17.29	17.74	17.78	17.38	17.53	---	---
8	17.42	17.41	17.37	17.12	16.76	17.28	17.75	17.80	17.37	17.53	---	---
9	17.42	17.43	17.37	17.13	16.76	17.28	17.75	17.77	17.34	17.53	---	---
10	17.43	17.46	17.37	17.13	16.76	17.28	17.76	17.76	17.28	17.54	---	---
11	17.40	17.29	17.37	17.13	16.85	17.29	17.79	17.77	17.27	17.54	---	---
12	17.36	17.42	17.38	17.13	16.86	17.34	17.80	17.77	17.27	17.54	---	---
13	17.18	17.46	17.38	17.02	16.96	17.34	17.80	17.82	17.27	17.55	---	---
14	17.10	17.48	17.38	16.89	16.99	17.34	17.81	17.82	17.25	17.55	---	---
15	16.92	17.52	17.38	16.89	17.01	17.40	17.81	17.83	17.26	17.55	---	---
16	16.68	17.51	17.38	16.89	17.03	17.44	17.82	17.75	17.26	17.59	---	---
17	16.77	17.53	17.41	16.85	17.07	17.45	17.82	17.74	17.25	17.61	---	---
18	16.80	17.57	17.43	16.85	17.07	17.48	17.71	17.69	17.21	17.62	---	---
19	16.88	17.52	17.49	16.85	17.07	17.51	17.72	17.69	17.21	17.63	---	---
20	16.97	17.51	17.49	16.85	17.09	17.53	17.72	17.69	17.17	17.65	---	---
21	17.01	17.36	17.50	16.86	17.09	17.53	17.72	17.68	17.18	17.67	---	---
22	17.08	17.35	17.56	16.87	17.15	17.53	17.70	17.68	17.18	17.67	---	---
23	17.11	17.35	17.57	16.88	17.16	17.52	17.70	17.68	17.18	17.67	---	---
24	17.15	17.34	17.60	16.89	17.18	17.52	17.70	17.48	17.20	17.67	---	---
25	17.20	17.34	17.60	16.90	17.21	17.61	17.72	17.49	17.22	17.68	---	---
26	17.21	17.29	17.60	16.90	17.21	17.65	17.71	17.49	17.26	17.69	---	---
27	17.22	17.29	17.60	16.92	17.21	17.65	17.71	17.41	17.26	17.72	---	---
28	17.21	17.29	17.62	16.92	17.21	17.65	17.72	17.41	17.31	17.73	---	---
29	17.22	17.29	17.65	16.93	---	17.64	17.73	17.41	17.31	17.73	---	---
30	17.22	17.28	17.65	17.04	---	17.64	17.73	17.41	17.31	17.73	---	---
31	17.23	---	17.66	17.04	---	17.63	---	17.41	---	17.73	---	---
MEAN	17.23	17.40	17.45	17.10	17.00	17.43	17.73	17.67	17.29	17.58	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 17.47 HIGHEST 16.57 FEB. 6, 7, 1998 LOWEST 17.73 JULY 28-30, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182657066162701. Local number, SA-3.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'57", long 66°16'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 20 ft north of San Antonio USGS # 1. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: San Antonio No. 3.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-80.0 ft (0-24.4 m), screened 65-75.0 ft (19.8-22.9 m). Depth 80.0 ft (24.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 19.6 ft (6.00 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m), casing, 3.38 ft (1.03 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 6, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 19, 1994 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 13.95 ft (4.25 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 11, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 19.03 ft (5.80 m), below land-surface datum, May 13, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17.81	17.44	17.45	17.94	17.33	17.46	17.87	18.01	17.57	17.68	18.01	17.77
2	17.79	17.45	17.48	17.92	17.35	17.49	17.92	18.03	17.58	17.70	18.02	17.79
3	17.81	17.46	17.51	17.89	17.37	17.52	17.97	18.00	17.58	17.73	18.03	17.79
4	17.72	17.45	17.53	17.88	17.38	17.58	18.00	18.00	17.56	17.68	18.07	17.78
5	17.57	17.46	17.56	17.76	17.10	17.60	18.01	17.91	17.56	17.68	18.10	17.71
6	17.50	17.52	17.55	17.71	16.71	17.58	18.02	18.01	17.52	17.73	18.09	17.73
7	17.53	17.54	17.54	17.34	16.89	17.58	18.04	18.08	17.51	17.72	18.09	17.61
8	17.54	17.52	17.57	17.34	17.04	17.58	18.02	18.04	17.52	17.76	18.07	17.60
9	17.54	17.54	17.59	17.35	17.08	17.62	18.05	17.95	17.47	17.78	18.05	17.57
10	17.56	17.57	17.59	17.36	17.11	17.67	18.07	18.01	17.41	17.80	18.03	17.62
11	17.51	17.40	17.59	17.38	17.16	17.66	18.07	18.04	17.40	17.81	18.00	17.66
12	17.46	17.52	17.60	17.24	17.20	17.66	18.05	18.06	17.41	17.81	17.98	17.68
13	17.29	17.55	17.60	17.23	17.24	17.69	18.06	18.07	17.44	17.84	17.98	17.71
14	17.19	17.57	17.61	17.01	17.27	17.74	18.08	18.08	17.38	17.87	18.01	17.72
15	17.03	17.61	17.63	17.00	17.25	17.75	18.10	17.99	17.37	17.87	18.04	17.76
16	16.78	17.60	17.67	17.04	17.28	17.78	17.97	17.96	17.44	17.90	18.06	17.75
17	16.87	17.63	17.68	17.08	17.31	17.83	17.86	17.91	17.35	17.92	18.07	17.74
18	16.90	17.65	17.70	17.08	17.32	17.87	17.87	17.88	17.33	17.94	18.02	17.76
19	16.99	17.59	17.76	17.09	17.37	17.87	17.89	17.88	17.28	17.93	17.99	17.71
20	17.08	17.59	17.78	17.11	17.39	17.87	17.90	17.87	17.41	17.93	17.92	17.74
21	17.13	17.42	17.78	17.12	17.42	17.87	17.85	17.78	17.45	17.85	17.91	17.49
22	17.19	17.35	17.79	17.13	17.43	17.87	17.83	17.77	17.44	17.85	17.95	15.13
23	17.22	17.36	17.81	17.15	17.44	17.91	17.86	17.79	17.45	17.90	17.95	14.90
24	17.26	17.37	17.83	17.13	17.46	17.94	17.89	17.64	17.48	17.91	17.93	15.74
25	17.33	17.37	17.84	17.16	17.47	17.97	17.88	17.62	17.49	17.93	17.72	15.95
26	17.33	17.39	17.86	17.17	17.44	18.00	17.86	17.60	17.50	17.96	17.58	16.22
27	17.35	17.39	17.87	17.20	17.33	17.97	17.87	17.53	17.54	17.97	17.57	16.26
28	17.36	17.41	17.88	17.25	17.44	17.97	17.88	17.50	17.54	18.00	17.62	16.41
29	17.36	17.43	17.89	17.28	---	17.97	17.94	17.51	17.59	18.00	17.57	16.39
30	17.34	17.44	17.91	17.32	---	17.90	18.01	17.55	17.63	18.03	17.68	16.28
31	17.37	---	17.94	17.32	---	17.88	---	17.57	---	18.02	17.73	---
MEAN	17.35	17.49	17.69	17.32	17.27	17.76	17.96	17.86	17.47	17.85	17.93	17.17
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 17.60	HIGHEST 14.51	SEPT. 22, 23, 1998	LOWEST 18.13	APR. 15, MAY 13, 1998							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182654066150600. Local number, TB-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'54", long 66°15'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.92 mi southeast of the Dorado bridge, 0.66 mi east of Hwy 693, 0.09 mi north of the intersection of Hwy 165 with Hwy 867, and 0.01 mi east of Hwy 165. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Toa Baja TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Tertiary Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-165 ft (0-50.3 m), screened 25-165 ft (7.62-50.3 m). Depth 167 ft (50.9 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 7.00 ft (2.10 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.60 ft (1.10 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 25, 1997. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- November 16, 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.04 ft (0.93 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 10, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 10.68 ft (3.25 m), below land-surface datum May 3, 4, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.95	9.79	9.58	9.96	9.69	9.70	10.05	---	---	---	10.19	9.90
2	9.80	9.75	9.69	9.92	9.76	9.79	10.18	---	---	---	10.24	9.90
3	9.87	9.76	9.78	9.83	9.78	9.82	10.30	---	---	---	10.23	9.85
4	9.76	9.74	9.76	9.89	9.78	9.91	10.22	---	---	---	10.33	9.83
5	9.52	9.75	9.83	9.80	9.32	9.92	10.31	---	---	---	10.31	9.55
6	9.58	9.75	9.81	9.72	9.05	9.85	10.26	---	---	---	10.19	9.63
7	9.66	9.78	9.81	9.31	9.33	9.79	10.32	---	---	---	10.18	9.43
8	9.70	9.80	9.92	9.36	9.37	9.83	10.24	---	---	---	10.18	9.43
9	9.78	9.81	9.90	9.43	9.36	9.93	10.31	---	---	---	10.09	9.39
10	9.76	9.89	9.88	9.45	9.42	9.97	10.34	---	---	---	9.94	9.51
11	9.65	9.74	9.86	9.49	9.49	9.90	10.27	---	---	---	9.96	9.52
12	9.63	9.83	9.85	9.38	9.53	9.88	10.24	---	---	---	9.89	9.60
13	9.43	9.79	9.76	9.47	9.58	9.93	10.24	---	---	---	9.88	9.57
14	9.31	9.79	9.78	9.17	9.58	10.03	10.30	---	---	---	10.00	9.68
15	9.06	9.81	9.76	9.35	9.55	10.03	10.35	---	---	---	10.07	9.77
16	8.84	9.72	9.80	9.41	9.62	10.10	10.17	---	---	---	10.12	9.73
17	9.13	9.76	9.71	9.50	9.69	10.16	10.06	---	---	---	10.06	9.70
18	9.23	9.77	9.89	9.53	9.72	10.20	10.12	---	---	---	9.96	9.70
19	9.34	9.72	10.05	9.58	9.76	10.14	10.17	---	---	---	9.99	9.52
20	9.48	9.74	10.06	9.59	9.73	10.12	---	---	---	---	9.98	9.50
21	9.59	9.54	10.09	9.60	9.78	10.11	---	---	---	---	9.77	9.03
22	9.65	9.54	10.06	9.60	9.80	10.14	---	---	---	---	9.83	4.27
23	9.70	9.60	9.97	9.62	9.77	10.19	---	---	---	---	9.82	4.68
24	9.73	9.61	10.00	9.56	9.79	10.24	---	---	---	---	9.68	4.70
25	9.82	9.61	9.98	9.62	9.74	10.28	---	---	---	---	9.39	7.95
26	9.80	9.64	10.00	9.55	9.71	10.20	---	---	---	---	9.50	8.35
27	9.76	9.64	10.02	9.61	9.60	10.17	---	---	---	---	9.50	8.48
28	9.77	9.68	9.98	9.66	9.66	10.12	---	---	---	---	9.55	8.61
29	9.76	9.66	9.90	9.67	---	10.11	---	---	---	---	9.59	8.65
30	9.74	9.62	9.94	9.63	---	9.92	---	---	---	---	9.75	8.65
31	9.73	---	9.95	9.67	---	9.99	---	---	---	10.16	9.79	---
MEAN	9.60	9.72	9.88	9.58	9.61	10.02	10.23	---	---	10.16	9.93	8.87

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 9.70 HIGHEST 4.04 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 10.42 APR. 15, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182530066135400. Local number, 216.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'30", long 66°13'54", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.61 mi northeast of Toa Alta plaza, 2.73 mi southwest of Sabana Seca U.S. Naval Radio Station, and 1.76 mi southeast of Hwy 2 km 17.7. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Pozo Navy-Campanillas.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m) 0-106 ft (0-32.3 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-106 ft (0-32.3 m), perforated 20-106 ft (6.10-32.3 m), diameter 10 in (0.25 m) 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m), perforated 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m). Depth 140 ft (42.7 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 13.0 ft (3.96 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 6, 1998. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.38 ft (2.86 m), below land-surface datum, June 23, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 18.40 ft (5.61 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 24, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14.52	14.84	14.57	16.16	16.31	14.63	15.90	15.73	15.30	14.74	15.81	15.04
2	15.00	14.86	14.55	16.33	16.14	14.66	15.86	15.83	15.37	14.69	15.70	15.07
3	14.98	14.93	14.54	15.86	16.18	14.66	15.93	15.85	15.41	14.71	15.81	15.07
4	15.09	14.76	14.60	15.79	16.13	14.71	15.97	15.89	14.33	14.66	15.90	15.06
5	14.87	14.82	14.49	15.80	14.34	14.82	15.98	15.82	14.77	14.60	15.93	14.97
6	14.71	14.82	14.47	15.45	14.26	14.77	15.81	15.87	15.16	14.64	15.88	14.98
7	14.70	14.81	14.49	15.47	14.28	14.80	15.88	15.99	15.28	14.63	15.95	14.51
8	14.77	14.39	14.51	15.47	14.26	14.80	15.88	16.05	15.33	14.62	15.98	14.74
9	14.77	14.12	14.47	15.46	14.22	14.86	15.96	15.99	15.38	14.68	16.05	14.71
10	14.83	14.15	14.65	15.59	14.30	14.92	15.92	16.19	15.30	14.77	15.84	14.81
11	14.89	14.69	14.71	15.66	14.37	14.92	15.93	16.13	15.31	14.77	15.70	14.89
12	14.59	14.81	14.67	15.64	14.44	14.80	15.90	16.19	15.37	14.64	13.85	14.91
13	14.29	14.85	14.77	15.55	14.46	14.87	15.86	16.16	15.45	14.68	13.93	14.93
14	14.29	14.96	14.83	15.58	14.46	14.87	15.60	16.34	15.41	14.52	14.03	14.93
15	14.32	15.08	14.84	15.76	14.40	15.88	14.97	16.05	15.27	14.45	14.50	14.87
16	14.20	14.98	14.88	15.76	14.40	15.95	14.19	16.00	15.27	14.46	15.07	14.92
17	14.19	14.92	14.93	15.94	14.40	15.02	14.88	15.89	14.88	14.47	15.06	14.90
18	14.26	14.95	14.92	15.89	14.40	15.98	15.11	15.53	14.89	14.69	14.14	14.91
19	14.27	14.88	15.01	15.93	14.43	15.96	15.10	15.32	14.86	14.72	14.43	14.95
20	14.37	14.77	14.84	15.91	14.43	16.00	15.14	15.25	14.92	14.79	14.71	15.01
21	14.38	14.44	15.19	15.94	14.46	16.10	15.09	15.07	14.94	14.80	14.88	14.85
22	14.42	14.37	15.16	15.94	14.50	16.10	15.09	15.21	14.98	14.93	14.86	10.85
23	14.45	14.44	15.44	15.96	14.45	16.19	15.12	15.51	14.84	15.14	15.15	10.37
24	14.52	14.38	15.69	16.14	14.60	16.19	15.19	15.14	14.85	15.26	15.12	10.52
25	14.64	14.41	15.66	16.20	14.74	16.16	15.22	15.35	14.80	15.39	14.94	10.56
26	14.62	14.46	15.62	16.16	14.79	16.16	15.19	15.19	14.80	15.67	14.92	10.62
27	14.26	14.46	15.72	16.21	14.62	16.16	15.15	15.25	14.84	15.63	14.84	10.65
28	14.69	14.46	15.73	16.29	14.64	16.22	15.19	15.16	14.87	15.77	14.88	10.67
29	14.72	14.50	15.76	16.30	---	16.25	15.54	15.19	14.88	15.76	14.95	10.69
30	14.79	14.57	15.68	16.28	---	16.04	15.65	15.19	14.92	15.77	15.02	10.70
31	14.79	---	16.45	16.32	---	15.90	---	15.25	---	15.76	14.97	---
MEAN	14.59	14.66	15.03	15.89	14.69	15.46	15.47	15.66	15.07	14.93	15.12	13.62

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 15.02 HIGHEST 10.36 SEPT. 23, 1998 LOWEST 16.45 DEC. 31, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182655066142400. Local number, 217.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'55", long 66°14'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 4.00 mi northeast of Toa Alta plaza, 3.40 mi northwest of Hwy 2 km 17.7, and 3.49 mi northwest of Sabana Seca US Naval Radio Station. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Monserrate TW-2.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial Deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-80.0 ft (0-24.4 m), perforated 10-80 ft (3.05-24.4 m). Depth 80.0 ft (24.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 3.30 ft (1.00 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.50 ft (1.07 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on November 6, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 0.02 ft (0.006 m), below land-surface datum, May 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 3.72 ft (1.13 m), below land-surface datum, May 13, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2.56	2.53	2.37	2.97	2.85	2.65	3.08	3.16	2.73	3.03	---	---
2	2.48	2.57	2.53	2.97	2.91	2.77	3.14	3.19	2.77	3.07	---	---
3	2.48	2.60	2.55	2.79	2.88	2.79	3.21	3.05	2.77	3.15	---	---
4	2.44	2.61	2.59	2.75	2.89	2.74	3.22	3.21	2.59	2.94	---	---
5	2.17	2.62	2.57	2.77	2.38	---	3.24	3.19	2.61	2.73	---	---
6	2.17	2.61	2.60	2.55	2.15	---	3.32	3.43	2.71	2.98	---	---
7	2.28	2.63	2.53	2.16	2.20	---	3.39	3.45	2.68	2.90	---	---
8	2.30	2.62	2.67	2.14	2.27	---	3.26	3.33	2.73	3.05	---	---
9	2.33	2.57	2.59	2.27	2.28	---	3.20	3.43	2.76	3.03	---	---
10	2.33	2.58	2.56	2.28	2.29	---	3.20	3.43	2.47	3.16	---	---
11	2.27	2.57	2.62	2.29	2.30	---	3.17	3.60	2.45	3.15	---	---
12	2.15	2.61	2.66	2.31	2.31	---	3.12	3.51	2.75	3.10	---	---
13	1.95	2.61	2.74	2.30	2.32	---	3.14	3.56	2.91	3.14	---	---
14	1.91	2.67	2.64	2.16	2.32	---	3.18	3.54	2.68	3.15	---	---
15	1.82	2.71	2.66	2.30	2.32	---	3.20	3.19	2.49	3.05	---	---
16	1.71	2.62	2.65	2.30	2.33	---	2.95	3.20	2.83	3.13	---	---
17	1.82	2.63	2.61	2.30	2.34	---	2.78	3.10	2.72	3.15	---	---
18	1.94	2.66	2.64	2.31	2.35	---	2.82	2.90	2.72	3.14	---	---
19	2.05	2.56	2.90	2.30	2.84	---	3.03	2.88	2.70	3.15	---	---
20	2.15	2.54	2.79	2.30	2.76	---	3.00	2.91	2.85	3.21	---	---
21	2.22	2.34	2.78	2.30	2.73	---	2.82	2.81	2.81	2.76	---	---
22	2.29	2.25	2.96	2.66	2.63	---	2.83	2.80	2.49	2.71	---	---
23	2.33	2.26	2.83	2.71	2.65	3.14	2.90	2.85	2.73	2.96	---	---
24	2.36	2.26	2.74	2.63	2.69	3.22	2.87	2.59	2.68	3.07	---	---
25	2.39	2.26	2.81	2.81	2.65	3.21	3.03	2.65	2.74	3.15	---	---
26	2.40	2.33	2.81	2.73	2.67	3.16	2.99	2.67	2.60	3.31	---	---
27	2.40	2.37	2.82	2.72	2.59	3.12	2.87	2.53	2.61	3.15	---	---
28	2.53	2.37	2.86	2.87	2.64	3.12	3.05	2.52	2.76	3.32	---	---
29	2.47	2.36	2.94	2.87	---	3.14	3.13	2.59	2.74	3.33	---	---
30	2.51	2.36	2.85	2.83	---	3.14	3.18	2.64	2.76	3.37	---	---
31	2.51	---	2.94	2.82	---	3.04	---	2.71	---	---	---	---
MEAN	2.25	2.51	2.70	2.53	2.52	3.02	3.08	3.05	2.69	3.08	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 2.73 HIGHEST 1.71 OCT. 16, 1997 LOWEST 3.64 MAY 11, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182441066082600. Local number, 219.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°08'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.47 mi west of Fort Buchanan Military Res. main gate, 1.74 mi northeast of Bayamón plaza, and 1.88 mi southwest of PR National Cemetery. Owner: US Department of Defense, Name: Buchanan Park No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 10 in (0.25 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 0-270 ft (0-82.3 m), perforated 46-685 ft (14.0-20.7 m), 88-120 ft (26.8-36.6 m), 160-191 ft (48.8-58.2 m), 240-270 ft (73.2-82.3 m). Depth 270 ft (82.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 66.0 ft (20.1 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.75 ft (0.23 m), above land-surface datum. Prior June 30, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.59 ft (1.09 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on January 28, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 34.9 ft (10.7 m), below land-surface datum, Nov. 12, 13, 14, 1989; lowest water level recorded, 55.67 ft (17.0 m), below land-surface datum, May 13, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	47.97	47.48	47.42	48.56	48.32	48.38	48.55	48.57	---	47.50	---	---
2	47.90	47.57	47.48	48.53	48.35	48.40	48.45	48.60	---	47.53	---	---
3	47.77	47.62	47.40	48.61	48.34	48.43	48.56	48.63	---	47.54	---	---
4	47.72	47.53	47.37	48.63	48.33	48.51	48.42	48.68	---	47.54	---	---
5	47.78	47.42	47.41	48.55	48.27	48.54	48.36	48.71	---	47.61	---	---
6	47.62	47.51	47.45	48.50	48.22	48.60	48.38	48.72	---	47.63	---	---
7	47.44	47.56	47.54	48.36	48.08	48.55	48.47	48.75	---	47.64	---	---
8	47.47	47.59	47.54	48.26	48.05	48.49	48.57	48.76	---	47.67	---	---
9	47.51	47.65	47.49	48.17	48.03	48.33	48.57	48.83	---	47.71	---	---
10	47.50	47.58	47.54	48.11	48.06	48.26	48.54	48.79	---	47.72	---	---
11	47.48	48.11	47.65	48.04	48.08	48.19	48.54	48.76	---	47.74	---	---
12	47.38	47.89	47.72	48.04	48.08	48.19	48.52	48.78	---	47.75	---	---
13	47.15	47.69	47.70	48.07	48.07	48.22	48.64	48.80	---	47.77	---	---
14	46.91	47.67	47.57	48.05	48.04	48.21	48.67	48.77	---	47.80	---	---
15	46.78	47.77	47.58	48.02	48.03	48.17	48.65	---	---	47.73	---	---
16	46.95	47.78	47.62	48.06	48.02	48.16	48.60	---	---	47.59	---	---
17	46.91	47.64	47.69	48.08	47.95	48.17	48.59	---	---	47.40	---	---
18	46.97	47.62	47.75	48.17	47.99	48.22	48.52	---	---	47.24	---	---
19	46.67	47.66	47.83	---	47.99	48.24	48.43	---	---	47.16	---	---
20	46.60	47.58	47.89	---	48.02	48.25	48.46	---	---	47.07	---	---
21	47.00	47.35	47.92	---	48.16	48.21	48.45	---	---	47.47	---	---
22	46.89	47.26	48.14	---	48.25	48.26	48.46	---	---	46.95	---	---
23	46.95	47.47	48.08	---	48.17	48.29	48.45	---	---	46.80	---	---
24	46.95	47.44	48.30	---	48.23	48.32	48.47	---	47.32	46.76	---	---
25	47.01	47.41	48.23	---	48.26	48.55	48.52	---	47.28	46.77	---	---
26	47.07	47.44	48.32	---	48.26	48.56	48.53	---	47.28	46.76	---	---
27	47.08	47.39	48.40	---	48.31	48.49	48.51	---	47.29	46.70	---	---
28	47.21	47.44	48.47	48.23	48.37	48.45	48.50	---	47.36	46.73	---	---
29	47.31	47.44	48.43	48.25	---	48.44	48.56	---	47.40	46.75	---	---
30	47.39	47.41	48.47	48.26	---	48.41	48.56	---	47.44	46.77	---	---
31	47.40	---	48.64	48.27	---	48.40	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	47.25	47.57	47.84	48.26	48.15	48.35	48.52	48.73	47.34	47.33	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 47.92 HIGHEST 46.55 OCT. 15, 1997 LOWEST 48.83 MAY 10, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182531066075900. Local number, 652.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'31", long 66°07'59", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.07 mi north of Hwy 22, 0.32 mi southwest of the intersection of Hwy 165 with Hwy 28, and 1.40 mi south of the Cataño ferry building. Owner: US Geological Survey,

WRD, Name: USGS Building 652.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 4.0 in (0.10 m), cased 0-192 ft (0-58.5 m). Depth 192 ft (58.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Pressure transducer with integrated electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of the 4.0 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.27 ft (1.00 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on May 14, 1997. Water level affected by marine tides.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 14, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 6.20 ft (1.89 m), below land-surface datum, May 26, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 9.02 ft (2.75 m), below land-surface datum, Dec. 13, 14, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.64	8.70	8.18	7.96
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.67	8.63	7.83	7.90
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.60	8.62	7.61	7.59
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.50	8.40	7.52	7.17
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.40	8.39	7.59	7.03
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.43	8.09	7.71	6.97
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.33	8.19	7.80	7.00
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.35	7.99	7.80	7.14
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.42	7.95	7.90	7.39
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.39	8.00	7.98	7.75
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.44	8.13	7.93	8.02
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.46	8.21	8.13	8.17
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.51	8.21	8.15	8.10
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.56	8.27	8.32	8.22
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.81	8.68	8.43	8.31	7.81
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.77	8.69	8.46	8.39	7.88
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.68	8.81	8.47	8.19	7.68
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.86	8.91	8.31	7.94	7.53
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.81	8.80	8.11	7.36	7.55
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.75	8.56	7.90	7.15	7.63
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.62	8.30	7.55	7.06	7.69
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.36	8.08	7.49	7.39	7.82
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.29	7.91	7.47	7.67	7.83
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.21	7.81	7.61	7.70	7.98
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.13	7.84	7.72	7.93	7.89
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.06	7.98	7.72	8.13	7.91
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.11	7.98	7.97	8.26	7.90
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.19	8.29	8.26	8.33	7.81
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.37	8.50	8.32	8.32	7.74
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.54	8.64	8.38	8.23	7.66
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.64	---	8.20	8.05	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.48	8.42	8.13	7.90	7.69

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 8.09 HIGHEST 6.96 SEPT. 6, 7, 1997 LOWEST 8.95 JUNE 18, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.54	7.51	7.41	7.78	7.63	7.38	7.57	---	7.33	---	---	---
2	7.39	7.50	7.26	7.81	7.80	7.53	7.55	---	---	---	---	---
3	7.26	7.60	7.37	7.89	7.97	7.81	8.00	---	---	---	---	---
4	7.06	7.72	7.69	7.95	7.93	7.89	8.12	---	---	---	---	---
5	6.99	7.76	7.82	8.01	7.67	7.85	7.98	---	---	---	---	---
6	7.14	7.80	7.81	7.80	7.44	7.84	7.86	---	---	---	---	---
7	7.25	7.91	7.96	7.83	7.98	8.02	7.98	---	---	---	---	---
8	7.26	7.98	8.25	7.67	7.60	7.94	8.01	---	---	---	---	---
9	7.45	8.12	8.26	7.41	7.14	7.82	8.17	---	---	---	---	---
10	7.66	8.26	8.31	7.10	7.21	7.55	8.04	---	---	---	---	---
11	7.84	8.14	8.23	7.12	7.35	7.51	8.00	---	---	---	---	---
12	7.79	7.95	8.12	7.01	7.48	7.44	7.82	---	---	---	---	---
13	7.74	7.82	7.90	6.74	7.53	7.48	7.99	---	---	---	---	---
14	7.04	7.69	7.78	7.02	7.50	7.66	8.04	---	---	---	---	---
15	7.18	7.54	7.66	7.02	7.26	7.71	8.01	---	---	---	---	---
16	6.88	7.43	7.75	7.16	7.53	7.62	8.00	---	---	---	---	---
17	7.16	7.37	7.72	7.31	7.70	7.65	7.68	---	---	---	---	---
18	7.03	7.53	7.90	7.37	7.84	7.84	7.84	---	---	---	---	---
19	7.11	7.53	8.17	7.41	7.88	7.89	7.77	---	---	---	---	---
20	7.29	7.65	8.25	7.51	7.95	7.97	7.83	---	---	---	---	---
21	7.46	7.60	8.31	7.67	8.09	7.90	7.81	---	---	---	---	---
22	7.67	7.90	8.28	7.86	8.05	7.84	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	7.90	8.04	8.40	7.99	7.99	7.85	8.25	---	---	---	---	---
24	8.13	7.68	8.30	7.95	7.90	7.91	8.18	---	---	---	---	---
25	8.25	7.60	8.33	7.95	7.60	8.08	8.03	---	---	---	---	---
26	8.19	7.43	8.26	7.86	7.53	8.09	7.94	7.24	---	---	---	---
27	8.01	7.35	8.22	7.74	7.52	8.02	8.06	6.90	---	---	---	---
28	8.09	7.13	8.03	7.70	7.48	7.71	---	6.89	---	---	---	---
29	8.04	7.34	7.82	7.52	---	7.58	---	6.88	---	---	---	---
30	7.84	7.65	7.78	7.56	---	7.53	---	7.18	---	---	---	---
31	7.55	---	7.71	7.53	---	7.57	---	7.10	---	---	---	---
MEAN	7.52	7.68	7.97	7.56	7.66	7.76	7.94	7.03	7.33	---	---	---
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 7.70	HIGHEST 6.20	MAY 26, 1998	LOWEST 9.02	DEC. 13, 14, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182511066045401. Local number, PN-2.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'11", long 66°04'54", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 1.58 mi northeast of Fort Buchanan Military Res. main gate, 2.95 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, and 2.45 mi southeast of US Naval Reservation in Miramar.
 Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: La Esperanza No. 2.
 AQUIFER.--Alluvium.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-40 ft (0-12.2 m), perforated 30-40 ft (9.15-12.2 m). Depth 40.0 ft (12.2 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--15-minute interval.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 13 ft (3.96 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 3.17 ft (0.97 m), above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on April 8, 1998.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1989 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 7.71 ft (2.35 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 23, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 11.90 ft (3.63 m), below land-surface datum, July 15, 16, 1991.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.43	9.97	8.94	10.73	10.16	10.11	10.42	10.52	9.45	10.49	9.12	8.86
2	9.45	9.98	8.97	10.73	10.26	10.16	10.41	10.54	9.53	10.54	9.21	8.97
3	9.28	10.04	9.06	10.60	10.30	10.19	10.42	10.62	9.61	10.57	9.33	8.76
4	9.19	10.05	9.16	10.50	10.35	10.32	10.43	10.64	9.60	10.57	9.42	8.65
5	9.05	10.04	9.26	10.42	9.99	10.33	10.47	10.67	9.64	10.53	9.55	8.53
6	8.92	9.99	9.30	10.23	9.56	10.33	10.53	10.73	9.70	10.57	9.65	8.43
7	8.90	9.99	9.40	9.71	9.40	10.34	10.59	10.76	9.75	10.62	9.72	8.25
8	8.89	9.99	9.52	9.36	9.40	10.34	10.54	10.74	9.79	10.66	9.72	8.17
9	8.90	10.02	9.59	9.23	9.37	10.35	10.56	10.72	9.71	10.67	9.76	8.11
10	8.98	10.11	9.66	9.11	9.32	10.35	10.60	10.75	9.63	10.69	9.74	8.14
11	9.02	10.11	9.72	9.03	9.39	10.36	10.65	10.79	9.51	10.69	9.77	8.26
12	8.92	10.19	9.81	8.99	9.46	10.36	10.66	10.81	9.49	10.72	9.78	8.38
13	8.75	10.26	9.86	9.05	9.55	10.37	10.69	10.88	9.46	10.75	9.82	8.52
14	8.61	10.31	9.94	8.99	9.56	10.37	10.68	10.92	9.48	10.82	9.91	8.64
15	8.45	10.32	10.01	9.03	9.54	10.38	10.73	10.76	9.57	10.66	9.96	8.57
16	8.39	10.33	10.07	9.08	9.52	10.38	10.68	10.47	9.67	10.16	10.03	8.39
17	8.44	10.34	10.12	9.15	9.61	10.39	10.36	9.97	9.75	9.86	10.05	8.44
18	8.49	10.38	10.17	9.21	9.64	10.47	10.23	9.56	9.78	9.58	10.00	8.50
19	8.63	10.27	10.21	9.28	9.73	10.53	10.21	9.36	9.82	---	9.53	8.27
20	8.82	10.10	10.25	9.39	9.78	10.60	10.17	9.21	9.86	---	9.31	8.17
21	8.93	9.82	10.30	9.49	9.74	10.56	10.20	8.99	9.95	---	9.18	8.20
22	9.07	9.41	10.38	9.57	9.78	10.54	10.24	8.94	10.00	---	9.00	7.92
23	9.18	9.30	10.39	9.65	9.87	10.58	10.29	8.91	10.03	---	8.92	7.75
24	9.30	9.33	10.40	---	9.94	10.70	10.32	8.97	10.09	---	8.92	7.80
25	9.36	9.32	10.43	---	10.02	10.75	10.36	9.07	10.16	---	8.61	7.88
26	9.46	9.24	10.48	---	10.05	10.80	10.41	9.16	10.21	---	8.51	8.02
27	9.60	9.01	10.53	---	10.09	10.85	10.49	9.20	10.27	---	8.52	8.00
28	9.71	8.99	10.56	10.00	10.09	10.81	10.50	9.30	10.32	---	8.47	8.01
29	9.79	9.01	10.60	10.07	---	10.83	10.47	9.35	10.37	---	8.44	8.11
30	9.88	9.01	10.68	10.10	---	10.68	10.50	9.36	10.41	---	8.58	8.10
31	9.94	---	10.71	10.11	---	10.52	---	9.43	---	9.06	8.73	---
MEAN	9.09	9.84	9.95	9.66	9.77	10.47	10.46	10.00	9.82	10.43	9.33	8.29

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 9.74 HIGHEST 7.71 SEPT. 23, 1998 LOWEST 10.94 MAY 14, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182435066052700. Local number, PN-5.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'35", long 66°05'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.94 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, 0.44 mi north of Escuela Superior Gabriela Mistral, and 1.19 mi northeast of WAPA TV radio antenna. Owner: US Geological Survey,

WRD, Name: Salud Mental No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 4.0 in (0.10 m), cased 4.0 in (0.10 m), 0-83.0 ft (0-25.3 m), perforated 73-83.0 ft (22.2-25.3 m). Depth 83.0 ft (25.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 85.0 ft (25.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 2.85 ft (0.87 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1989 to July 1, 1998, temporarily discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 25.37 ft (7.73 m), below land-surface datum, Feb. 5, 1993; lowest water level recorded, 32.82 ft (10.0 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 25-28, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28.85	28.10	28.20	28.88	28.98	29.25	29.67	29.83	29.26	28.62	---	---
2	28.84	28.10	28.20	28.89	29.01	29.27	29.68	29.84	29.22	---	---	---
3	28.78	28.10	28.20	28.89	29.04	29.28	29.69	29.85	29.17	---	---	---
4	28.80	28.14	28.20	28.90	29.06	29.31	29.71	29.85	29.11	---	---	---
5	28.80	28.16	28.20	28.92	28.95	29.34	29.71	29.86	29.04	---	---	---
6	28.79	28.11	28.20	28.91	29.00	29.35	29.72	29.86	29.02	---	---	---
7	28.77	28.15	28.21	28.89	29.03	29.37	29.73	29.88	28.99	---	---	---
8	28.75	28.15	28.22	28.89	29.05	29.34	29.75	29.88	28.97	---	---	---
9	28.74	28.17	28.24	28.89	29.05	29.39	29.76	29.90	28.92	---	---	---
10	28.72	28.20	28.25	28.89	29.05	29.42	29.76	29.91	28.84	---	---	---
11	28.66	28.23	28.27	28.88	29.06	29.46	29.76	29.91	28.80	---	---	---
12	28.62	28.26	28.29	28.87	29.07	29.50	29.77	29.92	28.75	---	---	---
13	28.58	28.28	28.31	28.86	29.08	29.52	29.76	29.93	28.73	---	---	---
14	28.53	28.30	28.33	28.85	29.08	29.53	29.79	29.94	28.69	---	---	---
15	28.48	28.33	28.35	28.84	29.08	29.54	29.80	29.96	28.66	---	---	---
16	28.46	28.33	28.37	28.83	29.08	29.51	29.77	29.97	28.64	---	---	---
17	28.42	28.35	28.39	28.83	29.09	29.53	29.75	29.97	28.63	---	---	---
18	28.38	28.39	28.44	28.83	29.10	29.55	29.77	29.96	28.61	---	---	---
19	28.33	28.41	28.47	28.82	29.12	29.55	29.78	29.94	28.60	---	---	---
20	28.29	28.46	28.52	28.80	29.13	29.56	29.79	29.93	28.58	---	---	---
21	28.25	28.46	28.54	28.82	29.15	29.57	29.80	29.86	28.58	---	---	---
22	28.22	28.40	28.56	28.83	29.17	29.58	29.79	29.82	28.58	---	---	---
23	28.20	28.38	28.59	28.85	29.18	29.60	29.79	29.79	28.56	---	---	---
24	28.17	28.34	28.61	28.86	29.19	29.62	29.80	29.72	28.55	---	---	---
25	28.16	28.30	28.64	28.87	29.20	29.63	29.80	29.68	28.55	---	---	---
26	28.13	28.26	28.68	28.88	29.22	29.66	29.80	29.64	28.55	---	---	---
27	28.11	28.24	28.71	28.90	29.23	29.66	29.80	29.57	28.56	---	---	---
28	28.10	28.23	28.75	28.91	29.24	29.69	29.81	29.52	28.58	---	---	---
29	28.10	28.22	28.79	28.92	---	29.70	29.81	29.43	28.59	---	---	---
30	28.10	28.20	28.83	28.93	---	29.61	29.83	29.36	28.60	---	---	---
31	28.10	---	28.86	28.95	---	29.65	---	29.31	---	---	---	---
MEAN	28.46	28.26	28.43	28.87	29.10	29.50	29.77	29.80	28.76	28.62	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 28.99 HIGHEST 28.10 Oct. 27-Nov. 3, 5, 6, 1997 LOWEST 29.97 MAY 16, 17, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182445066043401. Local number, PN-6.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'45", long 66°04'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.28 mi northeast of Escuela Dr. Pedreira, 3.52 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, and 0.53 mi south of Hiram Bithorn Stadium main gate. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Alsacia No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-27.0 ft (0-8.23 m), perforated 21-27.0 ft (6.40-8.23 m). Depth 27 ft (8.23 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--15-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 3.03 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR) replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on January 26, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1989 to November 27, 1991, Temporary discontinued, September 9, 1993 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.11 ft (0.95 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 18, 1989; lowest water level recorded, 13.65 ft (4.16 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 6, 7, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.21	9.40	8.67	9.95	9.73	9.81	9.51	9.62	8.24	9.13	8.17	7.63
2	9.23	9.39	8.70	9.91	9.74	9.84	9.52	9.68	8.27	---	8.28	7.73
3	9.07	9.50	8.75	9.84	9.80	9.88	9.54	9.71	8.29	---	8.30	7.57
4	9.07	9.44	8.80	9.83	9.87	9.90	9.64	9.67	8.28	---	8.41	7.54
5	8.99	9.37	8.84	9.82	9.27	9.99	9.67	9.67	8.31	---	8.51	7.40
6	8.96	9.41	8.89	9.50	9.04	9.96	9.70	9.71	8.31	---	8.55	7.21
7	8.90	9.49	8.99	9.17	8.97	9.92	9.72	9.71	8.32	---	8.61	6.89
8	8.89	9.56	9.08	8.89	8.99	9.79	9.67	9.64	8.29	---	8.55	6.71
9	8.81	9.61	9.10	8.88	8.96	9.84	9.68	9.64	8.30	---	8.54	6.57
10	8.75	9.65	9.18	8.85	8.98	9.93	9.75	9.70	8.18	---	8.55	6.60
11	8.83	9.67	9.21	8.83	9.01	10.00	9.79	9.79	8.17	---	8.56	6.70
12	8.66	9.72	9.31	8.83	9.08	10.03	9.85	9.85	8.15	---	8.54	6.77
13	8.53	9.70	9.35	8.84	9.16	10.04	9.83	9.89	8.16	---	8.53	6.83
14	8.28	9.80	9.39	8.85	9.18	10.08	9.77	9.91	8.17	---	8.63	6.88
15	8.15	9.82	9.42	8.92	9.05	9.96	9.78	9.63	8.24	---	8.72	6.75
16	8.13	9.67	9.48	8.95	9.15	9.86	9.56	9.40	8.30	---	8.83	6.65
17	8.14	9.63	9.55	---	9.21	9.90	9.42	9.12	8.31	---	8.87	6.69
18	8.21	9.67	9.55	---	9.28	9.96	9.41	8.77	8.35	---	8.81	6.81
19	8.31	9.49	9.54	---	9.39	10.00	9.43	8.69	8.42	---	8.29	6.28
20	8.40	9.43	9.60	---	9.44	10.01	9.37	8.64	8.51	8.17	8.12	6.26
21	8.50	9.19	9.64	---	9.45	9.98	9.36	8.30	8.57	7.84	7.95	6.25
22	8.59	9.01	9.70	---	9.52	10.04	9.35	8.24	8.57	7.77	7.88	5.41
23	8.72	8.93	9.69	---	9.61	10.08	9.38	8.24	8.63	7.83	7.84	5.44
24	8.83	8.91	9.71	---	9.68	10.12	9.45	8.23	8.69	7.83	7.72	5.44
25	8.93	8.89	9.77	---	9.76	10.14	9.49	8.24	8.77	7.85	7.34	5.44
26	9.03	8.83	9.82	---	9.78	10.15	9.46	8.23	8.82	7.93	7.28	5.45
27	9.16	8.78	9.85	9.51	9.77	10.14	9.44	8.21	8.87	7.92	7.27	5.41
28	9.24	8.84	9.86	9.54	9.78	10.11	9.46	8.24	8.93	7.91	7.25	5.41
29	9.30	8.87	9.89	9.61	---	10.01	9.48	8.26	8.97	7.94	7.28	5.41
30	9.36	8.74	9.95	9.68	---	9.71	9.54	8.25	8.98	8.04	7.43	5.32
31	9.39	---	9.98	9.72	---	9.55	---	8.25	---	8.09	7.54	---
MEAN	8.79	9.35	9.40	9.33	9.38	9.96	9.57	9.07	8.45	8.02	8.17	6.45

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 8.85 HIGHEST 5.29 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 10.18 MAR. 24-27, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182443066041502. Local number, PN-8c.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'43", long 66°04'15", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.29 mi east of Fort Buchanan Military Res. main gate, 3.83 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, and 0.16 mi southwest of Hospital del Maestro. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Parque Luis Muñoz Marin 1C.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10), 0-33.0 ft (0-10.1 m), perforated 33-40 ft (10.1-12.2 m). Depth 40.0 ft (12.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--15-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 13.0 ft (3.96 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on January 26, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1989 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +7.28 ft (+2.22 m), above land-surface datum, Sept. 21, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 16.18 ft (4.93 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 5, 6, 7, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14.53	14.73	---	15.24	15.10	15.24	15.24	15.39	14.07	14.90	14.33	---
2	14.33	14.78	---	15.24	15.12	15.26	15.26	15.41	14.11	14.95	14.43	---
3	14.10	14.81	---	15.20	15.13	15.26	15.29	15.43	14.15	15.02	14.51	---
4	14.33	14.83	---	15.22	15.18	15.28	15.33	15.44	14.15	14.96	14.56	13.59
5	14.32	14.84	---	15.23	14.45	15.29	15.33	15.45	14.16	15.00	14.62	13.56
6	14.34	14.87	---	14.98	14.44	15.23	15.36	15.49	14.07	15.07	14.68	10.32
7	14.35	14.89	---	14.18	14.33	15.27	15.39	15.50	14.12	15.16	14.73	3.21
8	14.42	14.92	---	14.08	14.35	15.26	15.39	15.50	14.01	15.19	14.67	2.76
9	14.05	14.95	14.57	14.08	14.38	15.30	15.42	15.51	14.04	15.23	14.75	+1.86
10	14.23	14.92	14.59	14.09	14.45	15.31	15.42	15.53	13.80	15.33	14.75	+2.42
11	14.33	15.02	14.63	14.14	14.47	15.32	15.44	15.55	13.87	15.38	14.59	+1.11
12	14.12	15.05	14.68	14.19	14.54	15.37	15.44	15.57	13.81	15.42	14.23	.88
13	14.14	15.07	14.73	14.21	15.04	15.38	15.23	15.59	13.90	15.45	14.39	4.43
14	13.11	15.09	14.78	14.18	15.04	15.40	15.37	15.59	13.98	15.48	14.55	4.68
15	13.32	15.11	14.81	14.32	15.04	15.30	15.41	15.26	14.03	15.47	14.67	4.68
16	13.44	14.90	14.84	14.42	15.06	15.32	15.08	15.21	14.10	15.46	14.77	5.78
17	13.55	---	14.87	14.50	15.08	15.38	15.02	14.91	14.13	---	14.85	5.80
18	13.63	---	14.91	14.56	15.09	15.39	15.12	14.44	14.12	---	14.85	8.57
19	13.73	---	14.95	14.57	15.09	15.38	15.15	14.40	14.22	---	14.25	2.89
20	13.85	---	14.98	14.63	15.09	15.41	15.16	14.40	14.29	14.20	14.36	2.88
21	13.93	---	15.01	14.69	15.10	15.41	15.16	13.97	14.36	13.60	14.04	2.88
22	14.03	---	15.05	14.76	15.10	15.43	15.17	13.93	14.40	13.47	14.06	+7.28
23	14.16	---	15.08	14.81	15.10	15.46	15.22	13.95	14.45	13.55	14.03	---
24	14.22	---	15.08	14.87	15.11	15.48	15.25	13.94	14.51	13.52	13.97	---
25	14.33	---	15.12	14.91	15.14	15.49	15.27	14.00	14.58	13.70	12.81	---
26	14.40	---	15.13	14.96	15.17	15.50	15.24	13.98	14.61	13.81	12.73	---
27	14.48	---	15.15	14.96	15.20	15.50	15.27	13.94	14.66	13.88	12.75	---
28	14.54	---	15.17	14.98	15.23	15.51	15.29	14.05	14.74	13.94	12.83	---
29	14.59	---	15.20	15.02	---	15.51	15.35	14.01	14.80	14.06	13.43	---
30	14.63	---	15.22	15.05	---	15.22	15.37	14.04	14.85	14.17	13.67	---
31	14.67	---	15.25	15.08	---	15.20	---	14.06	---	14.25	14.40	---
MEAN	14.14	14.92	14.95	14.69	14.91	15.36	15.28	14.82	14.24	14.63	14.20	3.91

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 14.10 HIGHEST +7.28 SEPT. 21, 1998 LOWEST 15.59 MAY 13, 14, 1998

+ above land-surface datum

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182417066042700. Local number, PN-10.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'17", long 66°04'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 3.96 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, 1.00 mi southwest of Escuela J.J. Osuna, and 2.26 mi east of WAPA TV radio antenna. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Las Américas No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-80.0 ft (0-24.4 m), 4 in (0.10 m), perforated pipe 80-90.0 ft (24.4-27.4 m). Depth 90.0 ft (27.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--15-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 16.0 ft (4.89 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 3.10 ft (0.95 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR) replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 23, 1998. Well affected by pumping during June 1994. [+ , above land-surface datum].

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1989 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +2.30 ft (+0.70 m), above land-surface datum, Jan. 9-12, 1993; lowest water level recorded, 6.92 ft (2.11 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 6-9, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2.98	2.81	2.56	---	2.96	2.81	2.96	2.67	1.77	---	2.68	3.35
2	2.88	2.83	2.56	---	2.98	2.85	2.97	2.67	1.76	---	2.78	3.35
3	2.67	2.85	2.57	---	2.99	2.87	2.95	2.66	1.76	---	2.87	2.53
4	2.68	2.85	2.59	---	3.01	2.88	2.94	2.66	1.77	---	2.98	2.30
5	2.62	2.85	2.61	---	2.76	2.92	2.90	2.66	1.87	---	3.08	1.96
6	2.62	2.85	2.67	---	2.81	2.94	2.90	2.65	2.19	---	3.15	1.95
7	2.62	2.85	2.70	---	2.81	2.97	2.89	2.65	2.48	---	3.21	1.59
8	2.62	2.85	2.74	---	2.81	2.95	2.89	2.64	2.64	---	3.24	1.43
9	2.55	2.87	2.79	---	2.74	2.95	2.88	2.64	2.76	---	3.25	1.23
10	2.55	2.89	2.79	---	2.73	2.94	2.86	2.63	2.78	---	3.25	1.27
11	2.60	2.92	2.79	---	2.74	2.95	2.85	2.63	2.83	---	3.26	1.29
12	2.58	2.94	2.83	---	2.92	3.00	2.84	2.62	2.92	---	3.25	1.29
13	2.46	2.98	2.87	2.37	3.06	3.02	2.82	2.62	2.98	---	3.25	1.29
14	2.14	2.99	2.89	2.31	3.07	3.04	2.77	2.61	3.04	---	3.26	1.30
15	2.19	3.00	2.89	2.31	3.02	3.04	2.76	2.61	3.09	---	3.31	1.17
16	2.22	3.01	2.89	2.32	2.98	3.01	2.75	2.62	3.18	---	3.36	1.19
17	2.28	3.01	2.91	2.32	2.93	3.01	2.75	2.65	3.26	---	3.38	1.21
18	2.36	2.99	2.93	2.32	2.93	3.01	2.73	2.47	3.31	---	3.39	1.23
19	2.43	2.95	2.96	2.32	2.93	3.00	2.73	2.26	3.36	---	3.38	1.00
20	2.48	2.92	2.95	2.32	2.93	3.01	2.72	2.06	3.40	2.76	3.38	1.03
21	2.52	2.41	2.96	2.38	2.94	3.01	2.72	2.02	3.46	2.53	3.38	1.02
22	2.57	2.57	2.99	2.47	2.95	3.00	2.72	2.00	3.49	2.53	3.38	.44
23	2.63	2.59	2.99	2.55	2.86	3.00	2.71	1.97	3.55	2.53	3.38	.59
24	2.65	2.63	3.01	2.60	2.80	3.02	2.71	1.94	---	2.39	3.37	.64
25	2.67	2.66	3.02	2.66	2.80	3.03	2.70	1.91	---	2.38	3.37	.65
26	2.69	2.68	3.03	2.73	2.79	3.05	2.70	1.89	---	2.31	3.37	.68
27	2.72	2.68	3.03	2.76	2.79	3.05	2.69	1.84	---	2.19	3.37	.67
28	2.73	2.69	3.04	2.82	2.79	3.05	2.69	1.79	---	2.08	3.37	.67
29	2.76	2.69	3.04	2.86	---	3.04	2.68	1.79	---	2.09	3.37	.70
30	2.78	2.57	3.05	2.88	---	2.97	2.68	1.78	---	2.34	3.36	.62
31	2.81	---	3.07	2.93	---	2.92	---	1.78	---	2.54	3.36	---
MEAN	2.58	2.81	2.86	2.54	2.89	2.98	2.80	2.34	2.77	2.39	3.25	1.32

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 2.64 HIGHEST 0.44 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 3.55 JUNE 23, 1998

+ above land-surface datum

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182349066032600. Local number, PN-13.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'49", long 66°03'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 5.15 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, 1.28 mi south of Escuela J.J. Osuna, and 0.69 mi southwest of University of Puerto Rico main gate. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Jardín Botánico No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m) cased 4.0 in (0.10 m), 0-45.0 ft (0-13.72 m), perforated 35-45.0 ft (10.67-13.72 m). Depth 45.0 ft (13.72 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 32 ft (9.75 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 2.84 ft (0.86 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on May 22, 1998. From July 30, 1998, monthly measurements only.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1989 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 6.96 ft (2.12 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 10, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 17.87 ft (5.45 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 7, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	16.90	16.81	16.82	17.28	17.23	17.20	17.32	17.47	---	17.26	---	---
2	16.47	16.83	16.85	17.27	17.25	17.22	17.38	17.49	---	17.25	---	---
3	16.39	16.86	16.86	17.03	17.26	17.23	17.43	17.50	---	17.27	---	---
4	16.61	16.86	16.87	17.22	17.27	17.23	17.47	17.49	---	17.18	---	---
5	16.61	16.73	16.89	17.25	16.11	17.26	17.50	17.49	---	17.19	---	---
6	16.64	16.87	16.90	16.39	16.68	17.17	17.51	17.52	---	17.27	---	---
7	16.60	16.89	16.93	16.20	16.94	17.22	17.54	17.53	---	17.10	---	---
8	16.64	16.91	16.95	16.83	16.98	17.18	17.46	17.53	---	17.28	---	---
9	16.23	16.93	16.96	16.87	16.80	17.25	17.51	17.52	---	17.21	---	---
10	16.47	16.80	16.98	16.88	16.98	17.28	17.53	17.52	---	17.30	---	---
11	16.54	16.97	16.98	16.90	17.02	17.29	17.53	17.53	---	17.28	---	---
12	16.36	16.99	17.01	16.92	16.95	17.32	17.53	17.55	---	17.30	---	---
13	16.33	16.99	17.03	16.81	17.00	17.34	17.22	17.58	---	17.33	---	---
14	15.23	17.01	17.05	16.69	17.02	17.35	17.43	17.58	---	17.35	---	---
15	16.12	17.03	17.05	16.91	16.88	17.22	17.48	17.20	---	---	---	---
16	16.20	16.69	17.07	16.96	16.99	17.26	16.61	17.30	---	---	---	---
17	16.31	16.92	17.03	16.98	17.01	17.32	17.12	17.34	---	---	---	---
18	16.35	16.95	17.08	17.00	17.04	17.37	17.29	17.23	---	---	---	---
19	16.40	16.81	17.08	16.93	17.07	17.29	17.35	17.19	---	---	---	---
20	16.46	16.90	17.12	17.02	17.08	17.37	17.35	17.22	---	---	---	---
21	16.48	16.10	17.13	17.05	17.10	17.37	17.31	17.12	---	---	---	---
22	16.55	16.71	17.15	17.07	17.13	17.41	17.34	---	---	---	---	---
23	16.59	16.77	17.17	17.10	17.15	17.44	17.40	---	---	---	---	---
24	16.62	16.78	17.16	17.12	17.17	17.47	17.43	---	17.18	---	---	---
25	16.65	16.76	17.20	17.15	17.19	17.48	17.44	---	17.19	---	---	---
26	16.67	16.77	17.22	17.18	17.19	17.49	17.35	---	17.16	---	---	---
27	16.71	16.77	17.22	17.19	17.19	17.49	17.21	---	17.19	---	---	---
28	16.74	16.82	17.24	17.21	17.19	17.50	17.38	---	17.20	---	---	---
29	16.77	16.83	17.26	17.23	---	17.50	17.43	---	17.21	---	---	---
30	16.79	16.81	17.27	17.23	---	17.19	17.46	---	17.24	---	---	---
31	16.80	---	17.27	17.23	---	17.04	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	16.49	16.83	17.06	17.00	17.03	17.31	17.38	17.42	17.20	17.26	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 17.07 HIGHEST 13.58 OCT. 14, 1997 LOWEST 17.59 MAY 13, 1998

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182406066034700. Local number, PN-19.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'06", long 66°03'47", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 4.65 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, 0.89 mi south of Escuela J.J. Osuna, and 0.78 mi southwest of University of Puerto Rico main gate. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Jardín Botánico No. 3.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m) cased 4.0 in (0.10 m), 0-48.0 ft (0-14.6 m), perforated 38-48 ft (11.6-14.6 m). Depth 48.0 ft.(14.6 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 32.0 ft (9.75 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 2.91 ft (0.88 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on May 22, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.84 ft (0.86 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 22, 23, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 13.43 ft (4.09 m), below land-surface datum, Nov. 8, 9, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.13	9.43	7.62	11.21	10.45	10.11	10.62	11.29	6.83	---	7.13	6.23
2	6.19	9.56	7.70	11.24	10.55	10.22	10.68	11.37	7.10	---	7.43	6.53
3	5.78	9.70	7.88	11.25	10.64	10.36	10.75	11.44	7.53	---	7.76	5.85
4	6.15	9.78	8.09	11.24	10.68	10.48	10.83	11.49	7.87	---	8.07	5.81
5	5.78	9.89	8.31	11.28	6.47	10.62	10.90	11.54	8.22	---	8.39	5.18
6	5.94	9.94	8.52	10.47	6.10	10.64	11.00	11.60	8.52	---	8.63	5.19
7	6.11	10.01	8.74	6.43	6.26	10.67	11.13	11.64	8.79	---	8.84	4.69
8	6.31	10.07	8.92	6.09	6.67	10.62	11.25	11.66	8.96	---	9.00	4.81
9	6.03	10.16	9.10	6.26	6.20	10.63	11.33	11.70	8.09	---	9.09	4.37
10	6.11	10.27	9.29	6.13	6.11	10.69	11.39	11.73	7.10	---	9.23	4.58
11	6.33	10.36	9.43	6.45	6.51	10.75	11.43	11.79	6.87	---	9.36	4.77
12	5.95	10.47	9.57	6.84	6.86	10.85	11.47	11.82	6.88	---	9.50	4.94
13	5.72	10.51	9.68	7.17	7.19	10.94	11.47	11.88	7.12	---	9.59	5.10
14	5.07	10.60	9.82	7.41	7.57	11.03	11.47	11.91	7.48	---	9.66	5.26
15	5.39	10.70	9.93	7.72	7.78	11.05	11.47	11.22	7.83	---	9.78	4.71
16	5.66	10.69	10.03	7.96	8.00	10.99	11.34	10.24	8.19	---	9.93	4.75
17	5.80	10.68	10.11	8.20	8.19	10.99	8.58	9.17	8.49	---	10.03	4.91
18	6.01	10.70	10.20	8.41	8.45	11.05	8.73	7.62	8.71	---	10.06	5.05
19	6.22	10.58	10.32	8.59	8.65	11.10	9.42	7.83	8.92	---	7.48	4.13
20	6.53	10.48	10.40	8.76	8.83	11.14	9.89	8.25	9.13	---	7.33	4.18
21	6.93	7.71	10.46	8.92	8.97	11.16	10.16	6.85	9.35	4.45	6.59	4.21
22	7.28	6.44	10.56	9.09	9.17	11.21	10.42	6.89	9.53	4.93	6.37	2.91
23	7.60	6.68	10.65	9.30	9.31	11.28	10.63	7.32	---	5.21	6.16	2.96
24	7.89	7.11	10.71	9.48	9.48	11.36	10.80	7.64	---	5.23	6.01	3.30
25	8.13	7.43	10.80	9.60	9.61	11.46	10.93	7.98	---	5.21	4.59	3.54
26	8.34	7.78	10.87	9.74	9.74	11.53	11.03	7.18	---	5.29	5.02	3.75
27	8.58	7.97	10.91	9.89	9.88	11.54	11.06	6.65	---	5.47	5.26	3.86
28	8.79	8.22	10.97	10.00	10.00	11.58	11.10	6.61	---	5.71	5.39	4.04
29	8.95	8.47	11.05	10.09	---	11.60	11.17	6.53	---	6.04	5.53	4.20
30	9.10	7.92	11.11	10.17	---	11.08	11.24	6.61	---	6.47	5.66	4.17
31	9.28	---	11.18	10.27	---	10.79	---	6.76	---	6.81	5.89	---
MEAN	6.81	9.34	9.77	8.89	8.37	10.95	10.79	9.49	8.07	5.53	7.70	4.60

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 8.54 HIGHEST 2.84 SEPT. 22, 23, 1998 LOWEST 11.91 MAY 14, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

181352066025300. Local number, CJ-TW19A.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'52", long 66°02'53", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.96 mi southwest of Caguas plaza, 1.02 mi northwest of Escuela Antonio S. Pedreira, and 0.30 mi southeast of Hwy 156 km 59.1. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CJ-TW19A, Bonneville.

AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-67.0 ft (0-20.4 m), screened 50-65 ft (15.2-19.8 m). Depth 67.0 ft (20.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 262 ft (79.8 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of casing 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- June 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 22.07 ft (6.73 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 25, 26, 27, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 25.70 ft (7.83 m), below land-surface datum, May 31, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	24.91	24.51	24.77	25.08	24.85	24.39	24.27	24.55	24.80	24.71	24.72	23.84
2	24.89	24.53	24.79	25.07	24.87	24.42	24.27	24.56	24.82	24.74	24.72	23.86
3	24.87	24.55	24.80	25.08	24.88	24.45	24.26	24.57	24.82	24.75	24.72	23.92
4	24.86	24.56	24.80	25.08	24.88	24.48	24.26	24.59	24.85	24.76	24.73	23.92
5	24.85	24.57	24.81	25.09	24.83	24.51	24.27	24.60	24.87	24.77	24.76	23.90
6	24.85	24.58	24.83	25.09	24.72	24.49	24.29	24.59	24.88	24.78	24.77	23.88
7	24.85	24.58	24.86	25.06	24.64	24.47	24.34	24.60	24.89	24.79	24.78	23.88
8	24.86	24.59	24.88	25.02	24.59	24.27	24.36	24.61	24.89	24.81	24.78	23.90
9	24.87	24.61	24.88	24.97	24.45	24.15	24.37	24.63	24.89	24.82	24.77	23.92
10	24.87	24.62	24.89	24.93	24.36	24.10	24.36	24.63	24.90	24.83	24.71	23.94
11	24.87	24.62	24.90	24.88	24.31	24.09	24.37	24.63	24.91	24.84	24.68	23.94
12	24.87	24.61	24.91	24.87	24.30	24.10	24.38	24.64	24.91	24.84	24.67	23.95
13	24.87	24.60	24.92	24.86	24.29	24.13	24.43	24.66	24.91	24.84	24.66	23.98
14	24.78	24.60	24.93	24.84	24.28	24.14	24.44	24.66	24.91	24.86	24.65	24.01
15	24.67	24.60	24.94	24.79	24.25	24.15	24.45	24.67	24.87	24.88	24.65	24.04
16	24.60	24.61	24.95	24.76	24.17	24.18	24.45	24.67	24.87	24.89	24.66	24.04
17	24.54	24.62	24.96	24.75	24.13	24.19	24.45	24.69	24.87	24.90	24.69	24.01
18	24.42	24.62	24.97	24.74	24.12	24.22	24.46	24.70	24.85	24.89	24.69	24.00
19	24.35	24.63	25.02	24.72	24.13	24.26	24.46	24.70	24.84	24.91	24.69	24.01
20	24.30	24.64	25.01	24.72	24.15	24.29	24.49	24.70	24.82	24.91	24.68	24.03
21	24.28	24.67	25.00	24.74	24.17	24.28	24.51	24.71	24.81	24.85	24.61	24.03
22	24.27	24.68	25.01	24.75	24.22	24.29	24.50	24.72	24.80	24.82	24.56	23.68
23	24.28	24.69	25.01	24.77	24.24	24.31	24.49	24.73	24.79	24.78	24.47	23.19
24	24.32	24.71	25.02	24.78	24.26	24.33	24.48	24.74	24.76	24.77	24.40	22.98
25	24.32	24.69	25.03	24.78	24.30	24.35	24.49	24.74	24.75	24.77	24.16	22.90
26	24.35	24.71	25.04	24.79	24.33	24.37	24.50	24.75	24.73	24.78	24.01	22.87
27	24.37	24.73	25.04	24.81	24.35	24.36	24.50	24.76	24.71	24.78	23.92	22.88
28	24.39	24.75	25.04	24.80	24.38	24.38	24.51	24.77	24.70	24.78	23.86	22.95
29	24.42	24.75	25.05	24.81	---	24.36	24.53	24.77	24.70	24.77	23.82	23.00
30	24.46	24.75	25.06	24.81	---	24.32	24.55	24.79	24.69	24.75	23.81	23.07
31	24.47	---	25.07	24.83	---	24.29	---	24.80	---	24.73	23.83	---
MEAN	24.61	24.63	24.94	24.87	24.41	24.29	24.42	24.68	24.83	24.81	24.50	23.68

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 24.56 HIGHEST 22.07 SEPT. 25, 26, 27, 1998 LOWEST 25.09 JAN. 4, 5, 6, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

181311066022500. Local number, CJ-TW11.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'11", long 66°02'25", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 1.13 mi south of the intersection of Hwy 156 with Hwy 52, 0.15 mi southeast of the inserction of Hwy 172 with Hwy 1, and 0.20 mi northeast of Escuela Antonio S.

Pereira. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CJ-TW11.

AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), 0-110 ft (0-33.5 m), screened 66-96 ft (20.1-29.3 m). Depth 110 ft (33.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 279 ft (85.0 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.04 ft (0.24 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 2, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 2, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 23.08 ft (7.03 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 27 29, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 28.73 ft (8.76 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 22, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.91	---	28.20	28.27
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.64	27.93	28.10	28.24	28.27
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.69	27.98	28.15	28.28	28.27
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.69	28.03	28.19	28.31	28.25
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.74	28.10	28.25	28.38	28.26
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.82	---	28.26	28.44	28.27
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.87	---	28.26	28.46	28.20
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.90	---	28.26	28.47	28.20
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.92	---	28.24	28.49	28.20
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.90	---	28.28	28.51	28.20
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.96	---	28.30	28.51	28.20
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.97	---	28.31	28.51	28.19
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.00	---	28.31	28.53	28.18
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.04	---	28.36	28.55	28.17
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.08	---	28.41	28.57	28.18
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.12	---	28.44	28.61	28.18
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.18	---	28.45	28.61	28.18
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.20	---	28.45	28.61	28.19
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.28	---	28.47	28.61	28.21
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.28	---	28.49	28.62	28.22
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.28	---	28.49	28.63	28.27
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.31	---	28.37	28.71	28.27
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.38	---	28.30	28.66	28.22
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.47	---	28.28	28.61	28.19
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.53	---	28.24	28.49	28.20
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.58	---	28.20	28.38	28.27
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.60	---	28.19	28.33	28.19
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.66	---	28.19	28.31	28.15
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.73	---	28.19	28.29	28.10
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.81	---	28.14	28.26	28.06
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.86	---	28.16	28.28	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.18	27.99	28.29	28.47	28.21
WTR YR 1997	MEAN 28.04	HIGHEST 26.63	MAY 2, 1997	LOWEST 28.73	AUG. 22, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	27.99	26.59	26.96	27.91	27.49	26.50	25.81	26.19	26.99	27.16	27.50	25.81
2	27.98	26.62	27.03	27.93	27.51	26.53	25.84	26.19	27.04	27.19	27.52	25.80
3	27.95	26.63	27.06	27.97	27.52	26.58	25.84	26.24	27.07	27.21	27.56	25.84
4	27.97	26.64	27.07	28.00	27.52	26.64	25.84	26.23	27.10	27.23	27.61	25.82
5	28.00	26.70	27.07	28.04	27.45	26.67	25.83	26.24	27.12	27.27	27.65	25.74
6	28.03	26.69	27.13	28.09	27.14	26.64	25.92	26.25	27.14	27.29	27.67	25.74
7	28.05	26.68	27.18	27.82	26.98	26.61	25.91	26.26	27.16	27.31	27.68	25.72
8	28.08	26.70	27.20	27.63	26.92	26.23	25.94	26.27	27.16	27.33	27.69	25.72
9	28.11	26.75	27.20	27.52	26.72	26.10	25.93	26.30	27.20	27.37	27.64	25.72
10	28.11	26.74	27.22	27.47	26.67	26.01	25.91	26.33	27.21	27.40	27.58	25.70
11	28.13	26.67	27.25	27.43	26.58	25.94	25.91	26.33	27.22	27.44	27.58	25.64
12	28.03	26.61	27.29	27.42	26.54	25.94	25.91	26.39	27.23	27.46	27.61	25.63
13	27.91	26.59	27.30	27.40	26.52	25.97	25.99	26.44	27.19	27.48	27.63	25.64
14	27.44	26.59	27.32	27.25	26.51	25.97	26.00	26.47	27.11	27.51	27.64	25.62
15	27.04	26.63	27.34	27.15	26.41	25.94	25.99	26.51	27.11	27.55	27.68	25.58
16	26.91	26.65	27.36	27.11	26.32	25.97	25.99	26.55	27.12	27.58	27.74	25.51
17	26.79	26.68	27.49	27.10	26.26	25.99	26.00	26.59	27.16	27.62	27.77	25.46
18	26.56	26.70	27.46	27.07	26.27	26.02	26.02	26.64	27.07	27.66	27.75	25.43
19	26.42	26.72	27.53	27.08	26.28	26.05	26.03	26.67	27.03	27.68	27.73	25.46
20	26.32	26.73	27.56	27.10	26.27	26.06	26.05	26.70	27.02	27.67	27.76	25.48
21	26.28	26.79	27.56	27.14	26.28	26.01	26.07	26.72	27.03	27.58	27.64	25.43
22	26.28	26.84	27.59	27.17	26.32	26.00	26.08	26.75	27.03	27.49	27.58	24.68
23	26.31	26.86	27.60	27.22	26.30	26.02	26.07	26.81	26.98	27.47	27.42	23.57
24	26.33	26.86	27.63	27.26	26.31	26.06	26.09	26.83	26.96	27.47	27.28	23.26
25	26.37	26.85	27.68	27.29	26.34	26.08	26.12	26.86	26.96	27.49	26.75	23.17
26	26.43	26.87	27.71	27.30	26.36	26.09	26.13	26.90	26.97	27.49	26.22	23.14
27	26.45	26.89	27.71	27.31	26.41	26.04	26.13	26.93	26.98	27.47	26.04	23.09
28	26.48	26.93	27.73	27.34	26.49	26.04	26.14	26.93	27.03	27.48	25.90	23.10
29	26.49	26.93	27.77	27.36	---	26.01	26.18	26.94	27.07	27.48	25.85	23.09
30	26.52	26.93	27.82	27.36	---	25.87	26.19	26.97	27.11	27.48	25.85	23.12
31	26.55	---	27.87	27.39	---	25.79	---	26.99	---	27.48	25.83	---
MEAN	27.17	26.74	27.41	27.44	26.67	26.14	26.00	26.56	27.09	27.44	27.27	24.96

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 26.75 HIGHEST 23.08 SEPR. 27, 29, 1998 LOWEST 28.13 OCT. 10, 11, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

181446066013400. Local number, CJ-TW20.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'46", long 66°01'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.63 mi east of Hwy 1, 1.59 mi west of the intersection of Hwy 189 with Hwy 931, and 0.70 mi northeast of the intersection of Hwy 189 with Hwy 1. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CJ-TW20.

AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), casing 4 in (0.10 m), 0-37.0 ft (0-11.3 m), screened 25-35 ft (7.62-11.3 m). Depth 35.0 ft (11.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 187.0 ft (57.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.63 ft (1.11 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 5, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 5, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 14.19 ft (4.32 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 22 1998; lowest water level recorded, 19.89 ft (6.06 m), below land-surface datum, July 15, 16, 17, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.55	19.78	19.37	18.23
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.54	19.78	19.35	18.33
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.53	19.81	19.36	18.36
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.48	19.82	19.12	18.41
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.60	19.53	19.87	19.05	18.48
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.65	19.57	19.86	19.09	18.50
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.69	19.58	19.86	19.09	18.35
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.71	19.61	19.83	19.12	18.29
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.73	19.66	19.81	19.16	18.38
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.73	19.68	19.86	19.23	18.51
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.74	19.67	19.86	19.22	18.62
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.74	19.66	19.84	19.23	18.64
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.75	19.69	19.81	19.25	18.39
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.73	19.71	19.87	19.27	18.09
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.70	19.70	19.89	19.30	18.02
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.70	19.69	19.88	19.34	17.93
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.68	19.72	19.89	19.34	17.93
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.67	19.75	19.85	19.28	18.02
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.66	19.76	19.85	19.27	18.08
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.64	19.74	19.85	19.29	18.14
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.63	19.74	19.82	19.33	18.24
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.63	19.77	19.68	19.36	18.19
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.66	19.78	19.56	18.90	18.18
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.63	19.76	19.55	18.80	18.23
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.62	19.76	19.47	18.39	18.30
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.62	19.77	19.45	18.27	18.42
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.62	19.77	19.46	18.34	17.96
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.64	19.77	19.47	18.28	17.84
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.60	19.79	19.39	18.11	17.85
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.57	19.80	19.38	18.07	17.91
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.57	---	19.35	18.15	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.66	19.68	19.72	18.99	18.23

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 19.25 HIGHEST 17.76 SEPT. 28, 1997 LOWEST 19.86 JULY 15, 16, 17, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17.94	18.06	18.44	19.39	18.98	18.26	18.04	18.50	18.74	18.30	18.14	16.59
2	17.98	18.11	18.54	19.38	19.03	18.33	18.11	18.53	18.79	18.34	18.18	16.70
3	17.92	18.16	18.60	19.38	18.99	18.40	18.10	18.60	18.82	18.36	18.24	16.92
4	17.97	18.19	18.60	19.38	18.99	18.48	18.09	18.65	18.87	18.37	18.32	16.88
5	18.06	18.25	18.63	19.40	18.68	18.53	18.07	18.68	18.71	18.38	18.38	16.71
6	18.15	18.24	18.65	19.44	18.22	18.45	18.11	18.69	18.64	18.41	18.44	16.62
7	18.21	18.24	18.74	18.89	18.10	18.39	18.26	18.72	18.67	18.42	18.44	16.56
8	18.27	18.26	18.80	18.60	18.11	18.00	18.25	18.73	18.69	18.43	18.22	16.59
9	18.34	18.32	18.80	18.51	17.67	17.78	18.19	18.75	18.72	18.48	17.86	16.25
10	18.37	18.33	18.83	18.33	17.50	17.75	18.13	18.75	18.74	18.52	17.63	16.17
11	18.38	18.21	18.87	18.28	17.57	17.77	18.15	18.74	18.76	18.56	17.65	16.20
12	18.27	18.19	18.93	18.34	17.67	17.86	18.16	18.79	18.77	18.60	17.77	16.32
13	18.16	18.19	18.93	18.40	17.76	17.93	18.29	18.84	18.77	18.66	17.84	16.50
14	17.66	18.22	18.95	18.24	17.82	17.95	18.34	18.83	18.76	18.71	17.90	16.63
15	17.11	18.27	18.98	18.15	17.55	17.94	18.35	18.79	18.81	18.79	17.98	16.80
16	16.93	18.25	19.00	18.20	17.41	17.97	18.35	18.75	18.88	18.85	18.13	16.80
17	16.88	18.25	19.03	18.26	17.38	18.03	18.31	18.79	18.93	18.90	18.24	16.84
18	16.83	18.25	19.07	18.28	17.46	18.10	18.31	18.80	18.58	18.89	18.16	16.91
19	16.84	18.26	19.13	18.33	17.55	18.16	18.33	18.81	18.46	18.85	17.95	17.01
20	16.93	18.27	19.13	18.40	17.66	18.21	18.36	18.83	18.42	18.79	17.91	17.07
21	17.04	18.35	19.11	18.48	17.73	18.15	18.27	18.81	18.46	18.49	17.63	16.87
22	17.21	18.38	19.16	18.54	17.87	18.19	18.13	18.79	18.37	18.34	17.27	15.95
23	17.35	18.43	19.15	18.62	17.91	18.25	18.10	18.84	18.24	18.33	16.94	14.34
24	17.44	18.47	19.16	18.66	17.96	18.33	18.14	18.87	18.25	18.39	16.84	14.60
25	17.54	18.48	19.20	18.72	18.04	18.40	18.21	18.86	18.07	18.48	16.28	14.82
26	17.65	18.51	19.22	18.76	18.09	18.38	18.26	18.90	17.97	18.49	15.96	15.08
27	17.73	18.42	19.19	18.79	18.16	18.31	18.29	18.86	17.98	18.47	15.95	15.05
28	17.82	18.44	19.22	18.83	18.25	18.30	18.36	18.77	18.08	18.28	15.94	14.96
29	17.89	18.42	19.26	18.86	---	18.28	18.45	18.74	18.16	18.06	16.11	15.06
30	17.94	18.40	19.30	18.85	---	18.06	18.49	18.75	18.23	18.07	16.27	15.18
31	17.99	---	19.35	18.88	---	17.99	---	18.75	---	18.10	16.47	---
MEAN	17.70	18.29	18.97	18.70	18.00	18.16	18.23	18.76	18.54	18.49	17.52	16.17

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 18.13 HIGHEST 14.19 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 19.46 JAN. 6, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

181539066014500. Local number, CJ-TW15.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'39", long 66°01'45", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.55 mi southeast of the intersection of Hwy 1 with Hwy 30, 0.75 mi southeast of the inserction of Hwy 1 with Hwy 52, and 0.06 mi north of Hwy 796. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CJ-TW15.

AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), 0-70.0 ft (0-21.3 m), screened 25-70 ft (7.62-21.3 m). Depth 70.0 ft (21.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 167.3 ft (51.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.75 ft (1.14 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 5, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 5, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 5.93 ft (1.81 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 14, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 9.58 ft (2.92 m), below land-surface datum, May 11, 12, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.57	8.05	7.76	7.11
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.62	8.09	7.81	7.20
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.67	8.09	7.84	7.21
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.77	8.11	7.32	7.23
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.87	8.15	7.45	7.25
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.64	7.95	8.16	7.50	7.30
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.68	8.00	8.17	7.55	7.19
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.71	8.00	8.15	7.61	7.28
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.70	8.00	8.13	7.66	7.32
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.68	7.97	8.13	7.71	7.33
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.68	7.94	8.14	7.69	7.39
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.69	7.91	8.16	7.67	7.39
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.73	7.94	8.16	7.62	7.03
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.73	8.00	8.19	7.53	7.06
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.77	8.04	8.21	7.53	7.09
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.80	8.08	8.22	7.53	7.14
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.76	8.18	8.16	7.49	7.16
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.79	8.24	8.15	7.36	7.22
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.82	8.22	8.05	7.46	7.28
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.83	8.18	7.97	7.45	7.33
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.79	8.19	7.94	7.44	7.35
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.75	8.20	7.83	7.19	7.34
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.75	8.19	7.81	6.84	7.36
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.74	8.14	7.85	6.97	7.42
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.68	8.14	7.85	6.52	7.48
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.63	8.15	7.88	6.70	7.34
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.58	8.14	7.94	6.83	6.99
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.54	8.14	7.92	6.91	7.08
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.47	8.10	7.92	6.96	7.13
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.44	8.05	7.89	7.01	7.21
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.50	---	7.73	7.07	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.69	8.02	8.04	7.35	7.24

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 7.67 HIGHEST 6.51 AU. 25, 1997 LOWEST 8.24 JULY 15, 16, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.19	6.99	7.73	8.28	8.90	8.69	8.98	9.43	9.04	8.56	9.15	8.55
2	7.08	7.05	7.76	8.33	8.94	8.73	8.96	9.44	9.03	8.66	9.20	8.51
3	7.02	7.09	7.78	8.33	8.95	8.78	8.98	9.46	9.03	8.72	9.27	8.46
4	7.04	7.10	7.78	8.32	8.97	8.84	9.06	9.48	9.02	8.69	9.31	8.53
5	7.07	7.16	7.79	8.32	8.97	8.80	9.06	9.48	8.87	8.72	9.31	8.62
6	7.13	7.24	7.81	8.32	8.01	8.82	9.08	9.43	8.87	8.80	9.07	8.51
7	7.15	7.34	7.85	8.30	8.12	8.54	9.11	9.46	8.89	8.90	8.73	8.56
8	7.20	7.39	7.86	7.90	8.19	8.64	9.13	9.49	8.88	8.75	8.72	8.65
9	7.24	7.43	7.89	7.77	7.67	8.72	9.19	9.52	8.85	8.87	8.83	8.72
10	7.23	7.32	7.87	7.72	7.66	8.81	9.21	9.54	8.85	8.97	8.94	8.78
11	7.20	7.37	7.89	7.87	7.76	8.89	9.25	9.57	8.83	9.02	8.99	8.86
12	7.10	7.43	7.91	7.99	7.84	8.88	9.23	9.58	8.82	9.04	9.04	8.85
13	7.03	7.45	7.95	8.10	7.88	8.91	9.18	9.46	8.80	9.09	9.07	8.82
14	6.02	7.49	7.98	8.20	7.91	8.93	9.22	9.48	8.78	9.15	9.17	8.77
15	6.07	7.51	7.99	8.19	7.73	8.99	9.27	9.54	8.80	9.22	9.25	8.75
16	6.12	7.50	8.00	8.16	7.83	9.03	9.29	9.47	8.82	9.26	9.20	8.72
17	6.25	7.51	7.94	8.25	7.91	9.08	9.32	9.49	8.81	9.30	9.08	8.70
18	6.40	7.53	7.96	8.31	7.98	9.11	9.21	9.50	8.04	9.33	9.16	8.64
19	6.50	7.55	7.99	8.37	8.07	9.04	9.23	9.46	8.16	9.21	9.01	8.65
20	6.58	7.58	8.02	8.42	8.16	9.12	9.27	9.36	8.25	9.17	8.90	8.19
21	6.67	7.60	8.05	8.47	8.25	9.17	9.31	9.37	8.31	8.96	8.93	6.27
22	6.76	7.62	8.00	8.54	8.33	9.21	9.31	9.37	8.25	9.05	8.30	6.10
23	6.78	7.66	8.04	8.53	8.38	9.20	9.33	9.34	8.22	9.04	7.96	6.41
24	6.79	7.68	8.04	8.59	8.45	9.21	9.36	9.32	8.27	9.05	8.18	6.61
25	6.86	7.69	8.05	8.65	8.51	9.21	9.39	9.31	8.30	9.13	8.00	6.73
26	6.90	7.66	8.09	8.70	8.56	9.22	9.41	9.24	8.17	9.16	8.15	6.68
27	6.93	7.64	8.16	8.75	8.61	8.75	9.42	9.19	8.21	8.95	8.30	6.73
28	6.94	7.67	8.18	8.80	8.65	8.75	9.43	9.17	8.26	8.88	8.44	6.71
29	6.93	7.69	8.17	8.83	---	8.84	9.45	9.14	8.35	8.97	8.54	6.74
30	6.94	7.69	8.18	8.87	---	8.91	9.44	9.11	8.44	9.04	8.62	6.81
31	6.98	---	8.20	8.87	---	8.97	---	9.07	---	9.10	8.62	---
MEAN	6.84	7.45	7.96	8.36	8.26	8.93	9.24	9.40	8.61	8.99	8.82	7.95

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 8.40 HIGHEST 5.93 OCT. 14, 1997 LOWEST 9.58 MAY 11, 12, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

181550065593200. Local number, 50.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'50", long 65°59'32", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 1.36 mi northwest of Gurabo plaza, 0.70 mi north of Estación Experimental Agrícola, and 2.42 mi southwest of Escuela José M. Gallardo. Owner: Gurabo Agricultural Experimental Station, Name: Gurabo.

AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 13 in (0.34 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-145 ft (0-44.2 m). Depth 145 ft (44.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 148 ft (45.1 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 12 in (0.30 m) casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1960 to March 1985, September 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.6 ft (3.86 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 9, 1975; lowest water level measured, 44.4 ft (13.5 m), below land-surface datum, June 18, 1975.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	30.50	---	29.20	30.68	---	30.48	29.99	29.09	28.73	31.46	33.02	30.96
2	30.46	---	29.21	30.82	---	30.54	30.04	28.63	29.04	31.15	33.02	30.99
3	30.34	---	29.20	30.93	---	30.60	30.07	25.77	29.28	31.98	33.04	31.11
4	30.24	---	29.19	31.04	---	30.68	30.16	26.67	29.39	32.52	33.09	31.05
5	30.17	---	29.21	30.81	---	30.78	30.15	28.66	29.62	32.86	33.15	31.09
6	30.14	---	29.26	30.63	---	30.67	30.11	29.36	29.58	33.11	33.17	31.05
7	30.09	---	29.35	30.14	---	29.32	30.13	29.76	29.68	33.22	33.20	31.07
8	30.06	---	29.42	29.79	---	29.42	30.10	28.18	29.76	33.85	32.79	31.01
9	30.00	---	29.30	29.61	---	29.74	30.09	27.49	29.91	33.59	32.47	31.08
10	29.97	---	29.44	29.41	---	29.83	30.08	27.02	30.88	33.69	32.24	31.05
11	29.94	---	29.56	29.28	---	29.82	30.11	27.30	31.47	33.80	32.14	31.08
12	29.90	---	29.62	29.13	---	29.84	30.09	27.30	31.81	33.92	32.05	31.08
13	29.96	---	29.67	29.03	29.83	29.85	30.11	26.72	32.03	34.07	31.98	31.08
14	28.44	---	29.74	28.98	29.84	29.86	30.08	24.20	32.21	34.13	31.96	31.14
15	28.29	---	29.80	28.93	29.82	29.88	30.00	26.41	32.28	34.28	32.00	31.17
16	28.41	---	29.86	28.84	29.83	29.89	29.95	26.74	32.52	34.37	32.06	31.20
17	28.71	26.48	29.93	28.79	29.82	29.99	29.87	26.90	32.13	34.44	32.10	31.29
18	28.88	28.38	29.98	28.78	29.45	30.05	29.85	26.97	31.44	34.54	31.93	31.30
19	28.94	28.79	30.05	28.78	27.96	30.08	29.89	27.02	31.10	34.61	31.94	31.37
20	28.99	29.03	30.09	28.80	28.48	30.13	29.89	27.06	30.79	34.65	31.95	31.36
21	28.98	29.18	30.15	28.82	29.32	29.49	29.56	27.12	31.32	34.33	31.83	31.72
22	29.05	29.26	30.24	28.88	29.72	29.65	29.88	27.17	31.59	34.13	31.70	25.80
23	29.10	29.28	30.33	28.98	29.96	29.84	26.74	27.32	31.73	33.96	31.76	23.80
24	29.19	29.27	28.56	29.02	30.13	29.89	25.31	27.36	31.86	33.79	31.70	22.87
25	29.24	29.23	28.17	29.06	30.24	30.03	28.22	27.40	31.95	33.65	30.22	22.36
26	29.30	29.22	27.96	29.15	30.31	30.05	29.09	27.52	32.02	33.52	29.71	22.07
27	29.33	29.25	27.85	29.21	30.41	30.02	29.48	28.53	32.09	33.43	30.72	21.94
28	29.40	29.27	27.84	---	30.45	29.98	29.67	28.67	32.13	33.26	30.81	21.86
29	29.44	29.24	28.17	---	---	29.90	29.81	29.12	32.11	33.19	30.88	23.97
30	28.43	29.20	29.90	---	---	29.94	29.84	27.51	31.88	33.11	30.90	26.92
31	---	---	30.44	---	---	29.94	---	28.28	---	33.05	30.89	---
MEAN	29.46	28.93	29.38	29.49	29.72	29.94	29.61	27.52	31.08	33.54	31.95	28.86

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 30.03 HIGHEST 21.77 SEPT. 29, 1998 LOWEST 34.67 JULY 20, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

182515065594100. Local number, 222.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'15", long 65°59'41", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 3.56 mi northwest of Carolina plaza, 1.21 mi northwest of Escuela Extensión El Comandante, and 0.74 mi southwest of Escuela Vistamar. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Campo Rico TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Surficial Deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m), above land-surface datum. Prior July 28, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.10 ft (0.94 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1986 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 4.33 ft (1.32 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 6, 1995; lowest water level recorded, 7.42 ft (2.26 m), below land-surface datum, Feb. 9, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.45	5.68	5.55	5.62	5.55	5.18	5.51	5.72	5.48	5.64	5.74	5.68
2	5.40	5.70	5.60	5.73	5.62	5.33	5.52	5.68	5.48	5.66	5.68	5.63
3	5.42	5.74	5.66	5.75	5.69	5.48	5.52	5.67	5.54	5.68	5.76	5.61
4	5.33	5.86	5.77	5.76	5.55	5.49	5.55	5.60	5.52	5.65	5.78	5.61
5	5.43	5.91	5.84	5.72	5.27	5.45	5.54	5.60	5.57	5.59	5.78	5.42
6	5.58	5.97	5.83	5.57	5.32	5.33	5.52	5.62	5.54	5.66	5.76	5.30
7	5.70	5.96	5.76	5.38	5.31	5.40	5.51	5.63	5.53	5.61	5.65	5.23
8	5.68	5.84	5.76	5.45	5.19	5.43	5.55	5.56	5.50	5.67	5.56	5.18
9	5.78	5.83	5.69	5.34	5.16	5.45	5.56	5.56	5.53	5.58	5.49	5.16
10	5.80	5.86	5.64	5.28	5.21	5.41	5.58	5.64	5.50	5.53	5.57	5.30
11	5.67	5.83	5.62	5.27	5.28	5.31	5.57	5.64	5.48	5.43	5.55	5.39
12	5.52	5.69	5.64	5.27	5.33	5.29	5.55	5.63	5.45	5.41	5.65	5.49
13	5.42	5.56	5.58	5.31	5.40	5.36	5.54	5.65	5.40	5.38	5.76	5.58
14	5.21	5.55	5.54	5.46	5.37	5.46	5.59	5.59	5.37	5.48	5.82	5.58
15	5.01	5.48	5.46	5.56	5.35	5.49	5.59	5.54	5.40	5.56	5.82	5.64
16	5.01	5.51	5.63	5.69	5.49	5.51	5.60	5.55	5.48	5.61	5.82	5.60
17	5.32	5.63	5.64	5.78	5.51	5.60	5.60	5.57	5.57	5.64	5.82	5.55
18	5.45	5.74	5.71	5.74	5.48	5.68	5.60	5.61	5.56	5.66	5.78	5.42
19	5.59	5.81	5.92	5.69	5.48	5.66	5.61	5.62	5.60	5.66	5.61	5.25
20	5.70	5.85	6.00	5.68	5.49	5.61	5.61	5.66	5.67	5.60	5.54	5.21
21	5.79	5.82	5.98	5.64	5.51	5.55	5.61	5.58	5.65	5.62	5.25	5.07
22	5.84	5.88	5.89	5.49	5.43	5.49	5.49	5.56	5.70	5.58	5.31	5.10
23	5.89	5.90	5.84	5.52	5.32	5.46	5.45	5.51	5.57	5.50	5.27	5.17
24	6.01	5.79	5.78	5.46	5.23	5.47	5.46	5.48	5.55	5.46	5.16	5.14
25	6.03	5.70	5.76	5.45	5.15	5.47	5.43	5.40	5.55	5.50	5.35	5.37
26	5.96	5.62	5.71	5.44	5.11	5.51	5.43	5.40	5.58	5.56	5.35	5.49
27	5.88	5.54	5.70	5.41	4.91	5.48	5.54	5.42	5.60	5.56	5.41	5.49
28	5.89	5.56	5.63	5.43	5.01	5.47	5.65	5.42	5.57	5.64	5.54	5.56
29	5.82	5.57	5.56	5.30	---	5.43	5.69	5.42	5.61	5.67	5.60	5.58
30	5.75	5.54	5.58	5.41	---	5.40	5.70	5.48	5.59	5.68	5.66	---
31	5.72	---	5.59	5.43	---	5.43	---	5.49	---	5.74	5.74	---
MEAN	5.61	5.73	5.71	5.52	5.35	5.45	5.56	5.56	5.54	5.59	5.60	5.41

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 5.55 HIGHEST 4.56 SEPT. 21, 22, 1998 LOWEST 6.4 NOW. 14, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

181540065580300. Local number, CJ-TW18.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'40", long 65°58'03", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.75 mi northeast of the intersection of Hwy 181 with Hwy 30, 0.88 mi south of the intersection of Hwy 943 with Hwy 181, and 0.01 mi west of Hwy 181. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CJ-TW18.

AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), 0-65.0 ft (0-19.8 m), screened 25-65 ft (7.62-19.8 m). Depth 65.0 ft (19.8 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 164.0 ft (50.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.65 ft (1.11 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on June 23, 1997. Found destroyed due to construction in the area. Since then, tape down measurements only.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 23, 1997 to November 19, 1997. Found destroyed, temporally discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 12.08 ft (3.68 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 16, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 15.81 ft (4.82 m) below land-surface datum, July 15, 16, 17, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.74	15.04	14.37
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.75	15.07	14.42
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.76	15.09	14.42
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.77	15.10	14.48
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.78	15.13	14.53
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.79	15.16	14.58
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.78	15.19	14.62
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.78	15.22	14.69
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.79	15.26	14.74
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.79	15.28	14.80
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.78	15.23	14.87
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.78	15.23	14.87
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.78	15.23	14.81
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.79	15.18	14.81
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.80	15.20	14.79
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.81	15.25	14.81
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.81	15.25	14.84
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.79	15.23	14.90
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.79	15.25	14.92
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.77	15.29	14.94
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.74	15.32	14.97
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.37	15.06	14.98
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.77	15.23	14.79	15.00
24	---	---	---	---	15.68	---	---	---	---	15.13	14.66	15.02
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.64	15.07	14.34	15.04
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.64	15.05	14.29	14.98
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.65	15.04	14.28	14.82
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.67	15.06	14.28	14.74
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.69	15.01	14.29	14.74
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.72	15.02	14.32	14.71
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.01	14.35	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.68	15.56	14.96	14.77

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 15.15 HIGHEST 14.28 AUG. 27, 28, 29, 1997 LOWEST 15.81 JULY 15. 16, 17, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14.72	13.74	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	14.54	13.91	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	14.39	13.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	14.35	13.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	14.35	14.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	14.35	14.12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	14.36	14.15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	14.40	14.20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	14.42	14.30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	14.47	14.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
11	14.51	13.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	14.49	13.93	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	14.48	13.93	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	12.25	13.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	12.27	13.95	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	12.14	13.96	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	12.14	13.99	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	12.21	14.08	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	12.32	14.12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	12.43	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	12.54	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	12.68	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	12.82	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	12.93	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	13.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	13.16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	13.27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	13.39	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	13.56	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	13.65	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	13.71	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	13.50	14.02	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 13.69 HIGHEST 12.08 OCT. 16, 1997 LOWEST 14.74 OCT. 1, 2, 1997

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level						
Feb. 19	14.39	Feb. 20	14.47	Mar. 24	15.46	June 15	14.80

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

18151306554601. Local number, CJ-TW3B.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'13", long 65°55'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.86 mi east of Gurabo plaza, 3.57 mi southwest of Hwy 186 km 4.7, and 1.39 mi southwest of Hwy 185 km 15.7. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CJ-TW3B.

AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-38 ft (0-11.6 m) screened 25-35 ft (7.62 m). Depth 38.0 ft (11.6 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 187 ft (57.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of casing 2.95 ft (0.90 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 10.64 ft (3.24 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 11, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 20.31 ft (6.19 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 19, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	19.27	18.02	18.29	18.70	18.75	17.97	18.54	18.50	18.81	18.90	---	---
2	19.27	18.04	18.31	18.71	18.76	18.02	18.56	18.50	18.82	18.90	---	---
3	19.28	18.05	18.34	18.71	18.76	18.04	18.57	18.53	18.82	18.90	---	---
4	19.28	18.07	18.34	18.73	18.76	18.06	18.58	18.55	18.82	18.90	---	16.41
5	19.28	18.08	18.34	18.74	18.72	18.08	18.59	18.58	18.82	18.90	---	16.39
6	19.27	18.09	18.35	18.75	18.63	18.08	18.60	18.59	18.82	18.90	---	16.36
7	19.26	18.10	18.38	18.75	18.55	18.09	18.63	18.62	18.82	18.90	---	16.35
8	19.26	18.11	18.39	18.75	18.48	18.11	18.64	18.63	18.82	18.90	---	16.34
9	19.26	18.12	18.38	18.74	18.40	18.12	18.66	18.63	18.82	18.90	---	16.34
10	19.26	18.13	18.39	18.74	18.30	18.14	18.67	18.63	18.82	18.90	---	16.34
11	19.26	18.12	18.40	18.71	18.20	18.14	18.68	18.60	18.82	18.90	---	16.34
12	19.25	18.10	18.41	18.70	18.12	18.16	18.69	18.57	18.82	18.90	---	16.35
13	19.22	18.09	18.41	18.69	18.10	18.24	18.72	18.56	18.82	18.90	---	16.39
14	18.92	18.09	18.42	18.68	18.07	18.24	18.72	18.56	18.82	18.90	---	16.43
15	18.54	18.09	18.43	18.67	18.04	18.24	18.73	18.56	18.82	---	---	16.44
16	18.34	18.10	18.45	18.65	17.97	18.25	18.74	18.57	18.85	---	---	16.44
17	18.18	18.11	18.47	18.64	17.94	18.29	18.75	18.59	18.85	---	---	16.44
18	18.10	18.13	18.49	18.64	17.91	18.30	18.76	18.62	18.85	---	---	16.47
19	18.04	18.13	18.52	18.63	17.88	18.33	18.78	18.63	18.85	---	---	16.48
20	17.98	18.13	18.53	18.63	17.85	18.34	18.80	18.65	18.85	---	---	16.48
21	17.96	18.14	18.54	18.64	17.85	18.35	18.75	18.67	18.85	---	---	---
22	17.95	18.15	18.57	18.65	17.85	18.37	18.69	18.68	18.85	---	---	---
23	17.96	18.17	18.58	18.67	17.85	18.39	18.64	18.69	18.85	---	---	---
24	17.96	18.17	18.59	18.68	17.86	18.40	18.59	18.70	18.85	---	---	---
25	17.96	18.19	18.60	18.69	17.89	18.42	18.56	18.72	18.86	---	---	---
26	17.96	18.21	18.62	18.69	17.91	18.43	18.54	18.73	18.87	---	---	---
27	17.96	18.24	18.63	18.71	17.93	18.44	18.52	18.75	18.87	---	---	---
28	17.96	18.26	18.64	18.71	17.95	18.47	18.51	18.76	18.87	---	---	---
29	17.96	18.26	18.65	18.72	---	18.48	18.50	18.77	18.90	---	---	---
30	17.96	18.29	18.67	18.73	---	18.50	18.50	18.78	18.92	---	---	---
31	17.97	---	18.69	18.74	---	18.51	---	18.80	---	---	---	---
MEAN	18.58	18.13	18.48	18.70	18.19	18.26	18.64	18.64	18.84	18.90	---	16.40

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 18.40 HIGHEST 15.92 SEPT. 21, 1998 LOWEST 19.28 OCT. 2-5, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HERRERA TO RIO ANTON RUIZ BASINS

182344065490801. Local number, RE-2A.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'44", long 65°49'08", Hydrologic Unit 2101005, 0.35 mi west of Hwy 187, 1.30 mi southwest of the intersection of Hwy 187 with Hwy 3, and 1.83 mi south of Punta San Agustín. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD,

Name: Río Espíritu-2A.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-22.0 ft (0-6.70 m), screened 3.00-22.0 ft (0.90-6.70 m). Depth 22.0 ft (6.7 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 5.78 ft (41.8 m), above mean sea level, from survey.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 5.60 ft (1.71 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on December 24, 1996 replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on January 14, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 24, 1996 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 0.41 ft (0.12 m), below land-surface datum, Feb. 2, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 6.02 ft (1.83 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 19, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	1.68	1.29	2.04	3.32	4.38	5.00	5.50	5.77	---
2	---	---	---	1.80	.44	2.08	3.36	4.41	5.02	5.53	5.77	---
3	---	---	---	1.88	.69	2.16	3.36	4.44	5.06	5.55	5.78	---
4	---	---	---	1.97	.95	2.23	3.43	4.47	5.06	5.55	5.79	---
5	---	---	---	2.04	.93	2.28	3.47	4.53	5.07	5.58	5.84	---
6	---	---	---	2.10	1.18	2.28	3.50	4.55	5.10	5.58	5.84	---
7	---	---	---	2.15	1.09	2.32	3.53	4.58	5.12	5.59	5.84	---
8	---	---	---	2.20	.84	2.35	3.55	4.59	5.13	5.59	5.88	---
9	---	---	---	2.26	.99	2.43	3.59	4.64	5.13	5.60	5.88	---
10	---	---	---	2.30	.96	2.45	3.64	4.64	5.16	5.63	5.88	---
11	---	---	---	2.36	.91	2.53	3.71	4.67	5.18	5.63	5.88	---
12	---	---	---	2.40	1.09	2.55	3.74	4.70	5.20	5.65	5.90	---
13	---	---	---	2.45	1.01	2.59	3.75	4.72	5.22	5.66	5.90	---
14	---	---	---	2.49	1.17	2.66	3.81	4.72	5.22	5.68	5.91	---
15	---	---	---	2.52	1.12	2.68	3.83	4.73	5.22	5.69	5.91	---
16	---	---	---	2.56	1.35	2.72	3.86	4.73	5.23	5.71	5.96	---
17	---	---	---	2.59	1.53	2.74	3.87	4.78	5.26	5.71	5.96	---
18	---	---	---	2.63	1.66	2.78	3.92	4.81	5.28	5.72	5.96	---
19	---	---	---	2.67	1.74	2.80	3.97	4.84	5.29	5.72	5.99	---
20	---	---	---	2.71	1.83	2.84	4.02	4.87	5.29	5.72	---	---
21	---	---	---	2.70	1.86	2.87	4.02	4.88	5.32	5.72	---	---
22	---	---	---	2.15	1.56	2.93	4.08	4.90	5.34	5.72	---	---
23	---	---	---	1.10	1.42	2.96	4.12	4.93	5.35	5.72	---	---
24	---	---	2.36	.77	1.51	3.02	4.14	4.96	5.35	5.74	---	---
25	---	---	2.30	.66	1.57	3.05	4.19	4.96	5.38	5.75	---	---
26	---	---	2.30	.91	1.72	3.09	4.23	4.97	5.43	5.75	---	5.61
27	---	---	2.31	1.17	1.84	3.16	4.26	4.99	5.43	5.75	---	5.42
28	---	---	2.28	1.37	1.93	3.17	4.28	4.99	5.43	5.75	---	5.35
29	---	---	2.19	1.40	---	3.25	4.34	5.00	5.43	5.75	---	5.32
30	---	---	1.65	1.52	---	3.26	4.35	5.00	5.47	5.77	---	5.27
31	---	---	1.60	1.62	---	3.30	---	5.00	---	5.77	---	---
MEAN	---	---	2.12	1.97	1.29	2.70	3.84	4.75	5.24	5.67	5.88	5.39

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 3.82 HIGHEST 0.41 FEB. 2, 1997 LOWEST 6.02 AUG. 19, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HERRERA TO RIO ANTON RUIZ BASINS--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.22	3.29	2.14	3.52	2.91	3.11	2.47	---	---	---	---	---
2	5.19	3.32	2.27	3.57	2.91	3.13	2.38	---	---	---	---	---
3	5.10	3.35	2.34	3.57	3.00	3.16	2.29	---	---	---	---	---
4	5.02	3.41	2.40	3.58	3.01	3.21	2.25	---	---	---	---	---
5	4.99	3.41	2.45	3.58	2.67	3.21	2.31	---	---	---	---	---
6	4.97	3.47	2.52	3.42	2.57	2.89	2.36	---	---	---	---	---
7	4.93	3.50	2.54	2.61	2.53	2.85	2.46	---	---	---	---	---
8	4.93	3.52	2.64	2.29	2.55	1.63	2.53	---	---	---	---	---
9	4.91	3.56	2.70	2.22	2.46	1.63	2.56	---	---	---	---	---
10	4.91	3.59	2.70	2.16	2.41	1.63	2.64	---	---	---	---	---
11	4.93	3.61	2.79	2.16	2.41	1.63	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	4.45	3.64	2.84	2.20	2.46	1.63	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	4.12	3.64	2.88	2.27	2.52	1.63	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	3.21	3.67	2.90	1.95	2.56	1.66	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	2.77	3.67	2.93	1.90	2.61	1.68	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	2.68	3.70	2.96	1.99	2.67	1.71	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	2.65	3.73	3.03	2.08	2.70	1.77	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	2.65	3.73	3.05	2.16	2.70	1.81	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	2.65	3.73	3.09	2.25	2.76	1.93	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	2.70	3.73	3.15	2.31	2.82	2.04	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	2.70	3.65	3.16	2.38	2.82	2.05	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	2.80	3.56	3.21	2.42	2.86	2.09	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	2.86	3.56	3.24	2.47	2.91	2.17	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	2.89	3.54	3.27	2.55	2.94	2.23	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	2.96	3.54	3.33	2.56	2.94	2.32	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	3.01	2.70	3.37	2.64	2.95	2.34	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	3.07	2.13	3.37	2.70	3.04	2.40	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	3.11	2.07	3.42	2.70	3.06	2.46	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	3.17	2.07	3.44	2.73	---	2.52	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	3.25	2.07	3.49	2.79	---	2.53	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	3.25	---	3.51	2.86	---	2.50	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	3.74	3.34	2.94	2.60	2.74	2.24	2.42	---	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 2.91 HIGHEST 1.63 MAR. 8-13, 1998 LOWEST 5.22 OCT. 1, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HERRERA TO RIO ANTON RUIZ BASINS

182223065455900. Local number, RM-02.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'23", long 65°45'59", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.06 mi south of Hwy 2 and 0.27 mi east of Hwy 181.

Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Pozo Río Mameyes No. 02.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled piezometer well, constructed in 1993 as part of a study of northeast of Puerto Rico, diameter 2 in (0.05 m), screened 13-24.0 ft (3.96-7.32 m). Depth 24.0 ft (7.32 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic Data Logger (EDL)--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land surface datum is about 20.0 ft (6.10 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: On shelter floor, 6.65 ft (2.03 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on Sept. 25, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 25, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.35 ft (2.85 m), below land-surface datum, June 1, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 14.08 ft (4.29 m), below land-surface datum, May 26, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12.74	---	---	---	13.94	14.00	12.82	13.36	9.37	---	13.61	---
2	11.93	---	---	13.97	13.96	14.00	12.94	13.48	9.37	---	13.76	---
3	11.62	---	---	13.96	13.96	14.00	12.86	13.54	9.82	---	13.82	12.43
4	11.69	---	---	13.85	13.97	14.06	12.88	13.58	10.52	---	13.84	12.31
5	11.87	---	---	13.73	13.39	14.06	13.06	13.58	11.06	---	13.91	12.37
6	11.91	---	---	13.39	13.04	12.49	13.14	13.58	11.11	---	14.03	---
7	11.91	---	---	12.32	12.94	12.05	13.31	13.64	11.84	13.55	14.03	12.50
8	12.42	---	---	---	12.97	9.48	13.50	13.72	12.01	---	13.97	---
9	12.73	---	---	---	13.06	10.05	13.50	13.73	12.44	13.27	13.87	---
10	12.73	---	---	---	13.10	10.69	13.63	13.72	12.50	12.99	13.82	---
11	12.83	---	---	---	13.25	11.20	13.72	13.73	12.83	12.94	13.82	---
12	12.53	---	---	---	13.36	11.50	13.81	13.81	12.97	12.94	13.88	---
13	12.28	---	---	---	13.45	12.01	13.63	13.87	12.77	13.09	13.94	---
14	11.57	---	---	---	13.58	12.38	13.57	13.94	12.62	13.33	13.96	---
15	11.57	---	---	---	13.67	12.50	13.50	13.84	12.74	13.45	13.99	---
16	11.57	---	---	---	13.72	12.50	12.19	13.64	11.56	13.46	13.99	---
17	11.57	---	---	---	13.78	12.94	10.34	13.63	11.42	13.50	13.99	---
18	11.57	---	---	---	13.88	13.13	10.84	13.63	11.77	13.59	13.99	---
19	11.57	---	---	---	13.88	13.19	---	13.72	11.98	13.55	13.96	---
20	11.72	---	---	---	13.97	13.31	---	13.78	12.01	13.42	13.89	---
21	12.04	---	---	---	13.96	13.33	---	13.87	12.34	12.83	13.78	---
22	12.28	---	---	---	13.96	13.34	---	13.93	12.50	12.64	13.58	---
23	12.50	---	---	---	13.96	13.40	---	13.97	12.73	12.68	13.46	---
24	12.70	---	---	13.89	13.93	13.50	---	14.00	12.94	12.86	13.45	---
25	12.83	---	---	13.94	13.87	13.54	---	14.05	13.09	12.92	12.02	---
26	12.89	---	---	13.96	13.89	13.57	---	14.08	13.24	12.94	11.35	---
27	12.98	---	---	13.99	13.93	13.59	---	13.91	13.34	13.09	11.54	---
28	13.13	---	---	13.99	13.93	13.53	12.99	13.88	---	13.22	11.80	---
29	13.14	---	---	13.99	---	13.59	13.09	13.85	---	13.40	11.96	---
30	---	---	---	13.88	---	12.91	13.25	9.37	---	13.43	---	---
31	---	---	---	13.87	---	12.83	---	9.37	---	13.58	---	---
MEAN	12.24	---	---	13.77	13.65	12.80	12.98	13.48	11.96	13.19	13.48	12.40
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 13.01	HIGHEST 9.35	JUNE 1, 1998	LOWEST 14.08	MAY 26, 1998							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HERRERA TO RIO ANTON RUIZ BASINS

181217065453000. Local number, ARR-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'17", long 65°45'30", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.01 mi south of Hwy 927 at Km 8.0 and 0.62 mi south of Hwy 31. Owner: Carlos Arroyo, Name: Arroyo TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 16.0 ft (4.87 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor, 4.80 ft (1.46 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on Oct. 26, 1997. Well is affected by stage in nearby Rio Blanco.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 26, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 4.95 ft (1.51 m), below land-surface datum, Jan. 7, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 10.65 ft (3.25 m), below land-surface datum, Apr. 6, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	9.42	8.41	9.84	9.77	9.93	10.34	---	---	---	---	---
2	---	9.39	8.74	9.33	9.81	9.96	10.30	---	---	---	---	---
3	---	9.50	8.88	9.61	9.85	9.98	10.41	---	---	---	---	---
4	---	9.57	8.97	9.41	9.88	10.03	10.54	---	---	---	---	---
5	---	9.53	9.09	9.28	7.27	10.08	10.61	---	---	---	---	---
6	---	9.39	9.20	7.29	8.64	10.13	10.65	---	---	---	---	---
7	---	9.51	9.24	5.66	8.91	10.13	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	---	9.71	9.31	7.30	8.98	9.98	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	---	9.38	9.38	7.91	8.27	10.13	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	---	6.34	9.45	7.06	8.72	10.20	---	---	---	---	---	---
11	---	7.92	9.54	7.63	8.92	10.26	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	---	8.29	9.68	7.84	8.87	10.31	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	---	8.46	9.72	8.04	9.06	10.33	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	---	8.62	9.75	8.06	9.15	10.36	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	---	8.80	9.78	8.45	9.03	10.16	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	---	8.49	9.82	8.65	9.22	10.16	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	---	8.33	9.72	8.83	9.29	10.28	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	---	8.64	9.74	8.87	9.35	10.36	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	---	8.47	9.54	8.93	9.41	10.40	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	---	8.85	9.71	9.09	9.46	10.44	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	---	8.55	9.25	9.18	9.58	10.21	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	---	8.96	9.40	9.25	9.67	10.35	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	---	9.08	9.54	9.32	9.70	10.33	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	---	8.99	9.26	9.36	9.75	10.47	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	---	9.20	9.47	9.38	9.81	10.53	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	---	6.15	9.66	9.45	9.85	10.52	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	---	7.40	9.69	9.56	9.88	10.39	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	---	8.10	9.74	9.64	9.90	10.39	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	9.29	8.41	9.78	9.67	---	10.34	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	9.34	8.12	9.83	9.70	---	10.42	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	9.39	---	9.87	9.73	---	10.09	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	9.34	8.65	9.46	8.75	9.29	10.25	10.47	---	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 9.33 HIGHEST 4.95 JAN. 7, 1998 LOWEST 10.65 APR. 6, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HERRERA TO RIO ANTON RUIZ BASINS

182138065431800. Local number, RS-02.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'38", long 65°43'18", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.87 mi southwest of Hwy 3, 0.39 mi south of the intersection of Hwy 992 with Hwy 991, 0.39 mi north of Hwy 983, and 0.07 mi east of Hwy 991. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Río Sabana No. 02.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-56.0 ft (0-17.1 m), screened 2.56-56.0 ft (0.78-17.1 m). Depth 56.0 ft (17.1 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 33.9 ft (10.3 m), above mean sea level, from topographic survey.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.34 ft (1.02 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 22, 1995 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 0.91 ft (0.28 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 14, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 7.13 ft (2.17 m), below land-surface datum, July 9-13, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.20	5.64	4.26	6.08	6.17	6.31	5.80	6.20	3.70	6.20	5.66	5.05
2	3.06	5.66	4.50	6.00	6.19	6.33	5.68	6.24	3.96	6.26	5.74	5.11
3	3.02	5.76	4.70	6.00	6.23	6.38	5.53	6.30	4.30	6.28	5.88	4.99
4	3.53	5.84	4.84	5.96	6.27	6.40	5.75	6.32	4.62	6.26	5.94	5.11
5	4.05	5.85	5.00	5.83	4.83	6.42	5.90	6.32	4.95	5.58	5.96	5.19
6	4.53	5.83	5.10	5.33	4.43	5.54	5.98	6.37	5.17	5.70	6.00	5.25
7	4.91	5.87	5.22	4.15	4.57	4.64	6.11	6.39	5.31	5.64	5.90	5.33
8	5.21	5.95	5.32	3.79	4.92	4.03	6.11	6.39	5.51	5.60	5.88	5.27
9	4.07	5.95	5.40	4.05	4.50	4.21	6.13	6.33	5.59	4.92	5.88	5.33
10	3.73	3.71	5.46	4.31	4.64	4.53	6.20	6.33	5.57	4.74	5.93	5.33
11	3.91	3.01	5.42	4.49	4.94	4.89	6.26	6.39	5.75	4.84	5.99	5.47
12	3.01	3.43	5.44	4.73	5.16	5.20	6.27	6.43	5.84	5.08	5.91	5.65
13	2.59	3.83	5.54	4.91	5.40	5.30	5.99	6.48	5.46	5.28	5.85	5.75
14	1.47	4.21	5.56	4.69	5.54	5.48	5.92	6.42	5.34	5.40	5.81	5.33
15	2.37	4.52	5.60	4.85	5.50	5.28	5.98	4.60	5.54	5.60	5.83	5.25
16	2.85	4.66	5.70	5.04	5.66	5.50	5.19	4.22	5.12	5.58	5.97	4.51
17	3.23	4.74	5.74	5.20	5.72	5.71	4.44	4.42	4.86	5.56	6.03	4.55
18	3.59	4.92	5.74	5.34	5.84	5.73	4.58	4.82	4.92	5.50	5.89	4.63
19	3.85	4.84	5.78	5.46	5.93	5.87	4.80	5.14	4.99	5.54	5.85	4.57
20	4.13	4.40	5.84	5.56	5.99	5.95	5.00	5.38	5.03	5.42	5.73	4.49
21	4.41	4.50	5.86	5.68	5.99	5.96	4.97	5.59	5.25	5.02	5.59	4.51
22	4.64	4.68	5.84	5.72	6.05	6.00	5.15	5.75	5.19	5.06	5.41	1.69
23	4.86	4.88	5.88	5.82	6.09	6.14	5.43	5.89	5.23	5.22	5.35	2.49
24	5.04	4.98	5.94	5.90	6.18	6.18	5.61	5.99	5.45	5.00	5.45	3.03
25	5.16	5.04	6.00	5.94	6.20	6.19	5.79	6.09	5.63	4.96	3.49	3.33
26	5.26	4.66	6.08	5.96	6.24	6.21	5.89	5.77	5.79	5.06	3.57	3.61
27	5.42	3.46	6.10	6.03	6.27	6.24	5.93	5.51	5.90	5.18	3.95	3.85
28	5.54	3.64	6.14	6.07	6.31	6.26	6.01	5.72	5.96	5.30	4.25	4.03
29	5.66	3.94	6.16	6.11	---	5.73	6.06	5.68	6.06	5.44	4.45	4.23
30	5.74	4.12	6.18	6.05	---	5.53	6.14	4.14	6.14	5.56	4.63	4.33
31	5.66	---	6.12	6.09	---	5.60	---	3.34	---	5.58	4.87	---
MEAN	4.18	4.75	5.56	5.39	5.63	5.67	5.69	5.71	5.27	5.43	5.44	4.58

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 5.27 HIGHEST 0.91 OCT. 14, 1997 LOWEST 6.48 MAY 13, 14, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HERRERA TO RIO ANTON RUIZ BASINS

182131065241100. Local number, RP-04.

LOCATION.--Lat. 18°21'31", long. 65°24'11", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 1.39 mi southeast of the intersection of Hwy 992 with Hwy 3, 0.40 mi southeast of the intersection of Hwy 983 with Hwy 3, 0.12 mi northwest of the intersection with Hwy 940 with Hwy 983, and 0.03 mi southwest of Hwy 983. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Río Pitahaya No. 04.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-39.0 ft (0-11.9 m), screened 4.00-39.0 ft (1.20-11.9 m). Depth 39.0 ft (11.9 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 82.1 ft (25.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic survey.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 4.18 ft (1.27 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 15, 1995 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 0.91 ft (0.28 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 18, 1995; lowest water level recorded, 14.05 ft (4.28 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 21, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	11.65	8.26	2.27	4.62	5.11	7.29	6.62	7.66	5.59	6.93	7.27	6.65
2	10.40	8.11	2.23	4.70	4.64	7.70	6.72	8.77	5.47	8.05	7.41	6.62
3	9.57	8.11	2.30	4.16	4.72	6.54	6.79	8.08	5.23	7.32	7.46	6.51
4	9.15	9.72	2.34	4.84	4.08	7.85	6.85	7.96	5.66	7.21	8.60	6.56
5	9.22	9.92	6.31	4.77	3.94	8.17	6.93	8.00	5.75	6.92	8.91	6.60
6	9.63	10.06	6.63	4.14	3.78	8.18	7.03	8.17	5.91	6.88	8.73	6.62
7	8.58	10.24	3.65	3.09	3.09	7.44	7.15	8.09	5.98	6.53	9.12	6.66
8	9.69	10.36	3.05	3.09	3.11	3.71	7.30	8.10	6.11	6.26	8.22	6.68
9	7.98	10.53	2.87	3.12	2.34	4.93	7.32	6.47	6.29	7.61	7.90	6.78
10	8.34	8.94	2.52	2.60	2.10	5.37	7.37	6.25	6.26	6.83	7.84	6.84
11	8.46	7.89	2.68	3.06	2.33	5.52	7.45	8.83	6.38	6.48	7.88	6.93
12	8.07	5.85	2.63	3.22	2.35	5.45	7.52	8.40	6.46	6.61	7.93	6.94
13	6.62	3.97	2.62	2.97	2.77	5.51	7.55	8.36	6.45	6.71	7.98	7.05
14	6.77	3.48	2.65	3.12	2.93	4.68	7.56	8.45	6.40	7.85	7.99	6.84
15	6.09	6.10	3.12	3.12	2.95	4.99	7.59	6.71	6.50	8.37	7.82	6.74
16	5.02	6.91	2.82	3.12	3.00	5.24	7.50	5.89	6.46	8.34	8.06	6.46
17	5.97	7.09	3.55	3.13	3.03	5.39	7.20	5.74	6.40	8.35	8.19	6.42
18	6.44	7.63	3.46	3.22	2.52	4.46	7.20	5.78	6.49	8.36	8.18	6.40
19	5.88	7.69	4.39	3.23	---	4.90	7.23	5.86	6.29	8.31	8.17	6.33
20	7.40	7.03	4.55	3.23	---	5.34	7.06	5.98	6.15	8.13	8.10	6.32
21	7.70	7.33	4.59	3.23	---	5.51	7.04	6.02	6.20	7.80	8.89	7.56
22	7.95	7.41	3.74	3.64	---	5.67	7.11	5.96	6.08	6.76	9.32	3.66
23	8.05	7.49	3.33	3.74	---	6.66	7.20	6.08	6.10	6.13	9.43	2.74
24	8.22	7.57	4.09	3.88	5.45	6.73	7.24	6.24	6.16	6.61	9.46	2.47
25	8.56	6.34	3.98	3.91	5.62	6.80	7.26	6.37	6.23	6.71	8.36	2.37
26	8.84	5.98	4.74	4.40	5.75	6.86	7.35	6.22	4.57	6.78	8.10	2.31
27	9.78	3.88	4.87	4.70	6.05	6.89	7.36	5.97	6.73	6.83	6.88	2.26
28	9.67	2.98	4.88	4.25	6.39	6.92	7.44	6.08	4.97	6.96	6.66	2.25
29	9.69	2.69	3.94	4.23	---	6.85	7.52	6.11	7.31	7.07	6.62	2.26
30	9.06	2.44	3.71	4.26	---	6.62	7.62	5.83	6.82	6.87	6.57	2.22
31	8.62	---	4.61	4.89	---	6.59	---	5.58	---	7.12	6.61	---
MEAN	8.29	7.07	3.65	3.73	3.83	6.15	7.24	6.90	6.11	7.22	8.02	5.43

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 6.18 HIGHEST 2.08 FEB. 10, 1998 LOWEST 12.18 OCT. 1, 2, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HERRERA TO RIO ANTON RUIZ BASINS

181823065401900. Local number, RF-04.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'23", long 65°40'19", Hydrologic Unit 2101005, 1.72 mi southwest of the intersection of Hwy 3 with Hwy 976, 1.44 mi west of Hwy 3, 1.33 mi northwest of Hwy 982, and 0.49 mi south of Hwy 976. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Río Fajardo No. 04.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m) 0-40.0 ft (0-12.2 m), screened 20-40 ft (6.1-12.2 m). Depth 40.0 ft (12.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 86.3 ft (26.3 m), above mean sea level, from topographic survey.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.50 ft (1.07 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on May 22, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 31, 1993 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 10.70 ft (3.26 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 14, 15, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 18.82 ft (5.74 m), below land-surface datum, July 21-25, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	13.63	14.22	---	15.88	16.02	16.17	16.67	17.28	---	---	---	---
2	12.67	14.34	---	15.90	16.11	16.29	16.66	17.46	---	---	---	---
3	12.48	14.41	---	15.93	16.17	16.36	16.69	17.63	---	---	---	---
4	12.68	14.51	---	15.94	16.22	16.46	16.72	17.80	---	---	---	---
5	12.86	14.59	---	15.94	15.35	16.54	16.76	17.96	---	---	---	---
6	13.01	14.64	---	15.94	14.45	16.59	16.79	18.10	---	---	---	---
7	13.18	14.70	---	14.30	14.26	16.65	16.75	18.21	---	---	---	---
8	13.32	14.74	---	12.87	14.26	16.37	16.75	18.32	---	---	---	---
9	13.44	14.73	---	12.83	13.71	16.28	16.78	18.41	---	---	---	---
10	13.00	12.27	---	12.92	13.52	16.28	16.81	18.47	---	---	---	---
11	12.95	---	---	13.06	13.58	16.30	16.88	18.55	---	---	---	---
12	13.01	---	---	13.22	13.76	16.34	17.01	18.61	---	---	---	---
13	12.83	---	---	13.41	13.93	16.44	17.12	18.68	---	---	---	---
14	10.70	---	---	13.58	14.06	16.53	17.21	18.77	---	---	---	---
15	10.88	---	---	13.76	14.25	16.44	17.33	18.61	---	---	---	---
16	11.37	---	14.93	13.95	14.43	16.27	17.33	17.56	---	---	---	---
17	11.80	---	14.98	14.11	14.64	16.23	16.31	16.84	---	---	---	---
18	12.09	---	15.10	14.29	14.80	16.25	15.91	16.80	---	---	---	---
19	12.45	---	15.23	14.48	14.94	16.28	15.86	16.83	---	---	---	---
20	12.68	---	15.30	14.66	15.07	16.34	15.90	17.04	---	---	---	---
21	12.87	---	15.38	14.80	15.22	16.42	15.94	17.28	---	---	---	---
22	13.04	---	15.46	14.94	15.42	16.49	16.00	17.60	---	---	---	---
23	13.20	---	15.51	15.10	15.54	16.56	16.03	17.52	---	---	---	---
24	13.36	---	15.56	15.25	15.69	16.59	16.03	17.31	---	---	---	---
25	13.51	---	15.62	15.41	15.75	16.67	16.06	17.13	---	---	---	---
26	13.68	---	15.65	15.57	15.87	16.77	16.25	17.03	---	---	---	---
27	13.80	---	15.68	15.66	15.98	16.85	16.47	17.06	---	---	---	---
28	13.92	---	15.73	15.76	16.06	16.93	16.68	17.25	---	---	---	---
29	14.03	---	15.75	15.82	---	17.00	16.89	17.40	---	---	---	---
30	14.12	---	15.80	15.89	---	17.00	17.09	17.95	---	---	---	---
31	14.13	---	15.84	15.96	---	16.81	---	18.46	---	---	---	---
MEAN	12.93	14.31	15.47	14.75	14.97	16.50	16.59	17.74	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 15.51 HIGHEST 10.70 OCT. 14, 15, 1997 LOWEST 18.81 MAY 15, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HERRERA TO RIO ANTON RUIZ BASINS

181917065382701. Local number, RF-12.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'17", long 65°38'27", Hydrologic Unit 2101005, 1.20 mi northwest of Punta Barrancas, 0.81 mi east of Hwy 3, 0.82 mi south of Hwy 195, and 0.61 mi east of Hwy 194. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Río Fajardo No. 12.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-34.0 ft (0-10.4 m), screened 3.75-34.0 ft (1.14-10.4 m). Depth 34.0 ft (10.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 13.7 ft (4.18 m), above mean sea level, from topographic survey.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 4.16 ft (1.27 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 11, 1995 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.71 ft (0.83 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 14, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 10.64 ft (3.24 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 21, 22, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.97	5.61	3.73	5.86	5.89	5.58	6.47	4.87	5.37	6.32	6.81	7.05
2	7.34	5.66	3.91	5.88	5.93	5.65	6.50	4.97	5.46	6.38	6.89	7.09
3	6.97	5.74	4.02	5.90	5.97	5.76	6.53	5.13	5.28	6.45	6.94	7.14
4	6.97	5.81	4.20	5.93	6.02	5.83	6.55	5.23	5.24	6.50	7.03	7.21
5	7.05	5.85	4.34	5.93	3.90	5.88	6.38	5.34	5.32	5.97	7.10	7.26
6	7.14	5.89	4.45	5.92	3.91	5.94	5.27	5.45	5.41	6.04	7.16	7.32
7	7.18	5.93	4.59	5.21	4.18	5.98	5.33	5.53	5.51	6.10	7.23	7.35
8	7.21	5.96	4.69	4.65	4.49	6.01	5.46	5.60	5.58	6.14	7.29	---
9	7.22	5.99	4.76	4.66	3.00	5.99	5.58	5.62	5.66	6.10	7.33	---
10	7.04	4.94	4.86	4.79	3.23	6.04	5.63	5.65	5.64	6.13	7.38	---
11	6.82	4.46	4.92	4.91	3.66	6.09	5.72	5.68	5.65	6.19	7.48	---
12	6.80	4.56	4.98	4.93	3.96	6.17	5.78	5.76	5.67	6.27	7.54	---
13	6.29	4.71	5.05	4.99	4.14	6.25	5.81	5.83	5.69	6.35	7.62	---
14	2.74	4.86	5.13	5.06	4.30	6.30	5.78	5.88	5.69	6.39	7.67	---
15	2.97	4.95	5.19	5.12	4.42	6.31	5.75	5.91	5.70	6.50	7.76	---
16	3.25	5.02	5.24	5.19	4.54	6.24	4.50	5.68	5.76	6.56	7.83	---
17	3.60	5.10	5.28	5.25	4.65	6.18	4.12	5.58	5.73	6.62	7.89	---
18	3.87	5.15	5.32	5.30	4.75	6.17	4.29	5.60	5.66	6.65	7.92	---
19	4.04	5.16	5.38	5.35	4.83	6.20	4.60	5.63	5.65	6.65	7.95	---
20	4.20	5.05	5.44	5.41	4.91	6.23	4.85	5.66	5.67	6.64	8.01	---
21	4.37	5.04	5.47	5.44	4.97	6.24	3.67	5.69	5.72	6.56	8.02	---
22	4.55	5.08	5.49	5.48	5.05	6.29	2.92	5.72	5.77	6.55	8.04	---
23	4.72	5.16	5.47	5.56	5.13	6.34	3.16	5.77	5.82	6.57	8.07	---
24	4.87	5.12	5.49	5.58	5.20	6.35	3.57	5.86	5.87	6.56	8.09	---
25	4.98	5.03	5.55	5.60	5.27	6.36	3.91	5.91	5.91	6.40	7.44	---
26	5.10	4.97	5.59	5.63	5.37	6.38	4.17	5.69	5.96	6.40	7.18	---
27	5.19	2.84	5.62	5.66	5.44	6.36	4.33	5.33	6.02	6.46	7.03	---
28	5.29	3.06	5.66	5.69	5.54	6.38	4.45	5.24	6.08	6.51	6.95	---
29	5.39	3.31	5.72	5.76	---	6.39	4.62	5.30	6.16	6.60	6.95	---
30	5.47	3.55	5.80	5.79	---	6.39	4.76	5.35	6.27	6.67	6.96	---
31	5.55	---	5.83	5.84	---	6.42	---	5.31	---	6.74	6.99	---
MEAN	5.55	4.99	5.07	5.43	4.74	6.15	5.02	5.54	5.70	6.42	7.44	7.20

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 5.68 HIGHEST 2.71 OCT. 14, 1997 LOWEST 8.09 AUG. 23, 24, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES BASINS

180358065503700. Local number, YDO-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'58", long 65°50'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 2.01 mi east of Central Roig, 1.37 mi north of Yabucoa Sun Oil Refinery, and 0.19 mi east of Hwy 53. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Yabucoa Deep Observation.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled piezometer well, constructed in 1993 as part of study of Valle de Yabucoa, diameter 2 in (0.05 m), screened in brackish water, 320-340 ft (97.5-104 m). Depth 350 ft (107 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 2.00 ft (0.61 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 7.30 ft (2.22 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on September 16, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 16, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 0.51 ft (0.15 m), below land-surface datum, Mar. 2, 3, 4, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 5.83 ft (1.78 m), below land-surface datum, June 10-17, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	3.69	---	---	1.83	---	.54	2.94	4.48	5.78	5.82	5.77	---
2	3.05	---	---	1.83	---	.51	3.04	4.49	5.78	5.82	5.77	---
3	3.93	---	---	1.83	---	.51	3.06	4.54	5.78	5.82	5.77	---
4	3.97	---	---	1.86	---	.51	3.08	4.63	5.82	5.82	5.77	---
5	3.95	---	---	1.86	---	.57	3.08	4.77	5.82	5.82	5.77	---
6	3.86	---	---	---	---	.70	3.13	4.81	5.82	5.82	5.77	---
7	3.77	---	---	---	---	.81	3.13	4.89	5.82	5.82	5.77	---
8	3.67	---	---	---	---	1.08	3.08	4.92	5.82	5.82	5.77	---
9	3.55	---	---	---	---	1.30	3.01	5.01	5.82	5.82	5.77	---
10	3.36	---	---	---	---	1.30	3.00	5.05	5.82	5.82	5.77	---
11	3.35	---	---	---	---	1.35	3.12	5.07	5.83	5.82	5.77	---
12	3.28	---	---	---	---	1.41	3.15	5.11	5.83	5.82	5.77	---
13	3.01	---	---	---	---	1.57	3.15	5.14	5.83	5.82	5.77	---
14	1.06	---	---	---	---	1.65	3.35	5.26	5.83	5.82	5.77	---
15	2.80	---	---	---	---	1.75	3.49	5.26	5.83	5.82	---	---
16	2.80	---	---	---	---	1.69	3.58	5.29	5.83	5.82	---	---
17	2.75	---	---	---	---	1.71	3.64	5.31	5.82	5.82	---	---
18	2.69	---	---	---	---	1.83	3.78	5.34	5.82	5.82	---	---
19	2.68	---	---	---	---	1.93	3.81	5.43	5.82	5.82	---	---
20	2.57	---	---	---	---	1.94	3.85	5.55	5.82	5.82	---	---
21	2.48	---	---	---	1.86	1.92	3.94	5.56	5.82	5.81	---	---
22	2.47	---	---	---	1.59	2.05	3.97	5.59	5.82	5.81	---	---
23	2.44	---	---	---	1.32	2.14	4.00	5.64	5.82	5.79	---	---
24	2.44	---	---	---	1.14	2.33	4.05	5.64	5.82	5.79	---	---
25	---	---	---	---	.99	2.44	4.14	5.64	5.82	5.79	---	---
26	---	---	---	---	.82	2.49	4.15	5.64	5.82	5.79	---	---
27	---	---	---	---	.66	2.49	4.15	5.64	5.82	5.79	---	---
28	---	---	---	---	.55	2.64	4.35	5.64	5.82	5.79	---	---
29	---	---	---	---	---	2.76	4.39	5.71	5.82	5.77	---	---
30	---	---	1.81	---	---	2.82	4.47	5.74	5.82	5.77	---	---
31	---	---	1.83	---	---	2.85	---	5.74	---	5.77	---	---
MEAN	3.07	---	1.82	1.84	1.12	1.66	3.57	5.24	5.82	5.81	5.77	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 4.14 HIGHEST .51 MAR. 2, 3, 4, 1998 LOWEST 5.83 JUNE 10-17, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES

180415065513900. Local number, 96.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'15", long 65°51'39", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.44 mi northwest of Escuela Eugenio María de Hostos 4.67 mi southwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad Luciano, and 3.93 mi southwest of Escuela Asunción López. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: USGS TW-2 or Yabucoa 7.
 AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 0-10 ft (0-3.05 m), diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased about 0-183 ft (0-55.8 m), perforated 56-81 ft (17.1-24.7 m), 102-123 ft, (31.1-37.5 m), 144-181 ft (43.9-55.2 m). Depth 181 ft (55.2 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 25 ft (7.62 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 4.00 ft (1.22 m), above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 25, 1978 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.67 ft (2.95 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 28.29 ft (8.62 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 20, 1980.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	20.64	18.25	18.18	18.38	18.18	16.52	19.75	21.39	20.33	21.71	21.59	20.10
2	20.15	18.34	18.09	18.33	18.16	16.41	19.82	21.39	20.30	21.73	21.52	20.09
3	20.05	18.49	18.06	18.36	18.14	16.32	19.85	21.43	20.43	21.78	21.41	19.99
4	20.12	18.55	18.06	18.46	18.18	16.26	19.83	21.56	20.41	21.44	21.33	19.95
5	20.39	18.62	18.06	18.52	18.20	16.27	19.95	21.66	20.41	21.19	21.30	19.93
6	20.46	18.64	18.08	17.79	18.16	16.39	20.06	21.73	20.42	21.19	21.10	19.76
7	20.36	18.67	18.13	17.86	18.23	16.68	20.12	21.74	20.56	21.27	21.01	19.58
8	20.09	18.72	18.03	17.96	18.29	17.06	19.97	21.73	20.72	21.37	20.96	19.52
9	20.13	18.76	17.96	17.85	18.28	17.17	19.97	21.77	20.82	21.42	20.98	19.52
10	20.38	18.63	17.77	17.68	18.35	17.16	20.09	21.83	20.97	21.68	21.04	19.07
11	20.52	18.79	17.49	17.48	18.51	17.34	20.31	21.84	21.09	21.77	21.07	18.93
12	20.56	18.87	17.50	17.39	18.63	17.38	20.43	21.84	21.21	21.74	21.00	18.90
13	20.32	18.89	17.75	17.36	18.73	17.63	20.47	21.96	21.18	21.66	20.90	18.79
14	19.16	18.95	17.97	17.38	18.81	17.59	20.67	21.98	21.24	21.78	20.82	18.99
15	19.49	18.92	18.00	17.40	18.75	17.50	20.83	22.01	21.32	22.11	20.80	19.17
16	18.96	18.87	18.07	17.46	18.68	17.45	20.89	22.08	21.29	22.27	20.77	19.14
17	17.86	18.79	18.13	17.47	18.61	17.61	20.89	22.09	21.24	22.40	20.76	19.18
18	17.59	18.75	18.23	17.45	18.31	17.64	20.93	22.09	21.22	22.45	20.74	19.31
19	17.43	18.76	18.29	17.40	18.09	17.69	20.99	22.19	21.09	22.43	20.70	19.31
20	17.29	18.46	18.32	17.43	17.97	17.79	21.04	21.92	21.03	22.68	20.74	19.10
21	17.13	18.37	18.38	17.42	17.89	17.79	21.12	21.71	21.06	22.79	20.81	18.96
22	17.06	18.38	18.33	17.57	17.65	18.01	21.15	21.66	21.08	22.85	20.84	16.39
23	17.08	18.46	18.34	17.69	17.39	18.07	21.17	21.68	21.17	22.89	20.78	15.13
24	17.17	18.54	18.34	17.77	17.19	18.19	21.22	21.72	21.29	22.84	20.71	14.00
25	17.27	18.63	18.33	17.83	17.08	18.28	21.35	21.77	21.36	22.82	20.11	13.10
26	17.48	18.67	18.33	17.89	16.89	18.36	21.39	21.82	21.38	22.67	20.22	12.41
27	17.59	18.60	18.44	17.95	16.76	18.50	21.38	21.80	21.46	22.49	20.14	11.60
28	17.68	18.55	18.50	18.02	16.62	18.87	21.41	21.80	21.57	22.22	19.86	10.78
29	17.70	18.42	18.51	18.10	---	19.16	21.38	---	21.65	21.84	19.68	10.18
30	17.94	18.29	18.51	18.14	---	19.41	21.39	---	21.66	21.71	19.89	9.78
31	18.16	---	18.45	18.16	---	19.66	---	---	---	21.65	19.99	---
MEAN	18.85	18.62	18.15	17.80	18.03	17.62	20.66	21.79	21.03	22.03	20.76	17.36

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 19.38 HIGHEST 9.67 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 22.90 JULY 23, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES BASINS

175855066023100. Local number, FID-2.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'55", long 66°02'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.25 mi north of Hwy 3 @ km 128.5, and 1.74 mi northeast of Arroyo plaza. Owner: Santón Trucking, Name: Fidel 2

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Unused water-table well, diameter 15 in (0.38 m). Depth 116 ft (35.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 41.0 ft (12.5 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor, 3.12 ft (0.95 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on December 11, 1996.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 11, 1996 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 21.39 ft (6.52 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 5, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 27.88 ft (8.50 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 16-28, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	25.62	24.87	25.20	25.70	25.10	25.05	24.71	25.82	26.25
2	---	---	---	25.64	24.64	25.25	25.71	25.20	25.10	24.73	25.88	26.33
3	---	---	---	25.63	24.55	25.26	25.66	25.27	25.01	24.75	25.81	26.37
4	---	---	---	25.51	24.57	25.28	25.64	25.31	25.07	24.82	25.67	26.45
5	---	---	---	25.29	24.68	25.27	25.64	25.34	25.15	24.91	25.55	26.53
6	---	---	---	25.13	24.35	25.34	25.62	25.37	25.22	24.98	25.44	26.61
7	---	---	---	25.01	24.43	25.39	25.59	25.38	25.24	25.01	25.33	26.69
8	---	---	---	24.79	24.52	25.41	25.59	25.53	25.30	25.02	25.28	26.76
9	---	---	---	24.75	24.62	25.44	25.61	25.60	25.35	25.05	25.23	26.86
10	---	---	---	24.92	24.70	25.49	25.65	25.62	25.38	25.08	25.08	26.94
11	---	---	25.89	25.03	24.75	25.52	25.63	25.70	25.39	25.13	24.90	26.99
12	---	---	25.88	25.07	24.83	25.53	25.59	25.66	25.38	25.15	24.77	27.04
13	---	---	25.86	25.13	24.91	25.51	25.51	25.67	25.37	25.21	24.88	27.04
14	---	---	25.83	25.18	24.95	25.46	25.34	25.60	25.36	25.26	24.97	27.03
15	---	---	25.81	25.16	25.02	25.40	25.20	25.45	25.35	25.28	25.04	26.80
16	---	---	25.79	25.05	25.08	25.38	25.13	25.40	25.32	25.29	25.10	26.62
17	---	---	25.81	25.02	25.13	25.39	25.07	25.34	25.26	25.31	25.21	26.65
18	---	---	25.84	25.00	25.19	25.36	25.09	25.32	25.29	25.36	25.28	26.72
19	---	---	25.77	25.01	25.24	25.41	25.01	25.29	25.20	25.38	25.41	26.78
20	---	---	25.66	24.98	25.28	25.48	25.03	25.23	25.06	25.40	25.54	26.87
21	---	---	25.51	25.00	25.21	25.50	25.08	25.12	25.03	25.36	25.65	26.89
22	---	---	25.47	25.02	25.08	25.55	25.05	25.05	25.01	25.36	25.64	26.55
23	---	---	25.45	25.03	25.14	25.58	25.00	25.03	25.00	25.39	25.53	26.54
24	---	---	25.54	25.08	25.15	25.60	24.92	25.02	24.95	25.41	25.63	26.60
25	---	---	25.58	25.10	25.09	25.62	24.87	25.03	24.93	25.44	25.71	25.54
26	---	---	25.60	25.15	25.19	25.64	24.91	25.13	24.82	25.51	25.76	25.43
27	---	---	25.61	24.99	25.18	25.66	24.89	25.22	24.73	25.57	25.82	25.43
28	---	---	25.61	25.17	25.14	25.69	24.95	24.79	24.75	25.59	25.90	24.95
29	---	---	25.61	25.12	---	25.67	24.99	24.74	24.68	25.64	25.98	25.04
30	---	---	25.61	25.13	---	25.70	25.05	24.81	24.72	25.70	26.07	25.30
31	---	---	25.60	25.02	---	25.70	---	24.94	---	25.76	26.17	---
MEAN	---	---	25.68	25.12	24.91	25.47	25.29	25.27	25.12	25.24	25.49	26.42

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 25.39 HIGHEST 24.34 FEB. 6, 1997 LOWEST 27.05 SEPT. 13, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES BASINS

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	25.49	23.73	---	---	24.10	24.67	25.17	25.90	26.88	27.29	27.69	27.87
2	25.66	23.76	---	---	24.14	24.71	25.19	25.89	26.94	27.18	27.75	27.87
3	25.81	23.86	---	---	24.18	24.74	25.28	25.87	27.00	27.07	27.78	27.87
4	23.27	23.96	---	---	24.21	24.68	25.36	25.87	27.05	27.10	27.80	27.87
5	21.45	24.04	---	---	24.20	24.73	25.43	25.91	27.10	27.15	27.83	27.87
6	21.56	---	---	---	24.02	24.76	25.50	25.93	27.16	27.21	27.87	27.87
7	21.94	---	---	---	24.07	24.74	25.59	25.91	27.21	27.28	27.87	27.87
8	22.25	---	---	23.57	24.12	24.79	25.58	25.92	27.26	27.35	27.87	27.87
9	22.47	---	---	23.65	24.16	24.82	25.51	25.98	27.30	27.42	27.87	27.87
10	22.68	---	---	23.52	24.25	24.84	25.47	26.03	27.34	27.50	27.87	27.87
11	22.87	---	---	23.55	24.33	24.86	25.46	26.09	27.38	27.55	27.87	27.87
12	23.16	---	---	23.47	24.37	24.89	25.47	26.16	27.43	27.60	27.87	27.87
13	23.36	---	---	23.49	24.40	24.90	25.48	26.21	27.48	27.66	27.87	27.87
14	23.55	---	---	23.51	24.45	24.87	25.51	26.25	27.53	27.65	27.87	27.87
15	23.52	---	---	23.68	24.40	24.84	25.57	26.31	27.57	27.75	27.87	27.87
16	23.54	---	---	23.80	24.41	24.88	25.62	26.36	27.61	27.78	27.87	---
17	23.57	---	24.11	23.82	24.39	24.93	25.56	26.40	27.60	27.79	27.88	---
18	22.31	---	24.16	23.91	24.38	24.93	25.44	26.46	27.60	27.80	27.88	---
19	22.34	---	24.19	23.98	24.42	24.93	25.46	26.51	27.57	27.82	27.88	---
20	22.52	---	24.19	24.05	24.46	24.92	25.56	26.55	27.56	27.81	27.88	---
21	22.68	---	24.20	24.09	24.49	24.88	25.64	26.60	27.57	27.65	27.88	---
22	22.72	---	24.22	24.13	24.57	24.95	25.68	26.67	27.57	27.59	27.88	---
23	22.86	---	24.17	24.15	24.60	24.98	25.59	26.71	27.59	27.57	27.88	---
24	22.96	---	24.05	24.17	24.63	25.05	25.60	26.78	27.61	27.54	27.88	---
25	23.01	---	24.10	24.12	24.67	25.05	25.64	26.82	27.63	27.53	27.88	---
26	23.11	---	24.03	24.10	24.68	25.10	25.67	26.71	27.67	27.53	27.88	---
27	23.20	---	23.93	24.12	24.64	25.10	25.72	26.62	27.70	27.53	27.88	---
28	23.29	---	23.93	24.14	24.66	25.10	25.77	26.68	27.62	27.54	27.87	---
29	23.41	---	23.55	23.97	---	25.06	25.82	26.71	27.52	27.56	27.87	---
30	23.52	---	---	23.99	---	25.14	25.86	26.74	27.39	27.60	27.87	---
31	23.62	---	---	24.04	---	25.15	---	26.78	---	27.64	27.87	---
MEAN	23.15	23.87	24.06	23.88	24.37	24.90	25.54	26.33	27.41	27.52	27.86	27.87

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 25.72 HIGHEST 21.39 OCT. 5, 1997 LOWEST 16-28, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES

175855066050500. Local number, ALG-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'55", long 66°05'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.97 mi east-southeast of the intersection of Hwy 16 with Hwy 3, 1.00 mi west of the intersection of Hwy 3 with Hwy 178, and 0.04 mi south of Hwy 3. Owner: PR Land

Authority, Name: Algarrobos.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well. Depth 57.0 ft (17.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 89.0 ft (27.1 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 2.95 ft (0.90 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 24, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 24, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 18.19 ft (5.54 m), below land-surface datum, June 26, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 33.85 ft (10.32 m), below land-surface datum, July 2, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.19	31.70	24.01	25.16	30.99	31.68
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.23	31.08	25.11	26.03	31.09	31.88
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.26	30.16	22.34	26.79	30.67	32.05
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.28	29.26	19.90	26.87	30.30	32.23
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.30	29.27	20.07	27.04	30.19	32.41
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.33	29.39	22.41	27.26	30.13	32.56
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.35	29.61	23.85	27.43	30.07	32.71
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.37	28.68	23.29	27.65	30.08	32.83
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.39	29.20	22.27	27.85	30.06	32.97
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.42	29.48	22.04	28.16	29.69	33.09
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.45	29.06	22.89	28.40	29.37	33.20
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.48	29.24	25.73	28.43	24.58	33.30
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.50	29.92	26.22	28.46	21.88	33.36
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.52	30.18	24.22	28.21	24.98	33.22
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.55	30.11	23.75	27.95	26.36	32.73
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.58	30.14	25.60	28.05	23.54	32.08
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.60	30.04	23.54	28.32	21.78	31.67
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.63	28.92	24.92	28.64	21.64	31.24
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.66	27.81	26.15	28.98	25.40	30.79
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.67	26.11	23.93	29.21	26.62	30.30
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.69	25.22	20.67	29.29	26.99	29.35
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.72	26.57	20.46	29.28	27.22	28.38
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.58	26.64	20.97	29.07	27.61	27.45
24	---	---	---	---	---	32.88	32.80	23.62	19.77	28.92	28.53	26.58
25	---	---	---	---	---	32.93	31.56	24.88	18.70	29.05	29.20	27.32
26	---	---	---	---	---	32.97	30.84	25.45	18.22	29.25	29.75	28.85
27	---	---	---	---	---	33.01	30.74	25.75	18.78	29.53	30.19	29.26
28	---	---	---	---	---	33.06	31.25	26.05	20.39	29.80	30.57	29.81
29	---	---	---	---	---	33.10	31.85	26.13	23.19	29.97	30.91	30.23
30	---	---	---	---	---	33.14	31.99	20.44	24.93	30.33	31.20	30.58
31	---	---	---	---	---	33.17	---	22.25	---	30.67	31.44	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	33.03	33.03	27.82	22.61	28.39	28.16	31.14

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 28.71 HIGHEST 18.19 JUNE 26, 1997 LOWEST 33.72 APR. 22, 23, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	30.87	29.34	29.41	31.72	31.99	32.84	33.70	21.29	27.47	33.79	26.44	32.08
2	31.10	29.46	29.48	31.79	32.02	32.89	33.71	22.23	27.22	33.84	28.10	32.11
3	31.28	29.58	29.58	31.86	32.06	32.93	33.71	24.80	27.10	33.73	29.12	32.15
4	31.48	28.93	29.65	31.92	32.10	32.97	33.71	25.43	27.63	33.37	29.81	32.19
5	31.66	27.77	29.74	31.98	32.14	33.00	33.71	23.43	28.28	32.18	30.33	32.23
6	31.83	26.83	29.82	32.02	32.17	33.03	33.70	23.28	28.98	31.42	30.81	32.28
7	31.98	26.33	29.91	32.01	32.19	33.05	33.69	24.59	29.64	31.16	31.16	32.30
8	32.11	25.98	30.00	32.02	32.20	33.10	33.69	25.58	30.19	30.89	31.48	32.10
9	32.24	25.75	29.99	32.01	32.21	33.14	33.69	26.89	30.62	30.71	31.74	31.90
10	32.39	25.24	29.52	31.97	32.23	33.17	33.69	27.89	30.99	30.57	31.97	31.64
11	32.48	25.63	29.14	31.95	32.25	33.20	33.69	28.50	31.30	30.32	32.17	31.50
12	32.60	26.23	28.96	31.92	32.29	33.23	33.70	29.03	31.57	29.09	32.38	31.41
13	32.69	26.71	29.29	31.89	32.33	33.27	33.70	29.58	31.79	27.91	32.55	31.37
14	32.12	27.08	29.76	31.85	32.36	33.30	33.70	30.03	31.99	27.33	32.72	31.28
15	29.66	27.41	30.02	31.81	32.38	33.34	33.70	30.43	32.16	27.90	32.88	31.14
16	28.41	27.67	30.20	31.78	32.40	33.37	33.70	30.76	32.35	28.12	33.01	31.03
17	27.70	27.87	30.32	31.75	32.42	33.39	33.70	31.05	32.50	27.86	33.14	30.94
18	27.37	28.05	30.43	31.73	32.43	33.42	33.70	31.31	32.64	27.53	33.26	30.89
19	27.25	28.20	30.56	31.71	32.47	33.44	33.71	31.54	32.78	27.47	33.36	30.86
20	27.19	28.32	30.66	31.70	32.51	33.49	33.71	31.71	32.90	27.37	33.45	30.83
21	27.26	28.46	30.76	31.70	32.54	33.52	33.71	31.75	33.01	26.85	33.55	30.79
22	27.48	28.59	30.87	31.70	32.57	33.54	33.71	30.92	33.11	26.40	33.64	24.97
23	27.75	28.70	30.96	31.72	32.61	33.56	33.57	30.05	33.22	25.07	33.71	20.51
24	27.99	28.80	31.04	31.74	32.64	33.58	31.57	30.04	33.30	23.99	33.77	21.39
25	28.22	28.88	31.14	31.76	32.69	33.61	29.55	30.14	33.37	25.08	32.97	22.40
26	28.44	28.99	31.22	31.79	32.73	33.62	28.26	29.96	33.44	26.35	32.49	23.13
27	28.63	29.06	31.31	31.81	32.77	33.64	27.00	30.24	33.52	26.52	32.19	23.52
28	28.80	29.16	31.40	31.85	32.81	33.66	25.34	30.34	33.59	26.23	32.04	23.77
29	28.96	29.24	31.49	31.89	---	33.67	24.55	30.23	33.67	24.41	32.02	23.93
30	29.08	29.31	31.57	31.92	---	33.68	22.59	29.52	33.73	24.04	32.03	24.08
31	29.23	---	31.63	31.96	---	33.69	---	28.14	---	25.07	32.06	---
MEAN	29.88	27.92	30.32	31.85	32.38	33.33	32.13	28.41	31.47	28.47	31.95	29.02

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 30.58 HIGHEST 20.51 SEPT. 23, 1998 LOWEST 33.85 JULY 2, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES BASINS

1757280660722000. Local number, BAR-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°57'28", long 66°07'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.65 mi west of Central Machete. 0.75 mi northwest of Playita Machete, 2.00 mi south of the intersection of Hwy 15 with Hwy 3, and 1.13 mi southeast of intersection of Hwy 710 with Hwy 3. Owner: PR Land Authority, Name: Barranca.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Hand-dug unused water-table well. Depth 38.0 ft (11.7 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 59.1 ft (18.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 4.60 ft (1.40 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on April 3, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 3, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 20.33 ft (6.20 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 24.21 ft (7.38 m), below land-surface datum, June 7, 8, 9, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.81	24.15	24.03	22.72	22.18
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.83	24.16	23.99	22.66	22.19
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.42	23.84	24.17	23.97	22.61	22.20
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.44	23.86	24.18	23.94	22.55	22.21
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.46	23.87	24.19	23.91	22.49	22.23
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.48	23.88	24.20	23.87	22.44	22.24
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.49	23.89	24.20	23.84	22.40	22.25
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.51	23.91	24.21	23.79	22.36	22.26
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.52	23.92	24.21	23.76	22.33	22.28
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.53	23.93	24.20	23.72	22.30	22.30
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.55	23.94	24.20	23.70	22.27	22.31
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.56	23.95	24.19	23.68	22.25	22.33
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.58	23.96	24.19	23.65	22.23	22.34
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.59	23.97	24.19	23.62	22.20	22.36
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.61	23.98	24.19	23.59	22.18	22.38
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.62	23.99	24.18	23.56	22.17	22.40
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.63	24.00	24.17	23.51	22.16	22.42
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.65	24.01	24.17	23.48	22.15	22.44
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.66	24.02	24.17	23.45	22.15	22.45
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.68	24.02	24.16	23.40	22.15	22.46
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.69	24.03	24.16	23.36	22.15	22.48
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.70	24.04	24.15	23.31	22.15	22.50
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.70	24.05	24.15	23.27	22.14	22.52
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.72	24.06	24.14	23.22	22.14	22.55
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.73	24.07	24.13	23.17	22.14	22.57
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.75	24.08	24.12	23.10	22.14	22.57
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.76	24.10	24.11	23.04	22.15	22.60
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.78	24.11	24.08	22.99	22.16	22.62
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.79	24.12	24.06	22.91	22.16	22.63
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.80	24.13	24.05	22.85	22.17	22.66
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.14	---	22.78	22.18	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.62	23.98	24.16	23.50	22.27	22.40

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 23.32 HIGHEST 22.13 AUG. 23, 1997 LOWEST 24.21 JUNE 7, 8, 9, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES BASINS--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	22.68	22.11	22.14	22.13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.42
2	22.69	22.11	22.13	22.14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.44
3	22.71	22.11	22.13	22.15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.45
4	22.73	22.11	22.12	22.16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.46
5	22.74	22.12	22.11	22.16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.48
6	22.76	22.12	22.10	22.17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.49
7	22.77	22.13	22.10	22.18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.50
8	22.79	22.13	22.09	22.19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.50
9	22.81	22.14	22.08	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.51
10	22.83	22.14	22.08	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.52
11	22.84	22.15	22.08	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.53
12	22.86	22.15	22.08	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.53
13	22.88	22.15	22.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.54
14	22.79	22.16	22.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.55
15	22.73	22.16	22.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.56
16	22.60	22.16	22.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.57
17	22.50	22.18	22.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.57
18	22.43	22.18	22.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.21	22.58
19	22.37	22.18	22.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.22	22.58
20	22.33	22.18	22.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.24	22.59
21	22.29	22.17	22.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.25	22.59
22	22.26	22.17	22.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.27	22.14
23	22.22	22.17	22.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.29	21.14
24	22.21	22.17	22.08	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.30	20.59
25	22.19	22.16	22.09	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.31	20.58
26	22.17	22.16	22.09	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.33	20.52
27	22.15	22.15	22.09	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.35	20.44
28	22.14	22.15	22.10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.36	20.39
29	22.13	22.15	22.11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.38	20.37
30	22.12	22.14	22.11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.40	20.34
31	22.11	---	22.12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.41	---
MEAN	22.51	22.15	22.09	22.16	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.31	21.98

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 22.20 HIGHEST 20.33 SEPT> 30, 1998 LOWEST 22.88 OCT. 13, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES BASINS

175719066085500. Local number, P-13

LOCATION.--Lat 17°57'19", long 66°08'55", Hydrologic Unit 2101004, 1.0 mi east of the intersection of Hwy 3 with Hwy 707, 0.28 mi south of Hwy 3, and 0.25 mi northwest of the Phillips Petroleum oil refinery. Owner: Phillips Petroleum, Name: Phillips Petroleum No. 13.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 33.0 ft (10.1 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.21 ft (0.98 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on April 15, 1998. Sampling performed on June 7, 1996 by private company.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 25, 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 14.47 ft (4.41 m), below land-surface datum, Mar. 22, 24, 1993; lowest water level recorded, 31.22 ft (9.52 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 24, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28.80	26.99	26.45	26.48	26.06	26.77	27.92	27.36	28.28	29.42	30.52	30.87
2	28.78	26.92	26.19	26.39	26.01	26.90	27.87	27.12	28.22	29.46	30.58	30.84
3	28.81	26.86	26.36	26.30	25.66	26.72	27.90	27.17	28.34	29.51	30.63	30.86
4	28.91	27.04	26.40	26.34	25.78	26.68	27.93	27.30	28.44	29.50	30.67	30.81
5	28.97	27.04	26.44	26.29	25.79	26.35	27.85	27.42	28.50	29.53	30.70	30.74
6	28.93	26.93	26.48	26.22	25.78	26.28	27.69	27.51	28.55	29.59	30.62	30.66
7	28.91	27.01	26.53	26.09	25.62	26.31	27.56	27.55	28.48	29.62	30.64	30.58
8	28.95	27.03	26.56	25.89	25.39	26.40	27.71	27.80	28.52	29.67	30.70	30.41
9	29.07	26.96	26.61	25.79	25.56	26.40	27.94	27.83	28.57	29.71	30.79	30.31
10	29.17	26.95	26.62	25.74	25.57	26.54	27.92	27.67	28.64	29.72	30.83	30.27
11	29.26	26.94	26.65	25.74	25.60	26.74	27.81	27.62	28.73	29.77	30.84	30.09
12	29.33	26.87	26.67	25.67	25.68	26.80	27.62	27.80	28.77	29.76	30.86	30.06
13	29.42	26.84	26.66	25.73	25.50	26.92	27.48	27.73	28.68	29.81	30.88	30.02
14	29.17	26.77	26.63	25.89	25.53	26.94	27.39	27.70	28.68	29.85	30.90	30.01
15	28.65	26.81	26.62	25.86	25.63	26.96	27.59	27.63	28.72	29.90	30.93	30.02
16	28.45	26.73	26.56	25.88	25.76	26.99	27.55	27.63	28.76	29.87	30.97	29.97
17	28.19	26.67	26.56	25.97	25.75	26.86	27.49	27.61	28.78	29.89	31.00	29.76
18	27.95	26.60	26.49	25.99	25.82	26.95	27.57	27.56	28.79	29.96	31.04	29.63
19	27.58	26.60	26.57	25.98	25.90	26.88	27.36	27.55	28.83	30.03	31.06	29.45
20	27.34	26.61	26.57	26.08	25.97	26.97	27.42	27.77	28.96	30.04	31.09	29.36
21	27.27	26.42	26.58	26.09	26.02	27.05	27.51	27.92	29.05	30.11	31.10	28.99
22	27.20	26.53	26.57	26.12	26.04	27.48	27.33	27.80	28.97	30.16	31.13	27.36
23	27.13	26.62	26.53	26.13	26.07	27.41	27.31	27.92	29.06	30.20	31.19	26.00
24	27.02	26.64	26.50	26.13	26.14	27.45	27.63	28.07	29.10	30.24	31.22	25.12
25	27.03	26.63	26.51	26.15	26.39	27.57	27.33	28.13	29.14	30.28	31.17	24.32
26	26.89	26.64	26.51	26.20	26.58	27.62	27.10	28.16	29.23	30.31	31.10	23.70
27	26.83	26.66	26.51	26.20	26.59	27.87	26.94	28.18	29.28	30.32	31.02	23.16
28	26.97	26.59	26.51	26.27	26.77	27.76	27.30	28.16	29.30	30.36	30.98	---
29	26.95	26.57	26.50	26.16	---	27.68	27.33	28.14	29.31	30.40	30.98	22.86
30	27.01	26.50	26.50	26.04	---	27.86	27.42	28.11	29.37	30.46	30.94	22.71
31	26.98	---	26.47	26.07	---	27.88	---	28.23	---	30.50	30.89	---
MEAN	28.13	26.77	26.53	26.06	25.89	27.03	27.56	27.75	28.80	29.93	30.90	28.58

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 27.84 HIGHEST 22.69 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 31.22 AUG. 24, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO QUEBRADA AGUAS VERDES

175858066100200. Local number, 6.
 LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'58", long 66°10'02", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 4.23 mi northeast of Central Aguirre Church, 4.08 mi northeast of Colegio del Perpetuo Socorro Church, and 1.77 mi northwest of Hwy 3 km 144.2. Owner: Doctor Bruno, Name: Juana 5.
 AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m). Depth 173 ft (52.74 m) reported, 110 ft (33.54 m) measured.
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 127 ft (38.7 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum. After Aug. 7, 1981, top of 16 in (0.41 m) casing, 1.55 ft (0.47 m), above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on April 15, 1998.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1960 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 26.20 ft (7.99 m), below land-surface datum, Dec. 10, 1979; lowest water level recorded, 65.95 ft (20.1 m), below land-surface datum, June 2, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	62.38	60.66	53.20	52.23	50.37	52.65	53.83	50.81	56.08	56.83	58.50	59.36
2	62.39	60.50	53.09	52.09	50.17	52.48	53.95	51.06	56.20	56.84	58.58	59.28
3	62.41	60.33	53.00	51.81	49.99	52.31	54.08	51.31	56.32	56.89	58.66	59.21
4	62.41	60.14	52.92	51.55	49.84	52.14	54.17	51.55	56.44	56.94	58.75	59.13
5	62.41	59.96	52.86	51.28	49.76	51.91	54.21	51.80	56.55	56.98	58.83	59.04
6	62.42	59.75	52.79	51.04	49.56	51.73	54.18	52.02	56.63	57.00	58.90	58.92
7	62.43	59.46	52.75	50.79	49.51	51.55	54.04	52.23	56.67	57.02	58.96	58.81
8	62.44	59.07	52.70	50.62	49.68	51.40	53.80	52.38	56.72	57.04	58.96	58.69
9	62.46	58.72	52.65	50.59	49.89	51.26	53.51	52.51	56.79	57.08	58.93	58.58
10	62.48	58.46	52.62	50.68	50.13	51.18	53.19	52.63	56.86	57.14	58.92	58.49
11	62.49	58.28	52.58	50.80	50.37	51.28	52.78	52.81	56.95	57.17	58.96	58.39
12	62.51	58.13	52.56	50.95	50.60	51.40	52.21	52.99	57.03	57.21	59.00	58.24
13	62.53	58.01	---	51.10	50.82	51.47	51.49	53.18	57.12	57.24	59.04	58.03
14	62.54	57.89	---	51.24	51.03	51.45	50.66	53.37	57.22	57.27	59.03	57.75
15	62.57	57.77	52.35	51.38	51.23	51.39	50.07	53.56	57.33	57.33	59.04	57.32
16	62.54	57.65	52.33	51.53	51.41	51.34	49.63	53.74	57.42	57.39	59.08	56.71
17	62.47	57.53	52.32	51.66	51.59	51.50	49.29	53.93	57.51	57.45	59.14	55.94
18	62.38	57.42	52.31	51.78	51.77	51.66	49.04	54.09	57.59	57.53	59.19	55.06
19	62.26	57.32	52.23	51.91	51.95	51.85	48.88	54.26	57.66	57.62	59.25	54.21
20	62.11	57.20	52.05	52.03	52.10	52.03	48.83	54.43	57.72	57.70	59.33	53.41
21	61.95	57.06	51.94	52.15	52.27	52.21	48.86	54.59	57.78	57.78	59.40	52.60
22	61.79	56.86	51.90	52.25	52.42	52.38	48.95	54.74	57.79	57.85	59.48	51.86
23	61.64	56.59	51.90	52.31	52.56	52.57	49.09	54.87	57.66	57.93	59.55	50.92
24	61.50	56.20	51.93	52.20	52.72	52.75	49.25	55.01	57.60	58.01	59.54	49.75
25	61.36	55.61	51.96	52.00	52.87	52.92	49.43	55.15	57.52	58.08	59.45	48.63
26	61.24	54.92	52.01	51.78	52.96	53.07	49.62	55.29	57.45	58.12	59.44	47.64
27	61.14	54.34	52.04	51.54	52.95	53.21	49.82	55.43	57.25	58.16	59.46	46.73
28	61.04	53.91	52.09	51.29	52.83	53.35	50.05	55.56	57.01	58.22	59.49	45.91
29	60.95	53.60	52.14	51.05	---	53.47	50.32	55.70	56.88	58.27	59.50	45.18
30	60.87	53.36	52.20	50.80	---	53.58	50.56	55.82	56.84	58.34	59.49	44.54
31	60.77	---	52.25	50.61	---	53.70	---	55.96	---	58.42	59.43	---
MEAN	62.03	57.56	52.40	51.45	51.19	52.17	51.26	53.64	57.09	57.51	59.14	54.61
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 55.05	HIGHEST 44.28	SEPT. 30, 1998	LOWEST 62.57	OCT. 15, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180002066132200. Local number, HW-TW-01.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'02", long 66°13'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 3.30 mi southwest of Cerro Guaraco, 8.71 mi southwest of Cayey plaza, and 2.80 mi southeast of Hwy 1 km 82.3 on Rabo del Buey. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: HW-TW-01.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-39.5 ft (0-12.0 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-38.2 ft (0-11.6 m), screened 32-37.0 ft (9.75-11.3 m). Depth 39.5 ft (12.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 190 ft (58.0 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on side of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 2.84 ft (0.87 m), above land-surface datum. Prior October 13, 1988, top of shelter floor, 3.48 ft (1.06 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 10, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 14, 1988 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 19.34 ft (5.89 m), below land-surface datum, Dec. 18, 1990 to Jan. 26, 1991; lowest water level recorded, 37.45 ft (11.4 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 10, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28.41	27.14	26.45	26.87	27.54	27.86	28.53	28.90	29.53	30.03	30.61	---
2	28.41	27.12	26.44	26.89	27.58	27.86	28.55	28.92	29.54	30.04	30.63	---
3	28.41	27.11	26.43	26.94	27.60	27.87	28.55	28.96	29.54	30.07	30.64	---
4	28.41	27.09	26.43	26.95	27.62	27.86	28.55	28.98	29.54	30.10	30.66	---
5	28.41	27.09	26.43	26.97	27.64	27.89	28.56	29.01	29.55	30.12	30.68	---
6	28.41	27.08	26.43	27.01	27.66	27.90	28.56	29.02	29.59	30.13	30.70	---
7	28.41	27.06	26.43	27.02	27.68	27.93	28.56	29.02	29.61	30.14	30.71	---
8	28.41	27.06	26.43	27.03	27.68	27.96	28.58	29.02	29.63	30.18	30.73	---
9	28.43	27.06	26.43	27.04	27.68	27.97	28.59	29.04	29.68	30.20	30.75	---
10	28.44	27.04	26.43	27.05	27.68	28.00	28.60	29.05	29.70	30.22	30.75	---
11	28.45	27.01	26.43	27.06	27.67	28.19	28.62	29.08	29.71	30.22	30.77	---
12	28.48	26.97	26.44	27.08	27.67	28.19	28.64	29.15	29.72	30.23	30.77	---
13	28.48	26.94	26.47	27.09	27.66	28.22	28.64	29.15	29.72	30.26	30.77	---
14	28.32	26.88	26.49	27.09	27.65	28.27	28.65	29.15	29.73	30.28	30.77	---
15	28.16	26.85	26.51	27.11	27.65	28.28	28.66	29.16	29.79	30.31	30.77	---
16	27.97	26.83	26.56	27.14	27.67	28.31	28.66	29.17	29.81	30.33	30.78	---
17	27.86	26.80	26.56	27.17	27.68	28.32	28.66	29.20	29.82	30.35	30.78	---
18	27.77	26.77	26.58	27.19	27.69	28.35	28.67	29.21	29.84	30.37	30.78	---
19	27.62	26.71	26.59	27.21	27.69	28.38	28.68	29.26	29.86	30.39	30.78	---
20	27.55	26.67	26.59	27.23	27.73	28.40	28.68	29.29	29.88	30.42	30.78	---
21	27.47	26.64	26.61	27.27	27.75	28.40	28.68	29.31	29.91	30.44	30.78	---
22	27.42	26.60	26.63	27.28	27.77	28.42	28.69	29.32	29.94	30.45	30.78	---
23	27.36	26.58	26.65	27.31	27.79	28.44	28.71	29.35	29.94	30.45	30.79	---
24	27.33	26.57	26.67	27.34	27.80	28.46	28.74	29.38	29.94	30.48	30.80	---
25	27.31	26.56	26.70	27.36	27.81	28.49	28.76	29.40	29.95	30.49	30.80	---
26	27.27	26.54	26.73	27.40	27.81	28.50	28.79	29.41	29.96	30.50	30.73	---
27	27.24	26.53	26.75	27.43	27.85	28.52	28.81	29.44	29.97	30.52	30.68	---
28	27.22	26.51	26.78	27.46	27.85	28.52	28.83	29.46	29.98	30.56	30.64	---
29	27.19	26.49	26.81	27.48	---	28.52	28.86	29.47	29.99	30.57	---	---
30	27.16	26.47	26.82	27.50	---	28.53	28.88	29.49	30.01	30.59	---	---
31	27.15	---	26.84	27.52	---	28.53	---	29.51	---	30.60	---	---
MEAN	27.90	26.83	26.57	27.18	27.70	28.24	28.66	29.20	29.78	30.32	30.74	---
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 28.45	HIGHEST 26.43	DEC. 3- 12, 1997	LOWEST 30.80	AUG. 24, 25, 1998							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180001066122002. Local number, HW-TW-03C.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'01", long 66°12'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 8.27 mi southwest of Cayey plaza, 2.38 mi southwest of Cerro Garau, and 3.45 mi southeast of Hwy 1 km 82.3. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: HW-TW-03C.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-220 ft (0-67.0 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-150 ft (0-45.7 m), open hole 150-220 ft (45.7-67.0 m). Depth 220 ft (67.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 270 ft (82.6 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.32 ft (1.01 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on April 15, 1998. Aquifer test performed during May 24, 25, 26, 1989.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 15, 1988 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 26.29 ft (8.01 m), below land-surface datum, Dec. 15, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 59.82 ft (18.2 m), below land-surface datum, Mar. 1, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	53.80	53.91	53.93	54.16	54.40	54.68	54.82	55.22	55.48	55.76	55.92	---
2	53.79	53.91	53.92	54.14	54.42	54.66	54.85	55.24	55.49	55.77	55.94	---
3	53.79	53.90	53.91	54.10	54.42	54.66	54.89	55.26	55.49	55.77	55.96	---
4	53.80	53.87	53.91	54.10	54.43	54.72	54.90	55.29	55.52	55.79	56.03	---
5	53.80	53.90	53.92	54.11	54.42	54.74	54.92	55.31	55.53	55.83	56.05	---
6	53.81	53.91	53.92	54.15	54.46	54.77	54.94	55.35	55.55	55.86	56.06	---
7	53.84	53.92	53.97	54.15	54.49	54.79	54.99	55.33	55.63	55.87	55.63	---
8	53.87	53.93	54.01	54.19	54.51	54.83	55.04	55.34	55.63	55.89	55.78	---
9	53.90	53.99	54.02	54.22	54.51	54.87	55.05	55.36	55.65	55.90	55.72	---
10	53.92	53.94	54.03	54.24	54.53	54.89	55.04	55.37	55.65	55.90	55.64	---
11	53.97	53.97	54.05	54.21	54.57	54.85	55.03	55.37	55.63	55.88	55.63	---
12	53.95	53.98	54.06	54.24	54.57	54.88	55.00	55.38	55.61	55.85	55.63	---
13	53.96	53.95	54.06	54.23	54.57	54.88	54.99	55.38	55.57	55.83	---	---
14	53.75	53.95	54.05	54.21	54.54	54.87	54.99	55.34	55.55	55.84	---	---
15	53.65	53.94	54.04	54.21	54.56	54.85	55.07	55.32	55.58	55.85	---	---
16	53.62	53.91	54.02	54.21	54.56	54.82	55.05	55.34	55.59	55.88	---	---
17	53.61	53.88	54.00	54.23	54.56	54.82	55.06	55.36	55.61	55.90	---	---
18	53.59	53.87	54.01	54.24	54.58	54.83	55.08	55.38	55.62	55.93	---	---
19	53.56	53.87	54.04	54.25	54.58	54.84	55.08	55.41	55.67	55.97	---	---
20	53.58	53.89	54.05	54.27	54.59	54.84	55.10	55.44	55.71	55.97	---	---
21	53.58	53.91	54.04	54.29	54.61	54.83	55.12	55.46	55.73	56.01	---	---
22	53.62	53.92	54.07	54.32	54.66	54.84	55.16	55.48	55.71	55.92	---	---
23	53.67	53.93	54.07	54.36	54.68	54.87	55.24	55.51	55.74	55.90	---	---
24	53.71	53.95	54.09	54.38	54.69	54.91	55.27	55.53	55.74	55.90	---	---
25	53.74	53.95	54.12	54.41	54.73	54.95	55.29	55.52	55.71	55.90	---	---
26	53.79	53.96	54.14	54.43	54.72	55.00	55.29	55.51	55.69	55.88	---	---
27	53.81	53.97	54.13	54.46	54.74	54.98	55.26	55.50	55.68	55.84	---	---
28	53.86	53.99	54.13	54.46	54.73	54.96	55.26	55.48	55.68	55.85	---	---
29	53.88	53.96	54.14	54.44	---	54.92	55.24	55.46	55.71	55.88	---	---
30	53.90	53.94	54.16	54.40	---	54.87	55.22	55.46	55.74	55.91	---	---
31	53.91	---	54.16	54.37	---	54.85	---	55.47	---	55.92	---	---
MEAN	53.78	53.93	54.04	54.26	54.57	54.84	55.07	55.39	55.63	55.88	55.83	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 54.78 HIGHEST 53.45 OCT. 15, 16, 1997 LOWEST 56.13 AUG. 7, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175947066130601. Local number, HW-TW5B.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'47", long 66°13'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 2.70 mi northeast of Central Aguirre Church, 6.16 mi northwest of Escuela de Guayama, and 2.70 mi northeast of Hwy 3 km 151.3. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: HW-TW-5B.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-52.0 ft (0-15.8 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-51.0 ft (0-15.5 m), screened 41-46 ft (12.5-14.0 m). Depth 52.0 ft (15.8 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 145 ft (44.2 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum. Prior October 13, 1989 top of shelter floor, 3.47 ft (1.06 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on April 15, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 13, 1988 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 5.93 ft (1.81 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 22, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 28.55 ft (8.70 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 14, 15, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	24.41	18.81	17.37	18.26	19.06	19.67	20.55	21.43	22.69	23.12	23.68	---
2	24.41	18.81	17.39	18.30	19.09	19.71	20.55	21.48	22.72	23.12	23.71	---
3	24.39	18.81	17.43	18.33	19.11	19.75	20.56	21.54	22.75	23.12	23.74	---
4	24.38	18.81	17.45	18.33	19.16	19.77	20.56	21.57	22.78	23.12	23.76	---
5	24.37	18.82	17.48	18.34	19.19	19.84	20.58	21.62	22.82	23.13	23.78	---
6	24.37	18.82	17.50	18.39	19.19	19.88	20.59	21.65	22.84	23.14	23.80	---
7	24.37	18.82	17.54	18.36	19.14	19.91	20.62	21.65	22.89	23.15	23.82	---
8	24.37	18.84	17.56	18.35	19.12	19.96	20.65	21.66	22.93	23.16	23.85	---
9	24.37	18.87	17.59	18.35	19.10	20.01	20.68	21.69	22.96	23.18	23.70	---
10	24.37	18.45	17.62	18.35	19.11	20.05	20.73	21.71	22.99	23.20	23.57	---
11	24.37	17.86	17.65	18.35	19.11	20.10	20.75	21.75	23.04	23.21	23.53	---
12	24.35	17.62	17.69	18.36	19.13	20.13	20.76	21.83	23.07	23.22	23.53	---
13	24.28	17.55	17.73	18.38	19.15	20.17	20.78	21.87	23.10	23.24	23.53	---
14	21.28	17.47	17.75	18.38	19.19	20.22	20.79	21.89	23.14	23.25	23.53	---
15	20.40	17.43	17.77	18.42	19.19	20.25	20.80	21.93	23.18	23.27	23.54	---
16	19.91	17.40	17.81	18.45	19.21	20.28	20.81	21.97	23.21	23.28	23.58	---
17	19.49	17.36	17.84	18.49	19.23	20.30	20.83	22.01	23.21	23.30	23.64	---
18	19.27	17.34	17.86	18.51	19.26	20.34	20.86	22.04	23.21	23.31	23.64	---
19	19.12	17.34	17.90	18.54	19.29	20.40	20.88	22.10	23.21	23.35	23.56	---
20	19.02	17.32	17.92	18.59	19.34	20.44	20.92	22.15	23.21	23.38	23.53	---
21	18.97	17.32	17.96	18.66	19.40	20.44	20.96	22.19	23.21	23.39	23.49	---
22	18.92	17.32	17.99	18.67	19.43	20.46	21.00	22.24	23.20	23.40	23.49	6.09
23	18.90	17.32	18.00	18.73	19.47	20.46	21.04	22.32	23.19	23.43	23.37	---
24	18.85	17.32	18.01	18.76	19.51	20.49	21.09	22.36	23.17	23.44	23.32	---
25	18.83	17.31	18.03	18.82	19.54	20.52	21.15	22.40	23.15	23.46	22.47	9.00
26	18.80	17.31	18.05	18.85	19.58	20.54	21.19	22.45	23.14	23.48	21.70	9.70
27	18.81	17.31	18.08	18.89	19.61	20.54	21.22	22.49	23.13	23.53	21.50	10.26
28	18.80	17.32	18.11	18.92	19.64	20.54	21.28	22.52	23.12	23.55	21.39	10.67
29	18.80	17.34	18.13	18.94	---	20.54	21.32	22.55	23.12	23.58	21.17	11.02
30	18.80	17.35	18.18	18.96	---	20.54	21.38	22.61	23.12	23.60	---	11.32
31	18.80	---	18.21	19.02	---	20.54	---	22.65	---	23.64	---	---
MEAN	21.37	17.86	17.79	18.55	19.27	20.22	20.86	22.01	23.05	23.31	23.27	9.72

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 20.46 HIGHEST 5.93 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 24.43 OCT. 1, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175957066123400. Local number, HW-TW-13.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'57", long 66°12'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 3.11 northeast of Central Aguirre Church, 5.76 mi northwest of Escuela de Guayama, and 2.03 mi northeast of Hwy 3 km 151.3. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: HW-TW-13.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-69.0 ft (0-21.0 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-69.0 ft (0-21.0 m), screened 4.0-69 ft (1.22-21.0 m). Depth 69.0 ft (21.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 203 ft (61.9 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.33 ft (0.71 m), above land-surface datum. Prior October 14, 1988, top of shelter floor, 3.47 ft (1.06 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on July 22, 1998

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 14, 1988 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 34.39 ft (10.5 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 27, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 48.12 ft (14.7 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 3, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	47.58	46.82	46.86	46.99	47.02	47.11	47.18	47.21	47.12	47.13	47.62	48.09
2	47.58	46.82	46.86	46.99	47.02	47.11	47.18	47.22	47.12	47.13	47.64	48.09
3	47.58	46.82	46.86	46.99	47.03	47.11	47.18	47.22	47.12	47.13	47.65	48.10
4	47.58	46.82	46.86	46.99	47.03	47.13	47.18	47.22	47.12	47.13	47.67	48.09
5	47.58	46.82	46.87	46.99	47.02	47.14	47.18	47.22	47.12	47.13	47.69	48.07
6	47.58	46.82	46.87	46.99	47.03	47.14	47.18	47.23	47.12	---	47.70	48.09
7	47.58	46.82	46.87	47.00	47.03	47.14	47.18	47.22	47.12	---	47.72	48.09
8	47.58	46.82	46.93	47.00	47.04	47.14	47.19	47.22	47.12	---	47.74	48.09
9	47.58	46.82	46.93	47.01	47.04	47.14	47.19	47.21	47.12	---	47.75	48.11
10	47.57	46.82	46.93	47.01	47.04	47.14	47.19	47.21	47.12	---	47.77	48.08
11	47.57	46.82	46.93	47.01	47.04	47.14	47.19	47.21	47.12	---	47.79	48.06
12	47.57	46.82	46.94	47.02	47.04	47.14	47.19	47.20	47.12	---	47.80	48.05
13	47.57	46.82	46.94	47.02	47.04	47.14	47.19	47.22	47.12	---	47.83	48.03
14	47.61	46.82	46.94	47.02	47.04	47.14	47.19	47.21	47.12	---	47.85	48.01
15	47.61	46.82	46.94	47.02	47.04	47.15	47.19	47.21	47.11	---	47.86	47.98
16	47.41	46.83	46.94	47.02	47.04	47.15	47.20	47.20	47.11	---	47.88	47.96
17	47.14	46.83	46.94	47.03	47.04	47.15	47.20	47.20	47.11	---	47.90	47.93
18	46.99	46.83	46.94	47.03	47.05	47.15	47.20	47.19	47.12	---	47.91	47.92
19	46.90	46.83	46.94	47.03	47.05	47.15	47.20	47.19	47.12	---	47.93	47.91
20	46.90	46.83	46.95	47.03	47.05	47.15	47.20	47.18	47.12	---	47.95	47.89
21	46.90	46.83	46.95	47.03	47.05	47.15	47.20	47.18	47.12	---	47.96	47.87
22	46.89	46.84	46.95	47.03	47.05	47.15	47.20	47.17	47.12	47.48	47.98	42.65
23	46.89	46.84	46.96	47.03	47.05	47.16	47.20	47.17	47.12	47.47	48.00	43.53
24	46.89	46.84	46.96	47.03	47.05	47.16	47.21	47.16	47.12	47.49	48.01	46.31
25	46.82	46.84	46.96	47.03	47.09	47.16	47.21	47.16	47.12	47.50	48.00	46.89
26	46.82	46.84	46.97	47.02	47.09	47.17	47.21	47.15	47.12	47.52	48.02	46.88
27	46.82	46.84	46.97	47.02	47.10	47.17	47.21	47.15	47.13	47.54	48.03	46.88
28	46.82	46.84	46.97	47.02	47.11	47.17	47.21	47.14	47.13	47.55	48.05	46.88
29	46.82	46.85	46.98	47.02	---	47.17	47.21	47.14	47.13	47.57	48.08	46.88
30	46.82	46.85	46.98	47.02	---	47.17	47.21	47.13	47.13	47.59	48.05	46.88
31	46.82	---	46.99	47.02	---	47.18	---	47.13	---	47.60	48.02	---
MEAN	47.24	46.83	46.93	47.01	47.05	47.15	47.19	47.19	47.12	47.40	47.87	47.41

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 47.19 HIGHEST 41.61 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 48.12 SEPT. 3, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175809066133100. Local number, CQ-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'09", long 66°13'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.49 mi southwest of the intersection of Hwy 706 with Hwy 3, 0.30 mi south of Hwy 3, and 0.12 mi east of Hwy 705. Owner: PR Land Authority, Name: Coqui Btr 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 18 in (0.46 m). Depth 199 ft (60.7 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 16.4 ft (5.00 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole in the side of the 18 in (0.46 m) casing, 1.33 ft (0.41 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well . Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on March 6, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 6, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.30 ft (1.00 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 22, 23, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 18.64 ft (5.68 m), below land-surface datum, May 29, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	15.26	14.08	12.79	13.92	13.53	13.02	13.42	16.13	15.88	15.81	---	16.32
2	15.15	15.35	14.61	13.64	13.24	12.48	13.57	16.47	15.74	15.90	---	16.26
3	15.05	15.86	12.96	14.43	13.20	12.73	15.66	16.64	15.65	---	---	16.19
4	15.02	15.68	13.05	13.66	13.50	12.83	14.16	16.76	15.41	---	---	16.02
5	15.05	14.24	14.43	13.44	13.25	13.05	14.85	16.19	15.42	---	---	15.99
6	15.02	13.98	14.55	13.42	13.67	13.03	16.02	16.63	15.47	---	16.16	14.17
7	15.02	13.91	14.60	13.28	13.22	13.04	16.18	17.08	15.39	---	15.94	16.07
8	15.27	13.80	14.66	13.06	14.31	13.02	14.38	17.24	15.36	---	15.93	16.09
9	15.13	13.72	13.94	13.04	13.65	12.98	17.07	17.36	15.40	---	15.77	16.12
10	15.14	12.62	13.60	12.96	13.48	12.90	16.97	17.35	15.38	---	15.72	16.19
11	15.00	12.32	13.47	12.95	13.44	12.92	17.05	17.39	15.36	---	16.27	16.21
12	15.07	12.40	13.58	12.93	13.40	12.92	17.15	17.46	14.01	---	16.75	16.24
13	15.23	12.41	13.59	12.87	12.95	12.94	17.21	17.46	13.27	---	16.82	16.29
14	14.08	12.46	13.38	13.08	13.44	12.93	17.09	17.50	12.62	---	16.86	16.29
15	13.02	12.53	13.28	12.89	13.37	12.92	17.20	17.61	15.37	---	16.90	16.16
16	13.06	12.58	14.38	12.96	13.23	12.94	18.25	17.65	15.45	---	16.92	16.03
17	13.05	12.60	14.62	12.85	13.15	12.97	17.72	17.71	15.50	---	17.20	14.58
18	13.05	12.53	13.91	12.85	13.35	13.05	17.62	16.88	15.54	---	17.27	15.85
19	13.04	12.59	13.52	12.84	13.58	13.11	17.61	17.52	15.59	---	16.99	15.92
20	13.05	12.61	13.42	13.49	13.27	13.15	17.62	17.70	15.45	---	16.95	16.00
21	13.07	12.68	13.35	14.30	13.08	13.20	13.57	17.79	15.63	---	16.93	15.99
22	12.59	12.43	13.31	13.33	13.12	13.23	17.15	18.00	15.71	---	16.80	7.06
23	12.45	12.49	13.40	13.33	13.66	13.27	17.38	17.90	15.58	---	16.83	3.37
24	12.44	12.65	13.32	13.21	13.44	13.24	17.42	17.89	15.81	---	16.79	4.04
25	13.96	11.96	13.30	14.10	13.34	13.29	17.47	18.04	15.88	---	16.10	4.44
26	14.38	12.51	13.27	13.99	13.24	13.37	17.55	18.13	15.89	---	16.24	4.43
27	14.18	12.62	13.41	13.22	13.07	13.43	17.58	18.07	15.75	---	16.25	4.32
28	12.94	12.73	13.33	13.06	12.85	13.47	17.72	18.08	15.44	---	16.28	4.24
29	12.64	12.80	14.26	13.14	---	13.60	16.99	18.21	15.67	---	16.23	4.19
30	12.50	12.79	14.56	13.10	---	13.57	14.54	17.93	15.71	---	16.17	4.09
31	14.41	---	14.61	13.09	---	13.67	---	16.29	---	---	16.53	---
MEAN	14.01	13.13	13.76	13.30	13.36	13.11	16.47	17.39	15.34	15.85	16.52	12.51

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 14.43 HIGHEST 3.30 SEPT. 22, 23, 1998 LOWEST 18.64 MAY 29, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180206066135500. Local number, RM-5.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'06", long 66°13'55", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 6.98 mi southwest of Cayey plaza, 0.63 mi east of Hwy 1 km 82.3 on Rabo del Buey, and 1.75 mi southeast of Capilla de Santa Marta. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: RM # 5.

AQUIFER.--Quaternary alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-34.0 ft (0-10.4 m), screened 24-34.0 ft (7.32-10.7 m). Depth 34.0 ft (10.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 276 ft (84.2 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.28 ft (1.00 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on June 3, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 9, 1989 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 5.56 ft (1.69 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 10, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 24.24 ft (7.39 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 20, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	20.95	11.71	11.51	11.68	11.83	11.84	11.56	11.83	11.79	12.00	13.62	11.67
2	20.90	11.71	11.53	11.68	11.83	11.84	11.66	11.84	11.82	12.00	13.76	11.71
3	20.85	11.74	11.54	11.68	11.83	11.85	11.51	11.84	11.84	12.03	13.88	11.46
4	20.78	11.75	11.56	11.68	11.83	11.85	11.61	11.84	11.85	12.04	14.01	10.88
5	19.48	11.75	11.57	11.68	11.76	11.85	11.65	11.85	11.84	12.04	14.15	11.23
6	17.96	11.77	11.58	11.68	11.51	11.86	11.68	11.85	11.85	12.03	14.32	11.37
7	17.09	11.78	11.60	11.68	11.63	11.86	11.70	11.86	11.86	12.04	14.19	11.42
8	16.55	11.79	11.62	11.68	11.67	11.86	11.34	11.87	11.86	12.04	12.74	11.50
9	16.11	11.80	11.62	11.68	11.69	11.87	11.51	11.87	11.86	12.04	12.06	11.52
10	15.56	9.85	11.62	11.68	11.69	11.87	11.60	11.80	11.86	12.05	12.09	11.59
11	15.27	10.61	11.63	11.68	11.75	11.87	11.63	11.81	11.86	12.05	12.09	11.66
12	13.18	10.78	11.64	11.68	11.75	11.87	11.50	11.81	11.86	12.10	12.10	11.69
13	12.73	10.88	11.64	11.68	11.76	11.87	11.50	11.81	11.90	12.17	12.13	11.72
14	9.74	10.97	11.65	11.68	11.76	11.87	11.52	11.76	11.90	12.34	12.14	11.73
15	10.44	11.05	11.66	11.68	11.72	11.87	11.63	11.76	11.91	12.50	12.17	11.73
16	10.47	11.11	11.66	11.70	11.73	11.87	11.67	11.77	11.91	12.61	12.27	11.73
17	10.79	11.16	11.68	11.70	11.73	11.87	11.68	11.77	11.91	12.73	12.39	11.74
18	10.84	11.23	11.68	11.70	11.73	11.87	11.71	11.77	11.91	12.88	12.43	11.77
19	10.97	11.26	11.68	11.71	11.74	11.87	11.75	11.79	11.92	13.01	12.56	11.75
20	11.11	11.30	11.68	11.81	11.75	11.87	11.75	11.79	11.92	13.19	12.73	11.77
21	11.23	11.36	11.68	11.81	11.76	11.82	11.76	11.79	11.93	13.26	12.83	11.77
22	11.33	11.37	11.68	11.81	11.78	11.82	11.77	11.80	11.76	13.42	11.58	6.70
23	11.40	11.38	11.68	11.81	11.79	11.82	11.77	11.83	11.82	13.47	11.70	8.07
24	11.45	11.40	11.68	11.82	11.80	11.82	11.78	11.83	11.86	13.32	11.80	8.60
25	11.52	11.43	11.68	11.82	11.82	11.82	11.80	11.84	11.90	13.18	9.59	8.99
26	11.58	11.46	11.68	11.82	11.83	11.82	11.81	11.86	11.92	13.16	10.78	9.43
27	11.62	11.47	11.68	11.82	11.83	11.82	11.81	11.81	11.96	13.16	11.12	9.77
28	11.65	11.49	11.68	11.82	11.84	11.81	11.81	11.78	11.96	13.16	11.31	10.08
29	11.68	11.50	11.68	11.82	---	11.81	11.83	11.79	11.98	13.18	11.35	10.36
30	11.70	11.51	11.68	11.82	---	11.81	11.83	11.82	11.98	13.31	11.46	10.58
31	11.70	---	11.68	11.83	---	11.46	---	11.79	---	13.48	11.58	---
MEAN	13.83	11.35	11.64	11.74	11.75	11.83	11.67	11.81	11.88	12.64	12.35	10.87

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 11.95 HIGHEST 6.63 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 20.97 OCT. 1, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180104066152300. Local number, RM-10.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'04", long 66°15'23", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 8.00 mi southeast of Coamo plaza, 1.07 mi northeast of Escuela de Coco, and 0.70 mi southwest of Escuela Sabana Llana. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: RM # 10.

AQUIFER.--Quaternary alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-37.0 ft (0-11.3 m), screened 27-37 ft (8.23-11.3 m). Depth 37.0 ft (11.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--15-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 164 ft (50.0 m), above mean sea level, from leveling survey.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.62 ft (1.10 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Pumping test performed on February 8, 1990. Well dry at 35.77 ft (10.9 m).

Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 11, 1998. From Sept. 14, 1998, monthly measurements only.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 13, 1989 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 18.0 ft (5.49 m), below land-surface datum, Nov. 9, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 35.77 ft (10.9 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 14 to Oct. 5, 1994

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	35.61	27.53	23.91	24.10	25.56	25.98	27.32	26.03	27.32	29.00	30.97	---
2	35.61	27.41	23.91	24.12	25.65	26.06	27.08	26.18	27.27	29.07	31.05	---
3	35.61	27.34	23.91	24.18	25.72	26.24	26.81	26.37	27.27	29.15	31.10	---
4	35.61	27.27	23.91	24.19	25.80	26.36	26.60	26.49	27.28	29.20	31.11	---
5	35.60	27.21	23.91	24.17	25.90	26.38	26.38	26.65	27.36	29.31	31.19	---
6	35.60	27.15	23.91	24.16	25.82	26.43	26.15	26.73	27.37	29.36	31.25	---
7	35.60	27.05	23.91	24.14	25.67	26.50	26.04	26.74	27.49	29.46	31.30	---
8	35.60	26.94	23.91	24.12	25.53	26.65	25.69	26.90	27.63	29.55	31.33	---
9	35.60	26.82	23.91	24.12	25.42	26.73	25.63	26.90	27.68	29.59	30.56	---
10	35.60	26.09	23.91	24.13	25.27	26.73	25.56	26.99	27.79	29.68	29.90	---
11	35.60	25.51	23.93	24.16	25.18	26.74	25.49	26.99	27.89	29.79	29.75	---
12	35.60	25.16	23.93	24.20	25.13	26.86	25.24	27.04	27.97	29.84	29.78	---
13	35.59	24.95	23.93	24.25	25.13	26.93	25.13	27.09	28.04	29.91	29.91	---
14	35.59	24.76	23.93	24.26	25.13	27.08	25.08	27.10	28.11	29.99	30.06	---
15	34.39	24.58	23.93	24.29	25.10	27.08	25.08	27.14	28.21	30.06	30.15	---
16	33.06	24.44	23.95	24.35	25.00	27.25	25.08	27.10	28.32	30.13	30.27	---
17	32.28	24.33	23.95	24.40	25.01	27.32	25.08	27.08	28.39	30.19	30.39	---
18	31.73	24.23	23.94	24.46	25.01	27.34	25.08	27.07	28.48	30.26	30.48	---
19	31.21	24.14	23.93	24.54	25.02	27.41	25.09	27.07	28.54	30.32	30.56	---
20	30.82	24.07	23.93	24.61	25.02	27.49	25.09	27.06	28.59	30.38	30.69	---
21	30.45	24.03	23.92	24.69	25.12	27.49	25.10	27.06	28.70	30.42	---	---
22	30.08	23.99	23.91	24.77	25.22	27.61	25.10	27.06	28.77	30.49	---	---
23	29.74	23.97	23.90	24.86	25.31	27.61	25.19	27.07	28.77	30.49	---	---
24	29.35	23.95	23.90	24.95	25.39	27.73	25.27	27.17	28.77	30.54	---	---
25	29.04	23.92	23.90	25.05	25.49	27.72	25.37	27.30	28.77	30.62	---	---
26	28.73	23.91	23.91	25.12	25.61	27.72	25.45	27.35	28.77	30.67	---	---
27	28.44	23.91	23.96	25.17	25.72	27.72	25.57	27.42	28.86	30.74	---	---
28	28.20	23.91	23.99	25.21	25.85	27.72	25.68	27.50	28.86	30.77	---	---
29	28.02	23.91	24.00	25.28	---	27.72	25.76	27.43	28.93	30.83	---	---
30	27.87	23.91	24.02	25.36	---	27.72	25.93	27.38	28.95	30.89	---	---
31	27.68	---	24.08	25.45	---	27.62	---	27.37	---	30.94	---	---
MEAN	32.56	25.21	23.93	24.54	25.38	27.09	25.64	26.99	28.17	30.05	30.59	---
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 27.20	HIGHEST 23.90	DEC. 23-26, 1997	LOWEST 35.61	OCT. 1-5, 1997							

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175910066155500. Local number, SA-D.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'10", long 66°15'55", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.55 mi south of Hwy 52, 0.92 mi north of the Salinas Speedway, and 2.27 mi northeast of the intersection of Hwy 1 with Hwy 3. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD,

Name: USGS piezometer D.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), 0-86.0 ft (0-26.2 m). Depth 86.0 ft (26.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 73.0 ft (22.3 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on Feb. 19, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 19, 1997 to September 30, 1997.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 35.80 ft (10.9 m), below land-surface datum, Feb, 19 1997; lowest water level recorded, 47.98 ft (14.6 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 7, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	37.01	39.67	41.36	42.68	44.24	45.55	46.86
2	---	---	---	---	---	37.09	39.73	41.38	42.72	44.24	45.56	46.89
3	---	---	---	---	---	37.33	39.74	41.42	42.76	44.43	45.53	46.95
4	---	---	---	---	---	37.39	39.76	41.45	42.78	44.38	45.66	46.98
5	---	---	---	---	---	37.47	39.77	41.62	42.81	44.38	45.63	47.00
6	---	---	---	---	---	37.54	39.79	41.55	42.87	44.37	45.63	47.00
7	---	---	---	---	---	37.68	39.84	41.57	42.91	44.46	45.70	47.05
8	---	---	---	---	---	37.81	39.89	41.63	42.96	44.42	45.74	47.05
9	---	---	---	---	---	37.90	39.94	41.68	43.11	44.58	45.75	47.21
10	---	---	---	---	---	38.05	40.13	41.70	43.21	44.62	45.75	47.24
11	---	---	---	---	---	38.14	40.11	41.67	43.15	44.63	45.81	47.28
12	---	---	---	---	---	38.31	40.19	41.67	43.20	44.89	45.88	47.35
13	---	---	---	---	---	38.43	40.23	41.69	43.37	44.91	45.88	47.41
14	---	---	---	---	---	38.54	40.41	41.71	43.35	44.90	45.92	47.40
15	---	---	---	---	---	38.70	40.38	41.73	43.35	44.93	45.95	47.49
16	---	---	---	---	---	38.76	40.41	41.88	43.36	45.12	46.03	47.46
17	---	---	---	---	---	38.85	40.49	41.84	43.48	45.09	46.05	47.56
18	---	---	---	---	---	39.03	40.56	41.87	43.48	45.08	46.36	47.57
19	---	---	---	---	35.86	39.05	40.60	41.93	43.48	45.07	46.32	47.64
20	---	---	---	---	35.96	39.07	40.71	42.12	43.62	45.09	46.42	47.68
21	---	---	---	---	36.00	39.12	40.86	42.21	43.63	45.09	46.43	47.69
22	---	---	---	---	36.11	39.20	40.79	42.19	43.63	45.08	46.55	47.67
23	---	---	---	---	36.22	39.24	40.85	42.17	43.78	45.09	46.58	47.66
24	---	---	---	---	36.32	39.31	40.93	42.21	43.97	45.10	46.54	47.66
25	---	---	---	---	36.54	39.38	41.14	42.28	43.97	45.10	46.53	47.68
26	---	---	---	---	36.71	39.43	41.07	42.45	43.98	45.10	46.66	47.70
27	---	---	---	---	36.86	39.52	41.11	42.42	43.98	45.12	46.62	47.70
28	---	---	---	---	36.95	39.60	41.18	42.48	44.06	45.15	46.63	47.70
29	---	---	---	---	---	39.63	41.22	42.53	44.07	45.19	46.65	47.70
30	---	---	---	---	---	39.62	41.39	42.57	44.31	45.33	46.73	47.72
31	---	---	---	---	---	39.62	---	42.70	---	45.34	46.76	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	36.35	38.57	40.43	41.93	43.40	44.86	46.12	47.40
WTR YR 1997	MEAN 42.93	HIGHEST 35.80	FEB. 19, 1997	LOWEST 47.72	SEPT. 30, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	47.72	---	---	40.20	38.79	38.72	38.98	39.62	40.66	41.74	43.36	44.03
2	47.72	---	---	40.32	38.96	38.94	38.98	39.72	40.86	41.75	43.32	44.01
3	47.72	---	---	40.07	38.82	38.95	38.99	39.66	40.87	41.99	43.46	43.95
4	47.88	---	---	39.96	38.80	38.82	39.00	39.92	41.00	41.69	43.54	43.76
5	47.95	---	---	39.87	38.81	38.93	39.00	39.92	40.91	41.67	43.68	43.61
6	47.98	---	---	39.81	38.75	39.00	39.05	39.85	40.86	41.65	43.73	43.55
7	---	---	---	39.67	38.67	38.82	39.06	39.85	40.86	41.86	43.68	43.41
8	---	---	---	39.61	38.61	38.83	39.08	39.81	40.98	42.03	43.72	43.38
9	---	---	---	39.49	38.56	38.95	39.08	39.86	41.05	42.12	43.68	43.38
10	---	---	---	39.39	38.71	38.96	39.03	39.85	41.24	42.14	43.55	43.36
11	---	---	---	39.30	38.64	38.98	39.05	40.07	41.12	41.97	43.68	42.98
12	---	---	---	39.40	38.62	38.91	39.06	40.05	41.33	42.04	43.82	43.03
13	---	---	---	39.23	38.83	38.98	39.09	40.11	41.25	42.31	44.14	42.95
14	---	---	---	39.10	38.68	39.05	39.10	40.09	41.24	42.40	44.16	42.97
15	---	---	---	39.08	38.66	38.92	39.11	40.06	41.32	42.53	44.29	42.78
16	---	---	---	39.04	38.66	39.01	39.13	40.01	41.23	42.52	44.16	42.60
17	---	---	42.00	39.06	38.59	38.95	39.10	39.98	41.18	42.66	44.37	42.56
18	---	---	41.98	39.06	38.64	39.03	39.16	40.16	41.25	42.53	44.29	42.37
19	---	---	41.72	39.08	38.60	38.99	39.14	40.04	41.25	42.52	44.28	42.20
20	---	---	41.56	38.93	38.78	38.98	39.32	40.11	41.23	42.68	44.27	42.19
21	---	---	41.43	38.97	38.81	38.93	39.26	40.16	41.23	42.59	44.29	42.19
22	---	---	41.28	38.87	38.72	38.96	39.40	40.34	41.15	42.62	44.28	41.87
23	---	---	41.17	39.01	38.82	39.03	39.36	40.18	41.09	42.75	44.26	41.86
24	---	---	41.08	38.87	38.73	39.27	39.55	40.20	41.25	42.97	44.21	39.70
25	---	---	40.92	38.85	38.73	39.12	39.57	40.53	41.23	42.90	44.15	39.14
26	---	---	40.93	38.96	38.81	39.06	39.53	40.39	41.24	42.89	44.15	38.96
27	---	---	40.70	38.95	38.90	39.06	39.61	40.32	41.29	43.12	44.13	38.32
28	---	---	40.78	38.84	38.76	39.05	39.66	40.32	41.52	43.17	44.13	38.02
29	---	---	40.51	38.89	---	39.01	39.67	40.44	41.59	43.08	44.13	37.78
30	---	---	40.45	38.82	---	38.99	39.74	40.52	41.66	43.15	44.14	37.27
31	---	---	40.44	38.79	---	38.98	---	40.47	---	43.38	44.02	---
MEAN	47.83	---	41.13	39.27	38.73	38.97	39.23	40.08	41.16	42.43	43.97	41.94

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 40.83 HIGHEST 37.08 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 47.98 OCT. 7, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175708066163000. Local number, EC-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°57'08", long 66°16'30", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.55 mi south of Playa de Salinas, 143 mi south of Hwy 3, and 0.98 mi West of Las Mareas community. Owner: US Geological Survey. WRD, Name: Pozo Monsanto (Ermitaño Central).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 112 ft (34.1 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 2.00 ft (0.61 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: On shelter floor 5.10 ft (1.55 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on July 15, 1997. Well level is affected by marine tides.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 15, 1997 to January 7, 1998, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +0.28 ft (+0.08 m), above land-surface datum, Jan. 7, 1998; lowest water level measured, 0.88 ft (0.27 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 8, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.26	.14
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.19	.18
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.12	.07
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.09	.15
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.09	.13
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.04	.12
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.07	.13
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.08	.25
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.16	.39
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.21	.41
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.25	.62
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.33	.34
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.32	.34
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.33	.29
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.26	.32	.21
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.32	.30	.14
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.33	.20	.14
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.26	.17	.17
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.15	.20	.15
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.13	.12	.19
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.14	.12	.24
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.16	.19	.29
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.07	.22	.40
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.07	.26	.40
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.07	.27	.31
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.08	.30	.38
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.14	.37	.28
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.24	.31	.23
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.27	.29	.18
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.25	.16	.20
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.22	.16	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	.19	.21	.25

WTR YR 1997 MEAN .22 HIGHEST +.13 JULY 19, 20, 1997 LOWEST .62 SEPT. 11, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.14	+.02	+.07	+.14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	.27	+.02	+.01	+.18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	.27	.01	.14	+.13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	.36	.14	.08	+.10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	.36	.05	.10	+.15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	.41	.17	.05	+.18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	.31	.19	.07	+.28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	.60	.22	.14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	.15	.18	.05	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	.03	.00	+.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
11	+.02	.00	+.13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	.01	+.06	+.13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	+.01	+.11	+.16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	.00	+.14	+.04	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	.02	+.12	+.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	.07	+.03	.08	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	+.06	+.09	+.04	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	+.09	+.05	+.02	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	+.03	+.03	.03	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	.03	.01	.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	.10	.09	.11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	.17	.00	.00	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	.18	.02	+.02	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	.22	+.01	+.12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	.20	.04	+.08	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	.16	+.04	+.13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	.13	+.12	+.17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	.18	+.12	+.14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	.15	+.13	+.10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	.05	+.10	+.10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	+.03	---	+.15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	.14	.00	+.03	+.17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
WTR YR 1998	MEAN .02	HIGHEST +.28	JAN. 7, 1998	LOWEST .88	OCT. 8, 1997							

+ above land-surface datum

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175903066165000. Local number, PG-07

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'03", long. 66°16'50", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.42 mi north of Hwy 3, 0.60 mi southeast of the intersection of Hwy 1 with Hwy 52, and 1.56 mi northeast of Punta Salinas. Owner: C. Godreau, Name: Pozo Godreau No. 7.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-120 ft (0-36.6 m), perforated 30-120 ft (9.1-36.6 m). Depth 120 ft (36.6 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 54.0 ft (16.5 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 20 in (0.50 m) casing, 3.63 ft (1.11 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on June 3, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 25, 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 24.62 ft (7.50 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 18, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 34.87 ft (10.6 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 3, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	34.09	33.33	32.16	30.83	29.71	29.30	---	29.21	30.02	30.85	---	---
2	34.09	33.31	32.13	30.77	29.70	29.29	---	29.24	30.07	30.89	---	---
3	34.09	33.29	32.09	30.71	29.67	29.29	---	29.27	30.15	30.92	---	---
4	34.09	33.28	32.06	30.66	29.66	29.30	---	29.30	30.15	30.95	---	---
5	34.09	33.27	32.02	30.59	29.65	29.30	---	29.32	30.16	30.96	---	---
6	34.09	33.24	31.97	30.54	29.64	29.29	---	29.34	30.21	30.98	---	---
7	34.09	33.24	31.94	30.48	29.59	29.28	---	29.39	30.24	30.99	---	---
8	34.09	33.24	31.89	30.43	29.56	29.28	---	29.39	30.27	31.03	---	---
9	34.09	33.22	31.84	30.37	29.53	29.29	---	29.40	30.30	31.08	---	---
10	34.09	33.18	31.80	30.33	29.51	29.29	---	29.42	30.32	31.09	---	---
11	34.09	33.08	31.77	30.28	29.47	29.29	---	29.47	30.34	31.14	---	31.12
12	34.09	33.02	31.74	30.23	29.46	29.29	---	29.47	30.37	31.17	---	31.11
13	34.09	32.96	31.70	30.19	29.46	29.29	---	29.49	30.40	31.20	---	31.08
14	34.09	32.92	31.66	30.14	29.44	29.29	---	29.51	30.44	31.22	---	31.00
15	34.09	32.85	31.48	30.10	29.42	29.30	---	29.53	30.47	31.25	---	30.95
16	34.09	32.79	31.57	30.06	29.40	29.32	29.17	29.55	30.50	31.29	---	30.90
17	34.05	32.74	31.53	30.03	29.38	29.33	29.17	29.58	30.50	31.33	---	30.85
18	33.99	32.69	31.48	30.01	29.37	29.35	29.17	29.61	30.52	31.37	---	30.81
19	33.86	32.64	31.44	29.97	29.36	29.36	29.17	29.64	30.54	31.40	---	30.76
20	33.83	32.58	31.39	29.95	29.34	29.38	29.17	29.68	30.56	31.43	---	30.71
21	33.80	32.55	31.35	29.90	29.32	29.38	29.16	29.70	30.60	31.45	---	30.67
22	33.60	32.51	31.29	29.89	29.32	29.39	29.16	29.75	30.67	---	---	30.31
23	33.59	32.47	31.25	29.88	29.32	29.41	29.16	29.78	30.67	---	---	29.16
24	33.52	32.44	31.21	29.86	29.32	29.43	29.16	29.82	30.70	---	---	28.57
25	33.47	32.41	31.13	29.85	29.30	29.44	29.16	29.85	30.72	---	---	28.39
26	33.45	32.37	31.09	29.82	29.30	29.44	29.17	29.87	30.73	---	---	28.21
27	33.42	32.33	31.04	29.81	29.30	---	29.17	29.89	30.76	---	---	28.05
28	33.40	32.29	31.00	29.78	29.30	---	29.18	29.90	30.79	---	---	27.89
29	33.39	32.25	30.95	29.76	---	---	29.19	29.94	30.80	---	---	27.75
30	33.38	32.22	30.90	29.73	---	---	29.20	29.98	30.83	---	---	27.63
31	33.36	---	30.86	29.72	---	---	---	30.00	---	---	---	---
MEAN	33.86	32.82	31.54	30.15	29.46	29.33	29.17	29.59	30.46	31.14	---	29.80

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 30.79 HIGHEST 27.55 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 34.09 OCT. 1-16, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175943066224800. Local number PS-07

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'43", long 66°22'48", Hydrologic Unit 2101004, 0.74 mi east of Hwy 153, 1.45 mi northeast of Estación Santa Isabel, and 1.98 mi north of Hwy 1. Owner: Luce and Company, Name: Paso Seco No. 7.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well. Depth 235 ft (71.6 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 89.0 ft (27.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Side of the casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping wells.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 27, 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 81.11 ft (24.72 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 3, 4, 6, 7, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 101.28 ft (30.87 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 13, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 1	91.89	Nov. 6	91.20	Feb. 17	91.18	May 18	89.53
Oct. 24	91.60	Jan. 14	91.35	Mar. 11	91.32	June 8	89.71

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175829066232200. Local number, 87.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'29", long 66°23'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.10 mi northeast of Santa Isabel plaza, 3.69 mi southeast of Escuela Playita Cortada, and 1.07 mi southeast of Estación Experimental Santa Isabel. Owner: Francisco Alomar, Name: Alomar 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), iron cased. Depth 112 ft (34.14 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 35.3 ft (10.8 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Bottom of clean-out shelter door, 2.50 ft (0.76 m), above land-surface datum. Prior to August 1981, top of recorder shelter floor, 4.00 ft (1.22 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital recorder (ADR) replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on December 16, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1967 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 8.45 ft (2.58 m), below land-surface datum, Dec. 10, 1970; lowest water level recorded, 49.18 ft (14.99 m) below land-surface datum, July 27, 1974.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	45.21	44.86	43.85	44.34	44.45	---	43.92	44.04	44.14	43.70	44.27	43.01
2	45.42	44.66	44.05	44.19	44.29	---	43.83	44.13	44.25	44.00	44.10	43.06
3	45.52	44.57	44.01	44.33	44.37	---	43.88	44.04	44.26	44.07	44.00	43.13
4	45.60	44.67	44.12	44.21	44.42	---	44.00	43.91	44.36	44.12	43.88	42.97
5	45.67	44.74	44.19	44.06	44.46	---	43.96	44.10	44.55	43.92	43.88	42.85
6	45.61	44.93	44.22	44.16	44.24	---	43.96	44.19	44.39	43.87	43.93	42.77
7	45.77	44.99	44.17	43.94	44.11	---	43.97	44.37	44.54	43.89	43.97	42.73
8	45.81	45.06	44.11	43.81	43.94	---	43.99	44.17	44.34	44.04	44.06	42.73
9	45.77	44.92	44.31	43.75	43.81	---	43.85	44.15	44.34	44.76	43.87	42.74
10	45.87	44.62	44.37	43.82	43.81	---	43.77	44.04	44.36	44.35	43.77	42.74
11	45.68	44.35	44.47	43.79	43.84	44.42	43.75	43.98	44.70	44.30	43.83	42.74
12	45.49	44.14	44.57	43.77	44.05	44.48	43.75	44.09	44.33	44.29	44.18	42.78
13	45.29	43.99	44.52	43.82	44.20	44.49	43.66	44.14	44.33	44.03	44.03	42.81
14	45.08	43.90	44.42	43.69	44.25	44.53	43.58	44.22	44.36	44.08	44.08	42.81
15	44.86	43.96	44.36	43.71	44.07	44.55	43.55	44.21	44.35	44.15	44.16	42.85
16	44.61	43.99	44.45	43.90	43.90	44.58	43.48	44.30	44.34	44.28	44.18	42.84
17	44.39	43.96	44.47	43.99	---	44.58	43.49	44.17	44.18	44.27	44.01	42.82
18	44.41	43.90	44.51	43.92	---	44.66	43.51	43.99	44.12	44.39	43.99	42.83
19	44.42	43.97	44.51	43.87	---	44.68	43.54	43.98	44.15	44.18	43.87	42.84
20	44.36	44.04	44.54	44.01	---	44.68	43.48	44.00	44.20	44.14	43.69	42.79
21	44.34	44.07	44.43	44.10	---	44.61	43.72	44.01	44.16	43.97	43.60	42.61
22	44.31	44.10	44.21	44.36	---	46.28	43.74	44.18	43.78	44.06	43.60	42.13
23	44.41	43.96	44.07	44.38	---	44.91	43.82	44.21	43.62	44.01	43.46	41.93
24	44.50	43.89	44.08	44.42	---	44.76	43.91	44.07	43.57	44.19	43.37	41.62
25	44.60	43.93	44.01	44.24	---	44.73	43.99	43.95	43.58	44.21	43.30	41.48
26	44.47	44.00	43.91	44.08	---	44.55	43.91	44.04	43.96	44.08	43.22	41.33
27	44.40	44.09	44.01	44.30	---	44.42	43.81	44.09	44.01	43.93	43.17	41.17
28	44.56	43.98	44.17	44.40	---	44.35	43.90	44.19	43.98	44.08	43.11	40.98
29	44.71	44.06	44.16	44.44	---	44.13	43.98	44.31	43.66	43.95	43.11	40.74
30	44.91	43.96	44.30	44.45	---	43.98	44.06	44.38	43.68	43.95	43.04	40.60
31	44.78	---	44.34	44.48	---	43.98	---	44.20	---	44.10	43.01	---
MEAN	44.99	44.28	44.26	44.09	44.14	44.59	43.79	44.12	44.15	44.11	43.73	42.38

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 44.04 HIGHEST 40.53 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 46.41 MAR. 22, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180020066261500. Local number, CA-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'20", long 66°26'15", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.04 mi north of the intersection of Hwy 536 with Hwy 1, 0.60 mi northwest of Central Cortada, and 0.10 mi west of Hwy 536. Owner: PR Land Authority, Name: Cabrera 1. AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 18 in (0.46 m). Depth 80.0 ft (24.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 65.6 ft (20.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on the top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.12 ft (0.95 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on Mar. 1, 1997. Well level affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 18, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 43.3 ft (13.2 m), below land-surface datum, Mar. 19, 20, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 55.0 ft (16.8 m), below land-surface datum, Apr. 14, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.78	46.62	47.87	---	---
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.94	46.67	48.06	---	---
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.86	46.70	50.57	---	---
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	44.14	45.87	46.74	48.72	---	---
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	44.27	45.93	46.77	48.29	---	---
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.23	46.08	46.82	48.39	---	---
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	44.26	46.08	46.80	48.05	---	---
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	44.48	46.06	46.75	48.15	---	---
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	48.78	47.44	46.74	48.15	---	---
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.78	46.10	46.78	50.70	---	---
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	44.90	46.07	46.84	50.92	---	---
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	48.09	46.12	46.87	50.30	---	---
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	48.22	46.15	46.91	49.61	---	---
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	48.66	46.22	46.97	48.53	---	---
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	47.92	46.23	47.02	48.61	---	---
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	47.01	46.26	47.02	48.87	---	---
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	49.50	46.25	47.02	---	---	---
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	47.91	46.26	49.05	---	---	---
19	---	---	---	---	---	43.60	45.51	46.27	49.10	---	---	---
20	---	---	---	---	---	43.31	48.19	47.81	48.41	---	---	---
21	---	---	---	---	---	43.60	45.39	46.46	47.36	---	---	---
22	---	---	---	---	---	47.50	45.51	46.40	47.47	---	---	---
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.01	46.50	50.59	---	---	---
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	49.29	46.48	50.67	---	---	---
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.71	46.44	47.91	---	---	---
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.61	46.45	47.67	---	---	---
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	48.90	46.47	47.80	---	---	---
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.06	46.58	47.95	---	---	---
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	50.01	46.59	50.49	---	---	---
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.87	46.57	48.16	---	---	---
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.65	---	---	---	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	44.50	46.75	46.33	47.62	48.99	---	---
WTR YR 1997	MEAN 47.12	HIGHEST 43.31	MAR. 19, 20, 1997	LOWEST 51.23	JULY 11, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	48.60	49.82	53.31	51.01	50.44	---	---	49.18	48.84
2	---	---	---	48.63	49.86	50.41	50.99	50.48	---	---	49.18	48.82
3	---	---	---	48.67	49.91	50.39	50.90	52.61	---	---	49.17	48.69
4	---	---	---	48.72	49.94	50.37	52.48	51.17	---	---	49.24	48.49
5	---	---	---	48.76	49.98	52.43	50.83	50.50	---	---	49.38	48.30
6	---	---	---	48.80	50.02	50.79	50.72	50.74	---	---	49.60	48.19
7	---	---	---	48.84	50.06	50.52	53.49	49.80	---	---	49.65	48.05
8	---	---	---	48.88	50.10	50.45	50.97	49.64	---	---	49.63	48.02
9	---	---	---	48.92	50.14	51.26	51.61	49.42	---	---	49.57	47.89
10	---	---	---	48.95	50.19	50.57	50.66	49.33	---	---	49.45	47.82
11	---	---	---	48.99	53.17	50.57	52.41	49.27	---	---	49.58	47.76
12	---	---	---	49.03	50.26	53.07	50.53	49.30	---	---	49.63	47.68
13	---	---	---	49.07	50.36	50.87	50.79	49.35	---	---	49.69	47.46
14	---	---	---	49.11	50.34	50.86	51.37	49.47	---	---	49.72	47.21
15	---	---	---	49.15	50.38	52.59	52.24	49.98	---	---	49.74	47.07
16	---	---	---	49.19	50.42	50.76	53.38	49.19	---	---	49.79	46.95
17	---	---	---	49.23	52.04	50.75	50.63	49.08	---	---	49.85	46.90
18	---	---	48.04	49.26	52.00	50.88	50.76	49.21	---	---	49.91	46.87
19	---	---	48.08	49.30	51.60	50.97	50.29	49.43	---	---	49.90	46.83
20	---	---	48.12	50.40	50.61	51.13	53.11	49.22	---	---	49.83	46.61
21	---	---	48.16	50.32	50.64	51.35	51.65	---	---	---	49.75	46.46
22	---	---	48.20	49.43	51.90	52.55	52.09	---	---	48.94	49.69	45.87
23	---	---	48.24	50.25	50.70	51.32	50.38	---	---	49.02	49.63	45.32
24	---	---	48.29	49.52	51.19	54.11	50.88	---	---	49.07	49.51	44.94
25	---	---	48.32	49.55	52.96	51.64	50.35	---	---	49.09	49.35	44.68
26	---	---	48.36	49.59	54.57	52.13	50.27	---	---	49.13	49.24	44.46
27	---	---	48.39	49.62	50.66	52.51	52.28	---	---	49.09	49.08	44.19
28	---	---	48.43	49.78	50.73	53.18	50.22	---	---	49.09	49.04	43.94
29	---	---	48.48	49.70	---	51.10	52.17	---	---	49.09	49.02	43.78
30	---	---	48.52	49.74	---	51.16	50.41	---	---	49.14	48.96	43.55
31	---	---	48.56	49.74	---	51.16	---	---	---	49.15	48.89	---
MEAN	---	---	48.30	49.28	50.88	51.46	51.33	49.88	---	49.08	49.48	46.72

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 49.72 HIGHEST 43.41 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 55.00 APR. 14, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180048066301800. Local number, FA-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'48", long 66°30'18", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 3.85 mi east of Central Mercedita, 2.13 mi south of the intersection of Hwy 149 with Hwy 52, and 0.64 mi west of hwy 149. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD,

Name: Fort Allen TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-201 ft (0-61.3 m), screened 30-201 ft (9.1-61.3 m). Depth 201 ft (61.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 38.0 ft (11.6 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on the top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.19 ft (0.97 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on March 12, 1997. Well destroyed for radar construction.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 12, 1997 to February 24, 1998, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 23.33 ft (7.11 m), below land-surface datum, Mar. 12, 13, 14, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 28.93 ft (8.82 m), below land-surface datum, Feb. 24, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.59	24.05	24.88	25.91	26.69	27.52
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.62	24.07	24.91	25.94	26.71	27.55
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.62	24.10	24.94	25.98	26.74	27.58
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.63	24.11	24.97	26.01	26.76	27.61
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.64	24.13	25.00	26.04	26.78	27.63
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.65	24.15	25.03	26.08	26.80	27.67
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.67	24.20	25.07	26.10	26.82	27.70
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.67	24.22	25.10	26.13	26.82	27.73
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.68	24.23	25.13	26.16	26.85	27.77
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.69	24.26	25.16	26.19	26.87	27.80
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.70	24.28	25.19	26.22	26.91	27.83
12	---	---	---	---	---	23.34	23.70	24.30	25.21	26.24	26.92	27.86
13	---	---	---	---	---	23.35	23.72	24.33	25.25	26.27	26.95	27.90
14	---	---	---	---	---	23.35	23.74	24.35	25.27	26.30	26.97	27.93
15	---	---	---	---	---	23.35	23.75	24.38	25.32	26.33	27.00	27.96
16	---	---	---	---	---	23.38	23.77	24.41	25.36	26.35	27.02	27.99
17	---	---	---	---	---	23.38	23.78	24.43	25.40	26.39	27.05	28.02
18	---	---	---	---	---	23.40	23.80	24.46	25.43	26.41	27.09	28.05
19	---	---	---	---	---	23.40	23.82	24.49	25.47	26.43	27.11	28.08
20	---	---	---	---	---	23.42	23.84	24.52	25.51	26.46	27.14	28.11
21	---	---	---	---	---	23.44	23.86	24.54	25.55	26.48	27.18	28.15
22	---	---	---	---	---	23.46	23.87	24.56	25.59	26.50	27.21	28.19
23	---	---	---	---	---	23.48	23.89	24.60	25.62	26.52	27.22	28.22
24	---	---	---	---	---	23.50	23.91	24.62	25.66	26.53	27.26	28.25
25	---	---	---	---	---	23.51	23.94	24.65	25.70	26.55	27.30	28.28
26	---	---	---	---	---	23.54	23.95	24.68	25.73	26.57	27.33	28.31
27	---	---	---	---	---	23.55	23.97	24.72	25.77	26.58	27.36	28.36
28	---	---	---	---	---	23.56	23.99	24.75	25.79	26.61	27.39	28.40
29	---	---	---	---	---	23.57	24.01	24.78	25.83	26.62	27.42	28.43
30	---	---	---	---	---	23.57	24.03	24.81	25.87	26.64	27.46	28.45
31	---	---	---	---	---	23.58	---	24.84	---	26.67	27.49	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	23.46	23.78	24.42	25.36	26.33	27.05	27.98

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 25.59 HIGHEST 23.33 MAR. 12, 13, 14, 1997 LOWEST 28.50 SEPT. 30, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28.50	28.92	28.67	28.58	28.62	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	28.54	28.92	28.67	28.58	28.64	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	28.57	28.92	28.66	28.58	28.65	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	28.60	28.93	28.66	28.58	28.65	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	28.63	28.93	28.65	28.59	28.69	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	28.67	28.93	28.65	28.58	28.70	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	28.69	28.93	28.65	28.58	28.70	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	28.71	28.93	28.65	28.58	28.70	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	28.76	28.93	28.65	28.57	28.71	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	28.79	28.93	28.65	28.57	28.72	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
11	28.80	28.93	28.65	28.57	28.74	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	28.83	28.91	28.65	28.56	28.74	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	28.86	28.89	28.65	28.56	28.75	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	28.88	28.88	28.64	28.55	28.76	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	28.90	28.85	28.64	28.54	28.76	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	28.90	28.85	28.64	28.54	28.76	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	28.91	28.82	28.65	28.53	28.76	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	28.91	28.80	28.64	28.53	28.77	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	28.90	28.79	28.64	28.52	28.78	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	28.90	28.78	28.63	28.52	28.79	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	28.90	28.77	28.63	28.52	28.79	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	28.90	28.76	28.62	28.52	28.80	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	28.90	28.75	28.61	28.52	28.82	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	28.91	28.74	28.61	28.52	28.82	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	28.91	28.73	28.60	28.53	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	28.91	28.72	28.59	28.55	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	28.92	28.71	28.59	28.56	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	28.92	28.70	28.59	28.57	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	28.92	28.69	28.59	28.58	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	28.92	28.68	28.58	28.59	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	28.92	---	28.58	28.60	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	28.82	28.83	28.63	28.56	28.73	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 28.71 HIGHEST 28.50 OCT. 1, 1997 LOWEST 28.93 FEB. 24, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

175950066354200. Local number, 141.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'50", long 66°35'42", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.71 mi southeast of Plaza Degetau at Ponce, 1.31 mi southeast of the intersection between Hwy 10 and Hwy 2, and 2.60 mi notheast of Muellle de Ponce. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Restaurada 8A.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused public supply well, diameter 16-10 in (0.41-0.25 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m)

2.00-20.0 ft (0.6-6.1 m), perforated 20-130 ft (6.10-39.6 m), 10 in (0.25 m) 128-165 ft (39.0-50.3 m), perforated. Depth 165 ft (50.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 24.0 ft (7.30 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Bottom edge of hole on side of casing 1.90 ft (0.58 m), above land-surface datum, 26.2 ft (7.67 m), above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Discontinued on Nov. 8, 1994 due to apparent collapsed casing, repair on August 7, 1996. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 12, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1981 to March 1, 1986, discontinued, November 18, 1991 to November 8, 1994, discontinued, August 7, 1996 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 11.2 ft (3.41 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 9, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 28.6 ft (8.71 m), below land-surface datum, July 9, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	26.15	24.45	---	23.41	---	23.54	22.84	24.66	24.43	23.51	23.33	21.78
2	26.16	24.55	---	23.02	---	23.69	22.81	24.73	24.42	23.54	23.44	21.85
3	26.18	24.60	---	22.94	---	23.54	22.71	24.73	24.36	23.64	23.46	21.93
4	25.89	24.49	---	22.87	---	23.70	22.71	24.41	24.45	23.63	23.49	21.89
5	25.50	24.55	---	23.34	---	23.75	22.69	24.16	24.53	23.57	23.52	21.76
6	25.44	---	---	23.87	---	23.77	22.69	24.20	24.53	23.62	23.49	21.75
7	25.37	---	---	24.02	---	23.83	22.72	24.20	24.52	23.52	23.48	21.71
8	26.01	---	---	23.92	---	23.86	22.70	24.16	24.52	23.51	23.38	21.67
9	26.04	---	---	22.92	---	23.89	22.74	23.99	24.50	23.51	23.25	21.64
10	26.06	---	---	23.64	---	23.87	22.78	24.01	24.54	23.50	23.17	21.74
11	25.96	---	---	23.87	---	23.88	22.81	24.00	24.60	23.64	23.17	21.63
12	25.94	---	---	23.98	23.07	23.96	22.68	23.98	24.61	23.68	23.17	21.68
13	25.88	---	---	23.96	22.88	23.92	22.64	23.57	24.59	23.67	23.20	21.67
14	25.69	---	---	23.98	22.76	23.80	22.57	23.60	24.56	23.69	23.10	21.53
15	25.61	---	---	24.04	22.64	23.70	22.52	23.97	24.52	23.71	23.06	21.54
16	25.30	---	24.13	23.88	22.65	23.74	22.50	23.95	24.24	23.76	22.97	21.38
17	25.00	---	24.11	24.05	22.60	23.84	22.50	24.09	24.61	23.80	22.96	21.32
18	24.80	---	23.44	24.07	22.55	23.84	22.50	24.14	24.52	23.77	22.80	21.33
19	24.70	---	24.06	24.09	22.57	23.87	22.50	24.31	24.46	23.68	22.80	21.31
20	24.55	---	24.09	24.09	22.06	23.72	22.54	24.35	24.44	23.65	22.77	21.30
21	24.63	---	23.86	24.14	21.77	23.77	22.56	24.36	24.39	23.62	22.69	21.23
22	24.65	---	23.98	---	21.70	23.66	22.56	24.39	21.95	23.62	21.98	17.23
23	24.64	---	24.05	---	22.29	23.71	22.58	24.42	20.85	23.53	22.41	15.67
24	24.44	---	24.07	---	23.16	23.72	22.63	24.42	20.37	23.64	22.43	14.79
25	24.41	---	24.08	---	23.41	23.42	22.63	24.35	20.02	23.63	22.27	14.34
26	24.36	---	24.10	---	23.43	23.43	22.55	24.36	21.37	23.61	22.01	14.13
27	24.29	---	24.09	---	23.46	23.28	22.44	24.37	22.92	23.54	21.85	17.40
28	24.28	---	24.09	---	23.52	23.27	22.43	24.40	23.20	23.44	21.79	18.03
29	24.29	---	24.11	---	---	23.17	21.96	24.39	23.24	23.35	21.80	18.40
30	24.18	---	24.12	---	---	23.19	24.40	24.44	23.41	23.32	21.77	18.71
31	24.35	---	24.14	---	---	22.88	---	24.41	---	23.34	21.81	---
MEAN	25.19	24.53	24.03	23.72	22.74	23.65	22.66	24.24	23.72	23.59	22.80	20.08

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 23.32 HIGHEST 14.12 SEPT. 26, 1998 LOWEST 26.18 OCT. 3, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

175934066364800. Local number, CO-3.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'34", long 66°36'48", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.35 mi southeast of the intersection of Hwy 10 with Hwy 2, 0.32 mi south of Hwy 2, 0.10 mi southwest of Plaza del Caribe Mall, and 1.90 mi north of Punta Carenero. Owner: Plaza del Caribe, Name: Constancia 3.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 13 in (0.33 m). Depth 84 ft (25.6 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 16.0 ft (4.90 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on the top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.12 ft (0.95 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 30, 1996, replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL,) installed during Mar. 19 to April 9, 1997. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), re-installed on April 9, 1997, replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on June 4, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 30, 1996 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 10.83 ft (3.30 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 17.96 ft (5.47 m), below land-surface datum, July 19, 20, 21, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1995 TO SEPTEMBER 1996
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.62	17.19	16.51	16.12
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.64	17.17	16.51	16.12
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.64	17.17	16.50	16.12
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.66	17.14	16.50	16.07
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.68	17.13	16.50	16.04
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.70	17.11	16.49	16.03
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.70	17.10	16.49	16.02
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.70	17.04	16.49	16.01
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.70	17.03	16.49	15.99
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.69	16.99	16.49	15.59
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.69	16.99	16.49	15.47
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.69	16.97	16.49	15.46
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.68	16.96	16.49	15.39
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.68	16.93	16.49	15.33
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.64	16.81	16.49	15.26
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.52	16.80	16.48	15.20
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.52	16.80	16.43	15.15
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.51	16.78	16.41	15.09
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.49	16.76	16.38	15.04
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.47	16.76	16.38	15.00
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.47	16.75	16.36	14.89
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.42	16.72	16.35	14.84
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.40	16.72	16.28	14.78
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.40	16.72	16.28	14.73
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.37	16.71	16.28	14.70
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.37	16.71	16.28	14.68
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.35	16.71	16.28	14.66
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.32	16.70	16.28	14.65
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.30	16.52	16.28	14.63
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.24	16.52	16.28	14.61
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.63	---	16.51	16.12	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.63	17.54	16.87	16.41	15.32

WTR YR 1996 MEAN 16.55 HIGHEST 14.59 SEPT. 30, 1996 LOWEST 17.70 JUNE 6-10, 1996

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS--continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14.57	14.32	13.56	13.66	14.08	14.66	15.16	15.88	16.94	17.71	17.86	17.45
2	14.55	14.27	13.54	13.65	14.09	14.68	15.16	15.91	16.96	17.73	17.86	17.43
3	14.52	14.26	13.52	13.64	14.11	14.69	15.17	15.94	16.97	17.75	17.86	17.42
4	14.50	14.25	13.51	13.64	14.13	14.73	15.17	15.99	16.98	17.76	17.82	17.41
5	14.50	14.24	13.51	13.63	14.14	14.74	15.17	16.06	16.99	17.77	17.81	17.38
6	14.49	14.23	13.51	13.63	14.16	14.76	15.16	16.08	17.04	17.78	17.79	17.36
7	14.48	14.22	13.51	13.63	14.18	14.78	15.16	16.10	17.08	17.79	17.79	17.34
8	14.46	14.20	13.52	13.63	14.19	14.80	15.18	16.12	17.09	17.80	17.78	17.32
9	14.45	14.18	13.53	13.65	14.21	14.81	15.21	16.13	17.14	17.80	17.76	17.28
10	14.44	14.03	13.53	13.67	14.23	14.83	15.21	16.15	17.15	17.83	17.74	17.27
11	14.44	14.04	13.53	13.70	14.25	14.85	15.24	16.22	17.17	17.84	17.73	17.27
12	14.44	14.02	13.54	13.72	14.28	14.87	15.27	16.30	17.19	17.86	17.68	17.26
13	14.44	13.97	13.55	13.73	14.31	14.89	15.29	16.32	17.21	17.87	17.68	17.26
14	14.44	13.96	13.55	13.74	14.33	14.92	15.32	16.35	17.23	17.89	17.68	17.26
15	14.46	13.94	13.56	13.76	14.36	14.92	15.33	16.39	17.29	17.91	17.66	17.26
16	14.48	13.94	13.57	13.78	14.38	14.93	15.34	16.45	17.32	17.92	17.62	17.26
17	14.49	13.92	13.60	13.80	14.40	14.96	15.36	16.54	17.35	17.92	17.57	17.26
18	14.50	13.88	13.61	13.83	14.43	---	15.38	16.55	17.37	17.93	17.53	17.26
19	14.50	13.86	13.64	13.85	14.45	15.01	15.41	16.58	17.40	17.95	17.48	17.27
20	14.42	13.77	13.65	13.87	14.47	15.02	15.44	16.60	17.41	17.96	17.46	17.28
21	14.41	13.76	13.67	13.88	14.52	15.03	15.48	16.64	17.45	17.96	17.46	17.30
22	14.40	13.74	13.68	13.91	14.53	15.04	15.52	16.68	17.47	17.89	17.46	17.31
23	14.39	13.72	13.69	13.91	14.55	15.05	15.54	16.71	17.49	17.89	17.46	17.32
24	14.38	13.70	13.71	13.93	14.57	15.07	15.57	16.74	17.50	17.89	17.46	17.33
25	14.38	13.68	13.71	13.94	14.60	15.10	15.59	16.75	17.53	17.89	17.46	17.34
26	14.38	13.65	13.71	13.95	14.62	15.13	15.63	16.79	17.58	17.89	17.46	17.35
27	14.38	13.63	13.70	13.97	14.63	15.15	15.70	16.81	17.60	17.87	17.46	17.35
28	14.36	13.62	13.70	13.98	14.65	15.16	15.74	16.86	17.63	17.87	17.46	17.35
29	14.35	13.59	13.70	13.99	---	15.16	15.79	16.89	17.66	17.86	17.46	17.35
30	14.34	13.57	13.69	14.05	---	15.15	15.84	16.92	17.69	17.86	17.46	17.35
31	14.34	---	13.66	14.06	---	15.15	---	16.93	---	17.86	17.45	---
MEAN	14.44	13.94	13.60	13.80	14.35	14.93	15.38	16.43	17.30	17.85	17.62	17.32
WTR YR 1997	MEAN 15.59	HIGHEST 13.61	DEC. 3-7, 1996	LOWEST 17.96	JULY 19, 20, 21, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS--continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17.35	16.12	16.10	16.36	16.36	16.23	16.32	15.90	16.08	15.50	15.26	14.04
2	17.37	16.11	16.11	16.34	16.36	16.24	16.32	15.90	16.08	15.50	15.26	14.00
3	17.38	16.09	16.13	16.33	16.38	16.27	16.23	15.91	16.07	15.51	15.25	13.97
4	17.26	16.08	16.14	16.31	16.39	16.30	16.23	15.91	15.91	15.51	15.25	13.79
5	17.24	16.08	16.15	16.30	16.29	16.33	16.23	15.94	15.91	15.50	15.25	13.79
6	17.26	16.07	16.16	16.21	16.28	16.34	16.23	15.95	15.91	15.49	15.24	13.69
7	17.27	16.07	16.18	16.15	16.28	16.35	16.22	15.97	15.91	15.49	15.16	13.67
8	17.28	16.07	16.19	16.15	16.26	16.37	16.22	15.97	15.90	15.48	15.15	13.65
9	17.29	16.08	16.20	16.15	16.23	16.37	16.21	15.97	15.90	15.49	15.08	13.61
10	17.29	16.01	16.21	16.15	16.23	16.38	16.21	15.97	15.87	15.50	15.04	13.59
11	17.10	16.00	16.23	16.16	16.22	16.40	16.21	15.97	15.87	15.51	14.99	13.69
12	17.12	16.00	16.27	16.16	16.21	16.42	15.99	15.97	15.86	15.51	14.97	13.68
13	17.11	16.01	16.29	16.17	16.21	16.43	16.01	15.99	15.85	15.51	14.94	13.64
14	16.86	16.01	16.31	16.19	16.20	16.45	16.02	16.00	15.84	15.52	14.92	13.57
15	16.77	16.02	16.32	16.19	16.19	16.47	16.01	16.01	15.83	15.53	14.89	13.56
16	16.61	16.02	16.34	16.20	16.17	16.50	15.99	16.03	15.82	15.55	14.83	13.22
17	16.57	16.02	16.34	16.21	16.16	16.52	15.99	16.03	15.81	15.57	14.80	13.23
18	16.53	16.02	16.34	16.21	16.16	16.54	15.98	16.05	15.75	15.58	14.78	13.22
19	16.40	16.02	16.36	16.21	16.16	16.56	15.97	16.07	15.75	15.39	14.73	13.21
20	16.37	16.02	16.37	16.21	16.16	16.59	15.97	16.08	15.74	15.43	14.70	13.21
21	16.34	16.02	16.38	16.22	16.17	16.59	15.97	16.09	15.73	15.44	14.68	13.19
22	16.31	16.03	16.38	16.23	16.17	16.59	15.95	16.09	15.55	15.45	14.66	12.13
23	16.30	16.03	16.39	16.26	16.17	16.59	15.95	16.10	15.55	15.45	14.65	11.28
24	16.24	16.04	16.39	16.29	16.18	16.59	15.95	16.11	15.55	15.46	14.62	11.17
25	16.20	16.05	16.40	16.30	16.19	16.58	15.93	16.11	15.54	15.46	14.17	11.06
26	16.17	16.06	16.41	16.31	16.20	16.54	15.91	16.12	15.53	15.47	14.21	10.98
27	16.16	16.07	16.40	16.32	16.22	16.51	15.90	16.12	15.52	15.47	14.20	10.91
28	16.16	16.08	16.39	16.33	16.23	16.47	15.90	16.10	15.49	15.30	14.17	10.87
29	16.16	16.08	16.37	16.33	---	16.44	15.90	16.10	15.50	15.23	14.14	10.84
30	16.15	16.09	16.37	16.34	---	16.43	15.90	16.10	15.50	15.26	14.10	10.83
31	16.13	---	16.36	16.35	---	16.31	---	16.09	---	15.26	14.07	---
MEAN	16.73	16.05	16.29	16.25	16.23	16.44	16.06	16.02	15.77	15.46	14.78	12.84

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 15.75 HIGHEST 10.83 SEPT. 30, 1998 LOWEST 17.38 OCT. 3, 4, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASIN

180045066381600. Local number AN-1

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'45", long 66°38'16", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.27 mi east of the intersection of Hwy 10 with Hwy 132, 0.60 mi northwest of Parque Montaner, and 0.04 mi south of Hwy 132. Owner: Albergue de Niños de Ponce, Name: Albergue de Niños.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 49.0 ft (14.90 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 5.42 ft (1.65 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR) replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 12, 1998.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 30, 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 28.57 ft (8.71 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 27, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 51.88 ft (15.81 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 30, 1994.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	30.98	29.63	30.97	32.24	32.47	32.74	33.31	33.87	34.76	34.58	35.82	34.61
2	30.94	29.61	31.05	32.68	32.48	32.81	33.38	33.95	34.82	34.65	35.79	34.51
3	30.97	30.21	31.09	32.21	32.54	32.82	32.85	33.94	35.36	34.94	35.82	34.44
4	30.80	30.30	31.12	32.03	32.47	33.41	33.39	34.00	34.91	35.08	35.87	34.35
5	30.77	30.51	31.21	31.88	32.46	32.99	33.39	33.86	34.95	35.18	35.87	34.24
6	31.26	30.02	31.08	31.77	32.43	33.79	33.41	33.94	34.99	35.27	35.92	34.14
7	30.98	30.12	31.13	32.01	32.34	33.01	33.41	33.99	35.03	35.36	35.94	34.03
8	30.96	30.06	31.28	31.55	32.29	32.92	33.55	34.48	35.09	35.55	35.52	34.20
9	31.07	30.05	31.31	31.52	32.32	33.45	33.81	34.09	35.59	35.51	35.31	33.95
10	30.98	30.25	31.37	31.82	32.36	33.82	33.15	34.08	34.72	35.60	35.32	33.88
11	30.74	30.28	31.46	31.88	32.39	33.36	33.22	34.11	34.60	35.62	35.64	34.28
12	30.60	30.23	31.38	31.97	32.37	34.06	33.35	33.84	34.52	---	36.11	33.74
13	30.89	30.11	31.41	32.03	32.39	33.55	33.51	33.71	34.49	---	35.91	33.67
14	30.46	30.06	31.45	32.49	32.37	33.53	33.60	33.74	34.46	---	35.74	33.67
15	30.36	30.10	31.63	32.14	32.39	33.44	33.59	34.12	34.52	---	35.75	33.64
16	30.15	30.19	31.56	32.16	32.43	33.56	33.62	34.07	34.90	---	35.75	33.34
17	30.14	30.37	31.73	32.17	32.45	33.60	34.13	34.15	35.09	---	35.76	33.40
18	29.99	30.49	31.79	32.15	32.68	33.41	33.72	34.20	35.19	---	35.74	33.38
19	29.92	30.53	32.28	32.15	32.51	33.41	33.71	34.28	35.31	---	35.67	33.33
20	29.97	30.60	31.84	32.17	32.55	33.82	33.85	34.33	35.37	---	35.67	33.28
21	30.09	30.66	31.87	32.21	32.58	33.28	33.90	34.37	35.39	---	35.60	33.17
22	30.02	30.27	31.96	32.28	32.54	33.24	34.07	34.39	35.47	---	35.57	31.65
23	29.95	30.35	32.01	32.31	32.54	33.32	33.91	34.44	35.54	35.80	35.58	30.45
24	29.88	31.01	32.36	32.33	32.54	33.34	33.94	34.44	35.57	35.81	35.56	29.69
25	29.68	30.75	32.12	32.33	32.55	33.29	33.95	34.46	35.55	35.82	35.44	29.21
26	29.66	30.82	32.15	32.35	32.54	33.28	33.93	34.53	35.73	35.79	35.29	28.77
27	29.85	30.75	32.13	32.42	33.14	33.24	34.43	35.04	35.19	35.80	35.18	29.03
28	29.70	30.80	32.13	32.42	33.24	33.25	34.05	34.66	35.12	35.82	35.13	29.18
29	29.64	30.81	32.16	32.48	---	33.23	34.07	34.69	34.84	35.83	34.98	29.15
30	29.67	30.79	32.21	32.47	---	33.78	33.74	34.70	35.13	35.81	34.80	29.20
31	29.71	---	32.25	32.43	---	33.31	---	34.72	---	35.83	34.75	---
MEAN	30.35	30.36	31.66	32.16	32.51	33.36	33.66	34.23	35.07	35.48	35.57	32.59

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 33.02 HIGHEST 28.57 SEPT. 27, 1998 LOWEST 36.27 JULY 27, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

180156066434000. Local number, LV-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'56", long 66°43'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.23 mi north of Hwy 2, 0.10 mi west of Hwy 385, and 0.14 mi east of Río Tallaboa. Owner: CORCO, Name: Luciana Ventura.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well. Depth 66.4 ft (20.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 66.0 ft (20.1 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map..

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on September 5, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 5, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 16.65 ft (5.07 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 23, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 28.87 ft (8.80 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 28, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.75
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.75
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.16
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.27
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.56
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.33
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.05
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.12
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.30
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.28
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.86
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.38
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.87
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.84
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.83
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.31
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.34
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.83
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.68
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.60
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.75
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.63
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.90
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	28.65
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	28.40
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.36
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.42
WTR YR 1997	MEAN 26.42	HIGHEST 24.33	SEPT. 10, 1997	LOWEST 28.87	SEPT. 28, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	26.55	24.42	24.85	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.50	23.97	23.84
2	26.18	24.18	25.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.62	24.64	23.70
3	26.13	24.73	24.98	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.31	24.88	23.48
4	25.89	25.04	24.79	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.26	24.83	22.78
5	26.23	25.13	24.63	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.20	24.86	22.54
6	26.58	25.22	24.68	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.58	25.03	22.71
7	27.17	25.16	24.92	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.64	24.79	22.29
8	26.70	25.13	25.29	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.30	24.38	22.76
9	25.13	25.19	25.19	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.34	24.36	22.47
10	24.97	25.14	25.20	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.35	23.94	22.59
11	25.18	25.06	24.57	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.35	23.69	22.68
12	25.06	24.60	25.37	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.39	23.50	22.65
13	24.70	24.16	25.36	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.12	23.62	22.87
14	24.40	24.05	25.51	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.59	23.87	22.76
15	23.90	24.09	25.30	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.73	23.31	23.13
16	23.49	23.86	25.38	---	---	---	---	---	24.66	24.67	23.10	23.21
17	23.74	23.81	25.39	---	---	---	---	---	25.05	24.85	23.08	23.49
18	23.65	23.61	25.46	---	---	---	---	---	24.47	25.08	23.12	23.29
19	23.57	23.63	24.95	---	---	---	---	---	24.39	24.69	23.13	23.73
20	23.93	23.62	24.93	---	---	---	---	---	24.37	24.85	23.25	23.42
21	23.88	24.27	25.09	---	---	---	---	---	24.43	24.77	23.21	23.19
22	23.91	23.81	25.10	---	---	---	---	---	23.93	24.87	23.18	21.26
23	24.02	24.33	25.48	---	---	---	---	---	24.11	24.19	23.08	16.75
24	23.67	24.61	24.63	---	---	---	---	---	23.54	24.51	23.20	---
25	24.15	24.55	24.29	---	---	---	---	---	23.82	24.67	23.19	---
26	24.13	24.70	24.54	---	---	---	---	---	23.69	24.00	23.18	---
27	24.37	24.77	24.90	---	---	---	---	---	23.25	24.67	23.16	---
28	24.50	24.65	25.29	---	---	---	---	---	23.71	24.40	23.39	---
29	24.59	24.84	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.47	23.97	23.47	---
30	24.16	24.87	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.28	24.20	23.33	---
31	24.77	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.07	23.53	---
MEAN	24.82	24.51	25.04	---	---	---	---	---	24.01	24.09	23.72	22.68

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 24.18 HIGHEST 16.65 SEPT. 23, 1998 LOWEST 27.23 OCT. 7, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

180133066503300. Local number, 132.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'33", long 66°50'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.90 mi southeast of Yauco plaza, 3.46 mi west of Guayanilla plaza, and 1.32 mi north of Escuela Segunda Unidad Barinas. Owner: Pittsburg Plate Glass 4, Name: Yauco 2. AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-20.0 ft (0-6.10 m), 12 in (0.30 m) perforated pipe 20-84.0 ft (6.10-25.6 m), 10 in (0.25 m) perforated pipe 84-190 ft (25.6-57.9 m). Depth 190 ft (57.9 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 75.0 ft (22.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.35 ft (0.72 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 17, 1998. [+ , above land-surface datum]. From July 27, 1998, monthly measurements only.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1972 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +0.12 ft (0.04 m), above land-surface datum, July 19, 1979; lowest water level recorded, 36.91 ft (11.25 m), below land-surface datum, June 27, 1974.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	32.78	24.26	22.81	25.18	---	22.42	25.88	24.39	22.43	---	---	---
2	32.69	24.26	22.89	25.03	---	22.47	25.55	24.51	22.29	---	---	---
3	32.48	24.25	22.86	24.90	---	22.58	25.30	24.57	22.25	---	---	---
4	32.58	24.20	22.97	24.77	---	22.65	25.00	24.67	22.20	---	---	---
5	32.40	---	23.11	24.73	---	22.83	24.81	24.81	---	---	---	---
6	32.29	24.24	23.13	24.77	---	22.92	24.66	24.91	---	---	---	---
7	31.56	24.26	23.26	24.67	---	22.92	24.65	24.93	---	---	---	---
8	31.96	24.26	---	24.59	---	22.93	24.56	25.02	---	---	---	---
9	31.05	24.20	---	24.53	---	23.03	24.51	25.04	---	---	---	---
10	29.94	23.98	---	24.58	---	23.15	24.50	25.04	---	---	---	---
11	29.30	23.76	---	24.63	---	23.30	24.41	25.00	---	---	---	---
12	28.60	23.58	---	24.56	---	23.45	24.39	25.08	---	---	---	---
13	28.09	23.34	---	24.58	---	23.50	24.25	25.10	---	---	---	---
14	27.11	23.21	---	---	---	23.67	24.13	25.17	---	---	---	---
15	26.63	23.14	---	---	---	23.85	23.99	25.10	---	---	---	---
16	26.23	22.98	---	---	---	23.90	23.93	24.86	---	---	---	---
17	25.95	22.84	---	---	---	24.03	23.92	24.62	---	---	---	---
18	25.41	22.64	---	---	22.77	24.18	23.79	24.44	---	---	---	---
19	25.11	22.56	---	---	22.57	24.35	23.64	24.39	---	---	---	---
20	24.85	22.58	---	---	22.48	24.49	23.53	24.29	---	---	---	---
21	24.54	22.55	---	---	22.49	24.52	23.60	24.12	---	---	---	---
22	24.39	22.55	---	---	22.38	24.61	23.77	23.91	---	---	---	---
23	24.74	22.49	---	---	22.36	24.81	23.79	23.62	---	---	---	---
24	24.56	22.54	24.96	---	22.41	25.00	23.87	23.45	---	---	---	---
25	24.59	22.61	25.13	---	22.31	25.14	23.96	23.26	---	---	---	---
26	24.51	22.57	25.15	---	22.29	25.20	24.00	23.21	---	---	---	---
27	24.35	22.67	25.20	---	22.31	25.27	24.00	23.16	---	---	---	---
28	24.36	22.61	25.18	---	22.37	25.38	24.07	23.10	---	---	---	---
29	24.37	22.71	25.24	---	---	25.44	24.18	22.90	---	---	---	---
30	24.30	22.66	25.35	---	---	25.56	24.28	22.77	---	---	---	---
31	24.22	---	25.42	---	---	25.77	---	22.60	---	---	---	---
MEAN	27.61	23.26	24.18	24.73	22.43	23.98	24.30	24.26	22.29	---	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 24.49 HIGHEST 22.19 JUNE 4, 1998 LOWEST 32.83 OCT. 1, 1997

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180132067033800. Local number, 143.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'32", long 67°03'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.86 mi south of Lajas plaza, 1.27 mi southeast of the Estación Experimental Agrícola, and 1.30 mi northwest of the intersection of Hwy 116 with Hwy 305.

Owner: Pedro P. Vivoni, Name: Vivoni, Hacienda Amistad.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of unknown age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused irrigation well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m). Depth 200 ft (60.98 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 52.5 ft (16.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole side of casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR) replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on January 14, 1998. From July 27, 1998, monthly measurements only.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1981 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 37.4 ft (11.4 m), below land, -surface datum, Nov. 20, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 40.85 ft (12.45 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 8, 9, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	40.75	40.68	40.56	40.70	40.62	40.50	40.63	40.67	40.74	---	---	---
2	40.75	40.68	40.59	40.68	40.62	40.52	40.67	40.66	40.76	---	---	---
3	40.75	40.68	40.61	40.66	40.57	40.52	40.68	40.68	40.77	---	---	---
4	40.78	40.67	40.60	40.64	40.59	40.54	40.67	40.67	40.78	---	---	---
5	40.80	40.68	40.58	40.64	40.48	40.56	40.65	40.70	---	---	---	---
6	40.83	40.67	40.58	40.67	40.54	40.55	40.66	40.69	---	---	---	---
7	40.84	40.66	40.62	40.64	40.53	40.57	40.70	40.69	---	---	---	---
8	40.83	40.63	40.64	40.66	40.53	40.59	40.76	40.67	---	---	---	---
9	40.83	40.65	40.64	40.67	40.53	40.63	40.77	40.72	---	---	---	---
10	40.77	40.65	40.63	40.67	40.59	40.64	40.73	40.72	---	---	---	---
11	40.76	40.67	40.64	40.65	40.62	40.63	40.74	40.70	---	---	---	---
12	40.71	40.67	40.65	40.66	40.58	40.63	40.72	40.73	---	---	---	---
13	40.70	40.64	40.64	40.66	40.58	40.65	40.77	40.74	---	---	---	---
14	40.56	40.63	40.64	40.64	40.58	40.64	40.78	40.72	---	---	---	---
15	40.58	40.63	40.63	40.64	40.58	40.60	40.78	40.70	---	---	---	---
16	40.62	40.64	40.62	40.65	40.55	40.60	40.78	40.71	---	---	---	---
17	40.65	40.63	40.62	40.66	40.52	40.60	40.74	40.73	---	---	---	---
18	40.66	40.61	40.63	40.64	40.52	40.63	40.69	40.75	---	---	---	---
19	40.67	40.59	40.66	40.62	40.52	40.63	40.68	40.75	---	---	---	---
20	40.66	40.57	40.65	40.63	40.52	40.62	40.70	40.77	---	---	---	---
21	40.65	40.59	40.63	40.63	40.51	40.59	40.71	40.75	---	---	---	---
22	40.66	40.57	40.65	40.65	40.55	40.62	40.72	40.75	---	---	---	---
23	40.67	40.58	40.64	40.68	40.53	40.65	40.72	40.76	---	---	---	---
24	40.66	40.59	40.64	40.66	40.54	40.69	40.73	40.77	---	---	---	---
25	40.66	40.58	40.65	40.67	40.54	40.73	40.74	40.75	---	---	---	---
26	40.67	40.57	40.66	40.66	40.52	40.73	40.74	40.75	---	---	---	---
27	40.66	40.57	40.63	40.67	40.53	40.71	40.71	40.77	---	---	---	---
28	40.67	40.60	40.63	40.68	40.52	40.68	40.70	40.76	---	---	---	---
29	40.69	40.58	40.65	40.66	---	40.67	40.72	40.75	---	---	---	---
30	40.68	40.55	40.67	40.62	---	40.63	40.71	40.75	---	---	---	---
31	40.67	---	40.69	40.60	---	40.61	---	40.75	---	---	---	---
MEAN	40.70	40.62	40.63	40.65	40.55	40.62	40.72	40.73	40.76	---	---	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 40.66 HIGHEST 40.42 FEB. 5, 1998 LOWEST 40.85 OCT. 8, 9, 1997

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180541067084000. Local number, CR-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'41", long 67°08'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 0.35 mi east of Hwy 311, 0.30 mi north of Hwy 102 in Central Cabo Rojo, and 0.50 mi northwest of the intersection of Hwy 102 with hwy 103. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Cabo Rojo 1.

AQUIFER.--Coquí Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 18.9 ft (12.0 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole in the side of the 12.0 in (0.30 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 25, 1996.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 25, 1996 to September 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.37 ft (2.86 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 27, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 28.41 ft (8.66 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 8, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1995 TO SEPTEMBER 1996
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.18	16.73	18.10	15.55
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.20	17.18	17.56	15.51
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.27	17.35	17.28	15.65
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.53	17.22	16.69	15.73
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.78	17.18	16.39	15.66
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.91	17.30	16.36	15.60
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.31	17.20	16.42	16.06
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.84	17.36	16.08	16.12
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.87	16.75	15.62	16.55
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.00	17.16	15.68	15.81
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.21	17.36	15.06	15.90
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.37	17.39	14.77	15.86
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.50	17.69	14.67	15.88
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.20	17.54	14.58	16.04
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.39	17.53	14.35	16.17
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.47	16.93	14.46	16.27
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.54	17.36	14.67	16.53
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.66	17.22	14.51	16.71
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.85	17.36	14.50	16.83
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.77	17.40	14.84	16.86
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.89	17.29	14.99	17.10
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.97	17.26	15.27	16.65
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.02	17.53	15.55	16.76
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.18	17.64	15.45	16.78
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.41	17.89	15.05	16.98
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.61	17.98	14.82	17.17
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.73	18.12	15.17	17.08
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.94	17.99	15.13	17.23
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.84	17.77	15.17	16.95
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.87	16.67	17.74	15.34	16.75
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.95	---	18.01	15.54	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.91	15.50	17.43	15.49	16.36
WTR YR 1996	MEAN 16.16	HIGHEST 13.76	MAY 29, 1996	LOWEST 18.29	JULY 31, 1996							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	
1	16.69	15.13	12.12	18.79	17.72	18.50	20.10	21.93	24.75	---	---	---	
2	16.69	15.76	12.26	18.87	17.80	18.55	20.11	22.05	24.80	---	---	---	
3	16.51	15.55	12.67	19.01	17.79	18.72	20.37	22.21	24.89	---	---	---	
4	16.34	15.57	13.14	18.90	17.56	18.97	20.31	22.19	24.83	---	---	---	
5	15.98	15.83	13.38	18.93	17.53	19.15	20.38	22.34	24.76	---	---	---	
6	15.38	15.71	15.08	19.00	17.27	19.21	20.32	22.49	24.75	---	---	---	
7	15.10	15.66	15.24	19.03	16.98	19.27	20.31	22.57	25.15	---	---	---	
8	15.03	15.78	15.50	19.29	17.05	19.21	20.35	22.49	25.38	---	---	---	
9	14.97	15.74	15.67	19.09	16.95	19.22	20.35	22.61	25.24	---	---	---	
10	14.85	15.23	15.86	18.53	16.95	19.26	20.52	22.48	25.40	---	---	---	
11	14.86	15.07	16.08	18.05	16.86	19.41	20.43	22.53	25.46	---	---	---	
12	14.88	14.98	16.20	17.67	16.77	19.39	20.54	22.53	25.56	---	---	---	
13	14.72	14.41	16.25	17.50	16.82	19.51	20.68	23.36	25.69	---	---	---	
14	14.66	14.34	16.37	17.58	17.03	19.60	20.69	23.53	26.02	---	---	---	
15	14.68	13.96	16.71	17.83	17.13	19.75	21.00	23.73	26.04	---	---	---	
16	14.66	13.52	17.02	17.73	17.28	19.78	20.95	23.98	26.14	---	---	---	
17	14.68	13.32	16.95	17.74	17.55	19.78	20.98	24.11	---	---	---	---	
18	14.96	13.15	17.09	17.83	17.80	19.86	20.99	24.11	---	---	---	---	
19	15.01	12.81	17.25	17.88	17.83	19.86	20.88	24.15	---	---	---	---	
20	14.95	12.42	17.24	17.83	17.88	19.95	20.89	24.15	---	---	---	---	
21	14.70	12.46	17.53	18.02	18.20	20.17	21.11	24.27	---	---	---	---	
22	14.75	12.32	17.66	17.81	18.19	20.24	21.04	24.27	---	---	---	---	
23	15.20	12.05	17.90	17.63	18.22	20.24	21.25	24.27	---	---	---	---	
24	15.42	11.78	18.19	17.58	18.32	20.28	21.29	24.34	---	---	---	25.97	
25	15.38	11.77	18.44	17.48	18.45	20.38	21.28	24.31	---	---	---	26.05	
26	15.26	12.06	18.51	17.43	18.44	20.54	21.30	24.43	---	---	---	25.94	
27	15.02	11.93	18.65	17.44	18.43	20.58	21.44	24.54	---	---	---	25.89	
28	14.94	12.00	18.63	17.42	18.42	20.60	21.56	24.63	---	---	---	25.93	
29	15.13	11.86	18.58	17.19	---	20.59	21.80	24.69	---	---	---	25.96	
30	15.45	11.87	18.66	17.43	---	20.45	21.85	24.77	---	---	---	25.44	
31	15.29	---	18.60	17.69	---	20.37	---	24.89	---	---	---	---	
MEAN	15.23	13.80	16.43	18.07	17.61	19.72	20.84	23.51	25.30	---	---	25.88	
WTR YR 1997	MEAN 18.80	HIGHEST 11.63	NOV. 25, 1996	LOWEST 26.39	JUNE 16, 1997								

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	24.87	18.39	20.35	23.56	26.16	24.94	27.75	---	---	---	---	19.95
2	24.50	18.56	20.46	23.58	26.42	25.01	27.78	---	---	---	---	19.40
3	24.03	18.75	20.60	23.59	26.57	25.37	27.90	---	---	---	---	18.74
4	23.89	18.85	20.80	23.63	26.62	25.54	28.00	---	---	---	---	17.98
5	23.59	18.96	20.86	23.69	26.43	25.81	28.04	---	---	---	---	17.48
6	23.50	18.97	20.86	23.75	26.16	26.01	28.05	---	---	---	---	17.01
7	23.38	18.72	20.92	23.77	25.98	26.08	28.19	---	---	---	---	16.45
8	23.00	19.03	20.96	23.91	25.59	26.22	28.41	---	---	---	---	16.21
9	22.47	19.22	21.09	24.09	25.43	26.32	---	---	---	---	---	16.11
10	21.90	19.14	21.28	24.33	25.47	26.70	---	---	---	---	---	16.43
11	21.54	19.14	21.31	24.23	25.34	26.88	---	---	---	---	---	16.66
12	21.14	19.11	21.42	24.03	25.21	27.04	---	---	---	---	---	16.93
13	20.81	19.20	21.63	23.92	25.02	27.04	---	---	---	---	---	16.96
14	20.16	19.23	21.71	24.10	24.89	26.99	---	---	---	---	---	16.92
15	19.16	19.35	21.82	24.30	24.82	26.85	---	---	---	---	---	16.98
16	18.33	19.33	22.23	24.42	24.64	26.84	---	---	---	---	---	16.73
17	17.74	19.45	22.32	24.54	24.65	26.78	---	---	---	---	---	17.06
18	17.36	19.61	22.48	24.62	24.69	26.78	---	---	---	---	---	17.37
19	17.10	19.58	22.56	24.77	24.61	26.88	---	---	---	---	---	17.70
20	16.97	19.55	22.69	24.86	24.62	26.92	---	---	---	---	---	18.09
21	17.00	19.59	22.61	25.07	24.64	26.97	---	---	---	---	---	18.00
22	17.03	19.67	22.76	25.35	24.73	26.94	---	---	---	---	---	14.31
23	17.08	19.79	22.89	25.46	24.68	26.90	---	---	---	---	---	11.45
24	17.52	19.86	23.14	25.56	24.80	26.97	---	---	---	---	---	10.54
25	17.51	20.04	23.16	25.53	24.87	27.07	---	---	---	---	---	9.98
26	17.73	20.18	23.08	25.55	24.81	27.10	---	---	---	---	---	9.58
27	17.82	20.31	23.11	25.60	24.95	27.37	---	---	---	---	---	9.50
28	17.87	20.46	23.27	25.64	25.05	27.46	---	---	---	---	---	11.23
29	17.96	20.37	23.27	25.78	---	27.60	---	---	---	---	---	12.56
30	18.06	20.44	23.39	26.03	---	27.68	---	---	---	---	---	13.55
31	18.23	---	23.50	26.14	---	27.85	---	---	---	---	20.02	---
MEAN	19.98	19.43	22.02	24.63	25.28	26.67	28.01	---	---	---	20.02	15.60

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 22.15 HIGHEST 9.37 SEPT. 27, 1998 LOWEST 28.41 APR. 8, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180628067084300. Local number, CR-TW9A.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'28", long 67°08'43", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.29 mi north of Cabo Rojo plaza, 1.54 mi northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad Antonio Acarón Correa, and 1.23 mi southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-9A.

AQUIFER.--Sandy and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-24.0 ft (0-7.32 m), screened 19-24 ft (5.79-7.32 m). Depth 24.0 ft (7.32 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 33.2 ft (10.1 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor, 4.51 ft (1.37 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Drilled on Mar. 25, 1992. Automatic Digital Recorder (ADR), re-installed on May 29, 1996.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1992 to January 1994, discontinued, May 27, 1996 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +0.24 ft (+0.07 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 8.53 ft (2.60 m), below land-surface datum, Mar. 21, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	4.95	3.37	4.02	5.62	7.17	7.41	---	---	---	---	---	3.07
2	4.71	3.44	4.09	5.66	7.17	7.51	---	---	---	---	---	2.56
3	4.55	3.49	4.11	5.73	7.17	7.60	---	---	---	---	---	1.96
4	4.46	3.53	4.14	5.77	7.17	7.71	---	---	---	---	---	1.60
5	4.40	3.59	4.18	5.83	7.16	7.83	---	---	---	---	---	1.74
6	4.37	3.60	4.22	5.89	7.06	7.91	---	---	---	---	---	1.53
7	4.34	3.60	4.27	5.94	6.84	8.01	---	---	---	---	---	.92
8	4.30	3.60	4.33	5.98	6.74	8.15	---	---	---	---	---	1.47
9	3.87	3.64	4.34	6.07	6.57	8.24	---	---	---	---	---	1.86
10	3.53	3.63	4.38	6.17	6.57	8.34	---	---	---	---	---	2.08
11	3.24	3.60	4.42	6.25	6.57	8.48	---	---	---	---	---	2.27
12	3.16	3.61	4.45	6.35	6.57	8.51	---	---	---	---	---	2.43
13	3.08	3.61	4.49	6.41	6.57	8.51	---	---	---	---	---	2.32
14	1.85	3.62	4.55	6.46	6.57	8.51	---	---	---	---	---	2.39
15	1.18	3.65	4.62	6.56	6.57	8.52	---	---	---	---	---	2.52
16	1.39	3.65	4.71	6.70	6.57	8.52	---	---	---	---	---	2.56
17	1.71	3.66	4.75	6.85	6.57	8.52	---	---	---	---	---	2.60
18	1.89	3.66	4.81	6.97	6.59	8.52	---	---	---	---	---	2.67
19	2.09	3.66	4.86	7.09	6.65	8.52	---	---	---	---	---	2.50
20	2.27	3.69	4.88	7.13	6.74	8.52	---	---	---	---	---	2.52
21	2.44	3.73	4.94	7.16	6.80	---	---	---	---	---	---	2.54
22	2.63	3.76	5.02	7.16	6.90	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	2.74	3.80	5.06	7.16	6.96	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	2.84	3.85	5.11	7.16	7.05	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	2.95	3.87	5.18	7.16	7.13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	3.03	3.91	5.25	7.16	7.14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	3.10	3.91	5.30	7.16	7.27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	3.17	3.95	5.39	7.16	7.36	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	3.23	3.96	5.46	7.16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	3.26	3.96	5.53	7.16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	3.30	---	5.61	7.17	---	---	---	---	---	---	3.07	---
MEAN	3.16	3.69	4.72	6.59	6.86	8.19	---	---	---	---	3.07	2.20

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 5.00 HIGHEST 0.87 SEPT. 7, 1998 LOWEST 8.53 MAR. 21, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180628067084301. Local number, CR-TW9B.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'28", long 67°08'43", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.29 mi north of Cabo Rojo plaza, 1.54 mi northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad Antonio Acarón Correa, and 1.23 mi southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: US Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-9B.

AQUIFER.--Cotuí Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-109 ft (0-33.2m), screened 104-109 ft (31.7-33.2 m). Depth 109 ft (33.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 33.2 ft (10.1 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 4.73 ft (1.44 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 29, 1996.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 29, 1996 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 6.18 ft (1.88 m), below land-surface datum, Nov. 23, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 23.38 ft (7.13 m), below land-surface datum, May 18, 19, 20, 1998.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1995 TO SEPTEMBER 1996
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.21	---	---	9.42
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.42	---	---	9.59
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.79
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.80
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.76
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.95
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.96
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.86	10.22
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.47	10.45
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.20	10.04
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.56
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.45
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.34	9.27
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.10	9.38
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.95	9.59
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.89	9.81
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.92	10.01
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.13	10.13
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.31	10.23
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.50	10.33
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.68	10.45
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.90	10.58
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.06	10.51
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.16	10.45
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.01	10.62
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.07	10.84
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.11	10.81
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.21	10.87
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.21	10.70
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.91	---	---	9.25	10.61
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.02	---	---	9.32	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.97	8.32	---	8.80	10.11

WTR YR 1996 MEAN 9.45 HOGHEST 7.92 MAY 29, 1996 LOWEST 10.88 SEPT. 28, 1996

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	10.47	9.71	7.60	11.67	11.17	12.95	13.98	15.78	18.14	19.85	23.19	15.79
2	10.37	9.90	7.71	11.67	11.28	12.98	14.01	15.93	18.19	19.99	23.16	15.74
3	9.85	10.12	7.96	11.67	11.43	13.02	14.04	16.05	18.27	20.14	22.46	15.68
4	9.45	10.30	8.34	11.67	11.42	13.05	14.08	16.15	18.33	20.28	21.89	15.59
5	9.18	10.42	8.79	11.67	11.23	13.08	14.11	16.21	18.41	20.39	21.55	15.50
6	9.01	10.49	8.99	11.67	11.10	13.12	14.14	16.24	18.29	20.57	21.27	15.46
7	8.93	10.56	9.12	11.67	10.97	13.15	14.18	16.32	18.46	20.77	21.04	15.41
8	8.93	10.60	9.30	11.66	10.91	13.18	14.21	16.38	18.60	20.90	20.85	15.42
9	8.95	10.21	9.47	11.66	10.93	13.22	14.24	16.45	18.75	21.08	20.61	15.46
10	9.10	9.77	9.60	11.54	11.07	13.25	14.27	16.47	18.87	21.28	20.46	15.45
11	9.25	9.49	9.70	11.11	11.15	13.28	14.31	16.56	18.99	21.46	19.89	15.50
12	9.19	9.30	9.77	10.71	11.15	13.32	14.34	16.66	19.12	21.59	19.64	15.52
13	9.31	8.33	9.87	10.54	11.13	13.35	14.37	16.77	19.26	21.72	19.44	15.49
14	9.41	7.86	9.94	10.55	11.25	13.38	14.41	16.89	19.43	21.89	18.96	15.54
15	9.52	7.58	10.17	10.84	11.51	13.41	14.44	17.00	19.59	22.03	18.47	15.54
16	9.56	7.41	10.42	10.96	11.80	13.45	14.47	17.09	19.76	22.16	18.16	15.61
17	9.61	7.32	10.53	10.98	12.03	13.48	14.55	17.22	19.94	22.29	17.89	15.64
18	9.60	7.23	10.58	11.00	12.25	13.51	14.63	17.34	20.16	22.42	17.64	15.64
19	9.51	6.84	10.64	11.08	12.38	13.55	14.71	17.45	20.03	22.44	17.42	15.65
20	9.51	6.72	10.70	11.17	12.50	13.58	14.82	17.58	19.81	22.50	17.25	15.66
21	9.55	6.70	10.87	11.20	12.58	13.61	14.96	17.68	19.77	22.57	17.10	15.69
22	9.58	6.30	11.10	11.15	12.72	13.65	15.01	17.73	19.73	22.63	16.96	15.72
23	9.65	6.19	11.29	10.91	12.75	13.68	15.09	17.82	19.61	22.70	16.87	15.93
24	9.88	6.30	11.47	10.73	12.79	13.71	15.16	17.88	19.57	22.77	16.76	15.98
25	10.04	6.53	11.61	10.67	12.82	13.75	15.24	17.86	19.54	22.84	16.50	16.05
26	9.82	6.77	11.67	10.71	12.85	13.78	15.31	17.85	19.52	22.93	16.38	16.07
27	9.63	7.01	11.67	10.75	12.89	13.81	15.42	17.88	19.52	23.05	16.20	16.08
28	9.41	7.26	11.67	10.70	12.92	13.84	15.48	17.88	19.55	23.17	16.05	16.14
29	9.23	7.36	11.67	10.60	---	13.88	15.56	17.93	19.65	23.29	15.98	16.12
30	9.60	7.41	11.67	10.75	---	13.91	15.66	18.02	19.75	23.31	16.01	15.10
31	9.72	---	11.67	10.99	---	13.94	---	18.08	---	23.24	15.84	---
MEAN	9.51	8.27	10.18	11.12	11.82	13.45	14.64	17.07	19.22	21.88	18.77	15.67
WTR YR 1997	MEAN 14.32	HIGHEST 6.18	NOV. 13, 1996	LOWEST 23.31	JULY 29, 30, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14.39	8.96	11.43	14.85	17.57	15.46	18.52	22.72	19.71	16.79	14.02	---
2	13.89	9.16	11.57	14.88	17.72	15.50	18.55	22.76	19.62	16.79	14.13	---
3	13.55	9.33	11.67	14.92	17.87	15.64	18.69	22.82	19.56	16.59	14.13	---
4	13.23	9.46	11.72	14.97	18.04	15.91	18.80	22.82	19.42	16.34	14.13	---
5	13.06	9.61	11.79	15.03	17.63	16.15	18.92	22.89	19.29	16.19	14.14	---
6	12.94	9.68	11.88	15.08	17.09	16.35	19.07	23.01	19.02	16.07	14.17	---
7	12.82	9.65	12.02	15.13	16.59	16.56	19.25	23.01	18.89	15.94	13.94	---
8	12.54	9.61	12.13	15.19	16.20	16.77	19.41	23.01	18.79	15.87	13.70	---
9	11.96	9.85	12.20	15.29	15.87	16.98	19.56	22.98	18.74	15.83	13.38	---
10	11.12	9.91	12.30	15.39	15.65	17.13	19.74	23.02	18.65	15.77	13.14	---
11	10.76	10.00	12.38	15.45	15.51	17.29	19.94	23.06	18.60	15.55	12.66	---
12	10.44	10.08	12.48	15.42	15.37	17.45	20.05	23.14	18.59	15.36	12.45	---
13	10.23	10.16	12.65	15.26	15.25	17.59	20.19	23.22	18.59	15.21	12.30	---
14	8.93	10.21	12.79	15.22	15.13	17.72	20.32	23.29	18.57	15.11	12.21	---
15	8.36	10.29	12.92	15.42	15.03	17.64	20.49	23.34	18.59	15.04	12.18	---
16	7.87	10.35	13.12	15.60	14.97	17.55	20.72	23.35	18.66	14.94	12.18	---
17	7.48	10.42	13.28	15.77	14.91	17.61	20.99	23.35	18.69	14.89	12.22	---
18	7.20	10.49	13.38	15.92	14.91	17.61	21.16	23.38	18.24	14.68	12.27	---
19	7.09	10.54	13.51	16.08	14.93	17.64	21.36	23.38	18.09	14.41	12.33	---
20	7.07	10.60	13.64	16.22	14.97	17.68	21.54	23.38	17.98	14.28	12.41	---
21	7.13	10.66	13.73	16.37	15.00	17.72	21.72	23.15	17.87	14.13	12.38	---
22	7.23	10.73	13.85	16.48	15.09	17.81	21.90	22.42	17.72	14.03	12.44	---
23	7.37	10.83	13.98	16.60	15.12	17.88	22.07	21.91	17.51	13.88	12.48	---
24	7.64	10.94	14.08	16.73	15.18	17.90	22.24	21.52	17.33	13.84	12.57	---
25	7.87	10.97	14.16	16.83	15.24	18.04	22.39	21.21	17.29	13.81	11.73	---
26	8.06	11.06	14.26	16.92	15.29	18.11	22.55	20.87	17.17	13.76	11.15	---
27	8.29	11.14	14.33	17.00	15.36	18.17	22.66	20.63	17.03	13.70	10.61	---
28	8.47	11.24	14.44	17.10	15.44	18.24	22.70	20.40	16.93	13.66	10.07	---
29	8.49	11.31	14.54	17.16	---	18.33	22.77	20.20	16.86	13.72	9.81	---
30	8.61	11.35	14.65	17.28	---	18.43	22.78	20.02	16.80	13.85	9.69	---
31	8.71	---	14.77	17.41	---	18.54	---	19.86	---	13.91	---	---
MEAN	9.77	10.29	13.09	15.90	15.82	17.34	20.70	22.39	18.29	14.97	12.50	---

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 15.55 HIGHEST 7.07 OCT. 19, 20, 1997 LOWEST 23.38 MAY 18, 19, 20 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO YAGÜEZ AND RIO GRANDE AÑACO BASINS

181232067083700. Local number, CI-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'32", long 67°08'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 0.10 mi east of Hwy 2, 0.92 mi southeast of the intersection of Hwy 104 with Hwy 2, and 0.20 mi southwest of the University of Puerto Rico, Mayagüez Campus.

Owner: Cervecería India, Name: Cervecería India.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled emergency use water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-100 ft (0-30.5 m), perforated 85-95.0 ft (25.9-28.9 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Pressure transducer with integrated electronic water level logger--60-minute interval.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m), above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.80 ft (0.85 m), above land-surface datum. Prior to Nov. 20, 1992, hole on side of casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on August 29, 1997.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 29, 1997 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 4.89 ft (1.49 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 15, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 18.82 ft (5.74 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 22, 1997.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.54
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.55
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.55
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.49
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.48
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.49
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.50
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.51
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.52
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.55
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.86
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.72
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.57
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.53
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.53
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.56
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.55
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.57
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.60
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.63
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.58
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.51
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.31
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.30
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.27
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.28
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.34
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.38
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.40
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.53	5.27
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.52	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.53	5.50

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 5.50 HIGHEST 5.10 SEPT. 29, 1997 LOWEST 6.59 SEPT. 10, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO YAGÜEZ AND RIO GRANDE AÑACO BASINS-Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.24	5.76	5.70	6.05	5.94	6.17	6.23	7.49	5.78	---	---	---
2	5.25	5.79	5.75	6.02	5.94	6.14	6.26	6.66	5.78	---	---	---
3	5.29	5.80	5.77	6.01	5.92	6.16	6.27	6.57	5.80	---	---	---
4	5.35	5.82	5.79	5.97	5.91	6.17	6.29	9.79	5.79	---	---	---
5	5.39	5.89	5.80	5.95	5.87	6.24	6.29	6.70	5.81	---	---	---
6	5.33	18.73	5.81	5.95	5.88	6.22	6.28	6.55	5.82	---	---	---
7	5.33	6.42	5.84	5.94	5.89	6.22	6.31	6.44	5.86	---	---	---
8	5.36	6.10	5.85	5.77	5.91	6.22	6.30	6.42	5.87	---	---	---
9	5.40	6.12	5.87	5.74	5.84	6.21	6.29	6.40	5.85	---	---	---
10	5.27	5.99	5.89	5.74	5.85	6.22	6.27	6.40	5.68	---	---	---
11	5.19	5.94	5.90	5.74	5.87	6.23	6.25	6.38	5.63	---	---	---
12	5.11	5.66	5.92	5.65	5.90	6.25	6.25	6.40	5.64	---	---	---
13	5.08	5.58	5.94	5.54	5.91	6.28	6.27	6.40	5.66	---	---	---
14	4.95	5.56	5.95	5.54	5.93	6.30	6.30	6.41	5.66	---	---	---
15	4.96	5.59	5.95	5.56	5.95	6.22	6.31	6.38	5.68	---	---	---
16	4.93	5.58	5.97	5.59	5.97	6.16	6.32	6.31	---	---	---	---
17	4.99	5.58	5.99	5.63	5.96	6.15	6.33	6.28	---	---	---	---
18	5.07	5.60	6.00	5.66	5.98	6.10	6.35	6.25	---	---	---	---
19	5.13	5.63	6.02	5.68	6.01	6.09	6.37	6.21	---	---	---	---
20	5.17	5.57	6.04	5.68	6.03	6.08	6.38	6.20	---	---	---	---
21	5.22	5.59	6.04	5.80	6.28	6.09	6.39	6.19	---	---	---	---
22	5.29	5.62	6.04	5.76	6.63	6.11	6.42	6.13	---	---	---	---
23	6.46	5.65	6.04	5.77	6.23	6.14	6.67	6.15	---	---	---	---
24	5.84	5.66	6.05	5.80	6.17	6.16	6.53	6.06	---	---	---	---
25	5.71	5.68	6.06	5.83	6.17	6.19	6.49	6.00	---	---	---	---
26	5.68	5.69	6.06	5.84	6.16	6.20	6.47	5.87	---	---	---	---
27	5.66	5.66	6.06	5.85	6.16	6.21	6.46	5.86	---	---	---	---
28	5.68	5.66	6.07	5.87	6.16	6.21	6.48	5.86	---	---	---	---
29	5.70	5.68	6.07	5.89	---	6.21	6.75	5.79	---	---	---	---
30	5.71	5.69	6.09	5.89	---	6.20	7.70	5.74	---	---	---	---
31	5.73	---	6.06	5.92	---	6.20	---	5.72	---	---	---	---
MEAN	5.37	6.18	5.95	5.79	6.01	6.19	6.41	6.39	5.75	---	---	---
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 6.02	HIGHEST 4.89	OCT. 15, 1997	LOWEST 18.82	OCT. 22, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

181911067140500. Local number, C-4.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'11", long 67°14'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 0.32 mi east of the intersection of Hwy 429 with Hwy 115, 0.75 mi northwest of the intersection of Hwy 411 with Hwy 115, and 0.01 mi north of Hwy 115. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Rincón-Calvache 4.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m). Depth 80 ft (24.8 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 23.0 ft (7.00 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole in the side of the 12 in (0.30 m) casing, 1.07 ft (0.33 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 30, 1996. Station discontinued on July 1, 1997 due to nearby highway construction. Well depth from specific conductance profile conducted on April 18, 1996.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 30, 1996 to Jult 1, 1997, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 6.63 ft (2.02 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 23, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 18.19 ft (5.54 m), below land-surface datum, June 2, 4, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1995 TO SEPTEMBER 1996
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.16	12.86	11.96	---
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.17	12.81	11.72	---
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.18	12.77	11.11	---
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.15	12.72	10.74	---
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.92	12.71	10.10	---
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.99	12.71	10.02	---
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.80	12.81	11.06	---
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.68	12.75	11.11	---
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.62	12.74	11.16	---
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.59	12.74	11.21	---
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.46	12.75	10.69	---
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.38	12.74	10.57	---
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.78	12.68	10.51	---
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.61	12.68	10.51	---
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.46	12.65	10.24	---
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.34	12.41	10.18	---
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.47	12.36	10.19	---
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.76	12.34	10.11	---
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.42	12.23	10.04	---
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.30	12.19	10.06	---
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.24	12.19	10.18	---
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.16	12.19	10.30	---
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.14	12.19	9.74	---
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.11	12.23	9.76	---
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.05	12.24	9.79	---
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.05	12.29	---	---
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.03	12.29	---	---
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.01	12.33	---	---
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.11	12.29	---	---
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.18	12.96	12.27	---	---
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.15	---	12.23	---	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.17	15.17	12.50	10.52	---

WTR YR 1996 MEAN 12.98 HIGHEST 9.67 AUG. 24, 25, 1996 LOWEST 18.19 JUNE2, 4, 1996

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	7.77	8.35	---	8.90	10.34	12.42	15.00	16.48	---	---	---
2	---	7.07	8.46	---	9.05	10.41	12.38	15.11	16.33	---	---	---
3	7.84	7.25	8.57	---	9.17	10.57	12.42	15.24	16.31	---	---	---
4	8.05	7.40	8.70	---	9.26	10.56	12.56	15.33	16.29	---	---	---
5	8.11	7.57	8.81	---	9.35	10.57	12.61	15.39	16.29	---	---	---
6	8.21	7.79	8.91	---	9.42	10.61	12.73	15.48	16.29	---	---	---
7	8.36	7.96	8.98	---	9.51	10.71	12.85	15.56	16.35	---	---	---
8	8.57	8.09	9.06	---	9.52	10.80	12.95	15.64	16.45	---	---	---
9	8.64	8.21	9.14	---	9.54	10.87	13.10	15.56	16.52	---	---	---
10	8.59	8.36	9.16	---	9.53	11.01	13.12	15.54	16.63	---	---	---
11	8.64	8.50	9.15	---	9.56	11.07	13.19	15.62	16.64	---	---	---
12	8.76	8.56	9.17	---	9.60	11.18	13.29	15.70	16.71	---	---	---
13	8.85	8.41	9.19	---	9.66	11.26	13.38	15.78	16.79	---	---	---
14	8.78	8.45	9.22	---	9.73	11.36	13.46	15.87	16.73	---	---	---
15	7.57	8.44	9.25	---	9.79	11.40	13.55	15.95	16.77	---	---	---
16	7.47	8.58	9.30	---	9.85	11.48	13.61	16.02	16.84	---	---	---
17	7.63	8.06	9.39	---	9.91	11.56	13.71	16.08	16.91	---	---	---
18	7.75	7.60	---	---	9.99	11.66	13.79	16.28	17.04	---	---	---
19	7.92	6.98	---	---	10.02	11.78	13.88	16.29	17.09	---	---	---
20	8.12	7.05	---	---	10.04	11.74	13.98	16.32	16.68	---	---	---
21	8.26	7.07	---	---	10.10	11.79	14.07	16.38	16.48	---	---	---
22	6.72	7.14	---	---	10.07	11.91	14.20	16.46	16.36	---	---	---
23	6.74	7.24	---	---	10.13	12.02	14.26	16.50	16.37	---	---	---
24	7.03	7.38	---	8.02	10.16	12.13	14.34	16.54	16.33	---	---	---
25	7.40	7.55	---	8.13	10.14	12.26	14.47	16.60	16.40	---	---	---
26	7.70	7.74	---	8.25	10.19	12.34	14.51	16.65	16.46	---	---	---
27	7.92	7.89	---	8.38	10.24	12.33	14.59	16.58	16.37	---	---	---
28	8.07	8.03	---	8.51	10.29	12.40	14.69	16.52	16.38	---	---	---
29	7.78	8.15	---	8.63	---	12.43	14.79	16.53	16.48	---	---	---
30	7.87	8.26	---	8.73	---	12.49	14.90	16.60	16.57	---	---	---
31	8.04	---	---	8.81	---	12.54	---	16.67	---	---	---	---
MEAN	7.98	7.82	8.99	8.43	9.74	11.47	13.59	15.99	16.54	---	---	---

WTR YR 1997 MEAN 11.60 HIGHEST 6.63 OCT. 23, 1996 LOWEST 17.10 JUNE 19, 1997

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

182017067143300. Local number, R-4.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'17", long 67°14'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 0.63 mi southeast of the intersection of Hwy 412 with Hwy 115, 1.13 mi south of the intersection of Hwy 413 with Hwy 115, and 0.01 mi north of Hwy 411. Owner: PR Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Rincón 4.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m), cased 0-69.0 ft (0-21.0 m). Depth 64.0 ft (21.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 39.0 ft (11.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of the 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.53 ft (1.08 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR), installed on May 30, 1996.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 30, 1996 to September 30, 1998.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 20.80 ft (6.34 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 27, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 34.07 ft (10.4 m), below land-surface datum, May 30, 1996.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1995 TO SEPTEMBER 1996
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.87	---	---	28.73
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.85	---	---	28.76
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.86	---	---	28.73
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.89	---	---	28.71
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.68	---	---	28.66
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.24	---	---	28.77
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	32.86	---	29.27	28.83
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	32.61	---	29.61	28.92
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	32.46	---	29.72	29.03
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	32.39	---	29.86	28.63
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	32.26	---	29.80	27.39
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	32.09	---	29.71	26.62
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.83	---	29.65	26.83
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.62	---	29.60	27.22
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.50	---	29.42	27.44
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.39	---	29.36	27.56
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.17	31.17	29.39	27.54
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.18	29.29	27.33
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.20	29.02	27.14
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.20	28.97	27.08
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.21	28.82	27.08
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.25	28.79	27.13
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.32	28.76	27.22
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.37	28.70	27.30
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.42	28.63	27.40
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.47	28.62	27.14
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	31.17	28.67	26.63
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	28.67	26.30
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	28.70	26.15
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	34.05	---	---	28.72	26.17
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.93	---	---	28.73	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	33.99	32.62	31.27	29.14	27.61

WTR YR 1996 MEAN 29.69 HIGHEST 26.14 SEPT. 29, 1996 LOWEST 34.07 MAY 30, 1996

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1996 TO SEPTEMBER 1997												
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200												
DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	26.24	25.56	26.87	29.26	29.20	30.02	31.50	32.10	32.68	32.70	32.03	30.37
2	26.33	25.42	26.94	29.27	29.26	30.06	31.53	32.13	32.53	32.66	32.03	30.28
3	26.41	25.30	27.02	29.50	29.31	30.13	31.55	32.14	32.42	32.63	32.04	30.22
4	26.50	25.27	27.12	29.59	29.37	30.17	31.57	32.18	32.36	32.61	32.07	30.16
5	26.59	25.28	27.19	29.60	29.43	30.20	31.58	32.19	32.36	32.64	32.13	30.02
6	26.64	25.32	27.27	29.71	29.49	30.21	31.59	32.16	32.38	32.65	32.20	29.95
7	26.72	25.40	27.35	29.80	29.55	30.36	31.56	32.17	32.40	32.67	32.26	29.93
8	26.81	25.43	27.45	29.84	29.56	30.42	31.56	32.17	32.43	32.66	32.30	29.93
9	26.89	25.47	27.52	29.93	29.57	30.46	31.57	32.15	32.48	32.68	32.33	29.95
10	26.94	25.56	27.60	29.95	29.56	30.51	31.58	32.17	32.53	32.71	32.38	29.97
11	26.95	25.65	27.68	29.98	29.50	30.57	31.49	32.23	32.57	32.73	32.42	30.01
12	26.93	25.71	27.78	30.04	29.30	30.61	31.55	32.25	32.60	32.75	32.35	30.05
13	26.93	25.81	27.86	30.10	29.14	30.65	31.58	32.40	32.63	32.77	32.24	30.06
14	26.97	25.92	27.93	30.16	29.09	30.74	31.61	32.53	32.65	32.79	32.22	30.11
15	26.74	26.03	28.03	30.21	29.13	30.77	31.61	32.55	32.66	32.80	32.20	30.16
16	26.41	26.13	28.10	30.24	29.17	30.78	31.62	32.62	32.68	32.74	32.07	30.18
17	26.18	26.20	28.18	30.26	29.23	30.87	31.73	32.65	32.72	32.71	31.86	30.20
18	26.09	26.23	28.28	30.40	29.30	30.90	31.77	32.64	32.76	32.71	31.71	30.23
19	26.09	26.26	28.36	30.46	29.37	30.97	31.87	32.60	32.79	32.60	31.62	30.26
20	26.16	26.26	28.44	30.51	29.43	31.01	31.92	32.60	32.69	32.37	31.64	30.29
21	26.23	26.24	28.51	30.55	29.51	31.05	31.98	32.62	32.55	32.15	31.63	30.33
22	26.06	26.17	28.60	---	29.57	31.09	31.96	32.65	32.53	32.06	31.56	30.28
23	25.83	26.14	28.67	---	29.60	31.13	31.94	32.70	32.55	32.05	31.53	30.26
24	25.70	26.19	28.77	29.04	29.68	31.19	31.94	32.73	32.57	32.06	31.41	30.24
25	25.65	26.26	28.81	28.94	29.73	31.21	31.97	32.76	32.60	32.08	31.03	30.17
26	25.62	26.35	28.85	28.91	29.79	31.24	31.99	32.76	32.51	32.12	30.74	30.10
27	25.62	26.47	28.99	28.94	29.89	31.27	32.01	32.71	32.59	32.16	30.57	30.09
28	25.63	26.58	29.05	28.98	29.94	31.35	32.03	32.73	32.66	32.18	30.50	30.11
29	25.60	26.67	29.10	29.02	---	31.39	32.05	32.68	32.70	32.13	30.44	30.13
30	25.57	26.79	29.19	29.08	---	31.43	32.08	32.75	32.72	32.07	30.43	30.11
31	25.56	---	29.24	29.15	---	31.47	---	32.76	---	32.04	30.43	---
MEAN	26.28	25.94	28.09	29.70	29.45	30.78	31.74	32.47	32.58	32.47	31.69	30.14
WTR YR 1997	MEAN 30.12	HIGHEST 25.26	NOV. 4, 1996	LOWEST 32.80	JULY 14, 15, 1997							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN--Continued

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	30.17	29.96	29.22	31.35	30.41	31.82	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	30.22	29.72	29.27	31.21	30.44	31.87	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	30.22	29.87	29.35	31.04	30.53	31.93	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	30.25	29.94	29.42	30.89	30.57	31.96	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	30.26	30.03	29.48	30.82	30.65	31.97	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	30.21	30.04	29.54	30.82	30.71	31.98	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	30.18	30.12	29.63	30.81	30.74	32.03	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	30.19	30.14	29.69	30.71	30.77	32.09	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	30.22	30.20	29.75	30.57	30.82	32.13	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	30.27	30.24	29.82	30.49	30.86	32.18	---	---	---	---	---	31.67
11	30.30	30.20	29.89	30.43	30.91	32.22	---	---	---	---	---	31.58
12	30.31	30.01	29.93	29.90	30.94	32.26	---	---	---	---	---	31.51
13	29.66	29.74	30.04	29.45	30.99	32.30	---	---	---	---	---	31.50
14	29.90	29.57	30.12	29.29	31.03	32.34	---	---	---	---	---	31.48
15	29.84	29.43	30.18	29.26	31.08	32.36	---	---	---	---	---	31.45
16	29.67	29.26	30.24	29.30	31.14	32.38	---	---	---	---	---	31.35
17	29.56	29.12	30.31	29.37	31.24	32.40	---	---	---	---	---	31.24
18	29.54	29.05	30.37	29.43	31.29	32.44	---	---	---	---	---	31.09
19	29.53	29.08	30.44	29.49	31.37	32.47	---	---	---	---	---	30.96
20	29.54	29.15	30.49	29.57	31.41	32.50	---	---	---	---	---	30.80
21	29.51	29.20	30.63	29.67	31.44	32.48	---	---	---	---	---	30.68
22	29.57	29.26	30.67	29.71	31.46	32.50	---	---	---	---	---	28.43
23	29.65	29.33	30.74	29.76	31.48	32.54	---	---	---	---	---	24.08
24	29.66	29.36	30.82	29.78	31.63	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.02
25	29.68	29.38	30.88	29.93	31.67	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.18
26	29.71	29.40	30.92	29.97	31.74	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.92
27	29.77	29.31	31.05	30.05	31.77	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.84
28	29.80	29.14	31.10	30.14	31.80	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.64
29	29.83	29.17	31.15	30.21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.56
30	29.88	29.18	31.22	30.26	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.05
31	29.91	---	31.31	30.31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	29.90	29.59	30.25	30.13	31.10	32.22	---	---	---	---	---	27.62

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 30.15 HIGHEST 20.80 SEPT. 27, 1998 LOWEST 32.57 MAR. 24, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

182442067091700. Local number, 200.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'42", long 67°09'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.40 mi south of Aguadilla plaza, 3.04 mi northeast of Aguada plaza, and 0.20 mi north of Hwy 2 km 146.4. Owner: Carmelo Sánchez, Name: Aguadilla Cement North Well.

AQUIFER.--Surficial deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Abandoned water-table industrial well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-20.0 ft (0-6.10 m), perforated 11-20.0 ft (3.35-6.10 m). Depth 20.0 ft (6.10 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Electronic water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.25 ft (0.99 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automated Digital Recorder (ADR) replaced by an Electronic Data Logger (EDL), installed on February 18, 1998. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 1.61 ft (0.49 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 22, 1998; lowest water level recorded, 9.60 ft (2.93 m), below land-surface datum, Feb. 20, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.24	6.42	6.20	---	7.55	---	8.31	---	7.22	---	---	---
2	7.28	6.40	6.23	---	7.65	---	8.37	---	7.15	---	---	---
3	7.31	6.46	6.27	---	7.75	---	8.39	---	7.17	---	---	---
4	7.31	6.52	6.33	---	7.79	8.53	8.39	---	7.22	---	---	---
5	7.31	6.52	6.35	---	7.73	8.46	8.39	---	7.26	---	---	---
6	7.36	6.57	6.35	---	7.76	8.40	8.42	---	7.19	---	---	---
7	7.40	6.58	6.37	---	7.80	8.40	8.42	---	7.04	---	---	---
8	7.41	6.58	6.45	---	7.84	8.08	8.45	---	6.91	---	---	5.08
9	7.45	6.58	6.52	---	7.85	8.09	8.46	---	6.91	---	---	5.10
10	7.51	6.61	6.54	---	7.89	8.09	8.47	---	6.97	---	---	5.13
11	7.51	6.72	6.58	---	7.93	8.10	8.47	---	7.01	---	---	5.22
12	7.51	6.71	6.58	---	8.00	8.18	8.47	---	6.68	---	---	5.28
13	7.34	6.42	6.58	---	8.05	8.18	8.47	---	6.46	6.17	---	5.24
14	6.92	6.43	6.60	---	8.10	8.19	8.52	---	5.60	5.97	---	4.16
15	6.81	6.26	6.61	---	8.15	8.19	8.52	8.49	5.56	6.06	---	3.90
16	6.66	6.22	6.66	---	8.23	8.22	8.52	8.33	5.46	5.80	---	3.84
17	6.65	6.24	6.70	---	8.32	8.24	8.50	8.29	5.37	5.71	---	3.86
18	6.68	6.29	---	---	---	8.26	8.50	8.28	5.45	5.77	---	3.86
19	6.78	6.29	---	---	---	8.27	8.50	8.28	5.18	5.87	---	3.31
20	6.91	6.36	---	---	---	8.19	8.54	8.26	5.26	5.96	---	3.19
21	6.94	6.43	---	---	---	8.19	8.54	8.13	5.44	6.04	---	3.27
22	7.05	6.44	---	---	---	8.16	8.54	8.17	5.59	6.11	---	1.81
23	6.12	6.46	---	7.25	---	8.17	8.55	8.03	---	6.20	---	2.04
24	6.16	6.58	---	7.29	---	8.21	8.55	7.81	---	---	---	2.43
25	6.16	6.15	---	7.33	---	8.22	8.55	7.81	---	---	---	2.48
26	6.20	6.09	---	7.40	---	8.24	8.56	7.81	---	---	---	2.60
27	6.26	6.07	---	7.45	---	8.25	8.56	7.45	---	---	---	2.65
28	6.32	6.06	---	7.50	---	8.22	8.57	7.39	---	---	---	---
29	6.34	6.07	---	7.54	---	8.22	8.58	7.41	---	---	---	---
30	6.36	6.09	---	7.47	---	8.28	8.58	7.43	---	---	---	---
31	6.39	---	---	7.51	---	8.28	---	7.36	---	---	---	---
MEAN	6.89	6.39	6.47	7.42	7.91	8.23	8.49	7.93	6.37	5.97	---	3.72

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 6.97 HIGHEST 1.61 SEPT. 22, 1998 LOWEST 8.59 APR. 30, 1998

**Surface-Water Records
for U.S. Virgin Islands**

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50252000 BONNE RESOLUTION GUT AT BONNE RESOLUTION, ST. THOMAS, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'57", long 64°57'34", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, on right bank near Hull Bay Road, 0.5 mi (0.8 km), upstream from mouth, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) northwest of Fort Christian, Charlotte Amalie.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.49 mi² (1.27 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1962 to February 1967, March 1979 to April 1981, May 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 280 ft (85 m), from topographic map. December 1962 to February 1967 and March 1979 to April 1981 at site about 100 ft (30 m), upstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.04	.03	.04	.06	.01	.03	.01	.02	.01	.04	.11	.02
2	.04	.03	.03	.05	.01	.03	.01	.02	.01	.04	.10	.02
3	.04	.03	.03	.06	.01	.02	.01	.02	.01	.04	.10	.02
4	.05	.04	.03	.06	.01	.02	.01	.02	.01	.07	.09	.01
5	.05	.04	.03	.08	.03	.01	.01	.01	.02	.05	.10	.02
6	.06	.04	.03	.47	.02	.01	.01	.02	.01	.05	.10	.02
7	.05	.04	.03	.89	.02	.01	.02	.02	.01	.06	.10	.04
8	.05	.04	.04	.05	.02	.01	.01	.02	.01	.07	.11	.03
9	.06	.04	.04	.02	.03	.01	.01	.02	.01	.05	.13	.02
10	.05	.06	.04	.02	.03	.01	.01	.02	.01	.06	.14	.01
11	.10	.08	.04	.01	.02	.01	.01	.02	.01	.07	.11	.01
12	.33	.04	.04	.01	.03	.01	.01	.02	.01	.07	.11	.01
13	2.2	.02	.04	.01	.03	.01	.05	.02	.01	.06	.11	.01
14	4.6	.02	.04	.01	.03	.01	.01	.02	.01	.06	.11	.01
15	1.2	.03	.04	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	.07	.12	.01
16	.33	.03	.04	.01	.03	.01	.28	.01	.01	.08	.13	.01
17	.21	.03	.05	.01	.02	.01	.02	.01	.14	.07	.14	.01
18	.14	.10	.04	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	.10	.10	.14	.02
19	.09	.10	.04	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	.04	.08	.13	.02
20	.07	.05	.04	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	.04	.10	.13	.01
21	.07	.03	.22	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	.04	.09	.18	9.6
22	.06	.03	.08	.01	.02	.01	.02	.01	.04	.09	.16	4.0
23	.06	.03	.06	.01	.02	.01	.02	.01	.04	.10	.13	.14
24	.06	.03	.05	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	.04	.11	.35	.06
25	.06	.02	.04	.01	.02	.01	.02	.01	.04	.09	.05	.04
26	.06	.03	.04	.01	.03	.01	.02	.01	.04	.09	.03	.03
27	.05	.02	.04	.01	.03	.01	.02	.01	.04	.09	.02	.03
28	.04	.03	.04	.01	.03	.01	.01	.01	.04	.09	.02	.03
29	.03	.03	.05	.01	---	.01	.02	.01	.04	.09	.01	.03
30	.03	.03	.06	.01	---	.01	.02	.01	.03	.10	.01	.03
31	.03	---	.06	.01	---	.01	---	.01	---	.11	.02	---
TOTAL	10.31	1.17	1.49	1.97	0.62	0.37	0.70	0.44	0.88	2.34	3.29	14.32
MEAN	.33	.039	.048	.064	.022	.012	.023	.014	.029	.075	.11	.48
MAX	4.6	.10	.22	.89	.03	.03	.28	.02	.14	.11	.35	9.6
MIN	.03	.02	.03	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.04	.01	.01
AC-FT	20	2.3	3.0	3.9	1.2	.7	1.4	.9	1.7	4.6	6.5	28
CFSM	.68	.08	.10	.13	.05	.02	.05	.03	.06	.15	.22	.97
IN.	.78	.09	.11	.15	.05	.03	.05	.03	.07	.18	.25	1.09

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1986 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	.47	.71	.061	.067	.058	.048	.060	.31	.12	.046	.058	.94	
MAX	3.09	4.22	.30	.35	.38	.31	.34	2.06	.89	.18	.23	8.91	
(WY)	1986	1988	1993	1992	1992	1987	1986	1987	1987	1988	1988	1989	
MIN	.011	.011	.002	.016	.005	.001	.000	.002	.004	.010	.010	.009	
(WY)	1997	1995	1995	1986	1995	1995	1995	1995	1995	1994	1994	1994	

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1963 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	23.74	37.90		
ANNUAL MEAN	.065	.10	.24	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			.77	1989
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.026	1969
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	4.6 Oct 14	9.6 Sep 21	169	Apr 18 1983
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00 Mar 25	.01 Jan 11	.00	Apr 11 1980
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.01 Mar 19	.01 Jan 11	.00	Jan 31 1986
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		117 Sep 21	1650	Apr 18 1983
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		2.98 Sep 21	7.00	Apr 18 1983
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	47	75	186	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.13	.21	.49	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	1.80	2.88	6.65	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.12	.10	.11	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.03	.03	.02	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.01	.01	.01	

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50252000 BONNE RESOLUTION GUT AT BONNE RESOLUTION, ST. THOMAS, VI--Continued

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50274000 TURPENTINE RUN AT MOUNT ZION, ST. THOMAS, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'55", long 64°53'20", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, on left bank at Mount Zion, 0.6 mi (0.9 km), east southeast from Donoe School, 0.5 mi (0.8 km), northwest from Mariendal, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) southeast from conjunction of roads 38 and 32.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.33 mi² (6.03 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to December 1969, October 1992 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 120 ft (36 m), from topographic map. Datum of gage for period of October 1992 to current year is 1.62 ft (0.49 m), higher than previous record.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Flow affected by three sewage treatment plants, Donoe, Old Tutu and New Tutu that discharges to a retention pond located 0.80 mi (1.28 km) upstream from station. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.26	e.56	.65	.55	.54	.47	.51	.29	.35	e.66	.19	.23
2	1.1	e.56	.58	.54	.56	.48	.69	.31	.42	e.66	.19	.48
3	.54	e.56	.57	.54	.39	.43	.48	.29	.32	e.77	.15	.27
4	.41	e.78	.59	.67	.40	.40	.47	.28	.32	e1.9	.13	.19
5	.35	e.78	.62	.66	1.1	.43	.40	.19	.38	e.94	.11	.20
6	.32	e.78	.61	2.6	.46	.47	.42	.19	.39	e.62	.63	.23
7	.30	e.78	.61	6.3	.41	.49	.48	.20	.41	e.94	1.1	.91
8	.38	e.78	.58	1.2	1.0	.46	.45	.24	.30	e.58	.60	.64
9	.35	e.78	.52	.93	.94	.42	.44	.17	.26	e.39	.37	.42
10	.30	e1.2	.57	.69	.57	.35	.42	.19	.31	e.35	.34	.29
11	.80	e1.7	.52	.98	.53	.33	.41	.22	.28	e.28	.31	.24
12	5.0	e1.1	.52	1.4	.50	.34	4.5	.18	e.39	e.26	.21	.21
13	9.2	.61	.69	1.0	.53	.37	1.7	.19	e.38	e.26	.23	.53
14	62	.46	.57	.72	.55	.77	.45	.13	e.40	e.36	.16	.29
15	5.3	.47	.52	.64	.52	.58	.35	.43	e.40	e.18	.25	.21
16	2.0	.47	.47	.57	.60	.42	.39	.22	e1.0	e.16	.54	.19
17	2.3	.44	3.0	.58	.51	.44	.36	.19	e1.9	e.60	.36	.19
18	1.2	2.2	1.4	.58	.47	.42	.28	.17	e.85	e.91	1.5	.17
19	1.0	1.1	.67	.64	.45	.43	.36	.58	e.45	e.32	.61	.29
20	.78	.70	1.0	.53	.41	.56	.32	.26	e.45	e.65	.47	.59
21	.74	.69	3.7	.52	.44	.45	.32	.14	e1.1	e.18	3.9	83
22	.68	.69	.85	.46	.46	.44	.39	.22	e1.1	e.14	.91	19
23	.67	.63	.69	.44	.45	.57	.21	.14	e.44	e.21	.29	1.9
24	.99	1.3	.65	.50	.42	.74	.20	.13	e.45	.20	6.6	1.1
25	.76	.79	.61	.50	.44	.54	.31	1.2	e.49	.18	1.1	.86
26	.69	2.3	.60	.54	.41	.44	.25	.70	e.53	.20	.70	.78
27	.66	.87	.56	.46	.44	1.4	.24	.37	e.62	.24	1.2	1.1
28	.61	.75	.56	.43	.44	1.2	.25	.43	e.35	.30	.42	.73
29	.56	.71	.57	1.0	---	2.2	.28	2.1	e.44	.21	.59	.67
30	.62	.66	.59	.49	---	1.1	.25	1.0	e.64	.37	.31	.65
31	.59	---	.57	.45	---	.63	---	.44	---	.20	.27	---
TOTAL	101.46	26.20	25.21	28.11	14.94	18.77	16.58	11.79	16.12	14.22	24.74	116.56
MEAN	3.27	.87	.81	.91	.53	.61	.55	.38	.54	.46	.80	3.89
MAX	62	2.3	3.7	6.3	1.1	2.2	4.5	2.1	1.9	1.9	6.6	83
MIN	.26	.44	.47	.43	.39	.33	.20	.13	.26	.14	.11	.17
AC-FT	201	52	50	56	30	37	33	23	32	28	49	231
CFSM	1.40	.37	.35	.39	.23	.26	.24	.16	.23	.20	.34	1.67
IN.	1.62	.42	.40	.45	.24	.30	.26	.19	.26	.23	.39	1.86

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1993 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	1.17	2.42	1.37	.63	.38	.31	.41	.37	.76	.41	.45	8.92
MAX	3.27	6.49	4.79	.91	.95	.61	.92	.77	3.16	.74	.80	38.0
(WY)	1998	1993	1993	1998	1997	1998	1993	1993	1993	1996	1998	1995
MIN	.33	.37	.23	.16	.13	.076	.025	.15	.18	.15	.16	.25
(WY)	1994	1996	1994	1994	1994	1995	1995	1995	1994	1994	1993	1994

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	295.89	414.70	
ANNUAL MEAN	.81	1.14	.81
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			3.43
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.00
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	62	Oct 14	83
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.09	Jul 31	.11
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.12	Jul 27	.19
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1060
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			5.35
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	587	823	1060
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.35	.49	.35
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	4.72	6.62	4.73
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.1	1.1	1.0
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.41	.50	.32
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.19	.21	.10

e Estimated

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50274000 TURPENTINE RUN AT MOUNT ZION, ST. THOMAS, VI--Continued

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50295000 GUINEA GUT AT BETHANY, ST. JOHN, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'55", long 64°46'50", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 600 ft (183 m), southeast of Bethany Church, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) east of Government House at Cruz Bay.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.37 mi² (0.96 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to October 1967, September 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (79 m), from topographic map. Prior to September 1982, at datum 1.00 ft (0.30 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.00	.03	.04	.02	.01	.00	.01	.01	e.01	.02	.00	.00
2	.02	.02	.03	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.01	.02	.01	.02
3	.00	.02	.02	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.01	e.02	.01	.00
4	.00	.02	.02	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.01	e.03	.01	.00
5	.00	.03	.02	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.02	e.02	.01	.00
6	.00	.03	.01	.03	.01	.02	.01	.01	e.01	e.02	e.01	.00
7	.00	.03	.01	.02	.01	.02	.05	.01	e.01	e.02	.01	.00
8	.00	.03	.01	.02	.01	.02	.01	.01	e.01	e.02	.00	.00
9	.00	.03	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.01	.01	e.01	e.03	.00	.00
10	.00	.04	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.01	.01	e.01	e.02	.00	.00
11	.00	.03	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.01	.01	e.01	.02	.00	.00
12	.42	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.01	.01	e.01	.02	.00	.00
13	2.2	.02	.02	.01	.01	.01	e.05	.01	e.01	.02	.00	.00
14	8.6	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	e.02	.01	e.01	.02	.00	.00
15	1.2	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.01	.01	e.01	.02	.00	.00
16	.27	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	e.33	.01	e.01	.01	.00	.00
17	.11	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	e.01	.01	e.02	.01	.00	.00
18	.06	.04	.02	.01	.00	.01	e.01	.01	e.01	.01	.00	.00
19	.04	.04	.02	.01	.00	.01	e.01	.01	.01	.01	.00	.00
20	.02	.03	.02	.01	.00	.01	e.01	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00
21	.02	.03	.02	.01	.00	.01	e.01	.01	.01	.00	.01	7.9
22	.01	.03	.02	.01	.00	.01	e.03	.01	.01	.00	.01	4.1
23	.01	.03	.02	.01	.00	.01	e.01	.01	.01	.00	.00	.30
24	.01	.02	.02	.01	.00	.01	e.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.08
25	.01	.01	.02	.01	.00	.01	e.01	.01	.01	.01	.00	.05
26	.01	.02	.01	.01	.00	.01	e.01	.01	.01	.01	.00	.03
27	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	e.02	.01	.01	.02	.00	1.2
28	.01	.01	.01	.01	.01	.02	e.01	e.01	.01	.01	.00	.16
29	.02	.01	.01	.01	---	.01	.01	.01	.01	.00	.00	.09
30	.02	.02	.01	.01	---	.01	.01	.03	.02	.00	.00	.06
31	.03	---	.02	.01	---	.01	---	e.01	---	.00	.00	---
TOTAL	13.10	0.70	0.52	0.40	0.19	0.34	0.74	0.33	0.33	0.42	0.09	13.99
MEAN	.42	.023	.017	.013	.007	.011	.025	.011	.011	.014	.003	.47
MAX	8.6	.04	.04	.03	.01	.02	.33	.03	.02	.03	.01	7.9
MIN	.00	.01	.01	.01	.00	.00	.01	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00
AC-FT	26	1.4	1.0	.8	.4	.7	1.5	.7	.7	.8	.2	28
CFSM	1.14	.06	.05	.03	.02	.03	.07	.03	.03	.04	.01	1.26
IN.	1.32	.07	.05	.04	.02	.03	.07	.03	.03	.04	.01	1.41

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1983 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	.071	.33	.028	.016	.008	.006	.27	.084	.010	.011	.014	.31				
MAX	.42	2.52	.11	.052	.032	.023	4.03	.89	.031	.041	.082	2.35				
(WY)	1998	1985	1989	1997	1997	1996	1983	1986	1987	1996	1983	1989				
MIN	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000				
(WY)	1992	1992	1987	1992	1992	1986	1995	1994	1991	1987	1991	1991				

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1963 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	19.06	31.15	
ANNUAL MEAN	.052	.085	.078
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			.35
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.00
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	8.6 Oct 14	8.6 Oct 14	110 Apr 18 1983
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00 Mar 26	.00 Oct 1	.00 Oct 3 1982
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00 Aug 1	.00 Oct 3	.00 Jan 9 1983
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		54 Oct 14	946 Apr 18 1983
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		2.48 Oct 14	5.33 Apr 18 1983
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	38	62	56
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.14	.23	.21
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	1.92	3.13	2.86
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.05	.03	.04
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.01	.01	.01
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.00	.00

e Estimated

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS
50295000 GUINEA GUT AT BETHANY, ST. JOHN, VI--Continued

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50345000 JOLLY HILL GUT AT JOLLY HILL, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°44'00", long 64°51'47", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, on Mahogany Road at Jolly Hill, 1.8 mi (2.9 km), northeast of Frederiksted.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.10 mi² (5.44 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to December 1968. Monthly measurements, 1962-69. October 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder, crest-stage gage and sharp-crested concrete control. Elevation of gage is 140 ft (43 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Low-water diversions upstream from station. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.00	.01	e.08	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
2	.00	.01	e.06	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
3	.00	.01	e.03	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
4	.00	.02	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
5	.00	.02	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
6	.00	.07	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00
7	.00	.01	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
8	.00	.01	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
9	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
10	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
11	.00	.00	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
12	.00	e.01	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
13	.03	e.03	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
14	1.3	e.02	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
15	1.4	e.04	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
16	1.0	e.04	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.06	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
17	.59	e.69	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.10	.00	.00	.00
18	.24	e.37	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00
19	.11	e.41	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
20	.08	e.64	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
21	.07	e.50	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	3.6
22	.06	e.59	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	5.1
23	.05	e.38	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.36
24	.04	e.33	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.30
25	.04	e.31	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.30
26	.01	e.26	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.29
27	e.00	e.18	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.30
28	e.01	e.13	e.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.29
29	.00	e.34	e.00	e.00	---	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.27
30	.00	e.17	e.00	.00	---	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.26
31	.01	---	e.00	.00	---	.00	---	.00	---	.00	.00	---
TOTAL	5.04	5.60	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.00	11.07
MEAN	.16	.19	.005	.000	.000	.000	.002	.000	.004	.000	.000	.37
MAX	1.4	.69	.08	.00	.00	.00	.06	.00	.10	.00	.00	5.1
MIN	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
AC-FT	.10	.11	.3	.00	.00	.00	.1	.00	.2	.00	.00	.22
CFSM	.08	.09	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.18
IN.	.09	.10	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.20

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1986 - 1998, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998
MEAN	.86	.73	.46	.27	.18	.088	.063	.086	.16	.077	.027	.71	
MAX	5.92	2.33	2.34	.88	.55	.34	.23	.46	1.43	.52	.18	3.80	
(WY)	1996	1988	1988	1988	1988	1990	1990	1992	1987	1987	1987	1995	
MIN	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
(WY)	1987	1992	1992	1992	1989	1989	1989	1989	1989	1989	1989	1991	

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1997 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1998 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1998

ANNUAL TOTAL	38.51	22.05		
ANNUAL MEAN	.11	.060		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			.22	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.94	1996
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1.4	Oct 15	5.1	Sep 22
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	Jun 16	.00	Oct 1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	Jun 16	.00	Oct 1
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			37	Sep 21
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			2.15	Sep 21
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	76		44	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.050		.029	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	.68		.39	1.42
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.29		.06	.59
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.04		.00	.03
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00		.00	.00

e Estimated

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS
50345000 JOLLY HILL GUT AT JOLLY HILL, ST. CROIX, VI--Continued

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**Ground-Water Records
for U.S. Virgin Islands**

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174225064472000. Local number, 2.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'25", long 64°47'20", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 0.90 mi southeast of the Experimental Station, 0.6 mi southwest of Christiansted Plaza, and 0.18 mi northeast of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64.

Owner: US Virgin Islands Government, Name: USGS-10, Fairplains 2 (FP2).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 20 ft (6.10 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at concrete base wall, 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water level affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1983 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 19.02 ft (5.80 m), below land-surface datum, Feb. 8, 1997; lowest water level recorded, 26.46 ft (8.06 m), below land-surface datum, Aug. 25, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	20.31	19.36	19.55	19.87	20.04	20.15	20.69	20.85	20.94	21.12	20.47	20.49
2	20.31	19.32	19.57	19.80	20.08	20.16	20.70	20.80	20.95	21.03	20.45	20.46
3	20.22	19.45	19.63	19.84	20.10	20.27	20.68	20.83	21.00	21.03	20.53	20.55
4	20.32	19.33	19.53	19.87	20.13	20.30	20.66	20.77	21.01	20.94	20.55	20.60
5	20.33	19.38	19.60	19.94	20.09	20.43	20.60	20.86	21.07	20.98	20.65	20.53
6	20.39	19.37	19.60	19.85	20.11	20.47	20.68	20.77	20.97	20.93	20.59	20.48
7	20.37	19.38	19.71	19.82	20.09	20.42	20.72	20.73	20.99	20.91	20.59	20.43
8	20.37	19.31	19.67	19.90	19.99	20.45	20.76	20.75	21.03	20.89	20.63	20.41
9	20.36	19.30	19.73	19.92	20.14	20.42	20.80	20.80	20.98	20.88	20.59	20.40
10	20.38	19.32	19.71	19.90	20.15	20.36	20.67	20.84	20.99	20.85	20.55	20.53
11	20.33	19.32	19.64	19.89	20.13	20.49	20.71	20.87	20.97	20.84	20.60	20.55
12	20.20	19.28	19.74	19.87	20.22	20.50	20.73	20.89	21.01	20.82	20.60	20.50
13	20.25	19.42	19.74	19.90	20.18	20.54	20.77	20.90	20.93	20.66	20.57	20.48
14	20.11	19.38	19.75	19.87	20.15	20.55	20.71	20.92	20.95	20.64	20.57	20.60
15	19.99	19.37	19.78	19.89	20.19	20.51	20.79	20.93	21.02	20.70	20.56	20.52
16	20.02	19.30	19.82	19.95	20.15	20.53	20.80	20.85	20.97	20.67	20.55	20.47
17	19.94	19.41	19.76	19.86	20.13	20.56	20.76	20.90	20.92	20.64	20.65	20.43
18	19.85	19.48	19.85	19.89	20.26	20.64	20.76	20.85	20.93	20.61	20.55	20.41
19	19.75	19.53	19.82	19.91	20.27	20.55	20.79	20.88	20.96	20.58	20.51	20.55
20	19.77	19.42	19.80	19.92	20.27	20.58	20.70	20.93	21.02	20.65	20.49	20.56
21	19.67	19.54	19.80	19.92	20.30	20.50	20.75	20.94	21.10	20.63	20.43	20.36
22	19.68	19.50	19.81	19.93	20.30	20.49	20.79	20.89	21.06	20.57	20.53	20.35
23	19.59	19.49	19.87	19.95	20.33	20.60	20.76	20.84	21.05	20.54	20.60	20.25
24	19.65	19.50	19.81	19.94	20.39	20.65	20.71	20.86	21.05	20.61	20.51	20.18
25	19.56	19.44	19.84	19.87	20.43	20.64	20.77	20.91	21.08	20.58	20.46	20.10
26	19.53	19.54	19.78	20.00	20.29	20.69	20.77	20.87	21.06	20.52	20.42	20.05
27	19.47	19.44	19.84	20.04	20.30	20.69	20.69	20.92	21.03	20.50	20.40	19.94
28	19.53	19.52	19.80	20.06	20.28	20.64	20.80	20.96	21.01	20.52	20.39	19.90
29	19.50	19.51	19.82	20.02	---	20.58	20.83	21.01	21.06	20.51	20.50	19.96
30	19.38	19.43	19.86	20.07	---	20.65	20.85	20.97	20.99	20.51	20.58	20.03
31	19.49	---	19.95	19.98	---	20.66	---	20.84	---	20.50	20.57	---
MEAN	19.96	19.41	19.75	19.92	20.20	20.51	20.74	20.87	21.00	20.72	20.54	20.37
WTR YR 1998	MEAN 20.33	HIGHEST 19.27	NOV, 10, 12, 1997	LOWEST 21.12	JULY 1, 1998							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174243064475100. Local number, 3.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'43", long 64°47'51", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 0.75 mi northwest of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64, 6.45 mi southwest of Christiansted Plaza, and 0.57 mi southwest of the Experimental Station.

Owner: US Virgin Islands Government, Name: Golden Grove - 6 (PW6).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Upper edge of hole at 8 in (0.20 m) casing, 4.20 ft (1.28 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 12.99 ft (3.96 m), below land-surface datum, Nov. 10, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 41.05 ft (12.5 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 15, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	27.67	25.97	26.41	27.09	27.46	27.68	28.16	28.65	29.06	29.48	29.56	29.31
2	27.66	25.97	26.45	27.10	27.46	27.70	28.18	28.65	29.09	29.45	29.55	29.31
3	27.65	25.97	26.45	27.10	27.46	27.73	28.20	28.68	29.11	29.45	29.54	29.36
4	27.66	25.98	26.45	27.10	27.46	27.77	28.20	28.67	29.12	29.47	29.55	29.36
5	27.67	26.00	26.46	27.12	27.50	27.78	28.19	28.70	29.12	29.50	29.56	29.35
6	27.69	25.99	26.46	27.13	27.52	27.78	28.21	28.70	29.14	29.51	29.53	29.33
7	27.67	25.99	26.53	27.13	27.52	27.78	28.24	28.71	29.16	29.50	29.52	29.32
8	27.67	26.01	26.55	27.15	27.52	27.83	28.26	28.70	29.19	29.50	29.51	29.32
9	27.67	26.04	26.56	27.17	27.53	27.84	28.26	28.73	29.21	29.51	29.50	29.31
10	27.65	26.07	26.58	27.17	27.55	27.86	28.24	28.73	29.22	29.51	29.49	29.31
11	27.65	26.07	26.60	27.16	27.56	27.90	28.26	28.73	29.23	29.53	29.49	29.28
12	27.63	26.08	26.64	27.19	27.57	27.92	28.26	28.76	29.24	29.59	29.50	29.28
13	27.60	26.08	26.65	27.19	27.57	27.93	28.29	28.78	29.25	29.64	29.49	29.28
14	27.55	26.04	26.67	27.18	27.55	27.93	28.31	28.78	29.27	29.65	29.47	29.29
15	27.51	26.06	26.70	27.20	27.59	27.93	28.31	28.79	29.28	29.66	29.47	29.31
16	27.26	26.08	26.71	27.23	27.61	27.93	28.31	28.80	29.29	29.66	29.49	29.30
17	27.01	26.10	26.78	27.23	27.60	27.95	28.31	28.82	29.30	29.66	29.49	29.30
18	26.66	26.13	26.78	27.23	27.63	27.96	28.35	28.85	29.30	29.64	29.43	29.29
19	26.45	26.15	26.81	27.24	27.60	27.99	28.44	28.87	29.32	29.64	29.42	29.31
20	26.28	26.16	26.81	27.26	27.61	27.99	28.52	28.89	29.32	29.62	29.41	29.33
21	26.09	26.19	26.80	27.29	27.62	27.96	28.57	28.89	29.32	29.62	29.40	29.10
22	26.00	26.20	26.86	27.30	27.66	28.00	28.59	28.90	29.35	29.62	29.41	29.33
23	25.96	26.20	26.86	27.32	27.67	28.01	28.65	28.92	29.38	29.61	29.41	29.22
24	25.91	26.22	26.87	27.34	27.67	28.08	28.68	28.92	29.42	29.61	29.36	28.94
25	25.83	26.22	26.90	27.36	27.66	28.12	28.69	28.92	29.43	29.62	29.39	28.66
26	25.83	26.27	26.91	27.37	27.64	28.12	28.69	29.00	29.41	29.60	29.38	28.40
27	25.81	26.30	26.90	27.38	27.66	28.10	28.69	29.02	29.42	29.58	29.34	28.17
28	25.83	26.32	26.94	27.45	27.69	28.12	28.71	29.02	29.44	29.58	29.33	28.03
29	25.84	26.35	26.98	27.43	---	28.10	28.72	29.03	29.45	29.58	29.34	27.88
30	25.84	26.34	27.02	27.41	---	28.11	28.65	29.05	29.47	29.58	29.35	27.87
31	25.87	---	27.08	27.44	---	28.12	---	29.05	---	29.58	29.36	---
MEAN	26.87	26.12	26.72	27.24	27.58	27.94	28.40	28.83	29.28	29.57	29.45	29.06

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 28.09 HIGHEST 25.77 OCT. 27, 28, 1997 LOWEST 29.66 JULY 14-19, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174316064480800. Local number, 13.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'16", long 64°48'08", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 5.25 mi east of Fort Frederick at Frederickstead, 0.95 mi southeast of Holy Cross Church, and 0.65 mi northeast of Adventure Ruins. Owner: US Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: WAPA-17 at Adventure well field.

AQUIFER.--Kingshill Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-95.0 ft (0-29.0 m), screened 10-40.0 ft (3.05-12.2 m). Depth 95.0 ft (29.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 75.0 ft (22.9 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.33 ft (0.71 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 28, 1990 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 0.27 ft (0.08 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 10, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 27.88 ft (8.50 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 6, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	13.04	10.17	10.70	10.78	10.77	11.38	12.45	---	14.05	14.90	15.25	16.34
2	13.07	10.15	10.76	10.78	10.77	11.42	12.62	---	14.07	14.92	15.28	16.39
3	13.07	10.11	10.80	10.78	10.79	11.47	12.68	---	14.10	14.93	15.31	16.48
4	13.06	10.07	10.80	10.78	10.83	11.52	12.73	---	14.14	14.93	15.36	16.52
5	13.10	10.05	10.84	10.78	10.83	11.62	---	---	14.16	14.71	15.40	16.57
6	13.15	10.03	10.89	10.78	10.86	11.68	---	---	14.19	14.73	15.41	16.61
7	13.17	10.02	10.96	10.70	10.91	11.76	---	13.61	14.20	14.82	15.43	16.67
8	13.21	10.02	10.99	10.20	10.94	11.80	---	13.62	14.22	14.79	14.82	16.73
9	13.22	10.02	11.03	10.11	10.96	11.89	---	13.62	14.24	14.64	14.80	16.37
10	13.24	10.02	11.03	10.15	10.98	11.95	---	13.63	14.25	14.73	15.07	16.34
11	13.24	10.02	11.03	10.26	11.01	12.03	---	13.64	14.27	14.85	15.21	16.46
12	13.24	10.02	11.03	10.35	11.04	12.08	13.07	13.67	14.30	14.94	15.30	16.54
13	12.40	10.02	11.01	10.35	11.08	12.13	13.07	13.69	14.32	14.97	15.39	16.64
14	10.36	10.02	11.01	10.39	11.10	12.18	13.10	13.72	14.39	15.01	15.43	16.73
15	9.88	10.03	11.00	10.43	11.11	12.21	13.13	13.72	14.43	15.03	15.50	16.75
16	10.41	10.03	11.00	10.43	11.13	12.27	13.18	13.74	14.47	15.06	15.57	16.80
17	10.76	10.05	10.99	10.50	11.13	12.28	13.08	13.78	---	15.06	15.67	16.85
18	10.83	10.07	10.98	10.50	11.18	12.31	13.02	13.82	---	15.08	15.71	16.92
19	10.91	10.09	10.98	10.53	11.21	12.36	13.03	13.84	---	15.10	15.79	16.94
20	10.93	10.13	10.98	10.53	11.22	12.36	13.11	13.88	---	15.12	15.85	16.96
21	10.93	10.18	10.89	10.53	11.26	12.37	13.13	13.91	---	15.14	15.91	16.98
22	10.87	10.20	10.55	10.57	11.28	12.41	13.18	13.93	---	15.13	15.93	13.41
23	10.83	10.28	10.55	10.61	11.31	12.47	13.24	13.96	---	15.13	15.97	12.10
24	10.83	10.34	10.58	10.63	11.34	12.52	13.28	13.97	---	15.13	16.02	12.19
25	10.82	10.38	10.62	10.63	11.37	12.57	13.31	13.99	---	15.13	16.02	12.59
26	10.82	10.44	10.64	10.63	11.37	12.61	13.35	14.01	---	15.14	16.02	12.74
27	10.44	10.50	10.67	10.64	11.37	12.63	13.38	14.04	---	15.15	16.02	12.89
28	10.36	10.54	10.68	10.66	11.37	12.63	13.43	14.07	---	15.18	16.02	12.75
29	10.30	10.61	10.68	10.67	---	12.48	13.48	14.09	---	15.20	16.14	12.79
30	10.30	10.66	10.75	10.74	---	12.48	---	14.10	---	15.24	16.22	12.87
31	10.21	---	10.76	10.75	---	12.44	---	14.04	---	15.24	16.28	---
MEAN	11.65	10.18	10.84	10.55	11.09	12.14	13.09	13.84	14.24	15.00	15.62	15.46

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 12.73 HIGHEST 9.83 OCT. 15, 1997 LOWEST 16.98 SEPT. 20, 21, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182038064550300. Local number, 6.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'38", long 64°55'03", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 1.12 mi east of Charlotte Amalie, 0.75 mi southwest of Winterberg Peak, and 1.08 mi southeast of Canaan. Owner: US Virgin Islands Government, Name: Grade School 3.

AQUIFER.--Volcanic breccia.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 70.0 ft (21.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 60 ft (18.3 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m), above land-surface datum.

Prior to June 27, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.90 ft (0.88 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 1.53 ft (0.47 m), below land-surface datum, Oct. 1, 1989; lowest water level recorded, 35.38 ft (10.8 m), below land-surface datum, July 21, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	24.06	17.95	20.47	23.13	23.23	25.01	24.81	26.34	27.58	27.27	28.36	23.85
2	24.30	18.12	20.66	23.21	23.36	24.79	24.83	26.46	27.66	27.42	28.44	24.09
3	24.46	18.31	20.84	23.31	23.47	24.90	24.93	26.56	27.73	27.58	28.55	24.36
4	24.64	18.53	20.99	23.39	23.59	25.08	25.00	26.66	27.81	27.75	28.66	24.55
5	24.85	18.77	21.17	23.50	23.73	25.26	24.98	26.75	27.90	27.87	28.77	24.73
6	25.09	18.98	21.24	23.50	23.81	25.42	25.08	26.84	28.00	27.91	28.90	24.94
7	25.33	19.19	21.26	23.02	23.87	25.57	25.26	26.91	28.09	27.95	29.00	25.14
8	25.60	19.40	21.43	22.03	23.95	25.72	25.44	26.98	28.20	27.98	28.99	25.25
9	25.84	19.62	21.59	21.58	24.01	25.87	25.60	27.01	28.29	27.81	28.94	25.09
10	25.96	19.83	21.70	21.39	24.00	26.00	25.75	26.63	28.40	27.73	28.92	25.06
11	26.06	19.75	21.86	21.30	24.01	26.12	25.91	26.10	28.50	27.75	28.95	25.12
12	25.82	19.60	22.03	21.12	24.05	26.24	26.07	25.91	28.62	27.84	29.01	25.23
13	23.77	19.60	22.19	20.32	24.11	26.37	25.89	26.10	28.72	27.94	29.02	25.40
14	20.10	19.63	22.37	19.69	24.16	26.47	25.27	26.37	28.82	28.06	29.02	25.44
15	17.55	19.74	22.52	19.62	24.25	26.50	25.00	26.65	28.94	28.18	29.05	25.42
16	16.23	19.87	22.69	19.74	24.33	26.45	24.93	26.82	29.04	28.32	29.10	25.47
17	15.35	20.03	22.85	19.94	24.41	26.41	24.74	26.61	29.15	28.44	29.17	25.57
18	14.58	20.18	22.81	20.16	24.47	26.39	24.63	26.38	28.75	28.44	29.22	25.69
19	14.18	20.17	22.76	20.42	24.57	26.40	24.65	26.52	27.68	28.33	29.19	25.68
20	14.08	19.99	22.80	20.70	24.67	26.46	24.75	26.74	27.17	28.28	29.10	25.82
21	14.15	19.96	22.76	20.98	24.77	26.48	24.86	26.93	27.02	28.16	28.92	25.88
22	14.39	20.05	22.17	21.24	24.87	26.52	25.00	27.08	26.93	28.07	27.76	22.33
23	14.68	20.15	21.97	21.53	24.97	26.57	25.15	27.23	26.65	28.08	27.04	19.28
24	15.02	20.28	21.97	21.78	25.05	26.60	25.32	27.39	26.57	28.13	26.84	18.08
25	15.39	20.35	22.07	22.02	25.13	26.60	25.51	27.54	26.61	28.08	25.32	17.48
26	15.78	20.41	22.19	22.23	25.14	26.60	25.67	27.69	26.69	28.06	24.24	17.20
27	16.15	20.21	22.34	22.44	25.20	26.60	25.82	27.79	26.78	28.09	23.83	17.13
28	16.52	20.05	22.53	22.65	25.27	26.37	25.94	27.86	26.89	28.11	23.57	17.18
29	16.90	20.10	22.71	22.81	---	25.96	26.06	27.93	27.00	28.16	23.48	17.35
30	17.27	20.25	22.88	22.96	---	25.39	26.20	27.82	27.13	28.23	23.53	17.60
31	17.65	---	23.03	23.11	---	24.94	---	27.62	---	28.29	23.67	---
MEAN	19.73	19.64	22.03	21.77	24.30	26.00	25.30	26.91	27.78	28.01	27.63	23.05

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 24.35 HIGHEST 14.07 OCT. 20, 1997 LOWEST 29.24 AUG. 18, 19, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182038064580000. Local number, 8.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'38", long 64°58'00", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 2.08 mi northwest of Charlotte Amalie, 0.50 mi northeast of Harry S. Truman Airport entrance on Hwy 302, and 1.15 mi southwest of Dorothea. Owner: US Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: Kirwan Terrace, VIEO-6.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial deposits, volcanic rock.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-56 in (0-17.1 m), screened 56-76.0 ft (17.1-23.2 m). Depth 76.0 ft (23.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 35.0 ft (10.7 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Drilled on July 1, 1991.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 2, 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 14.3 ft (4.37 m), below land-surface datum, Dec. 6, 7, 1996; lowest water level recorded, 32.7 ft (9.96 m), below land-surface datum, July 27, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	30.55	27.50	27.14	27.83	28.37	29.29	29.86	29.68	30.70	30.23	30.28	29.36
2	30.54	27.49	27.18	27.84	28.40	29.34	29.84	29.70	30.70	30.26	30.33	29.31
3	30.52	27.48	27.19	27.88	28.42	29.36	29.81	29.73	30.69	30.28	30.37	29.31
4	30.53	27.48	27.24	27.89	28.46	29.40	29.79	29.75	30.68	30.31	30.41	29.29
5	30.54	27.51	27.28	27.95	28.51	29.43	29.78	29.80	30.68	30.31	30.45	29.27
6	30.57	27.51	27.32	28.00	28.56	29.46	29.76	29.85	30.70	30.29	30.50	29.26
7	30.60	27.51	27.35	27.95	28.59	29.48	29.80	29.90	30.69	30.28	30.55	29.24
8	30.62	27.55	27.37	27.86	28.64	29.52	29.81	29.95	30.70	30.30	30.57	29.21
9	30.65	27.57	27.41	27.76	28.67	29.56	29.84	30.01	30.71	30.27	30.57	29.21
10	30.65	27.55	27.46	27.69	28.71	29.62	29.88	30.06	30.72	30.22	30.63	29.20
11	30.65	27.52	27.51	27.66	28.74	29.66	29.92	30.10	30.74	30.22	30.67	29.21
12	30.63	27.48	27.54	27.66	28.74	29.71	29.98	30.14	30.75	30.20	30.59	29.21
13	30.49	27.44	27.58	27.69	28.77	29.75	30.02	30.20	30.76	30.20	30.56	29.22
14	30.01	27.37	27.62	27.69	28.81	29.77	30.02	30.25	30.76	30.18	30.52	29.24
15	29.37	27.33	27.67	27.74	28.84	29.74	29.99	30.30	30.77	30.21	30.52	29.25
16	28.84	27.32	27.70	27.79	28.88	29.73	29.96	30.33	30.76	30.27	30.53	29.25
17	28.43	27.30	27.72	27.82	28.91	29.75	29.81	30.37	30.76	30.30	30.51	29.29
18	28.15	27.28	27.73	27.85	28.94	29.77	29.67	30.40	30.63	30.34	30.50	29.34
19	27.94	27.28	27.74	27.87	28.97	29.83	29.54	30.43	30.47	30.36	30.52	29.40
20	27.81	27.25	27.74	27.91	29.01	29.87	29.49	30.46	30.33	30.33	30.53	29.52
21	27.71	27.24	27.72	27.96	29.04	29.93	29.45	30.51	30.23	30.31	30.55	29.54
22	27.66	27.24	27.72	27.99	29.08	30.00	29.47	30.56	30.15	30.27	30.55	29.32
23	27.62	27.23	27.69	28.02	29.11	30.02	29.49	30.62	30.08	30.25	30.49	28.88
24	27.61	27.22	27.67	28.06	29.15	30.09	29.53	30.64	30.04	30.24	30.41	28.55
25	27.55	27.19	27.66	28.09	29.18	30.14	29.57	30.66	30.01	30.22	30.24	28.28
26	27.48	27.20	27.68	28.11	29.20	30.17	29.59	30.69	30.02	30.22	30.02	28.06
27	27.39	27.17	27.68	28.13	29.23	30.20	29.61	30.72	30.05	30.22	29.83	27.92
28	27.41	27.14	27.70	28.17	29.26	30.21	29.62	30.72	30.10	30.21	29.70	27.77
29	27.44	27.14	27.71	28.21	---	30.17	29.64	30.75	30.11	30.18	29.60	27.69
30	27.45	27.13	27.76	28.25	---	30.07	29.66	30.76	30.18	30.21	29.48	27.63
31	27.47	---	27.79	28.32	---	29.96	---	30.74	---	30.23	29.41	---
MEAN	29.06	27.35	27.56	27.92	28.83	29.77	29.74	30.28	30.49	30.26	30.34	28.97

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 29.22 HIGHEST 27.12 NOV. 28, DEC. 1, 1997 LOWEST 30.77 JUNE 14, 15, 16, 1998

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

181956064464500. Local number, 11.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'56", long 64°46'45", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 1.05 mi southeast of Cruz Bay plaza, 0.25 mi southeast of Bethany Church, and 0.48 mi southeast of Margaret Hill. Owner: US Virgin Islands Government, Name: Guinea Gut Well.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation (Donnelly, 1959).

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 85.0 ft (25.9 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 280 ft (85.36 m), above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Bottom of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.50 ft (0.46 m), above land-surface datum. Prior to June 28, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m), above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.71 ft (0.79 m), below land-surface datum, Jan. 3, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 34.18 ft (10.4 m), below land-surface datum, Sept. 6, 1995.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1997 TO SEPTEMBER 1998
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	23.41	8.43	7.31	10.28	11.87	16.10	19.43	14.60	16.39	19.05	21.39	22.06
2	23.41	8.29	6.36	10.43	12.03	16.27	19.51	14.69	16.39	19.18	21.46	22.06
3	23.29	8.26	6.22	10.56	12.15	16.42	19.54	14.82	16.39	19.30	21.51	21.89
4	23.09	8.26	6.21	10.67	12.32	16.60	19.61	14.90	16.40	19.39	21.58	21.81
5	22.93	8.23	6.25	10.75	12.45	16.76	19.68	14.86	16.38	19.46	21.68	21.74
6	22.85	8.28	6.33	10.78	12.50	16.91	19.76	14.87	16.39	19.55	21.76	21.73
7	22.78	8.35	6.45	10.67	12.57	16.97	19.84	14.91	16.52	19.67	21.84	21.72
8	22.75	8.44	6.55	10.58	12.74	17.13	19.84	14.90	16.61	19.77	21.86	21.70
9	22.71	8.53	6.62	10.58	12.90	17.31	19.81	15.02	16.74	19.80	21.85	21.69
10	22.67	8.64	6.75	10.61	13.02	17.46	19.78	15.10	16.83	19.84	21.86	21.69
11	22.64	8.63	6.90	10.61	13.16	17.63	19.80	15.17	16.96	19.88	21.90	21.68
12	22.60	8.71	7.13	10.62	13.29	17.80	19.82	15.31	17.06	19.96	21.93	21.69
13	19.45	8.63	7.30	10.41	13.41	17.95	16.05	15.43	17.15	20.04	21.95	21.72
14	14.11	8.67	7.36	10.30	13.44	18.07	13.61	15.53	17.28	20.15	21.99	21.74
15	12.04	8.75	7.54	10.35	13.57	18.15	12.81	15.49	17.42	20.23	22.05	21.78
16	10.77	8.90	7.70	10.45	13.71	18.29	12.94	15.46	17.55	20.32	22.13	21.81
17	10.00	8.96	7.86	10.52	13.83	18.41	12.98	15.49	17.63	20.41	22.16	21.82
18	9.48	9.05	8.00	10.59	14.00	18.60	13.15	15.52	17.65	20.48	22.16	21.86
19	9.14	8.53	8.15	10.67	14.17	18.74	13.31	15.58	17.76	20.57	22.12	21.89
20	8.91	8.46	8.29	10.74	14.39	18.85	13.50	15.67	17.87	20.64	22.16	21.91
21	8.72	8.57	8.41	10.87	14.60	18.96	13.63	15.75	18.00	20.72	22.13	21.82
22	8.58	8.63	8.57	10.93	14.84	19.07	13.77	15.87	18.08	20.82	22.15	16.15
23	8.49	8.71	8.71	11.09	15.05	19.14	13.89	15.95	18.10	20.89	22.13	13.31
24	8.43	8.76	8.89	11.26	15.26	19.20	14.01	16.04	18.14	20.97	22.11	11.85
25	8.32	8.71	9.07	11.31	15.43	19.25	14.13	16.12	18.26	21.05	22.06	11.02
26	8.29	8.52	9.26	11.43	15.59	19.33	14.24	16.22	18.36	21.13	22.02	10.49
27	8.28	8.16	9.43	11.48	15.74	19.38	14.28	16.35	18.49	21.20	21.99	9.47
28	8.23	8.16	9.64	11.44	15.92	19.43	14.40	16.46	18.62	21.26	21.96	8.22
29	8.27	8.20	9.83	11.52	---	19.37	14.50	16.56	18.76	21.31	21.97	7.72
30	8.34	8.19	10.03	11.59	---	19.36	14.59	16.54	18.91	21.34	21.99	7.51
31	8.45	---	10.23	11.72	---	19.38	---	16.45	---	21.36	22.04	---
MEAN	14.88	8.52	7.85	10.83	13.71	18.14	16.21	15.54	17.44	20.31	21.93	18.45

WTR YR 1998 MEAN 15.33 HIGHEST 6.04 DEC. 2, 1997 LOWEST 23.42 OCT. 1, 2, 1997

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CONVERSION FACTORS AND VERTICAL DATUM

Multiply	By	To obtain
<i>Length</i>		
inch (in.)	2.54×10^1	millimeter
	2.54×10^{-2}	meter
foot (ft)	3.048×10^{-1}	meter
mile (mi)	1.609×10^0	kilometer
<i>Area</i>		
acre	4.047×10^3	square meter
	4.047×10^{-1}	square hectometer
	4.047×10^{-3}	square kilometer
square mile (mi ²)	2.590×10^0	square kilometer
<i>Volume</i>		
gallon (gal)	3.785×10^0	liter
	3.785×10^0	cubic decimeter
	3.785×10^{-3}	cubic meter
million gallons (Mgal)	3.785×10^3	cubic meter
	3.785×10^{-3}	cubic hectometer
cubic foot (ft ³)	2.832×10^1	cubic decimeter
	2.832×10^{-2}	cubic meter
cubic-foot-per-second day [(ft ³ /s) d]	2.447×10^3	cubic meter
	2.447×10^{-3}	cubic hectometer
acre-foot (acre-ft)	1.233×10^3	cubic meter
	1.233×10^{-3}	cubic hectometer
	1.233×10^{-6}	cubic kilometer
<i>Flow</i>		
cubic foot per second (ft ³ /s)	2.832×10^1	liter per second
	2.832×10^1	cubic decimeter per second
	2.832×10^{-2}	cubic meter per second
gallon per minute (gal/min)	6.309×10^{-2}	liter per second
	6.309×10^{-2}	cubic decimeter per second
	6.309×10^{-5}	cubic meter per second
million gallons per day (Mgal/d)	4.381×10^1	cubic decimeter per second
	4.381×10^{-2}	cubic meter per second
<i>Mass</i>		
ton (short)	9.072×10^{-1}	megagram or metric ton

Sea level: In this report "sea level" refers to the National Geodetic Vertical Datum of 1929 (NGVD of 1929)—a geodetic datum derived from a general adjustment for the first-order level nets of both the United States and Canada, formerly called Sea Level Datum of 1929.

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